

Different Digits Selfie Fractions: Five Digits Numerator - Pandigital

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Abstract

The **addable fractions** are proper fractions, where addition can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. The same is true for other operations, such as, **addition, subtraction, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. For more details refer author's work [10]. This work brings **selfie fractions** with single and/or multiple representations in different digits with all operations. The numerator values are with five digits giving pandigital fractions. The results are in increasing order of numerator values. Also, numerator is always less than denominator. The different digits **selfie fractions** for two and three digits numerator are given in [13]. The repeated digits **selfie fractions** are given in [12].

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1 Introduction

Kieth [2, 3] for the first gave an idea of **dottable fraction**. It is a proper fraction where multiplication signs can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. Keith's [2, 3] idea was only with multiplication. For the first time, we extended it to other operations also, such as, with **addition, subtraction, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. See below some examples studied by author [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

1.1 Selfie Fraction

• Addable Fractions

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.} \quad (1)$$

• Subtractable Fractions

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.} \quad (2)$$

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• **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

• **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

• **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4 - 9 + 80}{5 \times (3 + 1)^2}, \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3 + 2^4) \times 9}{(5 - 1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.} \quad (5)$$

Observing the above examples, the numerator and denominator follows the same orders of digits in both sides of each fraction separated by operations. These type of fractions, we called **Selfie fractions**. There are two situations. One when all digits appearing in each fraction are distinct and second, when there are repetitions of digits. The idea of **equivalent e fractions** is explained below.

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have given **selfie fractions** with single value in each case. There are many fractions, that can be written in multiple ways. See below

• **Equivalent: Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} = \frac{1 + 453}{2 + 906} = \frac{145 + 3}{290 + 6} = \frac{1 + 45 + 3}{2 + 90 + 6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (6)$$

• **Equivalent: Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} = \frac{9 - 32}{18 - 64} = \frac{93 - 2}{186 - 4}, \text{ etc.} \quad (7)$$

• **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} = \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1 + 6 + 8 + 0}{59 + 472}, \text{ etc.} \quad (8)$$

• **Equivalent: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} = \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3 + 02}{81 + 54} = \frac{3 - 02}{81 - 54}, \text{ etc.} \quad (9)$$

• **Symmetric Equivalent: Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} = \frac{6 - 45}{12 - 90} = \frac{6 + 45}{12 + 90}, \text{ etc.} \quad (10)$$

• **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} = \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}, \text{ etc.} \quad (11)$$

• **Equivalent: Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} = \frac{7-3 \times (8-4^2)}{9 \times 05-1-6} = \frac{7 \times (3+8) + 4^2}{90 + (5-1) \times 6} = \frac{738+4+2}{905+1+6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (12)$$

In 2016, the author worked on **selfie fractions** in different ways and with different digits, i.e., without repetition of digits in numerators and denominators. See below resumed work.

- (i) Selfie Fractions: Addable - [5];
- (ii) Selfie Fractions: Dottable and Pontentiable - [6];
- (iii) Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [7];
- (iv) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable - [8];
- (v) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [9].

The combined and enlarged version of above five items can seen in author's two recent work [10, 11]. In this work our aim is to bring **selfie fractions** with mixed operations with single or multiple representations, in increasing order of numerator without repetition of digits. This paper brings **selfie fractions** with single and/or multiple representations in different digits with all operations. The numerator values are with five digits giving **pandigital fractions**. The results are in increasing order of numerator values. Also, numerator is always less than denominator. The different digits **selfie fractions** for two and three digits numerator are given in [13]. The repeated digits **selfie fractions** are given in [12]. Also, in all the case, the numerator is always less than denominator.

Remark 1.1. *In [11], the author worked with **pandigital selfie fractions**. The difference is that in [11] the work is in increasing order of equilvant fractions, including the results with 6-digits denominator. This work brings the results with numerator and denominator with five digits and the results are in increasing order of numerator. In another words, this is reorganized version of [11] with 5-digits numerator and denominator.*

Remark 1.2. *The following two situations are considered:*

- (i) *The first number of the r.h.s of the fraction are always positive, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{4 + 1508}{7 + 2639}$$

The following expression also give selfie fraction,

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{-4 + 1508}{-7 + 2639}$$

This kind of expressions are not considered as the first members of numerator and denominator are negative.

- (ii) *Even thought, the final expression is positive, but the numerator and denominator are not considered negative, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{2 + 1564}{9 + 7038} := \frac{2 - 1564}{9 - 7038}$$

- (iii) *In all the case, the numerator is always less than denominator.*

2 Different Digits Selfie Fractions: Five Digits Numerator - Pandigital

This section brings **selfie fractions** for the numerator 2-digits numbers. Due to high quantity of number there are lot of extra brackets like "(...)". These can be removed easily by simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10248}{75396} &:= \frac{1 \times 02 + 4 + 8}{7^{5-3} + 9 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{10 + 24 + 8}{75 + 39 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10248}{97356} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times 4) - 8}{97 - (3 + 56)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (2 - (4 - 8)))}{9 + (7 + (35 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (2 \times (4 - 8)))}{97 - ((3 \times 5) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (2 + (4 + 8)))}{(9 \times (7 \times 3)) - 56}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - (2 \times (4 - 8))}{9 \times (7 - ((3 - 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times 4) + 8}{(9 \times (7 \times 3)) - (5 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (2 \times (4 + 8)))}{(9 \times ((7 \times 3) + 5)) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^0 + 2)) + 4 \times 8}{9 - (7 \times (3 - 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((2 + 4) \times 8))}{(9 \times ((7 + 3) \times 5)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (2 + 4)) - 8}{((97 + 3) \times 5) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (2 + 48)}{(9 + (7 + 3)) \times (5 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (2 - (4 + 8)))}{97 - (3 + (5 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (2 + 4)) + 8}{(9 \times 73) - (5 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (2 \times 4))) \times 8}{(9 + (7 \times (3 \times 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(10^2) + (4 + 8)}{(9 + (7 + 3)) \times 56}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (2 + (4 - 8)))}{9 + (7 - (3 \times (5 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{102 + 48}{9 - ((7 - (3^5)) \times 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10268}{94375} &:= \frac{(1 + 02) \times 68}{(9 - 4) \times 375} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (26 + 8)}{(9 - 4)^{3+7-5}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10274}{69583} := \frac{(10 - 2) \times (7 + 4)}{6 \times (9 + 5) + 8^3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 02^7 + 4}{69 \times (5 + 8) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10275}{64938} := \frac{(1 + 02 \times 7) \times 5}{(6 - 4)^9 - 38}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 02 \times 75}{6 + 4 + 938}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10286}{39754} := \frac{10 + 286}{(3 \times 97 - 5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10287}{59436} := \frac{1 \times 02 \times 8 - 7}{59 - 4 + 3 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 02 + 8 + 7}{(5 + 9) \times (4 + 3) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 2 + 8 + 7}{(5 + 9 + 4 \times 3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{-1 \times 02 + 8 \times 7}{(59 - 4 - 3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10293}{47658} := \frac{10^2 - 9 \times 3}{(4 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10293}{64578} := \frac{10^2 - 9 \times 3}{6 - 4 + 57 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{43758} := \frac{(10^2) + (9 - 6)}{4 + (3 + (7 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((02^{9-6}))}{4 + (3 \times (7 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((02 \times 9) - 6))}{(4 - (3 \times 7)) \times (5 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{02}) + (9 + 6)}{4 - (3 - (75 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (2 - (9 \times 6)))}{4 + ((3 \times 75) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((2 + 9) \times 6)}{43 + (7 \times (5 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (2^{9-6})}{4 + ((37 + 5) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{02}) \times 96}{((4^3) \times 7) - (5 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 29)) \times 6}{4 + (3 + 758)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((2^9) - 6)}{(437 \times 5) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-02)) \times 96}{((4 \times 37) + 5) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{45738} := \frac{10 - 2 + 96}{457 - 3 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{102 + 9 \times 6}{(4 + 5) \times 7 \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{73458} := \frac{-1 \times 02 + 9 \times 6}{7^3 + 4 \times 5 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{102 + 9 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times (45 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{83754} := \frac{10 - 2 + 96}{837 + 5 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10325}{97468} := \frac{10 \times 3 \times 2 \times 5}{(9 \times 7 - 4) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10329}{68547} := \frac{1 + 03 - 2 + 9}{(6 + 8) \times 5 - 4 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03 + 29}{6^{8-5} - 4 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03 \times 2 \times 9}{6 \times (8 + 54) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times 3^2 + 9}{685 - 4 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{103 + 2 \times 9}{(68 + 5) \times (4 + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10345}{26897} := \frac{((1 - (-03))^4) \times 5}{26 \times (8 \times (9 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^{03}) + 4) \times 5}{(2 - 6) \times 8 + 97}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times 4))) \times 5}{((26 - 8) \times 9) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 34)) \times 5}{((2^6) - (8 - 9)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times (4 \times 5)}{2 + ((6 \times 8) + (9 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times 45}{(2 \times 6) + (8 + 97)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (3 - 4))) \times 5}{2 \times (6 - ((8 - 9) \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 - (3 - 4)) \times 5}{(2^6) + ((8 \times 9) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (3 \times 4)) - 5}{((26 + 8) \times 9) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 34) - 5}{(2 \times (6 \times (8 \times 9))) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (3 - (4 - 5)))}{2 - (((6 - 8) \times 9) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (34 + 5))}{2 + (6 + (89 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (34 - 5))}{2 - (6 - (89 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((3 + 4) \times 5))}{(2 - (6 - (8 + 9))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (3 \times (4 \times 5)))}{26 \times (8 - (9 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - ((3 - 4) \times 5)}{(2^{6+8-9}) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10^{3+4-5}}{26 \times (8 + (9 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 345}{26 + 897}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10354}{97862} := \frac{1 \times 035 - 4}{97 + (8 + 6)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10356}{28479} := \frac{((1^{03}) + 5) \times 6}{2 + ((8 \times (4 + 7)) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times 5))) \times 6}{(2^8) - (4 \times (7 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-03)) \times (5 + 6)}{((2^{8-4}) \times 7) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times 56}{2 + (8 \times ((4 \times 7) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 - (3 - 5)) \times 6}{2 \times ((8 - (4 - 7)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (3 \times 5)) - 6}{((2 \times 8) + (4 \times 7)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + (3 + 5)) \times 6}{(((2 + 8) \times 4) - 7) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (3 + 56))}{2 + (84 + 79)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((3 - 5) \times 6))}{((2 + (8 - 4)) \times 7) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (3 - (5 + 6)))}{2 + (8 - (4 - (7 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (3 - (5 \times 6)))}{2 - (8 - (4 + 79))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (3 - (5 - 6))}{(28 \times 4) + (7 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (3 + (5 - 6))}{28 - ((4 - 7) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{10^{3+5-6}}{(2^8) + ((4 \times 7) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (3 + (5 + 6))}{2 + (8^{4+7-9})}$$

$$:= \frac{103 - (5 - 6)}{284 - (7 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{29754} := \frac{(1 + 03) \times 6 \times 8}{2 + 9 \times (7 + 54)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{45792} := \frac{1 - 03 + 6 + 8}{4 + (5 - 7 + 9)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (-03 + 6) \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 9) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{03} \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times 7 + 9 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 03 + 68}{4 \times 5 \times (7 + 9) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{47952} := \frac{((1 - (-03)) \times 6) - 8}{4 + (7 + (9 \times (5 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((3 - 6) \times 8))}{((4 \times 7) + 9) \times (5 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times (6 \times 8)}{4 - (7 - (9 \times (5^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-03)) \times (6 + 8)}{(4 \times (7 \times 9)) + (5 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (3 + 68))}{4 + (7 \times ((9 \times 5) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 + 6))) \times 8}{((4 \times 7) + 9) \times (5 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-03)) \times 68}{(4 \times (7 \times (9 \times 5))) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{52974} := \frac{(1 + 03) \times 6 \times 8}{5 + 2 + 974}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{74592} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 36 \times 8}{74 \times (5 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{74952} := \frac{(10 - 3) \times 6 \times 8}{7^4 + (9 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{94752} := \frac{10 \times (3 + 6) \times 8}{94 \times 7 \times 5 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 03 \times 6 \times 8}{94 \times (7 + 5 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{97524} := \frac{(1 - 03 + 6) \times 8}{9 + (75 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{62985} &:= \frac{1 \times 03 + 7 + 4}{6 + 2 + 9 \times 8 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 037 + 4}{(6 \times 2 - 9) \times 85} \\ &:= \frac{(10 - 3 + 7) \times 4}{(6 - 2) \times (9 + 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 03 \times 7 \times 4}{(6 - 2 + 98) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 03) \times 7 \times 4}{(6 + 2 + 9) \times 8 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(10 - 3) \times 7 \times 4}{(6 + 29 \times 8) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{69825} &:= \frac{1 - 03 + 7 \times 4}{(6 + 9 - 8) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 03^7 - 4}{6 \times 98 \times 25} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{92568} := \frac{1 - 03 + 7 \times 4}{((9 - 2) \times 5 - 6) \times 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10392}{67548} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 2}{(6 + 7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times (9 \times 2)}{(6 + 7) \times (5 - (4 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{03}) \times 92}{(6 + 7) \times (54 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2}{(6 + 7) \times (5 + (4 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 2))}{6 - (7 \times (5 - (4 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (3 \times (9 + 2)))}{(6 + 7) \times (5 + (4 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 - (3 - 9))^2)}{6 \times ((7 \times 5) - (4 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 39) + 2)}{6 + (7^{5+4-8})} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (3 - (9 + 2)))}{6 - (7 - (5 + 48))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (3 - (9 - 2)))}{6 - (7 + (5 - (4 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((3 + 9) \times 2))}{((6 + (7 \times 5)) \times 4) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((3 + 9)^2))}{(6 + 7) \times ((5 + 4) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 2)))}{(6 + (7 \times (5 - 4))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (3 - (9 - 2))}{67 - ((5 \times 4) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (3 + (9^2))}{(67 \times (5 + 4)) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{42768} := \frac{1 - (0 - (39 - 5))}{4 \times (2 + ((7 \times 6) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (3 + (9 - 5))}{4 + (276 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 \times 3) - 9) \times 5}{(4 - (2 - 7)) \times (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 5}{4 \times ((2 \times 76) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + 39) \times 5}{(4 + ((2^7) - 6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(103 + 9) \times 5}{((42 \times 7) - 6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (3 \times (9 + 5))}{4 \times ((2 + 7) \times (6 \times 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46728} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{4 \times (6 + 7 \times 2 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46827} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{468 - 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46872} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{4 \times (6 + 8 \times 7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{47628} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{476 + 28}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{48762} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{4 + 8^{7-6+2}}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (39 + 5)}{48 \times (7 + 6^2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{62748} &:= \frac{10 \times (3 \times 9 - 5)}{(6 \times 27 + 4) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (39 + 5)}{6^2 \times 74 - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{72468} := \frac{1 + 039 - 5}{7 \times (2 + 4) \times 6 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{76824} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{78246} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{782 + 46}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{82467} &:= \frac{1^{03} + 9 + 5}{8 \times (2 \times 4 + 6) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{(-1 \times 03 + 9) \times 5}{(8 + 2 + 4 \times 6) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{82764} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{8^2 \times (7 + 6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{86427} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{864 + 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{86724} := \frac{1 + 039 - 5}{(8 + 67 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (3 + 9 - 5)}{8 \times (67 + 2 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10396}{27485} := \frac{10^3 - 96}{2 + 7^4 - 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10423}{96785} := \frac{1 - 0 + (4 - 2) \times 3}{((9 - 6) \times 7 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04^2 - 3}{(9 - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04 \times (2 + 3)}{(9 \times 6 - 7 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04^2 \times 3}{9 \times (6 \times 7 + 8) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 042 \times 3}{(9 - 6) \times 78 \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10437}{25986} &:= \frac{(1 \times 04 + 3) \times 7}{2 \times (59 + 8 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + 4) \times 3 \times 7}{2 \times (5 \times (9 \times 8) + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10437}{59682} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 4^3 + 7}{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 8 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10439}{75628} := \frac{104 + 39}{(7 + 5 \times 6) \times 28}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10439}{76285} &:= \frac{1^{04} \times 39}{(7 - 6) \times 285} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 043 + 9}{(7 \times 6 \times 2 - 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1^{04} + 3 + 9}{(7 + 6 - 2 + 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 04 \times 39}{76 \times (2 + 8 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (43 + 9)}{76 \times (2 + 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{10 + 4^3 - 9}{7 + 6^2 \times (8 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{67938} &:= \frac{((1^{04}) + 5)^2}{6 \times ((7 \times 9) - (3 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 45)) \times 2}{(67 \times 9) + (3 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{04}) \times (5 \times 2)}{67 + (9 - (3 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (4 \times 5)) + 2}{(6 + 7) \times (93 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (4 \times 5)) - 2}{(6 + 7) \times (9 \times (3 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (4 \times 5)) \times 2}{6 + ((7 + 9) \times (3 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 - (5 - 2)))}{6 - (7 - (9 - (3 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + (5 - 2)))}{67 + (9 - (3 \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - 52))}{6 \times (7 - (9 \times (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 \times 2)))}{(6 \times (7 \times (9 - 3))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 + 2)))}{6 + ((7 + 9) \times (3 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4^{5-2}))}{(6 \times (7 \times 9)) + 38}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + (5 \times 2)))}{(6 \times (7 + 9)) + (3 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 - (5^2)))}{(6 \times 7) + (93 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 - (5 + 2)))}{(6 \times (7 - 9)) + 38}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - (4 - (5 \times 2))}{6 + (7 \times (9 - (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((4 \times 5) + 2)}{(6 \times (79 \times 3)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (4 + (5 - 2))}{(6 + 7) \times ((9 \times 3) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((4 \times 5) + 2)}{(6 - (7 - (9 \times 3))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (4 \times (5 + 2))}{((6 + 79) \times 3) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (4 + (5 \times 2))}{6 \times (7 + ((9 \times 3) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (4 + 52)}{(6 + 7) \times (9 + (3 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{104 - (5 \times 2)}{(6 + 7) \times (9 + 38)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{73968} := \frac{1^{04} + 5^2}{7 - 3 \times (9 - 68)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04^{5-2}}{(7 + 3) \times (9 \times 6 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 04 \times (5 - 2)}{7 - 3 + 96 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 045 \times 2}{(7 + 39) \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{104 \times (5 - 2)}{(7 + 39) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{76983} := \frac{1^{04} \times 52}{7 \times 6 \times 9 + 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10458}{27639} := \frac{1 \times 04 \times 5 + 8}{2 + 7 \times (6 + 3) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 04 \times 5) \times 8}{(2 - 76) \times (3 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10459}{83672} := \frac{((10 + 4) \times 5) - 9}{8 \times (((3 + 6) \times 7) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + 5))) \times 9}{8 \times (3 \times (6 \times (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) - (5 - 9)}{8 \times (3 - ((6 - 7) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) \times (5 \times 9)}{8 \times (3 \times (6 + (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) \times (5 + 9)}{8 \times (3 + (6 + (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) \times 59}{(8^3) - ((6 \times 7) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) + (5 \times 9)}{8 \times (3 - (6 - (7^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{04}) + 59}{8 \times (3 \times (6 + (7 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - 5)))^9}{8^{3+6-7+2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 - (4 - 5)) \times 9}{(8 - (3 - 6)) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 4) + (5 \times 9)}{8 \times (36 + (7^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 45) - 9}{8 \times ((3 + 6) \times (7^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + (4 \times 5)) \times 9}{(8 - 3) \times (6 \times 72)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((4 + 5) \times 9))}{8 + ((3 + 6) \times 72)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 - (5 - 9)))}{8 \times ((3 \times 6) - (7 + 2))}$$

$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 \times (5 + 9)))}{8 \times (3 + (6 \times (7 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 - (5 + 9)))}{8 \times (3 - (6 - (7 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 9}{8 \times (3 \times ((7 \times 5) - 2))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + (5 \times 9)))}{8 \times (36 + (7 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 \times (5 - 9)))}{8 - ((3 - 67) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{(1^{04}) - (6 - 9)}{8 + (3 + (7 \times (5 - 2)))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + (5 + 9)))}{83 + (67 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{10 - (4 \times (5 - 9))}{((8 - 3) \times (6 \times 7)) - 2}$	$:= \frac{(1^{04}) + 69}{8 \times ((3 + 7) \times (5 + 2))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + 59))}{8^{3^{6-7+2}}}$	$:= \frac{10 - (4 - 59)}{(8 + (36 \times 7)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 9}{8 \times (3 + ((7 + 5) \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (45 - 9))}{8 \times ((3 \times (6 + 7)) - 2)}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((4 \times 5) - 9)}{(83 - (6 - 7)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times (4 \times 6)) + 9}{83 \times ((7 + 5) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (4 - 59))}{8 - (3 + (6 - (7 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((4 + 5) \times 9)}{8 + ((3^6) - (7 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times (4 \times 6)) - 9}{8 \times (3 \times (75 + 2))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 459)}{8 + 3672}$	$:= \frac{10 + (4 + (5 + 9))}{8 - ((3 - 6) \times 72)}$	$:= \frac{(10 + (4 - 6)) \times 9}{8 \times (3 \times ((7 + 5) \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 4) - (5 - 9))}{8 \times (3 + (6 - (7 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (45 \times 9)}{83 \times ((6 \times 7) - 2)}$	$:= \frac{(10 + (4 - 6))^9}{8^{3+7-5} \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - (5 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((3 \times (6 + 7)) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{104 - (5 - 9)}{8 \times (36 + 72)}$	$:= \frac{(10 + 4) \times (6 + 9)}{8 \times (3 \times (7 \times (5 \times 2)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - (5 + 9)))}{8 + (3 + (67 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{104 + (5 + 9)}{(8^3) + (6 \times 72)}$	$:= \frac{1 - ((0 \times 46) - 9)}{8 \times ((3 + (7 - 5)) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 \times (5 - 9)))}{8 \times ((3 - (6 - 7))^2)}$	$:= \frac{104 + 59}{8 + (3 \times (6 \times 72))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((4 \times 6) + 9))}{8 \times ((3 \times (7 + 5)) - 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - 59))}{(8 + 3) \times ((6 \times 7) - 2)}$	$:= \frac{1045 - 9}{(8^3) + (6^{7-2})}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((4 \times 6) - 9))}{83 - (7 - 52)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 5) + 9))}{8 \times (3 + ((6 + 7) \times 2))}$		$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 - (6 - 9)))}{8 - (3 - (7 + 52))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 + 5) \times 9))}{8 \times (3 + (6 + 72))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10465}{73892} := \frac{104 + 6 + 5}{7 \times (3 \times 8 + 92)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 \times (6 + 9)))}{(8^3) - ((7 + 5) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 + 5)^9))}{8 \times ((3 + 6)^{7+2})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10465}{97382} := \frac{10 \times 46 - 5}{9 + (73 - 8)^2}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 9)))}{8 \times (3 + (7 + (5 \times 2)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 - (5 - 9)))}{8^{3-6+7-2}}$		$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (4 + (6 - 9)))}{8 \times ((3 - (7 - 5)) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 \times 9)))}{8 \times (36 \times (7 - 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10469}{83752} := \frac{((1 - (-04)) \times 6) - 9}{8 \times (3 - (7 - (5^2)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (46 + 9))}{((83 + 7) \times 5) - 2}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + (5 + 9)))}{8 \times (3 + (6 + (7 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{((1 - (-04))^6) \times 9}{8 \times (375^2)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (46 - 9))}{8 \times ((3 \times (7 + 5)) + 2)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + 59))}{(8^3) + (6 - (7 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{((1^{04}) + 6) \times 9}{8 \times (3 \times (7 \times (5 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (4 - 69))}{8 - (3 \times (7 - (5 + 2)))}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((0 - (4 - 5))^9)}{8 \times (3 - (6 - (7 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 \times 6))) \times 9}{8 \times ((3 + (7 + 5))^2)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 469)}{8 + 3752}$

$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 - (4 - 6))^9)}{8^{3 \times (7-5)-2}}$	$:= \frac{10 \times ((4 + 6)^9)}{8 \times (((3 + 7)^5)^2)}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times (4 + 7)) + 6}{(3 + (92 - 8)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 4) - (6 - 9))}{8 \times (3 - (7 - (5 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (46 + 9)}{(8 + ((3^7) + 5)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times (4 + 7)) - 6}{3 \times ((9 \times 2 + 8) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 46) + 9)}{8 - ((3 - (7 \times 5)) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (46 - 9)}{8 \times (37 \times (5 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (7 + 6)))}{39 \times (2 + (8 - 5))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((4 - 6) \times 9))}{8 \times ((3^{7-5}) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{10^{4-6+9}}{8 \times ((3 + 7)^{5+2})}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{3 - (9 - ((2 \times 8) + 5))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - (6 \times 9)))}{((8 + (3 - 7)) \times 5)^2}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((4 \times 6) - 9)}{8 \times ((3 + (7 - 5))^2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + 76))}{3 + (9 \times (28 + 5))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 - (6 + 9)))}{8 + (3 + (75 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((4 + 6) \times 9)}{8 \times ((3 + 7) \times (5 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + 476)}{3 \times ((9 - 2) \times 85)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (4 \times (6 - 9)))}{8 \times (3 \times (7 - (5 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (4 - (6 - 9))}{8 \times (3 + (7 + (5 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 - ((4 - 7) \times 6)}{3 \times (9 + (2 \times (8 + 5)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) + 9))}{8 + (((3 \times 7) - 5)^2)}$	$:= \frac{10 + (4 + (6 \times 9))}{(8^3) + (7 + (5^2))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times ((4 \times 7) + 6)}{(3 + (9 \times 28)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) - 9))}{(8 - (3 - 7)) \times (5 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{10 + (46 - 9)}{8 \times (37 + (5 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (4 \times (7 + 6))}{39 \times ((2 + 8) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((4 + 6) \times 9))}{(8 - 3) \times ((7 + 5)^2)}$	$:= \frac{104 - (6 + 9)}{8 \times (37 + 52)}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (4 \times (7 - 6))}{3 \times (((9 \times 2) - 8) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 - (6 - 9)))}{8 + (3 - (7 - 52))}$	$:= \frac{104 - (6 - 9)}{8 \times ((3 \times (7 \times 5)) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((4 \times 7) + 6)}{(39 + (2 - 8)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 \times 9)))}{(8 - (3 - 7))^{5-2}}$	$:= \frac{104 + (6 \times 9)}{(8^3) + 752}$	$:= \frac{10 + (4 + (7 \times 6))}{3 + (9 \times (28 - 5))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 9)))}{(8^3) - (7 + (5^2))}$	$:= \frac{104 - 69}{8 \times (3 + (7 + (5^2)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (47 \times 6)}{3 \times (((9^2) - 8) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + (6 + 9)))}{8 - ((3 - 75) \times 2)}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{82935} := \frac{(1^{04} + 7) \times 6}{(82 - 9 + 3) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (4 + 69))}{8 \times (3 + (7 \times (5 \times 2)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{39285} := \frac{((1^{04}) + 7) \times 6}{3 + (92 + 85)}$	$:= \frac{(10 - 4) \times 7 - 6}{(8 + 2 + 9) \times 3 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (46 + 9))}{8 + (3 \times ((7 + 5)^2))}$	$:= \frac{((10 + 4) \times 7) - 6}{3 - (9 \times (2 - (8 \times 5)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{92538} := \frac{(1 - 04 + 7) \times 6}{92 + 5 \times 3 \times 8}$
$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 - (6 \times 9)))}{8 \times (3 \times (7 + (5 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{((10 - 4) \times 7) - 6}{3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 - 5)))}$	
$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 \times (6 - 9)))}{8 + (3 \times (7 + (5^2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^{04}) \times 76}{(3 - (9 \times (2 - 8))) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10489}{67253} := \frac{(1^{04} \times 8 + 9)}{6 + 7 + 2^5 \times 3}$
$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (4 - 69))}{8 + ((3 + 7) \times 52)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - 7))) \times 6}{(3 + (9 - (2 - 8))) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{10 + 4 \times 8 + 9}{6 \times (7^2 + 5) + 3}$
$:= \frac{10 - ((4 - 6) \times 9)}{8 \times ((3 \times 7) + (5 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - 7)))^6}{(3 + 9) \times ((2^8) \times 5)}$	

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{46893} &:= \frac{1+05-2+7}{4-6+(8+9)\times 3} &:= \frac{1\times(0+(5-(3-6)))}{2+(8+(9+(7-4)))} &:= \frac{(1-(0-(5+3)))\times 7}{84\times(2\times(9-6))} \\
 &:= \frac{1+05+27}{46+8+93} &:= \frac{1\times(0+536)}{2\times(8+(9^{7-4}))} &:= \frac{(1-(-05))\times(3\times 7)}{8\times(42\times(9-6))} \\
 &:= \frac{10+5\times(2+7)}{4\times 68-9\times 3} &:= \frac{1+(0-(5\times(3-6)))}{(2\times(8+(9+7))) - 4} &:= \frac{(1^{05})+37}{8\times((4\times(2+9))-6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+05\times 2)\times 7}{(4\times 6-8-9)^3} &:= \frac{1+(0-(5-36))}{2+(89-(7-4))} &:= \frac{(10\times(5+3))+7}{(8-4)\times(29\times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{49368} &:= \frac{(1+05)^2-7}{4\times(9-3)\times 6-8} &:= \frac{10\times((5-3)^6)}{(28\times(9\times 7))-4} &:= \frac{(10\times(5+3))-7}{8+((4+2)\times 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{10+5\times 27}{(4+9\times(3+6))\times 8} &:= \frac{10\times(5\times(3\times 6))}{2+((8\times 9)+(7^4))} &:= \frac{(10\times(5-3))-7}{8+(4\times((2\times 9)+6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10+5)^2+7}{(4+9+3)\times 68} &:= \frac{10\times(5+(3-6))}{28+(9\times(7-4))} &:= \frac{(10\times 5)-(3\times 7)}{8+(4\times(2+(9\times 6)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{86394} &:= \frac{(1+05)^2-7}{8+6\times 39-4} &:= \frac{10^{5+3-6}}{(2^8)-(9-(7\times 4))} &:= \frac{(10\times 5)-(3-7)}{(8\times 42)+96} \\
 &:= \frac{(10+5)^2+7}{8\times(6\times 39+4)} & & &:= \frac{(10^{5-3})-7}{(8+(4\times 29))\times 6} \\
 & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10536}{48729} &:= \frac{1\times((05-(3-6)))}{4+(8+(7+(2\times 9)))} &:= \frac{(10+(5-3))\times 7}{84\times(2^{9-6})} \\
 & & &:= \frac{1+(0-(5-36))}{4+(8\times(7+(2+9)))} &:= \frac{(10+5)\times(3\times 7)}{84\times(2\times(9+6))} \\
 & & &:= \frac{(10+(5-3))\times 6}{((4\times 8)+(7-2))\times 9} &:= \frac{1-((0\times 53)-7)}{8+(4-(2-(9\times 6)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10536}{28974} &:= \frac{(1-(0-(5\times 3)))\times 6}{(2+(8^{9-7}))\times 4} & &:= \frac{10\times(5-(3-6))}{((4+(8+7))^2)+9} &:= \frac{1-(0-((5\times 3)+7))}{8\times((4\times 2)+(9+6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{05})\times 36}{(2\times 8)+(9+74)} & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3\times 6)))}{(4\times((8+7)\times 2))-9} &:= \frac{1-(0-((5+3)\times 7))}{8\times(42+(9+6))} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(0-((5^3)+6))}{289+74} & &:= \frac{(1-(-05))\times 36}{487+(2^9)} &:= \frac{1-(0-((5-3)^7))}{8+4^{2+9-6}} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(0-((5^3)-6))}{2+((89-7)\times 4)} & & & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5-(3-7)))}{8\times(4+(2\times(9-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3\times 6)))}{2+(8\times((9-7)\times 4))} & & & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3\times 7)))}{8-(4\times(2-(9\times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(0-(53+6))}{2+(89+74)} & & & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3+7)))}{8+(4\times(2\times(9+6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(0-(53-6))}{(2\times(8^{9-7}))+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{10537}{84296} &:= \frac{((1-(-05))\times 3)+7}{8+((4-2)\times 96)} & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3-7)))}{8-(4-(2\times(9-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times(0-(5-(3+6)))}{(2+(8-9))\times(7+4)} & &:= \frac{((1-(-05))\times 3)-7}{8-((4^2)-96)} & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3+7)))}{8+(4\times(2\times(9+6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times(0+((5-3)\times 6))}{(2-(8-9))\times(7+4)} & &:= \frac{((1^{05})+3)\times 7}{8\times(4+((2\times 9)+6))} & &:= \frac{1-(0-(5+(3-7)))}{8-(4-((2\times 9)-6))} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times(0+((5-3)^6))}{(28+(9+7))\times 4} & &:= \frac{(1-(0-(5\times 3)))\times 7}{8\times(4+(2\times(9\times 6)))} & &:= \frac{1-(0-(53\times 7))}{8\times((42\times 9)-6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (5 - 37))}{8^{4^2-9-6}}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (3 + 7)))}{8 \times ((4 - 2) \times (9 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times 4))) \times 2}{3 + (6 \times (8 + (9 + 7)))}$
$:= \frac{1 + 0537}{8 + 4296}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 \times (3 - 7)))}{8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 4))) \times 2}{(3 + (6 - (8 - 9))) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 5) - (3 - 7))}{8 + (4 \times (2 \times (9 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - 37))}{(84 \times 2) + 96}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 54)) \times 2}{(3 \times ((6 + 8) \times 9)) + 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 53) + 7)}{8 - (4 + (2 - (9 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 - (5 \times (3 - 7))}{(8 \times 42) - 96}$	$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (4^2)}{(3 + (6 + (8 - 9))) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - (3 + 7)))}{8 + (4 \times (2^{9-6}))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times ((5 - 3) \times 7)}{8 \times (4 \times (29 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (4 + 2)}{3 - (6 - (8 + (9 + 7)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 \times (3 - 7)))}{8 \times (4 \times (2 + (9 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (5 - (3 - 7))}{8 \times ((4 + (2 + 9)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times 5) - (4^2)}{((3 \times 6) + (8 - 9)) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - 37))}{8 \times (4 \times (2^{9-6}))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + (3 \times 7))}{8 + (4 \times ((2^9) + 6))}$	$:= \frac{(10^{5+4}) \times 2}{(((3 \times 6) - 8)^9) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) + 7))}{8 - (4 \times ((2 - 9) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + (3 + 7))}{8 \times (((4^2) + 9) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{(10 + (5 \times 4)) \times 2}{3 \times (6 + (8^{9-7}))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5^3) + 7))}{8 \times ((4 + (2 \times 9)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (53 + 7)}{(8 + 42) \times 96}$	$:= \frac{(10 + 5) \times (4 \times 2)}{(3 + ((6 \times 8) + 9)) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 3) \times 7))}{8 \times (4 - (2 - (9 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((5 \times 3) - 7)}{8 \times ((4 + 2) \times (9 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{(10 + 54) \times 2}{(36 - 8) \times (9 + 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 3)^7))}{8^{4-2)^{9-6}}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((5 + 3) \times 7)}{8 \times ((4 - (2 - 9)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 - (4 - 2)))}{(3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))) - 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3) \times 7))}{8 - (4 - (2 \times (9 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((5 - 3) \times 7)}{8 \times (4 \times (2 \times (9 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5^{4-2}))}{3 + (6 + (89 - 7))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3)^7))}{(8^4) - ((2^9) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((5 - 3)^7)}{8 \times (42 + 96)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (4 \times 2)))}{3 + ((6 \times 8) - (9 - 7))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 - (3 - 7)))}{8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 - (3 - 7))}{8 \times ((4^2) + (9 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (4 - 2)))}{(3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))) + 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (3 + 7)))}{8 + (4 \times (2 + 96))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (3 \times 7))}{(8 + 4) \times ((2 \times 9) + 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + 42))}{3 + (68 + 97)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 + (3 + 7)))}{8 + (4 + (2 \times (9 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (53 + 7)}{8 \times (4 + ((2 + 9) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 4) \times 2))}{3 + (6 \times (8 + (9 - 7)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 + 37))}{8 \times (((4^2) - 9) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{105 - (3 - 7)}{8 + ((4^2) \times (9 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (4 + 2)))}{3 + (6 + (89 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (53 + 7))}{8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{105 - 37}{8 \times (4 \times (2 + (9 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (4 - 2)))}{3 - ((6 - 8) \times (9 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (53 - 7))}{8 \times (4 - ((2 - 9) \times 6))}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times 42))}{(3 + (6 \times (8 + 9))) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (3 \times 7)))}{8 \times (4 - (2 - (9 + 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10542}{36897} := \frac{((1 - (-05))^4) \times 2}{3 \times (6 \times (8 \times (9 \times 7)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (54 - 2))}{(3 + (6 + (8 + 9))) \times 7}$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (4^2)))}{3 \times (6 - (8 - (9 + 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (4 + 2)))}{3 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - 42))}{(36 - (8 + 9)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((5 + 4) \times 2)}{((3 \times 6) + (8 \times 9)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5^{4 \times 2})}{((3 - (6 - 8))^9) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5^{4-2})}{(36 + 89) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + (4 - 2))}{(36 + (8 - 9)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (54 \times 2)}{36 \times (8 + 97)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((5 \times 4) + 2)}{3 + ((6 \times (8 + 9)) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((5 + 4) \times 2)}{3 + (6 - (8 - 97))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (5 \times (4^2))}{(3 - (6 - 8)) \times (9 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (54 + 2)}{3 \times (6 + (8 + (9 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1054 + 2}{3689 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1054 - 2}{3689 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10549}{26873} := \frac{105 \times 4 - 9}{2 \times 6 \times 87 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10564}{79382} := \frac{10 \times 56 - 4}{(7 + 9)^3 + 82}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10569}{28743} := \frac{1 + 05 \times 6 \times 9}{2 - 8 + 743}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10578}{32964} := \frac{1 \times 05 \times 7 + 8}{(32 - 9) \times 6 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 \times 7 + 8)}{(329 + 6) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10579}{84632} := \frac{((1 - (-05)) \times 7) + 9}{8 \times (46 + 3 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - (-05)) \times 7) - 9}{8 \times ((4 \times 6) + (3^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^{05}) + 7) \times 9}{8 \times (4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^{05}) + 7)^9}{(8 + (4 \times 6))^{3 \times 2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times 7))) \times 9}{8 \times (4 \times ((6 + 3)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-05)) \times (7 \times 9)}{84 \times (6 \times (3 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-05)) \times (7 + 9)}{(8 - 4) \times (6 \times 32)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (7 \times 9)}{84 \times (6 \times (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (7 + 9)}{8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{05}) + (7 \times 9)}{8^{4-6+3+2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{05}) + (7 + 9)}{8 + ((4^{6-3}) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 7))) \times 9}{(8 - 4) \times (6 \times (3^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + 7)) + 9}{8 + (4^{6-3+2})}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 5) - (7 + 9)}{8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 5) - (7 - 9)}{8 \times (46 + (3 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 \times 7) + 9))}{8 \times (46 - (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 + 7) \times 9))}{(8 - 4) \times ((6^3) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 - (7 - 9)))}{8^{4-6+3} \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 \times (7 \times 9)))}{(8 - 4) \times 632}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 \times (7 + 9)))}{(8 + 4) \times (6 \times (3^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (7 \times 9)))}{8 \times (4 + (63 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (7 + 9)))}{8 \times (4 + ((6 + 3) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (7 - 9)))}{8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + 79))}{8 \times (4 + ((6 + 3)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (57 \times 9))}{(8^4) + ((6 \times 3) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (57 + 9))}{(84 \times 6) + 32}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (57 - 9))}{8 \times ((4 + (6 - 3))^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (5 - 79))}{8^{4+6-3^2}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 579)}{8 + 4632}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 - (5 - 7))^9)}{8^4 \times (6 - 3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 5) - (7 - 9))}{8 - (4 - (6 + (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 57) + 9)}{8 \times (4 + (6 - (3 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((5 - 7) \times 9))}{(8 + (4^{6-3})) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - (7 \times 9)))}{8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 \times (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - 79))}{8 \times ((4 \times (6 \times 3)) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 7) + 9))}{8 \times (4 \times (6 + 3 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 7) - 9))}{8 \times ((4 + (6 + 3)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 7) \times 9))}{8 + (4 \times ((6^3) - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 7)^9))}{(8^4) \times (6^{3^2})}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 - (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (4 - (6 - (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (7 \times 9)))}{84 \times (6 \times (3 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (7 + 9)))}{8 \times (4 \times ((6 \times 3) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 + (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (4 - (6 - (3 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (57 \times 9))}{8 + (4^6 \times (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (57 + 9))}{8 \times ((4^{6-3}) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (57 - 9))}{8 \times (4 \times (6 + (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - ((5 - 7) \times 9))}{8 \times (4 + (6 + (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (7 \times 9)))}{(84 \times 6) - 32}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (7 + 9)))}{84 + (6 + (3 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 \times (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (4 + (6 + (3 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - 79))}{(84 + (6^3)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - ((5 - 7) \times 9)}{8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 - (5 \times (7 - 9))}{8 + (4 \times (6 + 32))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)}{8 \times ((4 + (6^3)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)}{8 \times (4 \times (63 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 - (7 - 9))}{8 \times ((4 \times (6 \times 3)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 \times (7 + 9))}{(8 + (4 \times (6 \times 3)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + (7 + 9))}{84 \times ((6 \times 3) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + (7 - 9))}{8 \times (4 - (6 - 32))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((5 \times 7) + 9)}{8 - ((4 - (6^3)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)}{8 \times (4 \times ((6 - 3)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (5 \times (7 + 9))}{8 \times ((4 + 6) \times (3^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (7 \times 9))}{8 \times (46 + 32)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (7 - 9))}{8 \times (4 + ((6 - 3)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{105 - (7 \times 9)}{8 \times (4 + (6 + 32))}$$

$$:= \frac{105 - (7 - 9)}{(8 - 4) \times ((6^3) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{105 + (7 \times 9)}{84 \times ((6 \times 3) - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{29736} := \frac{1 + 05 \times (8 - 4)}{(2 + 9) \times 7 - 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{36792} := \frac{1 + 058 + 4}{3 \times 67 + 9 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{36 + (7 + 9)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{37296} := \frac{1 + 05 \times (8 - 4)}{3 + 7 \times (2 + 9) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 058 + 4}{37 \times 2 \times (9 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{37 \times 2^{9-6}}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + 8) - 4}{37 \times (2 \times 9 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{37926} := \frac{(1 + 05) \times (8 - 4)}{3 + 7 \times (9 + 2) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 05 \times 8 - 4}{3 \times (7 - 9 \times (2 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 05 \times (8 + 4)}{3 \times 7 \times 9 + 26}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{3 \times 79 + 2^6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 05) \times (8 + 4)}{3 \times (7 + 9^2) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 05) \times 84}{3 \times 7 \times (92 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{62937} := \frac{(10 \times 5 - 8) \times 4}{62 + 937}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{79632} := \frac{1 - 0 + 5 \times (8 - 4)}{(7 + 9 + 63) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 0 + 58 + 4}{79 \times 6 \times (3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (5 + 8) - 4}{79 \times (6 + 3 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 5 - 8) \times 4}{79 \times (6 \times 3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{105 + 84}{79 \times ((6 + 3) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{92736} := \frac{(10 \times 5 - 8) \times 4}{92 \times (7 + 3 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{105 + 84}{927 + 3^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10592}{84736} := \frac{((1^{05}) + 9) \times 2}{8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^{05}) + 9)^2}{8 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 9))) \times 2}{(8 - 4) \times ((7 + 3) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 9)))^2}{(8 + (4 \times 73)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-05)) \times (9 \times 2)}{8 \times (4 \times ((7 \times 3) + 6))}$$

$:= \frac{(1 - (-05)) \times (9 + 2)}{(84 + (7 - 3)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + 92))}{8 + (47 + (3^6))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 + 92)}{847 + (3 + 6)}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (-05)) \times (9 - 2)}{84 + (7 \times 36)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (5 - 92))}{8 - (4 - (7 + (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (59 + 2)}{8 \times (4 + (73 - 6))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (9 \times 2)}{(8 + (4 \times (7 - 3))) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 592)}{8 + 4736}$	$:= \frac{10 + (59 - 2)}{8 \times (4 + (7 \times (3 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (9^2)}{(8 + (4 \times 7)) \times (3 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((5 - 9) \times 2))}{8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{105 + (9^2)}{8 \times ((4 \times 7) + 3) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(1^{05}) \times (9 + 2)}{8 \times (47 - 36)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - (9 + 2)))}{8 + (4 \times (7 - (3 - 6)))}$	
$:= \frac{(1^{05}) + (9 \times 2)}{8 \times (4 + ((7 \times 3) - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (5 - (9 - 2)))}{8 + (4 + (7 + (3 - 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10598}{23467} := \frac{10 + 5 - 9 + 8}{(2^3 - 4) \times 6 + 7}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 9))) \times 2}{8 \times ((4 \times (7 - 3)) - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 9) + 2))}{8 \times (4 + (7 + 36))}$	$:= \frac{10 - (5 - 9) \times 8}{2 + (3 + 4 + 6) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 9)))^2}{8 \times (4 - (7 \times (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((5 + 9) \times 2))}{8 \times (4 + ((7 - 3) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{(1 \times 05 + 9) \times 8}{2^3 \times (4 \times 6 + 7)}$
$:= \frac{(10 \times 5) - (9 \times 2)}{8 - (4 - (7 \times 36))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 \times (9 \times 2)))}{8 \times ((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6)}$	
$:= \frac{(10 \times 5) - (9 + 2)}{(8 + (47 - 3)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 + (9 + 2)))}{8 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 - 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10634}{29857} := \frac{10 + 6 \times (3 + 4)}{2 - 9 \times 8 \times (5 - 7)}$
$:= \frac{(10 + 5) \times (9 - 2)}{84 \times (7 - (3 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (5 + (9 - 2)))}{(8 + (4 + (7 - 3))) \times 6}$	
$:= \frac{(105 - 9) \times 2}{((8 - 4)^{7-3}) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - ((5 - 9) \times 2))}{8 + (4 \times (7 + (3 + 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10635}{97842} := \frac{1 + 06 + 3 - 5}{9 + 7 + 8 \times 4 - 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 \times 9) + 2))}{8 \times ((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (9 \times 2)))}{8 \times (4 + (7 - (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 06 + 3 + 5}{(9 + (7 + 8) \times 4) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 \times 9) - 2))}{8 \times (47 + (3 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (9 + 2)))}{8 + ((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 06 - 3) \times 5}{9 + 7 + 84 \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 + 9) \times 2))}{8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - (9 - 2)))}{8 + (4 \times (7 + (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (6 + 3) \times 5}{9 \times 7 \times 8 + 4 - 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((5 + 9)^2))}{847 + (3^6)}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((5 + 9) \times 2)}{8 \times (47 - (3 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (6 - 3 + 5)}{9 \times (78 + 4) - 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 \times (9 + 2)))}{8 \times (47 + (3 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 \times (9 + 2))}{8 \times (47 + (3 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (6 + 3) - 5}{97 \times 8 + 4 + 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 \times (9 - 2)))}{(8 + (4 \times (7 + 3))) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (9 \times 2))}{8 \times (4 - (7 - 36))}$	
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (9 \times 2)))}{(8 + 4) \times (7 + (3 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (9^2))}{8 \times (4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6))}$	
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (9 - 2)))}{8 + (4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (5 + (9 - 2))}{8 \times ((4 \times (7 - 3)) + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10638}{95742} := \frac{((1 - (-06)) \times 3)^8}{(9^5) \times (7^{4 \times 2})}$
		$:= \frac{((1 - (-06)) \times 3) + 8}{9 \times ((5 \times 7) - (4 + 2))}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{((1 - (-06)) \times 3) - 8}{9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) - 2)} \\
 := \frac{((10 \times 6) - 3) \times 8}{9 \times (57 \times (4 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{((10 \times 6) - 3)^8}{9 \times (57^{4 \times 2})} \\
 := \frac{((10 - 6) \times 3)^8}{9 \times ((5 + 7)^{4 \times 2})} \\
 := \frac{((10 - 6) \times 3) - 8}{9 \times (5 - (7 - (4 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (-06)) \times (3 + 8)}{9 \times (5 + (74 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{(1^{06}) + 38}{9 + (57 \times (4 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{(10 \times (6 + 3)) + 8}{(9 + (5 + 7)) \times 42} \\
 := \frac{(10 \times 6) - (3 + 8)}{9 \times (57 - (4 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{(10 \times 6) + (3 \times 8)}{9 + (5 + 742)} \\
 := \frac{(10 - 6) \times (3 \times 8)}{9 \times ((5 + 7) \times (4 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((0 \times 63) - 8)}{9 + ((5 + 7) \times (4 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 \times 3) + 8))}{9 \times (5 + ((7 + 4) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6^3) + 8))}{9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4))^2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 + 3) \times 8))}{9 \times (57 + (4^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 - 3) \times 8))}{9 \times (5 \times (7 - (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 - 3)^8))}{(9^5) - (7 - (4^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 - (3 - 8)))}{9 + (57 + 42)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (3 + 8)))}{9 \times (5 + (7 + (4 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (3 - 8)))}{9 - (5 - (7 \times (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + 38))}{9 \times (5 \times (7 + (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (63 + 8))}{9 \times ((5 + 7) \times (4 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 \times (6 - 38))}{9 - (5 - (7 - (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - 638)}{9 + 5742} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 63) + 8)}{9 + (57 + (4 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (3 + 8)))}{9 \times 5^{7-4-2}} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 \times (3 - 8)))}{9 \times (5 \times ((7 - 4) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - 38))}{9 \times ((5 + (7 + 4)) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 3) + 8))}{9 + ((5 \times (7 - 4))^2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 3) - 8))}{9 \times (5 + (7 - (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 - 3) \times 8))}{9 \times ((5 + 7) \times (4 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 - 3)^8))}{9^{5^{7-4-2}}} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 - (3 - 8)))}{9 \times (5 + ((7 - 4) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3 \times 8)))}{9 \times ((5 + 7)^{4-2})} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3^8)))}{(9^5) \times ((7 - 4) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3 + 8)))}{9 \times ((5 + (7 \times 4)) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (3 + 8)))}{9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + 38))}{(9 + 57) \times (4 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (63 \times 8))}{9 \times ((5 + 7) \times 42)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (63 - 8))}{9 \times (57 - (4 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + 638)}{957 \times (4 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (3 \times 8)))}{9 \times (5 + (7 \times (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (3 + 8)))}{9 - (5 \times (7 - (4^2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 \times (3 - 8)))}{9 \times (5 + ((7 \times 4) - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - 38))}{9 \times ((5 \times 7) - (4 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 - (3 \times 8))}{9 \times (5 + (7 + (4^2)))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 - (3 + 8))}{9 + (5 + ((7 + 4)^2))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 \times (3 - 8))}{9 \times (5 - (7 - 42))} \\
 := \frac{10 \times (6 - (3 - 8))}{9 \times (5 \times ((7 + 4) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 \times (6 + (3 + 8))}{9 + (((5 \times 7) + 4)^2)} \\
 := \frac{10 + ((6 \times 3) + 8)}{(9 \times (5 - (7 - 4)))^2} \\
 := \frac{10 + ((6 \times 3) - 8)}{9 \times (5 + (7 + (4 \times 2)))} \\
 := \frac{10 + (6 + 38)}{9 \times (5 + (7 + 42))} \\
 := \frac{10 + (63 + 8)}{9 \times (5 + (74 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 + (63 - 8)}{9 \times (5 \times (7 + (4 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{106 - (3 + 8)}{95 \times (7 + (4 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{106 - (3 - 8)}{957 + 42} \\
 := \frac{106 + (3 \times 8)}{9 \times (5 \times ((7 \times 4) - 2))} \\
 := \frac{106 + (3 + 8)}{9 \times (5 + (7 \times (4^2)))} \\
 := \frac{106 - 38}{(95 + 7) \times (4 + 2)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10642}{59783} := \frac{10^{6-4} + 2}{597 - 8 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{25389} := \frac{10 + 6 + 4 - 7}{2 \times 5 \times 3 - 8 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{106 + 4 + 7}{(2 + 5 + 3 \times 8) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 064) \times 7}{2 \times 538 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{53928} := \frac{1 + 06 \times 4 \times 7}{(5^3 - 9 \times 2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{59283} := \frac{1 + 06 \times 4 \times 7}{59 \times 2 \times 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{85293} := \frac{(1 + 064) \times 7}{(8 - 5 + 2) \times 9^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{95823} := \frac{((1^{06}) + 4)^7}{9 \times 5^{8+2-3}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + 4))) \times 7}{9 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 2)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 - 4))) \times 7}{9 \times (5 + (8 + (2^3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (4 \times 7)}{(9 + 5) \times ((8 - 2) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (4 + 7)}{9 + (5 + (82 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times 47}{9 \times ((5 \times (8 + 2)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (4 \times 7)}{9 \times (((5 + 8) \times 2) + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (4 + 7)}{9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + 47}{((9 - (5 - 8))^2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(10^{6-4}) + 7}{958 + (2 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10^{6-4}) - 7}{9 + (5 + 823)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + (6 - 4)) \times 7}{9 \times (5 + (82 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((0 \times 64) - 7)}{9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 \times 4) + 7))}{(9 + (5 + 82)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 - 4) \times 7))}{9 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 - (4 - 7)))}{9 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (4 \times 7)))}{9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + 4 - 7))}{9 + ((5 \times (8 - 2)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (64 + 7))}{9 \times (5 + ((8^2) + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (64 - 7))}{(95 - 8) \times (2 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (6 - 47))}{9 - (5 \times (8 - (2^3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 647)}{9 + 5823}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 64) + 7)}{9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (4 \times 7)))}{9 + (5 + (8 \times 23))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (4 + 7)))}{9 + (5 + (8 + 23))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 \times (4 - 7)))}{9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - 47))}{9 \times ((5 \times 8) - (2 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 4) + 7))}{95 + (8 \times 23)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 + 4) \times 7))}{9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 - 4) \times 7))}{9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 - (4 - 7)))}{9^{5-8+2+3}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4 \times 7)))}{9 \times ((58 - 2) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4^7)))}{(9 + (5 + 82))^3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4 + 7)))}{9 \times (5 + ((8^2) - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (4 \times 7)))}{9 \times ((5 \times 8) - (2 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (4 + 7)))}{9 \times ((5 \times 8) - 23)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + 4 - 7))}{9 + (5 + (8 + (2 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + 47))}{9 \times (5 + (8 \times (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (64 - 7))}{9 \times (58 + (2 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (4 \times 7)))}{9 \times (5 + ((8 - 2) \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (4 + 7)))}{9 + (5 \times (8 - (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 \times (4 - 7)))}{9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 - (4 - 7))}{9 \times (5 + (82 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 + 4 - 7)}{9 + ((5 + 82) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((6 + 4) \times 7)}{9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2^3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((6 - 4) \times 7)}{9 + ((5 + (8^2)) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (6 + (4 + 7))}{9 \times ((5 \times (8 - 2)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (6 + 4 - 7)}{9 \times (5 - (8 \times (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (6 + 47)}{9 \times ((5 + (8 \times 2)) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (64 + 7)}{9^{5-8+2+3}}$$

$$:= \frac{106 - (4 \times 7)}{9 \times ((5 + 8) \times (2 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{106 - (4 + 7)}{9 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 2) + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{106 - (4 - 7)}{958 + 23}$$

$$:= \frac{106 - 47}{9 \times (58 - (2 - 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10653}{29748} := \frac{106 \times (5 - 3)}{2 \times (9 + 7 \times 4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10653}{97284} := \frac{1^{06} \times 53}{(9 + 7 \times 2 \times 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10654}{37289} := \frac{((1^{06}) + 5) \times 4}{3 + (7 + (2 + (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (5 \times 4)}{3 - (7 - (2 + (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (5 + 4)}{3 + (7 + ((2 \times 8) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (6 + 5)) + 4}{3 \times (7 \times (2 + (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times (6 + 5)) - 4}{372 + (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 \times 65) - 4}{(3^7) + (2 + (8 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + 6 + 5) \times 4}{3 \times (7 + (2 + 89))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 + 6) \times 54}{3 \times (7 \times (2 \times (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 - 6) \times (5 \times 4)}{(3 - 7) \times (2 - (8 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(106 + 5) \times 4}{3 \times (7 \times (2 + (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 - 5)^4))}{3 + (7 - (2 - (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (5^4)))}{(3^7) + ((2 \times 8) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (5 + 4)))}{37 + (2 + (8 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (5 - 4)))}{(3 \times (7 + 2)) - (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (65 - 4))}{(3 \times 72) - (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 + 5) \times 4))}{3 + (7 + (2 \times (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (5 + 4)))}{3 \times (((7 + 2) \times 8) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{3 \times (7^{2+8-9})}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (5 \times 4)))}{37 - ((2 - 8) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + 54))}{3 + ((7 + (2 \times 8)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (65 \times 4))}{(3 + 7) \times (2 + 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (5 + 4)))}{(3 \times (7 - 2)) + (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4)}{3 - (7 - (2 \times (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 - (5 - 4))}{(((3 \times 7) + 2) \times 8) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))}{3 \times (7 \times ((2 + 8) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 + (5 + 4))}{3 \times (7 \times ((2 \times 8) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (6 + 54)}{(3^7) + (2 - 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (65 \times 4)}{3 \times ((7 + 28) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{106 + (5 \times 4)}{((3 \times 7) + 28) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10658}{39274} := \frac{10 \times 6 \times 5 - 8}{(3 \times 92 - 7) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10659}{34782} := \frac{1 + 065 - 9}{3 \times 4 \times (7 + 8) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (6 - 5) \times 9}{3 \times (4 \times 7 - 8) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10659}{38247} := \frac{1 \times 06 + 5 \times 9}{3 \times (8^2 + 4 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10672}{49358} := \frac{-1 \times 06 + 7 \times 2}{4 \times (9 - 3) + 5 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 0 + 6 + 7 + 2}{4 + 9 + 3 + 58}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 06 \times 7 - 2}{(4 - 9) \times (3 - 5 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06} + 7)^2}{4 \times 9 \times (3 + 5) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + 6 + 72}{49 + 358}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10674}{85392} := \frac{((1^{06}) + 7) \times 4}{8 + (5 + (3 \times (9^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 + 6) \times 7) - 4}{853 + (9 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 - 6) \times 7) - 4}{8 + ((5 - 3) \times 92)}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 - 6)^7) \times 4}{8^{5 \times 3 - 9} \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + 7))) \times 4}{(8^{5-3}) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-06)) \times (7 + 4)}{(85 + 3) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (7 \times 4)}{(85 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (7 + 4)}{((8 + (5 - 3)) \times 9) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times 74}{8 \times (((5 + 3) \times 9) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (7 \times 4)}{8 \times (5 + ((3 + 9) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (7 + 4)}{8 + ((5 + 39) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 7))) \times 4}{8 + ((5 + 3) \times (9 - 2))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 7)))^4}{8 + (5 \times ((3 + 9) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (6 + 7)) + 4}{8 \times (53 + (9^2))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 6) + (7 \times 4)}{8 \times ((5 + 39) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 6) + (7^4)}{8 - (5 - ((3^9) + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (6 + 7)) \times 4}{((85 - 3) \times 9) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (6 - 7)) \times 4}{8 \times ((5 - 3) \times (9 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) - 4))}{(8 + 5) \times ((3 + 9) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 4)))}{8 - (5 - ((3 \times 9) + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 \times (7 - 4)))}{8 \times (5 + (3 + (9 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6^{7-4}))}{8 \times ((5^3) + 92)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (7 \times 4)))}{8 \times (53 - (9 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 4)))}{(8 + (5 + (3 \times 9))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (67 - 4))}{8 \times ((5 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (6 - 74))}{8^{5+3-9+2}} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 674)}{8 + 5392} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 \times 4)))}{8 \times ((5 - (3 - 9)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 4)))}{8 - (5 - (39 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) + 4))}{8 \times (5 + (39 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 4))}{8 \times (5 + (3 \times (9 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 4)))}{8 - (5 - (3 \times (9 - 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 + 4)))}{((85 \times 3) + 9) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 - 4)))}{8 + ((5^3) + (9 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 \times 4)))}{8 \times ((5 + (3 + 9)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 4)))}{8 \times (5 - ((3 - 9) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 4)))}{8 \times (5 - (3 - (9 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (67 \times 4))}{8 \times (((5^3) + 9) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (67 + 4))}{8 \times (53 + (9 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^4)}{8 + ((5 \times 3) - (9 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (7 \times 4)))}{(8 \times 5) + ((3 + 9)^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 4)))}{8 - (5 \times (3 - (9 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - 74))}{(8 - (5 - 3)) \times 92} \\ &:= \frac{10 - ((6 - 7) \times 4)}{8 \times ((5 - 3) \times (9 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{10 - (6 - (7 + 4))}{8 \times (5 + (3 + (9 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{10 - (6 - (7 - 4))}{((8 - (5 - 3)) \times 9) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (6 - (7 - 4))}{8 \times (5 + ((3 \times 9) - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (6 + 74)}{(8 + ((5 + 3) \times 9))^2} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((6 \times 7) - 4)}{8 \times (((5 \times 3) + 9) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((6 + 7) \times 4)}{8 \times ((5 \times (3 + 9)) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (6 - (7 - 4))}{8 \times (5 - (3 - (9 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (6 + (7 \times 4))}{8 \times ((5^3) - (9^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (67 - 4)}{8 + (((5 \times 3) + 9)^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10675}{39284} := \frac{(1 + 06) \times 75}{3 \times (9^2 \times 8 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times 6 - 7 \times 5}{(39 - 2 \times 8) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{06} \times 75}{3 \times ((9 + 2) \times 8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(10 - 6) \times 75}{3 \times 92 \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10679}{85432} := \frac{((1^{06}) + 7) \times 9}{(8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 3))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^{06}) + 7)^9}{(8^5 \times (4 - 3))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 - 6) \times 7) + 9}{8 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((10 - 6)^7) \times 9}{(8^5) \times (4 + 32)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (-06)) \times (7 + 9)}{(8 + (5 \times 4)) \times 32}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) - (7 - 9)}{8 \times (5 + (4 - (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (7 \times 9)}{8 \times (54 + (3^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times (7 + 9)}{8 + (5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) \times 79}{8 + ((5^4) - (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (7 \times 9)}{8^{5+4-3 \times 2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{06}) + (7 + 9)}{(8 + (5 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 7))) \times 9}{8 \times (5 + (4 + (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 7)))^9}{8^{5+4-3-2}}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(10 \times 6) - (7 - 9)}{8 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2)} \\
 := \frac{(10 + (6 - 7)) \times 9}{8 + (5 \times (4 \times 32))} \\
 := \frac{(10 + (6 - 7))^9}{8 \times ((5 + 4)^{3^2})} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) + 9))}{8 \times ((5 \times 4) + 32)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) - 9))}{8 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (7 \times 9)))}{8 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (7 + 9)))}{(8 + 54) \times 3 - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (5 \times (4 - 3)^2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (6 + 79))}{8 \times (54 + 32)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - (67 - 9))}{8 \times (54 + 3 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 \times (6 - 79))}{8 - (5 + (4 - (3^2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (0 - 679)}{8 + 5432} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{8 \times (5 - (4 - (3^2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{8 \times ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 9))}{8 \times (5 - (4 - 32))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 9)))}{8^{5-4+3-2}} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 + 9)))}{8 \times ((5 + 43) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 9)))}{8 \times (54 - 32)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 9)))}{8 \times (5 + (4 - (3 + 2)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^9)}{8 - (5 - (4 + (3^2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (7 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{8 \times ((5 \times 4) - (3^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{8 + ((5 + 43) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{10 - ((6 - 7) \times 9)}{8 \times (5 + ((4 + 3) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 - (7 \times 9))}{8 \times (5 + ((4^3) - 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 - (7 + 9))}{8 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{10 - (6 + (7 - 9))}{8 \times (5 - (4 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{10 \times ((6 \times 7) - 9)}{8 \times (5 \times (4^3 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 + (6 \times (7 + 9))}{854 - (3 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{10 + (6 + (7 + 9))}{8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 32)} \\
 := \frac{10 + (6 + (7 - 9))}{8 \times (5 + (4 + 3 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{10 + (67 - 9)}{(8 + (5 + 4)) \times 32} \\
 := \frac{106 - 79}{((8 \times 5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1067 - 9}{(85 + (4 + 3))^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{10 \times 6 \times (9 + 2)}{(3 + 7) \times 58 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{45738} := \frac{1 + 06 + 9 + 2}{4 + 5 \times 7 + 38} \\
 := \frac{1 + 069 + 2}{4 + (5 \times 7 + 3) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 06 \times 9 \times 2}{457 - 3 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{47385} := \frac{(10 - 6) \times (9 + 2)}{(4 - 7 \times (3 - 8)) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{53784} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 6 \times (9 + 2)}{(5 + 37) \times 8 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{57348} := \frac{(1 + 06) \times (9 + 2)}{5 \times 73 + 48} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{75438} := \frac{1 + 06 + 9 + 2}{(7 \times (5 + 4 \times 3)) + 8} \\
 := \frac{1 + 069 + 2}{(7 + 5) \times 43 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{83754} := \frac{1 - 06 + 9 + 2}{8 - 3 \times (7 - 5 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{-1 \times 06 + 9 \times 2}{(8 + 3 + 7) \times 5 + 4} \\
 := \frac{1 - 0 + 6 + 9 + 2}{(8 + 3 \times 7) \times 5 - 4} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 06 + 9 \times 2}{8 \times 3 \times 7 + 5 \times 4} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 06 \times 9 \times 2}{837 + 5 + 4}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{35478} := \frac{10 - 6 + 9 \times 2}{3 \times (5 \times 4 + 7) - 8} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 06 \times (9 + 2)}{3 + (5 \times 4 + 7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{35748} := \frac{1 + 06 + 92}{3^5 + (7 + 4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{37584} := \frac{1 \times 06 \times (9 + 2)}{((3 + 7) \times 5 + 8) \times 4}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10695}{34782} := \frac{1 \times 069 \times 5}{3 \times (47 \times 8 - 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10695}{74382} := \frac{10 \times (6 + 9) + 5}{7 \times (4 \times 38 + 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10725}{36894} := \frac{-1 \times 07 + 2^5}{3 \times 6 + (8 + 9) \times 4} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 07 \times 2) \times 5}{(3 - 6) \times (8 - 94)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{10 \times (7 - 2 + 5)}{(3 - 6 + 89) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 07) \times 25}{3 + 689 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10725}{39468} & := \frac{-1 \times 07 + 2^5}{3 + 9 + (4 + 6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 07 \times 2) \times 5}{3 \times (94 + 6 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + 7) \times 25}{(3 \times 9 - 4) \times 68} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10726}{35984} & := \frac{1 + (07 - 2) \times 6}{(35 - 9) \times (8 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times 7 - 2 - 6}{3 + 5 \times (9 + 8 \times 4)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10728}{46935} & := \frac{((1 - (-07))^2) - 8}{(4 - (6 - 9)) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 \times 2))) \times 8}{((4 \times 6) - 9) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07)) \times 28}{(4 + 6) \times (93 + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - 72)) \times 8}{(4 + 69) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{(1^{07}) \times (2 \times 8)}{4 + (6 \times (9 - (3 - 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(10^{7+2}) \times 8}{((4 + 6)^9) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + (7 + 2)) \times 8}{(4 + (6 + 9)) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + (2 \times 8)))}{(4 - (6 - 9)) \times (3 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + (2^8)))}{((4 \times 6) + 9) \times 35} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 72) + 8)}{4 + ((6 \times (9 - 3)) - 5)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7^2) \times 8))}{((4 - (6 - 9))^3) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 + 2) \times 8))}{((4 \times (6 + 9)) + 3) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 \times 8))}{(4 + 6) \times (9 + (3^5))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 + 8))}{(4 + (69 - 3)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 - 8))}{46 - (9 - (3^5))} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times ((7 + 2) \times 8)}{(4 + 6) \times (9 \times 35)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10735}{26894} & := \frac{10 \times (7 + 3) - 5}{2 + (68 - 9) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10735}{49268} & := \frac{10 \times (7 + 3) - 5}{4 \times 92 + 68} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10736}{25498} & := \frac{10 + (7 - (3 + 6))}{2 - ((5 \times (4 - 9)) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((07 + (3 + 6)))}{2 - (5 - (49 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (((07 - 3) \times 6))}{2 + (54 + (9 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times ((7 + 3) \times 6)}{25 \times (49 + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (3 + 6)))}{((2^5) - (4 + 9)) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (0 - (73 + 6))}{2 + ((5 \times (4 \times 9)) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + (7 + 3)) \times 6}{2 - (5 - (4 \times (9 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07)) \times (3 \times 6)}{2 + (5 \times (4 \times (9 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6}{(2^{5+4}) + (9 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6)}{2 \times (5 \times (49 + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 + 2) \times 8))}{((4 \times (6 + 9)) + 3) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 - 2) \times 8))}{(4 \times ((6 + 9) \times 3)) - 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 \times 8))}{(4 + 6) \times (9 + (3^5))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 + 8))}{(4 + (69 - 3)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (0 + (72 - 8))}{46 - (9 - (3^5))} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times ((7 + 2) \times 8)}{(4 + 6) \times (9 \times 35)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10738}{46592} & := \frac{(10 + 7) \times 3 + 8}{4^{6+5-9+2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10738}{69524} & := \frac{(10 + 7) \times 3 + 8}{6 \times 9 \times (5 + 2) + 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10742}{85936} & := \frac{((1^{07}) + 4)^2}{8 + ((5 + (9 \times 3)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 - 4))) \times 2}{8 + (59 + (3 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07)) \times (4 + 2)}{(8 + (59 - 3)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07)) \times 42}{8 \times ((59 - 3) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07))^{4 \times 2}}{8^{5 \times 9 - 36}} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (-07))^{4-2}}{8 + ((5 + 9) \times 36)} \\
 & := \frac{(1^{07}) + (4^2)}{8 \times (5 + (9 - (3 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times (7 - 4)) + 2}{8 \times (5 - (9 - 36))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times 7) - (4 \times 2)}{8 \times (59 - (3 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times 7) - (4^2)}{8 \times ((5 \times (9 + 3)) - 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times 7) - (4 - 2)}{8 \times (59 + (3 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + 7) \times (4 + 2)}{8 \times ((5 + (9 + 3)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + 7)^{4+2}}{8 \times ((5 + (9 + 3))^6)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 - 7) \times (4 + 2)}{(8 + (5 - 9)) \times 36} \\
 & := \frac{(10 - 7) \times 42}{8 \times ((5 + 9) \times (3 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - ((0 \times 74) - 2)}{8 - (5 - ((9 \times 3) - 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((7 \times 4) - 2))}{(8 - (5 - 9)) \times (3 \times 6)} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (7 - (4^2)))}{8 - ((5 - 9) \times (3 \times 6))} && \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((7 + 4)^2))}{(8 \times 5) + 936} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (7 - 42))}{8 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) + 6)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10759}{32648} := \frac{1 - 07 \times (5 - 9)}{(3 - 2 + 6 + 4) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((7 - 4) \times 2))}{8 + (((5 + 9) \times 3) + 6)} &:= \frac{10 - ((7 - 4) \times 2)}{8 + ((5 \times (9 - 3)) - 6)} && := \frac{10 + (7 - 5)^9}{3 \times (2 + 64) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 - (4 - 2)))}{8 - (5 - (9 + 36))} &:= \frac{10 - (7 - (4^2))}{8 - ((5 - 9) \times 36)} && \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (4 + 2)))}{8 + ((59 - 3) \times 6)} &:= \frac{10 \times ((7 - 4) \times 2)}{8 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 6)))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{23598} := \frac{(1 \times 07 + 6) \times 4}{2 \times (3 + 5) + 98} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (4 - 2)))}{(8 - ((5 - 9) \times 3)) \times 6} &:= \frac{10 \times (7 + (4 - 2))}{8 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 + 6)))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{25389} := \frac{10 \times (7 \times 6 + 4)}{2 \times 538 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + (4^2)))}{8 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) - 6)} &:= \frac{10 + (7 - (4 + 2))}{8 \times (5 + (9 + (3 - 6)))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{28359} := \frac{1 \times 0 + (7 + 6) \times 4}{2 \times 8 \times (3 + 5) + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + 42))}{8 \times (5 + (9 + 36))} &:= \frac{10 + (7 \times (4 \times 2))}{8 \times ((5 + (9 - 3)) \times 6)} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{38259} := \frac{(10 + 7 + 6) \times 4}{3 \times (8^2 + 5 \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (74 + 2))}{8 \times (5 + ((9 + 3) \times 6))} &:= \frac{10 + (74 + 2)}{8 \times (5 + (9 \times (3 + 6)))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{38295} := \frac{1 \times 0 + (7 + 6) \times 4}{3 - 8 + 2 \times 95} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (7 - 42))}{8 - (5 \times (9 - (3 + 6)))} &:= \frac{107 - (4 \times 2)}{(8 + (5 + 9)) \times 36} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{85293} := \frac{(10 + 7 + 6) \times 4}{(8 - 5 - 2) \times 9^3} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 742)}{8 \times (5 + (9 + (3^6)))} &:= \frac{107 - (4 + 2)}{85 + ((9^3) - 6)} && := \frac{10 \times (7 \times 6 + 4)}{(8 - 5 + 2) \times 9^3} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (7 - (4^2)))}{(8 + (5 - 9)) \times (3 \times 6)} &:= \frac{107 - (4 - 2)}{8 \times (5 \times ((9 \times 3) - 6))} && \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 \times 4) + 2))}{8 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 6)))} &:= \frac{107 \times (4 + 2)}{859 - 3) \times 6} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10783}{62594} := \frac{1 + 078 + 3}{(6 + 2) \times 59 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 \times 4) - 2))}{8 \times (5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6))} && \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 - (4 - 2)))}{8 + (5 - (9 - 36))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10745}{69382} := \frac{(10 - 7 + 4) \times 5}{6 \times 9 \times 3 + 8^2} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10792}{38456} := \frac{10 + 7 \times 9 - 2}{3 \times 84 - 5 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 \times 2)))}{8 \times (59 + (3 - 6))} && \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 + 2)))}{8 \times ((5 \times 9) + (3 - 6))} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10752}{39648} := \frac{(10 - 7 + 5) \times 2}{3 + (9 - 6 + 4) \times 8} && \blacktriangleright \frac{10794}{86352} := \frac{((10 - 7) \times 9) + 4}{(86 \times 3) - (5 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 - 2)))}{8 \times (5 - (9 - (3 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 + 07) \times 5 \times 2}{39 + (6 - 4)^8} && := \frac{((10 - 7) \times 9) - 4}{8 \times (6 + ((3 \times 5) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 + (4^2)))}{8 \times (5 + (9 + (3 + 6)))} &:= \frac{10 \times 7 \times 5 + 2}{3 - 9 + 6^4 + 8} && := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))^4}{8^{6-3} \times (5-2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (74 - 2))}{(8 - (5 - 93)) \times 6} &:= \frac{(10 - 7 + 5)^2}{(3 + 9 \times 6) \times 4 + 8} && := \frac{(1 - (-07))^{9-4}}{8^{6-3+5-2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1^{07}) + (9 + 4)}{(8 + (6 \times (3 + 5))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - 9)))^4}{8 \times (6 + (3 \times (5^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (7 + 9)) + 4}{8 \times ((6^3) - 52)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (7 + 9)) - 4}{8 \times ((6 - 3) \times 52)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 7) - (9 \times 4)}{8 \times (6 + (3 + (5^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (7 - 9)) \times 4}{(8 + (6 - (3 - 5)))^2} \\ &:= \frac{(10 - 7) \times (9 - 4)}{8 \times (6 + (3 \times (5 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(107 - 9) \times 4}{(8 + (6 \times (3 + 5)))^2} \\ &:= \frac{1 - ((0 \times 79) - 4)}{(8 - (6 \times (3 - 5))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((7 \times 9) - 4))}{8 \times (6 \times (3 + (5 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 - (9 - 4)))}{8 - (6 + (3 - (5^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (9 + 4)))}{8 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 5)) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (6 \times (3 + (5 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 4)))}{8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (6 - (3 - (5 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 + 94))}{8 \times (6 \times ((3 \times 5) + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (79 \times 4))}{8 \times ((63 \times 5) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (79 + 4))}{(8 + (6^3)) \times (5 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (79 - 4))}{8 \times (6 + (35 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (7 - 94))}{8 - (6 \times (3 - (5 - 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 794)}{8 + 6352} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 - (7 - 9))^4)}{8 \times (6 + (3 + (5 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 79) + 4)}{8 - (6 \times (3 - (5 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{8^{6+3-5-2}} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 4)))}{8 \times (6 - (3 - (5 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 4))}{8 \times ((6 - (3 - 5))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 - (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (6 + (3 - (5 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 4)))}{8 \times (6 + (35 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (6 + (3 + (5 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (79 - 4))}{8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((0 - (7 - 9))^4)}{8 \times (((6 - 3) \times 5) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{8 - (6 - (35 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 4)))}{8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 4)))}{86 - (3 \times (5 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (7 - 94))}{8 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 5)) - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 - ((7 - 9) \times 4)}{(8 + (6 + (3 - 5)))^2} \\ &:= \frac{10 - (7 - (9 \times 4))}{8 \times (6 + (35 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times ((7 + 9) \times 4)}{(8^{6-3}) \times (5 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (7 + (9 + 4))}{(((8 - 6)^3) \times 5)^2} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (7 + (9 \times 4))}{8 \times (63 - (5 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{10 + (7 + (9 - 4))}{8 + (6 \times (3 + (5^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (7 + 94)}{863 + (5^2)} \\ &:= \frac{107 + (9 - 4)}{(8 + 6) \times ((3 + 5)^2)} \\ & \text{---} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10829}{64753} := \frac{(1 - 08) \times (2 - 9)}{6 \times 4 \times 7 + 5^3} \\ & \text{---} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{42957} := \frac{-1 \times 08 + 36}{(4 + 2) \times 9 + 57} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{45279} := \frac{-1 \times 08 + 36}{(4 - 5 + 2 \times 7) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (8 - 3)) + 6}{(4 - (5 - 27)) \times 9} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{45927} := \frac{10 + 8^3 - 6}{(4 + 5) \times 9 \times 27} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{97524} := \frac{((1 - (-08)) \times 3) + 6}{9 + ((7 + 5) \times 24)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (-08)) \times 3) - 6}{9 \times (7 \times (5 + (2 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 + 8) \times 3) + 6}{9 + (7 + 524)} \\ &:= \frac{((10 - 8)^3) \times 6}{9 \times ((7 - 5) \times 24)} \\ &:= \frac{((10 - 8)^3) + 6}{9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 + 3)))^6}{9 \times ((7 + 5)^{2+4})} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 - 3))) \times 6}{9 \times (7 + (5 + 24))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (-08)) \times (3 + 6)}{9 \times (75 + (2 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{08}) - (3 - 6)}{9 \times (7 - (5 + (2 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{08}) \times (3^6)}{9^{7-5-2+4}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1^{08}) \times (3+6)}{9 - ((7 - (5^2)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 \times (3 \times 6)))}{(9 + (7 - (5 \times 2)))^4} &:= \frac{10 + (8 - 4) \times 5}{6 \times (7 + 2 \times (3 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{08}) + 36}{9 \times (7 + (5 \times (2 + 4)))} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 \times (3 + 6)))}{(9^{7-5}) \times (2 \times 4)} &:= \frac{1 + 084 + 5}{(6 + 7 \times 2^3) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (8 - 3)) + 6}{9 \times ((7 + (5 + 2)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 \times 36))}{9 \times ((7 + 5) \times 24)} &:= \frac{1 \times 0 \times 84 + 5}{6 - 7 + 23 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times 8) - (3 - 6)}{9 \times (75 + (2 \times 4))} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{9 \times (7 - (5 - 24))} &:= \frac{10 + 845}{(6 \times 7)^2 \times 3 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times 8) + (3 \times 6)}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 2) + 4))} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 + 6)))}{9 \times (7 - (5 \times (2 - 4)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10845}{93267} := \frac{1 + 08 - 4 + 5}{9 + (3 + 2 + 6) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((8 \times 3) - 6))}{9 \times (7 + ((5 - 2) \times 4))} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 - 6)))}{9 + (7 + (5 + 24))} &:= \frac{10 \times (8 - 4) - 5}{9 \times 32 + 6 + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((8 + 3) \times 6))}{9 \times (75 - (2 \times 4))} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 + 36))}{((9 + 7) \times (5^2)) - 4} &:= \frac{(10 - 8) \times 4 \times 5}{9 + (3 + 2) \times 67} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 - (3 - 6)))}{(9 - (7 - (5^2))) \times 4} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (83 - 6))}{9 \times (7 \times (5 + (2 + 4)))} &:= \frac{1^{08} \times 45}{9 \times (3 - 2 + 6 \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 \times (3 + 6)))}{9 \times (75 + (2 - 4))} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (8 - (3 + 6)))}{((9 - (7 - 5)) \times 2) + 4} & \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (2 \times 4))} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (8 \times (3 - 6)))}{9 \times ((7 \times (5 - 2)) + 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{62937} := \frac{10 \times (8 + 5) + 4}{(6 \times 2 \times 9 + 3) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (3 + 6)))}{9 \times (7 - (5 - (2^4)))} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (8 - 36))}{9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (2 + 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{72963} := \frac{1 + 08 + 5 + 4}{7 + 2 \times (9 \times 6 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (3 - 6)))}{9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 + 4)))} &:= \frac{10 - (8 - (3 \times 6))}{9 \times (7 + (5 + (2 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{108 \times (5 - 4)}{729 - 6 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + 36))}{9 \times ((7 \times (5 + 2)) - 4)} &:= \frac{10 + ((8 - 3) \times 6)}{9 \times ((7 + (5 - 2)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{1 \times 08 \times 5 - 4}{7 \times (29 + 6) - 3} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (8 - 36))}{9 - (7 - (5 - (2 - 4)))} &:= \frac{10 + (8 \times (3 \times 6))}{9 \times ((75 \times 2) + 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{73629} := \frac{108 \times 5 - 4}{7 + 3629} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 836)}{9 + 7524} &:= \frac{10 + (8 + 36)}{(9^{7-5}) \times (2 + 4)} & \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 8) - (3 - 6))}{9 + (7 - (5 - (2^4)))} &:= \frac{10 + (83 + 6)}{9 \times (75 + 24)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10857}{49632} := \frac{(1 + (-08)) \times (5 - 7)}{4^{9-6} \times (3-2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (8 - (3 \times 6)))}{9 \times (7 + (5 + (2 - 4)))} &:= \frac{10 + (83 - 6)}{9 \times (7 + (5 \times (2^4)))} &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (5 + 7)))}{4 \times (9 + (6 + (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (8 \times (3 - 6)))}{(9 - (7 - 52)) \times 4} &:= \frac{108 - (3 - 6)}{975 + 24} &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (8 - (5 \times 7)))}{(((4 \times 9) + 6) \times 3) + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (8 - 36))}{9 \times (7 + (5 + (2^4)))} \& := \frac{1 \times (0 + ((8 + 3) \times 6))}{9 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4)} &:= \frac{((1^{08}) + 5) \times 7}{4 \times ((9 \times 6) - (3 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (8 - (3 - 6)))}{9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 24)} \blacktriangleright \frac{10845}{67239} := \frac{1 - 0 + 8 - 4 + 5}{6 + 7 \times (2 - 3 + 9)} &:= \frac{(10 - 8) \times (5 \times 7)}{(4^{9-6}) \times (3 + 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(108^5) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times 6))^{3+2}}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 08 + 9)^6}{5 + 2 + 43 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{((10 + 9) \times 3) + 2}{8 \times (7 - (4 - 56))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((08 + 5) \times 7))}{(4 \times 96) + 32}$	$:= \frac{1 + 089 + 6}{5^2 + 437}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 3)))^2}{8 \times (((7 + 4) \times 5) - 6)}$
$:= \frac{10 \times ((8 - 5) \times 7)}{((4 \times 9) - 6) \times 32}$	$:= \frac{10 + (8 + 9) \times 6}{(5 + 24 \times 3) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 09) \times (3^2)}{8 \times ((7 - 4) \times (5 \times 6))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (5 - 7)))}{4 \times (9 - (6 - (3 + 2)))}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(1 + 09)^{3 \times 2}}{(8^{7-4}) \times (5^6)}$
$:= \frac{(10 + (8 \times 5)) \times 7}{(49 - (6 + 3))^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{45678} := \frac{1 + (09 - 2) \times 3}{4 \times 5 - 6 + 78}$	$:= \frac{(1^{09}) + (3 \times 2)}{8 + ((7 - (4 - 5)) \times 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (8 - 57))}{(4 + (9 - 6)) \times 32}$	$:= \frac{1 + 09 + 23}{4 + 56 + 78}$	$:= \frac{(1^{09}) + 3 + 2}{87 - (45 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{((10 + 8)^5) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times (6^3)))^2}$	$:= \frac{1 + 09 \times 2 \times 3}{(4 + 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8}$	$:= \frac{(1^{09}) + 32}{8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 \times 6)))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10857}{63294} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 \times 5 + 7}{6 \times (3 + 2) \times 9 + 4}$	$:= \frac{109 + 23}{(4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - 3)) - 2}{8 \times (7 + (45 + 6))}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{10 + 9^2 \times 3}{4^5 + 6 \times 7 - 8}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times 9) - (3 \times 2)}{8 \times ((7 \times 4) + 56)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{47925} := \frac{1 \times 08 + 6 + 3}{(4 - 7 + 9 \times 2) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{10 + 9^2 - 3}{(45 - 6 + 7) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times 9) - (3 + 2)}{8 \times (74 + (5 + 6))}$
$:= \frac{10 + 8 \times (6 - 3)}{(4 - 7 + 9) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{48657} := \frac{1 + 09 - 2 + 3}{(4 - 8 + 6 + 5) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{(10 \times 9) + (3^2)}{(87 + 45) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 08 \times 6 + 3}{(4 - 79) \times (2 - 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (09 - 2) \times 3}{(4 + (8 - 6) \times 5) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{(10 + (9 + 3)) \times 2}{8 \times (74 - (5 \times 6))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{49572} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 63}{4 \times (95 - 7 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 + 09 + 23}{4 + 86 + 57}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 - 3) \times 2))}{8 \times (7 - ((4 - 5) \times 6))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{49725} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 63}{(4 + 9 \times 7 - 2) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{10 + 92 - 3}{4 + 86 \times 5 + 7}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 - (3 + 2)))}{8 - (7 - (45 - 6))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{59427} := \frac{1 \times 08 + 6 + 3}{5 + 9^{4-2} + 7}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (9 + 2) \times 3}{(48 - 6) \times 5 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (3 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (45 - 6))}$
$:= \frac{10 + 8 \times (6 - 3)}{5 + 94 \times 2 - 7}$	$:= \frac{10 + 9^2 - 3}{4 \times (86 + 5 + 7)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (3 - 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 - 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(108 - 6) \times 3}{(5 + 9 \times 4)^2 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{75468} := \frac{1 + 09 - 2 + 3}{7 + 5 + 4 + 68}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + 3 + 2))}{(8 - 7) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{94572} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 6 + 3}{(9 \times (4 + 5) - 7) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (2 \times 3)))}{7 + (5 + (46 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (3 - 2)))}{8 \times (7 - (4 \times (5 - 6)))}$
<hr/>	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (93 + 2))}{8 \times ((7 + (4 + 5)) \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10896}{52437} := \frac{1^{08} + 9 + 6}{5 + 2 \times (43 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10932}{87456} := \frac{((1 + 09) \times 3) - 2}{(8 - 7) \times (4 \times 56)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (9 - 32))}{8 - (7 + (4 - (5 + 6)))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 932)}{8 + 7456} & & := \frac{10 + ((9 \times 3) - 2)}{8 \times (7 \times (4 - (5 - 6)))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{27648} := \frac{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}{2^7 \times 6 \times (4 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 93) + 2)}{8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 - 6)))} & & := \frac{10 + ((9 - 3) \times 2)}{8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 + 6)))} & & := \frac{10 \times (9 - 3)^5}{(2 + 7 - 6) \times 4^8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 3) + 2))}{8 \times ((7 \times 4) - (5 - 6))} & & := \frac{10 + (9 \times (3 \times 2))}{8^{7+4 \times (5-6)}} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}{27 \times 86 \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9^3) \times 2))}{8 \times (((7 - 4)^5) \times 6)} & & := \frac{10 + (9 + 32)}{8 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 + 6)))} & & := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{(2 + 78 + 6) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 - 3) \times 2))}{8 \times (7 + (4 - (5 - 6)))} & & := \frac{10 + (93 + 2)}{8 \times (7 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{28674} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{2 \times (8 \times 6 + 7 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 - 3)^2))}{8 \times ((7 + (4 - 5)) \times 6)} & & := \frac{109 - (3 + 2)}{8 \times (74 + (5 \times 6))} & & := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{((2 + 8 \times 6) \times 7) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 \times 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 - 6)))} & & := \frac{109 - 32}{(8 + (7 - 4)) \times 56} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{42768} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{4 \times 27 + 68} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 - (4 + (5 - 6)))} & & & & := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{4 \times (2^7 + 6) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 - 2)))}{8^{7-4+5-6}} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10934}{78526} := \frac{1 + 09 - 3 + 4}{7 + 8 \times (5 - 2 + 6)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{47628} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{4 \times 7 \times 6 + 28} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3^2)))}{(8 \times 74) + 56} & & := \frac{109 + 34}{7 + 85 \times 2 \times 6} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{48276} := \frac{10 + 935}{4^{8-2} + 76} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 + 2)))}{(8 + (7 + 45)) \times 6} & & := \frac{10 + 9 \times 3 - 4}{7 \times (8 + 5^2) + 6} & & := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{4 - 8 \times (2 - 76)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9^3))}{8 \times ((7 + (4 \times 5))^6)} & & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{48672} := \frac{10 \times (9 + 3)^5}{4^8 \times (6 + 7)^2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 - 2)))}{8 \times (((7 - 4) \times 5) - 6)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{24786} := \frac{1^{09} \times 3 \times 5}{(2 - 4 + 7) \times 8 - 6} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{78246} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{7 \times ((8 + 2) \times 4 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (3^2)))}{(8 + (7 + (4 + 5))) \times 6} & & := \frac{(1 \times 09 - 3) \times 5}{2 - 4 + (7 + 8) \times 6} & & := \frac{10 \times 9 \times (3 + 5)}{7 \times 8 \times 2 \times 46} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + 3 + 2))}{8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 + 6)))} & & := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{(2^4 - 7 + 8) \times 6} & & := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 35}{7 \times (82 \times 4 - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + 32))}{8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 \times 6)))} & & := \frac{10 \times 9 - 3 \times 5}{2 \times (4 + 78) + 6} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 9^3 \times 5}{((8 - 4) \times (6 \times 7))^2} \\
 &:= \frac{10 \times (9 - (3 + 2))}{8 + ((7 + 45) \times 6)} & & := \frac{10 \times 9 + 3 \times 5}{(24 - 7) \times (8 + 6)} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{10 \times (9 \times (3^2))}{((8 \times 7) + (4^5)) \times 6} & & := \frac{10 \times (9 - 3) \times 5}{2 \times (4 + 7 \times 8 \times 6)} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 3)^2)}{8 \times (745 - 6)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{24867} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 9 \times 3 \times 5}{(2 + 48) \times 6 + 7} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 3) + 2)}{8 \times ((7 \times 4) + (5 + 6))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{26487} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{26 - 4 + 87} & & & & \\
 & & & & & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{10942}{87536} := \frac{((1 + 09) \times 4) + 2}{8 \times (((7 + 5) \times 3) + 6)} \\
 & & & & & & & := \frac{((10 + 9) \times 4) + 2}{8 \times (75 - (3 - 6))} \\
 & & & & & & & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times 4))) \times 2}{(8 \times 7) + 536}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + 4))) \times 2}{8 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) + 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (4 - 2)))}{8 \times (7 + ((5 - 3) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (4^2)))}{8 + (((7 \times 5) - 3) \times 6)}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 4)))^2}{8 \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (4^2)))}{8 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (5 - (3 - 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 09) \times (4 + 2)}{(8 + (75 - 3)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (4 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 - 2)))}{8 \times (7 - (5 - (3 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 09) \times (4 - 2)}{8 \times (7 - (5 - (3 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (4 - 2)))}{(8 - (7 - (5 \times 3))) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + 42))}{(8 + (7 + 53)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 09)^{4-2}}{8 + ((7 + (5^3)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + 42))}{8 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - (4^2)))}{8 + (7 \times (5 - (3 - 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{09}) \times (4 + 2)}{8 - (7 - (53 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (94 + 2))}{8 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (9 - (4 + 2))}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 \times 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{09}) + (4 \times 2)}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (94 - 2))}{8 \times (75 + (3 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 4) - 2)}{8 \times ((7 \times 5) + (3 + 6))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{09}) + 42}{8 \times ((7^5 - 3) - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (9 - 42))}{8 - (((7 - 5) \times 3) - 6)}$	$:= \frac{10 + (9 - (4 + 2))}{(8 \times 7) + ((5 + 3) \times 6)}$
$:= \frac{(10 \times (9 + 4)) + 2}{8 \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (0 - 942)}{8 + 7536}$	$:= \frac{10 + (9 \times (4 + 2))}{8^{7+5-3-6}}$
$:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - 4)) - 2}{8 \times (7 + (5 + 36))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (9 - (4^2)))}{8 + (7 + (5 + 36))}$	$:= \frac{10 + (9 + (4 - 2))}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(10 \times 9) - (4 + 2)}{8 \times (7 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (9 - 42))}{(8 + ((7 + 5) \times 3)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{109 \times (4 + 2)}{(875 - 3) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(10 \times 9) + (4 \times 2)}{8 \times (7 \times (5 + (3 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) + 2))}{8 \times (7 - (5 - 36))}$	$:= \frac{109 + (4 - 2)}{8 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) + 6)}$
$:= \frac{(10^9)^{4-2}}{(8^7) \times ((5^3)^6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 - 4) \times 2))}{8 + (75 + (3 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{109 - 42}{(8 - 7) \times 536}$
$:= \frac{(10 + (9 + 4)) \times 2}{8 + ((7 + 53) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 - (4 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (5 - (3 + 6)))}$	
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 \times 4)^2))}{8 + (((7 + 5)^3) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 \times 2)))}{8 \times (75 + (3 - 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10947}{68352} := \frac{10 \times (9 + 4) - 7}{6 \times 8 \times (3 + 5) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 \times 4) + 2))}{8 \times (75 - 36)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4^2)))}{(8^{7-5}) \times (3 \times 6)}$	
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 + 4) \times 2))}{(8 - (7 - 5)) \times 36}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 + 2)))}{8 \times (7 + (53 - 6))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10953}{87624} := \frac{((1 + 09) \times 5) + 3}{((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 2) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 - (4 \times 2)))}{8 - (7 + (5 \times (3 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 - 2)))}{8 \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{((1 + 09) \times 5) - 3}{8 \times (7 + ((6^2) + 4))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 - (4 + 2)))}{8 - (7 + (5 - 36))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9^{4+2}))}{8 \times ((7 + (5 - 3))^6)}$	$:= \frac{((10 \times 9) - 5) \times 3}{8 \times (7 + (62 \times 4))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (4 + 2)))}{8 \times ((7^5 - 3) + 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 \times 2)))}{8 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 5))) \times 3}{8 \times (7 + (6 - (2 - 4)))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
& := \frac{(1+09) \times (5 \times 3)}{(8+(7 \times 6)) \times 24} & := \frac{1-(0-(9 \times (5-3)))}{8 \times (7-(6 \times (2-4)))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9+53))}{((8 \times 7)+6) \times (2 \times 4)} \\
& := \frac{(1+09) \times (5^3)}{(8+((7-6) \times 2))^4} & := \frac{1-(0-(9^{5-3}))}{8 \times (76+(2+4))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(95+3))}{8 \times (7 \times (6+(2 \times 4)))} \\
& := \frac{(1+09) \times (5+3)}{8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 2))-4)} & := \frac{1-(0-(9+(5 \times 3)))}{8 \times (7-(6-24))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(95-3))}{8 \times (76+(2^4))} \\
& := \frac{(1+09) \times (5-3)}{8-(76 \times (2-4))} & := \frac{1-(0-(9+(5-3)))}{8 \times ((7-(6-2)) \times 4)} & := \frac{1+(0-(9-53))}{(8 \times (7 \times 6))+24} \\
& := \frac{(1+09)^{5-3}}{8 \times (76+24)} & := \frac{1-(0-(9+53))}{(8+76) \times (2+4)} & := \frac{10 \times ((9 \times 5)+3)}{(8+7) \times ((6-2)^4)} \\
& := \frac{(1^{09})+(5 \times 3)}{8 \times ((7-6) \times (2^4))} & := \frac{1-(0-(95-3))}{(87+6) \times (2 \times 4)} & := \frac{10 \times (9-(5-3))}{8 \times (76-(2+4))} \\
& := \frac{(1^{09})+(5+3)}{8 \times (7-(6-(2 \times 4)))} & := \frac{1-(0 \times (9-53))}{8-(7 \times (6-(2+4)))} & := \frac{10 \times (9 \times (5-3))}{(8+7) \times (6 \times (2^4))} \\
& := \frac{(10 \times (9-5))-3}{8 \times (7+(6+24))} & := \frac{1-(0-953)}{8+7624} & := \frac{10^{9-5-3}}{(8 \times (7+6))-24} \\
& := \frac{(10 \times 9)-(5 \times 3)}{(8 \times 76)-(2 \times 4)} & := \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 95)+3)}{8 \times (7-(6+(2-4)))} & := \frac{10+((9 \times 5)+3)}{8+(76 \times (2+4))} \\
& := \frac{(10 \times 9)-(5-3)}{8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 2))+4)} & := \frac{1 \times (0-(9-(5 \times 3)))}{8 \times ((7-6) \times (2+4))} & := \frac{10+((9+5) \times 3)}{8 \times ((7 \times (6+2))-4)} \\
& := \frac{(10+(9 \times 5)) \times 3}{8 \times (((7+6)^2)-4)} & := \frac{1 \times (0-(9-53))}{8 \times ((7+(6-2)) \times 4)} & := \frac{10+((9-5) \times 3)}{8 \times (((7+6) \times 2)-4)} \\
& := \frac{(10+9) \times (5-3)}{8+((76-2) \times 4)} & := \frac{1 \times (0+((9 \times 5)+3))}{8 \times ((7 \times 6)+(2+4))} & := \frac{10+((9-5)^3)}{8 \times (76+(2-4))} \\
& := \frac{(109-5) \times 3}{8 \times ((76+2) \times 4)} & := \frac{1 \times (0+((9+5) \times 3))}{(8+(7+6)) \times (2^4)} & := \frac{10+(9 \times (5-3))}{8 \times (7 \times (6+(2-4)))} \\
& := \frac{1-((0 \times 95)-3)}{8+((7 \times (6-2))-4)} & := \frac{1 \times (0+((9-5)^3))}{8^{7-6-2+4}} & := \frac{10+(9+(5 \times 3))}{8 \times ((7 \times 6)-(2 \times 4))} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-((9+5) \times 3))}{8 \times (7+(6 \times (2+4)))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9-(5-3)))}{8 \times (7-(6-(2+4)))} & := \frac{10+(9+(5+3))}{(8+(7-6)) \times 24} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-((9-5) \times 3))}{((8+(7 \times 6)) \times 2)+4} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9 \times (5-3)))}{(8+(7 \times (6-2))) \times 4} & := \frac{10+(9+(5-3))}{8 \times (7+(6+(2 \times 4)))} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-((9-5)^3))}{8 \times (7+(62-4))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9^{5-3}))}{8 \times ((7-(6-2))^4)} & := \frac{109 \times (5-3)}{8+(7 \times (62 \times 4))} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-(9-(5+3)))}{8+((7-6) \times (2 \times 4))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9+(5 \times 3)))}{8 \times ((7 \times (6-2))-4)} & := \frac{109+(5 \times 3)}{((8 \times 7)+6) \times (2^4)} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-(9-(5-3)))}{8+(7 \times (6-(2-4)))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9+(5+3)))}{8 \times (7-(6-(2^4)))} & := \frac{109+53}{(8-((7-6) \times 2))^4} \\
& := \frac{1-(0-(9 \times (5+3)))}{8 \times (7+(62+4))} & := \frac{1 \times (0+(9+(5-3)))}{8 \times (7+(6+(2-4)))} & := \frac{109-53}{8 \times (7 \times (6-(2-4)))}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10954}{87632} &:= \frac{(1+09) \times 5 + 4}{(8-7) \times ((6^3) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{09}) + 5) \times 4}{(87 + (6+3)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 5))) \times 4}{8 \times ((7 + (6 - 3)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 5)))^4}{8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 3))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1+09) \times (5 \times 4)}{(8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 32} \\ &:= \frac{(1+09) \times (5+4)}{8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 3) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 95))^4}{(8^7) \times ((6 \times 3)^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{09}) + (5 \times 4)}{(87 - (6 - 3)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{09}) + (5 - 4)}{8 - (7 - (6 + (3^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 \times 5)) - 4}{8 \times ((7 + (6^3)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - 5)) + 4}{8 \times (76 - 32)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - 5)) - 4}{(8 + (7 - 6)) \times 32} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 9) - (5 \times 4)}{8 \times (76 - (3 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(109 + 5) \times 4}{8 \times (76 \times (3 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(109 - 5) \times 4}{8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 32)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - ((0 \times 95) - 4)}{8 + ((7 + (6 + 3)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 \times 5) + 4))}{8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 3)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 \times 5) - 4))}{8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (3 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 - 5) \times 4))}{8 \times (7 + (6 + 3 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + 54))}{8 \times (7 \times ((6 - 3)^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 + 4)))}{8 \times (76 + (3 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 - 4)))}{8 \times (7 - (6 - (3^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (5 \times 4)))}{(8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 3) - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (5 + 4)))}{8 \times (7 + (6 + (3 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (5 - 4)))}{87 + (6 - (3 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + 54))}{8^{7-6}+3^2} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (95 + 4))}{8 \times ((7 + (6 - 3))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 \times (9 - 54))}{8^{7-6 \times (3-2)}} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - 954)}{8 + 7632} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((0 \times 95) + 4)}{8 \times (7 + (6 - (3^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 - (9 - 54))}{8 \times (7 + (6 + 32))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 5) + 4))}{8 \times (7 \times (6 + (3 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 5) - 4))}{8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 3) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 - 5) \times 4))}{(8 - (7 - 63)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 - 5)^4))}{8 \times ((7 + (6 + 3))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 - (5 - 4)))}{8^{7-6+3-2}} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (5 + 4)))}{8 \times (76 + 3 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (5 - 4)))}{8 \times ((7 - 6) \times (3^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + (5 + 4)))}{8 \times (7 + (6 + 3 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 + 54))}{8 \times (7 \times ((6 - 3)^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (95 \times 4))}{(8 + (7 \times (6^3))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - (5 \times 4)))}{8 \times (7 + (6 - (3 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - 54))}{(8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 32} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (9 - (5 - 4))}{(8 \times 76) + 32} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (9 \times (5 + 4))}{(8 + 7) \times ((6^3) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 5) + 4)}{(8 + (76 \times 3)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 5) - 4)}{8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (3^2))} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((9 + 5) \times 4)}{(87 \times 6) + (3 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{10 + ((9 - 5)^4)}{8 \times (7 \times (6 + 32))} \\ &:= \frac{10 + (9 + (5 + 4))}{(8 - (7 - 6)) \times 32} \\ &:= \frac{109 - (5 - 4)}{8 \times (76 + 32)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 - 6) \times 2))}{3 \times (7 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (6 - 2)))}{3 \times (7 + (5 + (8 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((09 + (6 \times 2)))}{3 \times (7 + (5 + (8 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - (6^2)))}{(3 - (7 \times (5 - 8))) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{09}) + 6)^2}{(37 + 5) \times (8 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (((09 \times 6) + 2))}{3 - (7 \times (5 - (8 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{09}) + 62}{(3 - (7 - 58)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{((10 + 9) \times 6) - 2}{(37 - 5) \times (8 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{109 - (6 - 2)}{(3 + 7) \times ((5 \times 8) - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 9) + (6^2)}{3 \times ((7 + 5) \times (8 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 \times 9) - 6) \times 2}{((3 + 7) \times 58) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (96 + 2)}{3 \times (7 \times (5 \times (8 \times 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{37845} &:= \frac{10 \times 9 + 6^2}{(3 + 7 \times (8 + 4)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times 9 - 6) \times 2}{(37 - 8) \times 4 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{38745} := \frac{(1 + 09) \times 6 - 2}{(3 \times (8 + 7) - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{43587} := \frac{(10 \times 9 - 6) \times 2}{4 \times (3 \times 58 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{45738} := \frac{(10 + 9) \times 6 + 2}{4 + (57 + 3) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{48573} := \frac{(1 + 09) \times 6 - 2}{4 \times (8 + 57) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{57834} := \frac{(10 + 9) \times 6 + 2}{578 + 34}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{74385} &:= \frac{1 + 09 + 6 - 2}{((7 - 4)^3 - 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 09 \times 6 + 2}{(7 \times 4 \times 3 - 8) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + 9) \times 6 - 2}{(7 + 4 \times 3) \times 8 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{85347} := \frac{1 + 09 + 6 - 2}{8 \times 5 \times 3 - 4 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10963}{82574} := \frac{10 + 9 \times 63}{82 \times (57 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{23478} := \frac{10 + (9 + 6) \times 5}{2 + 3 \times 4 \times (7 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{27348} := \frac{10 + (9 \times 65)}{2 \times (734 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{78432} := \frac{10 + (9 + 6) \times 5}{(7 + 8 + 4) \times 32}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10968}{34275} := \frac{((1^{09}) + 6) \times 8}{(3 + (4 - 2)) \times (7 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 6))) \times 8}{(3 \times (42 - 7)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{09}) \times (6 \times 8)}{((3^4) \times 2) - (7 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (-09)) \times (6 - 8)}{(3 \times (4^2)) + (7 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(109 - 6) \times 8}{(3 + (4 \times (2^7))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (6 + 8)))}{(3 - (4 - 2)) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (6 - 8)))}{(3 + (4 - 2))^{7-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + ((9 + 6) \times 8))}{(3 + (4 - 2)) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (9 \times (6 \times 8)))}{3 \times ((4 + 2) \times 75)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (96 \times 8))}{(34 - 2) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (0 + (96 - 8))}{((3 \times (4^2)) + 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - (6 \times 8)))}{((3 \times (4 + 2)) + 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times ((9 - 6) \times 8)}{((3 \times 4) - 2) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + ((9 \times 6) + 8)}{(3 + ((4 + 2) \times 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{10 + (9 \times (6 + 8))}{3 + (427 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10974}{36285} := \frac{10 \times 9 - 7 \times 4}{3 \times (62 + 8) - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10975}{32486} := \frac{(1 + 09) \times 7 + 5}{3 \times (2 + (4 + 8) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{10 \times (9 - 7) + 5}{3 \times 24 + 8 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12047}{65398} := \frac{1 + (2 \times (0 - (4 - 7)))}{6 + ((5 \times 3) + (9 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - (4 + 7)))}{6 - (5 \times (3 - (9 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (2 + (-04))) \times 7}{6 \times (5 - (3 - (9 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (20 - 47)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 3) + 9)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((04 \times 7)))}{(6 + (5 + (3 \times 9))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - 0)) \times (4 \times 7)}{((6 \times (5 + 3)) + 9) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times (-04))) \times 7}{(6 \times 5) + (39 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 204) \times 7}{(6^5) - (3 - (9 + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12054}{63798} := \frac{1 + 2 \times 05 \times 4}{(6 \times 3 + 7) \times 9 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12054}{93786} := \frac{1 + 2 \times 05 \times 4}{9 \times 37 - 8 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12069}{37548} := \frac{((1 + (2 - 0))^6) - 9}{(3^7) + (5 + 48)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^2 + 0) \times (6 \times 9)}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 - 4) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 \times 6))) \times 9}{(3 \times (7 + 5)) + 48}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 \times 6)))^9}{(3^7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (-06))) \times 9}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - 0)) \times (6 \times 9)}{(37 + 5) \times (4 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((20 + 6) \times 9)}{(37 + 54) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (0 + (6 \times 9)))}{(3 + ((7 \times 5) + 4)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (20 \times (6 \times 9))}{3 \times (7 \times (5 \times (4 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - (6 + 9)))}{3 - (7 - (5 \times (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - 69))}{(37 - (5 + 4)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2^{-06+9})}{((37^{-5}) \times 4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (20 + (6 + 9))}{(((3 \times 7) + 5) \times 4) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (20 + 69)}{(3 + 7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (0 + (6 \times 9))}{(37 + 5) \times 48}$$

$$:= \frac{120 + 69}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12073}{96584} := \frac{((1^2 + 0) + 7)^3}{(9 - ((6 - 5)^8))^4}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{207}) + 3}{9 + (6 + (5 + (8 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (-07))) \times 3}{(9 + 6 + 5) \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2^{07})) \times 3}{9 \times ((6 \times 58) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 - 0)) \times 73}{(9 - 6) \times 584}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (20 + 7)) \times 3}{(9 - (6 - 5)) \times 84}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 207) \times 3}{96 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(12 \times (07)) + 3}{(9 - 6) \times (58 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(12 + (-07)) \times 3}{(9 + 6 - 5) \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (2 \times (0 - (7 - 3)))}{(9 + (6 - (5 - 8))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((2^{07})^3)}{((9 - (6 - 5)) \times 8)^4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((2^{07}) + 3)}{((9 \times (6 \times 5)) - 8) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 - ((0 \times 7) - 3))}{9 - (6 - (5 + (8 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (0 - (7 + 3)))}{(9 - (6 - 5)) \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (0 - (7 - 3)))}{(9 + (6 + (5 - 8))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (0 \times 73))}{9 + (6 + (5 - (8 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (0 + (7 - 3)))}{(9 - (6 - (5 + 8))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (20 - (7 + 3))}{(9 + 6 + 5) \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (20 \times (7 - 3))}{9 + (6 + (5^{8-4}))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (20 + (7 \times 3))}{(9 + (65 + 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (207 + 3)}{(9 + 6 + 5) \times 84}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (207 - 3)}{96 \times (5 + (8 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{2073}}{9 + (6 + (5 - (8 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((2 - (-07)) \times 3)}{(96 - (5 \times 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((20 - 7) \times 3)}{(9 + 6 - 5) \times (8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - (7 + 3)))}{9 + (6 + (5 + 84))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - (7 - 3)))}{((9 \times 6) - (5 \times 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 - (0 \times 73))}{9 + (6 + (5 + (8 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (20 + (7^3))}{(96 - 5) \times (8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{12 - (0 - (7 \times 3))}{(9 + (65 - 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{12 - (0 - 73)}{96 + 584}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times ((0 \times 7) + 3)}{9 \times ((6 - 5) \times (8 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{120 - (7 \times 3)}{9 \times (((6 \times 5) - 8) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{120 - 73}{((9 \times 6) + (5 \times 8)) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12084}{35796} := \frac{1 \times (208 + 4)}{3 + 5^{7-9+6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12087}{94563} := \frac{1 \times ((20 \times 8) - 7)}{(9 \times 45 - 6) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{34587} := \frac{12^{09-6}}{3^4 \times (5 + 8 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{35784} := \frac{(1 + 2 + 09) \times 6}{3 \times (5 \times (7 + 8) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^2 \times 096}{3 \times (5 + 7) \times 8 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 096}{3 \times (5 \times 7 \times 8 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{37548} := \frac{(1 + 20) \times 96}{(3 + 7) \times 5^4 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{38745} := \frac{1 \times 2^{0 \times 9 + 6}}{(3 \times (8 + 7) - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{45738} := \frac{(1 + 2) \times 096}{4^5 + 73 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{48573} := \frac{1 \times 2^{0 \times 9 + 6}}{4 \times (8 + 57) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{57834} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 096}{(5 \times 7 - 8) \times 34}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{73584} &:= \frac{1 \times ((2 \times (09)) - 6)}{(7 \times (3 \times 5)) - (8 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1^2 \times 096}{((7+3) \times 58) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((09 \times 6)))}{73 \times (5 + (8 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{12 \times ((09 \times 6))}{73 \times (58 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (209 - 6)}{73 \times (5 + (8 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (20 \times 96)}{73 \times (5 \times (8 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 20) \times 96}{7 \times (3 \times 584)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{83475} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 096}{(8 \times 34 - 7) \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12307}{98456} &:= \frac{((1+2)^3 + 0) \times 7}{9 \times ((8 + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - (3 - 0))) \times 7}{98 + ((4 \times 5) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 + 3)) \times (-07)}{(9 - 8) \times (4 \times 56)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) \times (30 + 7)}{(9 \times 8) + (4 \times 56)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) + (3 - (0 \times 7))}{9 + (8 + (4 + (5 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (2^3 + 0)) \times 7}{((98 + 4) \times 5) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (2^3 + 0))^7}{9 \times (8 \times ((4 + 5)^6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times (30 + 7)}{(98 \times (4 + 5)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times (30 - 7)}{((9 \times 8) + (4 \times 5)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2)^{3+0 \times 7}}{9 \times (8 \times (4 + (5 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(12 \times (3 - 0)) - 7}{(9 \times (8 \times 4)) - 56} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 - (2 - (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{9 - (8 - (4 + (5 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 - (3 - (-07)))}{98 + (4 - (5 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 \times (3 \times (-07)))}{(9 \times (8 \times 4)) + 56} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 + (3 + (-07)))}{9 + (8 - (4 - (5 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 - 307)}{9 \times (8 \times (4 + (5 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3 + 0) \times 7)}{(98 \times 4) + 56} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3 + 0)^7)}{(9 + (8 + (4 - 5)))^6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3 + 0) + 7)}{(9 - 8) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 7)}{(9 - (8 - 4)) \times 56} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (3 + (-07)))}{(9 + (8 - (4 + 5))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (3 \times (07)))}{(98 \times 4) - 56} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (30 - 7))}{98 + (45 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2^{3+0 \times 7})}{(9 - (8 + (4 - 5)))^6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{9 - (8 - (45 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (3 - (-07)))}{(9 + (8 + (4 - 5))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (30 + 7))}{((9 \times 8) - (4 \times 5)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1^{2307}}{9 - (8 + (4 - (5 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((2^3 + 0) \times 7)}{(9 - 8) \times 456} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 - (3 \times (-07)))}{(9 \times 8) + (4 \times (5 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 - (3 + (-07)))}{9 + (8 + (45 - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (3 - (-07)))}{9 + (84 + (5 + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{12 \times (3 \times (07))}{9 \times ((8 - 4) \times 56)} \\ &:= \frac{123 + 07}{984 + 56} \\ &:= \frac{123 - 07}{984 - 56} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12345}{98760} &:= \frac{((1 - (2 - 3)) \times 4)^5}{(9 - (8 - 7))^6 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times (34 + 5)}{9 \times (8 \times (7 + (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 - ((3^4) - 5))}{(9 + (8 - 7)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 \times (3 - 45))}{(98 \times 7) - (6 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - 5)))}{9 + (8 - (7 - (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (((2^3) + 4) \times 5)}{(9 - (8 - 7)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))}{(9 + 87) \times (6 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2 + 34) \times 5)}{(9 + (8 + 7)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((23 - 4) \times 5)}{(9 - 8) \times 760} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (3 - (4 - 5)))}{(9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1^{2345}}{9 - ((8 - 7)^6 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((2^3) + (4 + 5))}{(9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 - 5)))}{9 \times 8^{7-6+0}} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (3 - (4 - 5)))}{98 - (7 \times (6 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{12 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5))}{(9 + 87) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{47895} &:= \frac{12 \times 3 + 60}{47 \times 8 - 9 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 2 - 3 + 60}{4 \times 78 - 95} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{84975} &:= \frac{1 - 2 + 3 + 6 + 0}{8 + 49 - 7 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2 + 3) \times 6 + 0}{8 \times (4 + 9 + 7) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - 2 + 3)^6 + 0}{8 + 4 \times 9 \times (7 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 36 + 0}{(8 + (4 + 9) \times 7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 2^3 \times 60}{(8 + 4 \times 9) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12369}{45087} &:= \frac{(1 + (2 + 3) \times 6) \times 9}{4^5 + 0 \times 8 - 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12369}{54870} &:= \frac{1 - 2 \times (3 - 69)}{5 \times (48 + 70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12376}{85904} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 37 - 6}{8 \times 59 - 0 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{123 + 7 + 6}{8 \times 5 + 904} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12384}{96750} &:= \frac{(1 + 23 - 8) \times 4}{(9 - 6 + 7) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{12 \times 3 \times (8 - 4)}{(9 + 6) \times 75 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 23) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 - 6) \times 750} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 2^3 \times 84}{(9 + 6) \times 7 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12389}{47650} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 8 - 9}{(4 - 7 + 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{1^2 + 3 \times (8 + 9)}{4 \times (7 - 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{1 - 2^3 + 8 \times 9}{(4 + 7 - 6) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{84975} := \frac{12 + 3 + 89}{(4 + 76) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12390}{48675} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 3 + 9 + 0}{(4 + 8 + 6 - 7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 2 + 39 + 0}{4 + 86 + 75} \\ &:= \frac{12 \times 3 + 90}{(4 \times 8 + 67) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1^2 + 3 \times 9 + 0}{48 + 67 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12396}{80574} &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (3 + (9 - 6)))}{(8 \times ((0 \times 5) + 7)) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((2 \times 3) + (9 - 6))}{80 - (5 \times (7 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (3 + (9 - 6)))}{80 - (5 - (7 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((2 \times 3) + (9 + 6))}{(8 - (-05)) \times (7 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (((2 + 3) \times 9) - 6)}{(8 - (0 - 57)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (3 \times (9 + 6)))}{8 \times (((05 \times 7) + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (2 - (3 + (9 \times 6)))}{(8 - (-05)) \times (7 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3) + (9 \times 6))}{(80 \times 5) + (7 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{239}) \times 6}{8 - (0 - ((5 \times 7) - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 96)}{80 \times ((5 \times 7) + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12397}{46508} := \frac{(1 + (2 + 3) \times 9) \times 7}{4 \times 6 \times 50 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12397}{58604} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 3^{9-7}}{58 - 6 + 0 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 7}{5 \times 8 + 60 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 - (3 - 9) \times 7}{(58 - 6) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 2^3 \times 9 - 7}{(5 + 8) \times 6 \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 2 + 3 + 9) \times 7}{(5 + 86) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (-2 + 3 \times 9) \times 7}{(5 + 8) \times (60 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12430}{65879} := \frac{1 + 2^4 + 3 + 0}{6 + (5 + 8) \times 7 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 2 + 4) \times 30}{(6 + 5 \times 8 + 7) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12450}{68973} := \frac{1^{24} \times 50}{6 - 8 \times 9 + 7^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12463}{89507} := \frac{1 + 2 \times (4 \times 6 + 3)}{8 + 9 \times (50 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12480}{53976} := \frac{(1 + 2 \times 4) \times 80}{((5 - 3)^9 + 7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{70956} := \frac{1 + 2 \times (4 + 8 - 3)}{7 + 095 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{70965} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 48 \times 3}{(70 + 96) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{76950} := \frac{1 + 2 \times (4 + 8) \times 3}{(7 - 6) \times (9 \times 50)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 25 + 4 + 0}{73 + 98 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{95760} := \frac{((1 + 2)^4 - 8) \times 3}{(9 - 5) \times (7 \times 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12680}{95734} := \frac{(1 - 2 + 6) \times 8 + 0}{(95 + 7) \times 3 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12543}{69708} := \frac{125 - 4 \times 3}{6 + 9 \times 70 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12495}{38760} := \frac{12 \times (4 + 9 \times 5)}{3 \times 8 \times 76 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12684}{53907} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (6 + (8 - 4)))}{5 - (3 - (90 - 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12495}{67830} := \frac{1 - 2 \times (4 - 9 - 5)}{6 + 78 + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 + 4) \times (9 + 5)}{6 + (7 + 8) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (2 - 4) \times 9 \times 5}{(6 + 7) \times (8 + 30)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12567}{38940} := \frac{1 - 2 + 5 + 67}{3 \times 8 \times 9 + 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2^{6-8+4})}{5 + (3 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (6 - (8 \times 4)))}{(5 + (3 + (9 - 0))) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12573}{40986} := \frac{1 \times 257 - 3}{(40 + 98) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((2 \times (6 + 8)) + 4)}{53 + (90 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (6 + (8 \times 4)))}{5 \times ((3 \times (9 - 0)) + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12537}{60894} := \frac{1 \times (2 - (5 - (3 + 7)))}{6 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 4)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{30976} := \frac{1 - 2 - 5 + 84}{3 \times (09 - 7)^6}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - (2 - 6)) \times 8) + 4}{((5 - 3) \times 90) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (5 + (3 \times 7)))}{60 + ((8 \times 9) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 2^5 + 84}{3 \times (09 + 7) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(12 - (6 - 8)) \times 4}{(5 - 39) \times (-07)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((2 + (5 + 3)) \times 7)}{(60 + 8) \times (9 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{37609} := \frac{12 \times (5 \times 8 + 4)}{3^7 - 609}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (6 + (8 - 4)))}{5 + (39 - (-07))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (5 + 37))}{6 \times (((08 + 9) \times 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{90376} := \frac{1^{25} + 8 \times 4}{9 + 03 \times 76}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 5 + 84}{9 \times (03 + 76)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12690}{58374} := \frac{1 \times (2 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}{(5 \times 8) - ((3 \times 7) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 + (5 \times 3))) \times 7}{6 \times ((08 + 94))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{26}) + (9 - 0)}{5 + (8 + (3 \times (7 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (5 + 37)}{(60 + 8) \times (9 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12597}{34086} := \frac{1 + 2 \times 5^{9-7}}{3 \times (40 + 8) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{12 - (6 - (9 - 0))}{5 - (8 \times (3 - (7 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (5 \times (3 \times 7))}{60 \times (8 + 94)}$$

$$:= \frac{(12 \times 5 - 9) \times 7}{3 \times 40 \times 8 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (26 + (9 - 0))}{5 + (8 + (37 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (2 - 6)) \times (9 - 0)}{((5 + (8 \times 3)) \times 7) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12540}{73986} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 5 + 40}{7 + 3 \times 98 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12654}{83790} := \frac{1 + (-2 + 6 + 5) \times 4}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((2^6) - (9 - 0))}{5 + (8 \times (3 + (7 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{7^3 + 9 + 8 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{26}) \times 90}{(5 \times 8) + 374}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (5 + 40)}{7 \times (3 + 9 \times 8) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12670}{39458} := \frac{(1 + 2 + 6) \times 70}{394 \times 5 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{126 + (9 - 0)}{5 + (8 \times (3 + 74))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12690}{83754} &:= \frac{(1^{26}) + (9-0)}{8 - (3 - (7 + 54))} \\ &:= \frac{12 - (6 - (9 - 0))}{8 + (37 + 54)} \\ &:= \frac{(12 - 6) \times 90}{((8^3) \times 7) - (5 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - 6)) \times (9 - 0)}{(8 \times 37) + (5 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) - (6 - 90)}{(83 \times 7) - (5 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^2) + 6) \times 90}{(8 + 3) \times (7 \times 54)} \\ &:= \frac{126 + (9 - 0)}{837 + 54} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (26 - 90)}{(8 + 3) \times ((7 \times 5) + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12705}{49368} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 05}{4 \times (9 - 3) \times 6 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times 7 \times 05}{4 \times (9 - 3) \times 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12705}{86394} := \frac{1 + (2 + (7 - (0 \times 5)))}{8 - (6 \times (3 - (9 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 + (7 - (-05)))}{86 + (3 + (9 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 5)}{((8 + 6) \times 3) + 94}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (2 \times (7 - (-05)))}{8 + (6 + (39 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (2 - (7 - 0))) \times 5}{(((8 + 6) \times 3) + 9) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^2) \times (7 \times (05))}{8 + ((6 \times 39) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times 7)) \times (-05)}{(8 \times 6) + 394}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (7 \times (05)))}{(8^{6-3}) - (9 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (2 \times 70)) \times 5}{((8 \times 6) + 3) \times 94}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12736}{58904} := \frac{(1 \times 2 + 7 + 3) \times 6}{5 - (8 - 90) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 7 \times 3 \times 6}{(58 + 90) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12740}{86359} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 40}{8 + 6 \times 35 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12740}{89635} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 4 + 0}{8 + 9 \times (6 + 3 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12749}{53680} := \frac{1 + 2 - 7 \times (4 - 9)}{(5 + 3 - 6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(12 + 7) \times 4^9}{(5 + 3)^6 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 2 \times 7 + 4) \times 9}{5 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (7 \times 4 - 9)}{(5 - 3) \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 274 - 9}{(5 + 3 + 6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 2 + 7 \times 49}{5 \times 36 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12750}{34986} := \frac{(1 + 2 \times 7) \times 50}{3 \times 49 \times (8 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 750}{(3 + 4) \times 98 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12750}{38964} := \frac{(1 + 2 \times 7) \times 50}{3 \times (8 \times 96 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12765}{83490} := \frac{1 + 2 \times (7 + 6 + 5)}{83 \times 4 - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (7 + 6 \times 5)}{8 \times (3 + 4 \times 90)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12768}{93450} := \frac{1^2 \times 76 \times 8}{(93 - 4) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12780}{45369} := \frac{(12 - 7) \times 8 + 0}{4 + (5 - 3) \times 69}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 78 + 0}{4 \times (5 - 3 + 69)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 27 - 8 + 0}{4 - 5 + 3 + 69}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12780}{64539} := \frac{1 \times 2^7 - 8 + 0}{645 - 39}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{36540} := \frac{1 + (2 - 7 + 8) \times 9}{(3 - 6 + 5) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 2 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}{36 \times 5 - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2^7 - 8 \times 9}{(3 + 6 - 5) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 27 + 89}{3 \times (6 + 54) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{12 - 7 + 8 \times 9}{36 \times 5 + 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 2 + 7 + 8) \times 9}{3 \times 6 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{43065} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 78 - 9}{430 + 65}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{45360} := \frac{1 \times 2^7 \times 8 - 9}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{46305} := \frac{1 + 27 - 8 + 9}{(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 05}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 2 \times 7 + 8 \times 9}{4 + 6 + 305}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{63504} := \frac{1 + 27 - 8 + 9}{6 + 3 \times (50 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2^7 + 8 + 9}{6^3 + 504}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+2) \times (78+9)}{6^{3+5-04}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{36045} := \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{(360-4) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{128+04}{369+5+7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 283 - 4}{(5+7+9) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{36450} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7+9 \times 8)}{3^{6-4} \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1280-4}{(3^6+9) \times 5-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{75609} := \frac{1+2+8+3^4}{7-5+60 \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12804}{39576} := \frac{1-2+8+04}{3-9 \times 5+76}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 79 \times 8}{3 \times 6 \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1+28+04}{3 \times (9-5) \times 7+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12845}{69730} := \frac{1-2-8 \times (4-5)}{6+9-7+30}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+2) \times (7+9 \times 8)}{3^6-4-50}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+2+8) \times 04}{3 \times 9 \times 5+7-6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2^{8-4} + 5}{6 \times (9+7+3) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{45360} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7+9 \times 8)}{4 \times 5^3+60}$$

$$:= \frac{12+80-4}{3 \times 95-7-6}$$

$$:= \frac{1^2 \times 84 \times 5}{(69+7) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{45603} := \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{4 \times (560+3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+2 \times 80+4}{3+9 \times 57-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{53460} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7+9 \times 8)}{(5 \times 3-4) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{128+04}{395+7+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12857}{49036} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (8+5 \times 7)}{4+9 \times 036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{54036} := \frac{1 \times 2+7 \times (9-8)}{5 \times 4+03 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2+7+9 \times 8}{(54+03) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12830}{79546} := \frac{1^2 \times (8-3)+0}{7+9+5+4+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12859}{36740} := \frac{1+(2+(8+(5-9)))}{3+(6+(7+(4-0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1-2-7+98}{5 \times (40+36)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (8-3)+0}{7 \times (9-5+4)+6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^2) + ((8-5) \times 9)}{(3+(6-7)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{1+2 \times 7 \times 9+8}{5 \times (40 \times 3-6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1-2 \times 8+30}{79+5 \times 4-6}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(2-(8 \times (5-9)))}{((3 \times 6)+7) \times (4-0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{60435} := \frac{1 \times 2-(7-9) \times 8}{(60-43) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{12 \times (8-3)+0}{(7 \times 9-5+4) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(2+(8+(5 \times 9)))}{(3-(6-7)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{1-2+7 \times 9-8}{60 \times 4+3 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1-2+8) \times 30}{7 \times (9 \times 5 \times 4+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+(2 \times (8-5))) \times 9}{(3+(6 \times 7)) \times (4-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1-2-7+98}{60 \times (4+3)+5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((8 \times 5)+9))}{(3+67) \times (4-0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12804}{36957} := \frac{(1+2+8) \times 04}{3 \times 6 \times 9-5 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{56079} := \frac{1 \times 2+(8+3) \times 4}{5 \times (6 \times 07-9)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1+28) \times 5)+9}{((3 \times 6)-7) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{57960} := \frac{1+2 \times (8+3+4)}{5 \times (7+9)+60}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (5+9)))}{(3+(6+7)) \times 40}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(1+28) \times (5+9)}{(36-7) \times 40} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12860}{73945} := \frac{12 \times (8-6) + 0}{73 + (9+4) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2^8 - 60}{7 \times (39 \times 4 + 5)} \\ & := \frac{12 - 8 + 60}{7^3 + (9-4) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 28 \times 6 + 0}{7 \times 3 + 945} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12864}{95073} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8^{6-4}}{950 - 7 + 3} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12870}{59436} := \frac{1-2+8 \times 7+0}{5-9+43 \times 6} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12870}{64935} := \frac{128+70}{64+935} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12876}{35409} := \frac{1-(2-(8+(7-6)))}{35-(4-(-09))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(8+(7-6)))}{3 \times ((5 \times (4-0)) - 9)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7-6)))}{3+(5-(4 \times (-09)))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(8+(7+6)))}{3+(54-(-09))} \\ & := \frac{1-(2+(8-(7+6)))}{3-(5-(4-(-09)))} \\ & := \frac{(1+(28-7)) \times 6}{354-(-09)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((2 \times 87) + 6)}{((3 \times 5) + 40) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6)))}{3 \times ((5^4 + 0) - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1 \times (2 - (8 - (7 \times 6)))}{((3 \times 5) - (4 - 0)) \times 9} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12876}{39405} := \frac{(1 \times 2 + 8 \times 7) \times 6}{3 \times (9 \times 40 - 5)} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12876}{53940} := \frac{1+2-8+7 \times 6}{5 \times 39 - 40} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12879}{36450} := \frac{12 \times 8 + 7 \times 9}{3^{6-4} \times 50} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12879}{45360} := \frac{12 \times 8 + 7 \times 9}{4 \times 5^3 + 60} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12879}{53460} := \frac{12 \times 8 + 7 \times 9}{(5 \times 3 - 4) \times 60} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12903}{47685} := \frac{1-2+90+3}{4 \times (7+6 \times (8+5))} \\ & := \frac{1+2 \times 90+3}{(4+7+6) \times 8 \times 5} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12903}{48576} := \frac{1+(2+9) \times 03}{4 \times 8 \times (5-7+6)} \\ & := \frac{(-1+2 \times 9) \times 03}{4 \times 8 \times (5+7-6)} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12903}{57684} := \frac{(-1+2 \times 9) \times 03}{(5 \times (7+6) - 8) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{(12+90) \times 3}{57 \times 6 \times (8-4)} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12908}{53476} := \frac{1^2 \times (90+8)}{5 \times 3^4 + 7 - 6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 29 - 08}{5+3^4+7-6} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12935}{64078} := \frac{1 \times 2^9 + 3 + 5}{(6+40) \times 7 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{▶ } \frac{12936}{78540} := \frac{12+9 \times 36}{(7 \times 8 - 5) \times 40} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12936}{85470} := \frac{1+2+9 \times (3+6)}{8+547+0} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12948}{35607} := \frac{1-(2-(9+(4-8)))}{3-(5-(6-(-07)))} \\ & := \frac{1-(2-(9-(4-8)))}{3 \times (5+(6-(0 \times 7)))} \\ & := \frac{1-(2-(9+(4+8)))}{((3+5) \times (6-0)) + 7} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((2-9) \times (4-8))}{35-(6 \times (-07))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9+(4-8)))}{35-(6-(-07))} \\ & := \frac{(1+(2+(9-4))) \times 8}{(3^5) - (60+7)} \\ & := \frac{((1+(2 \times 9)) \times 4) + 8}{3 \times ((5+(6-0)) \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2+(94-8))}{(3^5) + (6+(-07))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((2+9) \times (4+8))}{356-(-07)} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9+(4+8)))}{3+(56-(-07))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (94-8))}{((3+5) \times 60) - 7} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2^{9+4-8})}{35+(60-7)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (((2^9) \times 4) - 8)}{3+5607} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12956}{38704} := \frac{1+2 \times (9+5 \times 6)}{3+8 \times 7 \times 04} \\ & \text{▶ } \frac{12958}{76043} := \frac{1^2+9 \times 5-8}{7+6^{0 \times 4+3}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{12960}{37584} := \frac{1-2-9+60}{3 \times (7+5 \times 8)+4} \\ & := \frac{1+29+60}{3 \times (7 \times (5+8)-4)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (9+6)+0}{3-7 \times (5-8) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2960}{37 \times 58 \times 4} \\ & \frac{12960}{37845} := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{3-7+845} \\ & \frac{12960}{37854} := \frac{1^2 \times 960}{3^7-8+5^4} \\ & \frac{12960}{38475} := \frac{1-29+60}{(3 \times (8-4)+7) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1^2 \times 96+0}{3 \times (8+4+7) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{3+847+5} \\ & \frac{12960}{43875} := \frac{1^2 \times 9+0}{(4^3+8-7) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 96+0}{(43+87) \times 5} \\ & \frac{12960}{47385} := \frac{1-29+60}{4-7+3 \times 8 \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 960}{4 \times (7^3+8) \times 5} \\ & \frac{12960}{48735} := \frac{1^2 \times 96+0}{4-8+73 \times 5} \\ & \frac{12960}{54378} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 960}{(5 \times 4)^3+7 \times 8} \\ & \frac{12960}{73584} := \frac{(1+2+9) \times 60}{7-3 \times 5+8^4} \\ & \frac{12960}{73845} := \frac{(1-2+9) \times 60}{7^3 \times 8-4-5} \\ & \frac{12960}{83745} := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{837+4^5} \\ & \frac{12960}{84375} := \frac{(1-2+9) \times 60}{((8-4) \times 3-7)^5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{12963}{54087} := \frac{1+2 \times (9+63)}{5+(40 \times (8+7))} \\ & \frac{12964}{53708} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (9-6+4)}{5-3+7 \times 08} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 2+9+6 \times 4}{5 \times (3 \times 7+08)} \\ & := \frac{1-2+9 \times 6-4}{5^3+70+8} \\ & \frac{12978}{46350} := \frac{1-(2-(9+(7-8)))}{4+(6+(3 \times (5-0)))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (29-(7+8))}{(4-(6-3)) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{1-(((2-9) \times 7)+8)}{(4+6) \times (3 \times (5-0))} \\ & := \frac{(12-9) \times (7 \times 8)}{4 \times ((6-3) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{(1^2) \times (9 \times (7 \times 8))}{4 \times ((6+3) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2+978)}{(4+6) \times 350} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (9 \times (7 \times 8)))}{4 \times (6 \times (3 \times 50))} \\ & \frac{12980}{74635} := \frac{1+(2+(9-(8-0)))}{7+(4 \times (6+(3-5)))} \\ & := \frac{12 \times (9-8)+0}{7+(4+(63-5))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9+(8-0)))}{74+(6+35)} \\ & := \frac{((1^2)^9) \times (8-0)}{((7+(4+6)) \times 3)-5} \\ & := \frac{12+(9 \times (8-0))}{7 \times ((4^{6-3})+5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times 980)}{7 \times (46 \times 35)} \\ & := \frac{((1^2)^9) \times 80}{(74+(6 \times 3)) \times 5} \\ & \frac{12984}{35706} := \frac{((1-(2-9)) \times 8)-4}{(3 \times (57-0))-6} \\ & := \frac{((12-9) \times 8)+4}{35-(7 \times (-06))} \\ & := \frac{(1+(2+(9-8)))^4}{3-(5-706)} \\ & := \frac{(1+(2+9)) \times (8 \times 4)}{(3 \times (5 \times 70))+6} \\ & := \frac{(1+(2+9)) \times (8-4)}{((3 \times 5)+(7-0)) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(1+(29-8)) \times 4}{(3^5)-(7+(-06))} \\ & := \frac{(12-9) \times (8+4)}{(3 \times (5 \times (7-0)))-6} \\ & := \frac{1-(2-(9-(8-4)))}{3-(5-(7-(-06)))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((2+9) \times (8+4))}{357-(-06)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((29-8) \times 4)}{(3 \times (5+70))+6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((9 \times 8)+4))}{3-(5-(70 \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (29 \times (8-4))}{(3^5)+(70+6)} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9-(8-4)))}{35-(7-(-06))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9+(8+4)))}{3+(57-(-06))} \\ & := \frac{1+(2+(9+(8-4)))}{3+((5 \times (7-0))+6)} \\ & := \frac{12 \times (9 \times (8+4))}{3570-6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12987}{36504} := \frac{(1 \times 29 + 8) \times 7}{(3^6) - (5 + (-04))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12987}{45630} := \frac{129 + 8 \times 7}{4 \times 5 + 630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13026}{48597} := \frac{1 \times 30 + 2 - 6}{(4 - 8 + 5) \times 97}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 026}{485 - 97}$$

$$:= \frac{130 \times 2 \times 6}{(4 + 8) \times 5 \times 97}$$

$$:= \frac{13 \times 02 \times 6}{485 + 97}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13029}{67854} := \frac{1 \times 30^2 + 9}{6 \times (785 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13048}{26795} := \frac{1 \times 30 \times 4 - 8}{2 - 6 \times (7 - 9 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13054}{92876} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 05 \times 4}{(9 - 2) \times (8 \times 7 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13056}{27948} := \frac{(1 + 3)^{05} \times 6}{2 \times (7 + 9^4 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13056}{29784} := \frac{1 + 30 - 5 + 6}{(2 + 9) \times 7 - 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13064}{59782} := \frac{1 \times 30 \times 6 + 4}{(59 \times 7 + 8) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13064}{78952} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 06 + 4}{78 + 9 + 52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13065}{29748} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 065}{2 \times (9 + 7 \times 4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13065}{97284} := \frac{1^3 \times 065}{(9 + 7 \times 2 \times 8) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{130 \times (6 - 5)}{972 - 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13067}{59428} := \frac{1 + 30 + 6 \times 7}{5 - 9 + 42 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13072}{59684} := \frac{1 + 3 + 072}{5 + 9 \times (6 + 8 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13076}{28954} := \frac{1^3 + 07 + 6}{(2 \times 8 - 9) \times 5 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 \times 07 \times 6}{2 - 8 + 95 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13095}{76824} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))}{(7 \times (6 + (8 - 2))) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (30 + (9 + 5))}{(76 - (8 + 2)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 - (-09)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (6 \times 8)) + (2^4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (30 + (9 \times 5))}{(7 + (6 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((30 - 9) \times 5)}{7 \times ((6 + (8 \times 2)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 5)))}{768 + 24}$$

$$:= \frac{130 + 95}{(7 + (6 \times 8)) \times 24}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (309 + 5)}{7 \times ((68 - 2) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (30 \times (9 + 5))}{7 \times ((6 + 82) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13095}{86427} := \frac{(1^{309}) \times 5}{8 - (6 - (4 + 27))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times ((0 \times 9) - 5)}{(8 \times (6 + 4)) - (2 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))}{8 + (64 + 27)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 + (-09))) \times 5}{((8 + 6) \times (4^2)) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^3 + 0) + 9) \times 5}{(86 \times 4) - (2 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 - (-09)) \times 5)}{((8 \times 6) - 4) \times (2 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 - (-09))) \times 5}{8 - (6 - 427)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 5)))}{864 + 27}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5)}{((8 \times 6) - 4) \times 27}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13098}{52746} := \frac{13 + 098}{5 - 2 + 74 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13208}{75946} := \frac{(1^3 + 20) \times 8}{(7 + (5 + 9)) \times 46}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 20)) \times 8}{(7 - 5) \times (9 \times 46)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (20 + 8)}{7 \times (5 - (9 \times (4 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (20 - 8)}{7 + (((5 + 9) \times 4) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(13 - (2 - 0)) \times 8}{(7 - (5 - 9)) \times 46}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (2 - (-08)))}{(7 \times 5) + (9 - (4 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 + (2 + (-08)))}{7 + (5 + (9 - (4 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 20) + 8)}{(7 \times (59 - 4)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (20 + 8))}{7 + ((5 \times 94) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (32 + (-08))}{(7 - ((5 - 9) \times 4)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (2 \times (-08)))}{7 + ((5 + (9 + 4)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (20 - 8))}{7 - (5 - (9 \times (4 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{13 \times (2 \times (08))}{((7 \times 5) - 9) \times 46}$$

$$:= \frac{132 + 08}{759 + 46}$$

$$:= \frac{132 - 08}{759 - 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13247}{96805} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (2 + 4 + 7)}{(9 + 6 \times 8) \times 05}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 24 - 7}{(9 + 6 + 80) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13248}{57960} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((2^4) - 8))}{5 \times (7 \times (9 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (2 + (4 \times 8)))}{(5 \times (7 + 9)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (24 + 8))}{(5 - (7 - 9)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((3^2) + 4) \times 8)}{(5 \times 79) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((32 \times 4) - 8)}{5 \times (7 \times (9 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (2 \times 48))}{(5 + (7 + 9)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times (2^4))) \times 8}{5 \times (7^{9-6} + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3^2) \times 48)}{5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (24 \times 8)}{5 \times (7 \times (96 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13248}{76590} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 24 \times 8}{(7 + 6 \times 5) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13250}{69748} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 250}{6 \times (9 \times 74 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13254}{78960} := \frac{1 + (3 + 2^5) \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times (9 + 6) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13257}{48609} := \frac{1 \times (3 - (2 + (5 - 7)))}{4 - (8 - (6 - (-09)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + ((2 \times 5) - 7))}{4 + ((8 - (6 - 0)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((2 \times 5) - 7))}{48 - (6 - (-09))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (2 - (5 - 7)))}{4 \times (8 - (6 + (-09)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (2 + (5 + 7)))}{4 + (8 - (6 \times (-09)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (2 \times (5 + 7)))}{4 + (86 - (-09))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3^{2-5+7})}{(48 \times (6 - 0)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((3 \times 2) + 5)) \times 7}{4 \times (8 + (60 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3^2) \times (5 + 7))}{(4 - (8 \times 6)) \times (-09)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times (2^5)) + 7}{486 - (-09)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times ((2^5) + 7)}{(4 \times 8) + (60 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((32 \times 5) + 7)}{4 + ((8 + 60) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13260}{98475} := \frac{1 + 3 + 2^6 + 0}{(9 \times (8 + 4) - 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13275}{84960} := \frac{(1 - (3 + (2 - 7))) \times 5}{8 \times (4 \times (9 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 27)) \times 5}{8 \times (4 + (96 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{327}) \times 5}{8 - ((4 \times 9) - 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((3 + 2) \times 7)) \times 5}{(8 + 4) \times (96 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3^2)) \times (7 + 5)}{8 \times ((4 \times 9) + 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 27)) \times 5}{(8 \times 4) + 960}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (2 \times 75)}{(8 - 4) \times 960}$$

$$:= \frac{(132 - 7) \times 5}{(8^4) - (96 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (2 + (7 \times 5)))}{8 + (4 \times (9 \times (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (2 + 75))}{8 \times (4 \times (9 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (27 - 5))}{(8 \times 4) + (96 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((3^2) - 7) \times 5)}{(8 - 4)^{9-6} + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (2 \times 7)) \times 5)}{8 - (4 - (9 \times 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (2^7)) \times 5)}{(8^4) + (96 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (2 + 7)) \times 5)}{(8 - 4) \times (96 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((2^7) \times 5))}{(8^4) \times (9 - (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (2 + 75))}{8 \times (4^{9-6} + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13284}{76950} := \frac{(1+32+8) \times 4}{(7-6) \times 950} \quad := \frac{(1+3^4) \times (2+8)}{5 \times (706-9)} \quad := \frac{1 \times (3 - (4 - (5 + 8)))}{67 + (2 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13290}{58476} := \frac{1 - (3 + (2 - (9 - 0)))}{5 + (8 - (4 - (7 + 6)))} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{13458}{67290} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 4)) \times 5) + 8}{(6 - (7 - 2)) \times 90} \quad := \frac{1 \times (3 - (4 + (5 - 8)))}{6 - (7 - (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}{(5 \times 8) + (4 \times (7 - 6))} \quad := \frac{((1+3)^4) - 58}{(6 + (7 - 2)) \times 90} \quad := \frac{1 \times (3 - (4 - 58))}{(6 \times (7^2)) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{13 + (2^9 + 0)}{5 \times ((84 - 7) \times 6)} \quad := \frac{1^{345} + 8}{6 \times (7 + 2) - 9 + 0} \quad := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 - 8)))}{6 + (7 + (2 + 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (2 + (9 - 0)))}{5 + (8 + (47 + 6))} \quad := \frac{(1^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 8)}{((6 \times 7) - 2) \times (9 - 0)} \quad := \frac{1 \times (3 + ((4 \times 5) + 8))}{67 - (2 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{13 - (2 - (9 - 0))}{5 + (84 - (7 - 6))} \quad := \frac{1^3 + (45 + 8)}{6 \times ((7 - 2) \times (9 - 0))} \quad := \frac{1 + ((3 \times (4 + 5)) + 8)}{(6 + (7 \times 2)) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1+3)^2) + (9 - 0)}{5 \times (((8 - 4) \times 7) - 6)} \quad := \frac{(1 + (3 \times 4)) \times 58}{(6 + 7) \times 290} \quad := \frac{1 + ((3 + (4 - 5)) \times 8)}{67 + (2 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0))}{(5 + ((8 - 4) \times 7)) \times 6} \quad := \frac{(1 + (3 + (4 - 5))) \times 8}{(6 \times (7 - 2)) + 90} \quad := \frac{1 + (3 \times (4 - (5 - 8)))}{6 + (7 \times 2 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3^2) + 90)}{5 \times (8 + (4 + 76))} \quad := \frac{(1 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5)^8)}{(6 + (7 \times 2))^9 + 0} \quad := \frac{1 + (3^{4+5-8})}{6 + (7 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{13 + (2 + 90)}{(5 \times 84) + (7 \times 6)} \quad := \frac{(13 - 4) \times (5 \times 8)}{(6 + (7 \times 2)) \times 90} \quad := \frac{1 + (3 + (4 - (5 - 8)))}{6 - (7 \times (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times 290}{58 \times ((4 \times 7) - 6)} \quad := \frac{(13 - 4) \times (5 + 8)}{(67 - 2) \times (9 - 0)} \quad := \frac{1 + (3 + (4 + (5 \times 8)))}{6 \times ((7^2) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + 2)^9 + 0)}{(5^8) \times ((4 \times 7) - 6)} \quad := \frac{(1 - 34) \times (5 - 8)}{(6 + (7^2)) \times (9 - 0)} \quad := \frac{13 + (4 + (5 + 8))}{6 \times (7 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times 290)}{58 \times ((4 + 7) \times 6)} \quad := \frac{1 - ((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 8))}{6 + ((7^2) + 90)} \quad := \frac{134 + (5 + 8)}{6 + (729 - 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13294}{57086} := \frac{1 - (3 + 2 - 9) \times 4}{5 + 70 - 8 + 6} \quad := \frac{1 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) \times 8))}{(67 \times 2) - (9 - 0)} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{13467}{58290} := \frac{1^3 \times 4 \times 67}{5 \times 8 \times 29 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3 \times (2 + 9)) \times 4}{570 + 8 + 6} \quad := \frac{1 - (3 + ((4 - 5) \times 8))}{6 \times ((7 \times 2) - (9 - 0))} \quad := \frac{(1 + 3 \times 4) \times 67}{(5 + 8) \times 290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13428}{57069} := \frac{1 + 3 - 4 + 2 \times 8}{5 - 7 \times (0 \times 6 - 9)} \quad := \frac{1 - (3 + (4 - (5 + 8)))}{((6 + 7) \times 2) + (9 - 0)} \quad := \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 4) - (7 - 0))}{(5 \times (9 \times 2)) - 68}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (4 + 2 \times 8)}{5 \times (7 \times 06 + 9)} \quad := \frac{1 \times (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 8)}{(6 + (7 + 2)) \times (9 - 0)} \quad := \frac{1 + (3 + (4 + (7 - 0)))}{5 - (9 - (2 + 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times 8)}{((6 + 7)^2) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times 4) + (7 - 0))}{5 + ((9^2) - (6 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3 + 4) \times (7 - 0)}{5 + ((9^2) + 68)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (47 - 0))}{((5 + 9)^2) - (6 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (47 - 0))}{5 \times (92 - (6 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{13 + (47 - 0)}{5 - (9 - 268)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3^4) - (7 - 0))}{5 \times (9 \times 2 + (6 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (4 \times (7 - 0)))}{((59 + 2) \times 6) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (34 + 70)}{(5 \times 92) - (6 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 4)) \times 70}{(5 + (9 \times (2 + 6))) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13480}{56279} := \frac{(1^3 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{5 \times 6 + 2^7 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13480}{92675} := \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - (8 - 0)))}{(9 - (2 \times (6 - 7))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (4 + (8 - 0)))}{9 + (26 + 75)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (48 - 0)}{(9 + ((2^6) - 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - 80))}{(92 \times 6) - (7 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times 4)) \times (8 - 0)}{(9 + (2 \times 67)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(13 - 4) \times 80}{(9 + 2) \times (6 \times 75)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (4 + 80)}{(9 + 2) \times (6 \times (7 \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13482}{59706} := \frac{1 + 3 + 4 + 8 - 2}{5 + 9 \times 7 - 06}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 8 + 2}{5 + 9 + 70 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 3 \times (4 - 8 + 2)}{5^{9-7} + 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13485}{26970} := \frac{((1 + 3) \times 4) + (8 - 5)}{2 + (6^{9-7+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 + (4 - 8)))^5}{2 + (69 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 4)) \times (8 + 5)}{26 \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{348} + 5}{2 - (6 - (9 + (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (4 + (8 + 5))}{((2 - 6) \times 9) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (4 + 85)}{(2 \times (6 \times 9)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3^4)) \times 85}{2 \times 6970}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 4)) \times (8 + 5)}{(2 \times 69) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 4))^{8-5}}{(2^6) \times (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (4 \times (8 + 5))}{26 \times (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 34) \times (8 - 5)}{2 \times ((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times (4 - (8 \times 5))}{(2 \times 6)^{9-7+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((3 \times (4 - 8)) + 5)}{2^{6-9+7+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((3 - 4) \times (8 + 5))}{26 + (9 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (4 \times (8 + 5)))}{(2 \times (6 + 9)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (4 \times 85))}{26^{9-7+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (4^{8-5}))}{2 \times (69 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (48 \times 5))}{2 + (6 \times (9 + 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 \times ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{2 \times ((6 \times 9) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 + (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{(2 \times 69) - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 + (4 - (8 + 5)))}{2 + (6 \times (9 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - 485)}{2 - (6 - 970)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (4 + 8)) - 5)}{(2^6) - (9 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 4) - (8 - 5))}{2 - ((6 \times 9) - 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 48) - 5)}{2 \times (69 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (4 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(2 - (6 - 9)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + 4) \times 85)}{(2 + (6 + 9)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{2 + (69 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}{2 \times (6 \times (9 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{2 \times (6^{9-7+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{26 + (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3^{4-8+5})}{2 + (6 - (9 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{2 + ((6 \times 9) + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (4^{8-5}))}{2 \times (6 - (9 - 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (4 + (8 \times 5)))}{2 \times ((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{3485}}{2 + 6) \times 9 - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3^4) - (8 + 5))}{2 \times (6 + (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + ((3^4) + (8 \times 5))}{(2 - 6) \times (9 - 70)} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5)}{2 \times (69 + (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((34 - 8) \times 5)}{269 - (7 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 - ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{(2^6) - (9 + (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{(2^6) + (9 + (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - 85))}{2 \times (6 + (9 + 70))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 \times ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{(26 \times 9) - 70} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{2 \times (6 + (9 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3^{4-8+5})}{2 \times (6 - (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{(2^6) \times (9 - (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + (4 - (8 - 5)))}{2 + (6 + (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + 485)}{2 + (6 + 970)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (34 \times (8 - 5))}{2 \times (6 + (97 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + 3485}{2 + 6970} \\
 := \frac{13 - ((4 - 8) \times 5)}{(2^6) + (9 - (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{13 - (4 - (8 \times 5))}{2 + (6 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{13 + (48 \times 5)}{((2^6) \times 9) - 70} \\
 := \frac{13 + 485}{26 + 970} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13485}{29760} := \frac{1 - 3 \times 4 + 8 \times 5}{2 + 9 - 7 + 60} \\
 := \frac{1 - 3 + (4 + 8) \times 5}{2 \times (9 - 7)^6 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 - 3 + 4 + 85}{2 \times (9 + 7) \times 6 + 0} \\
 \frac{13509}{82476} := \frac{1 - (3 - 5) \times 09}{8 \times 24 - 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13509}{86742} := \frac{1 - (3 - 5) \times 09}{(8 - 6)^7 - 4 - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 - 3 + 50 + 9}{8 \times (6 \times 7 + 4) - 2} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 50 + 9}{8 \times 6 \times 7 \times 4 - 2} \\
 \frac{13524}{78960} := \frac{1 + 3^5 \times 2 - 4}{(7 \times 8 - 9) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13524}{87906} := \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 - (2 - 4)))}{8 + ((7 \times (9 - 0)) - 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (3 - ((5 \times 2) + 4))}{87 - (9 - (0 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (3 - (52 + 4))}{8 + (7^{9-06})} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + (52 + 4))}{((8 \times 7) + (9 - 0)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((3 \times (5^2)) - 4)}{(87 - (9 - 0)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + (5 \times (2^4)))}{(8 - (7 - 90)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((3 + (5^2)) \times 4)}{8 \times (7 + (90 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 + (2 \times 4)))}{8 + ((7 + (9 - 0)) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((35 + 2) \times 4)}{(8 \times 7) + 906} \\
 \frac{13527}{48096} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 2)^7}{((4 - 8) \times (-09))^6} \\
 := \frac{((1 + 3)^5) \times (2 + 7)}{(4 \times (8 - 0))^{9-6}} \\
 := \frac{((13 + 5)^2) \times 7}{(4 + 80) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (3 - 5)) \times 27}{48 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (3 + 5)) \times (2^7)}{4^{8 \times 0 \times 9 + 6}} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 35) \times (2 + 7)}{(4 + (8 - 0)) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{(13 + 5) \times 27}{4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (5 - 2))^7)}{4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9^6)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((3^5) \times (2^7))}{48^{09-6}} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((3^5) + 27)}{4 \times (80 \times (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7))}{4 \times (8 - (0 \times 96))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((5^2) - 7))}{4 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (5 \times (2 + 7)))}{4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 27))}{480 \times (9 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (3^{5 \times 2 - 7})}{4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + 27))}{(4 \times (8 - 0)) + 96} \\
 := \frac{1 + (3 + (52 + 7))}{(4 \times 80) - 96} \\
 := \frac{135 + 27}{480 + 96} \\
 := \frac{135 - 27}{480 - 96} \\
 \frac{13528}{64970} := \frac{(135 - 2) \times 8}{(64 + 9) \times 70}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13542}{69708} := \frac{(1+3 \times 5 \times 4) \times 2}{6+9 \times 70-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13542}{97680} := \frac{1+3 \times (5+4)^2}{(9+7+6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(3-(54+8))}{(2 \times (7 \times (09))) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(3 \times (5-(4 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (70+9)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(3 \times (5-(4+8)))}{2 \times (7-(0-(9+6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(3 \times (5 \times (4-8)))}{2 \times (7-(0-(9 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(35-48)}{2-(70-96)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3-(5-4)) \times 8)}{2 \times (70-(9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (5+4)) - 8)}{(2 \times (7 - (-09))) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3^5) - 48)}{(2 - (7 \times (-09))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 4)) \times 8)}{2 + ((70 - 9) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (5 + 4)) \times 8)}{2 \times ((7 - (-09)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + 5) \times 48)}{(2^{7+0 \times 9}) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (5 - (4 + 8)))}{2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))}{2 + (70 + 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (5 - (4 - 8)))}{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (54 \times 8))}{27 \times (0 + 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3^{5+4-8})}{2 + (7 + (0 - (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + ((5^4) + 8))}{2 \times ((70 \times 9) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 - (4 - 8)))}{2 + (7 - (0 - (9 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 \times (4 + 8)))}{2 + (70 + (9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 \times 48))}{(2 + (70 + 9)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (54 - 8))}{2 + ((7 - (-09)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (35 + (4 \times 8))}{(2^{7+0 \times 9}) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1^{3548}}{2 - (7 \times (0 \times 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 4)) + 8)}{2 \times ((7 \times (09)) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3^5) + (4 - 8))}{(2 - 7) \times (0 - 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3 + (5 + 4)) \times 8)}{(2 \times 70) + (9 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((35 + 4) \times 8)}{2 + ((70 \times 9) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))}{2 \times (70 + (9 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8))}{(2^7 + 0) - (9 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (5 + (4 \times 8)))}{(2^7 + 0) + 96}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3^{5+4-8})}{2 \times (7 + (0 - (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + ((5 + 4) \times 8))}{(2 \times (70 + 9)) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 - (4 - 8)))}{(2 \times (7 - (-09))) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 \times (4 + 8)))}{2^7 + 0 \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + (4 + 8)))}{2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + (4 - 8)))}{2 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + 48))}{2 \times ((7 \times (09)) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (54 + 8))}{(2 \times (7 \times (09))) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3548}{2 + 7096}$$

$$:= \frac{135 - (4 \times 8)}{2 \times (7 - (0 - 96))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13548}{27096} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 5))^4) - 8}{2 \times (70 + (9 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 \times (5 - 4) \times 8}{2^{7-09+6}}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 \times (5 - 4) + 8}{2 + (70 - (9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times ((5^4) + 8)}{(2 \times (70 \times 9)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + (5 + 48)}{(2 + (7 - (-09))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (4^8)}{(2^7 + 0)^{9-6}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times (5 - 4))) \times 8}{2^{7 \times 0 \times 9 + 6}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 \times 4))) \times 8}{(2^7 + 0) \times (9 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 5)) \times (4 + 8)}{(2 + 70) \times (9 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (5 \times 48)}{(2^7 + 0) \times (9 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 35) \times (4 + 8)}{(2 + (7 - 0)) \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((3 \times 5) - 48)}{(2 \times (7 - 0)) + (9 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((5 - 4) \times 8))}{2 + (7 - (0 - (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (5 - (4 - 8)))}{2 \times (7 - (0 \times 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (5 \times (4 + 8)))}{(2 \times (70 - 9)) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (5 \times 48))}{2 + ((70 + 9) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (5 + (4 + 8)))}{((2 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 6}$$

$:= \frac{135 + 48}{270 + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13578}{40296} := \frac{1 - 3 \times (5 - 7 - 8)}{4 \times (029 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + (8 + 4)))}{6 + (7 + (92 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{135 - 48}{270 - 96}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (5 + (8 - 4)))}{6 + (79 - 20)}$
<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13580}{94672} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 58 + 0}{94 \times (6 + 7) - 2}$	$:= \frac{1 + (35 - (8 - 4))}{(6 - (7 - 9)) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{46980} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 5 + 7 - 2}{46 - 9 + 8 + 0}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{13 \times ((5 \times 8) - 4)}{(6 + 7) \times 9 \times 20}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 \times (5 + 7) + 2}{46 + 9 + 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13584}{60279} := \frac{1 + 3 - (5 - 8) \times 4}{6 - 0 + 2 + 7 \times 9}$	<hr/>
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{49068} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 5 + 7 - 2}{49 + 06 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13584}{67920} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 8) + 4}{(6 \times (7 \times 9)) + (2 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{24597} := \frac{(1 \times 3 + 60) \times 8}{2 \times 459 - 7}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 5 \times 7 - 2}{4 \times (90 + 6) - 8}$	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (5 + (8 + 4))}{67 + (9 \times (2 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{24759} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 08}{2 \times (4 \times 7 \times 5 - 9)}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 5 \times 72}{(4 + 90) \times (6 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{(13 + 5) \times 84}{6 \times (7 \times (9 \times 20))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{25974} := \frac{(1 \times 3 + 60) \times 8}{2 \times (5 \times 97 - 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{68904} := \frac{1 - 3 + 5 + 7^2}{6 \times (8 + 9 \times 04)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((5 \times 8) - 4))}{(6 + 79) \times (2 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27459} := \frac{1 + 3 + 60 - 8}{2 \times (7 + 45) + 9}$
$:= \frac{1^3 \times 572}{(6 + 8 \times 90) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (5 + (8 - 4)))}{(6 \times 7) - (9 - (2 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 60) \times 8}{(27 \times 4 + 5) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{80496} := \frac{1 + 3 + 5 \times (7 - 2)}{80 - 4 + 96}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((35 \times 8) - 4)}{(6 + (7 \times 9)) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27594} := \frac{1 \times 36 - 0 \times 8}{2 + 7 \times 5 + 9 \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 5 + 7^2}{8 \times (049 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (5 - (8 \times 4)))}{6 \times (7 + (9 \times (2 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 60 + 8}{2^7 + 5 + 9 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{94068} := \frac{1 + 3 + 5 \times (7 - 2)}{9 + 4 \times 06 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (5 - (8 - 4)))}{6 - (7 + (9 - 20))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 08}{(27 + 5) \times 9 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{96048} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 5 + 7 - 2}{96 + 04 - 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4))}{((6 \times 7) - 9) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27945} := \frac{(-1 + 36) \times 08}{(2^7 - 9 - 4) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 3 + 5 \times 7) \times 2}{9 \times 60 + 4 + 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 \times (8 - 4)))}{((6 + 7) \times 9) - (2 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 60) \times 8}{(2 \times 7 + 9) \times 45}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 5 \times 7 - 2}{(96 - 04) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 + (8 - 4)))}{67 - (9 - (2 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{45927} := \frac{((1^3) - 6) \times (-08)}{4 + (5 + (9 \times (2 \times 7)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 57 \times 2}{9 \times (60 + 4 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((3^5) - (8 + 4))}{(67 - 9) \times 20}$	$:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times 60) - 8}{((4 \times 5) + 9) \times 27}$
$:= \frac{13 \times (5 + 7) \times 2}{(9 + 60) \times 4 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 - ((5 - 8) \times 4))}{6 - (7 - (9^2 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - (6 - 0))) \times 8}{4 + (5 + (92 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{13 \times (57 + 2)}{9 \times 604 - 8}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (5 - (8 + 4)))}{6 + (7 \times (9 - (2 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (3 + 6)) \times (-08)}{4 \times (5 + ((9 - 2) \times 7))}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 + (3^{5-8+4})}{6 + (7 + (9 - (2 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^{360}) \times 8}{4 + (5 - (9 - 27))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1^3) \times (6 \times (08))}{(4 + (5 + 9)) \times (2 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{94752} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 6 + 08}{9 + 4 + 7 \times 5^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{75048} &:= \frac{(13 - 6) \times (2 + 9)}{(7 + 50 - 4) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^3) \times (60 \times 8)}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (2 + 7)))} & &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 60 + 8}{94 \times (7 + 5 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{78540} &:= \frac{1 + 362 - 9}{(7 \times 8 - 5) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 - 6)) \times (-08)}{4 + (5 - (9 \times (2 - 7)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{95742} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 60 - 8}{(9 + 5) \times 7 \times 4 + 2} & & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (36 - 0)) \times 8}{(4^5) - (9 \times 2 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{97524} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6 + 08}{9 - 7 \times (5 - 2^4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13642}{89750} &:= \frac{13 \times 6 - 4 + 2}{(8 + 9 - 7) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times (6 \times (-08))}{(45 - 9) \times (2 + 7)} & &:= \frac{(-1 \times 3 + 6) \times 08}{(9 + 75) \times 2 + 4} & &:= \frac{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 42}{(8 + 97) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + 60) \times 8)}{(4 + 59) \times 27} & &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (6 + 08)}{9 + (75 - 2) \times 4} & & \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 - 6) \times (-08))}{45 + (9 + 27)} & &:= \frac{1^3 \times 6 \times 08}{(9 + 75 + 2) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13650}{42987} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 650}{4 \times 2^9 - 8 + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (08)))}{(4 + (5 + 9)) \times 27} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (60 \times 8))}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 27))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13620}{98745} &:= \frac{(1^3) \times (6 - (2 - 0))}{9 + ((8 - 7) \times (4 \times 5))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{24795} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6 - 8 + 0}{2 \times 4 + 7 + 9 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (36 \times (08))}{45 + 927} & &:= \frac{1 - (3 + (6 - 20))}{9 + (87 - (4 + 5))} & &:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 6) \times 8 + 0}{2 + 4 + 7 + 9 \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (3 + (60 - 8))}{(4 + (5 + (9 \times 2))) \times 7} & &:= \frac{1 + (3 + (6 \times (2 - 0)))}{9 + (87 + (4 \times 5))} & &:= \frac{1^3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{(2 + 4) \times 7 + 9 \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{136 + (-08)}{459 - 27} & &:= \frac{(1^{36}) \times 20}{(9 - (8 - (7 \times 4))) \times 5} & &:= \frac{1^{36} \times 80}{(2 - (4 - 7) \times 9) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{49572} &:= \frac{1^3 \times (6 + 08)}{4 \times (9 + 5) - 7 + 2} & &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (2 - 0)))}{9 \times ((8 \times (7 - 4)) + 5)} & &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{247 + 9 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 36 - 08}{(49 - 5 + 7) \times 2} & &:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times 6) + 20}{(9 \times (8 + (7 \times 4))) - 5} & &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{(2 + 4) \times (7 \times 9 - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 60 - 8}{(4 + (9 + 5) \times 7) \times 2} & &:= \frac{1 - (3 - (62 - 0))}{(98 - (7 + 4)) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{29754} &:= \frac{1^{36} \times 80}{2 \times 97 - 5 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{52974} &:= \frac{1 \times 36 - 08}{5 \times 2 + 9 \times (7 + 4)} & &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6^2 + 0))}{9 \times (8 + (74 + 5))} & &:= \frac{13 \times 6 \times 80}{2 \times 9 \times 754} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{59724} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 6 + 08}{59 + (7 - 2) \times 4} & & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{45927} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80}{(4 + 5) \times 9^2 \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 36 + 0 \times 8}{5 - 9 \times (7 - 24)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{13624}{75980} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 62 - 4}{7 \times 5 + 980} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{59472} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80}{(5 + 9) \times 472} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{72954} &:= \frac{1 \times 36 - 0 \times 8}{7 + 2 \times 95 - 4} & & & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{74925} &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 60) \times 8}{(7 - 4) \times 925} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{54870} &:= \frac{(13 - 6) \times (2 + 9)}{5 \times 48 + 70} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{24570} &:= \frac{(1^3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{(2 + (4 - 5)) \times 70}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9))}{(2 - (4 - 5)) \times 70} &:= \frac{(13 - 6) \times (9 \times 8)}{2 \times (0 + (54 \times 7))} &:= \frac{1 + (3 + (6 \times (9 - 8)))}{2 - (0 - ((5 \times 4) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (6 + (8 \times 9))}{(2^4) \times (5 \times (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{1 - ((3 \times (6 - 9)) + 8)}{2 - (0 - ((5 - 4)^7))} &:= \frac{1 + (36 - (9 + 8))}{2 \times (0 - (5 \times (4 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{13 \times ((6 \times 8) + 9)}{(24 - 5) \times 70} &:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((6 \times 9) - 8))}{2 \times (0 + (5 + (4 \times 7)))} &:= \frac{1 + (369 + 8)}{20 + 547} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (6 \times 8))) \times 9}{24 \times (5 \times (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((6 + 9) \times 8))}{205 - (4 \times 7)} &:= \frac{13 - (6 - (9 + 8))}{20 + (5 + (4 + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{13 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{((2 \times 4) + 5) \times 70} &:= \frac{1 - (3 - (6 \times (9 - 8)))}{2 \times ((0 \times 5) - (4 - 7))} &:= \frac{13 - (6 + (9 - 8))}{2 - ((0 \times 54) - 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + 689}{2 \times ((4 + 5) \times 70)} &:= \frac{1 - (3 + (6 - 98))}{((2^{05}) \times 4) + 7} & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{2 \times (4 \times (5 \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 - (6 - 9)) \times 8)}{20 + (5 + 47)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13702}{45968} := \frac{1 \times 370 + 2}{4 \times (5 \times 9 - 6) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + ((3^6) + 89)}{((2^4) + 5) \times 70} &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (6 \times 9)) + 8)}{20 + (5 \times 47)} &:= \frac{13 + 7^{02}}{(45 - 9) \times 6 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{25740} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (6 \times 8 - 9)}{2^5 \times 7 - 4 + 0} &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (6 + 9)) \times 8)}{205 + (4 + 7)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{74250} &:= \frac{13 \times (6 \times 8 - 9)}{(7 + 4) \times 250} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (6 - (9 + 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (5 - 4))) \times 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13706}{29548} := \frac{13 + 70 - 6}{2 \times (95 - 4 - 8)} \\
 & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13694}{20875} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 6 \times (9 + 4)}{20 \times 8 - 7 \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((6 + 9) \times 8))}{20 \times ((5 \times 4) + 7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13706}{45892} := \frac{13 + 70 + 6}{4 + 5 + (8 + 9)^2} \\
 & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13695}{80427} &:= \frac{(1^3 + 6 \times 9) \times 5}{804 \times 2 + 7} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (9 - 8)))}{20 + ((5 - 4) \times 7)} & \\
 & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13698}{20547} &:= \frac{(1^3 + (6 \times 9)) \times 8}{20 \times (5 + (4 \times 7))} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (6 - (9 - 8)))}{2 \times (0 - (5 - (4 + 7)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13708}{45296} := \frac{13 + 7 \times 08}{4 \times (5 - 2 + 9 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{36}) \times 98}{(20 + (5 - 4)) \times 7} &:= \frac{1 \times (36 \times (9 - 8))}{2 - (0 - (5 + 47))} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times (7 + 08)}{4 + 52 + 96} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^3) - (6 - (9 + 8))}{2 - (0 - (5 + (4 + 7)))} &:= \frac{1 + (((3 + 6) \times 9) - 8)}{(20 \times 5) + (4 + 7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13708}{96254} := \frac{1 + 3 \times (7 + 08)}{9 + 62 \times 5 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1^3 + (69 - 8)}{((20 + 5) \times 4) - 7} &:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times (6 + 9)) + 8)}{20 + (54 + 7)} & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 - (6 - 9))) \times 8}{2 \times (0 - (5 - 47))} &:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times (6 + 9)) - 8)}{2 - (0 - (5 \times (4 + 7)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13720}{95648} := \frac{1 - 3 + 72 - 0}{(9 + 56 - 4) \times 8} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + (3 - ((6 - 9) \times 8))}{((2 \times (05)) - 4) \times 7} & \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (6 + (9 - 8)))}{(2 \times (0 + (5 \times 4))) - 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13725}{46890} := \frac{(1 + 3^{7-2}) \times 5}{4^6 + 8 \times 9 + 0} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + (3 + ((6 \times 9) - 8))}{20 + (5 \times (4 + 7))} & \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13728}{56940} := \frac{(1+3) \times (7 \times 2 + 8)}{5 \times (69+4) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (7 + (9 - 0)))}{48 + (2 - (6 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((3 + (7 + 9)) \times 4)}{8 \times ((0 \times 2) + 56)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{29058} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 7 \times 4 - 6}{2 \times 90 - 5 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 7) + (9 - 0))}{4 + ((8 \times (2 \times 6)) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 \times (7 - (9 \times 4)))}{8^{02-5+6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{29580} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 7 \times 4 - 6}{2 \times 9 \times 5 + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (7 + 90))}{((4 \times (8 \times 2)) + 6) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 7)) \times (9 + 4)}{802 + (5 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{82950} := \frac{(1+3)^{7-4} - 6}{(8 \times 2 - 9) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (37 - (9 - 0))}{4 + ((8^2) + (6 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (7 \times 9)) \times 4)}{8 \times (((02^5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (37 + (9 - 0))}{(48 \times 2) + 65}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (((3 \times 7) + 9) \times 4)}{(8^{02}) \times (5 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (7 - (9 - 0)))}{4 + (8 - (2 - (6 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((37 \times 9) - 4)}{(8^{02}) \times (5 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13760}{29584} := \frac{1 + 3 \times (7 + 6) + 0}{2 \times 9 \times 5 - 8 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (7 + (9 - 0)))}{4 + ((8 - 2) \times (6 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 7) \times 6 + 0}{2 + 95 + 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (37 + 90)}{4 \times (82 + (6 \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13795}{46280} := \frac{1 + 3 + 7 \times 9 - 5}{(4 \times 6 + 2) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(13 + 7) \times 6 + 0}{2 + (9 - 5)^{8-4}}$$

$$:= \frac{13 - (7 - 90)}{48 \times ((2 \times 6) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{137 + (9 - 0)}{4 + ((8 \times (2^6)) - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13804}{59276} := \frac{1^3 + 80 + 4}{5 - 9 \times (2 - 7 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13790}{48265} := \frac{((1^3)^7) + (9 - 0)}{4 + (((8 - 2) \times 6) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3 + 7) \times (9 - 0)}{4 + (8 \times (26 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times 7) + 90}{((4 + (8^2)) \times 6) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) - (7 - 90)}{4 + (((8^2) - 6) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (7 + (9 - 0))}{4 - (8 - (2 \times (6 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + (7 \times (9 - 0))}{4 \times (8 \times ((2 \times 6) - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^3 + (79 - 0)}{(48 + (2 + 6)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times (7 - (9 - 0))}{4 + (8 + (2 \times (6 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times (7 - 90)}{(48 \times (2 \times 6)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((3 \times 7) - 90)}{(4 \times (8^2)) - (6 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13794}{65208} := \frac{1 \times 3 - (7 - 9) \times 4}{6 \times 5 \times 2 - 08}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times 7 + 9 \times 4}{(6 + 5 + 2) \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (7 + 9) - 4}{6^{5-2} - 08}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 3^7 + 9 + 4}{65 \times 20 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13794}{80256} := \frac{1 \times (3 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{8^{0+2 \times (-5+6)}}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - 3) \times 7) + (9 \times 4)}{8 \times (((02 \times 5) + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (7 \times (9 - 4)))}{80 + (2 \times 56)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (7 + 9)) - 4)}{8 \times ((02 + (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 7)) \times (9 - 4)}{80 \times ((2 \times 5) - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13804}{67592} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 8 + 0 + 4}{(67 - 5 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13805}{94627} := \frac{1 \times (3 + 8) + 0 \times 5}{(9 + 4) \times (6^2 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{24957} := \frac{13 \times (8 - 06)}{2 \times (4 - 9) + 57}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8 \times 06}{2 + 4 + 95 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{13 \times (8 + 06)}{24 \times (9 + 5) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{47259} := \frac{13 \times (8 - 06)}{4 \times 7 + 2 + 59}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 806}{47^2 \times 5 - 9}$$

$:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 80 - 6}{(47 \times 2 - 5) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{50976} := \frac{(1 - 3 + 8 - 2) \times 4}{50 + 9 \times (7 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1^3 + (84 + 5)}{2 \times ((7 - 6) \times 90)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{59472} := \frac{13 \times (8 - 06)}{59 + 4 + 7^2}$	$:= \frac{13 \times (8 + 2 \times 4)}{(50 + 9) \times (7 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 38) \times (4 + 5)}{(2 + 76) \times (9 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{13 + 8 \times 0 \times 6}{5 \times (9 + 4) - 7 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{56970} := \frac{(1 - 3 + 8 - 2)^4}{5 + (6 + 9) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{(13 \times 8) + (4 - 5)}{2 \times (7 + (6 + 90))}$
$:= \frac{13 \times (8 + 06)}{(5 + 9) \times 4 \times 7 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{57960} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 24}{5 \times 7 \times (9 + 60)}$	$:= \frac{(13 + 8) \times 45}{(27 - 6) \times 90}$
$:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 80 + 6}{(5 + 9) \times (4 + 72)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{95760} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 24}{95 \times 7 \times 6 + 0}$	$:= \frac{(138 \times 4) - 5}{2 \times (7 + (6 \times 90))}$
$:= \frac{13 + 806}{(5 \times 9 + 4) \times 72}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 - ((3 - (8 + 4)) \times 5)}{2 + ((7 - 6) \times 90)}$
<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13827}{46509} := \frac{1 - 3 + 8 + 27}{4 \times 6 \times 5 - 09}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((8 + 4) \times 5))}{(2 \times (7 + 6)) + 90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13820}{79465} := \frac{1 - (3 - (8 - (2 - 0)))}{7 + (9 - (4 - (6 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{13 + 82 - 7}{4 \times (65 + 09)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + (4 + 5)))}{27 - (6 - (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + (2 - 0)))}{(7 \times (9 - 4)) + (6 + 5)}$	$:= \frac{138 + 27}{46 + 509}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + (4 - 5)))}{2 - (7 - (6 + (9 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 8)) \times (2 - 0)}{((7 - (9 - 4))^6) + 5}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + 45))}{2 \times ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (8 - 20))}{7 + ((9 \times (4 + 6)) - 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13840}{29756} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 - 4 + 0}{2 + 97 - 56}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (84 + 5))}{(2 \times (7 \times 6)) + 90}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 \times (2 - 0)))}{((7 + (9 + 4)) \times 6) - 5}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 8) \times 40}{(2 + 9 + 75) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 \times (8 - (4 \times 5)))}{(2^7) - (6 \times (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 8)) \times (2 - 0)}{(7 \times (9 + (4 + 6))) + 5}$	$:= \frac{(1^3 + 8) \times 40}{2 \times 9 + 756}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 \times (8 \times (4 - 5)))}{2 - ((7 \times 6) - 90)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 8) + 20)}{((7 + (9 \times 4)) \times 6) - 5}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 - (3 \times (8 - 45))}{(2^7) + (6 + 90)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (2 - 0)))}{7 + (9 + (4 \times 65))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13845}{27690} := \frac{((1 + 3)^8) \times (4^5)}{((2 \times 7) - 6)^9 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 + (8 \times (4 - 5)))}{2 + (7 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times 8) + 20}{(7 \times ((9 \times 4) + 6)) + 5}$	$:= \frac{(1 - ((3 - 8) \times 4)) \times 5}{2 \times (7 \times (6 + (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (((3 + 8) \times 4) + 5)}{(2 \times 7) - (6 - 90)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (8 \times 20)}{(7 + 9) \times (46 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 8)) \times (4^5)}{(2^7) \times (6 + 90)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (8 \times 4)) - 5)}{2 \times (7 - (6 - 90))}$
$:= \frac{138 + (2 - 0)}{794 + (6 + 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (8 - (4 - 5))}{2 \times ((7 - 6) \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 8) + (4 + 5))}{2 \times ((7 \times 6) - (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8^2 + 0))}{(7 + 9) \times (4 + 65)}$	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (8 \times (4 + 5))}{((2 + 7) \times 6) + 90}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((38 + 4) \times 5)}{(2 - 7) \times (6 - 90)}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (8 \times 45)}{((2 \times 7) - 6) \times 90}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (8 - (4 + 5)))}{2 \times (7 + (6 - (9 - 0)))}$

$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5)))}{2 + (76 + 90)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (38 \times (4 + 5))}{2 + (76 \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((3^{8-5}) - 4)}{(6 \times (9 \times 2)) + (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 + (4 - 5)))}{27 + (6 + (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (38 + (4 + 5))}{27 + (69 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 - (8 - (5 + 4)))}{6 + (9 - (2 - (7 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + ((8 \times 4) - 5))}{((2 - 7) \times 6) + 90}$	$:= \frac{1 + 3845}{2 + 7690}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 - (5 - 4)))}{6 + (92 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 - (4 - 5)))}{2 + (7 + (6 + (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{13 \times (8 - (4 - 5))}{2 \times ((7 + 6) \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (5 + 4)))}{(6 + 9) \times (2 + 70)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 + (4 \times 5)))}{(2 \times 76) - 90}$	$:= \frac{13^{8-4+5}}{2 \times (7 + 6)^9 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 + (5 - 4)))}{(6 + 9) \times (2 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 + (4 - 5)))}{2 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{138 \times (4 + 5)}{276 \times (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 - (5 + 4)))}{6 + (9 + (2 - (7 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (38 - (4 - 5))}{2 + (7 + (69 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{138 + 45}{276 + 90}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{6 + ((9 - 2) \times (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1^{3845}}{2 \times (7 - 6)^9 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13845}{60279} := \frac{1^3 \times 845}{60^2 + 79}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 + (5 \times 4)))}{6 + (9 + (2 \times 70))}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times (8 - 4)) - 5)}{2^{7+6-9+0}}$	_____	$:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (8 + (5 + 4)))}{((6 + 9) \times 2) + 70}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times 8) + (4 \times 5))}{(2 - (7 - 6)) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13847}{29056} := \frac{1 + (3 + 8) \times (4 + 7)}{2^{9+05-6}}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (38 - (5 + 4))}{(69 \times 2) + (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times 8) + (4 + 5))}{(2 \times 7) + (6 \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 3^{8+4-7}}{2^9 + 0 \times 56}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((3^{8-5}) \times 4)}{(6 \times 92) - (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((3 + (8 - 4)) \times 5)}{(27 \times 6) - 90}$	_____	$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (8 - (5 \times 4)))}{6 + ((9^2) - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 - (8 - (4 \times 5)))}{(2^7) - (6 + 90)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13854}{69270} := \frac{((1 + 3) \times 85) - 4}{(6 + (9 \times 2)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{6 - (9 - (2^7 + 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5))}{2 \times (7 + (6 \times (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (8 \times (5 - 4))}{(6 \times 9) - (2 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 - (5 + 4)))}{(6 - 9) \times (2 - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5)))}{2 \times (76 + (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1^3) \times (85 - 4)}{(6 + 9) \times (27 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{69 - (2 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (8 + (4 - 5)))}{2 \times (7 + (6 + (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1^3 + (8 \times (5 - 4))}{(6 \times 9) - (2 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 + (5 - 4)))}{6 - (9 + (2 - 70))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 - (4 + 5)))}{2 + (7 + (6 - (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(13 + 8) \times (5 \times 4)}{(6 + 9) \times (2 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (38 - (5 + 4))}{6 \times (9 \times 2 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 \times (4 + 5)))}{2 \times (7 + (69 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - ((8 \times 5) + 4))}{(6 + 9) \times (2 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (38 + (5 \times 4))}{((6 + 9)^2) + 70}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (8 + (4 \times 5)))}{2 - (7 - (69 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + (5 - 4)))}{(6 \times (9 - 2)) - (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{13 + ((8 \times 5) + 4)}{6 + (9 + 270)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (3 + (84 + 5))}{276 - 90}$	$:= \frac{1 - (38 - (5^4))}{6 \times ((9 - 2) \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{13 + (85 + 4)}{6 \times (92 - (7 - 0))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{138 - (5 - 4)}{692 - (7 - 0)} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{27594} & := \frac{13 \times 8 + 6 - 0}{2 - 7 \times (5 - 9 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{45927} & := \frac{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}{(4 + 5) \times 9 \times 27} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{59724} & := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{5 + (9 + 7^2) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{94752} & := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{9 \times (47 - 5) - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{97524} & := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{9 \times (7 \times 5 + 2 \times 4)} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13862}{54970} & := \frac{1 - (3 - 8) \times 6 - 2}{54 - 9 + 70} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13869}{40572} & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times 86 - 9}{4 \times 05 \times 7^2} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 + 8) \times 6) \times 9}{(40 - 5 + 7)^2} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 3 \times 86 + 9}{(4 \times (0 \times 5 + 7))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13869}{54270} & := \frac{1 \times (38 - (6 + 9))}{5 \times (4 + (2 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + ((3 + (8 - 6)) \times 9)}{5 \times (4 \times (2 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (38 + (6 \times 9))}{5 \times (4 - (2 - 70))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (3 \times (8 - 69))}{5 \times (4 + (2 \times 70))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 + (6 + 9)))}{(5 - 4) \times 270} \\
 & := \frac{(1^3 + 8) \times 69}{(5 + 4) \times 270} \\
 & := \frac{(13 + 8) \times 69}{((5 + 4)^2) \times 70} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13870}{92564} & := \frac{1 + 3 \times 8 + 70}{9 + 25^{6-4}} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13872}{95064} & := \frac{1 + 3 + (8 + 7) \times 2}{9 + (50 + 6) \times 4} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{45678} & := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 - 02)}{(4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 39 + 02}{4 + 56 + 78} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 3 + 9^{02}}{4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 3 + 90 - 2}{4 + 5 \times (67 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{13 + 90 + 2}{4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 3 \times 9 + 0 \times 2}{4 \times 5 - 6 + 78} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{48657} & := \frac{((1 + 3)^9 + 0) \times 2}{(4^8 + 6 - 5) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (3 \times 9)) \times (-02)}{(4 - (8 - (6 \times 5))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1^3) \times (9 \times (02))}{4 + (8 - (6 - 57))} \\
 & := \frac{(1^3) \times (90 \times 2)}{(4 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1^3) \times (90 - 2)}{4 \times (((8 + 6) \times 5) + 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1^3 + (9^{02})}{(4 \times 86) - 57} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (9 - 0))) \times 2}{4 \times (8 + (6 + (5 \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (9 - 0))) \times 2}{(4 + (8 + 6 - 5)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (39 - 0)) \times 2}{4 \times ((8 - 6) \times (5 \times 7))} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (9 \times (02))}{4 \times ((8 + 6 - 5) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (90 \times 2)}{(4 + 8) \times (6 \times (5 \times 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(13 - (9 - 0)) \times 2}{4 \times (8 - ((6 - 5)^7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - 3) \times (9 \times (-02))}{(48 - (6 \times 5)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (3 - (90 - 2))}{((4 \times 8) + 6 + 5) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (3 + (9 \times (-02)))}{4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (3 - 902)}{(4 + 86) \times (5 \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 2)}{4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((3 + (9 - 0))^2)}{(48 - 6) \times (5 + 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (90 \times 2))}{(48 + 6) \times (5 \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (90 - 2))}{(4 + 8) \times ((6 + 5) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 + (9 - (0 \times 2)))}{48 + (6 - (5 + 7))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 + (9 - (-02)))}{(4 - (8 - (6 + 5))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 + (9^{02}))}{(4 + (8 + (6 \times 5))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (3 + (9 + (-02)))}{(4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) + 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (39 \times (02))}{(4 \times ((8 + 6) \times 5)) - 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 - (9 \times (0 \times 2)))}{4 - (8 - (6 + (5 + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 \times (9 - (0 \times 2)))}{(4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 \times (9 + (-02)))}{(4 + (8 - (6 - 5))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 + (90 \times 2))}{(4 + (8 \times (6 + 5))) \times 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 + (3 + (90 + 2))}{4 \times (86 + (5 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (39 - (-02))}{4 + (86 + 57)} \\
 &:= \frac{13 - (9 - (-02))}{(4 + (8 - (6 + 5))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{13 - (9 + (-02))}{(4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) - 7} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + (9^{02})}{(4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5)) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + (9 + (-02))}{4 + (8 + (65 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{1390 + 2}{4865 + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1390 - 2}{4865 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{75468} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9 + 02}{7 + 5 - 4 + 68} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9^{02}}{(7 + 5 \times (4 + 6)) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{13 \times 9 + 02}{7 + 5^4 + 6 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13904}{28756} &:= \frac{1 + 39 - 0 + 4}{2 + 8 + 75 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13904}{65728} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 9 + 04}{6 + 5 + 7^2 - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + 90 - 4}{6 \times (5 \times 7 \times 2 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{139 + 04}{6 \times 57 \times 2 - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 90) \times 4}{(6 \times 5 \times 7 - 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13920}{75648} &:= \frac{1 + (3 + 9)^2 + 0}{756 + 4 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13920}{75864} &:= \frac{1 + 39 + 20}{7 + 5 \times 8^{6-4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13927}{58640} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 + 9) \times 2 - 7}{5 \times 8 \times (6 - 4) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + 9 \times 2 + 7}{5 \times (8 + 6 \times 4) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times (9 \times 2 + 7)}{5 \times 8^{6-4} + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 92) \times 7}{5 \times (8 + 6) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13946}{58720} &:= \frac{1 + 3 - 9 + 4 \times 6}{(5 - 8 + 7) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{26784} &:= \frac{((1 + 3)^9) \times 50}{((2 + 6)^7) \times (8 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3)^9) \times 50}{2 + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 9)) \times 50}{2 \times ((6 + 78) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times 9)) \times 50}{2 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (39 \times 50)}{2 \times (6 \times (78 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^3) \times 950}{((2^6) - 7) \times (8 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 39) \times 50}{(2^6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{46872} &:= \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{4 \times (6 + 8 + 7) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 39 \times 50}{468 \times 7 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{48267} &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 50}{4 \times (8 \times 2^6 + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 6 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{64728} &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 50}{6 \times (472 - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{(6 \times 4 + 7 - 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13956}{80247} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9 - 5 - 6}{8^{02} + 4 \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times (9 + 5 - 6)}{8 \times (02^4 + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 + 5) - 6}{80 \times 2 + 47} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - 3 \times 9 + 5 \times 6}{8 \times (-02 + 4) + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{139 - 5 + 6}{802 - 4 + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13960}{42578} &:= \frac{(1 + 39) \times 6 + 0}{4 \times (25 \times 7 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13962}{50478} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + (9 - 6)^2}{5 \times (04 + 7) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 9 \times 6) \times 2}{(50 + 4 - 7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{20748} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 + 9 - 6) \times 5}{20 \times (7 - 4) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 96 + 5}{2 \times 074 + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 39 + 6 \times 5}{(2 + 07 + 4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{20874} &:= \frac{13 \times (9 + 6) - 5}{2^{08} + 7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{27048} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 96 - 5}{(27 - 04) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 9 \times 6) \times 5}{2 \times 70 \times 4 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{40278} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 96 - 5}{(40 - 2) \times 7 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{47082} &:= \frac{(139-6) \times 5}{4 \times 70 \times 8 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{78204} &:= \frac{((1+3)^{9-6}) \times 5}{7 \times ((8^2+0) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^3) \times (9+6+5)}{7 \times (8 - (2 \times (-04)))} \\ &:= \frac{1^3 + (9+65)}{7 \times ((8^2+0) - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((3 \times 9) - 6)) \times 5}{7 \times (8 + (20 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times (9-6))) \times 5}{7 \times ((8 + (2-0)) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3^{9-6})) \times 5}{7 \times ((8+20) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(13 + (9-6)) \times 5}{7 \times (8 \times (2 \times (04)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (9+6)) - 5)}{7 \times (8 + (20+4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (9+6-5))}{7 \times (8 + (2^{04}))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((3 \times (9-6)) + 5)}{7 \times ((8 \times (2-0)) - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((39 \times 6) + 5)}{7 \times (8 \times (20+4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (3 - (9-65))}{7 \times (8 \times (2 - (-04)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (3 \times (9 - (6-5)))}{(7 + (8+20)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (39 - (6 \times 5))}{7 \times (8 - (2 \times (0 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (39 + (6 \times 5))}{(78+20) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{13 \times ((9-6) \times 5)}{7 \times ((8 \times 20) - 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{87024} := \frac{1+3+96-5}{(8+70 \times 2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{25704} := \frac{1 \times 396 - 8}{2 \times 5 + 704}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{40752} &:= \frac{1 + (-3 + 9 + 6) \times 8}{40 \times 7 + 5 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{45072} &:= \frac{1 + (-3 + 9 + 6) \times 8}{45 \times 07 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{50472} &:= \frac{1 \times 396 - 8}{50 \times 4 \times 7 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{54720} &:= \frac{1 - (3 - 9 - 6) \times 8}{5 \times (4 + 72) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{74205} &:= \frac{(1+39) \times (6+8)}{7 \times (420+5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13978}{25064} &:= \frac{1+3 \times 9 - 7 + 8}{2+5 \times (06+4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9 \times 7 - 8}{2 \times (50+6-4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13984}{25760} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8 + 4)}{2 \times 5 \times 7 \times 6 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(1+398) \times 4}{(2+5) \times 7 \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{24570} &:= \frac{(1^3+9) \times 8 - 6}{(2-4) \times (5-70)} \\ &:= \frac{1-3-9+8 \times 6}{2+(4+5) \times 7+0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{25704} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8 + 6}{(2^5+70) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1-3-9+8 \times 6}{(2 \times 5+7) \times 04} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{47250} := \frac{(13+98) \times 6}{(47-2) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{70245} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{70 \times 2^4 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{72450} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{(7+2^4) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{74025} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{(7+40) \times 25}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13987}{64025} := \frac{1-3 \times (9-8 \times 7)}{640+2 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{78693} := \frac{140 \times 2 - 5}{7 + (8-6)^9 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{93687} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 025}{9^3 - 68 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{98736} := \frac{(1+4-0 \times 2) \times 5}{(9+8) \times (7+3) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 40 \times 2 - 5}{(98-7-3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 025}{98 \times 7 + 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14035}{68972} := \frac{140 - 35}{6 \times (8 \times 9 + 7 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14039}{57268} := \frac{140 - 39}{5 \times 7 \times 2 \times 6 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14053}{96278} := \frac{1+40+53}{9+627+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14058}{79236} := \frac{14+05-8}{7 \times (9+2-3) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{14+0 \times 5+8}{7+9^2+36}$$

$$:= \frac{1+40+58}{7 \times 9^2-3-6}$$

$$:= \frac{140-5+8}{7 \times (9+2) + 3^6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14063}{25789} &:= \frac{1^4 + 06^3}{(2+5 \times 7) \times (8+9)} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((07+6)))}{((5+9) \times (8 \times 2)) - 3} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (0 - (7 - 6)))}{9 + (8 - (5 - (3^2)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14063}{78925} &:= \frac{1 \times 40 + 6 + 3}{(7+8) \times (9 \times 2) + 5} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (-07))) \times 6}{(59 - 8) \times (2 \times 3)} &:= \frac{1 \times (40 - (7 + 6))}{9 \times (8 + ((5 \times 3) - 2))} \\ & &:= \frac{14 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)}{(59 \times (8 - 2)) + 3} &:= \frac{1 \times (40 \times (7 - 6))}{((9 + 85) \times 3) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{29538} &:= \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{2 \times (9 + 538)} &:= \frac{1 \times (40 \times (7 - 6))}{5 - ((9 - (8^2)) \times 3)} &:= \frac{1 \times (40 + (7 \times 6))}{(9 \times (8^5 - 3)) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{39528} &:= \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{3 \times (9 + 52) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{89352} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 07 \times 6}{89 \times 3 + 5^2} &:= \frac{1^4 + 0 \times 76}{9 - (8 - (5 + (3 - 2)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{39852} &:= \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{3 \times (98 \times 5) + 2} &:= \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{8 \times (9 + (3 + 5)^2)} &:= \frac{1 + ((40 \times 7) + 6)}{9 + (8 \times ((5^3) \times 2))} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{98532} &:= \frac{((1 + (4 - 0)) \times 7) - 6}{(((9 \times 8) - 5) \times 3) + 2} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))}{(9 \times 8) + (5 \times (3 - 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{23598} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 07 + 6}{2^3 \times 5 + 9 + 8} &:= \frac{(1^{4+0 \times 7}) + 6}{9 + (8 \times (5 \times (3 - 2)))} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - (0 - (7 + 6)))}{9 \times (8 + (5 + (3 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 40 - 7) \times 6}{2 \times (3^5 - 9 \times 8)} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 0) \times (7 + 6)}{((9 + 8) \times 5) + (3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - (0 - (7 - 6)))}{9 + (8 + (5 \times (3 + 2)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{25398} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 07 \times 6}{2^5 + 3 \times (9 + 8)} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 0) \times 76}{(9 - 8) \times 532} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - (0 \times 76))}{(9 \times 8) - (5 + 32)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{28359} &:= \frac{(1 + 40 - 7) \times 6}{28 \times 3 \times 5 - 9} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 0) + (7 + 6)}{98 - (5 - (3 + 2))} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - (0 - 76))}{9 \times (8 + (53 + 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{29835} &:= \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{2 \times (98 - 3) + 5} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 0) + (7 - 6)}{9 - (8 - ((5 \times 3) - 2))} &:= \frac{1 + (40 \times (7 - 6))}{((9 + 8)^{5-3}) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{32589} &:= \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8 - 9)} &:= \frac{(1 + 40) \times (7 \times 6)}{98 \times ((5^3) - 2)} &:= \frac{1 + (40 + (7 - 6))}{(9 + (8 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{38295} &:= \frac{(1 + 40 - 7) \times 6}{3 \times (8 + 29) \times 5} &:= \frac{(14 \times (07)) + 6}{(98^5) - (3 - 2)} &:= \frac{1 + (40 + 76)}{9 \times (85 + (3 \times 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{52938} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 07 \times 6}{5 - (2 - 9) \times (3 \times 8)} &:= \frac{1 - ((4 \times (-07)) + 6)}{9 - (8 - (5 \times 32))} &:= \frac{14 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)}{(9 + (8 + 53)) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{58293} &:= \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 9 + 3} &:= \frac{1 - ((4 \times (-07)) - 6)}{(9 \times ((8 - 5)^3)) + 2} &:= \frac{14 - (0 - (7 \times 6))}{(9 \times (8 \times 5)) + 32} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{59823} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 \times 76))}{5 + (9 + (8 - (2 + 3)))} &:= \frac{1 \times ((4 - (-07)) \times 6)}{((9 \times 8) + 5) \times (3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{14 - (0 - (7 - 6))}{9 + ((8 - 5) \times 32)} \\ &:= \frac{14 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)}{5 \times (9 - (8 \times (2 - 3)))} &:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times (07)) + 6)}{(9 + 8) \times (5 + (3^2))} &:= \frac{14 - (0 - 76)}{98 + 532} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (-07))) \times 6}{5 + (98 + (2 - 3))} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 - (7 \times 6)))}{(9 \times 8) + ((5^3) \times 2)} &:= \frac{14 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)}{98 \times (5 + (3 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^4 + 0) + 7) \times 6}{5 + ((98 \times 2) + 3)} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 \times 76))}{9 - (8 + (5 - 32))} &:= \frac{14 \times (0 + (7 + 6))}{98 \times ((5 \times 3) - 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{14 + ((0 \times 7) - 6)}{9 - (8 - (53 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{140 \times (7 - 6)}{98 \times (5 + 3 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{140 + 76}{9 \times (8 + (5 \times 32))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14089}{76235} := \frac{1^4 + 08 \times 9}{76 \times 2 + 3^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14098}{76532} := \frac{1 - (4 + (0 - (9 + 8)))}{(7 \times (6 + 5)) - (3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 - (9 + 8)))}{((7 \times 6) + (5 \times 3)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - 4) \times (-09)) + 8}{((7 \times 6) + 53) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1^4 \times 098}{(7 - 6) \times 532}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (-09))) \times 8}{76 + 532}$$

$$:= \frac{140 \times (9 - 8)}{76 \times (5 + (3 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{14 \times ((09 + 8))}{76 \times ((5 \times 3) + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14208}{69375} := \frac{14 \times 2^{08}}{693 + 7^5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 20 \times 8}{(6 + 9 - 3 - 7)^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14308}{59276} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3 + 0 \times 8}{5 + 9 + 2 + 7 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{14 + 3 \times 0 \times 8}{5 + 9 + 2 + 7 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 4 \times (3 - 08)}{5 + 9^2 + 7 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14208}{75369} := \frac{(1 \times 4 - 2)^{08}}{7 \times (5^3 + 69)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14235}{67890} := \frac{1 + (4 - 2 + 3) \times 5}{6 \times 7 - 8 + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{14 \times 2^3 + 5}{6 \times 78 + 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14250}{39786} := \frac{(1 + 4) \times 25 + 0}{397 - (8 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{37098} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times (5 + 6)}{3 \times (70 + 9) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{38907} := \frac{1 + (4 - 2 + 5) \times 6}{3 + 8 \times (9 + 07)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{70389} := \frac{1 - 4 + 25 - 6}{7 - 0 \times 3 + 8 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{70983} := \frac{1 + 425 + 6}{(709 + 8) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{79380} := \frac{1 + 42 - 5 + 6}{7 \times (9 \times 3 + 8) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14265}{37089} := \frac{1 + (4^{2-6+5})}{3 - (7 + (0 - (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (2 - 6))) \times 5}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 8) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((4 \times 2) + 6)) \times 5}{3 \times ((7 \times (08)) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 4 + 30 + 8}{5 \times (9 + 2 \times 7 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 30 + 8}{5 \times (9 + 27) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - 26)) \times 5}{(3 \times 70) + 89}$$

$$:= \frac{((14 \times 2) + 6) \times 5}{370 + (8 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 - 2)) \times 65}{3 - (7 \times (0 - (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + 265)}{3 + (708 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14268}{73950} := \frac{(1 + 4) \times 2^6 + 8}{(7 + 3 \times 9) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{35679} := \frac{(1 + 4^2) \times 80}{3 + 5 \times 679}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{36975} := \frac{14 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{3 + 6 \times 97 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{39576} := \frac{1 + 42 - 8 + 0}{3 + 95 - 7 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 4)^2 + 80}{3 - (9 - 57) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{57936} := \frac{(1 + 4)^2 + 80}{5 \times 7 \times (9 + 3) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{73695} := \frac{1^4 \times 280}{(7^3 - 6 \times 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14320}{75896} := \frac{1 - 4 + 3 + 20}{7 - 5 + 8 + 96}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + 3)^2 + 0}{7 \times 5 \times 8 - 9 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times 3 \times 20}{((7 - 5)^8 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{14325}{87096} := \frac{1-4+3+25}{8 \times 7 + 096} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 43 + 2^5}{8 \times (7 \times 09 - 6)} \\ & \frac{14350}{26978} := \frac{(1+4-3) \times 50}{(2-6) \times (9-7 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{1^4 \times 3 \times 50}{2 \times (6+9 \times (7+8))} \\ & := \frac{(1+4) \times 3 \times 50}{2 \times (697+8)} \\ & := \frac{(1+4+3) \times 50}{2 \times (6 \times 9 - 7) \times 8} \\ & \frac{14350}{69782} := \frac{(1+4) \times 35 + 0}{69 + 782} \\ & \frac{14352}{87906} := \frac{1 \times 4^3 \times (5+2)}{8 \times 7^{9-06}} \\ & := \frac{(1-4+35)^2}{8 \times (790-6)} \\ & \frac{14352}{98670} := \frac{1-4+3^{5-2}}{9+86+70} \\ & := \frac{1-4+3 \times 5^2}{9 \times (8 \times 6 + 7) + 0} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (3+5^2)}{(9+8-6) \times 70} \\ & \frac{14360}{98725} := \frac{1+(4-(3-(6-0)))}{9-(8-((7^2)+5))} \\ & := \frac{(1^4+3) \times (6-0)}{98+(72-5)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4+(36-0))}{(9 \times ((8+7) \times 2)) + 5} \\ & := \frac{(1+(4+3)) \times (6-0)}{(9+(8+(7^2))) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (3 \times (6-0)))}{9 \times (87-(2^5))} \\ & := \frac{1+(43+60)}{(9 \times (8+72)) - 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (36-0))}{9 \times ((8+(7 \times 2)) \times 5)} \\ & \frac{14380}{95627} := \frac{1-4+3+80}{(9+5+62) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{(1+4) \times 3 \times 80}{95 \times 6 \times 2 \times 7} \\ & \frac{14382}{59670} := \frac{(1+4)^3 + 8 \times 2}{5 \times 9 \times (6+7) + 0} \\ & := \frac{1+4 \times (3+8) + 2}{5^{9-6} + 70} \\ & \frac{14382}{79560} := \frac{(1+4) \times 38 - 2}{(7+9) \times (5+60)} \\ & \frac{14385}{70692} := \frac{(1 \times 4 + 3 \times 8) \times 5}{706 - 9 \times 2} \\ & \frac{14396}{57820} := \frac{(1+4)^3 - 9 + 6}{5 \times (78 + 20)} \\ & \frac{14508}{36972} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 50 + 8}{(3+69+7) \times 2} \\ & \frac{14508}{67392} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 50 + 8}{6 \times (7+39+2)} \\ & \frac{14508}{79236} := \frac{14 \times 5 + 08}{(79-2^3) \times 6} \\ & \frac{14520}{73689} := \frac{1^4 \times 520}{7 \times (368+9)} \\ & \frac{14520}{98736} := \frac{(1^4) \times (5 \times (2-0))}{9-(8-(73-6))} \\ & := \frac{1+(4+(5 \times (2-0)))}{(9 \times (8+(7-3))) - 6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (45-20)}{(9+8) \times (7-(3-6))} \\ & := \frac{(1-4) \times (5-20)}{((9 \times 8) - (7 \times 3)) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (45 \times (2-0))}{9 \times (8+((7+3) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{1+(4+(5 \times 20))}{(9 \times (8 \times (7+3))) - 6} \\ & := \frac{(1^4+5) \times 20}{(9 \times (87+3)) + 6} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (2-0)))}{(9+8) \times (7+(3+6))} \\ & \frac{14527}{80396} := \frac{1+4 \times (5^2-7)}{8+0396} \\ & \frac{14529}{38076} := \frac{1-4+5 \times 2 \times 9}{38 \times (0 \times 7+6)} \\ & := \frac{145-29}{380-76} \\ & := \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 29}{380 \times (7-6)} \\ & := \frac{145+29}{(3+80-7) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(1+4 \times 5) \times 29}{38 \times 07 \times 6} \\ & \frac{14538}{29076} := \frac{((1+4) \times (5 \times 3)) - 8}{2+(90+(7 \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{((1+4) \times (5^3)) + 8}{(2 \times (90 \times 7)) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(1-((4-5) \times 3)) \times 8}{2^{9 \times 0 \times 7+6}} \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(1^4) \times (5 \times 38)}{2 - (9 \times (0 - (7 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times (5 - 3))^8)}{2 \times ((9 - (-07))^6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((5 \times 3) - 8))}{2 + (9 - (0 - (7 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times 5)) \times (3 + 8)}{(2 + (9 - 0)) \times (7 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((4^{5-3}) \times 8)}{2^{9-07+6}}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((5 + 3) \times 8))}{2 \times ((9 \times (07)) + 6)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times (5 + (3 \times 8))}{290 \times (7 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((4^{5-3}) - 8)}{2 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (5 - (3 - 8)))}{2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times (5 + (3 + 8))}{(2 \times (90 - 7)) - 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 + (5 + 3)) \times 8)}{2 \times ((9 - (-07)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (5 \times (3 + 8)))}{(2 \times (9 \times (07))) - 6}$
$:= \frac{(14 \times (5 \times 3)) + 8}{(2^9 + 0) - 76}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (5 - (3 + 8)))}{2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (5 \times 38))}{(2 - (9 \times (-07))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(14 \times 5) + (3 \times 8)}{(2 \times (90 + 7)) - 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (5 + (3 - 8)))}{2^{9+0 \times 7-6}}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (5 + (3 + 8)))}{29 - (0 - (7 + 6))}$
$:= \frac{(14 \times 5) + 38}{(29 - (-07)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 3) - 8))}{2 - (9 \times ((0 \times 7) - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (5 + 38))}{2 \times (90 - (7 \times 6))}$
$:= \frac{1 - ((4 - (5 \times 3)) \times 8)}{2 \times (90 - (7 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (5 + (3 + 8)))}{2 \times ((9 + (-07))^6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (53 + 8))}{(2 \times (9 \times (07))) + 6}$
$:= \frac{1 - ((4 + 5) \times (3 - 8))}{2 + (90 \times (7 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 - (3 - 8)))}{2 \times (90 - 76)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (45 - (3 - 8))}{2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 \times 6)))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((5 - 3)^8))}{2^{9+0 \times 7} - 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 \times (3 \times 8)))}{290 - (7 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (45 + (3 + 8))}{2 \times ((9 \times (07)) - 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (5 - (3 - 8)))}{2 + ((9 + (-07)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 + (3 \times 8)))}{2 + ((9 + (-07))^6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (45 + 38)}{2 + (90 + 76)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (5 \times (3 + 8)))}{(2 \times 90) - 76}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 + 38))}{(2 \times (9 - 0)) + 76}$	$:= \frac{1 + 4538}{2 + 9076}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (5 + (3 + 8)))}{(2 \times (9 - (-07))) - 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (53 - 8))}{2 + ((9 - (-07)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{14 + 5^3 + 8}{-2 + 9) \times 07 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 \times 8)))}{2 \times (90 - (7 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{1^{4538}}{2 - (9 \times (0 \times 76))}$	$:= \frac{14 + 53 + 8}{2 \times 9 + 07) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 + 8)))}{2 + (90 - (7 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4^{5-3}) - 8)}{2 \times (9 - (0 \times 76))}$	$:= \frac{145 + 38}{290 + 76}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (5 - (3 + 8)))}{2 - (9 + (0 - (7 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8))}{(2 \times (90 + 7)) + 6}$	$:= \frac{145 - 38}{290 - 76}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (5 \times (3 - 8)))}{2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + 5) \times 38)}{2 - (9 \times (0 - 76))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14538}{72690} := \frac{((1 + (4 + 5))^3) + 8}{7 \times ((2 + 6) \times 90)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (5 - 38))}{(2 \times (9 - 0)) + (7 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 - 5) \times (3 - 8))}{2 + (9 - (0 - (7 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{((1 - 4) \times (5 - 3)) + 8}{7 + ((2 \times 6) - (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((4 + 5) \times 3) - 8)}{(2 \times (9 - (-07))) + 6}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (5 + (3 - 8)))}{2 + (9 + (0 - (7 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (5 - (3 - 8)))}{7 \times (2 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 - (5 - 3))^8)}{2^{9+0 \times 76}}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times (5 + (3 \times 8)))}{2 \times (9 \times (0 + (7 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (5 + (3 + 8)))}{(7 \times (2 + 6)) + (9 - 0)}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (53 - 8))}{7 \times (2 \times (6 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 \times 8)))}{7 \times ((2^6) - (9 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 + (5 - (3 \times 8)))}{7 + ((2^6) + (9 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 + (5 \times (3 - 8)))}{7 \times 2 + (6 + 90)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + (5 + 3)) \times 8)}{(7 - 2) \times (6 + 90)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + 5) \times (3 \times 8))}{72 \times (6 + (9 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8))}{((7^2) + 6) \times (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 38)}{(7 + (2 \times 6)) \times 90} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 - (5 - (3 \times 8)))}{7 + (2 \times (6 \times (9 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 - (5 \times (3 - 8)))}{7 + (2 \times (69 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 - (5 + (3 - 8)))}{7 - (2 - (6 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + ((5 \times 3) + 8))}{(7 + (2 + 6)) \times (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (53 - 8))}{7 \times (26 + (9 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (((4 + 5) \times 3) + 8)}{(7 \times 2 + 6) \times (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 8)}{7 - ((2 \times 6) - 90)} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((4^{5-3}) - 8)}{((7 + 2) \times 6) - (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((45 \times 3) + 8)}{((7 \times 2) - 6) \times 90} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 - (5 - (3 \times 8)))}{((7 - 2) \times 6) + 90} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + ((5 + 3) \times 8))}{(7 - 2) \times (69 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 - (3 - 8)))}{(7 \times (2 \times 6)) - (9 - 0)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 + (3 + 8)))}{7 + (2 + (6 + 90))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (45 - (3 + 8))}{7 - (2 \times (6 - 90))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (45 + (3 + 8))}{((7^2) \times 6) - (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{14 + ((5^3) + 8)}{726 + (9 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{14 + ((5 - 3)^8)}{(7 + (2 + 6)) \times 90} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{39728} := \frac{1^4 \times 560}{(3 \times 9 \times 7 + 2) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 + 60}{3 \times (9 \times 7 - 2) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{39872} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 + 60}{(3 + 9) \times (8 + 7) - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{73892} := \frac{1 + 45 - 6 + 0}{7 \times (3 + 8 + 9 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 + 60}{7 \times (38 - 9) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}{7 \times (3 - 8 + 92)} \\
 := \frac{(1^4 + 5) \times 60}{7 \times 3 \times (89 - 2)} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14573}{82069} := \frac{1^4 \times (5 \times 7 + 3)}{8 \times 20 + 6 \times 9} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 4 - 5 + 7^3}{(8 + 206) \times 9} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{23976} := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 8 + 0}{2 + 3 + 9 \times 7 + 6} \\
 := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 + 80}{2^3 \times 9 + 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{26973} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{2 - 6 \times (9 - 7 \times 3)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + 4 - 5 + 80}{2 \times 69 + 7 + 3} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 + 80}{2 - 6 + 9 \times 7 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{67392} := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 8 + 0}{67 \times 3 + 9 - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + 4 + 580}{(6 + 7 + 39)^2} \\
 := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 80}{(6 + 7) \times (3 + 9)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{73629} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{7 + 3 \times 62 + 9} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 80}{7 + 3629} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{73692} := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 80}{7^3 \times 6 - 9 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{97362} := \frac{1 + 4 + 5 + 80}{9 \times (73 - 6) - 2} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14586}{39270} := \frac{1^4 + 5^{8-6}}{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1^4 \times (58 - 6)}{3 + 9 + 2^7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 + 4^{5-8+6}}{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{145 - 8 + 6}{392 - 7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 4) \times (58 - 6)}{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 70} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (5 + 86)}{(3 + 9 + 2) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14586}{72930} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 + 8))) \times 6}{7 + (293 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(1^4) \times ((5^8) + 6)}{((7 - 2)^9) + 30} \\
 := \frac{(1^4) \times ((5^8) - 6)}{((7 - 2)^9) - 30} \\
 := \frac{(1^4) \times (5 \times (8 \times 6))}{((7^2) - 9) \times 30}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(1^4) \times (5^{8-6})}{((7 \times 2) - 9)^3 + 0} \\
 := \frac{(1^4) \times (58 \times 6)}{((7^2) + 9) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 \times 8))) \times 6}{(7 - 2) \times (9 \times 30)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 + 8))) \times 6}{(7 + (2 + 9)) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (4 + 58)) \times 6}{(72 - 9) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 4) \times ((5^8) \times 6)}{((7 - 2)^9) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 4) \times (5 - (8 \times 6))}{(72 \times 9) - (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 4) \times (5 - (8 + 6))}{(7 - 2) \times (9 \times (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((4 - (5 + 8)) \times 6)}{7 - (2 - (9 \times 30))} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((4 - 5) \times (8 - 6))}{7 + (2 + (9 - (3 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (5 + (8 + 6)))}{(7 \times (2 + 9)) + (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (5 + (8 - 6)))}{7 \times 2 + (9 - (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 + (5 - (8 + 6)))}{7 + (2 - (9 - 30))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (5 - (8 - 6)))}{72 - (9 + (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (8 - 6)))}{(7 \times 29) - (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 - (8 - 6)))}{(7 \times 2) - (9 - 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 \times (8 - 6)))}{(7^2) - (9 - 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (5 + (8 - 6)))}{7 + ((2 \times 9) + 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (45 + (8 \times 6))}{(7 - 2) \times (93 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 - (5 - (8 - 6)))}{(7^2) - (9 + 30)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + (4 + ((5 \times 8) - 6))}{(7 - 2) \times (9 + 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 - (8 - 6)))}{7 + ((2 + 9) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 \times (8 - 6)))}{(7 + (2 \times 9)) \times (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5^{8-6}))}{((7 \times 2) - 9) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 + (8 + 6)))}{((7^2) - 9) \times (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{14 + (5 - (8 - 6))}{7 + (2 \times (9 + 30))} \\
 := \frac{14 + (5 \times (8 + 6))}{(7 - (2 - 9)) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{14 + (5 + (8 + 6))}{72 + (93 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{14 + (5 + (8 - 6))}{7 \times ((2 \times 9) - (3 - 0))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 - ((4 - (6 - 0)) \times 7)}{3 + (89 - 52)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 + (6 \times (-07)))}{3 + (8 + (95 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (6 - (0 \times 7)))}{(3 \times (8 + (9 + 5))) - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 + (-07)))}{(3 + (8 - 9))^{5-2}} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (60 - 7))}{((3 + 8) \times (9 + 5)) - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 - (6 + (-07)))}{(3 - ((8 - 9) \times 5)) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (6 - (-07)))}{3 \times (8 \times (9 - (5 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (4 + (60 + 7))}{3 \times (8^{9-5-2})} \\
 := \frac{1 + (46 - (-07))}{3 \times (8 \times (9 - (5 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{14 + (6 - (-07))}{3 + (8 + (9 + 52))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14592}{76038} := \frac{(1 + 4 + 59) \times 2}{7 + 60 \times (3 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14592}{76380} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (5 + 9 + 2)}{7^{6-3} - 8 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14596}{23780} := \frac{1 - 4 + 5 \times 9 \times 6}{(2 + 3) \times (7 + 80)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14607}{38952} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 - 0))) \times 7}{3 - (8 - (9 + 52))} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 - 0)))^7}{(3^8) - (9^{5-2})} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (4 - 60)) \times 7}{38 \times ((9 + 5) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{(1^4) \times (6 \times (07))}{(3 + (8 + (9 \times 5))) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 4) \times (6 - (0 \times 7))}{(3 - (8 - (9 \times 5))) \times 2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14625}{39078} := \frac{1 + 4 \times (6 + 25)}{390 - 7 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14625}{39780} := \frac{1 + 4 + (6 - 2) \times 5}{3 + 9 + 7 \times 8 + 0} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times 4 + 6) \times 2 \times 5}{(3 \times 9 + 7) \times 8 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14628}{39750} := \frac{(1 \times 4 + 6)^2 - 8}{(3 + 9 - 7) \times 50} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 4 \times 6 - 2) \times 8}{(3 + 97) \times 5 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14630}{78925} := \frac{14 - 6 + 30}{(7 + (8 + 9) \times 2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{14 \times 6 + 30}{7 + 8 \times (9^2 - 5)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14630}{92785} := \frac{1 \times 46 + 30}{92 + 78 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((4 + 6) \times 5) + 8)}{(7 + 3) \times (29 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (46 + (5 + 8))}{7 + (3 + 290)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14637}{89250} := \frac{1 - 4 + 6 \times 3 \times 7}{(8 + 9 - 2) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times 6) + (5 - 8))}{7 \times ((3 \times 2) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{14 \times (6 - (5 - 8))}{7 \times ((3 - 2) \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 4 \times 6) \times 3 + 7}{(8 + 92) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 + 6) \times 58)}{(7 + 3) \times 290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14673}{80592} := \frac{1 - 4 + 673}{8 \times 05 \times 92}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - ((6 - 5)^8))}{7 - (3 - (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14658}{73290} := \frac{(1^4 + 6) \times (5^8)}{7 \times ((3 + 2)^9 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - (5 \times 8)))}{7 + (3 + (2 \times 90))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14679}{35280} := \frac{1 + 4 \times (67 - 9)}{35 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + (4 \times 6)) \times 5) + 8}{7 \times (3 + (2 + 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - (5 + 8)))}{73 - (2 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14679}{50328} := \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{(5 - (0 - (3 - 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + (4 + 6)) \times 5) + 8}{7 \times ((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 \times (5 - 8)))}{(7 + 3) \times (2 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((4 + 6) \times (7 - 9))}{((5 - (-03))^2) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{((14 + 6) \times 5) + 8}{(7 - (3 - 2)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (6 - (5 - 8)))}{(7 - (3 + 2)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - 79))}{5 \times ((03 \times (2 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 \times 5))) \times 8}{(7 + 3 + 2) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (6 + (5 \times 8)))}{(7 + 3) \times (2 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - 79))}{5 - (0 - (3 + (2^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1^4 + (6 - (5 - 8))}{(7 \times 3) + (29 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 - (5 - 8)))}{7 - (32 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (7 + 9)))}{5 - (0 - (3 + (2 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (6 + 5))) \times 8}{(7 + 3) \times (2 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (46 + (5 + 8))}{7 + (32 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 \times (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{(5 \times (032)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 46) \times (5 - 8)}{(73 + 2) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((4 - (6 - 5)) \times 8)}{(7 \times (3 + 2)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times ((6 + 7) \times 9))}{(50 \times 32) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((4 - 6) \times 58)}{73 + (2^9 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (6 + (5 - 8)))}{7 - ((3 \times 2) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14685}{29370} := \frac{((1 - (4 - 6)) \times 8) - 5}{2 - (9 \times (3 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 - (5 - 8)))}{7 + (32 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times ((6 - 5) \times 8))}{73 + (2 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + 8))) \times 5}{(2 + 9) \times (3 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8)))}{(7 \times 32) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4^{6-5-8})}{7 + ((3^2) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{468}) \times 5}{2 \times (9 + (3 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 + (5 + 8)))}{73 - (2 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4^{6+5-8})}{(7^3) - (2 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^4) \times (6 \times (8 - 5))}{2 + ((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (65 + 8))}{(7^3) - (2 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 - (5 - 8)))}{7 \times (3 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^4) \times (6 + (8 \times 5))}{2 + (9 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (5 \times 8)))}{(73 \times 2) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (5 \times 8)))}{(7^3) + (2 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^4 + (6 + (8 + 5))}{2 \times ((9 \times 3) - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (46 \times (5 - 8))}{((7^3) \times 2) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (5 - 8)))}{7 + (3 \times (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + 6)) \times (8 + 5)}{293 - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((4 \times 6) + 5) \times 8)}{(7 - 3) \times 290}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (46 + (5 \times 8))}{(7^3) + (2 + 90)}$$

$:= \frac{(14 \times 6) - (8 + 5)}{(2^9) - 370}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (46 + (8 - 5))}{(2 + (9 + 3)) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{14 + (6 \times (8 \times 5))}{(2^9) + (3 - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(14 \times 6) + (8 + 5)}{2 \times ((9 \times 3) + 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 \times (6 + 8)) + 5)}{(2 \times (9 \times 3)) + 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14685}{79032} := \frac{(1 + 4 + 6) \times 8 \times 5}{790 \times 3 - 2}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((6 \times 8) - 5))}{(29 \times 3) - (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 \times 6) + (8 - 5))}{(2 + (9 - 3)) \times (7 - 0)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 \times (8 - 5)))}{2 - (9 - (37 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (6 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(2^9) + (3 + (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14695}{38207} := \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (9 + 5)))}{3 + (8 + (2 - (0 \times 7)))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 + (8 \times 5)))}{2 + ((9 + 3) \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 5)}{(29 - 3) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}{3 + ((8 \times (2 - 0)) + 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (6 + (8 + 5)))}{2^{9+3-7+0}}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (6 - 8))^5)}{2 - (9 - (3 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (9 - 5)))}{3 \times (8 - (2 + (-07)))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 \times ((6 - 8) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 - 3)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + 68) \times 5)}{(2^9) + (3 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - ((6 - 9) \times 5))}{38 - (2 \times (-07))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (8 + 5)))}{29 - (3 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (6 - (8 \times 5)))}{2 + (9 - (3 - 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (9 + 5)))}{38 + (20 + 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - 85))}{2 \times (9 - (3 - 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (6 - 85))}{2 \times ((9 + 3) \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 5)}{(3 \times (8 + 20)) + 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((4 \times 6) - 8)^5)}{(2 + (9 - 3))^7 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times (6 - (8 - 5)))}{2 \times (9 - (3 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 + (9 \times 5)))}{(3 + 8) \times (20 - 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 5)}{2 - (9 + (3 - 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((6 \times 8) + 5))}{(2 \times 93) - 70}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + 9))) \times 5}{3 + ((8 \times 20) - 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 5)}{2 \times (9 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((6 \times 8) - 5))}{29 - (3 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 \times 6) + (9 \times 5))}{((3 \times 8) + (2 - 0)) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - (8 + 5)))}{2 + ((9 \times 3) - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 \times (8 - 5)))}{2 \times (93 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 \times 6) + 95)}{3 \times (8 \times (20 - 7))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((6 + 8) \times 5))}{(2 + (9 - 3)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (8 \times 5)))}{2 + (93 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (46 - 9)) \times 5}{38 \times (20 - 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + ((6 \times 8) - 5))}{(2 \times (9 + 3)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (8 + 5)))}{2 + (9 + (37 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 \times 9))) \times 5}{(38 \times 20) + 7}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 - (8 - 5)))}{2 - (9 - (3 \times (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (8 - 5)))}{(2 - 9) \times (3 - (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14697}{32085} := \frac{14 - 6 + 9 \times 7}{(3 + 20 + 8) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 \times (8 + 5)))}{2 \times (9 + (3 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (46 - (8 + 5))}{2 \times ((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0))}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 \times (8 - 5)))}{2 + ((9 - 3) \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (46 - (8 - 5))}{2 + (93 - (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14703}{59826} := \frac{(1 + 4 \times 7) \times 03}{(5 + 9 \times (8 - 2)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (68 - 5))}{(2^9-3) + 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + 4685}{2 + 9370}$	$:= \frac{1 + 4 \times 70 \times 3}{59 \times (8^2 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (46 + (8 \times 5))}{2 \times (93 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{14 \times (6 - (8 - 5))}{2 + (9 + (3 + 70))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14703}{68952} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 7 + 0 \times 3}{68 \times (9 - 5 - 2)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1+4 \times 7) \times 03}{68 \times (9-5+2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1+4+7^{03}}{6 \times 8 \times (9+5^2)} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{23598} &:= \frac{1^4+7 \times 06}{2 \times 35-9+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{83592} &:= \frac{1-(4-7) \times 06}{8+3+5+92} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+4) \times (70+6)}{8 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{98325} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 70-6}{(9+83) \times 25} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14725}{80693} &:= \frac{1 \times 4-7 \times (2-5)}{80+6 \times 9+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14736}{90258} &:= \frac{1 \times 4+7+3-6}{9+02^5+8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (7+3-6)}{9 \times 02 \times 5+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14739}{50286} &:= \frac{1 \times 4+7-3+9}{5 \times 02+8 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+47+3) \times 9}{(5+02^8) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14756}{20398} &:= \frac{1+4+7+56}{2 \times (039+8)} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{23985} &:= \frac{(1-(4-7)) \times (6-0)}{(2^3)-(9-(8 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{14+(7 \times (6-0))}{(2 \times 39)+(8+5)} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(4-(7+60))}{2 \times (3+(9+(8 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1+(4+(7+60))}{((2+(3+9)) \times 8)+5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (4+(76-0))}{((2+3) \times 9)+85} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{39852} &:= \frac{1-(4-(7+(6-0)))}{3-(9-(8+(5^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1-(4+(7-60))}{3 \times (9 \times (8-(5-2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (4+(76-0))}{(3+9) \times (8+(5 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{14+(76-0)}{3 \times (9 \times ((8-5)^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-(4-7)) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times (8 \times (5-2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^4)^7) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times ((8-5) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+4) \times (76-0)}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 \times 5)-2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(14-7) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 \times 5)+2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4+7) \times 60}{(3 \times (9+(8-5)))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{52398} &:= \frac{1^{47} \times 60}{5 \times (2+39)+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{98523} &:= \frac{1 \times 4+76+0}{(9+(8+5)^2) \times 3} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14796}{30825} &:= \frac{(((1+4) \times 7)+9) \times 6}{(30-8) \times 25} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4+7) \times (9 \times 6)}{30 \times ((8-2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-((4-7) \times 9)) \times 6}{30+((8^2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-(4-7)) \times (9 \times 6)}{30 \times (8+(2+5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-(4-79)) \times 6}{(30+8) \times 25} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4)-(7-(9 \times 6))}{(30-(8+2)) \times 5} \\
 & \text{---} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+(4+7)) \times 96}{30 \times (8 \times (2 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+47) \times (9+6)}{30 \times ((8+2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+47) \times 96}{30 \times ((8^2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+479) \times 6}{30 \times (8 \times 25)} \\
 &:= \frac{(14-(7-9)) \times 6}{(30+(8+2)) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(14+(7-9)) \times 6}{3 \times (0+((8+2) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((4-(7-9)) \times 6)}{3 \times ((0 \times 8)+25)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((4+(7+9)) \times 6)}{(30 \times 8)+(2 \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (4-(7-(9+6)))}{(3 \times (0+(8+2))) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((7 \times 9)-6))}{(30 \times (8 \times 2)) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (7 \times (9-6)))}{(30 \times (8-2)) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{147-(9+6)}{(3-(-08)) \times 25} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14796}{32058} &:= \frac{1 \times (4-(7-(9+6)))}{3+(20-(5-8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1-(4-7)) \times 9)-6}{(3+(2-0)) \times (5+8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((4-(7-9)) \times 6)}{3 \times (2 \times ((05+8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4)-(7-(9 \times 6))}{(3-(2 \times (-05))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1+(4+(7+96))}{3 \times (20+58)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-(4 \times (7-9))) \times 6}{(3^2+0) \times (5+8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1-(4-(7 \times 9))) \times 6}{3 \times (20 \times (5+8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4+7) \times 96}{(3+205) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{479}) \times 6}{(3 \times (2 - (-05))) - 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14798}{20536} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - 7 + 9) \times 8}{2^{05} + 36} \\ &:= \frac{14 \times 7 \times (9 - 8)}{20 \times 5 + 36} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{39762} &:= \frac{(-1^4 + 8) \times 05}{39 - 7 + 62} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times 4 + 80) \times 5}{3 \times (9 \times 7 \times 6 - 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{62937} := \frac{(1 + 48) \times 05}{62 + 937}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{79632} := \frac{(1 + 48) \times 05}{79 \times (6 \times 3 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{92637} := \frac{(1 + 48) \times 05}{(9 + 2^6) \times 3 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{92736} := \frac{(-1 + 48) \times 05}{92 \times (7 + 3 + 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14806}{27593} &:= \frac{14 + 8 + 0 \times 6}{2 + 7 + 5 + 9 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(-1 + 4 + 8) \times 06}{2 \times 75 - 9 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{148 + 06}{275 + 9 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 80 \times 6}{2 + 75 \times (9 + 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14820}{35796} := \frac{(1 + 4 + 8) \times 20}{3 + 5^{7-9+6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{76950} := \frac{(1 - 4 + 8^2) \times 3}{(7 - 6) \times 950}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{79056} &:= \frac{1 - (4 + (8 - 23))}{(7 \times (9 - 0)) - (5 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 - 2) \times 3))}{79 + (0 - (5 - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (2 + 3)))}{(7 + (9 - (0 \times 5))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (2^3)))}{(7 - 9) \times (0 - 56)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (4 \times (8 \times (2 - 3)))}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5 +)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (82 + 3))}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (2 \times 3)))}{7 + (9 - (0 \times 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + 4)^{8-2}) \times 3}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5^6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{79605} := \frac{1 + 48 + 2 + 3}{(7 - 9 + 60) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{96075} := \frac{14 + 8^2 + 3}{(9 + 6) \times 07 \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14826}{70953} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8 + 2 - 6}{70 + (9 - 5)^3} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 48) \times 2 \times 6}{70 + (9 + 5)^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14835}{20769} &:= \frac{(((1 - (4 - 8))^3) + 5)}{((2^{07}) + (6 \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^4 + 8) \times (3 \times 5))}{((20 + (7 - 6)) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 4) \times (8 + (3 \times 5)))}{((2 \times (0 + 76)) + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + 35)))}{(2 - ((0 \times 7) - (6 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (83 + 5)))}{(2 - (0 - ((7 + 6) \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (83 - 5)))}{(20 + (76 + 9))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (8 - 3)) \times 5))}{(2 - (0 - (7 + (6 \times 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (8 \times (3 - 5))))}{(20 - (7 - (6 + 9)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 \times 8) - (3 - 5)))}{(2 + (0 - (7 - (6 \times 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((48 \times 3) + 5))}{(2 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 + 9))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (3 + 5))))}{((2 \times (0 - (7 - 6))) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 + (3 - 5))))}{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 6))) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + ((8 - 3) \times 5)))}{(2 \times (0 - (7 \times (6 - 9))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 - (3 - 5))))}{((2 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14835}{29670} := \frac{(1^4 + 8) \times (3^5)}{2 \times ((9 - 6)^7 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 + 4) \times 8) + (3 - 5)}{(2 \times (9 - 6)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - 4) \times 8) + (3^5)}{(2 \times 9) + (6 \times 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - 8)) \times 35}{(2 + (9 - 6)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^4) \times ((8 \times 3) - 5)}{(2 \times (9 \times 6)) - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^4) \times (8 \times 35)}{(2^{9-6}) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1^4 + (83 + 5)}{2 \times (96 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 - 3))) \times 5}{2 \times ((9 + 6) \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + 3)))^5}{(2^{9-6})^7 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 - 3))) \times 5}{(2 \times (9 + 6)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(14 + (8 \times 3)) \times 5}{2 + (9 \times (6 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(14 - 8) \times 35}{2 \times ((9 - 6) \times 70)}$$

$:= \frac{1 - ((4 - (8 - 3)) \times 5)}{2 + (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (8 + 3)) \times 5)}{2 \times (9 + (67 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{148 - 35}{296 - 70}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 + 3) \times 5))}{(29 \times 6) - 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (8 - 3)) \times 5)}{(2^9) - (6 \times 70)}$	<hr style="width: 100%;"/>
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 - 3) \times 5))}{2 \times (9 + (6 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 - 8) \times (3 - 5))}{2 - ((9 \times 6) - 70)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{32967} := \frac{(1 - 4 + 8) \times 50}{3 \times (2 \times 96 - 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times (3 \times 5)))}{2 \times (9 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (3 \times 5)))}{2 + (9 + (6 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1^{48} \times 50}{3 \times (2 \times (9 + 6) + 7)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times (3 + 5)))}{(2 \times 96) - 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (3 + 5)))}{2 + (9 + (6 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^4 + 8) \times 50}{32 + 967}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times 35))}{(2^9) + (6 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 \times (3 - 5)))}{2 \times ((9 - 6) \times (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{76329} := \frac{1^{48} \times 50}{7 \times (6 + 32) - 9}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 + (3 - 5)))}{2 - (9 - (6 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times (8 - (3 - 5)))}{(2 \times 9) - (6 - 70)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{76923} := \frac{(14 - 8) \times 50}{7 \times ((6 + 9)^2 - 3)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (83 + 5))}{2 \times (9 + (6 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((8 - 3) \times 5))}{2 - (9 - (67 - 0))}$	<hr style="width: 100%;"/>
$:= \frac{1 - (48 - (3^5))}{(2 + (9 \times 6)) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 - (3 - 5)))}{29 - (6 - (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14853}{29706} := \frac{((1 + 4)^{8-5}) + 3}{2^{9-7+06}}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times (8 + 3)) - 5)}{2 + (9 + (67 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (3 \times 5)))}{(2^{9-6}) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + 5))) \times 3}{(2 \times 9) - (7 \times (-06))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times 83) + 5)}{2 + (96 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + 35))}{29 + (67 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (4 - 8)) \times (5 \times 3)}{((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 - 8) \times (3 - 5))}{2 \times (9 + (6 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (83 \times 5))}{((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1^4 \times 8^{5+3}}{2 \times ((9 + (7 - 0))^6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 - (3 - 5)))}{2 + (96 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + 835)}{((2 \times 9) + 6) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + 8) \times 5)) \times 3}{(2 - (9 \times 7)) \times (-06)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 \times (3 \times 5)))}{2 \times ((9 \times 6) + 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (48 - (3 - 5))}{2 \times (9 + (6 \times (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - 5)))^3}{2 \times (9 - (7 + (-06)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 \times (3 + 5)))}{((2 + 9) \times 6) + 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (48 + 35)}{2 + (96 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 \times 5))) \times 3}{2 + (970 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 + (3 - 5)))}{2 \times (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 4835}{2 + 9670}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times 8)) \times (5 + 3)}{((2 \times 9) + 70) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 + 35))}{2 \times ((9 \times 6) - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{14 \times (8 + (3 + 5))}{(2^9) + (6 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4^{8-5})) \times 3}{(2 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (48 + (3 \times 5))}{2 + ((9 \times 6) + 70)}$	$:= \frac{14 + (8 \times 35)}{(2^9) + (6 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + 5))) \times 3}{(2 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + (((4 + 8) \times 3) + 5)}{((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{14 + (83 \times 5)}{2 \times (9 + (6 \times 70))}$	$:= \frac{(14 + 85) \times 3}{(2 + (97 - 0)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((4 \times (8 - 3)) + 5)}{2 \times (96 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{148 + 35}{296 + 70}$	$:= \frac{1 - (((4 - 8) \times 5) + 3)}{29 + (7 - (0 \times 6))}$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 := \frac{1 - ((4 \times 8) - (5^3))}{(2 \times (97 - 0)) - 6} & := \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 + (5 - 3)))}{29 - (7 + (-06))} & := \frac{1 + (48 \times (5 - 3))}{2 \times (97 - (0 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 - 5) \times 3))}{2 + (9 + (7 + (-06)))} & := \frac{1 \times (48 - (5 \times 3))}{2 + ((9 - (7 - 0))^6)} & := \frac{1 + (48 + (5 + 3))}{2 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (8 - (5 - 3)))}{2 - (9 - (7 - (-06)))} & := \frac{1 \times (48 - (5 - 3))}{(2^9) - (70 \times 6)} & := \frac{1 + (485 + 3)}{2 + (970 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times (5 \times 3)))}{2 \times (9 \times (7 - (-06)))} & := \frac{1 \times (48 \times (5 - 3))}{2 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6)} & := \frac{1 + 4853}{2 + 9706} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 6} & := \frac{1 \times (48 + (5 \times 3))}{2 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 6)))} & := \frac{14 \times ((8 - 5)^3)}{2 \times (9 \times (7 \times (06)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (8 + (5 - 3)))}{2 + ((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 6)} & := \frac{1^{4853}}{2 - (9 \times (7 \times (0 \times 6)))} & := \frac{14 \times (8 \times (5 - 3))}{(2^9) - (70 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (4 - (85 + 3))}{2 \times (9 + (70 + 6))} & := \frac{1 + (((4 \times 8) - 5) \times 3)}{(2 \times (9 + 70)) + 6} & := \frac{14 + (8 + (5^3))}{(2 - 9) \times (7 \times (-06))} \\
 = \frac{1 - (4 + (8 - 53))}{(2 - (9 + 7)) \times (-06)} & := \frac{1 + ((4 - (8 - 5))^3)}{2^{9-7+0 \times 6}} & := \frac{1485 + 3}{2970 + 6} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 \times (8 - 5)) - 3)}{2 \times 9^{7-06}} & := \frac{1 + ((4 \times (8 - 5)) + 3)}{2 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 6)))} & := \frac{1485 - 3}{2970 - 6} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 \times 85) + 3)}{2 + (9 \times (70 + 6))} & := \frac{1 + ((4 + (8 - 5)) \times 3)}{2 \times (9 + (7 - (-06)))} & \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + (8 + 5)) \times 3)}{2 \times (9 - (7 \times (-06)))} & := \frac{1 + ((48 \times 5) - 3)}{2 + ((9 + 70) \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{14865}{29730} := \frac{((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 6) - 5}{2 + ((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((4 + 8) \times 53)}{2 \times ((9 \times 70) + 6)} & := \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (5 \times 3)))}{2 + (9 + (7 - (-06)))} & := \frac{((14 + 8) \times 6) - 5}{2 \times (97 + 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((48 \times 5) + 3)}{(2 + (9 + 70)) \times 6} & := \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (5 + 3)))}{2 + (9 - (7 + (-06)))} & := \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + 6))) \times 5}{(2 + 9) \times (7 + (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 - (8 - 53))}{2 + ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6)} & := \frac{1 + (4 \times (8 + (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times 9) + (70 - 6)} & := \frac{(1 - (4 - 8)) \times (6 \times 5)}{297 + (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 5)^3))}{(29 + (7 - 0)) \times 6} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 - (5 - 3)))}{29 - (7 - (0 \times 6))} & := \frac{1^4 + (8 \times (6 \times 5))}{2 + ((9 + 7) \times 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (5 - 3)))}{2 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^6)} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 \times (5 - 3)))}{29 + (7 - (-06))} & := \frac{1^4 + (8 + (6^5))}{((2^9) + 7) \times 30} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (8^{5-3}))}{2^9 \times (7 - 06)} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 \times 53))}{2 \times (9 + (70 \times 6))} & := \frac{(1 + ((4 \times 8) - 6))^5}{2 \times ((9^7) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (85 + 3))}{(2 + 9) \times (70 - 6)} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8^{5-3}))}{2 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 6)} & := \frac{(14 \times 8) - (6 \times 5)}{2 \times (9 + (73 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + ((8 \times 5) + 3))}{(2 \times 9) + (70 + 6)} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (5 - 3)))}{29 + (7 + (-06))} & := \frac{(14 \times 8) + 65}{2 + (9 + (7^3 + 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 - (5 - 3)))}{2 \times (9 + (7 + (-06)))} & := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + 53))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))) + 6} & := \frac{(14 - 8) \times (6 + 5)}{2 \times ((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0))}
 \end{array}$$

$:= \frac{1 - ((4 - (8 + 6)) \times 5)}{2 + (97 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 4^{8-6+5}}{(2 \times (9 + 7))^3 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 + (48 + 6 + 5)}{2 \times ((9 - 7) \times 30)}$
$:= \frac{1 - ((4 \times 8) - 65)}{2 + ((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 - (6 - 5)))}{(2 \times 9) + (7 - (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (48 + 65)}{(2 \times 9) + (7 \times 30)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 + 6) \times 5))}{2 \times (97 - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (8 + (6 \times 5)))}{2 + (9 + (73 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 4865}{2 + 9730}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 - (6 - 5)))}{2 + ((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1^{4865}}{(2 \times (9 + 7)) - 30}$	$:= \frac{14 - (8 - (6 + 5))}{2 + (9 - (7 - 30))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 \times (6 - 5)))}{2 \times (9 - (7 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4^{8-6}) + 5)}{(2 + 9) \times (7 - (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{14 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))}{(2 \times 97) + 30}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 + 6 + 5))}{2^{9-7+3+0}}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (8 \times 6)) \times 5)}{(2^9) + (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{14 + ((8 - 6)^5)}{2 \times (9 + (7 + 30))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 - (8 + 6 - 5))}{2 \times ((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5)}{2 + ((9 - 7) \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{14 + (8 \times (6 \times 5))}{(2^9) - (7 - (3 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (8 - (6 \times 5)))}{2 + (9 \times (7 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((4 + 8) \times (6 \times 5))}{(2^9) + (7 \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{148 - (6 - 5)}{297 - (3 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (4 + (8 - 65))}{(29 + 7) \times (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (6 \times 5)))}{(2 + (9 + 7)) \times (3 - 0)}$	
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 \times (8 - 6)) - 5)}{29 + (7 - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (6 + 5)))}{2 - (9 + (7 - 30))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14896}{23750} := \frac{(1 + 48) \times 96}{2 \times 3750}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 + (8 + 6)) \times 5)}{2 \times (9 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5)))}{2 - (9 - (73 - 0))}$	
$:= \frac{1 \times ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5)}{2 \times (9 + (7 \times (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 \times (8 + 6 - 5))}{((2 + 9) \times 7) - (3 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14928}{53760} := \frac{1 + 4 + 928}{(5 + 3) \times 7 \times 60}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((48 + 6) \times 5)}{(2 + (9 + 7)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((8 \times 6) + 5))}{29 \times (7 - (3 - 0))}$	
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (8 - (6 \times 5)))}{29 - (7 - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5))}{2 + (97 - (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14935}{26780} := \frac{1 + 4 \times (9 + 3 - 5)}{2 - 6 + 7 \times 8 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (8 - (6 + 5)))}{2 - (9 - (7 \times (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5))}{2 - (9 - (7 + 30))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 49 + 3 + 5}{26 + 78 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 5))}{((2 + 9) \times 7) + (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 \times (6 + 5)))}{2 \times ((9 \times 7) + 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (4 - 9 \times 3) \times 5}{2 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6)^5))}{2^{9-7^3} + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 \times (6 - 5)))}{2 \times (9 + (7 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 9 \times 35}{2 \times 6 + 7 \times 80}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (6 + 5)))}{2 \times (9 + (7^3 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + 6 + 5))}{2 + (9 + (7 + 30))}$	
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5)))}{2 \times (9 - (7 - 30))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + 6 - 5))}{(2 \times 9) + (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14937}{85026} := \frac{1 + 49 - 37}{8 \times 5 \times 02 - 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (8 + 6 - 5))}{2 \times (9 \times (7 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + 65))}{(2 \times (9 \times 7)) + 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9 - 3 + 7)}{8 + (50 - 2) \times 6}$

$$:= \frac{1+4+93-7}{8^{5-02}+6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{27306} &:= \frac{1-4+98-5}{2^7+30+6} \\ &:= \frac{(1+49) \times 8+5}{2+7+3^{06}} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 50+2) \times 8}{4 \times (7^3-9-6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14952}{80367} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-5-2)}{-8 \times 03+67} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9+5+2)}{8 \times (036+7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{32076} &:= \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{320+76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{36720} &:= \frac{(1+4 \times 9) \times (8-5)}{36 \times 7+20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15029}{84637} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 02+9}{(8 \times 4+6) \times 3-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{20358} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-7)^6}{2 \times 03 \times 58}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{37260} := \frac{(1+4 \times 9) \times (8-5)}{3 \times 72+60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{29376} := \frac{1+50 \times 4+8}{2 \times (9 \times 3+7) \times 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{30528} &:= \frac{1 \times 4+9+7+6}{3+05 \times (2+8)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (97-6)}{30 \times 5^2-8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{60273} := \frac{1+49+85}{60 \times (2+7)+3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{37962} := \frac{1-5+048}{3 \times (7+(9+6) \times 2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{62370} &:= \frac{1+49 \times (8-5)}{623-7+0} \\ &:= \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{(6+2+3) \times 70} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(15-04) \times 8}{37 \times (9-6) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1+50+4) \times 8}{37 \times (9+6) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{35802} := \frac{1-4-9+76}{3-(5-80) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{63270} := \frac{(1-4+9) \times (8-5)}{6+(3-2) \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{39672} := \frac{15+04-8}{3 \times 9-(6-7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{53280} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (97-6)}{5 \times (3+2^8)+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9+8)-5}{(6+32) \times 7+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1^5+04 \times 8}{3 \times (9+6+7 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{53820} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-7+6)}{5^3-8-2+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 9 \times (8-5)}{6 \times (3 \times 2+70)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+50-4+8}{(3 \times 9-6) \times 7-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{58032} := \frac{1 \times 4-9+7+6}{5+8 \times 03+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{67230} := \frac{1-49+85}{(6+7)^2-3+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1+50+48}{3 \times (9+6+72)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{58320} := \frac{(1+4+9) \times 7+6}{5 \times (83-2)+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{73260} := \frac{1+4+9+8 \times 5}{7-3+260}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{76923} := \frac{(15+04) \times 8}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2+3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{83520} &:= \frac{(1-4+9+7) \times 6}{83 \times 5+20} \\ &:= \frac{(1+4+9) \times 7+6}{(8 \times 3+5) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{149+8+5}{732+60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{76302} := \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{7 \times 6+30^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15067}{34892} := \frac{1+5+06+7}{3+48-9+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{26307} := \frac{14-9+8 \times 5}{2 \times (6+30)+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14986}{73025} := \frac{(1+4) \times 9 \times 8-6}{(7^3+02) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1-5+06 \times 7}{3-4+8+9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{26730} := \frac{1+4 \times (9+8)+5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1+49 \times (8-5)}{267-3+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15028}{47396} := \frac{1 \times 5+0 \times 2+8}{47-3-9+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15067}{89243} := \frac{1+5+0 \times 6+7}{8+9 \times 2 \times 4-3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 50+67}{8 \times 92-43}$$

$$:= \frac{1-49+85}{2+67-3+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 50+28}{(47+3-9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{15 \times (06+7)}{8 \times 9 \times 2^4+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{15078}{23694} := \frac{1 + (5 + (0 - (7 - 8)))}{2 - (3 + ((6 - 9) \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 - ((0 \times 7) - 8))}{(2 \times ((3 \times 6) - 9)) + 4} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 - (0 - (7 + 8)))}{2 + (36 - (9 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - ((5 \times (-07)) + 8)}{2 \times (3 + (6 + (9 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (50 - (7 + 8))}{2 + (3 + ((6 \times 9) - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (50 + (7 - 8))}{2 - (3 - (6 \times (9 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1^5 + 0) \times (7 \times 8)}{(2 \times (3 - 6)) + 94} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 - (0 - 78))}{2 + (36 + 94)} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15078}{34692} := \frac{1 + 50 \times 7 + 8}{3 \times 4 \times 69 - 2} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15079}{24836} := \frac{1^5 + 07 + 9}{2 \times (4 - 8 + 3 \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 50 - 7 - 9}{2 \times (4 - 8 \times (3 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 07 + 9}{2 \times (48 - 3) - 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 5 + 079}{2 \times (4 + (8 + 3) \times 6)} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15084}{26397} := \frac{((1 + 50) \times 8) + 4}{((2^6) + 39) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 \times (-08))) \times 4}{2 - (6 - (3 \times 97))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 + (-08))) \times 4}{2 - (6 - (39 - 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 + (-08)))^4}{(2 \times (6^3)) + (9 + 7)} \\
 \\
 & := \frac{(1^{508}) \times 4}{2 + (6 - (3 - (9 - 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1^5 + 0) \times (8 \times 4)}{2 + (6 \times (3^9 - 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1^5 + 0) \times (8 + 4)}{2 + (6 - (3 - (9 + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 - (0 \times 8))) \times 4}{2 - (6 - (39 + 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))^4}{2 \times (6 \times (3 \times (9 \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 - (-08))) \times 4}{(2 + (6 - (3 - 9))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 - 0)) \times (8 + 4)}{2 \times (((6 \times 3) - 9) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 50) \times (8 - 4)}{((2 \times 6) + 39) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(15 - (-08)) \times 4}{(2 - (6 - (3 \times 9))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - 5) \times (0 - (8 \times 4))}{(26 - (3 - 9)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - 5) \times (0 - (8 + 4))}{(2^6) + ((3 \times 9) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(15 \times (08)) - 4}{(2 + ((6 - 3) \times 9)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (5 + (0 - (8 \times 4)))}{2 + (63 - (9 + 7))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (5 + (0 - (8 + 4)))}{2 \times (6 + (3 - (9 - 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (5 + (0 - 84))}{(2 + (6 + (3 + 9))) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (08)) + 4)}{(2 + ((6 \times 3) - 9)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (08)) - 4)}{2 + (63 - (9 - 7))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((50 \times 8) - 4)}{(2 + (6 + 3)) \times (9 \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((50 + 8) \times 4)}{((2^6) + (3 - 9)) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (0 + (8 + 4)))}{(2^{6-3}) + 97} \\
 \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (0 + (8 - 4)))}{26 + (3^9 - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{15 \times (0 + (8 + 4))}{2 + ((6^3) + 97)} \\
 & := \frac{150 \times (8 + 4)}{2 \times (((6^3) + 9) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1508 + 4}{2639 + 7} \\
 & := \frac{1508 - 4}{2639 - 7} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15086}{74239} := \frac{(-1 + 5) \times 08 + 6}{7 + 4 \times (2 + 3) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{150 + 8 - 6}{742 - 3 + 9} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15087}{24396} := \frac{150 - 8 \times 7}{2 + 4 \times 39 - 6} \\
 & \frac{15087}{49632} := \frac{1 + 50 + 8 \times 7}{4 \times 96 - 32} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15093}{24768} := \frac{1 + 50 + 9 + 3}{2 \times 4 \times (7 - 6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 + 9 \times 3}{2^4 \times (7 - 6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{150 + 9 - 3}{2^{4+7-6} \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 + 9^3}{2 \times (4 + 76) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 509 - 3}{2 \times 4 \times (7 + 6) \times 8} \\
 \\
 & \frac{15093}{27864} := \frac{1 - (5 - 09) \times 3}{2 \times 7 \times (8 - 6) - 4} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 - 9 - 3}{2 + 7 \times (8 + 6 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 + 9 \times 3}{2 + 78 + 64}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{1 \times 50 + 93}{((2 + 7) \times 8 - 6) \times 4} & := \frac{(1 + (5 \times 2)) \times (3 + 7)}{(60 - (9 - 4)) \times 8} & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((2^3) + 7))}{60 \times (9 + (4 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{150 + 9 - 3}{278 + 6 + 4} & := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 \times 3))) \times 7}{(6 - (0 - (9 \times 4))) \times 8} & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{((6 \times (09)) - 4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{46827} & := \frac{1 + 50 - 9 - 3}{46 + 82 - 7} & := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 + 3))) \times 7}{(60 \times (9 - 4)) + 8} & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (2 + (3 + 7)))}{6 \times (0 + ((9 - 4) \times 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{48762} & := \frac{1 + 50 - 9 - 3}{48 + 76 + 2} & := \frac{(1 + (5 + 23)) \times 7}{60 + (94 \times 8)} & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (2 + 37))}{60 \times (9 - (4 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 + 9 \times 3}{4 \times (8 - 7 + 62)} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (2 \times (3 + 7))}{(6 - (-09)) \times (4 \times 8)} & := \frac{1 \times (5^{2^3-7})}{60 - ((9 - 4) \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{62478} & := \frac{1 + (5 + 09) \times 3}{6 \times (24 + 7) - 8} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (2 + (3 \times 7))}{(60 \times 9) + (4 + 8)} & := \frac{1 \times (5 + ((2^3) + 7))}{(6 - ((0 \times 9) - 4)) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{78624} & := \frac{1 + (5 + 09) \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times (6 + 2 - 4)} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (2 + (3^7))}{(6 - (0 - (9^4))) \times 8} & := \frac{1 \times (5 + (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{60 + ((9 - 4) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 50 \times (9 - 3)}{7 \times (8 + 6) \times 2^4} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (2 + (3 + 7))}{6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 48)} & := \frac{1 \times (5 + (2 + (3 + 7)))}{((6 - (-09)) \times 4) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{87462} & := \frac{150 + 9 - 3}{(8 + 74 \times 6) \times 2} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 237}{6 \times (0 + 948)} & := \frac{1 \times (5 + (2 + (3 - 7)))}{(6 + (-09)) \times (4 - 8)} \\
 & \text{-----} & := \frac{(15 \times 2) + 37}{((60 + 9) \times 4) - 8} & := \frac{1 \times (52 - (3 - 7))}{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times 4))) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{47328} & := \frac{15 + 096}{4 \times (7^3 - 2^8)} & := \frac{(15 - 2) \times (3 + 7)}{(60 + (9 - 4)) \times 8} & := \frac{1 \times (52 + (3 \times 7))}{(60 \times (9 - 4)) - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{83472} & := \frac{1 + (5 + 09) \times 6}{(8 - 3) \times 47 \times 2} & := \frac{1 - ((5 - 23) \times 7)}{(60 \times 9) - (4 \times 8)} & := \frac{1^{5237}}{(6 \times (0 \times 9)) - (4 - 8)} \\
 & \text{-----} & := \frac{1 - (5 - ((2^3) \times 7))}{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times 4))) - 8} & := \frac{1 + ((5 \times 23) + 7)}{60 + (9 \times 48)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15207}{64938} & := \frac{15 + 207}{6 + 4 + 938} & := \frac{1 - (5 - (2 - (3 - 7)))}{(6 \times (0 \times 94)) + 8} & := \frac{1 + ((5 + (2 + 3)) \times 7)}{((60 + 9) \times 4) + 8} \\
 & \text{-----} & := \frac{1 - (5 - (2 \times (3 \times 7)))}{(6 - (0 - (9 + 4))) \times 8} & := \frac{1 + ((5 + 23) \times 7)}{(60 \times (9 + 4)) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15236}{84970} & := \frac{1 + 5 \times (2 - 3 + 6)}{84 - 9 + 70} & := \frac{1 \times ((5 - (2 - 3)) \times 7)}{6 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) - 8))} & := \frac{1 + ((5 - 2) \times (3 \times 7))}{(6 + ((0 \times 9) - 4))^8} \\
 & \text{-----} & := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (2 \times 3)) - 7)}{6 - (0 - (94 - 8))} & := \frac{1 + (5 - (2 + (3 - 7)))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 4)) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15237}{60948} & := \frac{((1 + 5)^2) \times (3^7)}{6 \times (0 + ((9^4) \times 8))} & := \frac{1 \times ((5 + 2) \times (3 \times 7))}{(60 \times 9) + 48} & := \frac{1 + (5 - (2 - 37))}{60 + ((9 + 4) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 - (2^3)))^7}{(6 \times (0 \times 9)) + (4^8)} & := \frac{1 \times (5 - (2 - (3 \times 7)))}{60 - (9 \times (4 - 8))} & := \frac{1 + (5 \times ((2 \times 3) + 7))}{6 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 - (2 - 3))) \times 7}{((60 - 9) \times 4) - 8} & := \frac{1 \times (5 - (2 \times (3 - 7)))}{((6 - (-09)) \times 4) - 8} & := \frac{1 + (5 \times (2 + (3 \times 7)))}{((6 \times (09)) + 4) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{1 + (5^{2^3-7})}{6 \times ((0 \times 9) - (4 - 8))} & := \frac{(15 - 2 + 4) \times 9}{708 + 6 - 3} & := \frac{15 + 3 \times 09}{2 - (4 - 7 - 8) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 - (3 - 7)))}{6 \times ((0 \times 94) + 8)} & & := \frac{1 + 53 + 09}{(2^4 - 7 + 8) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 \times (3 \times 7)))}{6 \times ((0 \times 9) + (4 \times 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15264}{97308} := \frac{1 - 5 + 2 \times (6 + 4)}{97 - 3 + 08} & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (30 - 9)}{2 \times (4 + 78) + 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{60 + ((9 \times 4) + 8)} & & := \frac{1 + 5^3 + 0 \times 9}{2 \times (4 + 7 \times (8 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 + (3 + 7)))}{6 \times ((0 \times 9) + (4 + 8))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15276}{30894} := \frac{1^5 \times (2^7 + 6)}{3 \times 089 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{24867} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 + 9}{(2 + 48) \times 6 + 7} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 + (3 - 7)))}{(6 + ((0 \times 9) - 4)) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15276}{83904} := \frac{1 \times 5^2 + 7 \times 6}{(83 + 9) \times 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{26487} := \frac{1 + 53 + 09}{26 - 4 + 87} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (2 + 37))}{(6 - (-09)) \times (4 + 8)} & & := \frac{1 + 5^3 + 0 \times 9}{2 + 6^{4-8+7}} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (23 - 7))}{(6 - (0 - (9 - 4))) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15280}{63794} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{6 + (3 + 79) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27468} := \frac{(1 + 53) \times 09}{2 \times (74 \times 6 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{15 \times (2 + (3 + 7))}{(6 - (-09)) \times 48} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15280}{94736} := \frac{15 - 2 - 8 + 0}{9 + 4 \times (7 - 3) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27648} := \frac{(1 + 5^3) \times 09}{2^7 \times (6 - 4) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{15 + (2 + (3 + 7))}{6 - (0 - (94 + 8))} & := \frac{1 \times 5 + 2 + 8 + 0}{9 - 4 \times 7 \times (3 - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27864} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 + 9}{(2 + 78 + 6) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{15 + (2 + 37)}{6 \times (0 - (9 \times (4 - 8)))} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 2 + 8 + 0}{(9 + 4) \times (7 + 3) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{28674} := \frac{1 + 53 + 09}{2 \times (8 \times 6 + 7 + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{15 + 237}{60 + 948} & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2 + 80}{(9 + 4 \times 7 \times 3) \times 6} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 + 9}{(2 + 8 \times 6) \times 7 + 4} \\
 & := \frac{152 - (3 - 7)}{6 \times (0 + ((9 + 4) \times 8))} & := \frac{1 + 52 - 8 + 0}{9 \times (4 + 7 \times 3 + 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{42768} := \frac{1 + 53 + 09}{4 \times 27 + 68} \\
 & := \frac{152 + (3 + 7)}{6 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 + 8)))} & & := \frac{1 + 5^3 + 0 \times 9}{(4 - 2 + 7 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1523 + 7}{60 \times (94 + 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15296}{47083} := \frac{(1 + 5 - 2)^{9-6}}{4 \times 70 - 83} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 + 9}{4 \times (2^7 + 6) - 8} \\
 & & & := \frac{1 + 5 + 309}{4^2 \times (7 + 6 \times 8)} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{15246}{90387} := \frac{1 + 5 - 2 + 4 + 6}{9 \times 03 + 8 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15308}{64792} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 30 + 8}{6 \times 4 + 79 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{46872} := \frac{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 09}{4 \times (6 \times 8 + 7 \times 2)} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{15246}{90783} := \frac{1 - 5 + 2 + 4 \times 6}{(9 + 07) \times 8 + 3} & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 - 8}{647 + 9^2} & := \frac{(15 + 3) \times 09}{4 \times (6 + 8 \times 7) \times 2} \\
 & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{47628} := \frac{((1 + 5)^3 + 0) + 9}{4 \times (7 + (6 \times 28))} \\
 & \blacktriangleright \frac{15249}{70863} := \frac{1 + 5 - 2 + 4 + 9}{7 + 08 \times (6 + 3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{24786} := \frac{15 - 3 + 09}{(2 - 4 + 7) \times 8 - 6} & := \frac{((1 + 5)^3 + 0) - 9}{4 \times (((7 + 6)^2) - 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (3 - 0))) \times 9}{4 \times (7 \times (6 + (2 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3 \times 09}{4 - 8 + 7 \times 62}$	$:= \frac{1 + (530 - 9)}{((7 \times 8) + 2) \times 46}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (53 - 0)) \times 9}{4 \times (7 \times (62 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{(15 + 3) \times 09}{4 + 8^{7-6+2}}$	$:= \frac{153 - (0 \times 9)}{(7 + (8 + 2)) \times 46}$
$:= \frac{(15 - (3 - 0)) \times 9}{4 \times (7 \times (6 - (2 - 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{62748} := \frac{(1 + 5 + 30) \times 9}{(6 \times 27 + 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{78624} := \frac{(1 + 53) \times 09}{78 \times (6^2 - 4)}$
$:= \frac{(15 + (3 - 0)) \times 9}{476 + 28}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{67284} := \frac{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 09}{(6 \times 7 + 2) \times 8 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{84672} := \frac{(1 + 5 + 3) \times 09}{(8 + 4 \times 6) \times 7 \times 2}$
$:= \frac{(1 - 53) \times (-09)}{4 \times ((7 + 6) \times 28)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{78246} := \frac{((1 + 5)^3 + 0) - 9}{(7 + (8 \times 2)) \times 46}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 3^{09}}{84 \times 6^{7-2}}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (53 \times (09))}{(47 + 6) \times 28}$	$:= \frac{(1^5) \times (30 \times 9)}{(7 + 8) \times (2 \times 46)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 53) \times 09}{8 \times 4 \times 6 \times 7 \times 2}$
$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{4 \times (7 - (6 + (2 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (3 - 0))) \times 9}{782 - 46}$	
$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (3 - (-09)))}{(4^{7-6+2}) - 8}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 - 0))) \times 9}{(7 \times ((8^2) - 4)) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15327}{80496} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (3 + 2^7)}{80 \times (49 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (30 + 9))}{4 \times (7 + ((6^2) - 8))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (53 - 0)) \times 9}{((7 \times 8) - 2) \times 46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15327}{89604} := \frac{1 - 5 + 3 + 27}{8 \times (9 + 6 + 04)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (30 - 9))}{(4 \times (7 + (6 \times 2))) + 8}$	$:= \frac{(15 - (3 - 0)) \times 9}{(7 \times (82 - 4)) + 6}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (3 \times 2 + 7)}{(89 + 6) \times 04}$
$:= \frac{1 + (53 - (0 \times 9))}{((4 + 76) \times 2) + 8}$	$:= \frac{(15 \times 30) - 9}{7 \times ((82 \times 4) - 6)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (32 + 7)}{8 \times 9 + 6^{04}}$
$:= \frac{1 + (53 - (-09))}{(4 \times (7 \times 6)) + 28}$	$:= \frac{(15 + (3 - 0)) \times 9}{782 + 46}$	
$:= \frac{1 + (530 + 9)}{4 \times (7 \times (6 \times (2 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((5^3 + 0) - 9)}{(7 \times 82) + (4 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15360}{49728} := \frac{(1^5 + 3) \times 60}{49 + 728}$
$:= \frac{15 \times (3 - (-09))}{4 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 2) + 8))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 5^{3+0 \times 9}}{7 \times (82 + (4 + 6))}$	
$:= \frac{15 + (30 - 9)}{4 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 2) - 8))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{(7 - (8 - 2)) \times 46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15368}{49720} := \frac{1 + 5 \times (36 + 8)}{4 - 9 + 720}$
$:= \frac{153 - (0 \times 9)}{(4 + (7 + 6)) \times 28}$	$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (3 - (-09)))}{(7 \times (8 + (2 + 4))) - 6}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{48276} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 30 + 9}{4 + 8 \times (-2 + 76)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (30 + 9))}{(7 \times (8 + 24)) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15384}{76920} := \frac{((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 8) + 4}{((7 \times 6) - 9) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{48762} := \frac{1 + 5 + 30 - 9}{4 + 8 + 76 - 2}$	$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (30 - 9))}{(7 - (8 - 24)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{(1^5) + (3 + 84)}{(7 + (6 + 9)) \times 20}$
$:= \frac{1 + 53 + 0 \times 9}{4 + (8 + 76) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{1 + (53 - (0 \times 9))}{((7 \times (8 - 2)) + 4) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (5^3)) \times (8 + 4)}{7 \times (6 \times (9 \times 20))}$
$:= \frac{(15 - 3) \times 09}{4 \times (8 + 76 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (53 - (-09))}{7 \times (((8 + 2) \times 4) + 6)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (53 - 8)) \times 4}{(7 - 6) \times 920}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(1+5) \times (38-4)}{((7 \times 6) + 9) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{1 - (5 + ((3-8) \times 4))}{(7 + (6-9)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{1 - (5 + (3 - (8 \times 4)))}{(7 \times (6+9)) + 20} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (((5^3) - 8) \times 4)}{(7+6) \times (9 \times 20)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((53 \times 8) - 4)}{7 \times ((6+9) \times 20)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((53+8) \times 4)}{(7 + (6 \times 9)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 - (3 - (8 \times 4)))}{(76+9) \times (2-0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 - (3 - (8-4)))}{7 - (6 - (9+20))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + ((3+8) \times 4))}{7 \times (6 + (9+20))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + (3 - (8-4)))}{7 + (6 + (9 - (2-0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + (3 \times (8-4)))}{(7 \times (6+9)) - 20} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + (3 + (8 \times 4)))}{(7 - (6-9)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + (3 + (8+4)))}{(7 - (6-9))^2 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (5 + (3 + (8-4)))}{(7 \times 6) + (9 \times (2-0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (((5 \times 3) - 8) \times 4)}{7 + (69 \times (2-0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((5+3) \times (8+4))}{(7 \times 69) + (2-0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 - (3 - (8-4)))}{(7 \times 6) - (9 - (2-0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 \times (3 + (8+4)))}{(7 \times (6 \times 9)) + (2-0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 \times (3 + (8-4)))}{(7-6) \times (9 \times 20)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 + (3 \times (8+4)))}{7 \times ((6+9) \times (2-0))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + (5 + (3 + (8+4)))}{7 + (6 + (92-0))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 + (3 + (8-4)))}{76 + (9-20)} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{26784} := \frac{15 + 3 \times 90}{2 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{27648} := \frac{15 + 3 \times 90}{2^{7+6+4-8}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{27864} := \frac{15 + 3 \times 90}{2^{7+8-6} + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{46872} := \frac{15 + 3 \times 90}{(4+6) \times 87 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{68742} := \frac{(15-3) \times 90}{6 + (8 + 7^4) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{72846} := \frac{1^{53} \times 90}{(7+2 \times 8 \times 4) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{82764} := \frac{1^{53} \times 90}{(8+2 \times 7)^{6-4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{84672} := \frac{15 + 3 \times 90}{(8+4 \times 6) \times 7^2} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15402}{78369} := \frac{1 - 5 + 40 - 2}{7 \times (8 + 3 \times 6) - 9} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15407}{38269} := \frac{1 + 54 + 07}{3 + 82 + 69} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15407}{63829} := \frac{1 - (5 - (4 - (-07)))}{6 - (3 - (8 + (2 \times 9)))} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (5 - (4 - 0))) \times 7}{6 - (3 - ((8^2) - 9))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 - (0 \times 7)))}{6 + ((3 + (8 - 2)) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 7)}{6 + ((3 \times 82) + 9)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 - 0))) \times 7}{((6 \times 3) - 8) \times 29}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(15 - (4 - 0)) \times 7}{(6 - (3 - 8)) \times 29} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 - 0))) \times 7}{6 + ((3 + (8^2)) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{154 - (-07)}{638 + 29} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (4 \times (07))}{(6 - 3) \times (8 \times 29)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (54 \times (07))}{6 + (3 \times (8 + (2^9)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((5 + 40) \times 7)}{(63 + 82) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (54 - 0)) \times 7}{(63 - 8) \times 29} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{29376} := \frac{1^5 + 40 \times 8}{(2 + 93 + 7) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{97263} := \frac{1^5 \times (40 + 8)}{(97 - 2 + 6) \times 3} \\
 := \frac{15 \times (40 + 8)}{9 + 72 \times 63} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{97632} := \frac{1^5 + 40 \times 8}{9 \times (76 \times 3 - 2)} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15423}{60897} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 4 \times 23}{60 \times 8 - 97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15423}{78069} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 4 \times 23}{7 \times 80 - 69} \\
 \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15430}{67892} := \frac{((1^5) + 4) \times 30}{678 - (9 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 54) \times (3 - 0)}{6 \times ((7 \times (8 + 9)) + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (5 - (4 + 30))}{6 \times (7 + (8 + (9 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times 4) + 30)}{(6 \times 7) + (89 \times 2)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 - 0)))}{6 + ((7 \times 8) + 92)} &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 4 \times 80}{(37 - 9)^2 \times 6} &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (4 \times (8 \times 6))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 + 7)))^2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5^{4-3+0})}{6 + ((7 - (8 - 9)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 80}{(3 + 7) \times (92 + 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + 5)^{4-8+6}}{(3 \times (0 \times 9)) + 72} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (4 \times 30))}{((6 \times 7) + 8) \times (9 + 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{69273} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{6 \times 9 + 2^7 - 3} &:= \frac{(15 \times 4) - (8 + 6)}{(30 + (9 + 7)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4^3 + 0))}{(((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9) + 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{72369} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{7 + (2 + 3 \times 6) \times 9} &:= \frac{(15 - 4) \times 86}{(30 \times (9 \times 7)) + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4 + 30))}{(6 - (7 - 89)) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 - 5 + 4 + 80}{7 - 2 + 369} &:= \frac{(154 + 8) \times 6}{3 \times (0 + (9 \times 72))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (54 + 30)}{((6 \times 7) - 8) \times (9 + 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{93267} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{9 \times (32 - 6) + 7} &:= \frac{1 - ((5 - (4 + 8)) \times 6)}{((3 - (-09)) \times 7) + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (4 \times 30)}{6 - (7 - (89^2))} & &:= \frac{1 - ((5 \times (4 - 8)) - 6)}{3 \times (0 + (9 + (7 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (4^3 + 0)}{6 \times ((78 \times 9) + 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15483}{70269} := \frac{1 + 5 + 4 \times (8 - 3)}{7^{02} + 69} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - ((4 \times 8) + 6))}{3 - (0 - ((9 \times 7) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (4 + (3 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + ((8 \times 9) - 2))} &:= \frac{1 + 5 - 4 + 8 + 3}{7 - 02 + 6 \times 9} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (4 + (8 \times 6)))}{3 \times (0 + ((9 + 7) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{15^{4-3+0}}{6 + (78 - (9 \times 2))} & &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (4 + (8 - 6)))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 - 7))) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{15 + (4 \times 30)}{6 - (7 \times (8 - 92))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15486}{29370} := \frac{1 \times 5 - (4 - 8) \times 6}{2 \times 9 + 37 + 0} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (48 - 6))}{(3 \times (09)) + (7^2)} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + 5 + 4 + 8 \times 6}{(2 + 9) \times (3 + 7) + 0} &:= \frac{1 - (5 \times (4 - (8 + 6)))}{3 - (0 - (97 + 2))} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{15479}{20863} := \frac{1 - 5 - (4 - 7) \times 9}{2 \times (08 + 6) + 3} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 - 4 + 86}{2 + 93 + 70} &:= \frac{1 - (5 + ((4 - 8) \times 6))}{((3 \times (09)) - 7) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (4 + 7) - 9}{20 + (8 + 6) \times 3} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + 48) \times 6}{2 - 9 \times (3 - 70)} &:= \frac{1 - (5 + (4 - (8 + 6)))}{3 \times (0 + (9 - (7 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 5 + 4 \times (7 + 9)}{2 \times 08 \times 6 - 3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15486}{30972} := \frac{(1^5) + (4 \times 86)}{30 \times (9 + (7 \times 2))} &:= \frac{1 - (5 + (4 - 86))}{30 + (9 \times (7 \times 2))} \\
 & &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times 4)) \times (8 - 6)}{3 - (0 - (9 + 72))} &:= \frac{1 - (54 - 86)}{3 + (0 - (9 - 72))} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{37926} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{(37 + 9) \times 2 + 6} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 + 8))) \times 6}{3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 72)} &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 - (4 - 8)) \times 6)}{(3 - (-09)) \times (7 + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (4 + 8) + 0}{3 \times (7 + (9 - 2) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + 4)) \times (8 \times 6)}{30 \times ((9 + 7) \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (4 + 8)) + 6)}{(3 - (0 - (9 \times 7))) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 4 + 80}{3 \times 79 + 2 + 6} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + 4))^{8-6}}{(3 - (0 - 97)) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 + (4 \times 8)) \times 6)}{3 - (0 - (9 \times (7^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (4 + 8) + 0}{3 \times 7 \times (9 + 2 \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - 4)) \times (8 + 6)}{(30 - (9 - 7)) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 + 4) \times (8 \times 6))}{(3 - (-09)) \times 72}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((5+4) \times (8-6))}{(3 \times (0+(9-7)))^2} &:= \frac{1 + ((5+4) \times (8+6))}{(30+97) \times 2} &:= \frac{15 + (4 - (8+6))}{(3 - (0 - (9-7))) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - ((4-8) \times 6))}{(30 \times (9-7)) - 2} &:= \frac{1 + ((5+4) \times (8-6))}{(3 - (0 - (9+7))) \times 2} &:= \frac{15 + (4 - (8-6))}{30 + (9 - (7-2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (4 - (8 \times 6)))}{3 - (0 - (97-2))} &:= \frac{1 + ((54-8) \times 6)}{((30 \times 9) + 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{15 + 486}{30 + 972} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (4 - (8+6)))}{30 - (9 - (7+2))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 - (4 - (8 \times 6)))}{(3 - ((0 \times 9) - 7))^2} &:= \frac{154 - (8-6)}{309 - (7-2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (4 - (8-6)))}{3 \times ((0 \times 97) + 2)} &:= \frac{1 + (5 - (4 - (8+6)))}{(3 \times (09)) + (7-2)} &----- \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (4 - 86))}{3 \times (0 + (9 + (7^2)))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 - (4 - (8-6)))}{3 + (0 - (9 - (7 \times 2)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15496}{32780} := \frac{1 - 5 - (4 - 9) \times 6}{3^2 \times 7 - 8 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 8) - 6))}{309 - (7^2)} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 - (8-6)))}{(3 \times (-09)) + (7^2)} &:= \frac{1 + 54 - 9 + 6}{3 + 27 + 80} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (4 - (8-6)))}{(3 - ((0 \times 9) - 7)) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 \times (8-6)))}{((3 - (-09)) \times 7) - 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15496}{70328} := \frac{1 - 5 - (4 - 9) \times 6}{70 + 3 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (4 + (8-6)))}{(3 - (-09)) \times (7-2)} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 + (8-6)))}{(30 \times (9-7)) + 2} &----- \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (48+6))}{30 \times (9 + (7+2))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 + 86))}{(30^{9-7}) + 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{27306} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 4 \times 9 + 8}{27 + 306} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (48-6))}{30 \times (9 + (7-2))} &:= \frac{1 + (5^{4-8+6})}{3 - ((0 \times 9) - (7^2))} &:= \frac{154 + 98}{2 \times (7 + 30) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5^{4-8+6})}{(3 \times (0 + (9+7))) + 2} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) + 6))}{30 + (9 + (7^2))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{62730} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 4 \times (9-8)}{62 - 7 + 30} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (4 - (8-6)))}{(3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (7 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) - 6))}{3 - (0 - ((9 \times 7) - 2))} &:= \frac{1 + 5 + 49 + 8}{6^2 \times 7 + 3 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (4 \times (8-6)))}{3 - (0 - (9 + (7 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4 - (8-6)))}{30 - (9 + (7-2))} &:= \frac{1 + 5 \times 4 \times 9 + 8}{6 \times 2^7 - 3 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (4^{8-6}))}{3 \times (0 + (9 + (7-2)))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4 \times (8-6)))}{(30 - (9+7)) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{73062} := \frac{((1+5) \times 4) - (9+8)}{7 + (30 - (6-2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (4 + (8+6)))}{(3 \times (0 + (9+7))) - 2} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4^{8-6}))}{30 + (9 + (7-2))} &:= \frac{(1^5) - (4 - (9+8))}{7 - (3 + (0 - 62))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (54 \times (8+6))}{(30-9) \times 72} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (4 + (8+6)))}{3 - (0 - (9 \times (7-2)))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 \times (9-8)))}{7 + (30 + 62)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{5486}}{(3 \times (0 \times 97)) + 2} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (48 \times 6))}{(3 - (-09)) \times (7^2)} &:= \frac{(1^5) + (49 - 8)}{(7 \times 30) - (6 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + ((5 \times 4) + (8+6))}{30 - (9 - (7^2))} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (48+6))}{3 \times (0 - (9 - (7^2)))} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (4+98))}{7 \times (30 + (6^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + ((5^4) - (8 \times 6))}{((3 \times (09)) + 7)^2} &:= \frac{15 - (4 + (8-6))}{3^{09-7} \times 2} &:= \frac{1 + ((5+4) \times (9+8))}{730 - (6-2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+5) \times ((4 \times 9) - 8)}{730 + 62}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15624}{79380} := \frac{(1+5 \times 6) \times (2+4)}{7+938+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5+6) \times (4 \times 2))}{7 - (0 - 389)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15604}{89723} := \frac{((1^5) + (6-0)) \times 4}{8 + (9 \times (7 \times 2 + 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15642}{70389} := \frac{(((1+5) \times 6) + 4) \times 2}{(7^{03}) + (8+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5+6) \times (4^2))}{703 + 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (5+6)) \times (-04)}{(8 + (9 - 7)) \times 23}$$

$$:= \frac{((15 \times 6) + 4) \times 2}{(70 + (3 \times 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 4) + 2))}{(70 + (3 - 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^5) \times (6 \times (04))}{(8 - (9 - 7)) \times 23}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (5 - (6 + 4)))^2}{(7 - (0 - (3 + 8))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (6 - (4 - 2)))}{70 + (3 + (8 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^5) \times (60 + 4)}{8 \times ((9 - 7) \times 23)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((5 + 6) \times 4)) \times 2}{(7 - (0 - 38)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (6 + (4 \times 2)))}{7 \times (0 - ((3 - 8) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (5 + 60)) \times 4}{((8 \times (9 \times 7)) + 2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (6 - 4))) \times 2}{7 - (0 - (3 + 89))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (56 \times (4 + 2))}{7 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (60 + 4)}{(89 + 7) \times 23}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (6 - 4)))^2}{(7 + (-03)) \times (8 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (56 \times (4 - 2))}{7 \times ((0 \times 3) + (8 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(15 - (6 - 0)) \times 4}{((8 + 97) \times 2) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times ((6 \times 4) + 2)}{703 + (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((5^{6-4}) - 2)}{(7 + (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 5) \times (6 \times (-04))}{8 \times ((9 + (7 \times 2)) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (6^{4-2})}{(70 + 38) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 - (6 - (4^2)))}{(7 \times (0 \times 3)) + (8 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(15 + (6 - 0)) \times 4}{(89 + 72) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - ((6 + 4)^2))}{(7^{03}) + 89}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + ((6 + 4) \times 2))}{((7 \times (03)) - 8) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 + (6 \times (-04)))}{(8 \times (9 + (7 - 2))) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (6 \times (4^2)))}{(70 - (3 \times 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 \times (4^2)))}{70 + 389}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5 + (6 - 0)) \times 4)}{((8 \times (9 - 7))^2) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (6 \times (4 - 2)))}{7 - (0 - (38 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 + (4 - 2)))}{7 \times ((0 \times 38) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5 + 60) \times 4)}{((8 \times 9) - 7) \times 23}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (6 + (4 - 2)))}{(7 - (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{156 - (4 + 2)}{(70 - (3 - 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 - (6 + (-04)))}{8 + (9 + (7 + (2 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (64 + 2))}{(7 - (0 - (3 \times 8))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{156 - (4 - 2)}{7 \times (0 + ((3 + 8) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 - (0 \times 4)))}{8 + (9 + ((7^2) + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (64 - 2))}{((7 \times (03)) + 8) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{156 + (4 + 2)}{(70 + (3 + 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 - (-04)))}{8 + (9 + (72 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 + (6 - (4^2)))}{7 - (0 - (3 + (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1564 + 2}{7038 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{156 + 04}{897 + 23}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 4)) - 2)}{(70 - (3 + 8)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1564 - 2}{7038 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{156 - 04}{897 - 23}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((5 \times (6 - 4)) + 2)}{7 - (0 - (38 + 9))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15672}{43098} := \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7 - 2)))}{(4 \times (3 - 0)) - (9 - 8)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 2)))}{(4 \times 30) - 98} & & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (6 + (8 - 7)))}{(4 \times (9 \times (3 - 0))) + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 - (6 - 7)) \times 2)}{4 + (30 - (9 - 8))} & & := \frac{1 + (56 - (8 + 7))}{((4 \times 9) + 30) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15729}{60348} & := \frac{(1 - 5) \times 7 \times (2 - 9)}{(60 + 34) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (6 + (7 - 2)))}{4 \times (3 - ((0 \times 9) - 8))} & & := \frac{1 \times ((5 - (6 - 8)) \times 7)}{(4 \times (9 + 30)) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 2)))}{4 - (3 \times (0 - (9 + 8)))} & & := \frac{(15 - (6 - 8)) \times 7}{(4 \times (93 - 0)) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{40986} & := \frac{1 - 5 + 7 \times 3 \times 2}{4 + 09 + 86} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 \times (7 - 2)))}{4 - (3 + (0 - 98))} & & := \frac{(1^{568}) \times 7}{4 + (9 + (3^{02}))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{49680} & := \frac{1 \times 57 \times (3 - 2)}{4 + 96 + 80} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (5 - ((6 \times 7) + 2))}{(4 \times (3 - 0)) + 98} & & := \frac{(1 + (56 - 8)) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times 30)) - 2} & & := \frac{1 \times 5 + 73 - 2}{(4 \times 9 - 6) \times 8 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 2))}{(4 \times 30) + (9 - 8)} & & & & := \frac{1 + 5 + 73 \times 2}{4 \times (9 + 6) \times 8 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7^2)))}{4 + (30 + 98)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15698}{20374} & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6 + 9 + 8}{20 + 37 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{64980} & := \frac{1 + 5 \times (7 - 3) + 2}{6 \times 4 - 9 + 80} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 2)))}{4 - (3 \times (0 - (9 \times 8)))} & & & & := \frac{1 + 5 \times 73 + 2}{(6 + 4 + 9) \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 2}{430 - (9 - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15703}{42896} & := \frac{15 + 70 - 3}{4^2 \times 8 + 96} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{69084} & := \frac{1 + 5 \times (7 - 3) + 2}{69 + 08 \times 4} \\
 & & & & & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (7^3 + 2)}{6 + 9084} \\
 & & & & & := \frac{(1 - 5 + 73) \times 2}{690 - 84} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15674}{83902} & := \frac{1 - 5 + 6 \times 7 - 4}{8 - (3 - 90) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15708}{49623} & := \frac{1 + 5 \times 7 + 08}{4 + (9 + 6^2) \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{96048} & := \frac{1 \times 5 + 73 - 2}{(9 \times 6 + 04) \times 8} \\
 & & & & & := \frac{1 + 5 + 73 \times 2}{960 - 4 \times 8} \\
 & & & & & := \frac{1 \times 57 \times 3 \times 2}{9 \times (60 \times 4 - 8)} \\
 & & & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15678}{20943} & := \frac{1 \times 56 + 78}{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15708}{92463} & := \frac{1 + 5 \times 7 + 08}{9 - 2 + 4 \times 63} & & \\
 & & & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{23904} & := \frac{(1 \times 5 + 6 - 8) \times 7}{2 \times (3 + 9 + 04)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15728}{90436} & := \frac{1 \times 5 - 7 - 2 + 8}{9 - 04 + 3 \times 6} & & \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (6 + 8) - 7}{2 \times (3 + 9) \times 04} & & := \frac{1 \times 5 - 7 + 2 + 8}{9 + 043 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{15736}{90482} & := \frac{1 + (5 + (7 - (3 + 6)))}{9 - (0 - (4 + (8 + 2)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{30429} & := \frac{1 + (5 + 6) \times (8 + 7)}{304 + 2 \times 9} & & := \frac{1 + 5 + 7 \times 2 - 8}{9 \times (04 + 3) + 6} & & := \frac{1 + (5 - (7 - (3 + 6)))}{(9 \times (-04)) + 82} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{49302} & := \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (8 + 7)))}{49 - (3 - (-02))} & & := \frac{1 + 5 - 7 \times (2 - 8)}{(90 + 4) \times 3 - 6} & & := \frac{1 - (5 - (7 + (3 + 6)))}{9 + (0 - (4 - (8^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((5 + (6 - 8)) \times 7)}{((4 \times 9) - (3 - 0)) \times 2} & & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 7 \times 2 \times 8}{90 \times 43 - 6} & & := \frac{1 + (5 + (7 - (3 - 6)))}{90 - (4 - (8 - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + 36))}{(90 + 48) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (73 - 6))}{9 \times ((048 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6))}{((90 - 4) \times 8) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{157 - (3 - 6)}{904 + (8 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 - (7 - (3^6)))}{90 + (4^{8-2})}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15738}{20496} := \frac{1 + 5 \times (7 + 3) - 8}{2 - 0 \times 4 + 9 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 5 \times (7 - 3 \times 8)}{2^{04} + 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15738}{94062} := \frac{1 + (5 \times (7 + 3) - 8)}{9 + 4 \times 062}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15768}{24309} := \frac{15 + 7 - 6 + 8}{2 - 4 + 30 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 5 + 7 + 6) \times 8}{2 \times (4 \times 30 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15768}{39420} := \frac{((1^5) + (7 \times 6)) \times 8}{(39 + 4) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (5 + 7)) \times (6 - 8)}{39 - (4 - 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{576}) \times 8}{3 + (9 + (4 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^5) \times (7 \times (6 + 8))}{(3^9-4) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (7 \times 6))) \times 8}{(3 + 9) \times (4 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (7 \times (6 \times 8))}{(3 + 9) \times 420}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 5) \times (7 - (6 + 8))}{(39 - 4) \times (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(15 + (7 - 6)) \times 8}{(3 + (9 + 4)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 57) \times (6 - 8)}{(3 \times 94) - (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - ((7 \times 6) - 8))}{3 \times (9 - (4 - 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (5 - (76 - 8))}{(3 + (9 - 4)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 - ((7 - 6)^8))}{3 - (9 + (4 - 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (7 - (6 + 8)))}{3 \times ((9 - 4) \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (7 \times (6 + 8)))}{(39 - 4)^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 - (6 - 8)))}{(3 \times (9 - 4)) + 20}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + (6 - 8)))}{(3 \times 9) - (4 - (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((5 \times 7) - (6 - 8))}{3 + (94 - (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 - (7 \times (6 - 8)))}{((3 + 9) \times 4) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5^{7-6^8})}{39 - (4 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (5 + (76 + 8))}{(3 \times (9 - 4))^2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (57 - (6 + 8))}{(3 \times (9 \times 4)) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{15 \times ((7 - 6) \times 8)}{3 \times ((9 - 4) \times 20)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15780}{36294} := \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + (8 - 0)))}{36 + (2 \times (9 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{15 + (7 + (8 - 0))}{3 - (6 \times (2 - (9 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (57 - (8 - 0))}{3 + ((6 \times (2 \times 9)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^5)^7) \times 80}{(((3 \times 6) + 2) \times 9) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{3 - (6 \times (2 - (9 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (5 - 7)) \times 80}{36 + ((2^9) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 - 0)))}{(36 \times (2 \times 9)) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15780}{69432} := \frac{1 + (5 + (7 - (8 - 0)))}{6 + ((9 - (4 - 3)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^5) \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{6 \times (9 - (4 - (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + (8 - 0)))}{(6 \times ((9 - 4) \times 3)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(15 \times 7) - 80}{6 + ((9 + 43) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{15 + (7 + (8 - 0))}{6 \times (9 + (4 + (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (7 + (8 - 0)))}{6 + (9 \times (4 + 32))}$$

$$:= \frac{((1^5)^7) \times 80}{(6 + (9 - 4)) \times 32}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{6 \times (((9 \times 4) - 3) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{157 + (8 - 0)}{694 + 32}$$

$$:= \frac{(15 + 7) \times 80}{(6^9-4) - 32}$$

$$:= \frac{15 \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{(6 + 9) \times (4^3 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (5 + 780)}{(6 \times (9 \times (4^3))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (57 + (8 - 0))}{6 + ((94 \times 3) - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15790}{26843} := \frac{1^{57} + 9 + 0}{2 + 6 + 8 + 4 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (7 + 9) + 0}{2 \times 68 \times (4 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{15 \times (7 + 9) + 0}{(26 + 8) \times 4 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{34608} &:= \frac{(15+79) \times 2}{(3+4) \times 60 - 8} &:= \frac{(15-8) \times (4+6)}{7 + ((9-2)^3 + 0)} &:= \frac{15 \times (8 - (4-6))}{(7 + (9 \times 2)) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{43680} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7 \times 9 - 2}{(4+3+6) \times 80} &:= \frac{(1-58) \times (4-6)}{(7 \times (9^2)) + (3-0)} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{60348} &:= \frac{15 \times 7 + 9 - 2}{60 \times (3+4) + 8} &:= \frac{1 - (((5-8) \times 4) - 6)}{(7 \times 9) + (2+30)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15862}{37904} := \frac{1 + (5+8) \times 6 - 2}{(37+9) \times 04} \\ & &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 - (4-6)))}{7 - (9 - (2+30))} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15834}{62790} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (8-3) + 4}{6^2 + 79 + 0} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 + (4+6)))}{7 \times (9 - (2 - (3-0)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15864}{79320} := \frac{((1 - (5-8))^6) \times 4}{((7+9)^3) \times 20} \\ & &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 + (4-6)))}{7 + (9 - (2 \times (3-0)))} &:= \frac{((15-8)^6) \times 4}{(7^{9-3}) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{29376} &:= \frac{1+58-4+0}{2 \times (93-7 \times 6)} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8+46))}{7 + ((9^2) \times (3-0))} &:= \frac{(1 - (5-86)) \times 4}{(79+3) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{32967} &:= \frac{15 \times 8 \times 4 + 0}{32 + 967} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (8 - (4+6)))}{((7+9) \times 2) + (3-0)} &:= \frac{(1^{586}) + 4}{7 + (9 + (3^2 + 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{67392} &:= \frac{1+58-4+0}{6 \times (7 \times 3 + 9 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (8 \times (4-6)))}{7 \times (9 + (2 \times (3-0)))} &:= \frac{(1^5) \times (8 \times (6 \times 4))}{(7+9) \times (3 \times 20)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{76923} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 8 \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2 + 3)} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (84-6))}{((7 \times 9) + 2) \times 30} &:= \frac{(1^5) \times (8 + (6-4))}{((7+9) \times 3) + (2-0)} \\ &:= \frac{1^5 \times 8 \times 40}{7 \times ((6+9)^2 - 3)} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8 - (4+6)))}{7 + (9 + (2 - (3-0)))} &:= \frac{(1^5) + (8 + (6+4))}{(7 \times 9) + (32 - 0)} \\ & &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8 - (4-6)))}{(7 + (9 \times 2)) \times (3-0)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (8-6))) \times 4}{7 - (9 \times (3-20))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15846}{79230} &:= \frac{((1 - (5-8))^4) \times 6}{((7+9)^2) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8 + (4-6)))}{7 + (9 \times 2 + 30)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5+8)) \times (6 \times 4)}{7 \times ((9+3) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^5) \times (8 \times (4 \times 6))}{(7+9) \times (2 \times 30)} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8+46))}{7 + (9 \times (2+30))} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times ((8 \times 6) - 4)}{((7 \times 9) + 3) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(1^5) + (84-6)}{79 \times (2 + (3-0))} &:= \frac{1 + ((5 \times 8) - (4 \times 6))}{7 + ((9^2) - (3-0))} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 - (6-4)))}{7 + (9 - (3 \times (2-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (8+4))) \times 6}{((7 \times 9) - 2) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 + ((5 \times 8) + (4-6))}{((7 \times 9) + 2) \times (3-0)} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 \times (6+4)))}{(7 + (9+3)) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (8+4))) \times 6}{(7 + (9+2)) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 + (5 - (8 - (4+6)))}{7 + ((9+2) \times (3-0))} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 + (6+4)))}{7 \times (9 + (3 - (2-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(15 \times (8 \times 4)) + 6}{(79+2) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 + (5 \times (8 + (4-6)))}{(79 \times 2) - (3-0)} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 + (6-4)))}{7 - (9 - (32-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(15 \times (8+4)) + 6}{7 + (923-0)} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (8 - (4-6)))}{(7 \times (9+2)) + (3-0)} &:= \frac{1 - (5 + (8-64))}{(7 + (9-3)) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(15+84) \times 6}{(7+92) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (84-6))}{(7 + (9-2)) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 \times (((5 \times 8) - 6) \times 4)}{(7 + (9 \times 3)) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((8 - 6) \times 4))}{(7 + 93) \times (2 - 0)} &:= \frac{1 + 58 + 73}{4 \times (90 + 6 \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{36024} := \frac{1 - 5 - 8 + 79}{(36 + 02) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 + 4)))}{(7 + 93) \times 20} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15873}{62049} := \frac{(1 + 58 + 7) \times 3}{(6 + 20 \times 4) \times 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{46230} := \frac{158 - 79}{46 \times (2 + 3) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8 - (6 + 4)))}{7 - (9 + (3 - 20))} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{64320} := \frac{158 - 79}{64 \times (3 + 2) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (8 \times (6 - 4)))}{7 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{23490} := \frac{1 + 5 + 876}{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 - 0} & & \\
 &:= \frac{1 + ((5 \times 8) - (6 \times 4))}{79 + (3 \times (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{23940} := \frac{1^5 + 8 \times 7 + 6}{2 - 3 \times (9 - 40)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15893}{27640} := \frac{1 \times (58 - (9 + 3))}{2 \times ((7 - 6) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 - (8 - (6 + 4)))}{(7 \times (9 - 3)) - (2 - 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{30429} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 8 - 7 + 6}{(3 + 04) \times 2 + 9} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (8 + 9))) \times 3}{(2 + (7 - 6)) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (8 - (6 + 4)))}{(7 - (9 - 3)) \times 20} &:= \frac{1 + 5 \times (8 - 7 + 6)}{30 \times (4 - 2) + 9} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (8 \times (9 + 3)))}{2 \times (76 + (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (8 + (6 + 4)))}{7 + (93 + 20)} &:= \frac{(1^{58} + 7) \times 6}{30^4 + 2 + 9} &:= \frac{(15 + 8) \times (9 - 3)}{2 - (7 \times (6 - 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (8 + (6 - 4)))}{7 + (93 - 20)} &:= \frac{1 + 58 + 7 + 6}{30 \times 4 + 2 \times 9} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 9) - 3))}{(2 + (7 + 6)) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (58 - (6 \times 4))}{7 \times ((9 \times 3) - (2 - 0))} & &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (89 + 3))}{((2 \times 7) + 6) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (8 \times (6 - 4))}{((7 \times 9) - 3) \times 20} &:= \frac{(1 - 5 + 8) \times 7 \times 6}{304 + 2 \times 9} &:= \frac{15 - (8 - (9^3))}{(2^7) \times (6 + (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{15 + ((8 \times 6) - 4)}{7 + (9 \times (32 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{30942} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 87 + 6}{3 + 094 \times 2} &:= \frac{15 + (8 \times 93)}{(27 + 6) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{15 + (8^{6-4})}{79 \times (3 + (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{39042} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 87 + 6}{3^{9-04} - 2} & & \\
 &:= \frac{15 + (8 + (6 \times 4))}{(79 \times 3) - (2 - 0)} &:= \frac{(15 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)}{3 + (90 \times (4 \times 2))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{26784} := \frac{1 + 59 - 03}{2 + 6 \times (7 + 8) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{158 + (6 + 4)}{7 \times ((9 - 3) \times 20)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{43092} := \frac{15 + (8 - 7) \times 6}{4^3 - 09 + 2} &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 + 90) \times 3)}{(2 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 4)} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 - (5 - 8) \times 7 + 6}{4 \times (30 - 9 - 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{46872} := \frac{1 + 59 - 03}{4 \times (6 + 8 + 7) \times 2} \\
 & &:= \frac{(15 - 8) \times (7 + 6)}{4 + 3 \times 09^2} &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (90 \times 3))}{(4 \times (6 + (8 - 7)))^2} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + 5 + (8 - 7)^6}{4 - 3 + 09 \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{48267} := \frac{1 + 59 + 0 - 3}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 6 - 7} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{15873}{49062} := \frac{1 - 5 \times (8 - 7 - 3)}{4 + (9 + 06) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{49302} := \frac{(15 - 8) \times 7 \times 6}{4 + 9 + 30^2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{64728} := \frac{1 + 59 + 0 - 3}{(6 \times 4 + 7 - 2) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{58} + 7 \times 3}{4 \times (9 + 06 + 2)} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{72846} := \frac{1 + 5 + 90 - 3}{(7 + 2 \times 8 \times 4) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 5 + 8 + 7) \times 3}{4 + 90 + 6 + 2} & & \\
 &:= \frac{1^5 + 8 + 7^3}{(4 + 90 \times 6) \times 2} & & \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1 - (5 - 903)}{(7 \times 2) + (8 + (4^6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{82764} & := \frac{1 + 5 + 90 - 3}{(8 + 2 \times 7)^{6-4}} \\ & \frac{15908}{34276} := \frac{1 \times 590 - 8}{(3^4 + 2^7) \times 6} \\ & \frac{15930}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{(2 + 7) \times 86 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{28674} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - 9)) \times (3 - 0)}{2 + (8 + (6 + (7 + 4)))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{(2 \times 8) + ((6 \times 7) - 4)} \\ & := \frac{1 - (5 - (9 + 30))}{((2 + 8) \times 6) + (7 - 4)} \\ & := \frac{(1^5) + (9 + 30)}{2 \times ((8 - (6 - 7)) \times 4)} \\ & := \frac{1 + (5 + (9 + 30))}{2 + (8 + (67 + 4))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 0)))}{2 \times (8 + ((6 \times 7) + 4))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9^3 + 0))}{(2 + (8 + (6 - 7)))^4} \\ & := \frac{1 + (59 + 30)}{2 - (8 - (6 \times (7 \times 4)))} \\ & := \frac{(15 \times 9) + 30}{286 + (7 + 4)} \\ & := \frac{(1 + 59) \times (3 - 0)}{(2 + (86 - 7)) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{(15 + 9) \times 30}{((2 - 8) \times (6 - 7))^4} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 30)}{((2^8) - 67) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{46728} & := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{4 \times ((6 \times (7 - 2)) - 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 + (5 + (9 + 30))}{((4 + 6) \times (7 \times 2)) - 8} \\ & \frac{15920}{84376} := \frac{(1 - 5 + 9) \times 2 + 0}{84 - 37 + 6} \\ & := \frac{((1^5)^9) \times 20}{(8 \times (4 + (3 + 7))) - 6} \\ & \frac{15928}{47603} := \frac{1 + 59 + 28}{47 + 6^3} \\ & \frac{15920}{84376} := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times 9) + 30)}{(4 + 6) \times (7 \times 2 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 + (59 + 30)}{((4 \times 6) + (7 + 2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(15 \times 9) - 30}{4 \times (67 + (2 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(1 - (5 - 9)) \times 30}{(46 + (7 + 2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(15 \times 9) + 30}{4 + (6 \times (72 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(1 + 59) \times (3 - 0)}{4 \times (6 \times (7 \times 2 + 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{48672} & := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{4 \times 8 \times (6 + 7)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{64782} & := \frac{(1 - 5 + 9) \times 3 + 0}{64 + 7 - 8 - 2} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (9 - 3) + 0}{6 + 4 + 7 \times 8 \times 2} \\ & := \frac{1 + 59 + 30}{6 \times (4 - 7 + 8^2)} \\ & := \frac{(1^5 + 9) \times 30}{6^4 - 78 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{76482} & := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{7 \times (6^4 - 82)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{84672} & := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{8 \times 4 \times 6 \times 7^2} \\ & \frac{15934}{62708} := \frac{(1 \times 59 + 3) \times 4}{(-6 + 2^7) \times 08} \\ & \frac{15936}{80427} := \frac{1 - 5 + 9 \times 36}{804 \times 2 + 7} \\ & \frac{15960}{24738} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 9 + 6 + 0}{(2 + 4 + 7) \times 3 - 8} \\ & := \frac{1 + 5 \times 9 - 6 + 0}{(2 - 4) \times (7 - 38)} \\ & := \frac{1 + 5 + 9 \times 6 + 0}{2^4 + 7 \times (3 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{(1^5 + 9) \times 60}{2 \times (473 - 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 + 59 + 60}{(2 + 4) \times (7 + 3 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 96 + 0}{2 + 4 + 738} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15960}{78432} & := \frac{1^5 + 9 + 60}{78 \times 4 + 32} \\ & \frac{15974}{28036} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 97 - 4}{2 \times (80 + 3) + 6} \\ & \frac{15984}{20736} := \frac{1 + 5 + (9 + 8) \times 4}{2^{07-3} \times 6} \\ & := \frac{1 - 5 + 9 + 8 \times 4}{2 \times (07 - 3) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{26307} &:= \frac{1+59-8-4}{2 \times (6+30)+7} &:= \frac{(1+(60+3)) \times 2}{485-97} &:= \frac{16 \times ((03+8))}{495+(7^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{26730} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 98+4}{(26+7) \times 30} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (032))}{485+97} &:= \frac{160+38}{4 \times (9+((5+7)^2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{27306} &:= \frac{(15+9) \times (8-4)}{2^7+30+6} &:= \frac{(1+(6-0)) \times 32}{(4+(8-5)) \times 97} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{52974} &:= \frac{1-6+038}{5 \times 2+9 \times (7+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{36720} &:= \frac{1-5+9+8 \times 4}{36+7^2+0} &:= \frac{1 \times (60 \times 32)}{(4+8) \times (5 \times 97)} &:= \frac{160-3+8}{5+2^9+7 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{37260} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 98+4}{(3 \times 7+2) \times 60} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{74925} &:= \frac{160+38}{(7 \times 4+9) \times 25} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{60273} &:= \frac{1+59+84}{60 \times (2+7)+3} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{27459} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03+8)}{2 \times (7+45)+9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{79542} &:= \frac{1+60+38}{7+9 \times 54-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{62370} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 98+4}{(6^2-3) \times 70} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{27945} &:= \frac{1 \times 60 \times (3+8)}{2 \times 7 \times 9+4^5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{95742} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03+8)}{(9+5) \times 7 \times 4+2} \\ & & &:= \frac{160+38}{(2+7 \times 9+4) \times 5} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16027}{49538} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-02+7}{(4+9) \times (5-3)+8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{45927} &:= \frac{1 \times 60-38}{4+5 \times 9+2 \times 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16059}{37842} &:= \frac{160-59}{(3+7 \times 8) \times 4+2} \\ &:= \frac{1-6+027}{4+9+5 \times (3+8)} & &:= \frac{1 \times 6+038}{45+9 \times (2+7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16059}{47382} &:= \frac{160-59}{4 \times 73+8-2} \\ &:= \frac{1+6^{02}+7}{4 \times (9-5 \times (3-8))} & &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03+8)}{(4+5+9 \times 2) \times 7} & & \\ &:= \frac{1+6 \times (02+7)}{(49+5) \times 3+8} & &:= \frac{16 \times (03+8)}{4 \times (5+9) \times (2+7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16074}{23598} &:= \frac{1+6 \times 07+4}{2 \times 35-9+8} \\ &:= \frac{1+60-2+7}{4 \times 9 \times 5+3 \times 8} & &:= \frac{160+38}{(4+59) \times (2+7)} & &:= \frac{(1+60) \times 7-4}{23+598} \\ &:= \frac{1+60+27}{(49-5 \times 3) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{47952} &:= \frac{160+38}{4 \times (79-5) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16074}{53298} &:= \frac{1+6 \times (07-4)}{53+2 \times 9-8} \\ & & & & &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 07-4}{5^3+2-9+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16029}{87543} &:= \frac{1 \times 6-02+9}{8+75-4 \times 3} & &:= \frac{1 \times (60-38)}{4+(9+(57-2))} & &:= \frac{1 \times 60-7+4}{5+(32-9) \times 8} \\ & & & & &\blacktriangleright \frac{16074}{82935} &:= \frac{160+7 \times 4}{(8+2 \times 93) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16032}{48597} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 032}{(4-(8-5)) \times 97} & &:= \frac{1-(6+(0-38))}{(49-(5-7)) \times 2} & & \\ &:= \frac{16^{0 \times 3+2}}{4+((85 \times 9)+7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{49572} &:= \frac{1 \times (6+(0-(3-8)))}{4+(((9-5) \times 7)+2)} & &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 07-4}{5^3+2-9+8} \\ &:= \frac{160 \times 32}{4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 97))} & &:= \frac{1 \times (6-(0-38))}{4 \times (9+(5 \times (7-2)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{16092}{35748} &:= \frac{160-9-2}{3^5+(7+4) \times 8} \\ & & &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((03+8)))}{(4+((9+5) \times 7)) \times 2} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{16092}{37548} &:= \frac{(1^6+0) \times (9^2)}{3 \times (7 \times (5-(4-8)))} \\ & & &:= \frac{1+(60+38)}{((49-5) \times 7)-2} & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^6 + 0) + 92}{(37 \times 5) + (4 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 - (-09)) \times 2)}{3 + (7 + (5 \times (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (0 - (9 \times 2)))}{3 - (7 - (5 \times (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (0 \times 92))}{(3 \times 7) + (5 - (4 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2))}{((3^{7-5}) \times 4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (0 + (9 \times 2)))}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (0 + (9 - 2)))}{((3 + 7) \times (5 + 4)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (0 + 92))}{((3 \times (7 - 5))^4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6^{0 \times 9 + 2})}{(3 \times (7 + 5)) + 48}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 - ((0 \times 9) - 2))}{3 \times (7^{5+4-8})}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 - (0 - (9 + 2)))}{3 \times (7 - (5 - (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (60 - (9 - 2))}{3 + (75 + 48)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (60 + (9 + 2))}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 - 4) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (60 + 92)}{3 \times (7 \times (5 + (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - (0 - (9 + 2))}{3 + (7 + (5 + 48))}$$

$$:= \frac{160 + 92}{3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16245}{83790} := \frac{1 + 6 \times (2 - 4 + 5)}{8 + (3 + 7) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16254}{39087} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (25 - 4)}{390 - 87}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16254}{79380} := \frac{1 + 62 + 5^4}{7 \times (9 - 3) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16275}{39804} := \frac{(1 + 6 - 2) \times 7 \times 5}{(3 \times 9 + 80) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16298}{57043} := \frac{((1 + 6)^2) + (9 + 8)}{(57 \times (04)) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{62}) \times 98}{(5 \times 70) - (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (6 - 2)) \times 98}{5 \times (7^{0 \times 4 + 3})}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times ((2 \times 9) - 8)}{5 \times (7 \times (0 + (4 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (2 + 98)}{5 \times (70 \times (4 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (29 - 8))}{57 + (0 - (4 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (((6 \times 2) - 9) \times 8)}{(5 + (7 - 0)) \times (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2 \times 9 - 8}{5 \times 70 \times (4 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (2 + 9)) - 8)}{5 + ((70 - 4) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 2) + 98)}{5 \times (70 + (4 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{5 + ((7 + (-04)) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (2 - 98))}{(5 \times 70) + (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{(5 \times (7 - 0)) + (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 + 8)))}{57 \times (0 + (4 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 - 8)))}{5 + (70 - (4 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 \times 8)))}{(5 + 70) \times (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{(5 \times (7 - 0)) - (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((6 \times 2) + (9 + 8))}{5 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 4) + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((6^2) - (9 + 8))}{5 \times (7 - (0 - (4 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (2 + (9 - 8)))}{5 \times (7 - (0 \times 43))}$$

$$:= \frac{16 + (2 + (9 \times 8))}{5 \times (70 - (4 + 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16302}{87945} := \frac{16 + 30 \times 2}{(87 - 9 + 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16340}{97825} := \frac{1 - 6 + 3^4 + 0}{(9 + 7 \times 8) \times (2 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16350}{98427} := \frac{1^{63} \times 50}{(9 - 8 + 42) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 + 3^5 + 0}{9 \times 84 \times 2 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3 \times 50}{9 \times (84 + 2) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16359}{20748} := \frac{(1 + 6 + 3) \times 5 - 9}{20 \times (7 - 4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - 3 \times 5) \times 9}{(2 + 07 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 63 + 59}{2 \times 074 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16359}{78204} := \frac{1 + (-6 + 3 \times 5) \times 9}{(78 + 20) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16375}{24890} := \frac{(1 - 6 + 3 + 7) \times 5}{2 - (4 - 8) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 63 + 7 + 5}{2 \times (48 + 9) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 6 + 3 \times 7 \times 5}{2 \times (4 + 8 \times 9) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - 6) \times 3) + 85}{7 \times ((2 - (-09)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (38 \times 5))}{720 + 94}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (63 - 8)) \times 5}{7 \times ((20 \times 9) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (38 \times 5)}{7 \times (209 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (6 \times 4)) \times (7 - 0)}{3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (4 \times 70)}{3 \times (((9 + 5)^2) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 4) \times 70)}{(3 + 9) \times (5 \times 28)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 - 4) \times 70)}{3 \times ((9 - 5) \times 28)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (4 + 70))}{3 + (9 \times (5 + (2 \times 8)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{27495} := \frac{1 + 63 - 8 + 0}{2 - 7 + 4 + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times 3 \times 8 + 0}{2 + (7 + 49) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{49725} := \frac{1 + 63 - 8 + 0}{4 - 9 + 7 \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 - 3 + 80}{4 + ((9 + 7)^2 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{59724} := \frac{(1 - 6) \times 3 + 80}{5 + (9 + 7^2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{74529} := \frac{1^{63} \times 80}{7 \times (45 - 2 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{92547} := \frac{1^{63} \times 80}{9^2 \times 5 + 47}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{94752} := \frac{(1 - 6) \times 3 + 80}{9 \times (47 - 5) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{97524} := \frac{(1 - 6) \times 3 + 80}{9 \times (7 \times 5 + 2 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16392}{45078} := \frac{1 \times (6 + (3 + (9 - 2)))}{4 - (5 \times ((0 \times 7) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (3 + (9 + 2)))}{4 - (5 + (0 - (7 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (3 \times (9 - 2)))}{4 - (5 + (0 - 78))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (3 \times (9 + 2)))}{4 + (50 + (7 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (39 + 2))}{(4 \times (5 \times (07))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (((6 + 3) \times 9) - 2)}{(4 \times (50 + 7)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 9)) + 2)}{450 - (7 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(163 + 9) \times 2}{(4^5 + 0) - 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16385}{49720} := \frac{(1 \times 6 - 3) \times 8 + 5}{4 \times (9 - 7 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3 + 8 \times 5}{4 \times 9 + 7 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16385}{72094} := \frac{1 - (6 + (3 - (8 + 5)))}{7 + (2 - (0 - (9 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (3 - 8))) \times 5}{(7^2 + 0) - (9 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + ((3 \times 8) + 5))}{7 \times ((2 \times (09)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (38 - 5))}{(7 \times 20) + (9 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (3 + (8 \times 5)))}{7 + (209 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16425}{30879} := \frac{1 - 6 + 4^2 \times 5}{3 \times (08 \times 7 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16470}{39528} := \frac{((1 - 6) \times 4) + 70}{(3 + (9 + (5 - 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^6) \times (4 \times 70)}{3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^6) \times 470}{3 \times (((9 \times 5) + 2) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^6) + (4 + 70)}{(3 - 9) \times (5 \times (2 - 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16472}{58930} := \frac{1 - 6 + (4 + 7)^2}{5 \times 89 - 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16478}{50932} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 4 - 7 + 8}{(5 + 09 + 3) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 6 - 4) \times 7 + 8}{50 + 9 + 3^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 4) \times (7 + 8)}{509 + 3 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16480}{75293} := \frac{1^6 \times 4 \times 80}{(7 - 5) \times (2 + 9^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4 \times 80}{(7 + 5) \times (2 + 9^3)}$$

$\frac{16482}{95073} := \frac{(1 \times 6 - 4) \times 82}{950 - 7 + 3}$	$:= \frac{(1^6) + (48 + 5)}{3 \times (29 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (48 + 5))}{(3 \times 2) + (9 \times 70)}$
$\frac{16485}{23079} := \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 - 5)))}{2 + (3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times ((4 \times 8) - 5)}{3 \times (2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times 485)}{3 \times (2 \times 970)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}{2 + (3 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (4 \times (8 \times 5))}{(3 + 29) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6^{4-8+5})}{3 \times (2^{9-7+0})}$
$:= \frac{1 + (64 - (8 \times 5))}{2 - (30 - (7 \times 9))}$	$:= \frac{1 - ((6 \times (4 - 8)) + 5)}{(3 \times (2 + 9)) + (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{(3 \times 2)^{9-7+0}}$
$:= \frac{(1^{64}) \times (8 \times 5)}{2 \times (30 + (7 - 9))}$	$:= \frac{1 - ((6 \times 4) - (8 \times 5))}{32 + (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (4 + (8 - 5)))}{(3 \times (2 + 9)) - (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{((1^{64}) + 8) \times 5}{(2 - 3) \times (0 - (7 \times 9))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 - ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{3 - (29 - 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (48 - 5))}{3 - (2 - (97 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + (4 - 8)) \times 5)}{2 - ((3 \times (-07)) + 9)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (4 \times (8 + 5)))}{(3 \times 29) + (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1^{6485}}{(3 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 - ((6 \times (4 - 8)) + 5)}{2 \times (30 - (7 + 9))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (4 + (8 - 5)))}{(3 \times 2) - (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (((6 \times 4) + 8) \times 5)}{329 - (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 48) \times 5)}{2 \times (3 \times ((07 \times 9)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (48 + 5))}{3 \times (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((6 + (4 - 8)) \times 5)}{(3 \times 2) + (9 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{(2^3 + 0) \times (7 \times 9)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 + (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{3 - (2 + (9 - 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((6 + (4 - 8))^5)}{3 + (2 - (9 - 70))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (48 + 5))}{2 + (3 - (0 - 79))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (6 + (4 - (8 + 5)))}{((3 - 2)^9) + (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((6 - 4)^{8-5})}{(3^2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (48 \times 5))}{(2 + 30) \times (7 \times 9)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (((6 - 4)^8) + 5)}{3 + ((2^9) + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 - ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{3 \times (2 + (9 + (7 - 0)))}$
$\frac{16485}{32970} := \frac{((1 + 6) \times 48) - 5}{32 + (9 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 4) + (8 + 5))}{((3^2) \times 9) - (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 \times (4 + (8 + 5)))}{3 + (29 \times (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{((1 + 64) \times 8) + 5}{((3 \times 2) + 9) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 4) + 85)}{(32 \times 9) - 70}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6^{4-8+5})}{3 + ((2 \times 9) - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (4 \times 8)))^5}{3 \times (2 \times (9^7 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + (4 - 8))^5)}{3 - (2 - (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + ((4 \times 8) + 5))}{(3^2) + (9 + 70)}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (4 + 8))) \times 5}{(3 - (2 - 9)) \times (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{3 - ((2 - 9) \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{3 + (2 + (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{(1^{64}) \times (8 \times 5)}{3 - (2 - (9 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}{32 - (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (4 - (8 - 5)))}{32 - (9 + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1^6) \times 485}{(3 - 2) \times 970}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 - 5)))}{(3 + 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{((3 + 2) \times 9) - (7 - 0)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{(3^2) \times (9 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (4 + (8 \times 5)))}{3 + (2 + (97 - 0))}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{3 + (2 + (9 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (4 + (8 + 5)))}{32 + (9 + (7 - 0))}$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (4 + (8 - 5)))}{3 + ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (64 - (8 - 5))}{(3 \times (2 \times 9)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (64 + 85)}{3 + (297 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - ((4 - 8) \times 5)}{(3^2) + (9 \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{16 \times (4 + (8 - 5))}{(3 + 29) \times (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 + ((4 \times 8) + 5)}{(3^2) + (97 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 + (48 \times 5)}{32 \times (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{16 + 485}{32 + 970}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16490}{53278} := \frac{1 - 6 + 490}{(5 \times 3)^2 \times 7 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{20358} := \frac{1^6 - 4 + 97}{2 \times (0 \times 3 + 58)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{25380} := \frac{(1^6 + 4) \times 9 + 7}{2 - 5 + 3 + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (4 - 9 + 7)}{2 \times (5 - 3 + 8) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 6 + 4 \times 9 \times 7}{2 \times 5 \times 38 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(16 + 4 \times 9) \times 7}{(2 \times 5 - 3) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 - 4)^9 + 7}{(2 + 5 + 3) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{16 \times (4 + 9) \times 7}{(25 + 3) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{25803} := \frac{1 + (6 - 4 + 9) \times 7}{2 + 5 \times 8 \times 03}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{37908} := \frac{1 \times 6 + (5 + 2) \times 4}{3 - 7 + 90 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6^{5-2} + 4}{3 + 7 \times 9 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{38097} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (5 - 2) \times 4}{(3 + 80) \times (9 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 5)^2 \times 4}{(3 + 80) \times (9 + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{39780} := \frac{(1 \times 6 - 5 + 2)^4}{3 \times (9 + 7 \times 8) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{79380} := \frac{1 - 6 + 52 + 4}{7 \times (9 \times 3 + 8) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{97308} := \frac{1 + 6 + 52 + 4}{9 \times 7 + 308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16530}{42978} := \frac{((1 + 6) \times 5) + 30}{4 + ((2 + 9) \times (7 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^6) \times (5 \times 30)}{(4 + 2) \times (9 + (7 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (5 \times 30)}{42 \times (9 + (7 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(16 \times 5) - 30}{4 - (2 - ((9 + 7) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (5 \times (3 - 0)))}{4 - (2 - (9 + (7 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (5 \times 30))}{(42 \times 9) + (7 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (5 + 30))}{4 + ((2 \times 9) + (7 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 + (5 - 30))}{4 + (2 \times (9 + (7 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 5) \times 30)}{(4 - (2 - 9)) \times 78}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (5^3 + 0))}{((4^2) + 9) \times 78}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (5 + 30))}{42 + (9 \times (7 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (65 \times (3 - 0))}{429 + 78}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (65 - 30)}{4 - (2 - (97 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (5 + (3 - 0)))}{((4 + 2) \times 9) - (7 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{165 - 30}{429 - 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16530}{48792} := \frac{1 - 6 + 5 \times 30}{4 \times (8 + 7 + 92)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16539}{87024} := \frac{(1 + 6 \times 5)^3 + 9}{8 \times 70^2 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + 5) \times 3 \times 9}{8 \times 70^2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16548}{70329} := \frac{1 - 6 + 5 - 4 + 8}{7 + 03 - 2 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 03 \times 2 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 8}{70 + 3 + 29}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 54 - 8}{70 \times 3 + 2 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 8)}{703 + 2 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 5 \times 4) \times 8}{(70 + 32) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16548}{70392} := \frac{165 + 4 \times 8}{70 \times (3 + 9) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16578}{39042} := \frac{1 + 6 \times (-5 + 7 \times 8)}{3 + 90 \times 4 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16578}{49302} := \frac{1 + 6 \times (-5 + 7 \times 8)}{4 + 9 + 30^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16587}{20349} := \frac{1 \times 6 + (5 + 8) \times 7}{203+4 - 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16587}{34920} &:= \frac{1^6 + 5 \times (8 + 7)}{(3 - 4 + 9) \times 20} &:= \frac{((16 + 7) \times 4) - 8}{((2 \times (09)) + 3) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times (6^{7+4-8})}{2 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 65 + 87}{(3 + 4 + 9) \times 20} &:= \frac{((16 - 7) \times 4) - 8}{(2 \times (0 \times 9)) + 35} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (74 - 8))}{2 - (0 - (93 - 5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16587}{93024} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + (5 + 8) \times 7}{9 \times 30 \times 2 + 4} &:= \frac{(1 - ((6 - 7) \times 4)) \times 8}{20 + ((9 - 3) \times 5)} &:= \frac{1 + (6 - (7 - (4 \times 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (9 - 3))) \times 5} \\ & &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - 7)) \times 48}{2 \times (0 + ((9 + 3) \times 5))} &:= \frac{1 + (6 - (7 - (4 + 8)))}{(2 \times (0 \times 9)) + (3 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{25839} &:= \frac{1 + 67 - 04}{2 + 5 + 83 + 9} &:= \frac{(1^{674}) \times 8}{2 \times ((0 \times 93) + 5)} &:= \frac{1 + (6 - (7 + (4 - 8)))}{(2 \times (0 \times 93)) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{16 \times 7 \times 04}{(2 \times 5 \times 8 - 3) \times 9} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 - 4))) \times 8}{2 - (0 - (93 + 5))} &:= \frac{1 + (6 - (7 - 48))}{2 \times (0 + ((9 - 3) \times 5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{38592} &:= \frac{1^6 + 7 \times 04}{3 + 8 \times (-5 + 9) \times 2} &:= \frac{(1 + (67 - 4)) \times 8}{20 \times ((9 \times 3) + 5)} &:= \frac{1 + (67 - (4 + 8))}{(2 - (0 - (9 + 3))) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{52983} &:= \frac{1 + 67 - 04}{5 + 2 \times 9 \times (8 + 3)} &:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (7 \times (4 \times 8))}{20 \times (93 + 5)} &:= \frac{1 + (67 + (4 \times 8))}{(20 \times (9 - 3)) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{89523} &:= \frac{1 + 67 - 04}{(8 + 9 - 5 \times 2)^3} &:= \frac{(16 - (7 - 4)) \times 8}{(20 + (9 - 3)) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 + (67 + (4 - 8))}{20 + ((9 + 3) \times 5)} \\ & &:= \frac{(16 \times 7) + (4 + 8)}{20 + (9 \times (3 \times 5))} &:= \frac{1 + (67 + 48)}{(2 - (0 - (9 \times 3))) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16720}{35948} &:= \frac{1 + 6 - 7 + 20}{3 \times 5 + 9 \times 4 - 8} &:= \frac{1 - (6 + (7 - (4 \times 8)))}{(2 - ((0 \times 9) - 3)) \times 5} &:= \frac{16 \times ((7 + 4) \times 8)}{20 \times (93 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7 \times 20}{3 \times (594 + 8)} &:= \frac{1 \times (((6 + 7) \times 4) + 8)}{(2 \times (09)) - 3) \times 5} &:= \frac{16 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8)}{20 \times (9 + (3 \times 5))} \\ & &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 - (7 - 4)) \times 8)}{2 \times ((0 \times 9) + (3 \times 5))} &:= \frac{16 + (7 \times 48)}{20 \times ((9 \times 3) - 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16724}{50398} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 72 - 4}{5^{03} + 98} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 4)) + 8)}{20 \times (9 - (3 - 5))} &:= \frac{16 + 748}{20 + 935} \\ & &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 74) + 8)}{(20 + 93) \times 5} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16748}{20935} &:= \frac{((1 - (6 - 7)) \times 4) + 8}{2 + (0 - (9 \times (3 - 5)))} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 74) - 8)}{(20 \times (9 \times 3)) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{20349} := \frac{1 - (6 - 7) \times (5 + 8)}{2 - 03 \times (4 - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (6 - 7))^4) \times 8}{(20 + (9 + 3)) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + (7 \times 4)) \times 8)}{20 \times (9 + (3 + 5))} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7 + 5 \times 8}{2 + 0 \times 3 + 49} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6) + 7) \times (4 \times 8)}{(2^{09-3}) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 7) \times (4 \times 8))}{(2^{09}) + (3 + 5)} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 7 \times (5 + 8)}{2^{03+4} - 9} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (6 \times 7)) \times 4) + 8}{(2 \times (-09)) + (3^5)} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 7) \times (4 + 8))}{(20 \times 9) + (3 \times 5)} &:= \frac{1 + 67 + 58}{2 \times 03^4 - 9} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 6) \times (7 \times 4)) - 8}{(20 \times (9 + 3)) - 5} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (7 \times (4 + 8)))}{2 \times (0 + (9 \times 35))} &:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 7) \times (5 + 8)}{(20 - 3) \times (4 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(1+67-5) \times 8}{2 \times 034 \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(1-(6-(7+5))) \times 8}{(4 \times (3-(0 \times 9)))^2}$	$:= \frac{(1^6) \times (7-(9-4))}{(5 \times (0 \times 3)) + (8-2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{23940} := \frac{(((1+6)^{7-5}) \times 8)}{(2+(3+9)) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{(1^6) + (75+8)}{4 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^6) \times (7+(9 \times 4))}{50-(3-82)}$
$:= \frac{((1^6)-(7-(5+8)))}{(2+(3+(9-(4-0))))}$	$:= \frac{1+((6 \times (7-5))+8)}{43-(0-(9+2))}$	$:= \frac{(1^6)+((7 \times 9)-4)}{5 \times (0+(38-2))}$
$:= \frac{((1+(6+7)) \times (5^8))}{((2+3)^9) \times (4-0)}$	$:= \frac{1+((6 \times (7 \times 5))-8)}{430+92}$	$:= \frac{(1^6)+(7+(9+4))}{50+(3+(8+2))}$
$:= \frac{((1+(6+7)) \times 58)}{(2+(3 \times 9)) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{(1^6)-(7-(5+8))}{4+(3-(0-(9+2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1+(6+(7-9))) \times 4}{50-((3-8) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{((1+6) \times ((7+5) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((3+9) \times 40))}$	$:= \frac{(16+(7+5)) \times 8}{4 \times ((3-(-09))^2)}$	$:= \frac{1-((6-7) \times (9-4))}{5-(0-(3+(8+2)))}$
$:= \frac{((16+(7+5)) \times 8)}{(2-(3-9)) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{(1+6) \times ((7 \times 5)+8)}{43 \times ((09 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{1-(6-(7 \times (9+4)))}{((5+(-03))^8)+2}$
$:= \frac{(1-((6-(7+5)) \times 8))}{(2 \times (39-(4-0)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{92340} := \frac{(1+6)^{7-5} \times 8}{9 \times 2 \times 3 \times 40}$	$:= \frac{1-(6-(7 \times (9-4)))}{5-(0-(3+82))}$
$:= \frac{(1-((6-7) \times (5+8)))}{((2 \times (3+9))-(4-0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{93024} := \frac{1-(6-7-5) \times 8}{9 \times 30-2+4}$	$:= \frac{1-(6-(7+(9+4)))}{5 \times (0+(3+(8-2)))}$
$:= \frac{(1-(6-(7+(5 \times 8))))}{(((2 \times 3)+9) \times (4-0))}$	$:= \frac{1+6+7 \times (5+8)}{9 \times 30 \times 2+4}$	$:= \frac{1-(6-(7+(9-4)))}{(5 \times (03))+(8-2)}$
$:= \frac{(1 \times (67-(5-8)))}{(2 \times 3)+(94-0)}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1-(6-(79+4))}{((5^{03})-8) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{(1+((6 \times (7-5))+8))}{(2-(3+(9-40)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16790}{28543} := \frac{1-(6-7) \times 9+0}{2+8-5+4 \times 3}$	$:= \frac{1-(6+((7-9) \times 4))}{(5 \times (03))-(8-2)}$
$:= \frac{(1+((6+(7 \times 5)) \times 8))}{((2+3) \times (94-0))}$	$:= \frac{(1+6) \times 7-9+0}{2 \times 8 \times 5-4 \times 3}$	$:= \frac{1-(6+(7-(9 \times 4)))}{5-(0-(3+(8^2)))}$
$:= \frac{(1+(6-(7 \times (5-8))))}{((2^3) \times (9-(4-0)))}$	$:= \frac{1^6+79+0}{2 \times (8+5 \times 4 \times 3)}$	$:= \frac{1-(67-94)}{5+(0-(3-82))}$
$:= \frac{(1+(67+58))}{((2+3) \times (9 \times (4-0)))}$	$:= \frac{(1-6+7) \times 90}{2-8 \times (5-43)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 7)-(9+4))}{5-((0 \times 3)-82)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{30429} := \frac{1-6+7 \times 5+8}{30 \times (4-2)+9}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 7)+(9-4))}{(5^{03})+(8 \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{(1+6) \times (7+5)-8}{30 \times 4+2 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16794}{50382} := \frac{((1-(6-7)) \times 9)+4}{5+(0-(3-(8^2)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((6+(7-9)) \times 4)}{(5-(-03)) \times (8-2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{32490} := \frac{1-(6-7-5) \times 8}{3-2+4+90}$	$:= \frac{(1-(6 \times (7-9))) \times 4}{(50 \times 3)+(8-2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6-((7-9) \times 4))}{(5 \times ((0 \times 3)+8))+2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{43092} := \frac{1-((6-7) \times (5+8))}{4 \times (3^{0 \times 9+2})}$	$:= \frac{(1-(6-7)) \times (9-4)}{5+((0-(3-8))^2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6-(7-(9-4)))}{5+(0-(3-(8+2)))}$
$:= \frac{1-((6-(7+5)) \times 8)}{4+(30+92)}$	$:= \frac{(1^6) \times ((7+9) \times 4)}{(5 \times (0+38))+2}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (79+4))}{50+(38^2)}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 \times (6 + (7 - (9 - 4)))}{5 - (0 - (3 + (8 \times 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (6 + (7 + (9 + 4)))}{(50 - (3 + 8)) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (6 + 794)}{50 \times (3 \times (8 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (67 + (9 + 4))}{5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 \times 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (679 - 4)}{(50 + (3 - 8))^2} \\
 := \frac{1^{6794}}{5 + ((0 \times 38) - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((6 \times 7) + (9 - 4))}{(50 - 38)^2} \\
 := \frac{1 + ((67 \times 9) - 4)}{50 \times (38 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 - (7 - (9 - 4)))}{5 \times (0 - (3 - (8 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 - (7 - 94))}{(50 - 3) \times (8 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6^{7-9+4})}{50 - (3 - (8^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (7 - (9 - 4)))}{(5 \times (0 - (3 - 8))) + 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (7 \times (9 - 4)))}{5 - (0 - ((3 + 8)^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (7 + (9 \times 4)))}{5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (7 + (9 + 4)))}{5 - (0 - (38 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (7 + (9 - 4)))}{(5 \times (0 + (3 + 8))) + 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + (67 - (9 - 4))}{(5^{03}) + (8^2)} \\
 := \frac{16 - (7 - (9 \times 4))}{(5^{03}) + (8 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{16 \times (7 + (9 + 4))}{5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8^2)))} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16805}{73942} := \frac{(1 + (6 - 8)) \times (-05)}{7 - (3 - (9 \times (4 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (8 + (-05)))}{(7 + (3 \times (9 - 4))) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (8 - (0 \times 5)))}{73 + (9 - (4^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (6 + (8 - (-05)))}{7 + (39 + 42)} \\
 := \frac{(16 - (8 - 0)) \times 5}{((7 \times (3 + 9)) + 4) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{((1^6) + (8 - 0)) \times 5}{7 + (3 + (94 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (6 + (8 - 0))) \times 5}{((73 + 9) \times 4) + 2} \\
 := \frac{(1^6) \times (80 + 5)}{(7 - 3) \times 94 - 2} \\
 := \frac{16 \times (8 \times (05))}{((7^3) + 9) \times (4 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (6 + (8 \times (-05)))}{7 + (3 + (9 \times (4^2)))} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (6 \times (8 - 0))) \times 5}{7 \times ((39 \times 4) - 2)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 6) \times (8 \times (05))}{7 + ((39 - 4)^2)} \\
 := \frac{(16 + 80) \times 5}{((7^3) + 9) \times (4 + 2)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16807}{94325} := \frac{1 + 6 \times 8 + 0 \times 7}{94 \times 3 - 2 - 5} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times 6 + 8) \times 07}{(9 \times 4 \times 3 + 2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 6 \times 8) \times 07}{(9 \times 43 - 2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8 \times 07}{9 + 4 + 3^{2+5}} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16830}{49572} := \frac{(1 - 6) \times (8 - 30)}{4 \times (95 - 7 \times 2)} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{168 - 3 + 0}{495 - 7 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16830}{49725} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8 + 30}{4 + 9 \times (7 + 2 + 5)} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 6) \times (8 - 30)}{(4 + 9 \times 7 - 2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{168 + 30}{(4 + 9) \times (7 + 2) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16830}{95472} := \frac{168 - 3 + 0}{9 \times (5 + 47) \times 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16835}{24790} := \frac{1 - (6 - 8 \times 3) \times 5}{2 \times (4 + 7 \times 9) + 0} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16842}{95037} := \frac{1 \times 6 - 8 + 4^2}{9 \times (5 + 03) + 7} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 6) \times (8 \times 4 + 2)}{9 \times 50 \times 3 - 7} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16872}{39045} := \frac{16 + 8 \times 72}{(3 \times 90 + 4) \times 5} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16905}{74382} := \frac{(1^6) \times (9 \times (05))}{(7 \times (4 + (3 \times 8))) + 2} \\
 := \frac{(1^6) + (9 + (-05))}{7 - (4 - (3 + (8 \times 2)))} \\
 := \frac{(16 - (9 - 0)) \times 5}{7 \times (4 + (3 \times (8 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{(16 \times 90) - 5}{(74 + 3) \times 82} \\
 := \frac{1 - (6 - (90 + 5))}{(7 + 4) \times (38 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 90) + 5)}{(7^4) + (3 - (8 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((6 + (9 - 0)) \times 5)}{(7 + 4) \times (3 \times (8 + 2))} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 90) \times 5)}{(7 + 4) \times (3 \times (8^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 - (0 \times 5)))}{7 + (43 + (8 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 + 05))}{7 - (4 - (3 + 82))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 + (-05)))}{(7 + (4 + (3 + 8))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (69 \times (05))}{74 + (38^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((6 \times (9 - 0)) - 5)}{(7 \times 4) + (3 \times (8^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 5)))}{(7 + 4) \times ((3 + 8) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 \times (9 + (-05)))}{((7 + (4 + 3)) \times 8) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (69 - (0 \times 5))}{7 \times (4 + (38 + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (69 + (-05))}{(74 \times 3) + (8^2)} \\ &:= \frac{16 + (9 + 05)}{7 + (4 + ((3 + 8)^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16905}{87423} := \frac{(16 - 9) \times 05}{8 \times (7 + 4^2) - 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16907}{38425} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 9 + 07}{3 + 8 + 4 + 2 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 9 + 07}{(3 \times (8 - 4) - 2) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 69 + 07}{(3 + 8 - 4) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{169 + 07}{(38 + 42) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 6 \times 9) \times 07}{(3 + 8 \times 4) \times 25} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 69 \times 07}{(3 + 8) \times 4 \times 25} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16920}{58374} &:= \frac{1^{69} \times 20}{5 + 8 \times (-3 + 7 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 20}{5 + 8 \times (3 + 74)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16920}{83754} &:= \frac{1^{69} \times 20}{8 + 37 + 54} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - 6 + 9) \times 20}{8 \times (3 + 7) \times 5 - 4} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 69) \times 2 + 0}{(8 + 3) \times 7 \times (5 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 20}{837 + 54} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16932}{54780} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 9 + 3 - 2}{54 - 7 + 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (9 - 3) - 2}{54 + 7 \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 + 9) \times 3^2}{5 \times (4 + 7) \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 9 \times 3) \times 2}{5 \times 4 \times 7 + 80} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (9 + 3 + 2)}{5 \times (47 + 8) + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16938}{25407} &:= \frac{((1 - (6 - 9))^3) + 8}{2 \times (54 - (0 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6)^9) - (3 - 8)}{2 + ((5 - (4 - 0)) \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6) + 9) \times 38}{2 \times (5 + (40 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (9 + 3))) \times 8}{(2 - 5) \times (4 \times (-07))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - 93)) \times 8}{(2^5) \times (40 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^6) + (9 + 38)}{25 + (40 + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times ((9 - 3) \times 8)}{((2^5) + 40) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + 6) \times (9 - (3 - 8))}{(25 - (4 - 0)) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{(16 \times 9) + 38}{((2 + 5) \times 40) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{(16 - 9) \times (3 \times 8)}{((2^5) + (4 - 0)) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (6 - ((9 \times 3) - 8))}{(2 + (5 - (4 - 0))) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (6 - (9 + (3 \times 8)))}{((2 \times 5) - (4 - 0)) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (6 - (9 + 38))}{2 + (54 - (-07))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (6 + (9 \times (3 - 8)))}{(2^5) - (4 \times (-07))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (6 + (9 - 38))}{25 + (4 - (-07))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (69 \times (3 - 8))}{(2^{5+4+0}) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (9 \times 3)) - 8)}{(2 + 5) \times (40 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (9 - 3)) + 8)}{2 \times (5 - (4 \times (-07)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((6 \times 93) - 8)}{25 \times (40 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 - (9 + (3 - 8)))}{2 + (5 - (4 - (0 \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((9 - 3) \times 8))}{25 + 407} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (9 - (3 - 8)))}{2 \times ((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 - (3 + 8)))}{(2 \times 5) - (4 - (0 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 - (3 - 8)))}{2 - (5 - (40 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (9 + (3 - 8)))}{2 + ((5 \times (4 - 0)) - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (((6 + 9) \times 3) - 8)}{2 + (5 \times (4 - (-07)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 - (9 - (3 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (5 \times (4 - 0))) - 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 - (9 - 38))}{2 + (5 + (40 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{16 - (9 + (3 - 8))}{2 + (5 + (4 - (-07)))}$$

$$:= \frac{169 - (3 + 8)}{2 + (5 \times (40 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{169 - (3 - 8)}{254 - (-07)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (9 - 5) - 4}{70^2 + 38}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (9 - 5) + 4}{70 \times 2 - 3 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 9 + 5 \times 4}{70 \times 2 - 3 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16954}{78023} := \frac{1 + 6 + 95 - 4}{7 \times 8^{02} + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16983}{25704} := \frac{1 + 6 \times 98 + 3}{2^5 \times 7 \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16983}{27540} := \frac{16 + 98 - 3}{(2 + 7) \times 5 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 9 \times 8 \times 3}{(2 \times 7 - 5) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 6) \times (9 - 83)}{2 \times 75 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 6 \times 98 + 3}{2 \times (7 + 5) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16940}{35728} := \frac{1 + 69 + 40}{(3 \times 5 + 7 \times 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6 \times 9) \times 4 + 0}{(3 + 57 - 2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16940}{72358} := \frac{16 \times 9 - 4 + 0}{(7^2 - 3) \times (5 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{25830} := \frac{1 + 6 + (9 - 7)^4}{2 - 5 + 8 + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + 9) \times (7 - 4)}{2^5 + 8 + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 9 + 7) \times 4}{2 \times (5 \times 8 + 30)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17024}{93856} := \frac{1 \times 70 + 2 + 4}{(93 - 8) \times 5 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{30258} := \frac{1 + 6 + (9 - 7)^4}{3 - 02 + 5 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{32085} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 9 + 7 \times 4}{(3 + 20 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{53820} := \frac{1 + 6^{9-7} + 4}{5 \times (3 \times 8 + 2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{43956} := \frac{1 + 7 \times (-02 + 8)}{4^3 - 9 + 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{49536} := \frac{(1^7 + 0) + (2 + 8)}{((4 + 9) \times (5 - 3)) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16952}{78403} := \frac{(1^6) \times (9 + (5 + 2))}{78 - (4 - (0 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((9 - 5) \times 2))}{(78 - (4 - 0)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (6 - (9 + 52))}{7 - (84 \times (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (9 + (5 - 2)))}{(7 \times (8 + 40)) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (6 + (95 + 2))}{78 + 403}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((6 \times 9) + 5)) \times 2}{(7 + 8) \times (40 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{16 \times ((9 + 5) \times 2)}{7 \times (8 \times (40 - 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16975}{38024} := \frac{1 - 6 + (9 + 7) \times 5}{3 \times (80 - 24)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 6 + 9) \times 7 - 5}{3 \times 80 - 2^4}$$

$$:= \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 75}{(380 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16975}{83420} := \frac{(1 + 69) \times (7 - 5)}{8 + 34 \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 + (0 - 28))}{49 - (5 \times (3 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{17 - (0 - (2 \times 8))}{4 \times (9 - (5 \times (3 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (70 - (2 \times 8))}{4 \times (9 - (5 - 36))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (70 - (2 - 8))}{4 \times (9 + (53 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (70 + 28)}{4 \times (9 \times (5 - (3 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((70 \times 2) - 8)}{(49 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{170 - (2 - 8)}{4 \times (9 + ((5^3) - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{170 + 28}{4 \times ((9 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16954}{70238} := \frac{1 + 6 - 9 + 5 + 4}{7 + 02 \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1^6 - 9 + 8^2}{70 + 3 \times 54}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{93456} := \frac{1 + 7 \times (-02 + 8)}{9 + 3 + 4 \times 56}$$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{93654} &:= \frac{(1+70) \times 2 - 8}{9 + ((3^6) - (5-4))} \\ &:= \frac{((1-7) \times (-02)) + 8}{(9^3) + (6 - (5^4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (-02))) \times 8}{9 - (3 - 654)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^7 + 0) \times 28}{93 + (65 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (-02))) \times 8}{(9 - 3) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (70 - 2)) \times 8}{((9^3) + (6 \times 5)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (0 - (2 \times 8))}{(9 + 3) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (7 + (0 - (2 + 8)))}{(9 \times (3 - (6 - 5))) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (7 + (0 - 28))}{(9 \times ((3 \times 6) - 5)) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 - (-02)) \times 8)}{(9 + (3 \times (6 \times 5))) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times (02)) - 8)}{93 - (6 + 54)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((70 \times 2) + 8)}{(9 \times (3 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((70 \times 2) - 8)}{(9^3) + (6 - (5 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 8))}{(9 + (3 + 65)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (0 + (2 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (3 + 65)) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (70 - (2 \times 8))}{((9 \times 3) + 6) \times (5 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (70 - (2 + 8))}{9 - (3 - (6 \times 54))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - ((0 \times 2) - 8))}{(9 + ((3 \times 6) - 5)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (2 \times 8)))}{9 + (3 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (2 + 8)))}{9 + (36 + 54)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (2 - 8)))}{9 - (3 - (6 - (5 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 \times 28))}{(9 + (3 - (6 - 5))) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (0 - (2 - 8)))}{(9^{3-6+5}) - 4} \\ &:= \frac{17 \times (0 + (2 \times 8))}{(9 + 365) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{17 \times (0 + (2 + 8))}{936 - (5 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{170 + 2 + 8}{936 + 54} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17034}{68952} &:= \frac{(170 - 3) \times 4}{(6 \times 8 + 9 - 5)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17034}{92685} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 034}{(9 + 2 \times (6 + 8)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{17 \times (0 \times 3 + 4)}{((9 + 2) \times 6 + 8) \times 5} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17043}{62985} &:= \frac{1 \times 70 - 4 + 3}{(6 \times 2 - 9) \times 85} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{34986} &:= \frac{1 \times 70 \times 5 - 2}{(3^4 + 9) \times 8 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{46893} &:= \frac{((1^7 + 0) + 5) \times 2}{4 - (6 - (8 + (9 \times 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^7 + 0) + 5)^2}{4 - (6 - (8 + 93))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - 7) \times (-05)) - 2}{((4 - 6) \times 8) + 93} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (-05))) \times 2}{(4 \times (6 \times 8)) + (9 - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 5))) \times 2}{(4 \times (6 + 8)) - (9 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (70 + 5)) \times 2}{4 + (6 \times ((8 \times 9) - 3))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(17 - (-05)) \times 2}{4 + (((6 \times 8) - 9) \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(17 - (-05))^2}{(4 + (6 - (8 - 9)))^3} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 - (-05)) \times 2)}{4 + (68 - (9 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 - (-05))^2)}{4 \times ((6 \times (8 + 9)) - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (0 - (5^2)))}{4 + (6 \times (8 + (9 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (0 + 52))}{(4 \times 68) + (9^3)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (0 - (5 - 2)))}{46 - (8 + (9 \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 \times 52))}{4 - (6 \times ((8 - 9) \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - 52))}{4 + (68 + 93)} \\ &:= \frac{170 + (5 \times 2)}{468 + (9 \times 3)} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{69384} &:= \frac{17 \times (05) + 2}{6 \times (9 \times 3 + 8 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (7 + 05)^2}{6 \times 9 \times (3 + 8) - 4} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{83496} &:= \frac{17 \times 05 + 2}{(8 + (3 + 4) \times 9) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{89436} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times (05 + 2)}{8 - 9 + 43 \times 6} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{83592} &:= \frac{1 + 706 + 4}{(8 + 35) \times 9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{93528} &:= \frac{1 + 706 + 4}{9 + 3^5 \times 2 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{93852} &:= \frac{((1 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) - 4}{((9 - 3) \times (8 \times 5)) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1^7 + 0) \times (6 \times 4)}{(9 + 3) \times (8 + (5 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^7 + 0) \times 64}{(9 \times 38) + (5 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$
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$:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (-06)))^4}{93 - (8 - (5 - 2))}$		$:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (-08))) \times 5}{((6 + (4 + 9))^2) \times 3}$
$:= \frac{(17 \times (06)) - 4}{(9 \times 3) + (8^{5-2})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17068}{23594} := \frac{1 \times ((7 \times (06)) - 8)}{(2 \times 3) + (5 + (9 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(170 \times 8) + 5}{(64 \times (9^2)) + 3}$
$:= \frac{1 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 4)))}{9 + (38 - (5^2))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (70 + (6 - 8))}{2 + (3 - (5 - 94))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((70 + 8) \times 5)}{6 \times (4 + ((9^2) \times 3))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times (06)) - 4)}{(9 \times (3 \times 8)) - (5 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{170 - 68}{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 9)) + 4)}$	
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4))}{((9 + 3) \times (8 + 5)) - 2}$	$:= \frac{17 \times (068)}{(2 + (3 \times 5)) \times 94}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17094}{52836} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 0 \times 9 + 4}{52 - 8 \times 3 + 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 4)))}{(9 \times (3 + (8 \times 5))) - 2}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (70 \times 68)}{2 \times (35 \times 94)}$	$:= \frac{17 + 09 - 4}{5 \times (2 + 8) + 3 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (70 - (6 + 4))}{(9 + (3 \times 8)) \times (5 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{17 \times ((06 + 8))}{((2 + 35) \times 9) - 4}$	$:= \frac{1 + 7 + 09 \times 4}{5 \times (2 + 8 \times 3) + 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (70 + 64)}{(93 \times 8) - (5 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{17 \times ((0 \times 6) + 8)}{(27^3) + (5 \times (9 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{1 + 70 - 9 + 4}{(5 \times 2 + 8 \times 3) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (706 - 4)}{9 + 3852}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17068}{43925} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 068}{(4 + 3 \times 92) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 + 70 + 94}{528 - 3 \times 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 + (-06))^4)}{9 - (3 - (8 - (5 - 2)))}$		
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - ((0 \times 6) - 4))}{9 - (3 - (8 + 52))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{26934} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{2 + (6 + 9 \times 3) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17205}{46398} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 20 - 5}{4 - 6 \times (3 - 9 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (6 \times 4)))}{9 - (3 - (85 \times 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{29346} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{2 + (9 - 3) \times 4 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17205}{96348} := \frac{1 + (7 + (2 + (-05)))}{((9 - 6) \times (3 \times 4)) - 8}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 4)))}{9 + (3 + (85 + 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{32964} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{3 \times (2 + 9 \times 6) - 4}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (2 + (-05)))}{((9 + (6 - 3)) \times 4) + 8}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 4)))}{93 - ((8 \times 5) - 2)}$	$:= \frac{170 \times (8 - 5)}{(32 + 9) \times 6 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (2 - (-05)))}{9 + (63 + (4 + 8))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 \times 64))}{9 - (3 - ((8 \times 5) - 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{64923} := \frac{1 + (7 + (0 - (8 - 5)))}{6 - (4 - (9 + (2^3)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times (2 - 0)) + 5)}{(9 + (6 + (3 - 4))) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (0 - 64))}{9 + (385 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (0 - (8 - 5)))}{6 + (4 \times (9 + (2 - 3)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (2 - 0))) \times 5}{(9 + ((6 - 3) \times 4)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7^{06-4})}{9 + (38 \times (5 + 2))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (70 - (8 \times 5))}{6 \times (4 + (9 + (2 \times 3)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((7^2 + 0) - 5)}{9 \times (((6 + 3) \times 4) - 8)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 4)))}{93 - (8 + 52)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 8))) \times 5}{(6 + (4 + 9)) \times (2^3)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (2 - (-05)))}{((9 + 63) \times 4) - 8}$
$:= \frac{17 \times (0 + (6 + 4))}{938 - (5 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{((1^7 + 0) + 8) \times 5}{(6 \times (4 \times (9 - 2))) + 3}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (2 \times (-05))}{(96 \times 3) + 48}$
$:= \frac{170 + (6 + 4)}{9 \times ((3 + 8) \times (5 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 - (-08)) \times 5)}{(6 \times (49 - 2)) + 3}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times 2)) \times (-05)}{((96 - 3) \times 4) - 8}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (05)))}{(9 + (6 + 34)) \times 8} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (2 \times (3 + 5)))}{6 - (8 - (94 - 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17253}{40896} &:= \frac{(1 + 7 - 2) \times 5 - 3}{-4 \times 08 + 96} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (20 - 5)}{(9 - (6 - (3^4))) \times 8} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (2 \times 35))}{(68 + 9) \times (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{(1 + 7 + 2 \times 5) \times 3}{4 \times 08 + 96} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 \times 20) + 5}{(9 \times (6^3)) - (4 + 8)} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (2 + (3^5)))}{68 + 940} & &:= \frac{(1 \times 7^2 + 5) \times 3}{4 \times (0 \times 8 + 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 72) \times (-05)}{(9 \times ((6^3) + 4)) + 8} & &:= \frac{1 \times (72 - (3 \times 5))}{((6 \times 8) + 9) \times (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + 725 + 3}{4 \times 08 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & & &:= \frac{1 \times (72 + 35)}{(6 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{(17 + 2 + 5)^3}{(4 \times 08)^{9-6}} \\
 & & &:= \frac{1 + (((7^2) \times 3) + 5)}{6 \times (8 + (94 - 0))} & &:= \frac{1725 + 3}{4^{0 \times 89 + 6}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17235}{68940} &:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 2) + 3) \times 5}{(6 + 89) \times (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + (((7^2) \times 3) - 5)}{(68 \times 9) - 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17253}{86904} &:= \frac{1 + 72 + 5 + 3}{8 \times 6 + 90 \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 7) \times (2^3)) - 5}{(68 - 9) \times (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 \times 2 + 35)}{(6 + (8 - 9)) \times 40} & &:= \frac{(1 + 7)^2 + 5^3}{8 \times 6 + 904} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - 23)) \times 5}{68 \times (9 - (4 - 0))} & &:= \frac{1 + ((7 + (2 \times 3)) \times 5)}{6 \times (8 + (9 \times (4 - 0)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17253}{89460} &:= \frac{1 + 7^2 \times 5 - 3}{(8 + 9 + 4) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 \times 2)) \times (3 \times 5)}{6 + (894 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 - ((2^3) - 5))}{(6 + (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0)} & & & \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (7 - (23 \times 5))}{(6 \times (8 \times 9)) + (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (2 - (3 \times 5)))}{(6 \times 8) + (9 \times (4 - 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17254}{60389} &:= \frac{(((1^7)^2) + 5) \times 4}{6 \times (0 - (3 - (8 + 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (7 + (2 - 35))}{6 + (8 + (94 - 0))} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 - (2 + (3 - 5)))}{68 - (9 \times (4 - 0))} & &:= \frac{(((1^7)^2) + 5)^4}{(60 + 3) \times (8 \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (((7^2) \times 3) + 5)}{(68 \times 9) - (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 + ((2^3) \times 5))}{6 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40)} & &:= \frac{((1 + 7)^2) \times (5 + 4)}{((6^{03}) + 8) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (((7^2) - 3) \times 5)}{(6 + (8 + 9)) \times 40} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (2 \times 35))}{(6 + (8 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0)} & &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (2 \times 5))) \times 4}{(60 \times 3) + (8 \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 23) - 5)}{6 \times (8 \times (9 + (4 - 0)))} & &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (23 - 5))}{68 + (9 \times (4 - 0))} & &:= \frac{1 - (7 - (2 + (5 \times 4)))}{60 - (3 - (8 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + (2 + 3)) \times 5)}{6 \times (8 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} & &:= \frac{17 + (2 + 35)}{6^{8-9+4+0}} & &:= \frac{1 \times (((7^2) + 5) \times 4)}{(60 + (3 \times 8)) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((72 \times 3) + 5)}{68 \times (9 + (4 - 0))} & & & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((2^5) + 4))}{(60 + 38) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (2 - (3 - 5)))}{(6 \times 8) - (9 \times (4 - 0))} & & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (2 + (3 - 5)))}{(6 - (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17250}{36984} &:= \frac{(1 + 7^2) \times 5 + 0}{(36 + 98) \times 4} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (5 + 4)))}{(60 - (3 + 8)) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (2 + (3 + 5)))}{(6 - (8 - 9)) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17250}{39468} &:= \frac{(1 + 7 \times 2) \times 50}{3 \times (94 \times 6 + 8)} & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (2 + (5 + 4)))}{((6 - (-03)) \times 8) - 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (23 - 5))}{(6 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))} & & & &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (25 + 4))}{(6 - ((0 \times 3) - 8)) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (25 - 4))}{6 - (0 - (3 + 89))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times 25) - 4)}{603 + (8 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 - ((2 \times 5) - 4))}{6 + ((0 \times 3) - (8 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (2 \times (5 - 4)))}{(6 \times (0 - (3 - 8))) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (2 + (5 + 4)))}{6 - (0 - (3 \times 89))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (2 \times (5 + 4)))}{(60 \times 3) - 89}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (2 \times (5 - 4)))}{6 - (0 - (38 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (2 + (5 \times 4)))}{6 - (0 - ((3 + 8) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{17 \times (2 \times (5 + 4))}{(60 + 3) \times (8 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17256}{40983} := \frac{1 + 7^{2+5-6}}{4 - 09 + 8 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 7 - 2 + 5 + 6}{40 + 9 - 8 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 7 - 2 + 56}{40 - 9 + 83}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 72 + 5 - 6}{(40 + 9 + 8) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 7 + 2 \times 56}{4 \times 09 \times 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17264}{83590} := \frac{(172 - 6) \times 4}{(8 - 3)^5 + 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{34695} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{(34 - 6) \times 9 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{34965} := \frac{1^7 \times 2^8 + 0}{(3 + 4) \times (9 + 65)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{35964} := \frac{1^7 \times 2 \times 80}{3^5 + 9 \times (6 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7 - 2) \times 80}{35 + 964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{49536} := \frac{17 + 28 + 0}{(4 \times 9 + 5) \times 3 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7 \times 2) \times 8 + 0}{4 \times (95 - 3 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{172 + 8 + 0}{4 \times (9 \times 5 \times 3 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^7 + 2) \times 80}{4 - 9 \times 5 + 3^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{64395} := \frac{1^7 \times 2^8 + 0}{6 \times (4^3 + 95)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{94536} := \frac{(1 + 7 \times 2) \times 80}{9^4 - 5 + 3 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17284}{35960} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2^8 - 4}{(3 + 59) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17284}{95360} := \frac{1^7 + 2^8 + 4}{(9 + 5 \times 3) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17286}{30954} := \frac{1^7 \times 2 \times 86}{309 - 5 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 7 - (2 - 8) \times 6}{3^{09-5} - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17286}{59340} := \frac{1 \times 7 + (2 + 8) \times 6}{5 \times (9 - 3 + 40)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17289}{63054} := \frac{1^{72} \times (8 + 9)}{63 - 05 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 7^2 - 8 + 9}{6 \times (30 + 5 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 7 \times (2 - 8) - 9}{(6 + 30 - 5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17290}{53846} := \frac{17 + 2 \times 9 + 0}{5^3 + 8 \times (4 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17298}{60543} := \frac{((1 + (7 - 2)) \times 9) + 8}{((60 - 5) \times 4) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{((1 - 7) \times 2) + (9 \times 8)}{6 \times (0 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((17^2) - 9) \times 8}{(6^{05}) + (4^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(17^2) \times 98}{(6 - (0 - (5 - 4)))^3}$$

$$:= \frac{(17^2) + (9 - 8)}{6 - (0 - ((5 - 4)^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - ((2 \times 9) + 8))}{6 - ((0 \times 5) - (4^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (2 \times (9 + 8)))}{60 - (5 - 43)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7^2) - (9 - 8))}{6 - (0 - (54 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{6 - ((0 \times 5) - 43)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times (2 + 9)) + 8)}{(60 \times 5) + (4 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times 2 + (9 - 8))}{60 - (5 - (4 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{(6 - (0 - (5 - 4))) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (2 - 98))}{(60 \times 5) + (4^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (2 + (9 - 8)))}{(6 - (-05)) \times (4 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + ((2 \times 9) + 8))}{60 - (5 - (4^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + ((2 \times 9) - 8))}{6 - (0 - (54 + 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17309}{56482} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 3 + 09}{(5 - 6 + 4 \times 8) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{17+30-9}{56+4+8^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{69258} := \frac{1+7^3-4+0}{6 \times 9 \times 25+8}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(7-(3+(5^2)))}{(6+(9-(4-0))) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17324}{69580} := \frac{1-7+32 \times 4}{6 \times 95-80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17342}{95680} := \frac{1+(7+3+4) \times 2}{(9+5+6) \times 8+0}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(7-(35-2))}{6+(94-(-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times (3+5)) - 2)}{6 \times (9 \times (4 - (0 \times 8)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{40986} := \frac{1 \times 7^3 + 2 + 5}{(40+98) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1+73+42}{(9+5-6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7+(3-5))^2)}{6+(94-(0 \times 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{86940} := \frac{(1+7+3) \times 2 \times 5}{(8-6)^9+40}$$

$$:= \frac{1^7+(3 \times 4)^2}{(9-5+6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7+35) \times 2)}{(6+(9 \times (4-0))) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{98406} := \frac{1^7 \times 3 \times 25}{9 \times (8+40) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 73 \times 4 - 2}{(9+5+6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((73+5) \times 2)}{6 \times ((9+(4-0)) \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17328}{69540} := \frac{(1 \times 7 \times 3 - 2) \times 8}{6 \times 95 + 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17352}{69408} := \frac{((1+7) \times (3^5)) + 2}{(6^9-4+0) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (3 - 52))}{(6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{((1+7) \times (3^5)) - 2}{(6^9-4+0) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (3 + (5 - 2)))}{6 \times ((9 \times (4 - 0)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (7 - 35)) \times 2}{(69 - 40) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + ((3+5) \times 2))}{6 + (94 + (-08))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{62985} := \frac{17 \times 3 \times 4 + 0}{6 \times 2 + 9^{8-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{73}) \times 52}{(6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (3 \times (5 + 2)))}{((6 \times 9) - 40) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{65892} := \frac{(1^{73}) + (4 - 0)}{(6 - 5) \times (8 + (9 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (3 - 5)))^2}{((6 \times 9) - (4 - 0)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (3 + (5 - 2)))}{((6+9) \times (4-0)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{17 - (3 + (4 - 0))}{(6 \times (5 - (8 - 9))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (7 + 3)) \times (5 \times 2)}{(6 + (9 + 40)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (73 - (5 + 2))}{6 \times ((9 \times (4 - 0)) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (3 + (4 - 0)))}{6 - (5 - (8 \times (9 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (73 \times 5)) \times 2}{(6 + (9 \times 40)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times 3) + 52)}{(6 - (9 - 40)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 3) + (4 - 0))}{6 + (5 - (8 - 92))}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 + 3) \times (5 \times 2)}{(6 + (94 - 0)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (3 + (5 - 2)))}{(6 - (9 - (4 - 0))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^7) + (34 - 0)}{(6 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 + 3) \times (5 - 2)}{6 \times ((9 - (4 - 0)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times ((3 \times 5) + 2))}{(6 + 9) \times (4 \times (08))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{73}) \times 40}{65 + (89 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 \times 2)))}{(6 - 9) \times (4 \times (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (3 \times (5 + 2)))}{(6 + 9) \times (40) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^7) \times (3 \times 40)}{6 \times (58 + (9 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (3 \times (5^2)))}{69 \times (4 - (0 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (3 + (5 + 2)))}{(69 \times (4 - 0)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 \times 3) + (4 - 0)}{(6 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 + 2)))}{(6 + 9) \times (4 - (0 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (3 \times (5 \times 2)))}{(6 + (9 + (4 - 0))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (73 - (4 - 0))}{((6 \times 5) + 8) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 - 2)))}{(6 - 9) \times (4 + (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (3 \times (5 \times 2)))}{(6 + (9 + (4 - 0))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (3 \times (5 - 2)))}{((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (3 + (5 - 2)))}{(6 - (9 + 4)) \times (-08)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (35 + 2))}{(6 + 9) \times (4 - (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (73 - (5 + 2))}{(69 \times (4 - 0)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{17 \times (3 \times (5 - 2))}{6 \times (94 - (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{173 + (5 + 2)}{(6 + 9) \times (40 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{173 + (5 - 2)}{(6 - 94) \times (-08)}$$

$$:= \frac{1735 + 2}{6940 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1735 - 2}{6940 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17360}{52948} := \frac{17 - 3 + 6 + 0}{5 + (2 + 9 - 4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 7 \times 3 + 60}{5 \times 2 \times (9 + 4) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 73 + 6 + 0}{(5 + 2) \times 9 \times 4 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1^7 \times 3 \times 60}{5 + 2^9 + 4 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 7 - 3) \times 60}{(52 + 9) \times (4 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17380}{29546} := \frac{1 + ((7 \times 3) + (8 - 0))}{2 + (95 - 46)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - 3)) \times (8 - 0)}{2 - ((9 - (5 \times 4)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((7 \times 3) - 80)}{((29 - 5) \times 4) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{73}) \times 80}{(2 \times (9 \times 5)) + 46}$$

$$:= \frac{17 + (3 + 80)}{2 \times (95 - (4 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 + 3) \times (8 - 0)}{2 - ((9 - 54) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 \times (3 - 80))}{2 \times (9 \times (5 + 46))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^7) \times 380}{2 + ((9 + 5) \times 46)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17385}{20496} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 3 + 85}{2^{04} + 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17385}{29640} := \frac{1 + (7 - 3 + 8) \times 5}{2 \times 9 \times 6 - 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17395}{62480} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (3 + 9 - 5)}{(6 + 2^4) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 - 3) \times (9 + 5)}{624 + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17402}{63958} := \frac{1 + 74 + 02}{6 + 3 \times 95 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17420}{39865} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 4 + 20}{(3 \times 9 - 8) \times 6 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17420}{63985} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 4 + 20}{6 \times (39 - 8) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17430}{25896} := \frac{1 + 74 + 30}{2 + 58 + 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{26390} := \frac{1 \times 7 - 4 + 5 \times 8}{26 + 39 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{62930} := \frac{1 \times 7 - 4 + 5 \times 8}{62 + 93 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7 - 4)^5 + 8}{(6 - 2) \times 930}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{69230} := \frac{1 \times 74 + 5 + 8}{69 \times (2 + 3) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{96320} := \frac{17 - 4 \times (5 - 8)}{9 \times 6 \times 3 - 2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 7 - 4) \times 58}{(9 - 6) \times 320}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 74 + 5 + 8}{96 \times (3 + 2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17460}{39285} := \frac{((1 - 7) \times 4) + 60}{3 - (9 - (2 + 85))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{74}) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - 4)) \times (6 - 0)}{3 + (9 + (2 + (8 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (4 \times (6 - 0))}{392 + (8 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (46 - 0)}{3 \times (92 \times (8 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (4 - (6 - 0))}{3^{9-2 \times (8-5)}}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 \times 4) + 60}{3 \times (9 + (2 + 85))}$$

$$:= \frac{(17 \times 4) - 60}{3 + (9 + (2 \times (8 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (4 + (6 - 0)))}{3 \times (9 - (2 \times (8 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (46 - 0))}{(3 + (9 - (2 - 8))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 60)}{3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 60))}{3 \times (9 \times (28 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (74 - (6 - 0))}{3 \times (9 + (2 + (8 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (74 + (6 - 0))}{3 + (92 + 85)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{3 \times (9 + (2 + (8 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + 60))}{3 \times (9 \times (2 \times (8 - 5)))}$$

$:= \frac{174 \times (6-0)}{3 \times (9 \times (2+85))}$	$:= \frac{((1-7) \times (4-6)) - 9}{5 \times (8 - (2 \times (3-0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((4 \times 6) - 9))}{(5 \times (8^2)) + 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17460}{82935} := \frac{1 - (7 - (4 + (6 - 0)))}{((8 - 2) \times 9) - 35}$	$:= \frac{((17 - 4) \times 6) + 9}{(5 \times (8^2)) - 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 - (6 - 9)))}{(5 \times (8 \times 2)) - 30}$
$:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (4 - (6 - 0))}{8 + ((2 \times (9 \times 3)) - 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (4 - 6))) \times 9}{(5 + (8 + 2)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + (6 + 9)))}{5 + (82 + (3 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - 4)) \times (6 - 0)}{82 + ((9 \times 3) + 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (7 + 4)) \times (6 - 9)}{(5 \times 8) + (2 \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + (6 - 9)))}{58 + (2 - 30)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{8 \times (2 + (9 + (3 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^{74}) \times 69}{5 \times ((8 \times 2) + 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + 69))}{(5 \times 8) + 230}$
$:= \frac{(17 \times 4) - 60}{8 - (2 - ((9 \times 3) + 5))}$	$:= \frac{(1^7) - (4 - (6 \times 9))}{5 \times ((8^2) - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (46 - 9))}{5 \times ((8 + 2) \times (3 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (4 - 60))}{8 \times (((2 + 9) \times 3) + 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 \times (4 \times 6))) \times 9}{((5 + 8)^2) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (74 - (6 \times 9))}{5 \times (8 + (2 \times (3 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (74 + (6 - 0))}{(82 - (9 - 3)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 \times 6))) \times 9}{5 \times ((8^2) \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (74 - (6 + 9))}{5 \times (8 + (2 + 30))}$
$:= \frac{((1 + 7) \times 4) + 60}{(8 \times (2 \times (9 \times 3))) + 5}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 - 4)) \times 69}{5 \times (8 \times (23 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{174 + (6 + 9)}{(5 + (8 \times 2)) \times 30}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{(8^2) + ((9^3) + 5)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (74 - 6)) \times 9}{(5 + (8^2)) \times 30}$	
$:= \frac{(17 - 4) \times 60}{((82 \times 9) + 3) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(17 + (4 \times 6)) \times 9}{5 \times (82 \times (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17493}{28560} := \frac{1^7 + 4 \times (9 + 3)}{2 + (8 + 5) \times 6 + 0}$
$:= \frac{(1^{74}) \times 60}{(8 + (2 + 9)) \times (3 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{(17 - 4) \times 69}{(5 + 8) \times 230}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 7 + 4 + 9)^3}{(2 + 8) \times 56 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17460}{92538} := \frac{1 - 7 + 46 + 0}{92 + 5 \times 3 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 - ((7 \times (4 - 6)) - 9)}{5 \times (8 + (2^3 + 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17493}{65280} := \frac{(1 - 7 + 4 + 9)^3}{(6 + 5 \times 2) \times 80}$
$:= \frac{17 \times (4 + 6) + 0}{925 - 3 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (4 \times (6 + 9)))}{5 \times (8 - (2 - 30))}$	
	$:= \frac{1 - (7 - (4 \times 69))}{5 \times ((8 - 2) \times 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{20385} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 4) \times 9 \times 6}{20 \times 38 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17469}{58230} := \frac{(((1^7) + 4)^6) \times 9}{(5^{8-2}) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 - (7 \times (4 - (6 + 9)))}{5 \times (82 - 30)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{23085} := \frac{1 - 7 + 49 \times 6}{2 \times (30 + 8) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 4) + 6) \times 9}{((5 \times 8) - 2) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((74 + 6) \times 9)}{5 \times (8 \times (2 \times 30))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{28350} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 4) \times 9 \times 6}{(2 + 8)^3 + 50}$
$:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 4) - 6) \times 9}{(5 + 8) \times (2 \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (4 - (6 + 9)))}{(5 \times (8 - 2)) + 30}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 7 \times (4 - 9)) \times 6}{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}$
$:= \frac{((1^7) + (4 + 6)) \times 9}{(5 + (8 - 2)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (4 + (6 - 9)))}{5 - (8 - (23 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{32805} := \frac{1 + (7^{4-9+6})}{3 \times (2 + (8 + (-05)))}$
$:= \frac{((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6) + 9}{(5 \times (8 \times 2)) + 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (4 - 69))}{5 \times (8 \times (2 \times (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 - (7 + ((4 - 9) \times 6))}{3 \times (2 + (8 - (-05)))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + (4 - 9))^6)}{(32 - (8 - 0)) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 - ((7 \times (4 - 9)) - 6)}{(5 \times (8 \times 3)) + 20} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17523}{84960} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 5^2) \times 3}{8 \times 4 \times (9 + 6) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (74 + (9 \times 6))}{3 \times (2 \times (8 \times (05)))} &:= \frac{1 \times (((7 - 4) \times 9) + 6)}{5 \times ((8 + 3) \times (2 - 0))} & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times ((4 \times 9) - 6)}{3 \times (2 \times (80 - 5))} &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + (4 - 9)) \times 6)}{5 \times (8^{3-2+0})} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17540}{69283} := \frac{1^7 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{69 + 2 \times (8 - 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 \times 9))) \times 6}{3 \times ((2 \times 80) + 5)} &:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (4 - (9 - 6)))}{5 - (8 - (3 + 20))} & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (49 + 6)}{3 \times (280 - 5)} &:= \frac{1 \times (74 \times (9 - 6))}{((5 \times 8) - 3) \times 20} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17543}{92680} := \frac{1 - 7 - 5 + 4^3}{(9 + 26) \times 8 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{74}) + (9 + 6)}{3 \times (2 + (8 - (0 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 - (9 - 6)))}{5 + (8 - (3 - 20))} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 5^4 + 3}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (4 - 9))) \times 6}{3 + (2 + (80 \times 5))} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4^{9-6}))}{5 \times (8 \times (3 \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{1 + 75 \times 4 \times 3}{(9 - 2) \times 680} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 \times (9 \times 6)))}{3 \times (28 \times (05))} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + (9 \times 6)))}{5 \times ((8 \times 3) + 20)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{50328} := \frac{17 + 4^{9-6}}{(5 \times 03)^2 + 8} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + (9 + 6)))}{5 + (83 + (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17563}{84920} := \frac{1 - 7 \times 5 + 6^3}{(8 + 4 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{52380} := \frac{(1 \times 7 - 4) \times 9 \times 6}{5 + 2 \times 3 \times 80} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + (9 - 6)))}{5 \times ((8 - 3) \times (2 - 0))} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{58320} := \frac{((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9) - 6}{5 \times (8 + (3 \times 20))} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 + 96))}{5 \times (8 \times (3^2 + 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17568}{32940} := \frac{1 \times (7 - (5 - (6 + 8)))}{3 \times (2 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 7)^4 \times 96}{5 \times 8^{3 \times 2} + 0} &:= \frac{1 + (74 - (9 \times 6))}{5 \times (8 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{17 + (5 - (6 - 8))}{3 \times (2 + (9 + (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - 49)) \times 6}{((5 \times 8) + 3) \times 20} &:= \frac{1 + (74 - (9 + 6))}{5 \times (8 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{1 - (7 - ((5 \times 6) + 8))}{((3 \times 2) + 9) \times (4 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{74}) \times (9 - 6)}{5 \times (8 - (3 \times (2 - 0)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{82350} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 4) \times 9 \times 6}{(8^2 - 3) \times 50} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + ((5 + 6) \times 8))}{(3 + 2) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{74}) \times 96}{(5 + (8 + 3)) \times 20} & \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 \times 4)) \times (9 - 6)}{58 \times (3 + (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17520}{63948} := \frac{(1 \times 7 - 5) \times 20}{6 \times (3 \times 9 - 4) + 8} &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 56) - 8)}{((3^2) + 9) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - 4)) \times 96}{5 \times (8 \times (32 - 0))} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 52 + 0}{6^3 - 9 + 4 + 8} &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + 56) \times 8)}{3 + (2 + 940)} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 - 4) \times (9 - 6)}{5 \times ((8 \times 3) + (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17520}{86943} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 5 \times 2 + 0}{8 \times (6 \times 9 - 4) - 3} &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (56 + 8))}{(3 + (2 \times 9)) \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 - 4) \times 96}{5 \times (832 - 0)} & \\
 &:= \frac{1 - ((7 \times (4 - 9)) + 6)}{(5 + (8 - 3))^2 + 0} &\blacktriangleright \frac{17523}{40986} := \frac{1 + 7 \times 5 + 23}{(40 - 9 - 8) \times 6} &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times ((5 + 6) \times 8)}{3 \times ((2 + 9) \times 40)} \\
 & & &:= \frac{(17 \times 56) + 8}{(3 + 2) \times (9 \times 40)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(1 - (7 - (5 + 6))) \times 8}{3 + (2 \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 8)}{(3^2) \times (9 \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((7 + (5 \times 6)) \times 8)}{3 + ((2^9) + 40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17568}{43920} & := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 5) + 6) \times 8}{(4 - 3) \times 920} \\
 & := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 5) - 6) \times 8}{(43 - 9) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + 7) \times 56) - 8}{((4^3) - 9) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (7 - (5 + 6))) \times 8}{(4 - (3 - 9))^2 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{(1^{756}) \times 8}{(4 - (3 - 9)) \times (2 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{(1^7) - (5 - (6 \times 8))}{(4 \times (3 \times 9)) + (2 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{(1^7) + (5 + (6 \times 8))}{43 + (92 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((7 + 5) \times 6)) \times 8}{(4^3 + 9) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 + (5 + 6))) \times 8}{4 \times (3 + (92 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(17 + (5 - 6)) \times 8}{(4 + (3 + 9)) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (7 - (56 + 8))}{4^3 + (9^2 + 0)} \\
 & := \frac{1 - (7 + ((5 - 6) \times 8))}{(4 \times 3) - (9 - (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (((7 - 5) \times 6) + 8)}{(4 \times (3 + 9)) + (2 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 56) - 8)}{4 \times ((3 + 9) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((7 + 5) \times (6 + 8))}{((4 \times 3) + 9) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((7 + 56) \times 8)}{(4 + 3) \times (9 \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 - (5 - (6 + 8)))}{4 \times (3 + (9 - (2 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 6) - 8))}{(43 \times 9) - (2 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 + (5 - (6 - 8)))}{(4^3) - (9 + 20)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 + 8)))}{((4 + 3) \times 9) + (2 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 - 8)))}{4 + (3 \times (9 - (2 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (7 + (5 + 68))}{(4 - (3 - 9)) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7 - (5 \times (6 - 8)))}{4 + (39 + (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7^{5+6-8})}{(4 + 39) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7 + ((5 \times 6) - 8))}{(4^3) - (9 - 20)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7 + (5 \times (6 \times 8)))}{(4 + (3 \times 9)) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7 + (56 + 8))}{(4 - 3) \times (9 \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{17 + (5 - (6 - 8))}{((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 20} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17582}{30694} & := \frac{1 \times 75 - 8 \times 2}{3 + 06 + 94} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17589}{32604} & := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (5 + 8) - 9}{(32 + 6) \times 04} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 75 + 89}{(3 + 2) \times 60 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17589}{40326} & := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 5 - 8 + 9}{40 + 3^2 \times 6} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17625}{39480} & := \frac{1 - 7 + 6 + 25}{(3 - 9) \times 4 + 80} \\
 & := \frac{(17 + 6 + 2) \times 5}{(39 - 4) \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17639}{28450} & := \frac{1 + 7 + 63 - 9}{(2 \times 8 + 4) \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{53928} & := \frac{1^7 - 6 + 40}{5 \times 3 \times 9 - 28} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (6 + 4) + 0}{5^3 + 9^2 + 8} \\
 & := \frac{(1^7 + 6) \times 40}{(5^3 - 9 \times 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{59283} & := \frac{(1^7 + 6) \times 40}{59 \times 2 \times 8 - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{89523} & := \frac{1 - 7 + 6 + 40}{(8 + 95) \times 2 - 3} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{23850} & := \frac{1 - 7 - 6 + 49}{2^3 - 8 + 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{28305} & := \frac{(17 - 6) \times 4 + 9}{2 + 83 + 0 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{30528} & := \frac{1^7 + 64 + 9}{(3 + 05) \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 76 \times 4 - 9}{(3 + 05)^2 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{53280} & := \frac{1 + 7 \times (6 \times 4 - 9)}{(5 - 3 + 2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 6 \times 4 - 9}{(5 + 3 - 2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{83250} & := \frac{1 + 7 \times (6 \times 4 - 9)}{(8 - 3) \times 2 \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 7 + 64 \times 9}{(8 + 3) \times 250} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17658}{29430} & := \frac{1 - (7 + (6 \times (5 - 8)))}{2 \times (9 + (4 - (3 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (7 - (6 - (5 + 8)))}{(2 \times 9) + (4 + (3 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 \times (76 - 58)}{2 \times ((9 - 4) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 - 8)))}{(2^{9-4}) + (3 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{((1 + (7 - 6))^5) - 8}{(2 \times (9 - 4)) + 30} \\
 := \frac{1 + (7 + (6 + (5 + 8)))}{2 + (9 + (4 + 30))} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times 8)}{29 - (4 - 30)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (7 - ((6 - 5)^8))}{2 + (9 - (4 - (3 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 8))}{2 + (9 \times (4 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (7 - (6 - (5 \times 8)))}{2 \times (9 - (4 - 30))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (7 + ((6 \times 5) + 8))}{2 + (9 + (4^3 + 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 - (5 - 8)))}{2 - (9 - (4 \times (3 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((7 + 65) \times 8)}{(2^{9-4}) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17658}{39240} := \frac{1 + 7 + (6 - 5)^8}{3 + 9 + 2 \times 4 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 76 - 58}{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 76 - 5 \times 8}{3 + 9^2 - 4 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 8}{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (6 - 5 + 8)}{(3 + 9)^2 - 4 + 0} \\
 := \frac{1 + 7 + 658}{(39 - 2) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17680}{53924} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 6 - 8 + 0}{5^3 - 9 + 2 + 4} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 7 - 6) \times 80}{(5 - 3)^9 - 24}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 - 7 + 6 + 80}{5 + 3 \times 9^2 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17682}{54309} := \frac{1 - 7 - 6 + 82}{5 \times (4 + 30 + 9)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (7 + 6)) \times 8 \times 2}{5 \times (4 \times 30 + 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17685}{94320} := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 + (8 - 5)))}{(9 - (4 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (7 - ((6 - 8) \times 5))}{(9 \times 4) + (3 \times 20)} \\
 := \frac{17 - (6 - (8 + 5))}{(9 \times (4 \times 3)) + 20} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (7 + (6 - 8))) \times 5}{(9 - (4 - 3)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{(1^{768}) + 5}{9 + (43 - 20)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (7 + (6 + (8 \times 5)))}{9 \times ((4 \times 3) + 20)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (7 + ((6 \times 8) + 5))}{(9 + (4 + 3)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{1 + (7 + ((6 + 8) \times 5))}{(9 + 4) \times (32 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{17 + (6 + 85)}{9 \times (4 + (3 \times 20))} \\
 := \frac{176 + (8 \times 5)}{9 \times (4 \times (32 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 \times (8 - 5)))}{(9 - (4 - 3))^2 + 0} \\
 := \frac{(17 - (6 + 8))^5}{9 \times ((4 \times 3)^2 + 0)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 7) \times (6^{8-5})}{9 \times (4^{3+2-0})} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17694}{53082} := \frac{((1 + (7 - 6)) \times 9) + 4}{5 - (3 + (0 - (8^2)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{((1 + 7) \times 6) + 94}{(53 \times (08)) + 2} \\
 := \frac{(1^{769}) \times 4}{5 - (3 + (0 - (8 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{(1^7) \times ((6 + 9) \times 4)}{5 \times (30 + (8 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{(1^7) \times (6 + (9 \times 4))}{5 + ((3 - (-08))^2)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (7 + 6)) \times (9 + 4)}{530 + (8 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (7 + 6)) \times (9 - 4)}{(5 + 30) \times (8 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (7 - 6)) \times (9 - 4)}{5 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 8) + 2))} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 7) \times (6 + 94)}{5 \times (30 \times (8 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 7) \times (6 - (9 \times 4))}{530 + (8 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((7 - (6 + 9)) \times 4)}{5 + (30 + (8^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - ((6 \times 9) + 4))}{(5 \times 30) + (8 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 \times (9 - 4)))}{5 + (3 - (0 - (8^2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 + (9 \times 4)))}{(5 \times (30 - 8)) - 2} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 + (9 + 4)))}{5 - (30 - (8^2))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 + (9 - 4)))}{5 \times (3 - (0 \times 82))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 - (6 + 94))}{((5 + 30) \times 8) + 2} \\
 := \frac{1 - (7 \times (6 - (9 + 4)))}{5 \times (3 \times (0 + (8 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (((7 \times 6) + 9) \times 4)}{530 + 82} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((7 - (6 - 9)) \times 4)}{5 \times (30 - (8 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 4))}{(5^3 + 0) + (8 \times 2)}
 \end{array}$$

$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + (6 - 9)) \times 4)}{(5 + (3 - 0)) \times (8 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (76 - (9 + 4))}{(5 \times (30 + 8)) + 2}$	$:= \frac{(17 + (8 - 0)) \times 5}{4 + (((6^2) \times 9) - 3)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 4)))}{5 + (3 - (0 - (8 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{17 - (6 - 94)}{5 + (308 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((7 + (8 - 0)) \times 5)}{(((4 \times 6) - 2) \times 9) - 3}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7^{6-9+4})}{(5 \times (3 - 0)) + (8 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{17 \times (6 \times (9 - 4))}{5 \times (308 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (8 - (0 \times 5)))}{4 + (6 + (2 + (9 \times 3)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (6 + (9 - 4)))}{(5 + (30 - 8)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{17 + ((6 \times 9) + 4)}{(5 \times (3 - (0 \times 8)))^2}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (8 - (-05)))}{4 + (6 \times (2 + (9 - 3)))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (69 + 4))}{5 \times (3 \times (0 + (8 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{17 + (6 + (9 - 4))}{5 - (3 + (0 - 82))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (7 + (8 + (-05)))}{(4 \times (6 + 2)) - (9 - 3)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (76 - (9 + 4))}{(5^3 + 0) + (8^2)}$	$:= \frac{176 - (9 + 4)}{5 + ((30 - 8)^2)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (8 + (-05)))}{4 - (6 - ((2 \times 9) - 3))}$
$:= \frac{1^{7694}}{5 + ((3 \times (0 \times 8)) - 2)}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{17 + (8 - (0 \times 5))}{(4 \times (6 + (2 + 9))) - 3}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 - (6 - 9)) \times 4)}{(5^{3+0 \times 8}) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{34569} := \frac{1 + 7 + 80 - 2}{34 \times 5 + 6 - 9}$	$:= \frac{17 + (8 - (-05))}{4 + (62 + (9 + 3))}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times 6) - (9 + 4))}{5 + (3 - (0 - 82))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{49536} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 8 \times 02}{49 - 5 \times (3 - 6)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 4))}{(5 \times 30) - (8 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{17 \times 8 + 02}{(49 + 5 \times 3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{35964} := \frac{1 + 7 \times 8 - 2 + 0}{3 \times 5 \times 9 - 6 \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 + (6 - 9)) \times 4)}{5 + (30 + (8 \times 2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{93654} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 8 \times 02}{9 \times (3 \times 6 - 5) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{43659} := \frac{(1 - 7 + 8) \times 20}{(4 - 3 + 6) \times (5 + 9)}$
$:= \frac{1 + ((7 - 6)^{9-4})}{5 + (3 + ((0 \times 8) - 2))}$	$:= \frac{17 \times 8 + 02}{9^3 + 6 - 5 - 4}$	$:= \frac{1 + 7 - 8 + 20}{(4 + 3)^{6+5-9}}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 - (6 - (9 + 4)))}{5 \times (3 - (0 - (8 - 2)))}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{1^7 \times 8 \times 20}{(4 + 3) \times (65 - 9)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 \times (6 + (9 - 4)))}{((5^3 + 0) - 8) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17805}{46293} := \frac{(1 - (7 + 8)) \times (-05)}{(4 - 6) \times (2 - 93)}$	$:= \frac{178 + 2 + 0}{(4 + (3 + 6) \times 5) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7^{6-9+4})}{5 + (3 - (0 - (8 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{(1^7) \times (8 \times (05))}{(46 \times 2) + (9 + 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{43956} := \frac{1 \times (7 + 8) \times 2 + 0}{4 \times (3 + 9 + 5) + 6}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (6 - (9 - 4)))}{5 + ((3 - (-08)) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{(1^7) \times (80 + 5)}{(4 \times 62) - (9 \times 3)}$	$:= \frac{17 + 8 + 20}{4^3 - 9 + 56}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (6 \times (9 + 4)))}{((5 - (3 - 0))^8) + 2}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (7 \times (8 - 0))) \times 5}{4 + (6 + (2 + (9^3)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{64395} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 8 - 20}{6 \times 4 + 3 \times 9 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (6 + (9 + 4)))}{5 + ((30 + 8) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (80 - 5)}{(4 \times 6) + ((2^9) \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{65934} := \frac{(1 \times 7 + 8) \times 2 + 0}{6 + 5 \times (9 + 3 \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (6 + (9 - 4)))}{(5 \times (3 - (-08))) + 2}$	$:= \frac{(17 - (8 - 0)) \times 5}{(4 + (6 + 29)) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{1 + 7 - 8 + 20}{6 + 5 + 9 \times (3 + 4)}$
$:= \frac{1 + (7 + (69 + 4))}{5 + ((30 \times 8) - 2)}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (8 \times (-05))}{4 \times (6 \times (29 - 3))}$	$:= \frac{1^7 \times 8 \times 20}{6 \times (5 + 93) + 4}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{178+2+0}{659+3+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{93456} &:= \frac{17+8+20}{9+3+4 \times 56} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{94365} &:= \frac{178-2+0}{943-6-5} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17829}{30564} &:= \frac{1 \times (7^{8+2-9})}{3 \times ((0 \times 56) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + ((8 \times 2) - 9))}{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (6 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (((7+8) \times 2) - 9)}{((3 \times (05)) - 6) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{17 + ((8 \times 2) + 9)}{3 - (0 - (5 + 64))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (7 - ((8^2) - 9))}{((3 \times (05)) + 6) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^7) \times (82 + 9)}{3 \times ((056 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 - (2 - 9)))}{3 \times ((056 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 \times 2) + 9))}{30 \times (5 \times (6 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (8 \times (2 - 9))}{((30 \times 5) - 6) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17829}{56034} &:= \frac{1 \times (7^{8+2-9})}{56 + (0 - 34)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 + ((8 \times 2) - 9))}{(5 + (6 - (0 \times 3))) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (((7+8) \times 2) - 9)}{5 + (60 - (3 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1+7) \times 8) - 29}{5 \times ((6 \times (03)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{17 + ((8 \times 2) + 9)}{(5 + (6 - 0)) \times (3 \times 4)} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17896}{42503} &:= \frac{1 \times 78 - 9 \times 6}{42 + 5 \times 03} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 &:= \frac{17 \times ((8 \times 2) - 9)}{(5 + (6 - 0)) \times 34} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 + (2 \times 9)))}{560 + (3 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{178 + (2 + 9)}{560 + 34} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 - 2) \times 9))}{((5 \times 60) - 3) \times 4} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{26439} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 850}{2 + 6^4 - 39} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{49623} &:= \frac{1 + 7 - 8 + 50}{4 + (9 + 6^2) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{62394} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 850}{62 + (3 + 9)^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{63294} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 850}{6 + 32 \times 94} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{92463} &:= \frac{1 + 7 - 8 + 50}{9 - 2 + 4 \times 63} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17853}{64920} &:= \frac{17 - 8 + 5 - 3}{6 + 4 \times 9 - 2 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{17 + 85 - 3}{(6 - 4) \times 9 \times 20} \\
 &:= \frac{178 + 53}{(6 + 4 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17854}{30962} &:= \frac{178 - 5 \times 4}{30 \times 9 + 6 - 2} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17856}{94023} &:= \frac{1 + 7 \times (8 - 5 + 6)}{9 \times 40 - 23} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17856}{94302} &:= \frac{1 + 7 \times (8 - 5 + 6)}{9 \times 4 + 302} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7 + 8 \times 5) \times 6}{((9 + 4) \times 3)^{02}} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times (8 + 56)}{(9 + 43)^{02}} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17860}{39245} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 8 + 60}{3 \times 9 \times (2 + 4) + 5} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17892}{34506} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (8 - 9))) \times 2}{3^{4+5-06}} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (7 - ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{(3 \times (4 \times (5 - 0))) - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (7 + ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{3^{4-5 \times 0 \times 6}} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^7) \times ((8 \times 9) - 2)}{3 \times (45 - (0 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 + (9 \times 2)))}{345 - (-06)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{3 + (450 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (8 - 92)}{3 \times ((4 + 50) \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17892}{45360} &:= \frac{1 - 7 \times (8 - 9 \times 2)}{4 \times 5 \times (3 + 6) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 7 + 8) \times 9 - 2}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6 + 0} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - 7 + 8 + 9 \times 6}{4 \times 2 + 5^{03}} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - 7 - 8 + 9 \times 6}{42 + 50 + 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\frac{17928}{30456} := \frac{1+78-9-6}{4-2+50 \times 3}$	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{17-9+6-3}{4+08 \times 2+5}$	$\frac{18042}{39576} := \frac{180+4+2}{395+7+6}$
$\frac{17928}{34056} := \frac{1+7+8 \times (9+6)}{4+2 \times 50 \times 3}$	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{17+9 \times (6-3)}{(4+08 \times 2) \times 5}$	$\frac{18042}{39576} := \frac{1+8 \times 04-2}{3^{9-5}-7-6}$
$\frac{17928}{34056} := \frac{1-7+9^2+8}{3 \times 045+6}$	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{1-7+9+63}{(4 \times 08-2) \times 5}$	
$\frac{17928}{63504} := \frac{1+(7+9)^2-8}{(3+40) \times (5+6)}$	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{1 \times 7+9 \times (6+3)}{4 \times (08+2) \times 5}$	$\frac{18054}{29736} := \frac{1 \times 8+05+4}{2 \times ((9-7)^3+6)}$
$\frac{17928}{63504} := \frac{1-7+9^2+8}{6 \times (3+50-4)}$	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{17+96-3}{(40+8+2) \times 5}$	
	$\frac{17963}{40825} := \frac{((1+7) \times 9-6) \times 3}{40+82 \times 5}$	$\frac{18063}{27945} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(2+7 \times 9+4) \times 5}$
$\frac{17936}{54280} := \frac{(1 \times 7+9+3) \times 6}{5^4-280}$	$\frac{17980}{45632} := \frac{17 \times 9-8+0}{4 \times (5 \times 6 \times 3+2)}$	$\frac{18063}{45927} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(4+59) \times (2+7)}$
		$\frac{18063}{47952} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{4 \times (79-5) \times 2}$
$\frac{17940}{28635} := \frac{1+7 \times 9+40}{2 \times (8 \times 6+35)}$	$\frac{17982}{36450} := \frac{1+79-8+2}{3 \times (6+4) \times 5+0}$	$\frac{18063}{49572} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{4 \times (9+(5+7)^2)}$
$\frac{17940}{32568} := \frac{1+(7+9) \times 4+0}{3 \times (2+5) \times 6-8}$	$\frac{17982}{45360} := \frac{17+982}{(45-3) \times 60}$	$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{1+(8-(0 \times 63))}{7-(4-(25+9))}$
$\frac{17940}{63825} := \frac{1+7 \times 9+40}{((6+3) \times 8+2) \times 5}$	$\frac{17982}{53460} := \frac{1+(7-9+8)^2}{5 \times 34-60}$	$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{1+(8-(0-(6+3)))}{7+(4+((2+5) \times 9))}$
$\frac{17940}{83265} := \frac{1+7 \times (9+4)+0}{8 \times 3^2 \times 6-5}$		$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{(1+(8-0)) \times 63}{7 \times ((42-5) \times 9)}$
	$\frac{17985}{32046} := \frac{(1-7+9+8) \times 5}{(3+20) \times 4+6}$	$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{1+(80-(6 \times 3))}{7-((4-(2^5)) \times 9)}$
$\frac{17945}{23680} := \frac{1+7+94-5}{2^3 \times 6+80}$		$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{(1+(8-0)) \times (6+3)}{(7+((4+2) \times 5)) \times 9}$
	$\frac{18023}{49765} := \frac{1 \times 8^{02}+3}{(4-9+7 \times 6) \times 5}$	$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{180 \times (6+3)}{74 \times (2 \times (5 \times 9))}$
$\frac{17952}{34680} := \frac{(1+7+9+5) \times 2}{3-4+6+80}$		$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{18 \times (063)}{74 \times ((2+5) \times 9)}$
$\frac{17952}{60384} := \frac{(1+7+9+5) \times 2}{6 \times 03 \times 8+4}$	$\frac{18032}{94576} := \frac{(18+03)^2}{9+4 \times 576}$	$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{180+(6+3)}{(7-4) \times 259}$
$\frac{17952}{60384} := \frac{1+79+52}{60+384}$		$\frac{18063}{74259} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (063))}{74 \times (2 \times (5+9))}$
	$\frac{18042}{36957} := \frac{180+4+2}{369+5+7}$	$\frac{18063}{74925} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(7 \times 4+9) \times 25}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18074}{63259} &:= \frac{(1^8 + 0) \times (7 \times 4)}{(6 + (3 - 2)) \times (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8 + 0) \times 74}{(6^3) - (2 - (5 \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (-07))) \times 4}{(6^3) - (2 \times (5 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (-07)))^4}{6 + (3 + (2 + (5 \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 0)) \times 74}{(6 + 3) \times 259} \\ &:= \frac{(18 + (-07)) \times 4}{(6 + 3 + 2) \times (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 + (0 - (7 + 4)))}{6 - (((3 - 2)^5) - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (-07)) \times 4)}{(6 + (3^2)) \times (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (07)) - 4)}{(6^3) - (25 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (0 - (7 \times 4)))}{6 \times ((3 \times (2 \times 5)) - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (0 \times 74))}{6 + (3 + ((2 \times 5) + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 7) + 4))}{(63 \times 2) - (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (0 + (7 - 4)))}{((6 + (3^2)) \times 5) + 9} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (80 + (7 \times 4))}{63 \times (2 - (5 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((8 + (-07))^4)}{6 + (3 + (2 + (5 - 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 - (0 - (7 + 4)))}{6 + (3 + (2 + 59))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 - (0 - (7 - 4)))}{6 - (3 \times (2 - (5 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 + (0 - (7 - 4)))}{6 + (3 - (2 - (5 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (80 - (7 - 4))}{(6^3) - (2 - 59)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (80 + (7 + 4))}{6 + (325 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{18 - ((0 \times 7) - 4)}{((6 + 3)^2) + (5 - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{18 - (0 \times 74)}{6 + (3 \times ((2 \times 5) + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times ((0 \times 7) + 4)}{(6 - (3 - 25)) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (0 + (7 \times 4))}{63 \times (2 \times (5 + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (0 + (7^4))}{((6 + (3 - 2))^5) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (0 + (7 - 4))}{6 + (3 \times (2 + 59))} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (0 + 74)}{6 \times (3 \times 259)} \\ &:= \frac{180 - (7 \times 4)}{(6 + 32) \times (5 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{180 \times (7 - 4)}{6 \times ((3 + (2^5)) \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18075}{29643} &:= \frac{(1 \times 8 + 07) \times 5}{2 \times (9 + 6) \times 4 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{52374} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 096}{5 + 2 \times 37 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{73254} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 096}{(7 \times 3)^2 - 5 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18204}{75369} &:= \frac{1 \times 82 \times 04}{7 \times (5^3 + 69)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18207}{35496} &:= \frac{(1 + 8 \times 2) \times 07}{3^5 + 4 - 9 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18207}{96543} &:= \frac{(1 + 8 \times 2) \times 07}{9 - 6 + 5^4 + 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18239}{67405} &:= \frac{1 + 8 + 2 + 3 + 9}{(6 + 7 + 4) \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 2 + 39}{(6 + 7 \times 4) \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 8^2 + 3 \times 9}{(-6 + 74) \times 05} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18239}{70564} &:= \frac{1 - (8 + 2) \times (3 - 9)}{(70 - 5 - 6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18240}{35796} &:= \frac{18^2 - 4 + 0}{3 + 5^{7-9+6}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18240}{93765} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2^4 + 0}{9^3 - 76 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18245}{73069} &:= \frac{1^{82} + 4^5}{(7 - 3)^{06} + 9} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 82 \times 4 \times 5}{(7 + 3^{06}) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18249}{75603} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2 - 4 + 9}{(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 03} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 2 \times 4 - 9}{7 \times 5 - 6 + 0 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18256}{37490} &:= \frac{1^{82} \times 56}{3 \times 7 + 4 + 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18256}{94703} &:= \frac{(18 - 2 \times 5) \times 6}{(9 + 4 + 70) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2 \times (5 + 6)}{(9 + 4) \times 70 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{34965} &:= \frac{1 + 8^2 - 7 + 0}{3 \times (4 \times 9 + 6 - 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{35496} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 27 + 0}{3 + 5 + 4 \times (9 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

	$:= \frac{(1^8 + 2) \times 70}{(3 + 5 \times (4 + 9)) \times 6}$		$:= \frac{18 \times 270}{6 \times 3 \times 945}$		$:= \frac{1 - ((8 + 2) \times (7 - 9))}{3 + ((0 - (4 - 6))^5)}$
▶ $\frac{18270}{45936}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 27 + 0}{4^5 - 936}$		$:= \frac{18 + (2 \times (7 - 0))}{((6 + 3) \times (9 + 4)) - 5}$		$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (2 - (7 \times 9)))}{((3 \times (04)) + 6) \times 5}$
▶ $\frac{18270}{46935}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8^2 - 7 + 0}{4 \times 6 \times (9 - 3) + 5}$		$:= \frac{18 + 270}{63 + 945}$		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (2 - 7)) \times 9)}{3 \times ((0 \times 4) + 65)}$
▶ $\frac{18270}{63945}$	$:= \frac{(1^{82}) \times 70}{(6 + (39 + 4)) \times 5}$				$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (2 + 7)) + 9)}{(3 - (0 - (4 \times 6))) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{(1^{82}) + (7 - 0)}{6 - (3 - ((9 - 4) \times 5))}$	▶ $\frac{18275}{40936}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8 \times 2 - 7) \times 5}{40 + (9 + 3) \times 6}$		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 27) + 9)}{((3^{04}) - 6) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8) - (2 - (7 - 0))}{6 - (3 - (9 + (4 + 5)))}$		$:= \frac{1^{82} \times 75}{(40 - 9 - 3) \times 6}$		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8^2) - (7 + 9))}{(3^{04}) - (6 - 5)}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8) + (27 - 0)}{6 + (3 + (94 - 5))}$		$:= \frac{(1 \times 82 - 7) \times 5}{40 \times (9 \times 3 - 6)}$		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 2) \times (7 \times 9))}{((30 \times 4) + 6) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 270}{(6 + 3) \times 945}$				$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 2) \times (7 + 9))}{(30 - (4 - 6)) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (2 + (7 - 0)))}{((6 - 3) \times 9) - (4 \times 5)}$	▶ $\frac{18279}{30465}$	$:= \frac{(((1 + 8)^2) + 7) \times 9}{30 \times (4 \times (6 + 5))}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - ((2 \times 7) - 9))}{(3 \times (0 \times 46)) + 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (27 - 0))}{(6 + (3 + (9 - 4))) \times 5}$		$:= \frac{((1^{82}) + 7) \times 9}{30 \times (4 \times (6 - 5))}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (2 - (7 - 9)))}{30 + ((4 - 6) \times 5)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (2 + (7 - 0)))}{(6^3) - (9 - 45)}$		$:= \frac{((1^8) + 2) \times (7 \times 9)}{304 + 6 + 5}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (82 - (7 - 9))}{(30 + (4 - 6)) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (2 \times (7 - 0)))}{((6 + (3 + 9)) \times 4) + 5}$		$:= \frac{(1 - (8 - (2 + 7))) \times 9}{3 \times (0 - ((4 - 6) \times 5))}$		$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 2) + (7 - 9))}{(3 + (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (82 - 70)}{6 + ((3 \times 9) + (4 + 5))}$		$:= \frac{(1^8) + ((2 \times 7) + 9)}{30 - ((4 - 6) \times 5)}$		$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (2 + (7 - 9)))}{3 \times (0 + (4 + 6 - 5))}$
	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 2) - (7 - 0))}{6 - (((3 - 9) \times 4) - 5)}$		$:= \frac{(1^8) + ((2 \times 7) - 9)}{3 + (0 - (4 - (6 + 5)))}$		$:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (2 - (7 - 9)))}{(30 \times 4) - 65}$
	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 2) + (7 - 0))}{6 - (3 - (9 \times (4 + 5)))}$		$:= \frac{(1^8) + ((2^7) - 9)}{(30 + (4 + 6)) \times 5}$		$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (2 + (7 + 9)))}{3 \times (0 + (4 + 6 + 5))}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (2 - (7 - 0)))}{6 + (((3 + 9) \times 4) - 5)}$		$:= \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 2) + 7)) \times 9}{3 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 \times 5)))}$		$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (2 + 79))}{3 \times (0 + ((4 + 6) \times 5))}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (2 - (7 - 0)))}{6 - (3 + (9 - (4 \times 5)))}$		$:= \frac{(1 + ((8^2) - 7)) \times 9}{30 \times ((4 \times 6) + 5)}$		$:= \frac{1 + (827 + 9)}{3 \times (0 + 465)}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (2 + (7 - 0)))}{6 + (3 + (9 + 45))}$		$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (2 - 7))) \times 9}{(3 - (-04)) \times (6 \times 5)}$		$:= \frac{18 \times ((2 \times 7) + 9)}{3 \times (0 + (46 \times 5))}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (27 - 0))}{6 \times (3 + 9 + 4 + 5)}$		$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (2 + 7))) \times 9}{(30 + (4 \times 6)) \times 5}$		$:= \frac{18 \times (2 + 79)}{(3^{04}) \times (6 \times 5)}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (82 + (7 - 0))}{6^3 + 94 + 5}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (27 \times 9)}{(3^{0 \times 4 + 6}) \times 5}$		$:= \frac{18 + (27 \times 9)}{((3^{04}) + 6) \times 5}$

	$:= \frac{18 + 279}{30 + 465}$	
▶ $\frac{18297}{40356}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 2 + 97}{4 \times (03 + 56)}$	$:= \frac{(18 \times (3 - 0)) - 6}{2 + (7 + (4 + 59))}$
		$:= \frac{(18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6}{2 + (7 + (4 \times (5 \times 9)))}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (3 + (-06)))}{2 + (7 - (4 + (5 - 9)))}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (83 - (0 \times 6))}{2 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 + 9)))}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (83 - (-06))}{(2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))) + 9}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (83 + (-06))}{(2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))) - 9}$
▶ $\frac{18304}{67925}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8^3 + 0 \times 4}{(6 \times 7 \times 9 + 2) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (3 - (-06)))}{2 - (7 - (4 - (5 - 9)))}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (3 - 0)) \times 6)}{2 + (7 + (45 - 9))}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (3 - (0 \times 6))}{(2 - (7 \times (4 - 5))) \times 9}$
▶ $\frac{18304}{92576}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (30 - 4)}{9 \times (257 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 30) + 6)}{(((2 + 7) \times 4) + 5) \times 9}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 30) + 6)}{(((2 + 7) \times 4) + 5) \times 9}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (3 - (-06))}{((2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5) \times 9}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (3 \times (06))}{2 \times (7 + (4 \times 59))}$
▶ $\frac{18306}{27459}$	$:= \frac{((1^8) + 30) \times 6}{(((2 + 7) \times 4) - 5) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + (3 - 0)) \times 6)}{((2 \times (7 - 4)) + 5) \times 9}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + (3 - 0)) \times 6)}{((2 \times (7 - 4)) + 5) \times 9}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (3^{06})}{((2^{7-4}) - 5)^9}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (30 \times 6)}{27 \times (4 \times (5 \times 9))}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (30 \times 6)}{27 \times (4 \times (5 \times 9))}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (30 + 6)}{27 \times (45 - 9)}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (30 - 6)}{2 \times ((7 \times 45) + 9)}$
		$:= \frac{18 + (30 \times 6)}{27 \times ((4 \times 5) - 9)}$
		$:= \frac{18 + (30 - 6)}{2 + (7 + (45 + 9))}$
		$:= \frac{1830 + 6}{2745 + 9}$
		$:= \frac{1830 - 6}{2745 - 9}$
		▶ $\frac{18306}{92547}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (3 - (-06)))}{(9 \times (2 + 5)) + (4 \times 7)}$
		$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - 0))) \times 6}{(9 \times (25 - 4)) - 7}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (3 - (0 \times 6))}{(((9 - 2) \times 5) + 4) \times 7}$
		$:= \frac{1 + (83 - (-06))}{(9 + (2 + 54)) \times 7}$
		$:= \frac{(18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6}{(92 - (5 - 4)) \times 7}$

$$:= \frac{18 \times (3 - (-06))}{(9 + (2 \times 54)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^8) \times 306}{((9 \times 25) - 4) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (3 - (-06)))}{(9 - 2) \times (5 + 47)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (35 \times 4))}{20 \times ((9 - 7)^6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (3 - (5 - 4)))}{2 \times (0 - (9 - (7 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (3 + (5 + 4)))}{2 - (0 - (9 + (7 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{183 - (5 - 4)}{209 - (7 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((8^3) + 59)}{2 \times ((6 \times 70) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(183 \times 5) + 9}{(2 \times 670) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (3 + 59))}{(2 \times (6 \times (7 - 0))) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18326}{40579} := \frac{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 2 + 6}{4 - 05 + 7 \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times (3 - 2 + 6)}{40 + 5 + 79}$$

$$:= \frac{18 \times (3 - 2 + 6)}{40 \times 5 + 79}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{62790} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 3 \times 5 - 4}{(6 + 2) \times 7 + 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 8^3 + 5^4}{6 \times (2 + 7 \times 9) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{69027} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 35 - 4}{6 \times (90 \times 2 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{76209} := \frac{1 + (8 - 3) \times (5 + 4)}{7 \times (6 + 20) + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{45792} := \frac{1 + 8 \times 3 + 60}{4 \times (5 \times 7 + 9 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{47952} := \frac{1 + 8 \times 3 + 60}{4 - 7 + 9 \times 5^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{49572} := \frac{1^8 + 3 + 6 + 0}{4 + 9 + 5 + 7 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 8 - 3) \times 6 + 0}{(4 \times (9 - 5) - 7)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{1^8 \times 3 \times 60}{495 - 7 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 8 + 3) \times 60}{4 \times 9 \times (5 + 7^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{20769} := \frac{(1 \times 8 \times 3 - 5) \times 4}{20 \times 7 - 6 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{20976} := \frac{((1 + (8 + 3)) \times 5) - 4}{2^{0 \times 97 + 6}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - (8 - 35)) \times 4}{2 \times (0 + ((9 - 7)^6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + ((8 + 3) \times 5)) \times 4}{2^{09 - 7 + 6}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 - 5))) \times 4}{20 + ((9 - 7) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 83) \times (5 \times 4)}{20 \times ((9 + 7) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(18 \times (3 + 5)) - 4}{20 \times (9 - (7 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(18 + 3) \times (5 + 4)}{(20 + (9 + 7)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(18 + 3) \times 54}{(209 + 7) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (35 \times 4))}{2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((8^3) - (5 - 4))}{2 - (0 - (97 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (3 - (5 + 4)))}{2 \times (0 + (9 - (7 - 6)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18359}{26704} := \frac{1 - (8 + ((3 - 5) \times 9))}{2^{(-6 + 7) \times 04}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (8 + ((3 \times 5) + 9))}{2 + ((6 \times (7 - 0)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{18 + (35 - 9)}{2^{6 + 7 \times 0 \times 4}}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (8 - 359)}{2^{6 + 7 - 04}}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - 5))) \times 9}{2 \times (6 + (70 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 3) \times (5 + 9))}{(2 + 6) \times (7 \times (04))}$$

$$:= \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 3) - 5) \times 9}{2 + (6 + (70 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(18 + (3 \times 5)) \times 9}{2 \times (6^{7 - 04})}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (35 \times 9))}{(2^6) \times (7 - (0 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((83 \times 5) - 9)}{(2 + 6) \times (70 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 - 8) \times (3 - (5 + 9))}{(2 - 6) \times (7 \times (-04))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{49725} := \frac{1 + 83 - 60}{4 - 9 + 7 \times 2 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{18 \times 3 - 6 + 0}{4 + 9 \times (7 + 2 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 8 + 3) \times 60}{(4 \times 97 + 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^8 + 3) \times 60}{(4 + 9 \times 7 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{75429} := \frac{(1 + 8 - 3) \times 60}{7 \times 5 \times 42 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{79254} := \frac{1^{83} \times 60}{7 \times (9 + 2^5 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{95472} := \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 - (6 - 0)))}{9 - ((5 \times (4 - 7)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^8) + (3 + (6 - 0))}{(9 - 5) \times (4 + (7 + 2))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{18 + (3 - (6 - 0))}{9 + ((5 \times 4) + (7^2))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 \times (3 - (6 - 0)))}{(9 \times (5 + 4)) + (7^2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 3) \times (6 - 0))}{((9 + 5) \times (4 + 7)) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 + (36 - 0))}{9 - (5 \times (4 - (7^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{18 - (3 - 60)}{(9 + 5) \times (4 \times 7) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) \times (3 \times 60)}{9 \times ((5 + 47) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(18 + 3) \times 60}{(95 - 4) \times 72} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18370}{64295}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((1^8) + 3)^7 + 0}{(64^2) \times (9 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times 3) - (7 - 0)}{6 + (4 \times (2^9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times 3) + (7 - 0)}{64 + ((2 + 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{83}) + (7 - 0)}{6 + ((4 \times 2) + (9 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) - (3 - 70)}{(6 \times 42) - (9 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) \times (3 + (7 - 0))}{6 - ((4^2) - (9 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) + (3 + 70)}{(6 \times (4 \times (2 + 9))) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 3)) \times (7 - 0)}{6 \times ((4 \times (2 + 9)) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 3)) \times (7 - 0)}{6 - (4 - (29 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 - (3 \times (7 - 0)))}{6 - (4 - (2 + (9 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 + (3 - 70))}{6 \times (((4^2) - 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 3) + 70)}{((6^4 - 2) \times 9) + 5} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18390}{25746}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}{(6 + 4) \times (2 \times (9 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 - (7 - 0)))}{6 - (4 \times (2 - (9 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 + (7 - 0)))}{((6 - 4) \times 29) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 3) + (7 - 0))}{(6 + (4 - 2)) \times (9 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 - (3 - 70))}{(6 \times 42) + (9 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 + (3 \times (7 - 0)))}{(6 + (4 + (2 + 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 + (37 - 0))}{64 + (2 + 95)} \\ &:= \frac{18 - (3 - (7 - 0))}{((6 + (4 - 2)) \times 9) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (3 + (7 - 0))}{(6 + (4 \times 2)) \times (9 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{18 + (3 + (7 - 0))}{6 + (4 \times ((2 \times 9) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^8) + 3) \times 90}{((2 \times 5) + 74) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{83}) \times 90}{((2^5) - (7 + 4)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{83}) + (9 - 0)}{2 - (5 - (7 + (4 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) \times (3 \times 90)}{2 + ((5 \times 74) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) + (39 - 0)}{2 + (((5 + 7) \times 4) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 3)) \times 90}{(2 \times 5) + 746} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 - (3 + (9 - 0)))}{25 - ((7 - 4) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (8 + (3 - 90))}{2 + (5 \times ((7 \times 4) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0))}{2 - (5 - ((7 + 4) \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18396}{42705}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (3 - 90))}{2 + ((5^{7-4}) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0)))}{2 + (57 - (4 + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 + (9 - 0)))}{2 \times (5 + (7 - (4 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + ((8 + 3) \times (9 - 0))}{2 - ((5 - (7 \times 4)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 - (3 - (9 - 0)))}{2 + (5 - (7 \times (4 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (83 - (9 - 0))}{2 + (57 + 46)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (839 - 0)}{(2 + 5) \times (7 \times (4 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{18 + (3 + (9 - 0))}{2 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 8 \times 3 + 9 - 6}{(4 + 2 + 7) \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times (3 \times 9 - 6)}{(4 + 2) \times 70 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18423}{76095}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times (84 + (2^3))}{(7 + (60 + 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{84}) \times 23}{(7 - (6 - 0)) \times 95} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (4 \times (2 + 3)))}{760 - 95} \\ &:= \frac{184 + 23}{760 + 95} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 4)) \times 23}{(7 + (6 - 0)) \times 95} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times 23))}{760 \times (9 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (4 \times 23)}{76 \times ((09 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{18432}{76950} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4^{3+2}}{76 \times 9 \times 50}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (4 \times 59))}{(2 + (6 - 3)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{(18 \times (4 + 7)) - 6}{2 \times (30 \times (9 - 5))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{26937} := \frac{1^{84} \times 50}{2 \times (6 + 9 \times 3) + 7}$	$:= \frac{(18 + 4) \times (5 + 9)}{2 + (6 \times (3 + 70))}$	$:= \frac{(18 + (4 \times 7)) \times 6}{((2 \times 30) + 9) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{29736} := \frac{1 + (8 - 4)^5 + 0}{2 \times (97 + 3^6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 + (5 \times 9)))}{(2^{6-3}) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 4) + 76)}{230 - 95}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{37269} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 450}{3 + 7269}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 \times (4 - 59))}{((2 \times 6) - 3) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + (4 \times 7)) \times 6)}{2 \times (3 \times (0 + (9 \times 5)))}$
$:= \frac{(18 + 4) \times 50}{3^7 + 26 + 9}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times (5 + 9)))}{(2^6) \times (3 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 4) \times (7 \times 6))}{2 \times ((30 - 9) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1^8 \times 450}{3 \times (7^2 \times 6 + 9)}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (4 + (5 \times 9))}{2 \times ((6 + 3) \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{2 + (3 - (0 \times 95))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{37296} := \frac{1 + (8 - 4)^5 + 0}{37 \times (2 + 9 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (84 \times (5 + 9))}{(2 + 6) \times (3 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (4 - 76))}{2 + (3 - (0 - 95))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{69372} := \frac{(1 + 8 - 4) \times 5 + 0}{6 + 9 \times (3 + 7) - 2}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 - (7 - 6)))}{2 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times 76))}{(2 + 30) \times 95}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{92736} := \frac{1 + (8 - 4)^5 + 0}{(9 - 2) \times (7 + 3^6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18462}{59730} := \frac{1 + 8 + 4 + 6 - 2}{5^{9-7} + 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{(2 - (3 + (-09))) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{93726} := \frac{1^8 \times 450}{(9 + 372) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 8 \times (4 - 6)) \times 2}{5 \times (9 + 7) + 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 + (7 - 6)))}{2 + (3 - (0 - (9 \times 5)))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18459}{26370} := \frac{1 - (8 - (4 + (5 \times 9)))}{(2^6) + (3 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 - 8 - 4 + 62}{5 \times (9 \times 7 - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (47 + 6))}{2 \times ((30 \times 9) - 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (4 + 59))}{(2 + 6) \times (3 + (7 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18476}{23095} := \frac{((1^8) + 47) \times 6}{(2^3 + 0) \times (9 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (4 \times (7 + 6)))}{((2 \times (3 - 0)) + 9) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (4 - 59))}{2 + ((6 \times 3) + 70)}$	$:= \frac{((18 + 4) \times 7) - 6}{230 - (9 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (4 \times 76))}{2 \times ((30 + 9) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{(1^{84}) \times (5 + 9)}{2 \times (6 - (3 - (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{((18 - 4) \times 7) - 6}{(2 + (30 - 9)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{(2 \times 30) - (9 \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (84 + (5 + 9))}{2 \times (63 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1^{84}) \times 76}{(2 - 3) \times (0 - 95)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (84 \times (7 - 6))}{(2 \times 30) + (9 \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 4)) \times (5 + 9)}{26 \times (3 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (4 + 7))) \times 6}{2 \times (30 + (9 \times 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (84 - 76)}{2 + (3 - ((0 \times 9) - 5))}$
$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (4 \times (5 \times 9)))}{263 + (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 4 - 7)) \times 6}{(2 - 3) \times (0 - (9 \times 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 4) - (7 + 6))}{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 9))) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 4)) \times 76}{(2 + (3 - 0)) \times 95}$	$:= \frac{18 - (4 - (7 \times 6))}{(2 + (3 - (-09))) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{(18 \times (4 + 7)) + 6}{((2 \times 30) - 9) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (4 + (7 \times 6))}{23 \times (0 + (9 \times 5))}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{184 + 76}{230 + 95} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18479}{20653} := \frac{1 + 8 \times (4 + 7 - 9)}{2 \times (06 + 5) - 3} \\
 := \frac{1 - 8 \times (4 - 7) + 9}{2 + 06^{5-3}} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 8) \times 4 + 79}{2 \times 06 \times 5 - 3} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18492}{36570} := \frac{(18 + 49) \times 2}{3 \times 65 + 70} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18495}{20736} := \frac{1 \times 8^4 + 9 + 5}{2^{07} \times 36} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18504}{76329} := \frac{1 \times (8^{5-04})}{7 - (6 - (3 + 29))} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (8 + 5)) \times (-04)}{(7 + (6 + (3^2))) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - 0))) \times 4}{7 \times ((6 - 3) \times (2 + 9))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (5 - (-04)))}{(7 - (6 - 32)) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - 0))) \times 4}{76 - (3 - (2 - 9))} \\
 := \frac{((1^8) + (5 - 0)) \times 4}{7 + (63 + 29)} \\
 := \frac{(1 - 85) \times (-04)}{7 \times (6 \times (3 \times (2 + 9)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 \times 504)}{7 \times ((6^3) \times (2 + 9))} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18506}{47239} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 5 \times 06}{(4 + 7) \times 2^3 + 9}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18526}{97340} := \frac{1 \times 85 - 26}{9 + 7 \times (3 + 40)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18532}{70964} := \frac{(1 \times 85 - 3) \times 2}{70 \times 9 - 6 + 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18534}{92670} := \frac{(1 + (8 + 5)) \times (3 \times 4)}{((9 \times 2) - 6) \times 70} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 534}{9 \times 2670} \\
 := \frac{1 - ((8 - (5 \times 3)) \times 4)}{(9^2) - (6 - 70)} \\
 := \frac{1 - (8 - ((5 - 3)^4))}{9 \times ((2 \times 6) - (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 - (8 \times (5 - (3 + 4)))}{9 \times 2 + (67 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (((8 - 5)^3) - 4)}{(9 \times (2 \times 6)) + (7 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (3 + 4)))}{92 - (6 \times (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (3 - 4)))}{9 + (2 + (6 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 + (3 - 4)))}{9 - (2 - (6 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 + ((5 \times 3) + 4))}{9 \times (2 + (6 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 - (3 - 4)))}{(9 - (2 + 6)) \times 70} \\
 := \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (3 - 4)))}{9 \times 2 + (6 \times (7 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{1^{8534}}{(9^2) - (6 + 70)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (((8 - 5)^3) \times 4)}{(92 \times 6) - (7 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (3 \times 4)))}{9 + ((2^6) + (7 - 0))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (3 - 4)))}{9 - ((2^6) - 70)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 - (5 + (3 - 4)))}{92 - (67 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 \times (5 - (3 - 4)))}{(9 + 26) \times (7 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (3 + 4)))}{9 + (2 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (3 - 4)))}{9 + (2 - (6 - 70))} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 + (5 + (3 + 4)))}{9 + (26 + 70)} \\
 := \frac{1 + (8 + (5 + (3 - 4)))}{9 + ((2 + 6) \times (7 - 0))} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18537}{46092} := \frac{18 + (5 + 3) \times 7}{(-4 + 6) \times 092} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 8 - 5) \times 37}{460 - 92} \\
 := \frac{185 + 37}{4 \times (60 + 9) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{1^{85} \times 37}{(4 + 6) \times 09 + 2} \\
 := \frac{1 + 85 \times (3 + 7)}{460^{9+2}} \\
 := \frac{18 \times 5 \times 37}{460 \times 9 \times 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18540}{93627} := \frac{1^8 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{9 \times 3 \times (6 - 2) - 7} \\
 := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{936 - 2^7} \\
 := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{9 \times (3 \times 6^2 - 7)} \\
 := \frac{1^{85} \times 40}{9 + 3 \times 62 + 7}
 \end{array}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{18543}{60927} := \frac{1+8+5 \times (4-3)}{60-9+2-7}$ $:= \frac{1 \times 8 + (5+4) \times 3}{6 \times 09 \times 2 + 7}$ $:= \frac{1 \times 85 - 43}{6 \times (09 + 2 \times 7)}$ $:= \frac{(1+8+54) \times 3}{(60+9) \times (2+7)}$ $:= \frac{1+8+5-4-3}{(6+09) \times 2-7}$ $:= \frac{(185+4) \times 3}{(60+9) \times 27}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (5 - 46))}{3 - ((7 \times (-09)) - 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (5 - 4)) \times 6)}{3 + (70 + (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) + 6)}{3 \times (70 - (9 \times 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) - 6)}{(3 - (7 \times (-09))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 5) \times (4 \times 6))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 9)^2}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 9) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - ((5 - 4)^6))}{3 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6)))}{3 \times (7 - (0 - (9 + 2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 + 6)))}{37 + (0 - (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 + (4 - 6)))}{3 + (7 - (0 \times 92))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 6))}{3 \times ((7 - (-09)) \times 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))}{37 - (0 - (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (54 - 6))}{3 \times ((7 - (-09))^2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{37 + (0 - (9 - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 \times 6)))}{37 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 + 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - (-09))) - 2}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + 46))}{(3 \times 70) - 92}$ $:= \frac{1^{8546}}{(3 + (7 + (-09))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) - (4 \times 6))}{((3 - 7) \times (-09)) - 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) + (4 + 6))}{3 + (7 - (0 - 92))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 + (5 - 4)) \times 6)}{(3 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 + 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6))}{3 + (70 - (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 5) \times 46)}{370 - 92}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6)))}{(37 + (-09)) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (4 + 6)))}{3 + (7 - (0 - (9 \times 2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 \times (4 - 6)))}{(3 + (7 - (-09))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 + (4 - 6)))}{3 + (7 - ((0 \times 9) - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - 46))}{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))^2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - (-09))) + 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + ((5 \times 4) + 6))}{(3 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 - 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + ((5 - 4)^6))}{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 + 6)))}{3 + (7 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - 0)) + (9 + 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 6)))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (54 \times 6))}{37 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 + (4 + 6))}{(3 \times 70) - (9 \times 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 + 46)}{3 \times (7 - (0 - (9^2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 - 46)}{3 - (7 \times (0 - (9 + 2)))}$ $:= \frac{18 + ((5 \times 4) - 6)}{3 - ((7 \times (-09)) + 2)}$ $:= \frac{18 + (5 + (4 + 6))}{3 + (70 - (9 - 2))}$
<hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin: 10px 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18546}{37092} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 + 4)))^6}{(3 + (70 - 9)) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{(1^{85}) \times 46}{((3 + (7 - 0)) \times 9) + 2}$ $:= \frac{(1^8) \times ((5 \times 4) + 6)}{3 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 2)))}$ $:= \frac{(1 + (8 \times (5 \times 4))) \times 6}{3 \times (7 \times (0 + 92))}$ $:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 5)) \times 46}{(3 - 7) \times (0 - 92)}$ $:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (5 \times (4 + 6))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 9)^2}$ $:= \frac{(18 + (5 + 4)) \times 6}{(3 - 7) \times (0 - (9^2))}$ $:= \frac{(18 + (5 - 4)) \times 6}{(3 \times 70) + (9 \times 2)}$ $:= \frac{(18 + 5) \times 46}{(37 - (-09))^2}$ $:= \frac{(185 + 4) \times 6}{(3^7 + 0) + (9^2)}$ $:= \frac{1 - (8 - (5 + (4 \times 6)))}{37 - (0 - (9 - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 - (8 - (5 + 46))}{3 - (7 + (0 - 92))}$ $:= \frac{1 - (8 + (5 \times (4 - 6)))}{3 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 9)) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6)))}{3 \times (7 - (0 - (9 + 2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 + 6)))}{37 + (0 - (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 + (4 - 6)))}{3 + (7 - (0 \times 92))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 6))}{3 \times ((7 - (-09)) \times 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))}{37 - (0 - (9 + 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (54 - 6))}{3 \times ((7 - (-09))^2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{37 + (0 - (9 - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 \times 6)))}{37 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 + 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - (-09))) - 2}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + 46))}{(3 \times 70) - 92}$ $:= \frac{1^{8546}}{(3 + (7 + (-09))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) - (4 \times 6))}{((3 - 7) \times (-09)) - 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) + (4 + 6))}{3 + (7 - (0 - 92))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - 46))}{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))^2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - (-09))) + 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + ((5 \times 4) + 6))}{(3 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 - 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + ((5 - 4)^6))}{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 + 6)))}{3 + (7 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - 0)) + (9 + 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 6)))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (54 \times 6))}{37 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 + (4 + 6))}{(3 \times 70) - (9 \times 2)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 + 46)}{3 \times (7 - (0 - (9^2)))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (85 - 46)}{3 - (7 \times (0 - (9 + 2)))}$ $:= \frac{18 + ((5 \times 4) - 6)}{3 - ((7 \times (-09)) + 2)}$ $:= \frac{18 + (5 + (4 + 6))}{3 + (70 - (9 - 2))}$

$:= \frac{18 + (5 + (4 - 6))}{3 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 \times (4 - 6)))}{9 + (27 \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{185 + 46}{(9 \times (2^7)) + (3 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{185 + (4 - 6)}{3 \times ((70 - 9) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (5 + (4 - 6)))}{9 + (2^7 - 3 + 0)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{185 + 46}{370 + 92}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 6))}{(9 \times 27) - (3 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18564}{39270} := \frac{(1 \times 8 + 5) \times (6 - 4)}{3 - 9 \times 2 + 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18546}{92730} := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 5) + 4) \times 6}{(9 - 2) \times (7 \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))}{(9 + (2 - 7)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 5 + 64}{3 + 92 + 70}$
$:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times (5 \times 4)) + 6}{927 + (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{(9 \times 2 + 7) \times (3 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18564}{72930} := \frac{1 + 8 - 5 + 6 + 4}{7 + 2 \times 9 + 30}$
$:= \frac{((1 + 8)^{5+4}) \times 6}{(9^{2+7}) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 + 6)))}{92 - (7 - 30)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 5 \times 6 + 4}{72 + 93 + 0}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 \times (5 - 4))) \times 6}{9 \times (27 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 - 6)))}{9 - (2 \times (7 - 30))}$	$:= \frac{18 + 56 - 4}{7 - 2 + 9 \times 30}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + 4))) \times 6}{(9 + (2 + 7)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (85 - (4 - 6))}{92 + (7^3 + 0)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 5)) \times 46}{92 \times (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) - (4 \times 6))}{(9^2) + (7 - (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18573}{60249} := \frac{1 + 8 \times (-5 + 7 + 3)}{60 \times 2 + 4 + 9}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (5 + (4 + 6))}{9 \times (2 + (73 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times 5) + (4 + 6))}{(92 - 7) \times (3 - 0)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 546}{9 \times 2730}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6))}{9 + (2 \times (73 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18576}{23490} := \frac{18 \times 57 + 6}{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 - 0}$
$:= \frac{(1 - 8) \times (5 \times (4 - 6))}{9 - (2 - (7^3 + 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 5) \times 46)}{9 + (2 \times (7^3 + 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18576}{49032} := \frac{185 - 7 - 6}{4 + 90 \times (3 + 2)}$
$:= \frac{(18 + (5 + 4)) \times 6}{(9^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6)))}{9 + ((2^7) + (3 - 0))}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(18 + (5 - 4)) \times 6}{((9^2) \times 7) + (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 - (4 + 6)))}{(9 - 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{25974} := \frac{(1 - 8 + 60) \times 3}{25 \times 9 - 7 + 4}$
$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (5 + (4 \times 6)))}{(9 + 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (5 + (4 - 6)))}{9 - (2 + (7 - 30))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{27495} := \frac{(1 - 8 + 60) \times 3}{(2 \times 7 \times 4 - 9) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (5 \times (4 - 6)))}{9 + (2 + (7 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 + 6)))}{9 + ((2 \times 7) - (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 60 - 3}{(2^7 + 4 + 9) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((8 \times 5) - 4) \times 6)}{(9 + 27) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 - (4 - 6)))}{9 - (2 - (73 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{29574} := \frac{(-1 + 8 + 6) \times 03}{2 - 9 - 5 + 74}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) - 6)}{((9 \times 2) - 7) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 6)))}{(9^2) - (7 \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{18 + 6^{03}}{2^9 - 5 \times 7 \times 4}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 5) \times 46)}{(9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{1 + (85 + (4 - 6))}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{45279} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 60 - 3}{4 + 5 + 2^7 \times 9}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((85 - 4) \times 6)}{9 \times ((2 + 7) \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{18 + (5 + (4 + 6))}{92 + (73 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{45792} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 6 \times 03}{4 \times (5 - 7 + 9 \times 2)}$

	$:= \frac{(-1+8+6) \times 03}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 9 - 2)}$	$:= \frac{(1^8) + (6 + (3 - 0))}{2 - (((7 - 9) \times 4) - 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 \times (3 - 0)))}{(2^7) - (94 - 5)}$
	$:= \frac{1 + 8 \times 6 + 03}{4^{5+7-9} \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(1^8) + (63 - 0)}{2 \times (7 + ((9 \times 4) + 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 + 30))}{2 + ((7 \times 9) - (4 - 5))}$
	$:= \frac{18 + 6^{03}}{4 + 5 + 7 \times 9^2}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 6)) \times 30}{27 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (6 - (3 - 0)))}{2 + (7 - (9 - (4 + 5)))}$
▶ $\frac{18603}{49725}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 8 + 60) \times 3}{(4 + 9 + 72) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 630}{(2 + 7) \times 945}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 - (3 - 0)))}{2 + (7 - (9 \times (4 - 5)))}$
▶ $\frac{18603}{52947}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 6 \times 03}{(5 - 2) \times 9 + 47}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 8) \times (6 - 30)}{2 \times (7 \times (9 + (4 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (3 - 0)))}{2 + (7 + (9 + (4 + 5)))}$
	$:= \frac{(-1 + 8 + 6) \times 03}{(5 - 2) \times (9 + 4 \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{(18 \times 6) + 30}{(2 \times (7 + 94)) + 5}$	$:= \frac{1 + (86 - (3 - 0))}{2 + (79 + 45)}$
	$:= \frac{1 + 8 \times 6 + 03}{5 \times 29 - 4 + 7}$	$:= \frac{(18 - 6) \times 30}{((2 \times 7) + 94) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 + (86 + (3 - 0))}{(2 \times (7 \times 9)) + (4 + 5)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 60 - 3}{5 \times (2 + (9 - 4) \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (6 + (3 - 0)))}{2 - (7 - (9 + (4 - 5)))}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (6 \times (3 - 0))}{27 \times (9 + (4 + 5))}$
▶ $\frac{18603}{74529}$	$:= \frac{(1 - 8 + 60) \times 3}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (63 - 0))}{2 - (7 - (94 - 5))}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (6 \times 30)}{27 \times (9 \times (4 \times 5))}$
	<hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/>	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 6) + 30)}{(2 \times (7 \times 9)) - (4 + 5)}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (6 + 30)}{27 + 945}$
▶ $\frac{18620}{73549}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8 - 6) \times 20}{7 + 3^5 - 4 - 9}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8^6) \times (3 - 0))}{(2^7) \times (9 \times (4^5))}$	$:= \frac{18 + (6 \times 30)}{2 + (((7 \times 9) - 4) \times 5)}$
	$:= \frac{18 + 62 + 0}{73 \times 5 - 49}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (3 - 0))}{2 + (7 + (9 + 45))}$	$:= \frac{18 + (6 + 30)}{(2 \times (7 + (9 \times 4))) - 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 6 \times 2 + 0}{7 - (3 - 5) \times 4 \times 9}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 30)}{(((2 \times 7) - 9)^4) + 5}$	$:= \frac{186 \times (3 - 0)}{27 \times ((9 \times 4) - 5)}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8 + 6) \times 20}{7 - 3 + 549}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 6) \times 30)}{2 + (7 + (9 \times (4 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{186 + 30}{279 + 45}$
	<hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/>	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 6)^3 + 0)}{2 + ((7 - (9 - 4)) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{186 - 30}{279 - 45}$
▶ $\frac{18630}{24975}$	$:= \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{(2 - (4 - 9) \times 7) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (6 - (3 - 0)))}{2 \times (7 - (9 - (4 \times 5)))}$	▶ $\frac{18630}{42795}$
▶ $\frac{18630}{27945}$	$:= \frac{((1^8) + 6) \times 30}{(27 + (9 \times 4)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (6 \times (3 - 0)))}{2 \times ((7 \times 9) + 45)}$	▶ $\frac{18630}{49275}$
	$:= \frac{(1^{86}) \times 30}{2 + (7 - (9 - 45))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (6 + (3 - 0)))}{2 + (7 + (94 + 5))}$	▶ $\frac{18630}{79245}$
	$:= \frac{(1^{86}) + (3 - 0)}{2 - (7 + (9 - (4 \times 5)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (6 + 30))}{27 + (9 \times 45)}$	▶ $\frac{18630}{92475}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8) \times (6 \times 30)}{27 \times (9 - (4 - 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (63 - 0))}{2 \times (7 \times (9 + 45))}$	▶ $\frac{18630}{95427}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{18639}{42750} := \frac{18 + 6^3 \times 9}{(4+2) \times 750}$	$:= \frac{(18 \times 6) + (4 + 5)}{(3^{7-2}) - (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 - (4 - 5)))}{37 + (2 - (9 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18639}{54207} := \frac{1 - 8 + 6^3 + 9}{5^4 + 2 + 07}$	$:= \frac{(18 + 6) \times (4 + 5)}{((3 \times 7)^2) - (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 + (4 - 5)))}{3 + (7 \times 2 + (9 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18640}{25397} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (6 + 4) + 0}{25 + (3 + 9) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{(18 - 6) \times 45}{(3 + (7 + 2)) \times 90}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (86 - (4 \times 5))}{(3 \times (7 \times 2)) + 90}$
$:= \frac{1^8 \times 6 \times 40}{(2 + 5)^3 - 9 - 7}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (6 + 45))}{3 - (7 - (2 + 90))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (86 - (4 - 5))}{3 \times ((7^2) + (9 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18643}{57920} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 64 + 3}{5 \times (7 + 9) \times 20}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 \times (6 - (4 + 5)))}{(3 \times 7) + (29 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (((8 \times 6) + 4) \times 5)}{3 + (7 + (2^9 + 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18643}{70952} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 64 + 3}{70 \times (9 + 5) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 \times (6 \times (4 - 5)))}{3 + (7 - (2 - 90))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 + (6 - 4)) \times 5)}{3 + (7 + (2 + 90))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18645}{37290} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + 4)))^5}{3 \times (72 + 90)}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (6 - (4 \times 5)))}{3 - (7 - (2 \times (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (6 - (4 + 5)))}{(3 \times (7 - 2)) + (9 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(1^{86}) \times (4 + 5)}{(3 \times (7 + 2)) - (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times (6 - 4)) + 5)}{3 \times (7 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (6 + (4 - 5)))}{3 + ((7 \times 2) - (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1^8) \times (6 \times (4 + 5))}{3 \times (7 + (29 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8^{6-4}) + 5)}{(3 \times (7^2)) - (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 \times ((6 \times 4) - 5))}{(3 \times 72) + 90}$
$:= \frac{(1^8) \times (6 + (4 \times 5))}{3 - (7 \times (2 - (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + (6 + 4)) \times 5)}{(3 + 7) \times (2 \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (6 + (4 - 5)))}{((3 - 7) \times 2) + 90}$
$:= \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 6) - 4)) \times 5}{((3 \times 7)^2) + (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (4 + 5))}{(3^7 - 2) + (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 - (4 - 5)))}{(3 \times 7) + (2 + (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + 4))) \times 5}{3 + (7 + (2 \times 90))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 64) \times 5)}{(3 + (7 - 2)) \times 90}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 \times (4 + 5)))}{(3 \times 72) - 90}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 - 4))) \times 5}{(3 + 7) \times (2 + (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((86 + 4) \times 5)}{((3 + 7)^2) \times (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (4 + 5)))}{3 + ((7 - 2) \times (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 6)) \times 45}{3 \times ((7 - 2) \times 90)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (6 - (4 \times 5)))}{3 - ((7^2) - 90)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (4 - 5)))}{3 + (7 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 6))^{4+5}}{(3^7) \times (2 \times (9 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (6 + (4 - 5)))}{(3 \times (7 - 2)) - (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + 45))}{3 \times ((7^2) - (9 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (6 + (4 \times 5))}{(3 + (7^2)) \times (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (6 + (4 - 5)))}{3 + (7 \times (2 + (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (64 + 5))}{(3 \times (7^2)) + (9 - 0)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (64 \times 5))}{(3 + 7) \times (2^9 + 0)}$	$:= \frac{1 + (86 - (4 - 5))}{3 - (7 - (2 \times 90))}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + ((6 \times 4) - 5))}{3 \times (7 + (2 + (9 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (86 - 45)}{3 - (7 + (2 - 90))}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + ((6 - 4) \times 5))}{(3 \times (7 + 2)) + (9 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{18 \times ((6 + 4) \times 5)}{(3 + 7) \times (2 \times 90)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 - (4 + 5)))}{((3 + 7)^2) - 90}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (6 \times (4 + 5))}{3 \times (72 \times (9 - 0))}$

$:= \frac{18 + (6 + (4 + 5))}{3 + (72 - (9 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{186 \times (4 + 5)}{372 \times (9 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{186 + 45}{372 + 90}$ $:= \frac{186 - 45}{372 - 90}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18654}{93270} := \frac{(((1^8) + 6) \times 5) - 4}{(9 \times 3) + (2^7 + 0)}$ $:= \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 6) - 5) \times 4}{(9 + 3 + 2) \times 70}$ $:= \frac{(1^{86}) + (5 \times 4)}{(9 + (3 \times 2)) \times (7 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{(1^8) + ((6 + 5) \times 4)}{9 + (3 \times (2 + 70))}$ $:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 + 4)}{9 \times (3 + (2 + 70))}$ $:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 654}{9 \times 3270}$ $:= \frac{(1 - 8) \times (6 - 54)}{(9 + 3) \times (2 \times 70)}$ $:= \frac{(18 - 6) \times 54}{(9 + 3) \times 270}$ $:= \frac{1 - (8 - (6 + (5 \times 4)))}{(9 \times 3) - (2 - 70)}$ $:= \frac{1 - (8 - (65 - 4))}{9 \times (3 + (27 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)}{9 + (3 + (2^7 + 0))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (5 + 4))}{9 \times ((3 - 2) \times 70)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 54)}{9 \times (3 \times (2 \times 70))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 6) \times (5 + 4))}{9 + (3 \times (27 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times ((86 - 5) \times 4)}{(9 - 3) \times 270}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{9 + ((3 - 2)^7 + 0)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (6 - 54))}{(9 - (3 + 2)) \times 70}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + ((6 \times 5) + 4))}{(9 - (3 \times 2)) \times 70}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 - (5 + 4)))}{9 + ((3^2) + (7 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{9 - ((3^2) - 70)}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 + (5 + 4)))}{(9 \times (3 + 2)) + 70}$ $:= \frac{1 \times (86 + 54)}{(9 + (3 - 2)) \times 70}$ $:= \frac{1^{8654}}{((9 - 3) \times 2) - (7 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{1 + ((8 + 65) \times 4)}{((9^3) \times 2) + (7 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (6 - (5 - 4)))}{9 - (3 - (2 \times (7 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 - (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{9 - (3 - (2 + (7 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))}{93 + (2 + 70)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 4)))}{9 \times ((3 + 2) \times (7 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (5 \times 4)))}{((9 \times 3) - 2) \times (7 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (5 + 4)))}{93 + (27 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + (5 - 4)))}{9 + (3 - (2 - 70))}$ $:= \frac{18 - ((6 - 5)^4)}{9 + ((3 \times 2) + 70)}$ $:= \frac{186 - (5 - 4)}{932 - (7 - 0)}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18675}{23904} := \frac{1 + ((8 - 6) \times (7 + 5))}{2 \times (3 + (9 - (-04)))}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 \times (6 + 7)) - 5)}{(23 + (9 - 0)) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{(1 + (8 - 6)) \times 75}{(2^3) \times (9 \times (04))}$ $:= \frac{(1 - (8 - 67)) \times 5}{((2 \times 3) + 90) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{1 + (86 - (7 + 5))}{2 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{(18 + 67) \times 5}{(2 \times (3 \times 90)) + 4}$ $:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 675}{(2 \times 3)^{9-04}}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{18675}{49302} := \frac{1 + (8 - 6) \times (7 + 5)}{(4 \times 9 - 3) \times 02}$ $:= \frac{1 + 8 + 6 + 7 \times 5}{(4 \times 9 + 30) \times 2}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18690}{73425} := \frac{1^8 + 69 + 0}{(7 + 3 \times 4^2) \times 5}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18693}{54270} := \frac{1 + 8 \times (6 + 9) + 3}{5 \times (4 - 2 + 70)}$ $:= \frac{(1 - 8 + 69) \times 3}{5 \times 4 \times 27 + 0}$ $:= \frac{1 + 86 + 9 - 3}{(5 - 4) \times 270}$ $:= \frac{186 \times 9 \times 3}{54 \times 270}$ $:= \frac{18 \times 6 + 9^3}{(5 + 4) \times 270}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{18697}{53420} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + 9))) \times 7}{5 \times (34 - (2 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(1^{86}) \times (9 \times 7)}{5 \times (34 + (2 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(1 + ((8 - 6) \times 9)) \times 7}{((5 \times 3) + 4) \times 20}$
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$:= \frac{(1 + (8 \times (6 + 9))) \times 7}{((5^3) - 4) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18706}{52934}$	$:= \frac{1 + 87 + 06}{5 \times 2 \times 9 \times 3 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18760}{29435}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times (7 + 60)}{29^{4+3-5}}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + 9))) \times 7}{((5^3) \times 4) - 20}$			$\blacktriangleright \frac{18760}{43952}$	$:= \frac{1 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 0}{(4 + 3 + 9) \times 5 + 2}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 - 9))) \times 7}{5 \times (3 \times (4 \times (2 - 0)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18720}{59436}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 72 + 0}{5 - 9 + 43 \times 6}$		
$:= \frac{1 - (8 + ((6 - 9) \times 7))}{(5 \times (3 \times 4)) - 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18720}{94536}$	$:= \frac{1 - 8 + 7 + 20}{9 + 4 \times (5 + 3 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18763}{45290}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 87 \times (6 - 3)}{(4 + 5 - 2) \times 90}$
$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (6 - 97))}{5 \times (3 \times (4^2 + 0))}$				
$:= \frac{1 \times (((8 \times 6) + 9) \times 7)}{(53 + 4) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18732}{49506}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 7 - 3 + 2}{4 \times 9 - 5 + 06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{30456}$	$:= \frac{18 - 7 + 9 \times 2}{3 + 04 \times (5 + 6)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((8 \times 6) - 9) \times 7)}{(5 + 34) \times 20}$		$:= \frac{(1 - 8 + 7^3) \times 2}{4 \times (9 \times 50 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{34560}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 87 \times 9 \times 2}{(3 + 45) \times 60}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (((8 + 6) \times 9) - 7)}{5 \times (34 \times (2 - 0))}$			$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{35640}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 \times (7 + 9 + 2)}{35 + 6 \times 40}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (9 + 7))}{(5 + 3) \times (4 \times 20)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18734}{50692}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 - (7 + 34))}{5 - (0 - (6 + (9^2)))}$		$:= \frac{18 - 7 + 9 \times 2}{3 + 56 - 4 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (9 - 7))}{(5 + (3 - 4)) \times 20}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (73 + 4))}{5 - (0 - ((6 + 9)^2))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{36540}$	$:= \frac{1 - 8 + 7 \times 9 - 2}{(3 - 6) \times (5 - 40)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - 6) \times (9 \times 7))}{5 \times (3 \times (4 + 20))}$		$:= \frac{1 + (8 \times (7 + (3 \times 4)))}{506 - 92}$		$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 7 + 92}{3 \times (6 \times 5 + 40)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (6 + (9 \times 7)))}{((5 \times 3) - 4) \times 20}$		$:= \frac{187 + 34}{506 + 92}$		$:= \frac{1 - 8 + 7 + 9 \times 2}{36 - 5 + 4 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 + (8 + (6 + 97))}{((5 - 3)^4) \times 20}$		$:= \frac{(18 \times (7 \times 3)) - 4}{(5 - (-06)) \times 92}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 8 - 7) \times 9^2}{3 \times (65 + 40)}$
		$:= \frac{187 \times (3^4)}{506 \times (9^2)}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 8 + 7) \times 9 \times 2}{(3 + 6 + 5) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18703}{26945}$		$:= \frac{187 \times (3 + 4)}{506 \times (9 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{43065}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + 7 + 9) \times 2}{(4 + 3 \times 06) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18703}{92564}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (7 \times 34))}{(50 + 6) \times 92}$		$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 7 \times 9^2}{4 \times 30 \times (6 + 5)}$
			$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{63504}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 7 \times (9 - 2)}{6^3 - 5 \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18705}{24639}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18759}{43602}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 7 + 59}{43 \times (6 - 02)}$		
		$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times 75 - 9}{43 \times 6^{02}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18905}{47362}$	$:= \frac{1 + 89 + 05}{4 \times (7 + 3) \times 6 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18706}{49352}$			$\blacktriangleright \frac{18905}{72436}$	$:= \frac{1 + 89 + 05}{7 \times (2^4 + 36)}$

	$:= \frac{18 \times (90 + 5)}{(7 + 2)^4 - 3 - 6}$	
	$:= \frac{(1 - (8 - 9)) \times 40}{2 \times (3 + ((6 \times 7) + 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (9 \times (4 - 0)))}{((2 \times (3 + 6)) - 7) \times 5}$
▶ $\frac{18907}{35624}$	$:= \frac{1 + 8 \times (90 + 7)}{3^5 \times 6 + 2 + 4}$	$:= \frac{(1 - (8 - 9))^4 + 0}{2 - (3 \times (6 - (7 + 5)))}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0)}{((2 \times 3) + 67) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (9 - (4 - 0)))}{2 - (3 + (6 - (7 + 5)))}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 9)) \times (4 - 0)}{(2 + (3 + (6 + 7))) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (9 - 40))}{2 + (36 + (7 + 5))}$
▶ $\frac{18927}{35640}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + 92) \times 7}{3 \times (5 + 6) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 9)) \times 40}{((2 + 3) \times 6)^{7-5}}$
▶ $\frac{18927}{36450}$	$:= \frac{1 + (8 + 92) \times 7}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 50}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))}{(2 + 3) \times (6 + 75)}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + 8) \times (9 \times 40)}{2 \times (3 \times 675)}$	$:= \frac{189 + 42}{3 \times 5 + 6 \times 70}$
▶ $\frac{18936}{52074}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 9) \times (3 - 6))}{5 - (2 \times (0 - (7 - 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 89) \times (4 - 0)}{2 \times ((3 + (6 \times 7)) \times 5)}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 - (9 - (3 + 6)))}{5 + (20 - (7 - 4))}$	$:= \frac{(18 + 9) \times (4 - 0)}{(2 \times (3 + 67)) - 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 - (9 - 3)) \times 6)}{(5 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{(18 + 9) \times 40}{2 \times ((3 + 6) \times 75)}$
	$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (9 - 36))}{52 - (0 - (7 - 4))}$	$:= \frac{(18 - 9) \times (4 - 0)}{(2 \times ((3 \times 6) + 7)) - 5}$
	$:= \frac{(1 - ((8 - 9) \times 3)) \times 6}{(5 \times (2 \times (07))) - 4}$	$:= \frac{1 - (8 + (9 - 40))}{2 \times (3 + (6 \times (7 - 5)))}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8) - (9 - 36)}{5 - (2 + (0 - 74))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 9) + (4 - 0))}{(2 \times (3 + (6 \times 7))) + 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 + (8 - (9 - 36))}{5 + (20 + 74)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 9) + 40)}{(23 \times 6) + (7 - 5)}$
	$:= \frac{(1^8) + (93 + 6)}{(5 + 20) \times (7 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40)}{2 - (3 - (6 + (7 \times 5)))}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 + (3 \times 6)))}{520 + 74}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((8 + 9) \times (4 - 0))}{(2 \times (3 + (6 \times 7))) - 5}$
	$:= \frac{18 + (9 + (3^6))}{5 + 2074}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))}{(2 + (3 + 67)) \times 5}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 \times 40))}{(2^3) \times (6 \times 75)}$	$:= \frac{18 \times 9 \times (5 + 4)}{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 60}$
▶ $\frac{18940}{23675}$	$:= \frac{((1^8) + 9) \times 40}{(2^{3+6}) - (7 + 5)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 + (4 - 0)))}{2 \times (3 + (67 - 5))}$
	$:= \frac{(1 - (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0)}{2 + (3 - ((6 - 7) \times 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 + 40))}{((2^3) + 6) \times (7 \times 5)}$
		$:= \frac{18942}{35670}$
		$:= \frac{18942}{70356}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 9 + 4 \times 2}{(7 - 03) \times 5 + 6}$
		$:= \frac{1^8 + 94 \times 2}{703 + 5 - 6}$
		$:= \frac{1 + 8 - 9 + 42}{(7 \times 03 + 5) \times 6}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times (9 - 4 + 2)}{(70 + 3 + 5) \times 6}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times 8 - 9 + 42}{7 + 5 \times 30 + 6}$
		$:= \frac{18942}{75306}$
		$:= \frac{18952}{40376}$
		$:= \frac{1 \times 89 + 5 - 2}{40 \times 3 + 76}$
		$:= \frac{18954}{20736}$
		$:= \frac{18954}{26730}$
		$:= \frac{18954}{32760}$
		$:= \frac{1 + 8 \times (9 + 5) + 4}{2 + 07 \times 3 \times 6}$
		$:= \frac{(1 + 8 \times 9 + 5) \times 4}{2 + 6 \times 73 + 0}$
		$:= \frac{189 + 54}{(3 - 2) \times 7 \times 60}$
		$:= \frac{18 \times 9 \times (5 + 4)}{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 60}$
		$:= \frac{18954}{37206}$
		$:= \frac{18954}{60372}$
		$:= \frac{1 + 8 - 9 + 54}{(3 + 7)^2 + 0 + 6}$
		$:= \frac{1 + 8 + 9 + 5 + 4}{(6 + 037) \times 2}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1+8+9 \times 5 \times 4}{60 \times (3+7)+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18957}{60342} & := \frac{1+8 \times 9+5-7}{(60-3) \times 4-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{40572} & := \frac{1-8+96-3}{40+(5+7)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{42570} & := \frac{1+8 \times (9-6+3)}{4 \times 2 \times 5+70} \\ & := \frac{(1-(8-9) \times 6)^3}{(4+2+5) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18964}{23705} & := \frac{(((1+8) \times 9)-6) \times 4}{(2+(3+70)) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{((1-(8-9))^6)-4}{((2^3)+(7-0)) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(1-(8-(9+6))) \times 4}{2+(3-(7 \times (-05)))} \\ & := \frac{1-(8-(9+(6+4)))}{(2 \times (3+(7-0)))-5} \\ & := \frac{1-(8-(9+(6-4)))}{2+(3-(7 \times (0 \times 5)))} \\ & := \frac{1-(8+(9-64))}{(2+(3+(7-0))) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (((8 \times 9)+6) \times 4)}{2 \times (3 \times (70-5))} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((8+(9+6)) \times 4)}{(2+(3 \times (7-0))) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((8+96) \times 4)}{(2^3) \times (70-5)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times ((89-6) \times 4)}{(2 \times (3 \times 70))-5} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (8 \times ((9+6) \times 4))}{(2^3) \times (70+5)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9-(6-4)))}{2+(3+(70-5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9+64))}{2 \times ((3+70) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{1 \times (8+(9 \times (6 \times 4)))}{(2^3) \times (7 \times (05))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8-(9-(6 \times 4)))}{2 \times (3+(7-(-05)))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8-(9-64))}{2+(3+(70+5))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8+(9-(6+4)))}{2 \times (3+(7+(-05)))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8+(9-(6-4)))}{2 \times (3+(7-(0 \times 5)))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8+(9+(6+4)))}{23+(7-(-05))} \\ & := \frac{1+(8+(9+(6-4)))}{(2 \times (3+(7-0))) + 5} \\ & := \frac{1+(89-(6+4))}{2 \times ((3+(7-0)) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{18+((9 \times 6)+4)}{(2-(3 \times 7)) \times (-05)} \\ & := \frac{1896+4}{2370+5} \\ & := \frac{1896-4}{2370-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18964}{70253} & := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (9+6-4)}{70+2^{5+3}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{46053} & := \frac{(1+8+9) \times 7-2}{4+60 \times 5-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{56304} & := \frac{1 \times 8+9+7 \times 2}{5+6+3^{04}} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 8^{9-7}-2}{5 \times (6+30)+4} \\ & := \frac{(18 \times 9-7) \times 2}{5 \times (6 \times 30+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{60543} & := \frac{1+8 \times 9-7+2}{(60-5) \times 4-3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18975}{23460} & := \frac{(1+8+9-7) \times 5}{2^{3+4}-60} \\ & := \frac{(1+8 \times 9-7) \times 5}{2 \times 34 \times 6+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19024}{35786} & := \frac{1+9^{02} \times 4}{3 \times 5+7 \times 86} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19024}{85376} & := \frac{1+9^{-02+4}}{8+(53+7) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19026}{58437} & := \frac{(1 \times 9-02) \times 6}{58+4^3+7} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 90+2^6}{5 \times 8 \times 4 \times 3-7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19032}{56784} & := \frac{1+9^{03}+2}{56 \times (7+8 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{24786} & := \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{2 \times (4 \times 78-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{24867} & := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+48) \times 6+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{27864} & := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+78+6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{28674} & := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+8 \times 6) \times 7+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{28764} & := \frac{1+9+035}{2^{(8-7) \times 6}+4} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 90 \times (3+5)}{(2+8+7) \times 64} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 03 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times (7+6)-4} \\ & := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 035}{28+7 \times 64} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{42768} & := \frac{1-9+03^5}{4 \times (2^7+6)-8} \end{aligned}$$

	$:= \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{4 \times (27+6) \times 8}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19056}{73842} := \frac{1 \times (9 - (0 - (5 - 6)))}{7 - (3 \times (8 - (4^2)))}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 6) + 8))}{(52 \times 4) - (3 + 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{48276} := \frac{1 - 9 + 03^5}{4 - 8 \times (2 - 76)}$			$:= \frac{1 + (9 - ((0 \times 5) - 6))}{(7 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4 - 2)}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (90 - (6 + 8))}{(((5 \times 2) - 4)^3) - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{78246} := \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{7 \times (8-2) \times 46}$			$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (-05)) \times 6)}{(7 \times (3 + 8)) + (4^2)}$		$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (0 - (6 + 8)))}{5 + (24 + 37)}$
			$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (0 - (5 \times 6)))}{73 + (84 - 2)}$		$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (0 - (6 - 8)))}{(5 \times (2 + (4 - 3))) + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19038}{72645} := \frac{1^9 \times 038}{7+2 \times (64+5)}$			$:= \frac{(1^9 + 0) \times 56}{7 - ((3 - 8) \times 42)}$		$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (0 - (6 - 8)))}{5 + (2 \times (4 + (3 + 7)))}$
	$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 038}{7 \times 2 + 6^4 - 5}$		$:= \frac{1 + (90 - (5 + 6))}{(7 \times ((3 + 8) \times 4)) + 2}$		$:= \frac{190 - 6 + 8}{524 - 3 + 7}$
	$:= \frac{(1+9) \times 038}{(7^2 \times 6 - 4) \times 5}$		$:= \frac{(1-9) \times (0 - (5 + 6))}{(7^3) - (8 - (4 + 2))}$		$:= \frac{190 + 6 + 8}{524 + 37}$
			$:= \frac{1 - (9 + (0 - 56))}{(7 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4 + 2)}$		
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{37825} := \frac{190 + 4 \times 6}{(3 \times 7 + 8^2) \times 5}$					$\blacktriangleright \frac{19072}{34568} := \frac{(1^9 + 07) \times 2}{3 + 4 + 5 \times 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{75328} := \frac{1 + 90 + 4 - 6}{(7 + 5 + 32) \times 8}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19068}{52437} := \frac{((1^9 + 0) + 6) \times 8}{((5 \times 2) + (4 \times 3)) \times 7}$			$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 07) \times 2}{3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 - 8}$
			$:= \frac{(1 - (9 - 0)) \times (6 - 8)}{5 - (2 - (4 + 37))}$		$:= \frac{1 - 9 + 072}{3 + 45 + 68}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19047}{62583} := \frac{1 + 9 + 04 - 7}{6 - 2 - 5 + 8 \times 3}$			$:= \frac{(1^9 + 0) \times (6 \times 8)}{(5^2 + 4 - 3) + 7}$		$:= \frac{(-1 + 9) \times 07 \times 2}{3 \times 45 + 68}$
	$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 04 + 7}{6 + 2 + 58 + 3}$		$:= \frac{(1^9 + 0) \times 68}{(52 \times 4) - (3 \times 7)}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 9 \times 07) \times 2}{(3 - 4 + 5 \times 6) \times 8}$
	$:= \frac{1 + 9 \times (-04 + 7)}{6 - 2 + 5 + 83}$		$:= \frac{(1 + (9 + (-06))) \times 8}{(5 \times ((2^4) + 3)) - 7}$		$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 07)^2}{(3^4 - 5) \times 6 + 8}$
	$:= \frac{(1 + 9 - 04) \times 7}{6 \times (2 \times (5 + 8) - 3)}$		$:= \frac{(1 + (9 - 0)) \times (6 + 8)}{5 \times (((2 \times 4) + 3) \times 7)}$		
	$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 04) \times 7}{62 \times 5 - 8 - 3}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 9) \times (0 - (6 - 8))}{5 + (2 \times (4 + (3 \times 7)))}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{28356} := \frac{190 - 7 + 4}{2 \times (83 + 56)}$
	$:= \frac{(19 + 04) \times 7}{6 \times 2 + 5 + 8^3}$		$:= \frac{(1 + 9)^{-06+8}}{5 \times (((2^4) \times 3) + 7)}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{65382} := \frac{190 - 7 + 4}{65 + (3 \times 8)^2}$
			$:= \frac{(1 - 9) \times (0 - (6 + 8))}{5 + (2 + (43 \times 7))}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{82365} := \frac{19 - 0 + 7 - 4}{(8 + 2 + 3 + 6) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19053}{64728} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (05 + 3)}{(6 - 4)^7 \times 2 - 8}$			$:= \frac{1 - (9 + (0 - (6 \times 8)))}{(5 \times 24) - (3 + 7)}$		
			$:= \frac{1 - (9 + (0 - 68))}{5 + ((2^4) \times (3 + 7))}$		$\blacktriangleright \frac{19075}{36842} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 07 \times 5}{(3 \times 6 + 8)^{4-2}}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19075}{62348} := \frac{(1+9) \times 07 \times 5}{(62+3^4) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{19 - (0 - (7+6))}{2 \times (3 + (8 + (4+5)))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (2 + (5 - 8)))}{(6 \times 7) - (4 - (-03))}$
<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19076}{23845} := \frac{1^9 + 07^6}{2^3 + 8^4 \times 5}$	$:= \frac{19 - (0 - (7 - 6))}{2 + (3 + ((8 - 4) \times 5))}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (2 - (5 - 8)))}{((6 + 7) \times (4 - 0)) - 3}$
$:= \frac{(1 - (9 \times (-07))) \times 6}{(2^3) \times ((8 + 4) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{190 - (7 \times 6)}{(2 + (3 + (8 \times 4))) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (2 + (5 + 8)))}{6 \times (7 + (4 - (-03)))}$
$:= \frac{1^9 \times 076}{23 + 8 \times (4 + 5)}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19085}{24637} := \frac{(19 - 08) \times 5}{2 \times 46 - 3 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (25 + 8))}{6 + ((7 + 40) \times 3)}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (0 \times 7))) \times 6}{(2 \times (3 + (8 \times 4))) + 5}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19203}{64875} := \frac{19 + 203}{(6 - 4 + 8) \times 75}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (25 - 8))}{(6 + 7) \times (4 - (-03))}$
$:= \frac{(1 + (90 - 7)) \times 6}{((2 + 3)^{8-4}) + 5}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19206}{45738} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 20 - 6}{457 - 3 + 8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (92 + (5 \times 8))}{6 \times (74 - (-03))}$
$:= \frac{(1 - 9) \times (0 - (7 \times 6))}{2 \times ((38 + 4) \times 5)}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19206}{83754} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 20 - 6}{837 + 5 + 4}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((9 \times 2) - (5 + 8))}{(6 \times (7 - (4 - 0))) + 3}$
$:= \frac{(19 + (-07)) \times 6}{((2 \times (3 + 8)) - 4) \times 5}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19256}{70384} := \frac{1 + 9 + 25 - 6}{70 + 3 \times (8 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{1 + ((9 + 2) \times (5 + 8))}{6 \times (7 \times (4 \times (03)))}$
$:= \frac{1 - (9 + (0 - 76))}{(2 + (3 + (8 + 4))) \times 5}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19258}{67403} := \frac{1 - ((9 - 2) \times (5 - 8))}{6 + (7 + (4^{03}))}$	$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (2 \times (5 - 8)))}{6 + (7 + (40 + 3))}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 - (-07)) \times 6)}{2 \times (3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5))}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19260}{58743} := \frac{1^{92} \times 60}{5 \times (8 + 7 \times 4) + 3}$	$:= \frac{1 + (9 + ((2 \times 5) - 8))}{6 \times (7^{4-03})}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (-07)) \times 6)}{(2 - (3 - (8 - 4))) \times 5}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 - (9 - (2 \times (5 + 8)))}{6 - (7 - (4^{03}))}$	$:= \frac{(1 + 9)^2 + 60}{5 \times 8 + 7 \times 4^3}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (-07))^6)}{2 \times (3 - (8 - 45))}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 - (9 - (2 + (5 \times 8)))}{6 - (7 - (40 \times 3))}$	<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{34680} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 2^7 + 5}{34 \times 68 + 0}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 6)))}{2 \times ((3 - 8) \times (4 - 5))}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 - (9 + (2 - (5 \times 8)))}{6 - ((7 - 40) \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{40863} := \frac{1 - 9 - 2 + 7 \times 5}{4 \times (08 + 6) - 3}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (90 - (7 \times 6))}{2 \times (3 + ((8 \times 4) - 5))}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 - (9 + (2 - 58))}{6 \times (7 \times (4 - (0 \times 3)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{43860} := \frac{(1 + 9) \times 2^7 + 5}{43 \times (8 + 60)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (90 + (7 \times 6))}{2 + (3 + (8 \times (4 \times 5)))}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 \times ((9^2) - (5 - 8))}{6 \times (7 \times (4 - (-03)))}$	
$:= \frac{1 + (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))}{2 \times (3 + (8 + (4 - 5)))}$	<hr/> $:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (2 - (5 - 8)))}{6 + (7 + (4 + (-03)))}$	
$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (0 - (7 \times 6)))}{2 + (3 + ((8 + 4) \times 5))}$		
$:= \frac{1 + (9 + ((0 \times 7) - 6))}{2 - (3 \times (8 - (4 + 5)))}$		
$:= \frac{1 + (90 + (7 + 6))}{(2 \times (3 + 8)) + 4 \times 5}$		

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{36045} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{(360-4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{62478} := \frac{(-1+9+3) \times 05}{6 \times (24+7) - 8}$	$:= \frac{1 + (9+3 \times 4) \times 5}{(6^2+7) \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{36450} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 4 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{72468} := \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{7 \times (2+4) \times 6-8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{45360} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 2 + 78}{4 \times 5 + 3 \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{76824} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{24768} := \frac{1 + (9 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))}{2^{4+(7-6)^8}}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (2+7+8)}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{78624} := \frac{(-1+9+3) \times 05}{7 \times 8 \times (6+2-4)}$	$:= \frac{((1+9)^3) + 50}{(2^4) \times (76+8)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (2^7+8)}{(45+3) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{(1-9+30) \times 5}{7 \times 8 \times (6-2+4)}$	$:= \frac{(1^{93}) \times 50}{2 \times (4 \times ((7-6) \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{45603} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times (560+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{82764} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{8^2 \times (7+6)+4}$	$:= \frac{(1+(9+3)) \times 50}{2 \times (4 \times ((7+6) \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{46053} := \frac{1+9 \times 2+7-8}{46+0 \times 5-3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{86427} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{864+2+7}$	$:= \frac{(1^9) \times (3 \times 50)}{2 \times ((4 \times 7) + 68)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times (605-3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{86724} := \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{(8+67-2) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{((1^9)+3) \times 50}{(2^{4+7-6}) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{56304} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 2 + 7 \times 8}{5 \times (6+30) + 4}$	$:= \frac{(-1+9 \times 3) \times 05}{8 \times (67+2+4)}$	$:= \frac{19 \times (3 \times 50)}{(2+4) \times (76 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (27+8)}{5 \times (6 \times 30+4)}$		$:= \frac{1 \times ((9-3) \times 50)}{(2+(4+(7 \times 6))) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{63504} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2+7-8}{(6+3+5) \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{45678} := \frac{(1+9-3) \times 20}{4+5 \times 67-8}$	$:= \frac{(1+(9-3)) \times 50}{((2+4) \times 76)-8}$
$:= \frac{19 \times (2+7+8)}{(6^3+50) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{54786} := \frac{(1+9-3) \times 20}{5+4 \times 7 \times (8+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{27864} := \frac{1 + (9 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))}{2^{7-8+6} + 4}$
$:= \frac{(19-2) \times (7+8)}{6 \times 35 \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{74865} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 3 + 2 + 0}{74 - 8 \times 6 + 5}$	$:= \frac{((1+9)^3) + 50}{27 \times ((8+6) \times 4)}$
	$:= \frac{1-9+32+0}{74+8+6+5}$	$:= \frac{(1^{93}) \times 50}{2+(7 \times (8+(6-4)))}$
	$:= \frac{(1+9 \times 3) \times 2+0}{7+(48-6) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((9+3) \times 50)}{27 \times (8+(6 \times 4))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{42768} := \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{4 \times (2+7 \times 6-8)}$	$:= \frac{(1-9) \times (3-20)}{74 \times 8-65}$	$:= \frac{(1^9) \times (3 \times 50)}{27 \times ((8-6) \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{(-1+9 \times 3) \times 05}{4+276+8}$	$:= \frac{(1+9 \times 3)^2+0}{7 \times (4+86 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{((1^9)+3) \times 50}{278+(6+4)}$
$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{(4-2+7) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{86457} := \frac{(1^9+3) \times 20}{8+(6+4) \times 5 \times 7}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((9-3) \times 50)}{27 \times (8 \times (6-4))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{46728} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{4 \times (6+7 \times 2 \times 8)}$		$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (3 \times 50))}{27 \times (8+64)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{46827} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{468-2+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19345}{62780} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 3) \times 4 + 5}{6^2 \times 7 - 80}$	$:= \frac{(1+(9-3)) \times 50}{((2^7)-(8-6)) \times 4}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{((1+9)^3) - 50}{(2+7) \times 8 + (6^4)} \\ & := \frac{(1+9) \times (3 \times 50)}{27 \times (8 \times (6+4))} \end{aligned} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19364}{80752} \quad := \frac{(1+9) \times (3+6) + 4}{8 \times 07 \times (5+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{46827} \quad := \frac{1^{93} \times 50}{46+82-7} \quad := \frac{19+ (3+6)^4}{80 \times 7^{5-2}} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19456}{70832} \quad := \frac{(1+9 \times 4 - 5) \times 6}{708 - 3^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{48762} \quad := \frac{1^9 \times 3 \times 50}{46 \times 8 + 2 - 7} \quad := \frac{1 \times 936 + 4}{80 \times 7 \times (5+2)} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19458}{37260} \quad := \frac{1+9+45-8}{3 \times (7-2) \times 6+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{48762} \quad := \frac{1+9+3 \times 5+0}{48+7+6+2} \quad := \frac{1 \times 94 \times (5+8)}{(37+2) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{87462} \quad := \frac{1^{93} \times 50}{48+76+2} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19380}{25764} \quad := \frac{1 \times 93 - 8 + 0}{(2+5) \times 7 + 64}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{87462} \quad := \frac{(1+9-3) \times 50}{4+876+2} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19380}{62475} \quad := \frac{19 \times 3 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (2+47) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{87462} \quad := \frac{1+9+3 \times 5+0}{87+4 \times 6+2} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19380}{74256} \quad := \frac{1^9 \times 380}{(7 \times 4 - 2) \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19350}{87462} \quad := \frac{(1^9+3) \times 50}{(8+74 \times 6) \times 2} \quad := \frac{(1+9) \times (4+6 \times 5)}{(7+3^2) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1-((9-3) \times (5-7))}{(2 \times ((08-4))) + 6} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19432}{86750} \quad := \frac{1-9+4+32}{8+67+50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1-((9 \times (3-5)) - 7)}{2 - (0 - ((8 \times 4) - 6))} \quad := \frac{(1+9+4) \times 3 \times 2}{(8+67) \times 5+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 \times ((9 \times 3) + (5+7))}{((20-8) \times 4) - 6} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19437}{65208} \quad := \frac{(19+4) \times 3 - 7}{6^{5-2} - 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 - (9 - (3+57))}{2 - (0 - (8+46))} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 + 4 \times 3 \times 7}{6 \times 52 + 0 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 \times (9 + ((3+5) \times 7))}{(2 \times ((08 \times 4))) + 6} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 + 43 \times 7}{65 \times 2 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 + ((9 - (3-5)) \times 7)}{(2 - (0 - (8+4))) \times 6} \quad \blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19437}{80256} \quad := \frac{(19+4) \times 3 - 7}{8 \times (02+5 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 \times (93 + (5-7))}{20 + (84-6)} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 + 4 \times 3 \times 7}{(80-2) \times 5 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{1 + (9 + ((3^5) + 7))}{(2^{08}) + (4 \times 6)} \quad := \frac{(19+4 \times 3) \times 7}{8 \times 02 \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{193 - (5-7)}{(2^{08}) - 46} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 + 43 \times 7}{80 \times (2 \times 5 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19357}{20846} \quad := \frac{(1-94) \times (3-7)}{8 \times 02^5 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19467}{23058} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{2 \times (3 + 058)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19467}{28350} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{(2+8) \times 3 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19467}{80325} \quad := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{(80+3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \frac{19468}{37052} \quad := \frac{1+94+6-8}{3 \times (7+052)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19470}{36285} &:= \frac{19-4+7+0}{3 \times (6-2+8)+5} \\ &:= \frac{1-9+4+70}{36+2+85} \\ &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (4+7)+0}{3 \times (62+8)-5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19470}{62835} &:= \frac{19-4+7+0}{6+(2+8+3) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1+94-7+0}{6-2+8 \times 35} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19485}{20736} := \frac{(1+9 \times 48) \times 5}{2^{07} \times 3 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19485}{72063} := \frac{(1+9 \times 48) \times 5}{7+20^{6-3}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19502}{84376} := \frac{(1 \times 9+5)^{02}}{8 \times (4^3+7 \times 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{26784} &:= \frac{1+9-5+30}{2-6+7 \times 8-4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (5+30)}{2 \times 6^{7-8+4}} \\ &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (5+30)}{(2+6+7) \times 8 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{46872} &:= \frac{((1^9)+5) \times 30}{(4-(6-8)) \times 72} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{95}) \times 30}{4 \times (6 \times (8-(7-2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(9 \times 5)) \times 30}{46 \times (8 \times (7+2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(9-5)) \times (3-0)}{4 \times (6+(8-(7-2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(9-5)) \times 30}{(4+68) \times (7-2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (5-(3-0))}{4 \times (6-(8-(7 \times 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1+9)^{5-3}+0}{4 \times (6+((8 \times 7)-2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1-9) \times (5-30)}{4 \times ((6 \times 8)+72)} \\ &:= \frac{(19+5) \times 30}{4 \times (6 \times (8 \times (7+2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{1 \times ((9+5) \times 30)}{(4+68) \times (7 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((9-5) \times 30)}{((4 \times 6)+8) \times (7+2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (5+30))}{(46+8) \times (7 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (95+30)}{(4+6) \times ((8+7) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (95-30)}{4 \times ((6 \times 8)-(7+2))}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(9-(5-30))}{(4-(6-8)) \times (7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(9+(5 \times 30))}{4 \times (((6+8) \times 7)-2)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+9+5^3+0}{(4-((6-8) \times 7))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(9+(5+30))}{(4-(6-(8 \times 7))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(9+530)}{4 \times (6 \times ((8 \times 7)-2))}$$

$$:= \frac{195+30}{468+72}$$

$$:= \frac{195-30}{468-72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{64728} := \frac{1+9-5+30}{6 \times (4+7 \times 2)+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19536}{87024} := \frac{1+9^{5-3}+6}{8 \times 7^{-02+4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19548}{60273} := \frac{(1+(9-5)) \times (4+8)}{60+((2^7)-3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(9+(54+8))}{(60+(2 \times 7)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{1+(95-(4+8))}{602-(7^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((5 \times 4)-8))}{60+273}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9+(5+4)) \times 8)}{60+((2^7) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9-5) \times 48)}{602-(7+3)}$$

$$:= \frac{1-(9+(5 \times (4-8)))}{60-(2+(7 \times 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19560}{27384} := \frac{((1^9)+5) \times 60}{2 \times (7 \times (3 \times (8+4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{95}) \times 60}{2 \times (7+(3+(8 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+(9-5)) \times (6-0)}{2+((7+3) \times (8-4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1+9) \times (5+(6-0))}{2 \times (73+(8-4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1-9) \times (5-60)}{2 \times (7 \times ((3+8) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(19+5) \times 60}{(27-3) \times 84}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 \times 5)+60)}{2-(7-(38 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9+5) \times 60)}{2 \times ((73 \times 8)+4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (5 \times (6-0)))}{(2+7) \times (38+4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9+(5+(6-0)))}{2 \times (7+(3+(8-4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (95-60)}{(27 \times 3)-(8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{1+((9+5) \times (6-0))}{(2^7)+(3-(8+4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1+((9-5) \times (6-0))}{2+((7 \times 3)+(8+4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (5 - 60))}{2 - (7 - (3 \times (8 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 \times (5 + (6 - 0)))}{(2^7) + (3 \times (8 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (5 \times (6 - 0)))}{(2 + (7 - (3 - 8))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (5 + 60))}{2 + (7 + (3 \times (8 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (95 - (6 - 0))}{2 - ((7 - 38) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{195 + 60}{2 + ((7^3) + (8 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{195 - 60}{27 \times (3 + (8 - 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19560}{74328} := \frac{1 \times (9 + (5 + (6 - 0)))}{74 - ((3 \times 2) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((9 - 5) \times (6 - 0))}{7 + (4 + (3 \times 28))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (95 - (6 - 0))}{(7 - (4^3)) \times (2 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (9 - 5)) \times (6 - 0)}{74 + (32 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (5 \times (6 - 0)))}{((7 \times 4) - (3^2)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^{95}) \times 60}{(74 \times 3) - (2 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (5 + 60))}{(7 \times 43) - (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((9 + 5) \times (6 - 0))}{(7 \times (43 + 2)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 \times 5) + 60)}{7 \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{195 + 60}{(((7 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19570}{28634} := \frac{1^9 \times 570}{2 - (8 - 6^3) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19572}{64308} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5 + 7 + 2}{6 \times 4 + 30 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 - 5) \times 7 \times 2}{64 \times 3 - 08}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^9 + 5) \times 7^2}{6 + 4 \times 30 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 \times 5 \times (7 + 2)}{6^4 + 30 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 9 \times (5 - 7) + 2}{64 - 3 + 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{20736} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 4}{2 + 07 + 3 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 \times 5 - 8 - 4}{(2 + 07 - 3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (5 + 8 + 4)}{(2 + 07) \times 3 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 + 5 \times 8 \times 4}{(20 + 7 + 3) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 \times 5 \times 8 - 4}{2^{07} \times 3 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 \times 58 + 4}{(20 + 73) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{36720} := \frac{1 \times ((9 + (5 - 8)) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 + (7 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - ((9 \times (5 - 8)) - 4)}{3 \times (6 + (7 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 - (5 - 8)) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (9 \times (5 - (8 + 4)))}{3 \times ((6 \times 7) - (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (5 - 84))}{3 + (6 \times (7 + 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^9) \times (58 \times 4)}{3 + (6 \times (72 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 9) \times ((5 \times 8) - 4)}{3 + (672 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 95) \times (8 - 4)}{(3^6) - (7 + (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (95 + 8)) \times 4}{3 \times ((6 + 7) \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (9 + 5)) \times (8 \times 4)}{(3 + (6 \times 7)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 + 5) \times (8 - 4)}{36 \times (7 - (2 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{67320} := \frac{(1 - 9 + 5 \times 8) \times 4}{6 \times 73 + 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{76032} := \frac{1 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 4}{7 + 60 - 3 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{35478} := \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{3 + (5 \times 4 + 7) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{37584} := \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{((3 + 7) \times 5 + 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{43758} := \frac{1 + 96 + 02}{4 + 3 \times 75 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{45738} := \frac{(1^9) \times (6 \times (02))}{4 \times (5 + (7 + (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(1^9) \times (60 \times 2)}{4 \times (5 + (73 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (6 - (0 \times 2)))}{4 + (5 - (7 + (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (6 \times (0 \times 2)))}{4 + (5 + (7 - (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (6 \times (-02)))}{45 - (7 - (3 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (6 - (0 \times 2)))}{45 + (73 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (6 - (-02)))}{4 \times ((5 \times (7 + 3)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (6 \times (02)))}{(4 \times 57) + (3 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (6 - (0 \times 2)))}{(4 - 5) \times (7 \times (3 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (96 - (0 \times 2))}{(4 \times (57 - 3)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 - (6 + (-02)))}{4 + (5 \times (7 + (3 - 8)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 + (9 + 602)}{4 \times ((5 \times 73) - 8)} &:= \frac{(19 \times 6 + 4) \times 7}{(5 + 3) \times 280} &:= \frac{1 \times ((9 - 6)^{8-3})}{240 + 57} \\
 &:= \frac{19 \times (6 - (0 \times 2))}{(4 \times 57) + 38} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{82305} := \frac{19 - 6 \times (4 - 7)}{(8 + 23) \times 05} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{24570} := \frac{(1^{96} + 8)^3}{(2 \times 4 + 5) \times 70} \\
 &:= \frac{19 \times (60 \times 2)}{4 \times (5 \times (7 \times 38))} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{57024} := \frac{(1 \times 9 - 6)^{8-3}}{5 \times 70 \times 2 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{19 + (6 - (-02))}{4 + ((5 \times 7) + (3 \times 8))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19650}{42837} := \frac{1^{96} \times 50}{(42 - 8) \times 3 + 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{74250} := \frac{(1^{96} + 8)^3}{(7 + 4) \times 250} \\
 &:= \frac{196 - (-02)}{457 - (3 - 8)} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{53784} &:= \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{(5 + 37) \times 8 - 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19650}{48732} := \frac{1^{96} \times 50}{4 \times (8 + 7 \times 3 + 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19703}{45628} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 7 + 03}{4 \times (5 + 6 - 2) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{73458} &:= \frac{1 + 96 + 02}{7^3 + 4 \times 5 + 8} &:= \frac{1 + 9 \times (6 + 5) + 0}{4 \times (8 \times 7 + 3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 70 - 3}{4 + 5 \times 6^2 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{83754} &:= \frac{19 - 6 - 02}{8 - 3 \times (7 - 5 \times 4)} &:= \frac{(1 \times 9 - 6) \times 50}{4 \times (87 + 3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 703}{45 \times 6^2 + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 9 + 6 \times 02}{(8 + 3 + 7) \times 5 + 4} &:= \frac{(1 + 9 - 6) \times 50}{487 + 3^2} &:= \frac{1 + 9 \times 7 \times 03}{4 \times 5 \times (6 + 2 \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{196 + 02}{837 + 5 + 4} &:= \frac{(1 + 9 \times 6) \times 5 + 0}{4 - 8 + 7^3 \times 2} &:= \frac{19 \times 7 + 0 \times 3}{4 \times 5 + 6^2 \times 8} \\
 & &:= \frac{1^9 \times 6 \times 50}{4 + 8 + 732} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19608}{34572} &:= \frac{19 \times (6 - 0 \times 8)}{(34 - 5) \times 7 - 2} & &\blacktriangleright \frac{19706}{25384} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (7 + 06)}{(2 \times 5 \times 3 + 8) \times 4} \\
 & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19620}{85347} &:= \frac{1^{96} \times 20}{8 - 5 + 3 \times 4 \times 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{24057} := \frac{(1 - (9 - (6 + 8))) \times 3}{2 \times (4 - ((0 \times 5) - 7))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{19708}{24635} := \frac{((1 + 9)^7 + 0) \times 8}{((2^4) - 6)^{3+5}} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 + (9 + (6 + (8 + 3)))}{2 - (4 + (0 - (5 \times 7)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (9 + 7)) \times (-08)}{((2^4) - 6) \times (3 \times 5)} \\
 & &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (6 - 8))) \times 3}{2 + (40 - (5 - 7))} &:= \frac{(1^9) \times (70 \times 8)}{(2 + (46 \times 3)) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19642}{35807} &:= \frac{1 \times 964 + 2}{3 \times (580 + 7)} &:= \frac{((1^9) + (6 + 8)) \times 3}{2 - (4 + (0 - 57))} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 8}{2 \times ((4^6 - 3) \times 5)} \\
 & &:= \frac{1 \times (9^{6-8+3})}{(2 \times (4 - (-05))) - 7} &:= \frac{(19 - (7 - 0)) \times 8}{2 \times (4 \times ((6 - 3) \times 5))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{28305} &:= \frac{(19 - 6) \times 4 + 7}{2 + 83 - 0 \times 5} &:= \frac{1 - (9 - (68 + 3))}{(2 + (4 - (-05))) \times 7} &:= \frac{1 - (9 + (7 \times (-08)))}{(2 - (4 - 6)) \times (3 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{53280} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 6 \times 4 \times 7}{(5 + 3 - 2) \times 80} &:= \frac{1 - (9 - (6 + 83))}{2 + (40 + 57)} &:= \frac{1 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^8)}{((2 - (4 - 6))^3) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 9 \times 6 + 4) \times 7}{(5 + 3^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (6 \times 8)) \times 3)}{2 + ((40 \times 5) + 7)} & \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 8)}{2 \times ((4 + 6) \times (3 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (7 \times (08)))}{(24 - 6) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{2 + (4 + (6 + (3 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (7 - (-08)))}{(24 - (6 \times 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (7 + (-08)))}{2 + (4 + (6 + (3 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 8)}{2 \times ((4 + (6 - 3)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(2 - (4 - (6 \times 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 \times (7 - (-08)))}{((2^4) + (6 \times 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + (9 + (70 - 8))}{2 \times (4 + (6 + 35))}$$

$$:= \frac{19 - (7 - (0 \times 8))}{2 + (4 - (6 - (3 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{19 - (7 - (-08))}{(2 - (4 - (6 - 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{19 - (7 + (-08))}{(2^4) - (6 - (3 \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19720}{46835} := \frac{1 + 9 + 7 \times 2 + 0}{4 + 68 - 3 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 7) \times 2 + 0}{4 - 6 + 83 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 - 7) \times 20}{(4 + 6) \times 8 + 3 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 9 \times 7) \times 2 + 0}{4 \times (68 + 3 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 - 7) \times 20}{(46 - 8) \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19720}{64583} := \frac{(1 \times 9 - 7) \times 20}{6 \times 4 \times 5 + 8 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 - 7) \times 20}{(6 \times 45 - 8) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19728}{34056} := \frac{19 \times 7 \times 2 + 8}{(3 + 40) \times (5 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19728}{34560} := \frac{19 + 7^2 \times 8}{(3 + 4 + 5) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19734}{25806} := \frac{1 + (9 - 7)^3 + 4}{25 - 8 + 0 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9 + (7 - 3) \times 4}{2^5 + 8 - 06}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 7 - 3) \times 4}{2 \times 5 \times 8 - 06}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 + 7) \times 3 \times 4}{2 + 5 \times 80 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 73 - 4}{(25 - 8) \times 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19734}{65208} := \frac{1 - 9 + 73 + 4}{(6 + 5) \times 20 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 + 7 - 3) \times 4}{6 \times 52 - 08}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - 9 \times (7 - 3 \times 4)}{(-6 + 5^2) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19750}{34286} := \frac{1^9 \times 750}{3 \times (428 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19758}{60342} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 7 + 58}{(60 - 3) \times 4 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19760}{25384} := \frac{(19 + 7) \times 60}{2 \times 5^3 \times 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19760}{53248} := \frac{19 + 76 + 0}{5 + 3 + 248}$$

$$:= \frac{1^9 \times 760}{(5 - 3 + 2)^4 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19762}{34850} := \frac{19 \times 76 + 2}{(3 + 48) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19762}{84350} := \frac{1^9 + 7 \times 6 - 2}{(8 \times 4 + 3) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + 9^{(7-6) \times 2}}{(8 - 4 + 3) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{23058} := \frac{1 \times (9 - (7 - (6 + 4)))}{2 \times ((3 \times (05)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (7 + (6 - 4)))}{(2^3 + 0) + (5 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (9 - ((7 \times 6) - 4))}{2 + (30 - (5 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 4))}{(2 \times (30 - 5)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (9 - (7 \times (6 - 4)))}{2 - (3 + ((0 \times 5) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 + ((9 \times 7) - (6 + 4))}{2 + (3 - (0 - 58))}$$

$$:= \frac{1 - (9 - (76 + 4))}{(2 - 30) \times (5 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 - 7) \times (6 + 4)}{2 \times (30 + (5 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(19 - 7)^{6-4}}{((2 + 30) \times 5) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + (9 - 7)) \times 64}{(23 - (-05)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(1 + 9) \times (7 \times (6 \times 4))}{(2 + (3^{05})) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{28350} := \frac{(19 + 7 \times 6) \times 4}{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{1 \times 976 \times 4}{2 \times 8 \times 350}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{32805} := \frac{(19 + 7 \times 6) \times 4}{3 + 2 + 80 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{53802} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 7 + 6 - 4}{(5 \times 3 - 8^{02})}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{58320} &:= \frac{1+9 \times (7+6)+4}{5 \times 8 \times 3^2+0} & \frac{19832}{54760} &:= \frac{1+(9+8 \times 3) \times 2}{5-(4-7) \times 60} & \frac{19845}{32760} &:= \frac{1+984-5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{82350} &:= \frac{1 \times (9-(7-(6+4)))}{8-((2^3)-50)} & \frac{19834}{67520} &:= \frac{1 \times (9+8) \times 3-4}{(6+7+5) \times 20} & \frac{19845}{62370} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (8+4 \times 5)}{32 \times (7+6)+0} \\ &:= \frac{1+(9+(7 \times (6-4)))}{(8-(2 \times 3)) \times 50} & & & & \frac{19845}{62370} &:= \frac{1+(9-8)^4+5}{6+23-7+0} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((7-6) \times 4))}{(8-(2+3)) \times 50} & \frac{19836}{27405} &:= \frac{(1+9 \times 8+3) \times 6}{2 \times 7 \times (40+5)} & & & := \frac{1 \times 9-8+4 \times 5}{62-3+7+0} \\ &:= \frac{1-(9-(7 \times (6-4)))}{8+(2+(3 \times (5-0)))} & \frac{19836}{47025} &:= \frac{1 \times 98+3 \times 6}{(4+7) \times 025} & & & := \frac{1+98+4 \times 5}{6-2+370} \\ &:= \frac{1+(9+((7 \times 6)-4))}{8 \times ((2+3) \times (5-0))} & \frac{19836}{54720} &:= \frac{1-9+(8+3) \times 6}{(5-4+7) \times 20} & \frac{19845}{67032} &:= \frac{1-9+8+45}{6+(70+3) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1+(97+(6+4))}{(8-(2-3)) \times 50} & & & & & := \frac{(1+9) \times 8 \times (4+5)}{(6+70) \times 32} \\ &:= \frac{(1^9) \times (7 \times (6 \times 4))}{(8+(2 \times 3)) \times 50} & \frac{19836}{57420} &:= \frac{1 \times 9-8+3 \times 6}{57-4+2+0} & \frac{19845}{67230} &:= \frac{(19-8) \times 4+5}{(6+7)^2-3+0} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(9-7)) \times 64}{(8+(2^3)) \times 50} & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (((9 \times 7)-6) \times 4)}{((8+2)^3)-50} & & & \frac{19856}{32704} &:= \frac{1+9+8+5-6}{(3-2) \times 7 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((9-7) \times (6^4))}{((8-2)^3) \times 50} & & & & & := \frac{9 \times 8+5 \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(19-7) \times 64}{8 \times ((2^3) \times 50)} & & & & & := \frac{(1+9) \times (8+5)+6}{32 \times 7-0 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1-(97-(6^4))}{((8+2)^3) \times (5-0)} & & & & & := \frac{19 \times 8-5+6}{3^2 \times 7 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19765}{30284} &:= \frac{1+9 \times (7+6) \times 5}{30^2+8-4} & \frac{19836}{75240} &:= \frac{19-8+3 \times 6}{7 \times 5 \times 2+40} & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19782}{45360} &:= \frac{1^9+78 \times 2}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6+0} & \frac{19837}{64052} &:= \frac{1+9 \times 8+3+7}{6 \times (40+5)-2} & \frac{19872}{34560} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times 7-2}{3^4+5-6+0} \\ & & & & & & := \frac{198+7+2}{3 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6+0} \\ & & & & & & := \frac{1+9 \times (8+7)+2}{(3-4+5) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19824}{30576} &:= \frac{1+9 \times (8-2)+4}{3 \times 05+76} & \frac{19845}{20736} &:= \frac{1 \times 98 \times 45}{2^{07} \times 36} & \frac{19872}{35604} &:= \frac{(1 \times 9+8+7) \times 2}{3 \times 5 \times 6-04} \\ & & & & & & := \frac{(1-9+8 \times 7) \times 2}{3 \times 56+04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19824}{50736} &:= \frac{19 \times (8-2)+4}{50+7 \times 36} & \frac{19845}{26730} &:= \frac{1 \times 9+84+5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0} & \frac{19872}{40365} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7-2)}{(4+03+6) \times 5} \\ & & & := \frac{(19-8) \times 4+5}{2+67-3+0} & & & \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7+2)}{40+3 \times 6 \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(1+(9+(8 \times 7))) \times 2}{(5+6) \times (30+4)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((01+(6+7)))}{8+((3+(5+4)) \times 9)}$
$:= \frac{(1+9+8) \times 7+2}{4 \times (0 \times 3+65)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (8 \times (7-2)))}{5 \times (6 \times (30+4))}$	$:= \frac{(2+(0-(1-6))) \times 7}{8+(3 \times (5 \times (4+9)))}$
$:= \frac{(19 \times 8)+72}{(4+03) \times 65}$	$:= \frac{1+((9 \times 8)+(7-2))}{5+(6^{3-0 \times 4})}$	$:= \frac{(2-(0-(1+6))) \times 7}{(83-54) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{1-9+8 \times 7^2}{4 \times 03 \times 65}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(20-(1+6)) \times 7}{((8 \times 3)+5) \times (4+9)}$
$:= \frac{(1+9-8)^7 \times 2}{40 \times (3 \times 6-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20137}{49568} := \frac{2+01+3+7}{4+9+5+6+8}$	$:= \frac{(2-(0-16)) \times 7}{(8^3)+(5-(4-9))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{43056} := \frac{1 \times (9-(8-(7-2)))}{4-((3 \times (-05))+6)}$	$:= \frac{20+13-7}{4 \times (9+5-6+8)}$	$:= \frac{(20+16) \times 7}{((8 \times (3 \times 5))-4) \times 9}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (9+(8-(7-2)))}{(4 \times (3-(-05)))-6}$	$:= \frac{2+01 \times 37}{(4+(9+(5-6))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(2^{01 \times 6}) \times 7}{8+(3 \times ((5^4)-9))}$
$:= \frac{1+((9 \times 8)-(7^2))}{4+((3-(-05)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{2+(-01+3)^7}{4 \times (9-5+6) \times 8}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(1^9) \times ((8+7) \times 2)}{4^3-05+6}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 013 \times 7}{4 \times 95+68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20169}{47385} := \frac{20+(1+6) \times 9}{(4-7 \times (3-8)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{1+(98+(7+2))}{(4+(30+5)) \times 6}$	<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20169}{53784} := \frac{((2-(-01))^6)-9}{(53+7) \times (8 \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times (9 \times (8+(7 \times 2)))}{430+(5-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20139}{48657} := \frac{20+13 \times 9}{4 \times (86-5)+7}$	$:= \frac{((2 \times (-01))+6) \times 9}{((5-3)^7)-(8 \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{1 \times ((98 \times 7)-2)}{(4+(3^{05})) \times 6}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(2-(0-(1+6))) \times 9}{(53-(7-8)) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{53406} := \frac{1+9-8+7 \times 2}{53-4-06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20163}{59784} := \frac{20 \times (1+6)+3}{((5+9) \times 7+8) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2-(-01)) \times (6+9)}{(5^3)+(7-(8+4))}$
$:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7-2)}{5+3^4+0 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20163}{87945} := \frac{20-1+6^3}{(8-7)^9+4^5}$	$:= \frac{(2-(-01)) \times 69}{(53-7) \times (8+4)}$
$:= \frac{(1 \times 9+8+7) \times 2}{5^3+4-0 \times 6}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(2 \times (0+(1 \times 6)))+9}{53+(7-(8-4))}$
$:= \frac{(1 \times 9+87) \times 2}{(5+3^4) \times 06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20167}{58394} := \frac{2 \times 01 \times 67}{(5+83+9) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2^{01 \times 6}) \times 9}{((5-3)^7) \times (8+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{56304} := \frac{1 \times (9-(8-(7-2)))}{5+((6-(3-0)) \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{20 \times 1 \times 67}{5 \times 8 \times (3+94)}$	$:= \frac{(2+(0-(1-6))) \times 9}{(5+37) \times (8-4)}$
$:= \frac{1+((9 \times 8)-(7^2))}{5+(63-(0 \times 4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20167}{83549} := \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 16))+7}{8+(3+(5+(4+9)))}$	$:= \frac{(2+(-01)) \times (6 \times 9)}{53+(7+84)}$
$:= \frac{(1^9)-(8-(7^2))}{5-(6-(30 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{2+(0-(1-(6+7)))}{83+(5 \times (4-9))}$	$:= \frac{(2+(-01)) \times (6^9)}{((5-(3-7)) \times 8)^4}$
$:= \frac{(1-(9-(8 \times 7))) \times 2}{(5+(63-0)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2-(0-(1^6))) \times 7}{(8 \times (3+(5+4)))-9}$	$:= \frac{(2+(-01)) \times (6+9)}{5 \times (3-(7-(8+4)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 + (-01)) \times 69}{(53 - 7) \times (8 - 4)}$	$:= \frac{20 \times ((1 + 6) \times 9)}{5 \times (3 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (16 + 9))}{7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) - 5))}$
$:= \frac{(20 - (1 + 6)) \times 9}{(5 + (3 \times 7)) \times (8 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{20 + (1 - (6 - 9))}{(5 \times (3 - 7)) + 84}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (16 - 9))}{7 \times ((8 - (4 + 3)) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{(20 - (1 - 6)) \times 9}{5 \times ((3 + 7) \times (8 + 4))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (1 + (6 \times 9))}{(5 + (3 \times (7 + 8))) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - 169)}{(7 + (8 + 4)) \times 35}$
$:= \frac{(20 \times (1 \times 6)) + 9}{(5 + (3 + 78)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{20 + 169}{(5 + 37) \times (8 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 9)))}{7 \times ((8 - 4) \times (3 \times 5))}$
$:= \frac{(20 + (1 \times 6)) \times 9}{(5 - 3) \times (78 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{201 - (6 + 9)}{((5^3) + (7 - 8)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{20 \times ((1^6) \times 9)}{7 \times ((8 + (4 \times 3)) \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{(20 + (1 - 6)) \times 9}{5 \times ((3 + (7 + 8)) \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{201 - (6 - 9)}{(((5 - 3)^7) + 8) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{201 + 69}{78 + (4 \times (3^5))}$
$:= \frac{(20 + 1) \times 69}{(53 - 7) \times 84}$	$:= \frac{201 + (6 - 9)}{((5^3) + 7) \times (8 - 4)}$	
$:= \frac{(201 - 6) \times 9}{5 \times (3 \times (78 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{201 + 69}{(53 + 7) \times (8 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20174}{85936} := \frac{2 + 01 + 74}{8 \times (5 + (9 - 3) \times 6)}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((1^6)^9))}{(5 + (3 \times (7 - 8))) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20169}{78435} := \frac{((2 - (-01))^6) + 9}{(78 + 4) \times 35}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20174}{95368} := \frac{2 \times 01 \times (7 + 4)}{(9 - 5 + 3 + 6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((1^6) + 9))}{5 + (3^{7-8+4})}$	$:= \frac{((2 \times (-01)) + 6) \times 9}{7 \times (8 + (4 + (3 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 01 + 74}{9 + 5 \times (3 + 68)}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 - (6 - 9)))}{(5 \times (3 - (7 - 8))) - 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 9}{(7 - (8 - (4^3))) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{2^{01 \times 7} + 4}{(9 \times (5 + 3) + 6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 + (6 \times 9)))}{(53 - (7 + 8)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (-01)) \times (6 + 9)}{7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) + 5))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 0174}{95 + 3^6 + 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 + (6 + 9)))}{53 + (7 - (8 + 4))}$	$:= \frac{(2^{01 \times 6}) \times 9}{7 \times (((8 - 4)^3) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{20 - (1 - 7) \times 4}{9 - 5 + 3 \times 68}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 + 69))}{(((5 + 3) \times 7) - 8) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 9}{7 \times ((8 - (4 - 3)) \times 5)}$	
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (16 + 9))}{(5 + ((3 \times 7) - 8)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (-01)) \times (6 \times 9)}{(7 - (8 - 43)) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20175}{86349} := \frac{(-2 \times 01 + 7) \times 5}{8 + 63 + 4 \times 9}$
$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (16 - 9))}{(5 \times (3 - (7 - 8))) + 4}$	$:= \frac{(20 + (1 - 6)) \times 9}{7 \times ((8 + (4 + 3)) \times 5)}$	
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - ((1 - 6) \times 9))}{(53 + 7) \times (8 - 4)}$	$:= \frac{(20 + 1) \times (6 + 9)}{7 \times (((8 \times 4) + 3) \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20176}{35984} := \frac{20 + 1 + 76}{3 \times 59 - 8 + 4}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 9)))}{(5 - (3 - 7)) \times (8 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{(20 + 16) \times 9}{7 \times ((8 + 4) \times (3 \times 5))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20176}{58394} := \frac{2 + 017 \times 6}{5 + (83 - 9) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 + 9)))}{5 - (3 \times (7 - (8 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 + (6 + 9)))}{7 \times (8 + (4 + (3 - 5)))}$	
$:= \frac{20 \times ((1^6) \times 9)}{(5 + (3 + 7)) \times (8 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (1 + 69))}{7 \times (8 + (4 \times (3 + 5)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{36594} := \frac{2 + 01 + 7 \times 8}{3 \times 6 - 5 + 94}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{63954} &:= \frac{2+01+7 \times 8}{6^3-9-5 \times 4} &:= \frac{20 \times (1 \times (9+6))}{(43+7) \times (5+8)} &:= \frac{2-0 \times 3+4 \times 9}{86+75+1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{93456} &:= \frac{20+1 \times 7-8}{(9+3-4) \times (5+6)} &:= \frac{20 \times (1 \times 96)}{(4^3) \times (7+58)} & \\ &:= \frac{2-01+7 \times 8}{(9+(3+4) \times 5) \times 6} &:= \frac{20+(1+(9+6))}{((4+(3+7)) \times 5)+8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20356}{97418} &:= \frac{2-(03-5) \times 6}{9 \times 7+4 \times 1^8} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (01+7 \times 8)}{(9+3) \times 4 \times (5+6)} &:= \frac{20+196}{(43-7) \times (5+8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3+56)}{(9 \times 7+4 \times 1) \times 8} \\ & & &:= \frac{20 \times (3+5)-6}{9^{7-4} \times 1+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{34578} &:= \frac{(2+01 \times 9) \times 6}{(3+4) \times 5+78} &:= \frac{201+9-6}{457-3+8} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{43758} &:= \frac{((2 \times (-01))+9) \times 6}{4^3+((7 \times 5)-8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{57834} &:= \frac{2 \times (-01+9)+6}{5 \times (7+8)-3 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(2-(-01)) \times 96}{(43+(7 \times 5)) \times 8} &:= \frac{2 \times (01+9 \times 6)}{5 \times 7 \times (8-3+4)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3+5+8)}{4-6 \times (1-9)+7} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0+(1 \times 9)))+6}{4-(3+(7-58))} &:= \frac{(2+01 \times 9) \times 6}{(5 \times 7-8) \times (3+4)} &:= \frac{2^{03} \times (5+8)}{4 \times (61-9+7)} \\ &:= \frac{(2+(-01)) \times (9 \times 6)}{4+((3 \times (7 \times 5))+8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{74358} &:= \frac{2 \times (-01+9)+6}{7 \times 4 \times 3+5-8} &:= \frac{2 \times 03^5+8}{4^{6-1}+97} \\ &:= \frac{(20-(1^9)) \times 6}{((4 \times 3)+7) \times (5+8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (01+9 \times 6)}{7 \times (4^3-5)-8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{46719} &:= \frac{2 \times 03 \times (5+8)}{46+7 \times 19} \\ &:= \frac{(20+(1+9)) \times 6}{((4^3) \times 7)-58} &:= \frac{2+0196}{(7-4)^{3-5+8}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{96174} &:= \frac{2+035-8}{9 \times (6+1)+74} \\ &:= \frac{(201-9) \times 6}{4 \times ((3+75) \times 8)} &:= \frac{(2+01 \times 9) \times 6}{7 \times 43-58} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{97614} &:= \frac{2 \times 03 \times (5+8)}{9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 1-4} \\ &:= \frac{2-(0-(1+(9+6)))}{43-(7+(5-8))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{75438} &:= \frac{20-1+9+6}{7 \times (5+4 \times 3)+8} & \\ &:= \frac{2-(0-(1+(9-6)))}{4+(3-(7-(5+8)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{83457} &:= \frac{20-(1-9) \times 6}{8+(34+5) \times 7} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{45198} &:= \frac{2 \times 03+67}{(4+5) \times (1+9+8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 19)+6)}{(4 \times (3 \times 7))-58} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{83754} &:= \frac{20-1+9+6}{(8+3 \times 7) \times 5-4} &:= \frac{20+3 \times 6 \times 7}{4-5 \times (1-9) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0-((1-9) \times 6))}{(4 \times ((3+7) \times 5))+8} &:= \frac{201+9-6}{837+5+4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{51894} &:= \frac{20+3 \times 6 \times 7}{(5-1+89) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0+((1+9) \times 6))}{4-((3-(7 \times 5)) \times 8)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{85374} &:= \frac{-2 \times 01+9+6}{8+5 \times (3 \times 7-4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{95418} &:= \frac{2 \times 03+67}{9 \times (5+41-8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0+(1 \times (9+6)))}{4+((3 \times 7)+(5 \times 8))} & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0+(1 \times 96))}{((4^3)-(7+5)) \times 8} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20349}{86751} &:= \frac{2 \times 03+4+9}{8+6 \times (7+5)+1} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20376}{59184} &:= \frac{203 \times 7-6}{5+9+1 \times 8^4} \\ & & & &\blacktriangleright \frac{20376}{89145} &:= \frac{2^{03} \times (7-6)}{(8 \times (9-(1 \times 4)))-5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2^{03+7-6}}{(8+(9+(1-4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{20+(3+(7-6))}{(8+(9+(1 \times 4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{20 \times (3-(7-6))}{(8-(9 \times (1-4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2-(0-(3+7))) \times 6}{(8 \times ((9+1) \times 4)) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{2-(0-(3 \times (7 \times 6)))}{8 \times ((9+(1+4)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{-03+7}) \times 6}{((8 \times (9+1)) + 4) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2^{0 \times 37+6}}{8 \times (((9+1) \times 4) - 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9)) + 4}{8 - (1 - (5 + 76))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9)) - 4}{8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 3)) + (9 \times 4)}{8 \times (1 \times (5 + (7 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 3)) + (9 - 4)}{8 - (1 \times ((5 - 7) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 3)) + 94}{8 \times (1 \times (5 + (7 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 \times 9))) + 4}{8 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 7) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 + 9))) + 4}{8 \times (15 - (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (03)) - (9 - 4)}{8 + (1 - (5 \times (7 - 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(20 \times 3) - (9 \times 4)}{(8 + (15 - 7)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(20 \times 3) + 94}{8 \times ((1^5) + 76)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 3) - (9 \times 4))}{8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 3) - (9 + 4))}{8 + (1 + (57 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 39) - 4)}{8 + (15 + (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 4))}{81 + (57 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (3 + (9 + 4)))}{8 \times (1 - (5 - (7 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (3 + (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (1 \times (5 \times (7 - 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{20394}{65817} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3 + 9) + 4}{6 \times (5 + 8 \times 1) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 03 \times 9 \times 4}{6 \times 58 \times 1 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{20 + 39 \times 4}{6 - 5 + 81 \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2 \times (03)) + (9 \times 4)}{(8 + (1 - 5)) \times (7 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (03)) + (9 + 4)}{81 - (5 \times (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (03)) + (9 - 4)}{8 - (1 + (5 - (7 \times 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (3 + 94))}{(8 + (1 + 57)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (39 + 4))}{(8 + (15 + 7)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (3 - 94))}{8 \times (1^{576})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{20394}{81576} &:= \frac{((2 - (-03)) \times 9) + 4}{(8 \times 15) + 76} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (-03)) + 9)^4}{81 \times (5 - (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((2^{03}) \times 9) + 4}{8 \times (1 - (5 - (7 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((20 \times 3) - 9) \times 4}{815 + (7 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((20 - 3) \times 9) - 4}{((81 + 5) \times 7) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 4}{8 + ((1 + 5) \times 76)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 + 9))) \times 4}{8 + ((1 + (5 \times 7)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (-03)) \times (9 + 4)}{8 + ((1 + 5) \times (7 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - 39)) \times 4}{8 \times (1 + (5 + 76))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + 39)) + 4}{8 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 7) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (-03)) + (9 + 4)}{(8 - 1) \times (5 - (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{2^{-03+9} - 4}{8 \times (1 + ((5 \times 7) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) - (9 - 4)}{8 - (1 - (5 \times (7 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) \times (9 + 4)}{8 \times (1 + (57 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) + (9 \times 4)}{8 - ((1 - 5) \times (7 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) + (9 + 4)}{8 + ((1^5) \times 76)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) + (9 - 4)}{(8 + (1 - 5)) \times (7 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{03}) + 94}{8 \times (1 \times (57 - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - 394)}{8 + 1576} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 3) + (9 \times 4))}{8 \times (((1 + 5) \times 7) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 39) + 4)}{8 \times (1 \times (5 - (7 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (3 - (9 \times 4)))}{(8 + (1 + (5 \times 7))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (3 - (9 + 4)))}{8 + (1 - (5 - 76))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (3 - 94))}{8 \times (15 + 76)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((3 + 9) \times 4))}{8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (3 \times (9 + 4)))}{8 - ((1 - 5) \times 76)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (3 \times (9 - 4)))}{(8 + (1 \times (5 + 7))) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (3 + (9 + 4)))}{8 \times (15 + (7 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (3 + (9 - 4)))}{8 \times (15 - (7 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (39 + 4))}{8 - ((1 - 57) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-03+9-4}}{8 - (1 \times (5 - (7 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - ((3 - 9) \times 4))}{8 \times (1 - ((5 - 7) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 4)))}{8 + ((15 + 7) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (3 - (9 + 4)))}{8 \times (1 + (5 \times (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 - (3 - (9 \times 4))}{8 - ((1 - (5 \times 7)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (3 \times (9 \times 4))}{8 \times (1 + (57 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (3 \times 94)}{8 \times (157 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (39 + 4)}{(8 - (1 - (5 \times 7))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{203 - (9 - 4)}{8 \times ((15 \times 7) - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20398}{45167} := \frac{2 \times (-03 + 9 + 8)}{4 \times 5 \times 1 + 6 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-03+9} - 8}{4 \times ((5 - 1) \times 6 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (03 + 9) \times 8}{4 \times 51 + 6 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20398}{65471} := \frac{2 \times (039 - 8)}{6 \times (5 + 4 \times 7) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20416}{39875} := \frac{2 \times 04 \times 16}{(3 - 9 + 8 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 + 4) \times 16}{3 + 9 \times (8 + 75)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20439}{81756} := \frac{((2 - (-04))^3) - 9}{817 + (5 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^{04}) \times 3) - 9}{(81 \times (7 - 5)) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 + 3))) \times 9}{(((8 - 1) \times 7) + 5) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 - 3))) \times 9}{(8 + 1) \times ((7 - 5) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (-04)) \times (3 \times 9)}{8 \times (1 \times (75 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (-04)) \times (3 + 9)}{8 \times (((1^7) + 5) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (-04)) \times 39}{(81 + 75) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 43)) + 9}{(8 - (1 \times (7 - 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 \times 3))) - 9}{(8 + (1 \times (7 - 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 + 3))) - 9}{8 + (1 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (04)) - (3 - 9)}{8 - (1 + (7 - 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (04)) + (3 \times 9)}{8 + ((17 + 5) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (04)) + 39}{8 - ((1 - 7) \times (5 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (-04)) + (3 \times 9)}{8 - (1 - (75 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{04}) - (3 - 9)}{8 - (1 - (75 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{04}) \times (3 \times 9)}{8 \times ((1 + (7 \times 5)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{04}) + (3 + 9)}{(8 + (1 - 7)) \times 56}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 4) - (3 \times 9)}{8 - ((1 - (7 \times 5)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 4) + (3 + 9)}{8 \times (((1 + 7) \times 5) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 4) + (3 - 9)}{8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 + (4 + 3)) \times 9}{81 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 43) - 9)}{8 - (1 - (7 + (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((4^3) - 9))}{(8 - ((1 - 7) \times 5)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((4 - 3)^9))}{8 - (1 \times (7 - (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (4 - (3 - 9)))}{8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (4 \times 39))}{8 \times ((17 \times 5) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (4 + (3 + 9)))}{8 + (1 + (7 + 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (4 + 39))}{(8 + (17 + 5)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (43 - 9))}{8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (4 - 39))}{8 \times (1^{756})}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - 439)}{8 + 1756}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 4) + (3 + 9))}{8 \times (1 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (4 - (3 + 9)))}{8 \times (1 \times (7 - (5 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (4 \times (3 - 9)))}{8 \times (1 - (7 - (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((4 \times 3) + 9))}{(81 \times (7 - 5)) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((4 \times 3) - 9))}{8 + (17 + (5 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4^3 + 9))}{8 \times (1 + ((7 + 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((4 + 3) \times 9))}{8 \times (1 \times (7 + 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4 - (3 - 9)))}{8 + (1 \times ((7 + 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4 \times (3 + 9)))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 - 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4 + (3 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((1^7) + (5 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4 + (3 + 9)))}{8 \times (17 + (5 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (4 + 39))}{8 - ((1 - 7) \times 56)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (43 - 9))}{8 \times (((1 + 7) \times 5) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-04-3+9}}{8 + (1 \times (7 - (5 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{04 \times 3 - 9}}{8 + (1 - (7 - (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - ((4 - 3)^9))}{8 + (1 \times (7 - (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (4 - (3 + 9)))}{8 \times (1 - (7 - (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (4 \times (3 - 9)))}{8 \times (1 + ((7 - 5) \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 - (4 \times (3 - 9))}{(8 + (1 + 7)) \times (5 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times ((4 \times 3) + 9)}{8 \times (1 \times (7 \times (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times ((4 \times 3) - 9)}{8 \times (1 + ((7 \times 5) - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + ((4 - 3)^9)}{8 - (1 - (7 \times (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (4 - (3 - 9))}{(8 + (1 \times (7 + 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (4 \times (3 \times 9))}{8 \times (1 + (7 + 56))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (4 \times 39)}{8 \times ((1 + 7) \times (5 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (4 + 39)}{(8 - (1 - (7 \times 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{204 - (3 - 9)}{(8 + (1 \times 7)) \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20451}{78693} := \frac{20 \times 4 \times 5 + 1}{7 + (8 - 6)^9 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20468}{91375} := \frac{2 \times 046 - 8}{(9 - 1 - 3) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 04 \times (6 + 8)}{(9 + 13 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{51678} := \frac{2 \times (04 + 9) - 3}{51 + 6 - 7 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (049 - 3)}{((5 + 1) \times 6 - 7) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{57816} := \frac{(20 + 49) \times 3}{578 + 1 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{61578} := \frac{(20 + 49) \times 3}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{67518} := \frac{(20 + 49) \times 3}{675 - 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{81675} := \frac{2 \times 04 \times 9 - 3}{(8 \times 1 \times 6 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{87561} := \frac{2 + 04 \times 9 \times 3}{8 + 7 \times (5 + 61)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20514}{97836} := \frac{2 \times 05 - 1 + 4}{9 + 7 \times 8 + 3 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + 5 + 14}{97 + 83 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20534}{71869} := \frac{((2^{05}) + 3) \times 4}{7 \times ((1^8) + 69)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^{05}) - 3) \times 4}{7 \times (1 + ((8 \times 6) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5^3))) + 4}{7 \times (1 + ((8 + 6) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 + 3))) + 4}{7 + (1 + (8 + (6 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + 53)) + 4}{7 \times ((1^8) + (6 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{053}) \times 4}{7 \times (1 \times ((8 - 6)^9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{053}) - 4}{7 \times (1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{05}) + 34}{7 \times (18 + (6 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 - (5 + 3)) \times 4}{7 \times (1 + (8 + (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times (5 + 3)) - 4}{7 \times (1 + (8 + 69))}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 - 5) \times (3 \times 4)}{(((7 + 1) \times 8) + 6) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 5) - 34)}{7 - (1 - (8 \times (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((5 - 3)^4))}{7 \times ((1^{86}) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (5 - (3 - 4)))}{7 + (18 - (6 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (5 + (3 + 4)))}{((7 + 1) \times 8) - (6 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (5 + (3 - 4)))}{7 \times (18 - (6 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (5 - 34))}{7 \times 1^{869}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (0 - 534)}{7 + 1869}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (5 \times (3 - 4)))}{7 \times (1 \times (8 + (6 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) + 4))}{7 \times (1 + ((8 - 6) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) - 4))}{7 \times (1 \times (8 - (6 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((5^3) - 4))}{7 \times (1 + (8 \times (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 - (3 - 4)))}{7 \times (1 + (8 + (6 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 + (3 + 4)))}{7 + (1 \times (8 + 69))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 + 34))}{7 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 6) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (53 + 4))}{7 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 6) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (53 - 4))}{7 \times (18 - (6 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-05+3 \times 4}}{7 + ((1 + (8 \times 6)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-05+3+4}}{7 - (1 \times (8 - (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-05 \times (3-4)}}{7 \times ((1^8) + (6 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{05+3-4}}{7 \times (1 - (8 - (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times ((5 - 3) \times 4)}{7 + (1 + (8 \times 69))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times (5 + (3 + 4))}{7 \times (1 \times (8 \times (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times (5 + (3 - 4))}{7 \times (1 + ((8 \times 6) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (5 \times 34)}{7 \times (1 \times (86 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{205 - (3^4)}{7 \times (1 - (8 - 69))}$$

$$:= \frac{205 - (3 + 4)}{7 \times ((18 \times 6) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{205 - (3 - 4)}{718 - (6 - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20536}{41978} := \frac{2^{05} + 36}{4 + 1 \times 9 \times (7 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20541}{93687} := \frac{(2 + 05) \times 41}{93 \times (6 + 8) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20548}{97136} := \frac{2 + 05 - 4 + 8}{9 + 7 + 1 \times 36}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 05 \times (4 - 8)}{97 + 13 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20574}{83916} := \frac{2 + 05^{7-4}}{(83 - 9) \times (1 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20583}{61749} := \frac{((2 - (-05)) \times 8) + 3}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 - (-05)) \times 8) - 3}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 - (-05))^8) \times 3}{(((6 + 1) \times 7)^4) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^{05}) - 8) \times 3}{6 \times (1 + (7 + (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((20 \times 5) - 8) \times 3}{(6 + 17) \times (4 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{((20 - 5) \times 8) - 3}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) + 4) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)) \times 3}{6 + (1 + (74 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (5 \times 8))) \times 3}{(61 \times 7) - 49}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (5 + 8))) \times 3}{(6 \times (17 + 4)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (-05)) \times (8 \times 3)}{6 \times (1 + (74 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (-05)) \times (8 - 3)}{6 + (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8)) + 3}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))^3}{6 \times ((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) + 3}{6 + (1 + (7 + (4 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 58)) + 3}{6 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))) + 3}{6 - ((1 - (7 \times 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 + 8))) - 3}{(6 \times (17 - 4)) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (05)) + (8^3)}{6 \times ((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (05)) + 83}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) - 4) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (-05)) + (8 \times 3)}{6 + (1 - (7 \times (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (-05)) + (8 + 3)}{6 - (1 + (7 + (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{-05+8}) \times 3}{6 \times (1 \times (7 - (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{05}) + (8 \times 3)}{6 \times (1 + ((7 - 4) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (5 - 8))) \times 3}{(6 - (17^4)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 - (5 - 8)) \times 3}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 5) - (8 \times 3)}{6 \times (1 + ((7 \times 4) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 5) - (8 + 3)}{6 + ((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 5) + (8 - 3)}{(6 + (1 + (7 \times 4))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 \times 5) - 83}{6 + (((1^7) + 4) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 + (5 + 8)) \times 3}{(6 - (1 - (7 \times 4))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 + (5 - 8)) \times 3}{(6 + (1 \times (7 + 4))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 + 58) \times 3}{6 \times ((17 - 4) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(20 - 5) \times (8 + 3)}{(6 - 1) \times ((7 + 4) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 \times 3))}{6 \times (1 + (7 - (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 + 3))}{(6 \times ((1^7) + 4)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 - 3))}{(6 \times ((1^7) + 4)) - 9}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 - ((0 \times 58) - 3)}{6 + ((1^{74}) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - ((5 \times 8) - 3))}{(6 \times (17 + 4)) - 9} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - ((5 + 8) \times 3))}{6 + ((17 - 4) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (5 \times (8 + 3)))}{6 + (174 - 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (5 \times (8 - 3)))}{(6 + (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (5 + (8 + 3)))}{6 \times ((1^{74}) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (5 + (8 - 3)))}{6 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 9)))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (5 + 83))}{6 \times (((1^7) + 4) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - (58 + 3))}{6 + (174 + 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 \times (5 - 83))}{6 \times (1^{749})} \\
 := \frac{2 - (0 - 583)}{6 + 1749} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 - (5 - 8))^3)}{6 \times (1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 9))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 \times 3))}{(6 - (1 - (7 + 4))) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 + 3))}{(6 \times 17) - (4 \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 - 3))}{((6 - 1) \times 7) + (4 - 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 5) + 83)}{6 \times (1 \times (74 + 9))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 58) + 3)}{6 + (1 \times (7 - (4 - 9)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 - (5 - (8 \times 3)))}{6 + ((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 - (5 - 83))}{((6 \times (1 + 7)) + 4) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) + 3))}{6 \times (1 - (7 - 49))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) - 3))}{6 \times (1 \times ((7 \times 4) + 9))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 \times (8 \times 3)))}{(6 + (1 \times 74)) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 \times 3)))}{(61 \times (7 - 4)) - 9} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 + 3)))}{6 - (1 - (7 \times (4 + 9)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 - 3)))}{6 \times ((1^{74}) + 9)} \\
 := \frac{2^{-05+8+3}}{(61 \times (7 - 4)) + 9} \\
 := \frac{2 + ((0 - (5 - 8))^3)}{(6 \times (17 - 4)) + 9} \\
 := \frac{2 + (0 - ((5 - 8) \times 3))}{6 + (1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 9))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (0 - (5 - (8 \times 3)))}{6 + (1 + (7 + 49))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (0 - (5 - (8 + 3)))}{6 - ((1 - (7 - 4)) \times 9)} \\
 := \frac{20 - (5 + (8 + 3))}{6 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 9)))} \\
 := \frac{20 - (5 - 83)}{6 \times ((1^7) \times 49)} \\
 := \frac{20 \times (5 + (8 - 3))}{6 \times (1 + ((7 + 4) \times 9))} \\
 := \frac{20 + (5 \times (8 + 3))}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) + 9} \\
 := \frac{20 + (5 \times 83)}{(6 \times (1 + (7 - 4))) + 9} \\
 := \frac{20 + (58 + 3)}{(6 + (17 + 4)) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{205 + (8 - 3)}{617 + (4 + 9)} \\
 := \frac{2058 + 3}{6174 + 9} \\
 := \frac{2058 - 3}{6174 - 9}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20587}{63491} := \frac{2^{05} + 87}{6 - 3 + 4 \times 91} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20618}{93574} := \frac{2 \times 06 + 1^8}{9 - 3 + 57 - 4} \\
 := \frac{2 + 06 + 18}{9 + 3 \times 5 \times 7 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20631}{74589} := \frac{2 + 06 + 31}{7 + 45 + 89} \\
 := \frac{(20 + 6) \times 3 \times 1}{(7 - 4) \times (5 + 89)} \\
 := \frac{(20 + 6) \times (3 + 1)}{7 + 45 \times 8 + 9} \\
 := \frac{20 \times 6 - 3 \times 1}{((7 + 4) \times 5 - 8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20654}{31879} := \frac{2 \times (065 + 4)}{3 \times 1 \times (8 + 7 \times 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20675}{98413} := \frac{(2 \times 06 - 7) \times 5}{(9 + 8) \times (4 + 1 \times 3)} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 06 + 7) \times 5}{9 \times 8 \times (4 + 1) - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20679}{41358} := \frac{(2 - (-06)) \times (7 \times 9)}{4 \times (1 + ((3^5) + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - (-06)) \times (7 + 9)}{4 + (1 + ((3^5) + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7)) + 9}{4 - (1 - (3 + (5 \times 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7)) - 9}{4 + (1 \times (3 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 6)) + (7 \times 9)}{(41 \times 3) - (5 - 8)}
 \end{array}$$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 67)) + 9}{4 + (1^3 + (5 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((6 + 7) \times 9))}{4 - (1 - ((3^5) - 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (67 + 9))}{(4 - (1 - 35)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 + 7))) + 9}{(4 \times (1 \times 3)) + 58}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 9)))}{4 + (1 \times (3 + (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (67 - 9))}{4 \times ((1^3) \times 58)}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 + 7))) - 9}{41 - ((3 \times 5) - 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 9)))}{4 - (1 + (3 \times (5 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2^{0 \times 67 + 9}}{((41 \times 3) + 5) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 - 7))) + 9}{4 + (1 - (3 \times (5 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (6 + 79))}{(4 - (1^3)) \times 58}$	$:= \frac{2^{06-7+9}}{(4 \times (1 - (3 - 5))) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (06)) + (7 + 9)}{(4 \times (1 - (3 - 5))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (67 + 9))}{4 \times (1 \times (3 \times (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^9)}{4 - (1^3 + (5 - 8))}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (06)) + 79}{((41 - 3) \times 5) - 8}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (67 - 9))}{(4 - (1^3)) \times (5 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{4 \times (1 \times (3 - (5 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (-06)) + (7 \times 9)}{41 + (3 + 58)}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (6 - 79))}{4 \times 1^{358}}$	$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{4 \times (1 + (3 - (5 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (-06)) + (7 + 9)}{(4 - (1 - (3 - 5))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - 679)}{4 + 1358}$	$:= \frac{20 - ((6 - 7) \times 9)}{4 - (1 + (3 - 58))}$
$:= \frac{(2^{06}) - (7 + 9)}{4 \times ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 6) + (7 \times 9))}{(4 \times (13 \times 5)) - 8}$	$:= \frac{20 - (6 - (7 + 9))}{4 + (1 - (3 - 58))}$
$:= \frac{(2^{06}) + (7 \times 9)}{4 - (1 - ((3^5) + 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 6) + (7 + 9))}{4 - (1 - (3 + 58))}$	$:= \frac{20 \times (6 - (7 - 9))}{(4 + (1 + 35)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{(2^{06}) + (7 + 9)}{4 \times (1 + (3 \times (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 67) + 9)}{4 \times ((1^{35}) + 8)}$	$:= \frac{20 + (6 + (7 \times 9))}{4 + (1 \times (3 \times 58))}$
$:= \frac{(2^{06}) + (7 - 9)}{4 + (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (6 - (7 \times 9)))}{4 \times ((13 \times 5) - 8)}$	$:= \frac{20 + (6 + (7 + 9))}{4 - ((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 8))}$
$:= \frac{(20 \times 6) - (7 + 9)}{4 \times ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{4 \times (1 - (3 \times (5 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (67 + 9)}{4 \times ((1^3 + 5) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{(20 \times 6) - (7 - 9)}{4 \times (1 \times (3 + 58))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{4 + (1 + (3 + (5 \times 8)))}$	$:= \frac{206 - 7 + 9}{413 - 5 + 8}$
$:= \frac{(20 \times 6) + (7 - 9)}{4 \times (1^3 + 58)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (6 - 79))}{4 + ((1 + 35) \times 8)}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(20 + 6) \times (7 + 9)}{(4 \times (1 \times 3)) \times (5 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 9))}{(4 \times (1 \times 35)) - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20683}{49751} := \frac{20 + 6 + 8 + 3}{4 + 9 + 75 + 1}$
$:= \frac{(20 + 67) \times 9}{((4 - 1)^3) \times 58}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 9)))}{4 + (1 + (35 - 8))}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(20 - 6) \times (7 + 9)}{(41 + (3 \times 5)) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 \times 9)))}{4 - ((1 - 35) \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20691}{45738} := \frac{2 + 06 \times 9 + 1}{45 + 73 + 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - ((0 - (6 - 7))^9)}{4 + (1^3 + (5 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 9)))}{(4 - (1 - (3 + 5))) \times 8}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 67) - 9)}{4 - (((1 - 3) \times 5) - 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 9)))}{(4 + (1 \times (3 - 5))) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{41895} := \frac{2^{07} \times 3 \times 6}{(41 + 8) \times 95}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{48195} &:= \frac{2^{0 \times 7 + 3 + 6}}{(4 + 81) \times (9 + 5)} &:= \frac{(2^{0 \times 7 + 6}) + 9}{((41 + 5) \times 3) + 8} &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 76) + 9)}{4 - (1 + (5 - 38))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{51984} &:= \frac{(20 + 7 - 3) \times 6}{5 \times (1 + 9 \times 8) - 4} &:= \frac{(2^{07}) - (6 \times 9)}{4 + ((15 + 3) \times 8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 - (6 \times 9)))}{(4 \times (15 \times 3)) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{59184} &:= \frac{(20 + 7 - 3) \times 6}{5 \times (91 - 8) - 4} &:= \frac{(2^{07}) + (6 \times 9)}{4 + (15 \times (3 \times 8))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))}{(4 \times 15) + (3 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{91584} &:= \frac{2 + 07 - 3 + 6}{9 + 1 \times 5 \times 8 + 4} &:= \frac{(2 + (-07)) \times (6 - 9)}{4 + (1 - (5 \times (3 - 8)))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 - 69))}{4 \times (1 + (53 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (07 - 3) \times 6}{(9 \times 1 \times 5 + 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(20 - (7 - 6)) \times 9}{(4 + (1 \times 5)) \times 38} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) + 9))}{(4 \times (1 \times 53)) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 - 7 - 3) \times 6}{9 + (1 - 5 + 8)^4} &:= \frac{(20 \times 7) - (6 \times 9)}{4 \times (1 \times (5 + 38))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) - 9))}{4 + ((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{91854} &:= \frac{2 + 07 \times 3 \times 6}{9 \times (1 + 8 + 54)} &:= \frac{(20 + 76) \times 9}{4 \times ((1 + 53) \times 8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 + 6) \times 9))}{4 \times (1 \times ((5^3) - 8))} \\
 & &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 76) - 9)}{4 - (1 + (5 - (3 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 - (6 - 9)))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20769}{41538} &:= \frac{((2 - (-07)) \times 6) - 9}{(41 \times (5 - 3)) + 8} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((7 + 6) \times 9))}{((4 - 1)^5) + (3 - 8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 + 9)))}{4 - ((1 - 53) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (07)) + 6) \times 9}{(4 - 1) \times (5 \times (3 \times 8))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 9)))}{4 + (1 - (5 - (3 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 \times 9)))}{4 \times (1 \times (53 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (07)) - 6) \times 9}{(4 - (1 - (5 \times 3))) \times 8} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 \times (6 \times 9)))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 \times 38))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 + 9)))}{(4 - (1 - (5 + 3))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 9}{4 + ((1^5) \times 38)} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + (6 + 9)))}{4 + (1 + (5 + 38))} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(4 - (1 \times (5 - 3))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - 6))) + 9}{4 + (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8)))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + (6 - 9)))}{4 + ((1^{53}) \times 8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + 69))}{(4 - (1 - 5)) \times 38} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 76)) + 9}{41 - ((5 \times 3) + 8)} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + 69))}{4 \times (15 + (3 \times 8))} &:= \frac{2^{0 \times 76 + 9}}{(4 - (1 - (5^3))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 6))) + 9}{4 + ((1 + 5) \times (3 + 8))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (76 + 9))}{41 + ((5^3) + 8)} &:= \frac{2^{-07 + 6 + 9}}{(4 \times (1 + (5^3))) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 6))) - 9}{4 + (1 + (5 + (3 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (76 - 9))}{4 + (1 + ((5^3) + 8))} &:= \frac{2^{07 + 6 - 9}}{4 - (1 - (5 + (3 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (07)) + (6 \times 9)}{4 \times (1 - (5 - 38))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (7 - 69))}{4 \times (1 - (5 + (3 - 8)))} &:= \frac{2 + ((0 \times 7) - (6 - 9))}{4 - (1 \times (5 - (3 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (07)) + (6 + 9)}{4 - (1 - (5 \times (3 + 8)))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - 769)}{4 + 1538} &:= \frac{2 + (0 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{((4 - (1 + 5)) \times 3) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (-07)) + (6 \times 9)}{4 \times (1 - (5 - (3 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 9))}{((4 - (1^5))^3) \times 8} &:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - (6 \times 9)))}{(4 \times 15) + 38} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (-07)) + 69}{(4 + (1 + 5)) \times (3 + 8)} &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 + 9))}{4 + (1 + (5 \times (3 + 8)))} &:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - (6 + 9)))}{4 + (1 \times (5 + (3 + 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))}{4 - (1 - (5 + 38))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - 69))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - 3))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{20 - ((7 - 6)^9)}{4 + (1 - (5 - 38))} \\ &:= \frac{20 - (7 - (6 + 9))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 - 3))) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{20 \times (7 + (6 - 9))}{(4 + (1 + (5 \times 3))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{20 + (7 + 69)}{(4 - (1 - 5)) \times (3 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{20 + (76 + 9)}{(41 \times 5) - (3 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{207 - (6 + 9)}{4 \times ((15 - 3) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2076 - 9}{4 \times (1 + 5) + 38} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{20793}{41586}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((2 \times (07)) + 9) \times 3}{(4 - 1) \times ((5 \times 8) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (07)) - 9)^3}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{((20 + 7) \times 9) - 3}{(4 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)) \times 3}{(4 + (15 - 8)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 3}{(4 + 1) \times ((5 + 8) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 3}{(4 + (1 + (5 + 8))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + 9)))^3}{((4 - 1)^5) \times (8 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (-07)) \times (9 + 3)}{4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - 79)) \times 3}{(4 \times (15 \times 8)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 7)) + 93}{(4 \times ((1 + 5) \times 8)) - 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 \times 9))) + 3}{(4 - (1 - (5 \times 8))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 9)))^3}{4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) + 3}{(4 + (1^5)) \times (8 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) - 3}{4 + (1 + (5 + (8 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (07)) + (9 \times 3)}{4 + (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (07)) + (9 - 3)}{4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (07)) + 93}{4 + (15 \times (8 + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (-07)) + (9 \times 3)}{(4 \times ((1^5) \times 8)) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (-07)) + 93}{(4 \times (1 + (5 \times 8))) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{0 \times 7 + 9})^3}{(4 \times (1 \times 5)) \times (8^6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{07}) - (9 - 3)}{4 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{07}) \times (9 - 3)}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{07}) + (9 + 3)}{4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(20 - (7 - 9)) \times 3}{41 + (5 + 86)} \\ &:= \frac{(20 \times 7) - (9 \times 3)}{(4 \times (1 \times 58)) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(20 \times 7) - (9 + 3)}{4 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(20 \times 7) + (9 - 3)}{4 + ((1 + 5) \times (8 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(20 \times 7) - 93}{4 - (1 - (5 + 86))} \\ &:= \frac{(20 + 7) \times (9^3)}{((4 - (1^5))^8) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(20 + 7) \times (9 - 3)}{(41 + (5 + 8)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(20 + 79) \times 3}{(41 + 58) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(20 - 7) \times (9 + 3)}{4 \times (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(207 + 9) \times 3}{(41 - 5)^{8-6}} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 7) - (9 + 3))}{4 - (1 - (5^{8-6}))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 79) - 3)}{4 - (1 - (5 + (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((7 + 9) \times 3))}{4 \times (1 \times (5^{8-6}))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 - (9 - 3)))}{4 - (1 - (5 - (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 \times (9 - 3)))}{4 + ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + (9 \times 3)))}{(4 + ((1^5) \times 8)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 3)))}{(4 - (1 \times (5 - 8))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 3)))}{4 + (1 + (5^{8-6}))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (79 - 3))}{4 + (158 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (7 - 93))}{4 \times (1^{586})} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - 793)}{4 + 1586} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 - (7 - 9))^3)}{4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (9 + 3))}{4 + (1 - (5 - (8 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 7) + 93)}{(4 + (1 \times 58)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 79) + 3)}{4 \times (1 \times (5 - (8 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 3))}{4 + (1 + (5 + (8 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 - (9 \times 3)))}{4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 + 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 3)))}{(4 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{20 - (7 - (9 + 3))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 + 8))) - 6}$	$:= \frac{(20 \times 8) - (1^7)}{(3 - (4 - (6 \times 9))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (7 - 93))}{4 \times ((1^5) \times 86)}$	$:= \frac{20 - (7 - (9 - 3))}{4 + (1 \times ((5 \times 8) - 6))}$	$:= \frac{(20 + (8 - 1)) \times 7}{3 \times (4 + (6 + 95))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) + 3))}{(4 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{20 - (7 - 93)}{4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(20 - 8) \times 17}{(3 - (4 - 69)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) - 3))}{(4 + (1^5)) \times (8 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{20 \times (7 + (9 - 3))}{4 + ((1 + 5) \times 86)}$	$:= \frac{(208 - 1) \times 7}{(3 + 4) \times (69 \times 5)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 3))}{4 \times ((1^5) \times (8 \times 6))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (7 \times (9 + 3))}{4 \times (1 \times (58 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((8 - 1) \times 7))}{34 + (6 + (9 \times 5))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((7 + 9)^3))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (7 + (9 + 3))}{(4 + ((1^5) + 8)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 - (1 \times 7)))}{3 + (4 - (6 - (9 - 5)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 + 3)))}{4 \times ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{2079 + 3}{4158 + 6}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 - (1^7)))}{3 + (4 - (6 - (9 + 5)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 - 3)))}{4 + (158 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{207 - 93}{(41 + (5 - 8)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 \times (1 + 7)))}{(3 + (4 + (6 + 9))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7^{9-3}))}{4 \times ((15 - 8)^6)}$	$:= \frac{2079 - 3}{4158 - 6}$	$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 + 17))}{3 + (46 - (9 - 5))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 3)))}{4 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 8) - 6))}$		$:= \frac{2 - (0 - (81 + 7))}{3 \times (46 + (9 - 5))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 + 3)))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 + 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{34695} := \frac{((2 \times (08)) - 1) \times 7}{(3 \times (4 \times (6 + 9))) - 5}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 8) - (1 - 7))}{(3 + (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 3)))}{4 \times (15 - (8 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 - 1))) \times 7}{3 \times ((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (8 \times (1 - 7)))}{(3 \times (46 + 9)) - 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (7 + 93))}{(4 \times (1 \times 5))^{8-6}}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 8)) - (1 - 7)}{(3 - (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (8 - 17))}{3 \times ((4 \times 6) - (9 + 5))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (79 + 3))}{4 \times (1 - (5 - 86))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 - 1))) + 7}{3 - (4 \times (6 - (9 + 5)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (8 + (1 \times 7)))}{3 - (4 - (6 + (9 \times 5)))}$
$:= \frac{2^{0 \times 79 + 3}}{4 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (08)) + (1 + 7)}{((3 - (4 - 6)) \times 9) - 5}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (81 \times 7))}{(3 + 4) \times (6 \times (9 \times 5))}$
$:= \frac{2^{-07 + 9 + 3}}{4 \times (1 \times (5 - (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(2^{08-1}) + 7}{(3 - (4 - 6)) \times (9 \times 5)}$	$:= \frac{20 \times (8 + (1 \times 7))}{((3^4) \times 6) + (9 + 5)}$
$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 3)))}{4 \times (1 + (5 \times (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(2^{08}) + (1 + 7)}{(34 + (6 \times 9)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{20 \times (8 + (1^7))}{((3^4) - 6) \times (9 - 5)}$
$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 3)))}{4 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (-08)) \times (1 - 7)}{3 \times ((4 \times 6) - (9 - 5))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (8 \times (1 + 7))}{(3^4) + ((6 \times 9) + 5)}$
$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - (9 - 3)))}{4 + (1 - (5 - (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(20 \times (8 \times 1)) - 7}{3 \times (((4 + 6) \times 9) - 5)}$	$:= \frac{20 + (8 + 17)}{(3 - (4 \times (6 - 9))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 + (0 - (7 - 93))}{4 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(20 \times (8 - 1)) + 7}{(34 + (6 + 9)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{20 + (81 + 7)}{3 \times (46 + (9 + 5))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{20+817}{(3+(4 \times 69)) \times 5} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((8-3) \times 5))}{(((9-1) \times 6) + 7) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (8 - (5 \times 3)))}{(7 \times (1 - (4 - 9))) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{208 + (1 + 7)}{346 + (9 + 5)} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (8 - (3 - 5)))}{9 - (1 - (6 + 74))} &:= \frac{20 + (8 \times (5 \times 3))}{(7 + 1) \times (4 \times (9 + 6))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{35964} &:= \frac{2^{08} + 1^7}{(3 \times 5 + 96) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (8 \times 35))}{(9 \times (1 + 6)) + (7^4)} &:= \frac{208 + (5 - 3)}{(71 + 49) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{65934} &:= \frac{2^{08} + 1^7}{6 \times 5 \times 9 \times 3 + 4} &:= \frac{20 \times (8 + (3 - 5))}{(9 - 1) \times (6 \times (7 + 4))} & \\
 & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20835}{91674} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 - 3))) \times 5}{(9 - (1 - 6)) \times (7 + 4)} & \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (-08)) \times (3 \times 5)}{(9 + 1) \times (6 \times (7 + 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20851}{69743} := \frac{2 - 0 + 85 \times 1}{69 + 74 \times 3} & \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 83)) + 5}{(9 \times (1 - (6 - 7))) + 4} & \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 - 3))) + 5}{((9 + (1^6)) \times 7) - 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20853}{71496} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 8) - 5)) \times 3}{7 + (1 + (4^{9-6}))} & \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{0 \times 8 + 3}) \times 5}{9 - (1 - (6 \times (7 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 \times 5))) \times 3}{(7 + 1^4) \times (9 \times 6)} & \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{08-3}) \times 5}{(9 + 167) \times 4} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 8) + 5)) - 3}{7 + (14 + (9 - 6))} & \\
 &:= \frac{(20 \times (8 + 3)) + 5}{916 + 74} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 \times 5))) - 3}{(7 + (1 + (4 \times 9))) \times 6} & \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (8 + 3)) \times 5}{9 - (1 - 674)} &:= \frac{(2^{0 \times 8 + 5}) + 3}{(7 + (1 \times (4 + 9))) \times 6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{35784} := \frac{20 \times (9 - 1) + 6}{3 \times (5 + 7) \times 8 - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 + (3 \times 5)))}{(9 + (1^6)) \times (7 + 4)} &:= \frac{(20 \times 8) + (5 \times 3)}{(7 - 1) \times (4 + 96)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{53784} := \frac{2 \times (0 - (9 - 16))}{5 + (3 + (7 \times (8 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (83 + 5))}{9 \times (16 + (7 \times 4))} &:= \frac{(20 \times 8) + (5 + 3)}{(7 - (1^4)) \times 96} &:= \frac{2 \times ((09 - (1 - 6)))}{(5 + ((3 \times 7) - 8)) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (83 - 5))}{9 + ((1 + 6)^{7-4})} &:= \frac{(20 + 8) \times (5 + 3)}{(7 + 1^4) \times 96} &:= \frac{(2 + (-09)) \times (1 - 6)}{5 + (3 + (78 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 8) + (3 \times 5))}{((9 - (1 + 6))^7) + 4} &:= \frac{(20 + 8) \times (5 - 3)}{(7 - (1 + 4)) \times 96} &:= \frac{2 + ((0 \times 9) - (1 - 6))}{(5 \times (3 + 7)) - (8 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 8) + 35)}{(9 + (1 + 67)) \times 4} &:= \frac{(20 + 8)^{5-3}}{7 \times (1 \times (4 \times 96))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (9 \times (1 \times 6)))}{53 + (7 + 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 83) + 5)}{9 + (1 + (6 + (7 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (8 + 53))}{(7 - (1^4))^{9-6}} &:= \frac{(20 \times 9) + 16}{(5 + 37) \times (8 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((8 + 3) \times 5))}{(9 + (16 \times 7)) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (85 - 3))}{(7 - (1 \times 4)) \times 96} &:= \frac{20 \times (9 - (1 - 6))}{(53 + 7) \times (8 + 4)} \\
 & & &:= \frac{(20 \times (9 - 1)) - 6}{(5 \times ((3 + 7) \times 8)) - 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{73584} := \frac{20 \times (9 - 1) + 6}{(7 + 3) \times 58 + 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{78435} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (9 - 1))) \times 6}{(7 + 8)^{4+3-5}}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times 1))) + 6}{78 + (4 + (3 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{(20 + 9) \times 16}{7 + (((8 + 4)^3) + 5)}$ $:= \frac{(209 - 1) \times 6}{78 \times (4 \times (3 \times 5))}$ $:= \frac{2 + 09 - 1 - 6}{7 + 8 \times (4 - 3)^5}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - (9 \times (1 \times 6)))}{(7 - (8 - 43)) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - (9 + (1^6)))}{(7 - (8 - 4)) \times (3 \times 5)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((9 + 1) \times 6))}{7 + (8 + 435)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 - (1^6)))}{(7 \times 8) - (4 - (3 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 - (1 - 6)))}{7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) - 5))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 \times (1 \times 6)))}{((7 \times (8 + 4)) - 3) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 + (1^6)))}{7 + (8 + (4 \times (3 \times 5)))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 + (1 - 6)))}{7 - (8 + (4 - 35))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (91 \times 6))}{7 + ((8^4) - (3 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{2^{0 \times 91 + 6}}{(7 \times ((8 \times 4) + 3)) - 5}$ $:= \frac{2^{-09 + 16}}{(7 + 8) \times (4 \times (3 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{20 \times (9 - (1^6))}{((7 \times 8) + (4^3)) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{20 \times (9 - (1 - 6))}{78 + (4 \times (3^5))}$ $:= \frac{20 + ((9 - 1) \times 6)}{7 - (8 \times (4 - 35))}$	$:= \frac{20 + (9 + (1 + 6))}{(7 + (8 + (4 \times 3))) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{209 - (1^6)}{((7 \times 8) - 4) \times (3 \times 5)}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{20943}{75816} := \frac{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3}{(7 + 5) \times (8 + 1) \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{20943}{85176} := \frac{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3}{8 \times (5 \times 17 + 6)}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{20958}{63714} := \frac{2^{09} - 5 - 8}{6^3 \times 7 + 1 + 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{20958}{64371} := \frac{2 + 09 - 5 + 8}{6 + 43 - 7 + 1}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (-09 + 58)}{6 \times (43 + 7) + 1}$ $:= \frac{20 \times 9 + 58}{6 - 4 + 3^{7-1}}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{20961}{87543} := \frac{2 + 09 + 6 \times 1}{8 + 75 - 4 \times 3}$ $:= \frac{209 - 6 + 1}{(8 \times 7 \times 5 + 4) \times 3}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{20967}{83145} := \frac{2 \times (-09 + 67)}{(8 \times 3 - 1) \times 4 \times 5}$ $:= \frac{20 - 9 \times (6 - 7)}{(8 + 3 \times (1 + 4)) \times 5}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{20986}{73451} := \frac{((2 - (-09)) \times 8) - 6}{(73 \times 4) - (5 \times 1)}$ $:= \frac{((2 \times (09)) - 8) \times 6}{7 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 + 1)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (9 - 8))) \times 6}{73 - (4 + (5 + 1))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (9 - 8))) + 6}{7 \times (3 + (4 - (5 \times 1)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 9)) + (8 \times 6)}{7 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 - 1)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 98)) + 6}{7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 - 1)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times 8))) + 6}{7 \times ((3^4) - (5 + 1))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (09)) - (8 - 6)}{7 + (3 + (45 + 1))}$ $:= \frac{(2^{0 \times 9 + 8}) \times 6}{7 \times (3 \times (4^{5-1}))}$ $:= \frac{(2^{09}) \times (8 \times 6)}{7 \times (3 \times (4^{5+1}))}$ $:= \frac{(20 + (9 - 8)) \times 6}{7 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 1))}$ $:= \frac{(20 + 9) \times (8 - 6)}{7 \times (34 - (5 \times 1))}$ $:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 9) - 86)}{(73 + 4) \times (5 - 1)}$ $:= \frac{2 - ((0 \times 98) - 6)}{7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 \times 1)))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((9 \times 8) + 6))}{7 \times (34 + (5 + 1))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((9 \times 8) - 6))}{7 \times (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 1)}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - ((9 + 8) \times 6))}{7 + ((3 + 4) \times 51)}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - (9 \times (8 - 6)))}{7 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 1))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - (98 - 6))}{7 \times (3 + (45 - 1))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 \times (9 - 86))}{7 - (3 \times (4 - (5 - 1)))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (0 - 986)}{7 + 3451}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 9) + (8 \times 6))}{7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - 1)))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 86)}{7 \times ((3^4) + (5 \times 1))}$
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$$:= \frac{2 \times ((0 \times 98) + 6)}{7 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (9 - (8 \times 6)))}{7 \times (34 + (5 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (9 - (8 + 6)))}{7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 + 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (9 - 86))}{7 \times ((3^4) - (5 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((9 \times 8) - 6))}{(73 + 4) \times (5 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + ((9 + 8) \times 6))}{(7 + (3 + 4)) \times 51}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 - (8 - 6)))}{7^{3+4-5 \times 1}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 \times (8 - 6)))}{7 \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 \times 6)))}{7 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 + 6)))}{7 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 - 6)))}{7 \times (3 + (4 + (5 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (0 + (98 + 6))}{734 - (5 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{-09+8+6}}{7 \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 \times ((9 - 8) \times 6)}{7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + ((9 \times 8) + 6)}{7^{3-4+5-1}}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + ((9 + 8) \times 6)}{7 \times ((3 \times (4 \times 5)) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + ((9 - 8) \times 6)}{7 \times (3 + (4 + (5 + 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + (9 \times (8 - 6))}{7 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{209 \times (8 + 6)}{((7 + 3) \times (4^5)) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20987}{64315} := \frac{20 \times 9 - 8 \times 7}{6 \times 4^3 + 1 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{20 + 9 \times (8 + 7)}{(64 + 31) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21036}{57849} := \frac{(2 - (1 + (-03))) \times 6}{5 + ((7 \times 8) - (4 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 103) + 6}{578 - (4 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (10 \times 3)) \times 6}{(5 + 7) \times (8 + (4 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 10) \times (3 + 6)}{(5 + (7 \times (8 - 4))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(21 - (-03)) \times 6}{(5 + (7 + (8 \times 4))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (1 - (0 - (3 - 6)))}{5 - (7 - (8 - (4 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (10 \times (3 - 6))}{5 + (78 - (4 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (-03)) \times 6)}{5 + (78 + 49)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((10 + 3) \times 6)}{(5 \times (7 \times (8 + 4))) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((10 - 3) \times 6)}{(5 \times (7 \times 8)) - 49}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 - (3 + 6)))}{5 - (7 - (8 + 49))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (0 + (3 \times 6)))}{(((5 \times 7) - 8) \times 4) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (0 - (3 - 6)))}{(5 \times 7) - (8 - (4 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (10 \times (3 + 6))}{5 \times ((7 + (8 - 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (10 + 36)}{((5 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1^{03} \times 6}}{5 + ((7 + (8 + 4)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (0 - (3 - 6)))}{(5 \times (7 - 8)) + 49}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((10 + 3) \times 6)}{5 + ((7 \times (8 \times 4)) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 - (0 - (3 + 6)))}{5 + (7 + (8 + (4 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{210 + 3 \times 6}{578 + 49}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21045}{98637} := \frac{210 + 4 \times 5}{98 \times (6 \times 3 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21054}{73689} := \frac{((2 \times 10) + 5) \times 4}{(7^3) + (6 - (8 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 \times (-05))) \times 4}{7 \times (3 - (6 - (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 + (-05))) \times 4}{73 - (6 - (8 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 + (-05)))^4}{7 \times ((3 + 6) \times (8 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - (-05))) + 4}{7 \times (3 + (6 + (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - (-05))) - 4}{7 + (3 \times (6 - (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (05))) + 4}{7 + (3 + ((6 \times 8) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (10 \times 5)) - 4}{(7^3) - (6 - (8 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (10 + 5)) + 4}{((7 + (3 + 6)) \times 8) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 10) + 54}{7 \times (36 - (8 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 105) + 4}{7 \times ((3 \times 6) + 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - (-05))) + 4}{7 + (3 \times (68 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 - (-05))) \times 4}{7 + (3 + (6 \times (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 - 0)) \times 54}{7 \times (3 + (6 + (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (1 \times (0 - (5 \times 4)))}{((7 + 3) \times 6) + (8 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (-05)) \times 4)}{73 + (6 + 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (-05))^4)}{7 \times (3 \times (6 \times (8 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((10 + 5) \times 4)}{7 \times (3 + ((6 \times 8) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 \times 4)))}{7 \times (3 \times (6 - (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{7 \times (3 + (6 - (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 - 54))}{7 + (3 \times ((6 + 8) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (0 + (5 + 4)))}{7 \times (3 - (6 \times (8 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (10 \times (5 + 4))}{7 \times ((3 \times 6) + (8 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (10^{5+4})}{7 \times (((3 \times 6) - 8)^9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (10 + (5 + 4))}{7 \times (36 - (8 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 - 4)))}{73 - (68 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (0 \times 54))}{7^{3+6-8} 9}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((1 - (-05)) \times 4)}{73 - ((6 - 8) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((1^{05}) \times 4)}{7 + (3 - (6 - (8 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((10 + 5) \times 4)}{(7^3) - ((6 + 8) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{7 + (36 + (8 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (10 + 54)}{7 \times ((3 \times (6 + 8)) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1054}{7 + 3689}$$

$$:= \frac{21 - (0 - (5 + 4))}{7 + (3 + (6 + 89))}$$

$$:= \frac{21 \times ((0 \times 5) + 4)}{7 \times (3 + ((6 \times 8) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{210 \times (5 - 4)}{7 \times (3 + (6 \times (8 + 9)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21054}{93786} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 05 \times 4}{(9 - 3 + 7) \times 8 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 10 + 54}{(9 - 3) \times 7^{8-6}}$$

$$:= \frac{210 + 54}{(9 + 3) \times 7 \times (8 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + 05)^4}{(9^3 - 7) \times 8 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21056}{97384} := \frac{2 + 1^{05} \times 6}{9 - 7 + 3 + 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 05 \times 6}{(9 + 7 + 3) \times 8 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 1) \times 056}{(97 \times 3 - 8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1^{05} \times 6}}{(9 + 73 - 8) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 05) \times 6}{9 + (73 + 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21063}{54978} := \frac{2 \times 10 + 6^3}{5^4 + 9 \times (7 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21076}{43589} := \frac{2 + 10 + 76}{4 - (3 - 5) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 07 \times 6}{4 + 3 - 5 + 89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21087}{45369} := \frac{2 \times (10 + 8 \times 7)}{4 \times (5 - 3 + 69)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21356}{79804} := \frac{2 - 13 + 5 \times 6}{79 - 8 + 0 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 35 + 6}{(79 - 8) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21358}{79640} := \frac{2 - 1 + 3^5 - 8}{(7 + 9 + 6) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21360}{85974} := \frac{2 \times 1^3 \times 60}{8 \times 59 + 7 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21360}{94785} := \frac{2 \times (1 + 3) \times 6 + 0}{9 + 4 \times (7 \times 8 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 1 + 3 + 60}{9 + (47 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1+3} \times 6 + 0}{9 \times 47 + 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21368}{50749} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (3 - 6))) + 8}{50 - (7 - (4 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (3 - (6 + 8)))}{((5 - (-07)) \times 4) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 \times (3 - 6))) \times 8}{5 \times (((07 \times 4) - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (36 - 8))}{50 + (74 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 - (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{(5 \times (074)) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{(50 \times 7) + 49}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + ((1 + 3) \times 6)) \times 8}{507 - (4 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + 36)) \times 8}{(50 + 7) \times (4 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(21 - 3) \times (6 \times 8)}{(50 + 7) \times (4 \times 9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21375}{64980} &:= \frac{2 \times 1^3 \times 75}{6 \times (4 + 9 \times 8) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 - 3 + 7) \times 5}{(6 + 4 + 9) \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 3 \times 75}{6^4 + 9 \times 8 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21380}{45967} &:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 38 + 0}{4 + 5 \times (9 + 6) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 1 - 3 + 80}{4 - (5 - 9) \times 6 \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 138 + 0}{(4 + 5 \times 9 - 6) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 3 \times 80}{4^5 + 9 + 6 - 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21384}{70956} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 38 \times 4}{7 - 0 + 9 \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21385}{40796} := \frac{(2 + 1 \times 3 + 8) \times 5}{4 \times 07 + 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21386}{90457} := \frac{(2 + 1)^3 \times 8 + 6}{904 + 5 \times 7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21390}{74865} &:= \frac{(2 - (1 - 3)) \times (9 - 0)}{7 \times (48 - (6 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + 3)) + 90}{7^4 \times (8 - 6) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - 3)) + 90}{7 \times ((4 \times 8) + 6 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + 3)) \times (9 - 0)}{74 + (86 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + 3)) + 90}{7 + (4 \times (86 + 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 - ((1^3) - (9 - 0))}{7 + (4 \times (8 - (6 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (1 - (3 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (1 - (3 + 90))}{7 \times (4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (1 \times (3 - (9 - 0)))}{7 + ((4^8 - 6) + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times ((1^3) \times 90)}{7 \times ((4 + (8 + 6)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1^3 + (9 - 0))}{7 \times ((4 - (8 - 6)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + 3) \times (9 - 0))}{7 \times (4 \times (8 + 6 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + 3) \times 90)}{7 \times ((4 + 8) \times (6 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + 3)^9 + 0)}{7 \times (4^{8+6-5})}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (3 - (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (4 - (8 - (6 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (3 \times 90))}{7 \times ((48 + 6) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (3 + (9 - 0)))}{7 + (4 + (8 + 65))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (39 - 0))}{(7 - 4) \times (86 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (3 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (4 \times (8 - (6 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (3 + (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (4 + (8 + 6 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (39 - 0))}{7 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1^{39}+0}}{7^{4+8-6-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (13 - (9 - 0))}{7 - (4 - ((8 \times 6) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1^3 + (9 - 0))}{74 - ((8 - 6)^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 - (3 - 90))}{(7 + (4 \times (8 + 6))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (3 + 90))}{7 \times (48 \times (6 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (39 - 0))}{7 \times ((4^8 - 6) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (13 - (9 - 0))}{7 + (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1390}{7 + 4865}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + (3 + 90)}{7 \times (4 + ((8 \times 6) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + (39 - 0)}{7 \times ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21408}{36795} := \frac{2^{1-4+08}}{(3 + 6 - 7 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 4 \times 08}{36 + 79 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1^4 \times 08}{(3 + 6 + 79) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (40 + 8)}{3 + 67 + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1 \times 4} \times 08}{(3 \times 6 + 7) \times 9 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 140 + 8}{(3 + 6 \times (7 + 9)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21408}{76935} := \frac{2^{1-4+08}}{7 - 6 \times 9 \times (3 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (40 + 8)}{(7 \times 6 + 9 \times 3) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21450}{78936} := \frac{(2 - 1 + 4) \times 5 + 0}{7 \times (8 + 9 - 3) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1^4) \times 50}{(7 - 8 + 93) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 1) \times 4 \times 50}{7 - (8 - 9) \times 3^6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21456}{93870} &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (4 - 5)) \times 6)}{(9 \times 3) + (8 + 70)} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1 \times (4 - 5 + 6)}}{(9 + (3 + 8)) \times (7 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))}{((9 \times 3) + 8) \times (7 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - 1) \times (4 \times 56)}{(9 - (3 - 8)) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+4-5+6}}{(9 + (3 - 8)) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + 4) \times 56)}{((9 \times 3) + 8) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1^4 + 5)^6)}{(9^3) \times (8 \times 70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21465}{97308} := \frac{(2 - 1 - 4 + 6) \times 5}{(9 - 7) \times 30 + 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21468}{59037} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (4 - (6 - 8)))}{5 - (9 + (0 - 37))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (4 + (6 + 8)))}{(5 \times (9 - 0)) + (3 + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (4 + 6))) + 8}{(5 + (9 + (-03))) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (4 + (6 + 8)))}{5 + (90 - (3 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (4 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 + (90 + 37)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times ((4 + 6) \times 8))}{(5 \times 90) - (3 + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (4 \times 6))) \times 8}{590 - (3 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{214 + (6 + 8)}{590 + 37} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (4 - (6 - 8)))}{59 + (0 - 37)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (1 + (4 - 6))) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 - 0)) + (3 \times 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (146 + 8)}{(5 \times 90) - (3 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21470}{63958} := \frac{21 + 4 + 70}{6 + 3 \times 95 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21473}{68950} := \frac{(2 + 14) \times 7 - 3}{(6 - 8 + 9) \times 50}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21480}{73569} &:= \frac{(2 - 1 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{73 - 5 + 69} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - 1^4) \times 80}{7 - 3 + 5 \times 6 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21483}{56079} := \frac{2 \times (1 - 4) + 83}{5 \times 6 \times 07 - 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21483}{97650} &:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 4 + 8 - 3}{(9 + 7 - 6) \times 5 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2 - 1 + 4 + 83}{(9 - 7 + 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 1 + 4 \times 8 \times 3}{9 \times (7 - 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 4) \times (8 + 3)}{(9 + 7 - 6) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (14 + 8) \times 3}{(9 - 7) \times 6 \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21504}{38976} &:= \frac{2^{1+5} + 0 \times 4}{3 + (8 + 9) \times 7 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 50 - 4}{3 \times (8^9 - 7 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1^5 \times 04}}{38 - 9 \times (7 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 1 \times 50) \times 4}{(38 - 9) \times (7 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21504}{89376} &:= \frac{2^{1+5} + 0 \times 4}{8 \times (9 \times 3 + 7) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+5} \times 04}{(8 + 9 - 3) \times 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21507}{68943} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 50 + 7}{68 \times (9 - 4) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21509}{78364} := \frac{21 + 50 \times 9}{78 \times (3 \times 6 + 4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21536}{87490} &:= \frac{2 + 1 + 5 \times (3 + 6)}{(8 + 7) \times (4 + 9) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (5 - 3)^6}{8 \times (74 - 9) + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 - 5 + 36)}{8 + 7 \times 4 \times 9 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+5} \times 3 \times 6}{(8 \times 7 - 4) \times 90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21546}{79380} := \frac{2^{1^5+4} + 6}{7 \times (9 + 3 + 8) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 + 5 + 4^6}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21546}{83790} := \frac{2 + 1 + 54 + 6}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{21 + 54 + 6}{(8 - 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times (5 + 46)}{8^3 - 7 + 90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21549}{78360} := \frac{2 - 1 \times 5 + 4 \times 9}{(7 - 8 + 3) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1 \times 5 \times 4) \times 9}{(7 + 8 - 3) \times 60}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2-1+5 \times (4+9)}{78 \times 3+6+0} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 154 \times 9}{7 \times 8 \times 3 \times 60} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21564}{97038} &:= \frac{((2+(1^5))^6) \times 4}{(9-(7-0)) \times (3^8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2-(1^5)) \times (6 \times 4)}{9 \times (7+(0-(3-8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (1+56)) + 4}{9 \times (70-(3+8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2+(15+6)) \times 4}{9 \times (70-(3 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2+1) \times (5 \times (6+4))}{9 \times (70-(3-8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2-1) \times (56 \times 4)}{970+38} \\ &:= \frac{(21-5) \times (6+4)}{9 \times ((7-(-03)) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2-(1-(5-(6-4)))}{9 \times (7-(0-(3-8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2-(1-(5^{6-4}))}{9 \times ((7 \times (03)) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2-(1-(5+64))}{9 \times (7 \times (0-(3-8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (((1+5) \times 6) + 4)}{9 + ((7^{03}) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (((1+5)^6) \times 4)}{((9-(7-0)) \times 3)^8} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1^5) + 64)}{9 \times (70 + (3-8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((15 \times 6) + 4)}{9 \times (70 + (3 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6-4)))}{9 + (70 + (3+8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6 \times 4)))}{9 \times ((7 \times (03)) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6+4)))}{9 \times (7 - ((0 \times 3) - 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6-4)))}{9 \times (7 - (0 \times 38))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + ((5+6) \times 4))}{9 \times (7 - (0-38))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (5 - (6+4)))}{9 \times ((7 + (-03)) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1^{564})}{9 - (7 \times (0 \times 38))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (5 - (6-4)))}{9 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 3)) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 - (5 - 64))}{9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4))}{9 \times (7 - (0 - (3+8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (5 \times (6-4)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - 38))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 + (5 - (6-4)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (3+8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 + (5 + (6+4)))}{9^{7+03-8}} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (156 + 4)}{9 \times (70 + (3+8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (156 - 4)}{9 \times (7 \times (0 + (3+8)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 1564}{9 + 7038} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21584}{39760} &:= \frac{2-1+5+8 \times 4}{3-9+76+0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21603}{87549} &:= \frac{2-1+6 \times 03}{8^{7-5}+4+9} \\ &:= \frac{(2-1) \times (60-3)}{8 \times 7 \times 5 - 49} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21604}{57938} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+6+04)}{5+7+9+38} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+6}+04}{5+7+9 \times 38} \\ &:= \frac{216+04}{579+3+8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21630}{47895} &:= \frac{2^{1+6}-30}{4 \times 78-95} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21630}{84975} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+6) \times 3+0}{8 \times (4+9+7)+5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 63+0}{(8+(4+9) \times 7) \times 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21645}{39780} &:= \frac{2^{1^6+4}+5}{3+9+7 \times 8+0} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+6}+4 \times 5}{(3 \times 9+7) \times 8+0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21658}{93704} &:= \frac{2+(1+6+5) \times 8}{(9-3) \times 70+4} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21670}{95348} &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times 6)) - (7-0)}{9+(5-((3-4) \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21573}{49068} &:= \frac{2 \times (15 \times 7 - 3)}{(4 + 9 \times 06) \times 8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21580}{46397} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+5) + 8+0}{4 \times (6 \times 3 - 9) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1 \times 5} + 8+0}{(46-3) \times (9-7)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{21583}{70964} &:= \frac{215-8 \times 3}{70 \times 9 - 6+4} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((1^6) + (7 - 0))}{9 + (5 \times (3 - (4 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))}{9 + (53 - (4 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + (6 - (7 - 0))}{(9 - (5 - (3 + 4))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (16 + (7 - 0))}{9 + (5 + (3 \times (4 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (1 + (6 - 70))}{9 + (5 + (34 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1^6) \times 70)}{((9^{5-3}) - 4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - 6)) + 70}{9 + (5 \times (3 + 48))}$$

$$:= \frac{21 - (6 - 70)}{9 + (5 \times ((3^4) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 16) \times 9) + 7}{5 + 3 + 408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21697}{83450} := \frac{2 - 1 + 6 \times (9 - 7)}{8 - 3 + 45 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 6 \times (9 - 7))}{(8 + 3 \times 4) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 6 \times 9) + 7}{(8 - 3 + 4) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 + 6 \times 97}{(8 - 3) \times 450}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1^7)) \times 35}{((4 \times 9) - 6) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (7 - 3))) \times 5}{(4 - (9 - 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 17) \times 35}{(4 + (9 + 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(21 + 7) \times (3 + 5)}{(4^{9-6}) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 \times (3 \times 5)))}{4 \times ((9 + 6) \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times 735)}{((4 \times 9) + 6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + ((7 - 3) \times 5))}{4 \times ((9 - 6) \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((1^7) \times (3^5))}{(4 + (9 - 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((7 \times 3) + 5))}{4 \times (96 - 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21693}{80574} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 6 + 9 - 3}{8 \times (0 \times 5 + 7) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 + 6 + 9 + 3}{80 - 5 + 7 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1 \times 6} + 9 - 3}{(8 + 057) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 1 + 6) \times (9 + 3)}{8 \times (05 \times 7 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 16 \times (9 - 3)}{(8 + 05) \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21730}{56498} := \frac{2 \times (1 + (7 - (3 - 0)))}{(5^{6-4}) + (9 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (17 - 30)}{5 - (6 + ((4 - 9) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{5 + (6 + (49 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (1 - (7 - (3 - 0)))}{5 + ((6 + (4 - 9)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{1 \times 7}) - (3 - 0)}{5 \times (64 + (9 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1 - 7)) \times 30}{(5 + (64 + 9)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1 + 7)^3 + 0}{5 \times (((6 - 4)^9) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((7^3) + 5))}{(4 + 96) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (7 + (3^5)))}{496 + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{21 \times ((7 + 3) \times 5)}{((4 \times 9) - 6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{21 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5)}{4 \times ((9 - 6) \times 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + ((7^3) \times 5)}{496 \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + (7 + 35)}{(4^{9-6}) + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + 735}{4 \times (9 \times (6 \times (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{217 - 35}{4 \times (96 + (8 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21697}{53408} := \frac{2 - 1 + 6 \times (9 - 7)}{(5 + 3 - 4) \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 6 \times (9 - 7))}{(5 - 3) \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 + 6^{9-7}}{(5 + 3 + 4) \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times (6 + 9) + 7}{(5 - 3)^4 \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 1 + 6 + 97}{(5 + 3) \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{40986} := \frac{2 \times (17 - 3) \times 5}{4 \times (09 \times 8 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 73 - 5}{40 + 98 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{49680} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 + 7)^3)) + 5}{49 \times (6 \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{86940} := \frac{((2 \times (1 + 7)) + 3) \times 5}{(86 + 9) \times (4 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 17) \times 3) + 5}{(8 + (6 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1^73)) \times 5}{8 - ((6 - 9) \times (4 - 0))}$$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + (7 \times 3))) - 5}{((8 \times 6) - 9) \times (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times ((17 + 3) \times 5)}{8 \times (6 + (94 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((7 \times 3) + 5))}{8 \times ((6 \times 9) - 40)}$
$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + 73)) - 5}{8 + (6 \times (94 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (7 - 35))}{8 \times (69 - 40)}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5))}{8 \times (6 + (9 - (4 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{(2^{1 \times 7}) + (3 - 5)}{(8 + 6) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times ((7 + 3) \times 5))}{8 \times ((6 \times 9) - (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5)))}{(8 - (6 - 9)) \times (4 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(2 + ((1 + 7) \times 3)) \times 5}{8 \times (69 - (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5))}{(8 \times (6 + 9)) + 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (7 \times (3 \times 5)))}{(8 \times (6 \times 9)) - (4 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(2 + (1 \times (7 + 3))) \times 5}{8 \times (6 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5)))}{(8 - 6) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (7 \times 35))}{(8 \times 6) + 940}$
$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (7 \times 3))) \times 5}{8 \times ((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 + 35))}{8 \times (6 + (9 \times (4 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (7 + (3 \times 5)))}{8 - (6 - (94 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(2 + 17) \times (3 + 5)}{8 + ((6 + 9) \times 40)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (73 + 5))}{8 \times (6 \times (9 + (4 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 1^{735}}{(8 \times 6) - (9 \times (4 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(2 - 1) \times (7 \times (3 + 5))}{8 + (6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + ((7 + 3) \times 5))}{(8 \times 6) + (9 \times 40)}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (7 + (3 - 5)))}{(8 - 6)^{9-4+0}}$
$:= \frac{(21 \times 7) - (3 + 5)}{(8 \times 69) + (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (7 - (3 - 5)))}{(8 \times (6 + 9)) - 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (7 + 35))}{86 + (94 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(21 \times 7) + (3^5)}{((8 \times 6) - 9) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (73 \times 5))}{8 \times (6 + (9 \times 40))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (73 - 5))}{8 + (69 \times (4 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(21 + 73) \times 5}{(8 - 6) \times 940}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (73 - 5))}{((8 - 6)^9) + 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + (173 + 5)}{(8 - 6) \times (9 \times 40)}$
$:= \frac{2 - ((1 - (7 + 3)) \times 5)}{(8 - 6) \times (94 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (17 - (3 - 5))}{8 \times (6 + (9 + (4 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 1735}{8 + 6940}$
$:= \frac{2 - (1 - ((7 - 3) \times 5))}{(8 \times 6) + (9 \times (4 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 - (7 - (3 + 5)))}{(8 \times (6 - 9)) + 40}$	$:= \frac{21 + (7 \times (3 + 5))}{(8 + 69) \times (4 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{2 - (1 - (7 \times (3 + 5)))}{((8 \times 6) + 9) \times (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5)))}{((8 - 6)^9) \times (4 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{96048} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7 \times 3 \times 5}{960 - 4 \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (1 - (7 + (3 \times 5)))}{(8 + (6 + 9)) \times (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 + (3 - 5)))}{8 - ((6 - 9) \times 40)}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 1^7) \times 35}{(9 \times 6 + 04) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (1 + (7 - 35))}{(8 \times (6 + 9)) - (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 1^{735}}{8^{6-9+4+0}}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{2 \times (((1 + 7)^3) \times 5)}{((8 - 6)^9) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((1 + (7 - 3)) \times 5)}{8 + (6 + (94 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21736}{45980} := \frac{2 - 1 + 7 + 3 \times 6}{4 + 59 - 8 + 0}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + (7 + 3)) \times 5)}{8 \times (6 + (9 + 40))}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((1 + 7) \times (3^5))}{8 + (6^{9-4+0})}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + (7 - 3)) \times 5)}{(8 + (6 - 9)) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 - (7 \times (3 - 5)))}{8 + ((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21740}{36958} := \frac{2 \times (1^7 + 4) + 0}{3^{6-9+5} + 8}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + 7) \times (3 + 5))}{(8 \times 69) - 40}$	$:= \frac{2 + (1 - (7 - 35))}{(8 \times (6 + 9)) + (4 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + 7)) + (4 - 0)}{3 - (6 - ((9 \times 5) - 8))}$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1^7)) \times 40}{(3 \times (6 + (9 + 5))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (7 + 40))}{3 + (69 + (5 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1^7) \times 40)}{(36 \times (9 - 5)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1^7)) \times 40}{(3 \times 69) + (5 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 \times 7)) \times 40}{(3^6) - (9 \times (5 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + 7)) \times 40}{(3^6) + (9 - 58)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21749}{83650} := \frac{2 + 1 \times 7 \times 4 + 9}{(8 - 3) \times 6 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7 \times 4 + 9}{(8 + 3 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (17 - 4) \times 9}{(8 \times 3 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21780}{93654} := \frac{21 + 7 - 8 + 0}{(9 + 3 + 6) \times 5 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 78 + 0}{9 \times 36 + 5 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 178 + 0}{9 \times (3 \times 6 \times 5 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21793}{50468} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7 + 9 + 3}{5 \times 04 + 68}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1 + 7 + 9) \times 3}{50 \times 4 - 68}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (17 - 9) + 3}{50 - 4 + 6 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1^7 \times 93}{5 \times (-04 + 6 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21798}{45360} := \frac{2 + 179 - 8}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21835}{67490} := \frac{2 \times (1 + 8 - 3 + 5)}{6 - 7 \times 4 + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 1 + 8 + 35}{6 \times 7 + 4 + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 8 \times 3) + 5}{6 + 74 + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + 83 - 5}{6^{7-4} + 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21835}{96074} := \frac{(2 + (1^{83})) \times 5}{9 + (60 - (7 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 - (3 - 5)))}{(9 + (6 - (-07))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (18 - 3)) \times 5}{(9 \times (6 \times (07))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (8 \times 3))) \times 5}{9 \times (6 \times ((07 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (183 - 5)}{9 \times (60 + (7 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 \times (3 \times 5)))}{96 \times ((07 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 \times 35))}{(9 + 607) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (1^{83})) \times 5}{96 + (0 - 74)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21843}{50967} := \frac{(2 \times (18 \times 4)) - 3}{(50 - (9 - 6)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (8 - 4))) \times 3}{(5 \times (09)) + 67}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1^{84}))^3}{5 + (0 - (9 - 67))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1^8))^{4+3}}{5096 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (8 \times 4))) \times 3}{(50 - (9 + 6)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (8 + 4))) \times 3}{5 \times (0 + ((9 - 6) \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times (8 + 43)}{((5 \times (09)) + 6) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(21 + (8 \times 4)) \times 3}{(50 + (9 - 6)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (((1 - 8) \times 4) - 3)}{((5 - (-09)) \times 6) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((1 - 8) \times (4^3))}{50 \times ((9 - 6) \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((1 - 8) \times 43)}{(5 - (0 - 96)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (1 \times (8 - (4 \times 3)))}{5 + (0 - (9 \times (6 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((1 + (8 + 4)) \times 3)}{(5 - (-09)) \times (6 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times ((8 - 4) \times 3))}{5 - (0 - (9 + (6 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + ((8 \times 4) - 3))}{(5 - (0 - (9 + 6))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (8 \times (4 - 3)))}{(5 \times (0 \times 9)) + (6 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (18 \times (4 + 3))}{(5 - (-09)) \times (6 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 1^{843}}{(5 \times (0 \times 96)) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + ((8 + 4) \times 3))}{((5 - (-09)) \times 6) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + ((8 - 4) \times 3))}{5 \times ((0 \times 96) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (8 + (4 - 3)))}{50 - (9 + (6 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (8 + 43))}{50 + (9 + 67)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (1 + (84 + 3))}{5 \times ((0 \times 9) + (6 \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{21 + (8 \times (4 \times 3))}{((5 \times (09)) - 6) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{218 + (4 + 3)}{5 \times (0 + ((9 + 6) \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{2184-3}{5096-7}$$

$$:= \frac{2+18 \times 7-9}{(6+4^3) \times 5+0}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(1+(9+(4+8)))}{6-(0-(3+57))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21856}{70349} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times (8+5)+6}{70-3+4 \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{21 \times (8+7)-9}{(6+4 \times 3) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(1+(9+(4-8)))}{((6+(-03)) \times 5)+7}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(1+(9+48))}{60+(3 \times (5 \times 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{35964} := \frac{(2+1) \times (8+7)+0}{3+5 \times (9+6)-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21945}{36708} := \frac{2-1+9+45}{36+7 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21945}{67830} := \frac{2 \times (1+9+4)+5}{(6 \times 7-8) \times 3+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21960}{34587} := \frac{2 \times (1+9)+60}{34+5+87}$$

$$:= \frac{2+1+87+0}{(3 \times 5+9) \times 6+4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+1 \times 9) \times (4+5)}{6 \times 7 \times 8-30}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1^9 \times 60}{((3+4) \times 5-8) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+1+9) \times 60}{(34 \times 5-8) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{53946} := \frac{(2-1) \times (8+7)+0}{5^3-94+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21948}{60357} := \frac{(2-(1-(9+4))) \times 8}{((60+3) \times 5)-7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-1) \times 960}{3 \times (4+5) \times 8 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (8+7)+0}{5 \times (3+9+4)-6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-(1-9)) \times 48}{60 \times ((3 \times 5)+7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+1) \times (8+7)+0}{5 \times 3 \times 9-4 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (1+(9-4)))+8}{(6 \times (0+(3+5)))+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21973}{65408} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7+3}{(-6+54) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{64395} := \frac{2+1+8+7+0}{6+43+9-5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+(1 \times 9)) \times (4+8)}{6-(0-357)}$$

$$:= \frac{2+1+87+0}{(6+4) \times 3 \times 9-5}$$

$$:= \frac{2-(1+(9-(4+8)))}{6-(0-(3-(5-7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{21+87+0}{6 \times (4 \times (3+9)+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((19-4) \times 8)}{603+57}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{34056} := \frac{2 \times (1+97 \times 8)}{(3+40) \times 56}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{34650} := \frac{2 \times (1+97 \times 8)}{(3+46) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1-8+70)}{6+(4^3+9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1-(9-(4 \times 8)))}{6 \times (0+((3 \times 5)+7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{35046} := \frac{2 \times 19+7-8}{35-0+4 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{21+8+7+0}{64+3 \times (9+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (94-8))}{(60 \times (3+5))-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{35640} := \frac{21 \times 9-78}{3 \times (56+4)+0}$$

$$:= \frac{2-18+70}{6 \times 4+3 \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1+(9-(4-8)))}{(6-((0 \times 3)-5)) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{43065} := \frac{2 \times (1+9) \times 7+8}{(4^3-06) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1+(9+(4 \times 8)))}{60+(3 \times 57)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{53460} := \frac{2 \times (1+9) \times 7+8}{5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21879}{64350} := \frac{2-1+(8+7) \times 9}{(6-4)^3 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (9+(4-8)))}{60+(35-7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 19+7-8}{5 \times (3 \times 4+6)+0}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{1+8}+7-9}{(6+4) \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(1 \times (94-8))}{6-(0-((3^5)-7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(21+9+7) \times 8}{(5+3+4) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-(1-8) \times 7) \times 9}{(6 \times 4+3) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(1+(9-(4-8)))}{6-(0-(3+(5 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{21+978}{5 \times 3^4 \times 6+0}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{2 \times (1 + 9 \times 78)}{(53 + 4) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{65340} & := \frac{21 \times 9 - 78}{6 \times (5 \times 3 + 40)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21987}{45360} & := \frac{219 \times 8 - 7}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23016}{87954} & := \frac{2 \times (30 - 16)}{8 + 79 + 5 \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (30 + 1) - 6}{(8 + 7) \times (9 + 5) + 4} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23046}{79158} & := \frac{2 - 3 + 04 \times 6}{7 + 9 \times 1^5 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{23 + 046}{79 + 158} \\
 & := \frac{23^{-04+6}}{79 \times (15 + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{230 - 46}{79 \times 1^5 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 30 \times 46}{79 \times 15 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + 30) \times 46}{(7 \times 91 - 5) \times 8} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23056}{41789} & := \frac{2^{3-05+6}}{4 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 9} \\
 & := \frac{2^{3+0 \times 5} \times 6}{4 + 1 - 7 + 89} \\
 & := \frac{2^3 \times 05 \times 6}{(4 + 1) \times (78 + 9)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23058}{69174} & := \frac{((2 \times (3 - 0)) - 5)^8}{6 + (9 - (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\
 \\
 & := \frac{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 5) - 8}{6 + (9 \times ((1^7) + 4))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 + 30) \times 5) + 8}{6 \times (9 + (1 + 74))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 + 30) \times 5) - 8}{6 \times ((9 \times (1 + 7)) + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (3 \times (-05))) \times 8}{6 \times ((9 + (1 + 7)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (3 - 0)) \times (5 - 8)}{6 - (9 - (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 5)))^8}{(6^{9-1}) \times (7 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (-05))) + 8}{6 - (9 - (1 + 74))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (05))) + 8}{6 \times (9 - (1 - (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (05))) - 8}{6 \times (9 - (1 - (7 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (-05))) + 8}{6 + (9 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (30 - 5)) - 8}{6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times 30) - (5 \times 8)}{6 \times (9 + (1^{74}))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times 30) + (5 \times 8)}{(69 - (1 - 7)) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times 30) + (5 + 8)}{(6 - 9) \times (1 - 74)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times 30) + 58}{6 \times ((9 \times (1 \times 7)) - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2^{3-0 \times 5})^8}{6 \times (((9 - 1)^7) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2^{3-0 \times 5}) + 8}{6 \times (9 - (1^{74}))} \\
 \\
 & := \frac{(2^3 + 0) \times (5 + 8)}{(6 + (9 \times (1 + 7))) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{(2^3 + 0) + (5 + 8)}{(6 \times (9 + 1)) + (7 - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 5))) \times 8}{6 \times (9 + (1 \times (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (3 - (-05))) \times 8}{6 \times ((9 + (1^7)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (3 - 0)) \times (5 + 8)}{6 + (9 \times (17 + 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (30 - 5)) \times 8}{6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + 3)^{-05+8}}{(((6 \times 9) - 1) \times 7) + 4} \\
 & := \frac{(23 - (-05)) \times 8}{6 + (9 \times (1 \times 74))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - 30) \times (5 - 8)}{(69 + (1 - 7)) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{2 - ((3 \times (0 \times 5)) - 8)}{6 \times (9 - (1 + (7 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 - ((3 \times (-05)) + 8)}{6 + (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 - ((3 \times (-05)) - 8)}{(6 + 9) \times ((1^7) + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{2 - (3 \times ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 - (3 \times (0 - (5 + 8)))}{6 + (9 \times (17 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{2 - (3 \times (0 \times 58))}{6 \times (9 - 1 - 7)^4} \\
 & := \frac{2 - (3 \times (0 - 58))}{6 \times (91 - (7 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{2 - (3 + ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{6 - (9 + ((1 - 7) \times 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 - (3 + (0 - 58))}{6 - (9 - 174)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (30 \times (5 - 8))}{(6 + (9 \times (1 \times 7))) \times 4} \\
 := \frac{2 - (30 - 58)}{6 + (9 + (1 + 74))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((3 - (-05)) \times 8)}{6 \times ((9 + (1 \times 7)) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((3 \times (05)) - 8)}{6 \times (9 + (1 - (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((30 + 5) \times 8)}{6 \times ((9 + 1) \times (7 \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 - (5 \times 8)))}{6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 - (5 + 8)))}{6 - (9 \times (1 - (7 + 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 \times 58))}{6 + (9 + (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8))}{6^{9-1 \times 7} \times 4} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))}{6 \times (9 \times (17^4))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times 3^{0 \times 5 + 8}}{6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3^{-05+8})}{6 \times (9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 + (0 - (5 - 8)))}{6 \times (9 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (30 - (5 + 8))}{6 \times (91 - 74)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (30 \times (5 \times 8))}{(6 - 9) \times (1 - (7^4))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (30 + (5 \times 8))}{(6 + (9 \times 1)) \times (7 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{2^3 + 0 \times 58}{6 - (9 \times (1 - (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2^{3-05+8}}{6 \times ((9 - (17^7)) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 + ((3 - (-05)) \times 8)}{6 \times (9 - ((1 - 7) \times 4))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 + ((3^{05}) + 8)}{69 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))} \\
 := \frac{2 + ((30 \times 5) + 8)}{6 \times (91 - (7 + 4))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{6 + (9 - ((1 - 7) \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 \times 58))}{6 + (9 \times (17^4))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 - 58))}{6 + (9 + 174)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))}{6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3^{-05+8})}{6 + ((9 + (1 - 7))^4)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 - (5 + 8))}{(6 \times (9 \times 1)) + (7 - 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 - (5 - 8))}{6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 + (5 \times 8))}{6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 + 58)}{6 \times (9 \times ((17^7) + 4))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (305 - 8)}{69 \times (17 - 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 + 3058}{6 + 9174} \\
 := \frac{23 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)}{69 - ((1 - 7) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 - (5 + 8))}{6 + (91 + (7 + 4))} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 \times 58)}{6 + (91 - (7 \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 - 58)}{69 + 174} \\
 := \frac{23 \times (0 - (5 - 8))}{69 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))} \\
 := \frac{23 + ((0 \times 5) - 8)}{(6 + (9 \times 1)) \times (7 - 4)} \\
 := \frac{230 + (5 - 8)}{6 + (9 \times (1 + 74))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{230 + 58}{6^{9+1-7} \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23058}{91476} := \frac{2 \times (3 - 0 + 58)}{9 - 1 + 476} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23069}{58174} := \frac{2^3 + 06 + 9}{5 + 81 - 7 \times 4} \\
 := \frac{23 \times (-06 + 9)}{58 \times 1 \times (7 - 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 - 30 \times (6 - 9)}{58 \times (1 + 7 - 4)} \\
 := \frac{2 + 306 - 9}{58 \times (17 - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23075}{84916} := \frac{2 \times (3 + 07) + 5}{8 + (4 + 9 + 1) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 + 07) \times 5}{8 \times (4 \times (9 + 1) + 6)} \\
 := \frac{(23 + 07) \times 5}{(84 + 9 - 1) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23079}{46158} := \frac{((2^3 + 0) \times 7) - 9}{46 + ((1 + 5) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 7) - 9}{4 \times (6 + (15 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - (3 \times (-07))) \times 9}{46 \times ((1^5) + 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 - (3 + (-07))) \times 9}{(4 \times ((6 - 1) \times 5)) + 8} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (-07))) + 9}{4 + (6 \times ((1^5) + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (0 \times 7))) + 9}{4 + (6 + ((1^5) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (07))) + 9}{4 + ((6 \times 15) + 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (3 - 0)) + (7 + 9)}{4 + ((6 - (1^5)) \times 8)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(2 \times (3 - 0)) + (7 - 9)}{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (30 + 7)) + 9}{46 + (15 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (30 + 7)) - 9}{4 + (6 + (15 \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times 3)^{-07+9}}{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times 30) - (7 + 9)}{4 + (6 \times (1 + (5 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times 30) + (7 + 9)}{4 \times (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times 30) + (7 - 9)}{4 \times (6 + (15 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2^{3+0 \times 7}) \times 9}{(4 \times 6) + (15 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2^{3+0 \times 7}) + 9}{46 + (1 - (5 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2^3 + 0) \times (7 + 9)}{4 \times (6 + (1 \times 58))} \\
 := \frac{(2^3 + 0) + (7 \times 9)}{4 + (6 \times (15 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 7))) \times 9}{(4 + 6) \times ((1^5) + 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 7)))^9}{(4 + (6 \times 1)) \times (5^8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (3 - (-07))) \times 9}{4 \times (6 \times ((1^5) + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (3 - 0)) \times (7 + 9)}{4 \times ((6 - (1^5)) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 - 3) \times (0 - 79)}{((4 + 6) \times 15) + 8} \\
 := \frac{2 - ((3 \times (-07)) + 9)}{4 + (6 \times (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (3 - (0 - (7 - 9)))}{4 - (6 - (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (3 \times (0 - (7 + 9)))}{4 + ((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (3 \times (0 \times 79))}{4 - ((6 - (1 + 5)) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (3 + (0 - (7 + 9)))}{4 - (6 + ((1 - 5) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (30 - (7 \times 9))}{(4 + 6) \times (15 - 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 - (30 - (7 \times 9))}{(4 + 6) \times (15 - 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((3 - (-07)) \times 9)}{(4 + (6 - 1)) \times (5 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((3 \times (07)) + 9)}{(4 + (6 + (1 \times 5))) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((3 \times (07)) - 9)}{(4 \times (6 - (1 - 5))) + 8} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{((4 \times (6 + 1)) + 5) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}{4 - (6 \times (1 - (5 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 \times 79))}{4 + (6 - (1 + (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 - (0 - 79))}{4 \times ((6 \times 15) - 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 \times (0 - (7 - 9)))}{4 + (6 + (1 + (5 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 \times (0 + (7 + 9)))}{4 \times (6 \times ((1^5) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3^{-07+9})}{4 \times (6 - (1 \times (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))}{4 \times (6 - ((1^5)^8))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (30 - (7 + 9))}{4 - (6 - (1 \times 58))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (30 + (7 - 9))}{(4 + (6 - (1 - 5))) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2^3 + 0 \times 79}{4^{6-1+5-8}} \\
 := \frac{2^{3 \times (-07+9)}}{(4^{6+1-5}) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2^{3^{-07+9}}}{4^{6-158}} \\
 := \frac{2^{3-07+9}}{4^{6+1 \times 5-8}} \\
 := \frac{2 + ((3 - (-07)) \times 9)}{4 \times (6 + (1 \times (5 \times 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (1 + 5))) - 8} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}{4 + (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 - (7 - 9)))}{4 + (6 - (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 \times 79))}{4 - (6 + (1 - (5 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 - (0 - 79))}{4 + (6 + 158)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3^{-07+9})}{4 - (6 \times (1 \times (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))}{4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 - (7 + 9))}{4 \times (6 - (1 + (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 - (7 - 9))}{4 + (6 + (1 \times 58))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 + (7 + 9))}{4 \times (6 \times (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 + (7 - 9))}{4 \times (6 + ((1^5) + 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (30 + 79)}{(46 \times (1 \times 5)) - 8} \\
 := \frac{2 + 3079}{4 + 6158} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 - (7 \times 9))}{4 + ((6 + 15) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 - (7 + 9))}{4 + (61 + (5 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 \times 79)}{4 + (6 \times (15 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{23 - (0 - 79)}{(4 \times 61) - (5 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{23 \times (0 - (7 - 9))}{(4 \times (6 + 15)) + 8} \\
 := \frac{23^{-07+9}}{46 \times (15 + 8)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{23 + (0 - (7 - 9))}{4 + (6 + (1 \times (5 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{230 - (7 - 9)}{461 - (5 - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{230 - 79}{4 \times 61 + 58} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{41796} &:= \frac{230 - 8 \times 5}{4 \times (1 + 79 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{47196} &:= \frac{2 + 3 - 0 + 8 \times 5}{4 - 7 - 1 + 96} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{49761} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 08 \times 5}{4^{9-7} \times 6 + 1} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 30 \times (8 - 5)}{4 \times ((9 + 7) \times 6 + 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + 308 + 5}{4 + 9 \times (76 - 1)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23091}{86457} &:= \frac{2 \times (30 - 9) + 1}{(8 + 6 + 4 + 5) \times 7} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23108}{76954} &:= \frac{2 + (3 + 10) \times 8}{7 \times (6 + 9 \times 5) - 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23157}{94860} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 15 - 7}{(9 - 4) \times (8 + 60)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23157}{98604} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 1 \times 57}{(9 \times 8 - 6) \times 04} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23160}{89745} &:= \frac{2^{3+1^6} + 0}{8 + 9 \times (7 + 4 - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 1 + 60)}{8 \times (9 \times 7 + 4 - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 160}{8 \times (97 - 4) \times 5} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{64890} &:= \frac{2 - ((3 \times (1 - 7)) + 5)}{6 - ((4 - 8) \times (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (1 \times (7 + 5)))}{6 - (4 + (8 - 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + 17)) + 5}{6 \times (4 + (8 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^3) - (1 - 7)) \times 5}{(6 - 4) \times (8 + 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (((3 - 1)^7) + 5)}{(6 \times 48) + 90} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 - (1 - 7)) \times 5}{(6^4) - 890} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (3 + 175)}{(64 - 8) \times (9 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^3 \times 1) \times (7 \times 5)}{64 + (8 \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 + 1) \times (7 \times 5)}{6 \times (4 \times (8 + 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 + 1) \times 75}{(64 - 8) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{80649} &:= \frac{2 + 3^{1^7} \times 5}{80 - 6 + 4 + 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{90846} &:= \frac{2 - 3 + 1 + 75}{9 \times 08 \times 4 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{2^3 \times 1 \times 75}{(90 + 8) \times 4 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{96408} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 17 + 5)}{9 \times 6 \times 4 - 08} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - 3 \times (1 - 7)) \times 5}{96 + 40 \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 31) \times 75}{(-9 + 6^4) \times 08} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23184}{57960} &:= \frac{((2^3) + 1) \times 84}{5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 31) + 84}{5 \times (79 - (6 - 0))} \\
 \hline
 &:= \frac{(2^{3+1}) \times 84}{5 \times (7 \times (96 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times (1^8))) \times 4}{5 \times (7 + (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 + (1 + 8))) \times 4}{(5 \times (7 + 9)) + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 31) \times (8 \times 4)}{((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 + 1) \times 84}{(5 + 79) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((3 \times 18) + 4)}{5 \times (7 - (9 - 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((3 + 18) \times 4)}{(5 - (7 - 9)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4)))}{5 \times ((7 + 9) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4)))}{(5 + (7 - 9)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 - 4)))}{57 + (9 - (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (1 \times 84))}{(5 + (7 + 9)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (1^{84}))}{5 + (7 + (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (18 \times 4))}{(5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (18 + 4))}{5 - ((7 - 9) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (31 + 84)}{(5 \times 7) + (9 \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{3 \times 1^{84}}}{5 \times (7 - (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((3 - (1 - 8)) \times 4)}{5 \times (7 \times (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((3 - 1) \times 84)}{5 \times (79 + (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((31 \times 8) - 4)}{5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (3 - (1 - (8 \times 4)))}{5 + (79 + (6 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 + (3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4)))}{5 \times (79 - 60)} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 \times (18 - 4))}{5 \times (7 + (9 + (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{2 + 3184}{5 + 7960} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23184}{95760} & := \frac{23 + 184}{9 \times (5 \times 7 + 60)} \\ & := \frac{23 \times (1 + 8 + 4)}{95 \times (7 + 6) + 0} \\ & := \frac{23 \times 1^{84}}{95 \times (7 - 6) + 0} \\ & := \frac{23 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}{(9 - 5) \times 760} \\ & := \frac{23 \times (1 + 8) \times 4}{9 \times 5 \times 76 + 0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{57681} & := \frac{2 \times 3^4 - 09}{(5 + 7 \times 6) \times 8 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{86751} & := \frac{2 - 3 \times (4 - 09)}{8 \times (6 + 7 - 5) - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{87516} & := \frac{2 \times 3^4 - 09}{8 \times 7 + 516} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23415}{60879} & := \frac{2 + (3 - (4 + (1 - 5)))}{60 - ((8 \times 7) - 9)} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + ((4 - 1) \times 5))}{60 + (8 - (7 + 9))} \\ & := \frac{2 - (3 - (41 + 5))}{(6 - ((0 \times 8) - 7)) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (3 \times (4 + (1 + 5)))}{60 + (87 + 9)} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (34 + 1)) + 5}{60 + ((8 + 7) \times 9)} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 1) \times 5))}{6 \times (((08 \times 7) + 9))} \\ & := \frac{(2 + (34 \times 1)) \times 5}{6 \times ((087 - 9))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23415}{86970} & := \frac{2 \times (3 - 4 + 15)}{8 + 6 \times (9 + 7) - 0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23460}{78591} & := \frac{2 \times (3 + 4) + 6 + 0}{(7 + 8) \times 5 - 9 + 1} \\ & := \frac{2 + 3 \times 46 + 0}{7 \times (8 + 59 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{(2 - 3 + 4) \times 60}{7 \times 85 + 9 - 1} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23478}{69015} & := \frac{2 + 3 \times 4 \times (7 + 8)}{6 \times 90 \times 1 - 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{51678} & := \frac{2 + (3 - (4 - (9 - 0)))}{5 + (16 - (7 - 8))} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 4)) - (9 - 0)}{(5 \times (1 - (6 - 7))) + 8} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (3 + 4)) - (9 - 0)}{5 - (1 - (6 - (7 - 8)))} \\ & := \frac{2 - (3 - (4 \times (9 - 0)))}{5 - (1 \times (6 - 78))} \\ & := \frac{2 + (34 + (9 - 0))}{5 + (16 + 78)} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (34 - (9 - 0))}{5 \times (1 + (6 + (7 + 8)))} \\ & := \frac{2 - ((3 \times 4) - 90)}{((5 - 1) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8} \\ & := \frac{2 - (3 \times (4 - 90))}{516 + (7 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(2 - (3 - 4)) \times 90}{516 + 78} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{61857} & := \frac{2 \times (3^4 + 9) + 0}{6 \times (1 + 85 - 7)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{71568} & := \frac{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 - 0}{7 \times 1 \times 568} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{75168} & := \frac{2 + (3 - (4 - (9 - 0)))}{(7 \times 5) - (1 - (6 - 8))} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 4)) - (9 - 0)}{(7 + (5 - (1 \times 6))) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (3 + 4)) - (9 - 0)}{7 - (5 - (1 \times (6 + 8)))} \\ & := \frac{2 - (3 - (4 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (((5 - 1) \times 6) - 8)} \\ & := \frac{2 + (34 + (9 - 0))}{(7 - (5 - 16)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (34 - (9 - 0))}{(7 \times ((5 - 1) \times 6)) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times 3) + (49 - 0)}{(7 \times ((5 - 1) \times 6)) + 8} \\ & := \frac{2 + ((3 + 4) \times (9 - 0))}{(((7 \times 5) + 1) \times 6) - 8} \\ & := \frac{2 - ((3 \times 4) - 90)}{(7 - (5 \times 16))^8} \\ & := \frac{2 - (3 + (4 - 90))}{((7 \times (5 - 1)) + 6) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(2 + (3 - 4)) \times 90}{((7 \times (5 + 1)) - 6) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times 3) + (4 + 90)}{((7 \times 5) - (1 - 6)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 \times (4 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 + (5 \times (1 + 68))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times ((3^4) + (9 - 0))}{(7 + (5 \times 1)) \times (6 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{78561} & := \frac{(2 + 3 - 4) \times 90}{7 \times (8 + 5 \times (6 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (3^4 + 9) + 0}{7 + 85 \times (6 + 1)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{23495}{61087} & := \frac{2 + (3 - (4 - (9 - 5)))}{6((10^8) \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{(2 - (3 + (4 - 9))) \times 5}{6 - (10 - (8 \times 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - 4)) + 9) \times 5}{(6 - (1 + (-08))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (34 - 9)) - 5}{61 - (0 - (8 \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (3 - (4 + 9))) \times 5}{6 + (10 \times (8 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(23 - (4 - 9)) \times 5}{((6 \times 10) - 8) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (4 \times (9 \times 5)))}{(61 \times (08)) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (3 + (5 - (1 + 7)))}{(9 \times (4 \times (0 \times 6))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (3 + (5 - 17))}{(9 \times (4 - (0 \times 6))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((3 \times (5 + 1)) - 7)}{(9 - (4 + (-06))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((3^5) - (1 - 7))}{(9 + (40 \times 6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((3 + (5 + 1)) \times 7)}{9 \times (4 \times (0 + (6 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (5 - (1^7)))}{94 + (0 - (6 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (5 - (1 - 7)))}{(9 - (4 \times (-06))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1 \times 7)))}{9 \times ((4 \times (06)) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1^7)))}{9 \times (4^{-06+8})}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1 + 7)))}{(9 \times 40) - (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3^{5-1^7})}{9 \times (4 - (0 - 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (5 - (1^7)))}{(9 + (4 + (-06))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (5 \times (1 + 7)))}{(9 + (40 - 6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (5 \times 17))}{(94 + (-06)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (5 + (1^7)))}{9 \times (4 \times (0 - (6 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (35 - (1 \times 7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (06))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((3^{5 \times 1}) + 7)}{940 + 68}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 - (5 - (1 \times 7)))}{(9 \times (4 - (0 \times 6))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 \times (5 \times (1 \times 7)))}{(9 \times 40) + 68}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 \times (5 + (1^7)))}{94 + (0 - (6 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + ((5 + 1) \times 7))}{94 \times (0 - (6 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 - (1^7)))}{9 \times (4 - (0 \times 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 \times (1^7)))}{(9 - (4 - (0 \times 6))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 + 17))}{9 \times (4 - ((0 \times 6) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + 517)}{9 \times ((40 \times 6) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (35 \times (1 \times 7))}{940 + (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{23 - (5 - (1 + 7))}{(9 + (4 - (0 \times 6))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{235 + 1 + 7}{9 \times (40 + 68)}$$

$$:= \frac{235 - 17}{940 - 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23517}{96480} := \frac{235 - 1^7}{(9 - 6) \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23540}{69871} := \frac{(2 \times 3 + 5) \times 40}{(6 + 9) \times 87 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23541}{86907} := \frac{2^3 + 5^{4-1}}{8 + 69 \times 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{68094} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (5 - 7))) - 1}{(6 - 8) \times (0 - (9 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 + 7 + 1))}{(6 \times (8 - (0 \times 9))) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 - (3 - 5)) \times 7) - 1}{6 \times (8 - (0 - (9 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7 - 1)}{68 - (0 - (9 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{((6 + (8 - 0)) \times 9) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23504}{78196} := \frac{(-2 + 3 \times 5) \times 04}{78 - 1 + 96}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 3 \times 50 + 4}{7 + 8^{1 \times 9 - 6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23517}{94068} := \frac{((2^3) + 5) \times 17}{(9 + (4 - 0)) \times 68}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + (5 \times 1))) + 7}{94 - (0 - (6 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^3) + (51 - 7)}{(9 \times (4 \times (06))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 3) \times (5 \times (1 + 7))}{(94 - (-06)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 3) \times (5 + (1 \times 7))}{(9 - (4 - 0)) \times (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 3) \times (5 + 17)}{(9 + (40 + 6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(23 \times (5 - 1)) - 7}{(9 - (4 - 0)) \times 68}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 35) \times (1 - 7)}{9 \times (40 + (6 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (3 - (5 \times 17))}{((9 \times (4 - 0)) + 6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (3 - (5 + 17))}{(9 \times (4 - 0)) + (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (3 \times (5 - 17))}{(9 + (4 - (-06))) \times 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{2 \times (35 - (7 + 1))}{((6 \times (8 - 0)) - 9) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 - 3 - 5 + 98}{4 + 6 + 170} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23715}{48960} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times (7 - 1) - 5}{4 - (8 - 9) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 1)}{(6 - (8 \times (-09))) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times 35 - 9 + 8}{4 + 61 + 70} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 - 7 \times (1 - 5))}{4 \times (8 + 9) + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 7) + 1))}{6 \times (8 \times ((09 + 4)))} &:= \frac{2 + 3 \times (5 \times 9 + 8)}{(46 - 1) \times 7 + 0} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23715}{94860} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (7 \times 1))) + 5}{((9 - 4) \times 8) + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (3 + (57 + 1))}{(6 + (8 - 0)) \times (9 + 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{47610} := \frac{2 + 3^5 - 9 - 8}{(4 + 7 \times 6) \times 10} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + 71)) + 5}{(94 + 8) \times (6 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{235 + 71}{68 \times ((09 + 4))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{61047} := \frac{2^{3+5} - 9 \times 8}{6 + 10 \times 47} &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times 71)) \times 5}{(9 - 4) \times 860} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{69840} &:= \frac{(2 - 3 + 5) \times 7 - 1}{(6 + 9) \times 8 - 40} & &:= \frac{(2 + (3 + (7 \times 1))) \times 5}{(9 - 4) \times (8 \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (35 - 7 - 1)}{(6 + 9) \times 8 + 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23607}{58194} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6 + 07}{5 + 8 - 1 + 94} &:= \frac{(2 + (37 \times 1)) \times 5}{(9 - (4 - 8)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 5 + 71}{6 \times (9 - 8) \times 40} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23607}{59841} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6 + 07}{(5 + 9) \times 8 - 4 + 1} &:= \frac{(23 - (7 - 1)) \times 5}{(9 - 4) \times (8 + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{235 + 7 + 1}{(6 + 9) \times (8 + 40)} & &:= \frac{(23 \times (7 \times 1)) - 5}{(9 + 4) \times (8 \times (6 - 0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{89046} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (5 - 7))) - 1}{(8 \times (9 + (-04))) - 6} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23640}{57918} := \frac{(2 - 3 + 6) \times 4 + 0}{57 - 9 + 1^8} &:= \frac{(23 \times 7) + (1^5)}{9 \times (4 + (8 + 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (3 - 5)) \times 7) - 1}{(8 + (9 - (0 \times 4))) \times 6} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6 + 4 + 0}{5 \times (7 + 9) + 18} &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (7 \times (1^5)))}{(9 \times (4 - 8)) + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{(8 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 + 6)} &:= \frac{236 + 4 + 0}{579 + 1 + 8} &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (7 + (1 - 5)))}{94 - (86 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{23 + (5 + 71)}{8 + ((90 \times 4) + 6)} & &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (7 + 15))}{(9 \times 4) + (8 \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 1)}{(8 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 \times 6)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23650}{48719} := \frac{2 \times 3 - 6 + 50}{(4 + 8) \times 7 + 19} &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (71 + 5))}{(9 + (4 - 8)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{235 + (7 + 1)}{8 + (904 + 6)} & &:= \frac{2 - (3 \times (7 - 15))}{(9 \times 4) + (8 + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^3) \times ((5 \times 7) + 1)}{8 \times (90 + 46)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23691}{54087} := \frac{2 + 3 \times (69 + 1)}{540 - 8 \times 7} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 - (7 - 15))}{(9 \times 4) - (8 - 60)} \\
 & &:= \frac{(2 + 3) \times (6 \times 9 - 1)}{5 + 40 \times (8 + 7)} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (7 - (1^5)))}{9 \times (4^{8-6+0})} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{41607} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 5) + 98}{(4 - 1) \times (60 + 7)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (7 - (1 - 5)))}{((9 \times 4) + 8) \times (6 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 3 + 5 + 9) \times 8}{4 \times 1 \times (60 + 7)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{23698}{75140} := \frac{236 - 9 \times 8}{(7 + 5 + 1) \times 40} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1 + 5)))}{948 + 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{46170} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 5 - 9 - 8}{46 - 1^{70}} & &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1^5)))}{(9 \times (4 + 8)) + 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 \times (3 + (7 - (1^5)))}{9 \times (4 \times (8 - (6 - 0)))} & & & & & & := \frac{(23 - 8) \times 5 + 0}{41 + 97 - 6} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (3 + (7 \times (1^5)))}{94 - (8 + (6 - 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{23751}{49068} & := \frac{2 + 3^7 - 5 \times 1}{(4 + 90) \times 6 \times 8} & & & & \\ & := \frac{2 + ((3 + 7 + 1) \times 5)}{(9 \times (4 \times 8)) - 60} & & & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23851}{46970} & := \frac{23 \times 85 \times 1}{(46 + 9) \times 70} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 \times (7 \times (1^5)))}{94 - (8 - (6 - 0))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{54168} & := \frac{2 \times 37 - 9 + 0}{5 \times 4 \times (1 + 6) + 8} & & & & \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 \times (7 + (1 + 5)))}{((9 + 4) \times 8) + 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{61854} & := \frac{2 \times (3 - (7 - (9 - 0)))}{6 + ((1^8) \times (5 \times 4))} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23856}{97104} & := \frac{(2 + 3 + 8) \times 5 + 6}{9 + 7 \times 10 \times 4} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + ((7 + 1) \times 5))}{94 + (86 - 0)} & & := \frac{2 - (3 - (7 + (9 - 0)))}{((6 + (1^8)) \times 5) + 4} & & & & \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + (7 - (1^5)))}{((9 + 4) \times 8) - 60} & & := \frac{23 - (7 - (9 - 0))}{((6 + 1) \times 8) + (5 + 4)} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23870}{41695} & := \frac{2 \times (3 + 8) \times 7 + 0}{4 + (-1 + 6 \times 9) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + (7 \times (1 + 5)))}{94 \times (8 - (6 - 0))} & & := \frac{2 + (37 - (9 - 0))}{6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4)))} & & & & \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + (7 \times (1^5)))}{(9 \times (4 + 8)) - 60} & & := \frac{(2 \times 3) + (79 - 0)}{61 + (8 \times (5 \times 4))} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23871}{49056} & := \frac{2 \times (38 + 71)}{4 + 90 \times 5 - 6} \\ & := \frac{2 + (3 + (7 + 15))}{94 + (8 + (6 - 0))} & & := \frac{2 \times ((3 + 7) \times (9 - 0))}{(61 \times 8) - (5 \times 4)} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23871}{56940} & := \frac{23 + 87 - 1}{(56 + 9) \times 4 + 0} \\ & := \frac{2 + (37 \times (1 + 5))}{(9 \times 4) + 860} & & := \frac{2 \times (3 + (7 + 90))}{(6 \times (1 + 85)) + 4} & & & & \\ & := \frac{2 + (37 - 15)}{94 + (8 - (6 - 0))} & & := \frac{23 + (7 + 90)}{6 \times (1 \times ((8 + 5) \times 4))} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23874}{96015} & := \frac{2 \times (3 - 8 + 74)}{9 \times 60 + 15} \\ & := \frac{237 \times (1 + 5)}{948 \times (6 - 0)} & & := \frac{(23 + 7) \times (9 - 0)}{(6 - (1 - 8)) \times 54} & & & & \\ & := \frac{237 + (1 + 5)}{9 \times (48 + 60)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{65148} & := \frac{2 \times 37 - 9 + 0}{6 \times 5 + 148} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{23897}{41560} & := \frac{2 - (3 - (8 + (9 + 7)))}{4 + ((1 + 5) \times (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{237 - 15}{948 - 60} & & & & & & := \frac{2 + ((3 \times (8 + 9)) - 7)}{(4 \times (1 \times 5)) + 60} \\ & & & & & & & := \frac{2 + (3 + (8^{9-7}))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 0)))} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{23716}{59048} & := \frac{(2 + 3) \times 7 \times (1 + 6)}{5 \times (90 + 4 \times 8)} & & & & & := \frac{(2 \times 38) + (9 + 7)}{4 + (156 - 0)} \\ & & & & & & & := \frac{23 \times (8 - (9 - 7))}{4 \times ((1^5) \times 60)} \\ & & & & & & & := \frac{((2^3) \times 8) + 97}{(4 + 1) \times (56 - 0)} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{23718}{49560} & := \frac{2 \times 37 + 1 - 8}{4 \times (95 - 60)} & & & & & := \frac{2 \times ((3 + 89) \times 7)}{4 \times (1 \times 560)} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{23718}{54069} & := \frac{2 \times (3 + 7 \times 1 \times 8)}{5 \times 40 + 69} & \blacktriangleright \frac{23850}{41976} & := \frac{2^3 - 8 + 50}{4 - 1 + 9 + 76} & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((3 \times 89) + 7)}{(4 - (1 - 5)) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23976}{51840} := \frac{2 + 3 + 9 \times 7 + 6}{5 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2^3 + 97 + 6}{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 9) + 7 + 6}{5 \times 1 \times 8 + 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23985}{61470} := \frac{(2 + 39) \times (8 + 5)}{6^{1 \times 4} + 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24017}{86359} := \frac{2 \times (40 + 1 \times 7)}{86 + 3^5 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24037}{59168} := \frac{2 + 4 + 0 \times 3 + 7}{5 + 9 \times (1 - 6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^4 + 03 + 7}{5 - 9 + 1 \times 68}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 40 + 3 + 7}{59 + 1 + 68}$$

$$:= \frac{24 \times 03 - 7}{5 \times (9 + 1 - 6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 40 \times 3 + 7}{5 - 9 \times (1 - 68)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 40 - 3) \times 7}{(5 + 9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24057}{91368} := \frac{2 + 40 + 57}{9 - 1 + 368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24058}{93617} := \frac{2 + 4 - 0 + 5 \times 8}{9 \times 3 \times 6 + 17}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24063}{75891} := \frac{2^4 + 0 \times 6 - 3}{7 \times (5 - 8 + 9) - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 06 + 3)}{7 - 5 + 8 \times (9 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 40 - 6 + 3}{7 + (5 + 8) \times 9 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (40 - 6) - 3}{(7 + 5) \times (8 + 9) + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 4 \times 06) \times 3}{(7 - 5)^8 - 9 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 40 + 63}{7 + 5 \times 89 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24068}{79315} := \frac{2 + 40 - 6 + 8}{(7 - 9 + 31) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24087}{36519} := \frac{2 \times (4 - 0 + 8) + 7}{3 - 6 + 5 \times (1 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24087}{69153} := \frac{2 + 4 \times (08 + 7)}{6 \times 9 - 1 + 5^3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 4 + 087}{6 \times 9 \times 1 \times 5 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 08) + 7}{6 + 91 - 5 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24138}{65709} := \frac{2 - 4 \times (1 + 3 - 8)}{65 - 7 - 09}$$

$$:= \frac{24 + 138}{6 \times (5 + 70) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24138}{75096} := \frac{2 - 4 \times (1 + 3 - 8)}{7 \times (5 + 09 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 4 + 1 + 38}{7 \times (5 + 09 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{24 + 138}{(75 + 09) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((4 + 1)^3 - 8)}{7 \times (50 + 9 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 4^{13-8}}{7 \times (50 \times 9 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24150}{63798} := \frac{(24 - 1) \times 50}{6 + 379 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24153}{79680} := \frac{2 \times 41 + 5 \times 3}{(7 - 9 + 6) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24168}{39750} := \frac{24 + 16 \times 8}{(3 + 9 - 7) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 41 - 6) \times 8}{(3 \times 9 - 7) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{4+1} + 6) \times 8}{(3 + 97) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24173}{60958} := \frac{2 \times (4 - 1 + 7) + 3}{6 \times 0 \times 9 + 58}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 41 + 7 + 3}{60 \times (9 - 5) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(24 - 1) \times (7 + 3)}{60 \times 9 + 5 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24190}{36875} := \frac{2 \times 41 \times 9 + 0}{3 \times (68 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24198}{36075} := \frac{2 + (4 - 1) \times 9 \times 8}{360 - 7 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24309}{57816} := \frac{2 - 4 + 30 + 9}{5 + 78 - 1 + 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{24 + 309}{5 + 781 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24309}{61758} &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 30 + 9}{6 + (-1 + 7 + 5) \times 8} \\ & \text{-----} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24318}{60795} &:= \frac{((2 \times 4)^3) - 18}{(6 - (-07)) \times 95} \\ &:= \frac{((2^4) + (3 \times 1)) \times 8}{(60 + (7 + 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (4^3 + 1)) + 8}{(6 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (4 + (3 \times 1))) \times 8}{(6^{-07+9}) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 4) \times 318}{6 \times (0 + 795)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (4 - (31 \times 8))}{(60 + (7 \times 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((4 \times 31) + 8)}{60 \times (7 + (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((43 - 1) \times 8)}{60 \times (7 \times (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 - (3 - (1 + 8)))}{60 + ((7 - 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 - (3 - 18))}{(6 \times (0 \times 7)) + 95} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (3 - (1^8)))}{(6 + (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1 \times 8)))}{6 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1^8)))}{6 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (3 + (1 \times 8)))}{(60 - (7 + 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4^{3-1^8})}{6 - (0 - (79 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (3 - (1^8)))}{6 \times ((0 \times 79) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (3 - (1 - 8)))}{60 - ((7 - 9) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (3 \times (1 \times 8)))}{60 + ((7 + 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (3 \times 18))}{(60 + (7 - 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (3 + (1 \times 8)))}{(6 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (31 \times 8))}{60 \times (7 + (9 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (43 + (1 \times 8))}{((6 \times (07)) + 9) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2^{4-3+1^8}}{6 - ((0 \times 7) - (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2^{4-3 \times 1^8}}{(6 \times (0 \times 79)) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + ((4^3 - 1) \times 8)}{(60 \times 7) - 95} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4^{3-1^8})}{(6 \times (0 \times 7)) + (9 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4^{3 \times 1^8})}{((6 \times (07)) - 9) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4 + (3 - (1^8)))}{(6 - (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (43 - (1^8))}{(6 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (43 - (1 + 8))}{6 - (0 - (79 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{24 + 318}{60 + 795} \\ &:= \frac{243 - (1 + 8)}{(6 - (-07)) \times (9 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{38961} &:= \frac{2 \times 45 \times 7 + 0}{38 + 961} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times 5 \times 7 + 0}{(3 + 8)^{9-6} + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{69381} &:= \frac{(2 - 4 + 5) \times 70}{6 \times 9 \times (3 + 8) - 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{83916} &:= \frac{2 + (4 + 5) \times 7 + 0}{8 \times 3 \times 9 \times 1 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - 4) \times (5 - 70)}{(83 - 9 \times 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{86931} &:= \frac{(2 - 4 + 5) \times 70}{8 + 6 + 9^3 \times 1} \\ & \text{-----} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24597}{83106} &:= \frac{2 \times 459 - 7}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06} \\ & \text{-----} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24618}{59307} &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 6 + 18}{5 \times (9 + 3) - 07} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (6 - 1) \times 8)}{5 + 9 \times (30 - 7)} \\ & \text{-----} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{38097} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 6 - 5) + 1}{3 \times 8 + 0 \times 9 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{2^{4+6-5} + 1}{3 \times (80 - 9 \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 46 - 5 + 1}{3 + 8 \times 09 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 - 4 + 6 + 51}{3 + 80 + 9 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 46 \times 5 - 1}{3 \times (8 + 09) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times (65 + 1)}{3 \times (809 + 7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{38907} &:= \frac{2 \times (46 - 5) + 1}{3 + 8 \times (9 + 07)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{60795} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 381}{60 \times (7 + 9) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{67095} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 3^{8-1}}{670 \times 9 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{95760} &:= \frac{2 \times 43 \times (8 + 1)}{(9 - 5) \times 760} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{96750} &:= \frac{2 + 43 + 81}{(9 - 6 + 7) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{90387} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (6 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (0 - ((3 - 8) \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2^{4 \times (6-5)} - 1}{((9 + (-03)) \times 8) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (4 - 6)) \times (5 + 1)}{90 - (3 - (8 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (4 - ((6 \times 5) - 1))}{9 - (0 - (3 + 87))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{4+6-5}) + 1}{90 + (38 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 6) - 5)) + 1}{90 - (3 - (8 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 6) + 5)) - 1}{(9 \times ((03 \times 8))) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{(24 - 6) \times (5 + 1)}{9 - (0 - 387)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + ((46 \times 5) - 1)}{903 - (8 \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4 \times ((6 \times 5) + 1))}{(90 - (3 \times 8)) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2^4) \times ((7 + 1) \times 6)}{30 \times (8 \times (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^4) \times (7 + 16)}{(3 - (0 - 89)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (4 \times (7 + 1))) \times 6}{3 \times (0 + ((8 + 9) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (4 + 7 - 1)) \times 6}{3 + (0 - (8 - 95))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (47 + 1)) \times 6}{(3 - (0 - (8 \times 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((4 - 71) \times 6)}{(30 \times (8 + 9)) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (4 - (7 - (1^6)))}{(3 \times (0 \times 89)) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((4 \times (7 + 1)) + 6)}{(3 \times (0 \times 8)) + 95} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((4 \times (7 + 1)) - 6)}{(30 - (8 + 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((4 \times (7 - 1)) + 6)}{((3 \times (08)) - 9) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((4 + (7 \times 1)) \times 6)}{((3 \times (08)) + 9) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (7 \times (1 \times 6)))}{3 - (0 - (8 \times (9 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (7 + (1 + 6)))}{(3 \times (0 \times 8)) + (9 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (47 + (1 + 6))}{3 \times ((0 \times 8) + (9 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4 + (7 - (1^6)))}{3 - (0 - (8 + (9 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4 + (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(3 - (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times ((7 - 1) \times 6)}{3 \times (0 + (8 \times (9 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times (7 \times 16)}{30 \times (8 \times (9 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times (7 + (1 \times 6))}{30 + (8 \times (9 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{24 \times (71 + 6)}{30 \times ((8 \times 9) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{24 + 716}{30 + 895} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24687}{93051} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 - 6) + 8 \times 7}{(9 + 30) \times 5 + 1} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 4 \times 6 \times (8 - 7)}{93 + 05 \times 1} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + 6 \times 8) \times 7}{9 \times 305 - 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times ((7 - 1) \times 6))}{30 \times (8 + (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7 - (1^6)))}{(3 - ((0 \times 8) - 9)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7 - (1 - 6)))}{30 \times (8 - (9 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7 \times 1^6))}{3 - (0 - ((8 \times 9) - 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24718}{93056} &:= \frac{(2 + 4) \times 7 + 1 + 8}{(9 \times 3 + 05) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 71 + 8}{9 + 305 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{247 + 1 \times 8}{930 + 5 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24705}{86193} := \frac{(-2 + 47) \times 05}{8 \times (6 + 1) + 9^3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7 + (1^6)))}{3 - (0 - ((8 \times 9) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(3 + (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24735}{60819} := \frac{247 + 3 + 5}{608 + 19}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24716}{30895} &:= \frac{((2^{4 \times 7} \times 1) \times 6)}{3 \times (0 + ((8^9) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (7 \times 1))) + 6}{3 - (0 - (8 \times (9 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + 71)) + 6}{(30 \times 8) - (9 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + ((7 - 1) \times 6))}{(3 - (0 - (8 + 9))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (7 - (1^6)))}{3 - (0 - (8 + (9 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (7 - (1 - 6)))}{3 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24759}{30618} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times 7 \times 5 - 9)}{3 \times 06 \times 18} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24759}{61308} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 - 7 + 5 \times 9)}{6^{1 \times 3} - 08} \\ &:= \frac{(2^4 + 7 + 5) \times 9}{6 \times 13 \times 08} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times 9}{6 \times 130 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24769}{80135} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times (7-6) + 9}{(8+01 \times 3) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{31059} := \frac{24 + 786}{(3+1)^{05} - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{31590} := \frac{2+47+8-6}{31 \times 5 - 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{39015} := \frac{2^4 \times 78 - 6}{(390+1) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{95013} := \frac{2-4+7 \times (8-6)}{9+50-13}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7+8) - 6)}{9 \times (50-1-3)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times (7+8) - 6}{9 \times 50 - 13}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (4+7) \times (8-6)}{95 - 01 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4+7 \times (8-6))}{(9 \times 5 + 01) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24790}{36815} := \frac{2 \times (4+7 \times 9) + 0}{3 \times 68 \times 1 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{31806} := \frac{(24+7 \times 9) \times 5}{3 \times (180+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{36801} := \frac{(2 \times 4 - 7) \times 95}{3 \times (6 \times 8 - 01)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{86130} := \frac{2-4+7+9+5}{8+61-3+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+4) \times 7 - 9 + 5}{8-6+130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24831}{56079} := \frac{2+4+83 \times 1}{5 \times 6 \times 07 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24831}{76095} := \frac{2^4 \times 8 - 3 - 1}{(7+60+9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{248+31}{760+95}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4+8+3) + 1}{(7-6) \times 095}$$

$$:= \frac{248 \times (3+1)}{760 \times (9-5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-4+8)^3 + 1}{760-95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24857}{31906} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times 8 + 5) - 7}{3 - 1 + 90 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24857}{39061} := \frac{2 - (4 + (8 \times (5 - 7)))}{(3 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (4 - (8 - 5))) \times 7}{(3 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (8 - (5 - 7)))}{(3 \times (9 - (-06))) - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (4 - (8 + 57))}{3 + (90 + (6 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (4 + (85 + 7))}{3 + (90 + 61)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2+4) \times 8) + 57}{3 \times ((9 \times (06)) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (4 + (8 + 5))) \times 7}{(3 \times 90) - 61}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 4) - (8 - (5 \times 7))}{3 - (9 + (0 - 61))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (4 - (8 - 5))) \times 7}{3 + (9 + ((0 \times 6) - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (4 \times (8 - (5 - 7)))}{3 - (9 \times (0 - (6 + 1)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24875}{36019} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times (8+7) + 5}{3 \times 60 + 1^9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24876}{31095} := \frac{((2^4) \times 8) + 76}{3 \times ((10 \times 9) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^4) \times 8) - 76}{(3 + (1 + 09)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((2+4) \times 8) + 76}{31 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (4 - (8 \times 7))) \times 6}{310 + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (4 - 8)) \times (7 \times 6)}{3 \times (10 + 95)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 8) + 7)) + 6}{((3 \times 10) - 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (8 + 7))) + 6}{(3 - (1 + (-09))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + 8)) + 76}{(3 \times 10) + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 48) + 76}{310 - 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{4 \times (8-7)}) \times 6}{3 \times (10 \times (9-5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^4) \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)}{310 \times (9-5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^4) \times (8 + (7 + 6))}{3 \times (10 \times (9 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^4) + (8 \times (7 + 6))}{3 \times ((1 + 09) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (4 \times (8 + 7))) \times 6}{(3 + (10 \times 9)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (4 \times (8 - 7))) \times 6}{3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (4 - ((8 + 7) \times 6))}{(3 + (10 + 9)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (4 - ((8 - 7) \times 6))}{(3 \times (1 \times (0 \times 9))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (4 - (8 + (7 \times 6)))}{(3 - (1 \times (-09))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (((4 \times 8) + 7) \times 6)}{(3 + 10) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (((4+8) \times 7) - 6)}{(3 \times 10) + 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((4 \times (8+7)) + 6)}{3 \times (10 + (9 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((4 + (8+7)) \times 6)}{3 \times (1 \times (0+95))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((4 + (8-7)) \times 6)}{(3 \times 10) + (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 - (8-76))}{(3 + (1-0)) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (8 + (7-6)))}{(3 - (1-0)) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 \times (8-7)^6)}{(3 - (1^{09})) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 + ((8-7) \times 6))}{(3 \times (1+09)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (8 + (7 \times 6)))}{3 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{4 \times (8-7)^6}}{(3 + (1^{09})) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (((4 \times 8) - 7) \times 6)}{(3 - (1-0)) \times 95}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((4 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6)}{(3 \times (10 \times 9)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (4 + ((8-7) \times 6))}{3 \times (1 - (0 - (9-5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24897}{31605} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 89) + 7}{(3 + 1) \times 60 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24956}{70831} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times 95 - 6)}{708 \times 3 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{31860} := \frac{2 \times (4 - 9) + 57}{3 \times 18 + 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 4 + 95 - 7}{(3 - 1^8) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{36108} := \frac{2 + 4 + 95 - 7}{(3 \times 6 - 1) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{36801} := \frac{2 - (4 - 9) \times 5 \times 7}{3 \times (6 + 80 + 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{68103} := \frac{2 - (4 - 9) \times 5 \times 7}{6 \times (8 \times 10) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24960}{31785} := \frac{2 \times 4^{9-6} + 0}{3 \times 1 \times 7 \times 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24975}{61830} := \frac{(2 - (4 - 9) \times 7) \times 5}{61 \times 8 - 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24986}{70153} := \frac{2 + 4 \times (9 - 8) \times 6}{70 + 1 + 5 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25017}{86349} := \frac{2^5 - 01^7}{8 + 63 + 4 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25034}{87619} := \frac{((2 + 50) \times 3) + 4}{8 \times (7 + ((6 + 1) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 50) \times 3) - 4}{(87 \times 6) + (1 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (5 - (-03))) + 4}{(8 - (7 - 6)) \times (1 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (03))) - 4}{87 - (6 - (1 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 50) + (3 \times 4)}{8 \times (7 \times (6 + (1^9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{5+0 \times 3}) + 4}{(8 \times 7) + (61 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{5+0 \times 3}) - 4}{((8 + 7) \times 6) - (1 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^5 + 0) \times (3 + 4)}{8 \times (7 \times (6 - (1 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 50) \times (3 - 4)}{8 \times (7 + (6 - (1 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (5 \times (0 \times 34))}{8 - (7 - (6 \times (1^9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (5 + (0 - (3 + 4)))}{8 - (7 + (6 - 19))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 \times (03)) + 4)}{(8 - (7 - 6)) \times 19}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 \times 4)))}{(8 \times 7) + ((6 + 1) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 + 4)))}{8 + (76 \times (1^9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 - 4)))}{8 + (7 - (6 - 19))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (0 \times 34))}{87 - (61 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + (0 - (3 - 4)))}{8 + ((7 \times 6) + (1 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (50 + (3 + 4))}{(8 + (7 + 6)) \times 19}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{5-03} \times 4}{8 \times (7 \times (6 + (1 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{5+0 \times 34}}{8 \times (7 + (6 + (1^9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((5 + (-03))^4)}{8 + (7 - (6 \times (1 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 - (0 - (3 + 4)))}{8 - (7 + (6 \times (1 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 - (0 - (3 - 4)))}{8 + (7 + (6 \times (1^9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{25 \times (0 + (3 \times 4))}{(8 + 7) \times (61 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{250 - 34}{(8 + (76 \times 1)) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25079}{84136} := \frac{2 - 50 + 79}{8 \times (4 + 1 \times 3 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{250 + 7 - 9}{841 - 3 - 6}$$

$\frac{25086}{34917} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 08 - 6}{3 \times 4 \times (9 - 1) + 7}$	$\frac{25140}{38967} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 1 + 4) + 0}{(3 - 8 + 9) \times 6 + 7}$ $:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1 \times 4 + 0}{3 + 8 + 9 + 6 \times 7}$ $:= \frac{2^{5+1} - 4 + 0}{3 \times (8 \times (9 - 6) + 7)}$	$\frac{25197}{46308} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 1 + 9 \times 7}{4 + 6 \times (30 - 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 1^9 \times 7}{4 \times (6 + 3 + 08)}$
$\frac{25098}{41736} := \frac{250 - 9 \times 8}{41 \times 7 + 3 + 6}$	$:= \frac{25 \times 1 \times 4 + 0}{38 + 9 \times (6 + 7)}$	$\frac{25197}{80364} := \frac{(25 + 1) \times 9 - 7}{80 \times (3 + 6) + 4}$
$\frac{25098}{71346} := \frac{250 - 9 \times 8}{(7 + 1 + 3) \times 46}$ $:= \frac{250 + 9 + 8}{713 + 46}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times 14 + 0}{3 \times 8 \times 9 - 6 + 7}$	$\frac{25317}{49068} := \frac{(2^5 \times 3 + 1) \times 7}{(4 + 90) \times (6 + 8)}$
$\frac{25130}{97648} := \frac{2^{5 \times 1} + 3 + 0}{(9 - 7) \times 64 + 8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 1 \times 30)}{9 + 7 + (6 - 4)^8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 130}{((9 - 7)^6 + 4) \times 8}$	$\frac{25160}{97384} := \frac{25 + 1 \times 60}{9 + (7 + 3) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\frac{25317}{68094} := \frac{2 + 5 \times (3 + 1) + 7}{6 \times (8 + 09 - 4)}$ $:= \frac{2 + 5 + 3 \times 17}{(6 \times 8 - 09) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{(2^5 - 3) \times (1 + 7)}{6 \times 8 \times (09 + 4)}$
$\frac{25137}{40698} := \frac{2 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 7))}{40 - (6 \times (9 - 8))}$ $:= \frac{2 + (5 \times (1^3 + 7))}{(4 \times ((06 + 9))) + 8}$ $:= \frac{(2 + (5 - (1 - 3))) \times 7}{4 - ((0 \times 6) - 98)}$ $:= \frac{((2 \times (5 + 1)) + 3) \times 7}{(4 - (-06)) \times (9 + 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + 13) \times 7)}{4 \times ((06 \times (9 + 8)))}$ $:= \frac{2513 + 7}{40 \times (6 \times (9 + 8))}$ $:= \frac{((2 + (5 - 1))^3) \times 7}{(40 - 6) \times (9 \times 8)}$	$\frac{25164}{37890} := \frac{2 \times 51 + 6^4}{3^7 + 8 - 90}$ $\frac{25194}{38760} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 19) + 4}{38 + 7 \times 6 + 0}$ $:= \frac{25 + (1 + 9) \times 4}{3 \times 8 + 76 + 0}$ $:= \frac{(2 + 5 - 1) \times (9 + 4)}{(3 - 8 + 7) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{2 + 5 \times (19 + 4)}{3 \times (8 - 7) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 1) \times (9 + 4)}{(3 + 8 - 7) \times 60}$	$\frac{25317}{68904} := \frac{2 \times (53 - 1) - 7}{6 \times (8 + 9 \times 04)}$ $\frac{25317}{69840} := \frac{2 + 5 \times (3 + 1) + 7}{(6 + 9) \times 8 - 40}$ $:= \frac{2 + 5 + 3 \times 17}{(6 + 9) \times 8 + 40}$ $:= \frac{253 + 1 + 7}{(6 + 9) \times (8 + 40)}$
$\frac{25137}{86940} := \frac{(25 + 13) \times 7}{(8 + 6 + 9) \times 40}$	$\frac{25194}{67830} := \frac{2 + 5 + 1 + 9 - 4}{6 + 7 - 8 + 30}$ $:= \frac{2 + 5 - (1 - 9) \times 4}{67 + 8 + 30}$ $:= \frac{(2 + 5 - 1) \times (9 + 4)}{6 \times 7 \times (8 - 3) + 0}$ $:= \frac{(25 + 1) \times 9 \times 4}{(6 + 78) \times 30}$	$\frac{25340}{78916} := \frac{25 \times 3 - 40}{7 + (8 + 9 \times 1) \times 6}$ $:= \frac{25 \times (3 + 4) + 0}{7 - 8 + 91 \times 6}$
	$\frac{25194}{76038} := \frac{25 \times 1 \times 9 - 4}{7 + 60 \times (3 + 8)}$	$\frac{25380}{64719} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 3 + 8) + 0}{6 \times (4 + 7 - 1) - 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{25384}{61790} &:= \frac{(2+5+3) \times 8 - 4}{6+179+0} & \frac{25413}{80967} &:= \frac{254+1+3}{809+6+7} & & \frac{(2+54) \times (9 \times 6)}{3 \times (18 \times 70)} \\ & & & & & \frac{(2+54) \times (9-6)}{3 \times ((1^8) \times 70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25389}{40176} &:= \frac{2 \times (5-3+89)}{(40+1+7) \times 6} & & & & \frac{(25+4) \times 96}{(3+1) \times 870} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25389}{64701} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3 - 8 + 9}{6+4+70-1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{25467}{39180} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4-6) + 7}{3+9+1 \times 8+0} & & \frac{2 - ((5 \times 4) - (9 \times 6))}{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2+5+3 \times 8) \times 9}{6+4+701} & &:= \frac{2+5+4+67}{39+1+80} & & \frac{2 - (5 - (4 + (9 - 6)))}{3 + (1 + (8 - (7 - 0)))} \\ & & &:= \frac{2 \times (5^4 + 6 - 7)}{3 \times (9 - 1) \times 80} & & \frac{2 - (5 - (49 + 6))}{3 - (1 \times (8 - 70))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25398}{47061} &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (3+9) + 8)}{4 \times (70 - 6 - 1)} & &:= \frac{2 \times 54 \times (6+7)}{3 \times 9 \times 1 \times 80} & & \frac{2 - (5 \times ((4-9) \times 6))}{3 + (187 - 0)} \\ & & &:= \frac{2 \times (5-4) \times (6+7)}{39+1^8+0} & & \frac{2 - (54 - 96)}{3 - (18 - 70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25408}{63917} &:= \frac{2+54+08}{6 \times (3 \times 9 + 1) - 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{25467}{80319} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4-6) + 7}{8 \times (03+1) + 9} & & \frac{2 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 9)) + 6)}{31 \times (8 + (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{2^5 \times 4 + 0 \times 8}{(6+39+1) \times 7} & &:= \frac{(2 \times 5 + 4) \times 6 + 7}{8 + 031 \times 9} & & \frac{2 \times (5 - (4 - (9 - 6)))}{3 + ((1^8) \times (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^5 + 40) \times 8}{(6^3 - 9 \times 1) \times 7} & &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4) \times (6+7)}{(80+3-1) \times 9} & & \frac{2 \times (5 + (4 + (9 + 6)))}{3 + (1 + (8 \times (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2+54) \times 08}{(6 \times 3 \times 9 - 1) \times 7} & &:= \frac{2 \times (5-4) \times (6+7)}{80+3-1^9} & & \frac{2 \times (5 + (4 + (9 - 6)))}{31 - (8 - (7 - 0))} \\ & & & & & \frac{2^{5-4+9-6}}{(3 \times (1+8)) - (7-0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{73689} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4+1) + 0}{7+3 \times (6+8) + 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{25496}{31870} &:= \frac{((2^5) - 4) \times (9 \times 6)}{3 \times ((1+8) \times 70)} & & \frac{2^{5+4-9+6}}{3 - (1 - (8 + 70))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (4-1) + 0}{7-3-6+89} & &:= \frac{(2 - (5 - (4 + 9))) \times 6}{3 \times (18 + (7 - 0))} & & \frac{2 + ((5 - 4) \times (9 \times 6))}{(3 - (1 - 8)) \times (7 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4 \times 1 + 0}{7 \times 3 + 6 + 89} & &:= \frac{(2 \times 54) + 96}{(31 \times 8) + (7 - 0)} & & \\ &:= \frac{2+5+4-1+0}{(7-36) \times (8-9)} & &:= \frac{(2^5) - (4 \times (9-6))}{((3+1) \times 8) - (7-0)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{25608}{73914} := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 6 - 08)}{7+3 \times (9+1) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4) \times 10}{(7+3+6 \times 8) \times 9} & &:= \frac{(2^5) \times ((4 \times 9) + 6)}{3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 70))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{25608}{91374} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6 - 08}{9+1 \times 37 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{93786} &:= \frac{2+54-1+0}{9 \times 3 \times 7 + 8 + 6} & &:= \frac{(2^5) \times (4 + (9 - 6))}{(3 + (1^8)) \times 70} & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{98736} &:= \frac{(25-4) \times 10}{9 \times (87+3) + 6} & &:= \frac{(2 + (5 - (4 - 9))) \times 6}{3 + (1 \times (87 - 0))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{25640}{37819} := \frac{(2+5-6) \times 40}{3+7 \times 8 \times 1^9} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (56 + 4) + 0}{3 \times 7 \times 8 \times 1 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 5) \times 6 \times 40}{3 \times (7 + 819)}$$

$$:= \frac{(25 - 6) \times 40}{(3 + 7 \times 8) \times 19}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25641}{90783} := \frac{2 + 5 + 6 \times (4 + 1)}{(9 + 07) \times 8 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25647}{89301} := \frac{(25 - 6) \times 4 + 7}{(8 + 9)^{3-01}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25697}{40381} := \frac{25 - (6 - (9 - 7))}{(4 \times ((0 \times 3) + 8)) + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 - ((6 - 9) \times 7))}{4 \times ((03 + (8 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((5 \times 6) - (9 \times 7))}{((4 - (-03)) \times 8) - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 56) - (9 \times 7)}{40 + (38 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (56 - (9 - 7))}{4 - (0 - (3 + 81))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (5 - 6)) \times (9 \times 7)}{((40 - 3) \times 8) + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (5 + (6 - (9 + 7)))}{4 - ((0 \times 3) - (8 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^5) - (6 - 9)) \times 7}{4 - (0 - 381)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 5) \times (6^{9-7})}{403 - (8 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + (6 + 9)) \times 7)}{40 \times (3 + (8 \times 1))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{31689} := \frac{(2^5 + 70) \times 4}{(3 - 1)^6 \times 8 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{39168} := \frac{2^5 - 7 - 04}{3 \times (9 - 1^6) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 5 + 70 - 4}{(3 + 9 \times 1^6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 5) \times (70 - 4)}{(3 + 91 - 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{63189} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 70 - 4}{(6^3 - 1) \times 8 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{81396} := \frac{(2 \times 5 - 7) \times 04}{8 - (1 + 3 - 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 + 7 + 04}{(8 - 1^3) \times 9 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{25 + 7 + 04}{(8 - 1 + 3 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(25 - 7) \times 04}{81 \times 3 - 9 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times 7 + 04)}{(8 - 1)^3 - 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{83916} := \frac{(2 \times 5 + 7) \times 04}{8 \times 3 \times 9 \times 1 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{96831} := \frac{(2^5 + 70) \times 4}{(9 - 6) \times 8^3 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25709}{48136} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 70) - 9}{4 \times (8 + 1 \times 3) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25714}{60398} := \frac{25 \times 7 + 1 - 4}{6 + 0398}$$

$$:= \frac{257 + 1^4}{6 \times (03 + 98)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^5 + 7 + 1 \times 4}{6 - 03 + 98}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25740}{69381} := \frac{2^5 \times 7 - 4 + 0}{6 \times 9 \times (3 + 8) - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25740}{86931} := \frac{2^5 \times 7 - 4 + 0}{8 + 6 + 9^3 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25760}{93184} := \frac{25 \times 7 - 60}{(9 + 3 + 1) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2^5 \times 7 + 6 + 0}{(9 \times 3 - 1) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25783}{96140} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 7 - 8 - 3}{(9 \times 6 + 1) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (7 \times 8 + 3)}{(9 \times 6 + 1) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25803}{64719} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8 \times 03}{(6 + 4 \times 7 \times 1) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25806}{43197} := \frac{2^5 + 8 + 06}{4 + 3 + (1 + 9) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times 8 + 06}{(4 + (3 - 1) \times 9) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25806}{73491} := \frac{2^5 + 8 + 06}{(7 + 3) \times (4 + 9) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{69741} := \frac{(((2 \times 5) + 8) \times 30)}{(6 \times (9 \times ((7 \times 4) - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(((2 \times 5) - 8) \times 30)}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (4 \times 1))))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 - (5 - 8)) \times 30)}{((6 + 9) \times ((7 \times 4) - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^5) \times (8 \times 30))}{((6 \times (9 - 7))^{4 \times 1})}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^5) + (8 + 30))}{((((6 \times 9) - 7) \times 4) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^5) + (8 - 30))}{(6 + (9 + (7 + (4 + 1))))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 58) \times (3 - 0))}{6 \times 9^{7-4-1}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - (5 - (83 - 0)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (4 - 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((5 \times 8) + 30))}{(6 \times (((9 + 7) \times 4) - 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 \times (3 - 0))))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 + (4 + 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 + (3 - 0))))}{(6 + (97 \times (4 - 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 + (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(6 \times (((9 - 7) \times 4) + 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5 + (83 - 0)))}{(((6 \times 9) + 7) \times 4) - 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (58 - 30))}{(69 + (7 + (4 + 1)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{74169} &:= \frac{2^5 + 8 + 30}{7 \times (4 + 1) \times 6 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{97416} &:= \frac{2 - 5 + 8 + 30}{97 + 41 - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{2^5 + 8 + 30}{(9 + 7 \times (4 + 1)) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25836}{71049} &:= \frac{(2^5) + (8 - 36)}{7 - (1 - (0 - (4 - 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - (5 - (8 - (3 - 6)))}{7 + (10 - (4 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 + (8 + (3 - 6)))}{7 - (10 - (4 \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{5+8-3-6}}{7 + (1 - (0 - (4 \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 + (8 + (3 - 6)))}{7 - (1 + (0 - 49))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 + (8 + (3 + 6)))}{7 + (10 + 49)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 5) + ((8 \times 3) - 6)}{((7 + 10) \times 4) + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{25 + (8 - (3 - 6))}{(7 - (1 \times (-04))) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{710 - (4 - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{258 + (3 \times 6)}{710 + 49} \\
 &:= \frac{(25 + (8 + 3)) \times 6}{((7 \times 10) - 4) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + 8) \times (3 \times 6))}{((7 - (1 - 0))^4) - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25839}{40716} &:= \frac{2 + 58 - 3 \times 9}{4 \times (07 + 1 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (8 \times 3 + 9)}{40 \times (7 + 1 \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25839}{61074} &:= \frac{2 - 5 \times (8 - 3 - 9)}{6 \times (1 + 07) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + 58 - 3 \times 9}{6 \times (10 + 7 - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{25 + 8 \times (3 + 9)}{6 + 10 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25890}{67314} &:= \frac{(2^5) - (8 + (9 - 0))}{(6 + 7) \times (3 \times (1^4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 + 8)) + (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7) \times (3 + (1 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 5) \times 8) + (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7)^{3-1^4}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7) \times (31 - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (8 + (9 - 0)))}{(6 \times (73 \times 1)) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 5) - 8) \times 90}{6 \times (73 + (1 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 8) + 90)}{673 - (1 - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25893}{60417} &:= \frac{(((2 + 5) \times 8) + 9) \times 3}{(60 + (4 + 1)) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 + 5) \times 8) - 9) \times 3}{(6 - (0 - 41)) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^5) - 8) \times (9 \times 3)}{(6^{04-1}) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (5 - 8)) \times (9 - 3)}{(6 - (0 - (4 \times 1))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 - (8 - 9))) + 3}{(6 + ((0 \times 4) - 1)) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9))) + 3}{((60 \times 4) + 1) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9))) - 3}{((60 \times 4) - 1) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{5-8+9}) \times 3}{(60 + (4 \times 1)) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5 - (8 - 9))) \times 3}{60 - (4 \times (1^7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 58) \times (9 + 3)}{60 \times (4 \times (1 \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - 5) \times (8 - (9 \times 3))}{(60 - 41) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((5 - (8 - 9)) \times 3)}{60 - (4 \times (1 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (8 - (9 + 3)))}{6 \times ((0 \times 41) + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (8 - (9 - 3)))}{(6 + (0 - (4 \times 1))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((5 \times (8 + 9)) + 3)}{6 \times (0 + ((4 + 1) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((5 \times 8) + (9 \times 3))}{((6 \times (04)) - 1) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 \times (8 - (9 - 3)))}{60 - (4 \times (1 + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 \times (8 + (9 - 3)))}{6 \times (0 + (4 \times (1 \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5^{8-9+3})}{(6 - (0 - (4 - 1))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 + (8 - (9 + 3)))}{(6 \times (0 \times 41)) + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 + (8 - (9 - 3)))}{(6 + (0 - (4 - 1))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 + (8 + (9 - 3)))}{(6 - ((0 \times 4) - 1)) \times 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 + 893)}{60 \times ((4 + 1) \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (58 - (9 \times 3))}{(6 - (0 - (4 + 1))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (58 - (9 - 3))}{6 \times (0 + (4 + 17))}$$

$$:= \frac{2589 + 3}{6041 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{258 - 93}{(60 - (4 + 1)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{2589 - 3}{6041 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25896}{47310} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times (8 + 96)}{(4 + 7)^3 - 1 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25916}{73408} := \frac{25 \times 9 - 16}{(-7 + 3^4) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25917}{30846} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9 \times 17}{30 \times 8 - 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25917}{40863} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9 \times 17}{40 \times 8 - 63}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25930}{67418} := \frac{(2^5) - (9 \times (3 - 0))}{6 - (7 + (4 - 18))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^5) - (9 + (3 - 0))}{(6 \times (7 + (4 - 1))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (5 + 9)) - (3 - 0)}{(6 \times (7 + 4)) - (1^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 9) - 30)}{6 \times ((7 \times (4 - 1)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{(6 + 7) \times (4 + (1 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (5 - (93 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (4 \times (1 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 + (93 - 0))}{(67 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 0)))}{(6 + 7) \times ((4 - 1) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 9) + 30)}{6 + ((7 + 41) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (5 - 9)) \times 30}{(6 + 7) \times (4 \times (1 + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25938}{47160} := \frac{2 + 5 \times (9 + 3 - 8)}{4 + (7 - 1) \times 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (9 + 3 \times 8)}{(4 + 7 - 1) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{25 \times 9 \times (3 + 8)}{(4 + 71) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 9) - 3 + 8}{(4 + 7 - 1) \times 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2^5 \times (9 + 3 \times 8)}{4 \times (7 + 1) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 59 + 3) \times 8}{(4 + 7) \times 160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25947}{31806} := \frac{(2 - 5 + 9) \times 4 + 7}{(3 + 1) \times 8 + 06}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 \times (9 - 4 + 7)}{3 - 1 + 80 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25963}{74180} := \frac{2 + (5 - (9 - (6 + 3)))}{7 + (4 + (1 + (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((5 \times (9 - 6)) - 3)}{7 + (41 - (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 - (9 - (6 \times 3)))}{(7 + (4 - 1)) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((5 \times 9) + (6 + 3))}{(7 - (4 + 1)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + 9) \times (6 - 3))}{(7 - (4 \times 1)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 - 5) \times 9) + (6^3)}{(7 - 4) \times 180}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + ((9 \times 6) - 3))}{(7 - (4 - 1)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{((25 \times 9) + 6) \times 3}{(7 + 4) \times 180}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (5 \times (9 \times (6 \times 3)))}{(7^4) - (1 + 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{259 \times (6 \times 3)}{74 \times 180}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + 9) \times 63)}{7 \times (4 \times 180)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times 59) - 6) \times 3}{(7 + (4 + 1)) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25973}{60148} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 9) + 7 + 3}{(6 + 01 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 5 + 9 \times 7 - 3}{6 \times (014 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 9 \times 7) - 3}{60 \times (1 + 4) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (9 + 7 + 3)}{(60 - 1 - 4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{30186} := \frac{25 + 9 + 7 - 4}{30 - 1 + 8 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 + 9 \times 7 + 4}{3 \times 0 \times 1 + 86}$$

$$:= \frac{259 - 74}{301 - 86}$$

$$:= \frac{25 \times 9 - 7 + 4}{3 \times 01 \times 86}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 5 \times 9) \times 7 + 4}{301 + 86}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{38610} := \frac{25 + 9 + 7 - 4}{3 - 8 + 6 \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 5 + 9 \times 7 \times 4}{386 - 1 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(2+59) \times 74}{(3+8) \times 610} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times 59 - 7) \times 4}{(3+8) \times 6 \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{63180} & := \frac{25+9+7-4}{6+3+1+80} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (5+9) \times 74}{63 \times 1 \times 80} \\ & := \frac{25 \times 9 - 7 + 4}{(6-3) \times 180} \\ & := \frac{(2+5) \times 9 \times 74}{63 \times 180} \\ & := \frac{(2+5+9) \times 74}{6^{3-1} \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{83106} & := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 97 - 4)}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{25986}{47031} & := \frac{2 \times (5 + 9 \times 8 - 6)}{47^{-03} + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26015}{97438} & := \frac{2 \times (60 - 1 \times 5)}{(97 \times 4) + (3 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26019}{37485} & := \frac{2 \times (60 - 1^9)}{3 + 7 + 4 \times 8 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26047}{31598} & := \frac{2^6 + 04 - 7}{3 - 1^5 + 9 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26071}{54839} & := \frac{(-2+6) \times 07 + 1}{5 + 4 \times (8 - 3 + 9)} \\ & := \frac{2^6 - 07 + 1}{5^4 - 8^3 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26104}{59738} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 104}{(5+9+7^3) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{26130}{97485} := \frac{2-6+1 \times 30}{9+7-4+85} \\ & := \frac{26 \times 1 \times 3 + 0}{(9+7 \times 4) \times 8 - 5} \\ & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 130}{97 \times (4+8) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 13 + 0}{97 + 485} \\ & := \frac{2+6 \times 1 \times 30}{9 \times 74 + 8 + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26190}{38475} & := \frac{2 \times (6+1+90)}{3 \times (8+4+7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26190}{43875} & := \frac{2 \times (6+1+90)}{(4^3 + 8 - 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26190}{48735} & := \frac{2 \times (6+1+90)}{4 - 8 + 73 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26307}{51948} & := \frac{2 \times (6+30) + 7}{(5-1+9) \times (4+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26145}{38097} & := \frac{2 \times (6+14) - 5}{3 \times (80 - 9 \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{2 + (6+1-4)^5}{3 \times (8+09) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26145}{79380} & := \frac{2 \times (61 \times 4 + 5)}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26145}{90387} & := \frac{2 \times (6+14) - 5}{90 + 38 - 7} \\ & := \frac{2 + (6+1-4)^5}{903 - 8 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26150}{39748} & := \frac{26 - 1^5 + 0}{3 + 9 \times (7 - 4) + 8} \\ & := \frac{2 \times ((6-1) \times (5-0))}{3 - (9 - (74+8))} \\ & := \frac{26 - (1 - 50)}{3 + ((9 \times 7) + 48)} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (6 \times (1 \times 50))}{(3 + (9 + 7)) \times 48} \\ & := \frac{(2 + (6 \times 1)) \times 50}{(3 + (9 + 7)) \times (4 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(2^{6-1}) \times 50}{39 + ((7^4) - 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26394}{57081} & := \frac{2 \times (6+3) \times 9 + 4}{5 \times 70 + 8 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26394}{87150} & := \frac{2+6 \times (39-4)}{(8+7-1) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{2 + (6+3) \times 94}{8 \times 7 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26481}{59073} & := \frac{2+6+4 \times 8-1}{5+9+073} \\ & := \frac{2^6 - 4 - 8 \times 1}{5+90+7 \times 3} \\ & := \frac{26 \times (4+8-1)}{5+90 \times 7+3} \\ & := \frac{26 \times (48-1)}{5+907 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26491}{58370} & := \frac{2^6 + 4 - 9 \times 1}{(5+8) \times (3+7) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26549}{30178} & := \frac{265+4+9}{301+7+8} \end{aligned}$$

<hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> <p>► $\frac{26574}{89301} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 5 \times 7) + 4}{(8 + 9)^{3-01}}$</p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> <p>► $\frac{26580}{49173} := \frac{(2-6) \times 5 + 80}{(4 \times 9 + 1^7) \times 3}$</p> $:= \frac{(2+6) \times 5 + 80}{(4 + (9+1) \times 7) \times 3}$ $:= \frac{2-6 \times (5-8) + 0}{4 \times (9+1^7) - 3}$ $:= \frac{2+6 \times 5 + 8+0}{4+91-7 \times 3}$ $:= \frac{2+6 \times (5+8) + 0}{491-7^3}$ <hr style="width: 20%; margin-left: 0;"/> <p>► $\frac{26709}{53418} := \frac{((2 \times 6) - (7-0)) \times 9}{(5-3) \times 41 + 8}$</p> $:= \frac{(2^6) - (7-0) \times 9}{(53+4) \times 18}$ $:= \frac{((2+6) \times (7-0)) + 9}{5 \times (34 - (1 \times 8))}$ $:= \frac{((2+6) \times (7-0)) - 9}{5 + ((3^4 \times 1) + 8)}$ $:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (7-0))) \times 9}{(5 - (3-4)) \times (1+8)}$ $:= \frac{(2 - (6+7)) \times (-09)}{((5 \times 3) - 4) \times 18}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (6 - (7-0))) + 9}{5 + (3 \times (4 - (1^8)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7-0))) + 9}{5 \times (3 + (4 - (1-8)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7-0))) - 9}{5 - (3 - (4 \times (1 \times 8)))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times 6) - (7 - (0 \times 9))}{5 + ((3 \times 4) + (1-8))}$ $:= \frac{(2^6) - (7 - (-09))}{(5 + (3 + (4 \times 1))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(2^6) + (7 - (-09))}{(5 + (3 \times (4 + 1))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{(2 + (6 - (7 - 0))) \times 9}{5 + ((3 \times 4) + (1^8))}$ $:= \frac{(2+6) \times (7 - (0 \times 9))}{(5 + (3 \times (4 - 1))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{(2+6) \times (7 - (-09))}{(5 + (3^{4-1})) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{(2+6) \times (70-9)}{((5^3) - (4-1)) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{(26 - (7-0)) \times 9}{((5 \times 3) + 4) \times 18}$ $:= \frac{(2-6) \times (7 \times (-09))}{((5+3)^{4-1}) - 8}$ $:= \frac{2 - ((6 - (7-0)) \times 9)}{5 + (3 - (4 - 18))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{5 - (3 - (4 \times (1^8)))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 - (7 - (-09)))}{5 - (3 - (4 + 18))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 - (70 + 9))}{5 \times ((3 \times 4) + 18)}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 - (70 - 9))}{(5^3) - (4 - (1 - 8))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (7 \times (0 \times 9)))}{5 + (3 - (4 \times (1^8)))}$ $:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (7 + (-09)))}{5 + ((3 \times (4 + 1)) + 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((6 \times (7-0)) + 9)}{(53 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((6^7 + 0) \times 9)}{(5 - (3 - 4)) \times (1 + 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((6 - 7) \times (-09))}{5 + (3 - (4 \times (1 - 8)))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (6 - (7 + (-09)))}{5 + (3^{4-1^8})}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times (7 - (-09)))}{(53 - (4 + 1)) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(5 \times (3 \times (4 \times 1))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 - (-09)))}{(5 + (3 + (4 - 1))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 + (-09)))}{5 - (3 + (4 - 18))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (67 - (-09))}{(5 + (34 - 1)) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2^{-6+7} \times 0^9}{(5 + (3 \times 41)) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2^6 + 7 \times 0 \times 9}{(5 + ((3 \times 4) - 1)) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2^{6-7+0^9}}{(5+3)^{4-1^8}}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(5 \times (3 - 4)) - (1 - 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 - (7 + (-09)))}{5 + (3 \times (4 + (1^8)))}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{5 + (3 + (4 + 18))}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 - (-09)))}{(5 - (3 - (4 \times 1))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 + (-09)))}{5 + (3 + (4 \times (1^8)))}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 + (70 + 9))}{(5^3) + (41 + 8)}$ $:= \frac{2 + (6 + (70 - 9))}{(5^3) + (4 + (1 + 8))}$ $:= \frac{2 + (67 + (-09))}{5 + ((3 \times 41) - 8)}$ $:= \frac{26 - (7 - (0 \times 9))}{5 + (3 \times (4 - (1 - 8)))}$ $:= \frac{26 - (7 \times (-09))}{(5 \times (34 \times 1)) + 8}$ $:= \frac{26 - (7 + (-09))}{(5 - (3 - (4 + 1))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{26 \times (70 \times 9)}{((5+3)^{4+1}) - 8}$ $:= \frac{26 + (7 - (0 \times 9))}{53 + (4 + (1 + 8))}$ $:= \frac{26 + (70 + 9)}{5 \times (34 + (1 \times 8))}$
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$$:= \frac{267 - (0 \times 9)}{534 \times (1^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{267 - (-09)}{534 + 18}$$

$$:= \frac{267 \times (09)}{534 \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{267 + (-09)}{534 - 18}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((6 - 7) \times 10)}{9 - (3 + (4 - (8 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 - (3 - (4 - (8 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (7 + (1 - 0)))}{9 - ((3 + (4 - 8)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (7 - 10))}{9 - (3 - (4^{8-5}))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 0))}{(93 \times 4) - 85}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{((9 + (3 + 4)) \times 8) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{9 - ((3 - (4 \times 8)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (7 + (1 - 0)))}{(9 + (34 - 8)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 - (3 - (48 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 \times 10))}{(9 + (3 \times 4)) \times (8 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26710}{93485} := \frac{(2 - (6 - 7)) \times 10}{(9 - (3 \times (4 - 8))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (6 \times 7)) + 10}{(9 \times (3 \times (4 + 8))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 67) + 10}{9 \times (3 + (48 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (6 + 7)) \times 10}{(9 + (3 \times (4 \times 8))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (6 - 7)) \times 10}{((9 + 3) \times 4) - (8 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 6) \times (7 - (1 - 0))}{9 + (3 \times (48 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(26 - 7) \times 10}{(9^3) - (4^{8-5})}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 - (7 - 10))}{(9 + (3 \times 4)) \times (8 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 - (3 \times (4 - 85))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 + ((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9 \times 3) + (4^{8-5})}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (7 - 10))}{9 + (3 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{6+7-10}}{(9 \times 3) + (4 - (8 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((6 \times 7) + 10)}{9 \times (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (7 + (1 - 0)))}{9 + (3 + (4 + (8 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{26 \times (7 + (1 - 0))}{(9^3) - (4 - (8 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{267 - (1 - 0)}{934 - (8 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26730}{49815} := \frac{26 - 7 + 3 + 0}{49 - 8 \times 1^5}$$

$$:= \frac{267 - 3 + 0}{498 - 1 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 6 \times 7) \times 3 + 0}{(49 - 8) \times (1 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26730}{84159} := \frac{(2 + 6 \times 7) \times 30}{8^4 + 1 + 59}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26730}{98415} := \frac{26 - 7 + 3 + 0}{9 \times (8 - 4 + 1 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 67 - 3 + 0}{9 \times (8 + 4 + 15)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 6 \times 7) \times 3 + 0}{9 \times (8 + 41 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(26 + 7) \times 30}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 6 \times 73 + 0}{9 \times (8 + 4) \times 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26784}{35910} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 4}{35 \times (9 + 10)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26785}{30194} := \frac{2 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 5}{30 - (1 - 9) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 5)}{30 + 1 \times 94}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26790}{31584} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 7 + 90}{(31 + 5 - 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26790}{35814} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 7 + 90}{3 \times (5 \times 8 + 1) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26793}{84501} := \frac{2 + (6 - 7 + 9) \times 3}{8 \times 4 + 50 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 6) \times 7 \times 9 + 3}{8 \times 4 \times 50 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{26 \times (7 + 93)}{8 \times (4^5 + 01)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26809}{37145} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 80 - 9}{(37 - 14) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26815}{74390} := \frac{2 \times (68 - 1 - 5)}{74 + 3 \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 6 + 8 + 15}{74 + 3 + 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26871}{35490} := \frac{2 \times (68 \times 7 + 1)}{35 \times 4 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26871}{43095} := \frac{2 - 6 + 8 \times 7 + 1}{4 + 3^{09-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (68 \times 7 + 1)}{(4 + 30) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26890}{45713} := \frac{2 \times (6 + (8 - (9 - 0)))}{4 + (5 + (7 + (1^3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((6 - 8) \times (9 - 0))}{4 - (5 \times (7 - 13))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (8 \times (9 - 0)))}{4 \times ((5 \times 7) - (1^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 - (8 - 90))}{(4 \times (5 \times 7)) + 13}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times 6) + 8) \times 90}{45 \times (71 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (6 - 8)) \times 90}{(4 + 5) \times (71 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (8 + 90))}{(4^5) - (7 \times (1 \times 3))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26894}{31075} := \frac{2 + (68 - 9) \times 4}{310 - 7 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2^6 \times 8 - 9 \times 4}{(3 + 107) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26901}{34587} := \frac{(2 \times 6) - (9 \times (-01))}{3 \times (4 + (5 \times (8 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 + (-01)))}{((3 + 4) \times 5) + (8 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{26 - (9 \times (-01))}{3 - (45 - 87)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (9 \times (-01)))}{3 \times (4 \times (5 + (8 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (90 \times 1))}{34 + (5 + 87)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (69 - (-01))}{3 \times (45 + (8 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 690) - 1}{3 \times (4 + 587)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (69 + (-01))}{3 - (4 - ((5 + 8) \times 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26907}{53814} := \frac{((2^6) - (9 - 0)) \times 7}{5 \times ((3 + 8) \times 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^6) \times (9 - 0)) + 7}{53 \times (8 + 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^6) + 90) \times 7}{(538 + 1) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 6) \times (9 - 0)) - 7}{53 + (81 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (9 - 0))) \times 7}{5 \times (3 + (8 - (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (6 - (9 - 0))) + 7}{5 + (3 + (8 - 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (9 - 0))) - 7}{(5^3) + (81 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 6) - (9 - (0 \times 7))}{5 - (3 - (8 - (1 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 6)^{9-07}}{(5 + 3) \times ((8 + 1) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 6) + (9 - (0 \times 7))}{5 - (3 - (8 \times (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 6) + (90 - 7)}{5 \times (38 \times (1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) - (9 - (-07))}{(5 + 3) \times (8 + (1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) - (9 + (-07))}{(5 \times (3 \times (8 \times 1))) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) \times (9 - (-07))}{(5 - 3)^{8+1} \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) \times (9 + (-07))}{(5 - 3)^8 \times 1^4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6)^{9-07}}{(5 - 3) \times (8 \times 1 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) + (9 + (-07))}{(5^3) + (8 - (1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^6) + (90 + 7)}{((5 \times 3) + 8) \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (6 - 9)) \times (-07)}{5 + (3 - (8 - 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 6)^{9+0 \times 7}}{(5 - 3)^{8-1} \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((6 - (9 - 0)) \times 7)}{(5 \times (3 + (8 - 1))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 - (3 - (8 \times (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (9 - (-07)))}{5 - (3 - (8 + 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (90 + 7))}{(5 \times (38 \times 1)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (90 - 7))}{((5 - 3) \times 81) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 \times 7)))}{5 + (3 - (8 - (1 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 \times (9 \times (-07)))}{5 \times (38 \times 1 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (6 + (9 \times (-07)))}{(5^3) - (8 - (1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((6 \times (9 - 0)) + 7)}{5 + ((3 \times 81) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((6 \times 90) + 7)}{5 + ((3^8-1) - 4)}$$

$:= \frac{2 \times ((6 + (9 - 0)) \times 7)}{5 \times (3 \times ((8 - 1) \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (9 + (-07)))}{5 + (3 \times (8 + (1 - 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(2^6) \times (9 + (1 - 0))}{7 \times ((5 + 3) \times (4 \times 8))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((6 + (9 - 0))^{7})}{((5 \times 3)^{8-1}) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (90 + 7))}{5 \times (38 + (1 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (6 \times 9)) \times 10}{(7^{5-3}) \times (4 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 - (9 + (-07)))}{5 + (3 + (8 \times (1^4)))}$	$:= \frac{26 - (9 \times (0 \times 7))}{(5 \times (3 + 8)) + (1 - 4)}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (6 + 9)) \times 10}{7 \times ((5 \times (3 \times 4)) + 8)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{((5 \times (3 + 8)) - 1) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{26 \times (9 - (0 \times 7))}{((5^3) - (8 \times 1)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 6) \times (9 + (1 - 0))}{7 \times ((5 + (3 - 4)) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times (9 - (-07)))}{((5 \times 3) + 81) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{26 \times (9 + (-07))}{(5 + (3 \times (8 - 1))) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(26 \times 9) + (1 - 0)}{7 \times (5 + ((3^4) + 8))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 \times (3 + (8 + 1^4))}$	$:= \frac{26 + (9 + (-07))}{(5 \times (3 + (8 + 1))) - 4}$	$:= \frac{(26 + 9) \times 10}{((7 + 5) \times (3^4)) + 8}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 - (-07)))}{(5 + 3) \times (8 - (1 - 4))}$	$:= \frac{269 - (0 \times 7)}{538 \times (1^4)}$	$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (9 \times (1 - 0)))}{7 - (5 + (3 \times (4 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (90 - 7))}{(5 + (3 + 81)) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{269 + 07}{538 + 14}$	$:= \frac{2 - (6 - (9 + 10))}{7 + (5 \times (3 - (4 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (69 + (-07))}{5 + (3^{8+1-4})}$	$:= \frac{269 - 07}{538 - 14}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (6 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}{7 \times ((5 - (3 - 4)) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{2^6 + 9 \times 0 \times 7}{(5 + (3 \times (8 + 1))) \times 4}$		$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 \times (1 - 0)))}{7 \times (5 + (3 - (4 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2^{6-9+07}}{5 + (3 \times (8 + 1^4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{43875} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 9 - 10}{(4 - 3) \times (8 + 7) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 + 10))}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 + 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2^{6+9-07}}{(5 - 3)^{8+1^4}}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 69 \times 1 + 0}{(4 + 3 + 8)^{7-5}}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 - 10))}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2 + ((6 \times (9 - 0)) - 7)}{((5 \times 3) - 8) \times 14}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{47385} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 9 - 10}{4 \times 7 \times 3 - 8 + 5}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (69 + (1 - 0))}{7 \times (5 + (3 + 48))}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6 - (9 + (-07)))}{5 + (3 + (8 - (1 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 69 \times 1 + 0}{4^{7-3} - 8 - 5}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((6 \times 9) - (1 - 0))}{((7 - 5) \times (3^4)) - 8}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{(5 + ((3 \times 8) - 1)) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{58374} := \frac{2^6 - 9 + 10}{5 + 8 \times (3 \times 7 - 4)}$	$:= \frac{26 + (9 \times (1 - 0))}{7 \times (5 - (3 - (4 + 8)))}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (9 + (-07)))}{5 + ((3 \times (8 + 1)) - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{75348} := \frac{((2 \times 6) + 9) \times 10}{(7^{5-3}) \times (4 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{26 + (9 + 10)}{75 + (3 + 48)}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6 \times (90 - 7))}{(5^3) \times (8 \times (1^4))}$	$:= \frac{((2^6) - 9) \times 10}{7 \times ((53 \times 4) + 8)}$	$:= \frac{26 + (9 - 10)}{7 + ((5 \times 3) + 48)}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6^{9-07})}{((5 + 3) \times (8 + 1)) + 4}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + 9)) + 10}{(7 - (5 - (3 \times 4))) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{87354} := \frac{26 \times (9 + 1) + 0}{8 \times 7 \times 3 \times 5 + 4}$
$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 - (3 - (8 \times 1 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + 9)) - 10}{7 + (53 + (4 - 8))}$	
$:= \frac{2 + (6 + (9 - (-07)))}{5 + (3 + (8 \times (1 + 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(2^6) - (9 - 10)}{7 + (5 \times (3 + (4 \times 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26930}{45781} := \frac{2 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 0}{4 \times 5 + 7 + 8 - 1}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 \times (6 + 9) + 30}{45 + 7 \times 8 + 1} \\ & := \frac{2^6 + 9 - 3 + 0}{45 - 7 + 81} \\ & := \frac{(2 - 6 + 9) \times 30}{4^{5+7-8} - 1} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{26937}{50184} & := \frac{2 \times (69 - 3 + 7)}{(50 + 18) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26937}{84501} & := \frac{2 \times (69 - 3 + 7)}{8 + 450 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26937}{85410} & := \frac{2^6 + 93 + 7}{(8 + 5) \times 4 \times 10} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{26970}{41385} & := \frac{2 + 6 + 9 \times 70}{41 \times 3 \times 8 - 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{26973}{51840} & := \frac{26 + 973}{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{26978}{35014} & := \frac{(2 - 6) \times (9 - 7 \times 8)}{3^5 + 01^4} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (6 \times 9 - 7) \times 8}{(3^5 + 01) \times 4} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{26980}{37145} & := \frac{(2 - 6) \times (9 - 80)}{371 + 4 \times 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{36594} & := \frac{2 + 70 - 1 + 8}{3 \times 6 - 5 + 94} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{56943} & := \frac{2 \times (70 + 1 + 8)}{5 \times 69 - 4 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{63954} & := \frac{2 + 70 - 1 + 8}{6^3 - 9 - 5 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 \times (70 + 1 + 8)}{6 - (3 - 95) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{65493} & := \frac{2 \times (70 + 1 + 8)}{6 + 5 + 4 \times 93} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{94563} & := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (-01))) + 8}{(9 \times (4 + 5)) + (6 - 3)} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (7^{01})) - 8}{9 + (4 + (5 + (6 - 3)))} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (-01))) + 8}{(9 - 4) \times (5 + (6 + 3))} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (70 \times 1)) - 8}{9 + (456 - 3)} \\ & := \frac{(2 + (7 - 0)) \times 18}{9 \times (4 + (56 + 3))} \\ & := \frac{(2 - 7) \times (0 - (1 \times 8))}{(9 + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 3} \\ & := \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 \times 18))}{9 - (4 - (5 - (6 - 3)))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (1 \times 8)))}{(9 - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 \times 18))}{94 - (5 \times (6 + 3))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 + 8)))}{9 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 3)))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 + 18))}{945 - 63} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 + (0 - (1^8)))}{(9 + (4 - (5 - 6))) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 8)))}{94 - (5 - (6 + 3))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (70 - (1^8))}{(9 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 3} \\ & := \frac{2^{7-01^8}}{9 + (4 - (5 - (6^3)))} \\ & := \frac{2 + ((7 - (-01)) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((4 \times 5) + 6)) - 3} \\ & := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (1^8)))}{94 - (56 + 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (1 + 8)))}{9 - (4 + (5 - 63))} \\ & := \frac{2 + (7 + (0 - (1^8)))}{9 + (4 + (5 \times (6 - 3)))} \\ & := \frac{2 + (70 + 18)}{94 + (5 + (6^3))} \\ & := \frac{2 + (70 - 18)}{9 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 3)))} \\ & := \frac{27 - (0 - (1 + 8))}{9 + ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 3)} \\ & := \frac{27 + (0 - (1^8))}{94 + ((5 - 6) \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{270 \times (1 + 8)}{945 \times (6 + 3)} \\ & := \frac{270 \times 18}{945 \times (6 \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{270 + 18}{945 + 63} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{27034}{59861} & := \frac{2 \times 7 + 0 \times 34}{5 \times (9 - 8) \times 6 + 1} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (7 + 03 + 4)}{5 + 9 + 8 \times 6 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{2 + (7 + 03) \times 4}{5 \times 9 + 8 \times 6 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{2 \times 7 \times (0 \times 3 + 4)}{5 + (9 + 8) \times (6 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{2^7 + 03 \times 4}{5 \times (9 - 8 + 61)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{27051}{64389} & := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 05 + 1}{6 \times 43 - 89} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27051}{83496} & := \frac{2^{7-0 \times 5-1}}{8 \times (34 + 9 + 6)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{69138} & := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 54))}{6 + (9 + ((1^3) \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (1^3))) - 8} \\
 := \frac{27 - (0 \times 54)}{6 - (9 \times ((1^3) - 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 5))) \times 4}{6 + (91 + (3 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - 7) \times (0 - (5 + 4))}{6 + ((9 \times 13) - 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (70 + (5 + 4))}{69 + 138} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 70) \times (5 + 4)}{69 \times (1 \times (3 \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2^7 + 0) - (5 \times 4)}{6 \times (9 - (1 - 38))} \\
 := \frac{270 - 54}{69 \times ((1^3) \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{27 \times ((05 + 4))}{69 \times (1^3 + 8)} \\
 := \frac{270 - (5 + 4)}{691 - (3 \times 8)} \\
 := \frac{270 \times (5 - 4)}{6 \times (91 + (3 \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{270 + 54}{69 \times (1 + (3 + 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{91683} := \frac{2 + 7 + 05 + 4}{9 + 1 + 6 \times 8 + 3} \\
 := \frac{270 - 54}{9^{1-6+8} + 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{93186} := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 54))}{9 + (((3 - 1) \times 8) + 6)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{((9 - (3 - 1)) \times 8) + 6} \\
 := \frac{27 - (0 \times 54)}{9 - (3 - (1 + 86))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (5 \times 4)))}{93 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (70 + (5 + 4))}{93 \times (1 + (8 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 70) \times (5 + 4)}{93 \times (18 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{270 - 54}{(9^3) + (1 + (8 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{27 \times ((05 + 4))}{(9^3) + (18 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 70) \times 54}{9 \times (31 \times (8 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{270 + 54}{93 \times (18 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{27 \times (054)}{9 \times (3 \times 186)} \\
 \frac{27063}{45198} := \frac{2 + (70 - 6) \times 3}{4 - 5 \times (1 - 9) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27063}{51894} := \frac{2 + (70 - 6) \times 3}{(5 - 1 + 89) \times 4} \\
 \frac{27064}{89351} := \frac{270 + 6 - 4}{893 + 5 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27069}{54138} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 6) \times 9}{5 \times ((4 \times (1 \times 3)) + 8)} \\
 := \frac{((2 \times (7 - 0)) - 6) \times 9}{((5 \times (4 - 1)) + 3) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{((2 - 7) \times (-06)) + 9}{54 + (1 \times (3 \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{((2 - 7) \times (-06)) - 9}{54 - (1 + (3 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - (7 - 0)) \times (6 - 9)}{5 + (4 + (13 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 6))) - 9}{5 + (4 + ((1^3)^8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (-06))) + 9}{5 \times (4 - (1 - (3 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (-06))) - 9}{5 + (4 + (1 + (3 \times 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (06))) - 9}{5 \times (41 - (3 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 - 0)) + (6 \times 9)}{(5 + (4 \times (1 \times 3))) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (7 - 0)) + (6 + 9)}{(5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 38} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (7 - (-06))) \times 9}{54 \times (13 - 8)} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (7 + (-06))) \times 9}{54^{1^{38}}} \\
 := \frac{(2 + (7 - 0)) \times 69}{(5 + 4) \times 138} \\
 := \frac{(27 - (-06)) \times 9}{54 \times (1 \times (3 + 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - 7) \times (0 - (6 \times 9))}{5 \times (4 + (13 \times 8))} \\
 := \frac{(27 \times (06)) + 9}{(5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 38} \\
 := \frac{(2 - 70) \times (6 - 9)}{(54 - (1 \times 3)) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(270 + 6) \times 9}{((5^4) - (1 + 3)) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2 - ((7 + (-06))^9)}{5 - (4 - ((1^3)^8))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 \times ((0 \times 6) - 9))}{((5 + 41) \times 3) - 8} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 - (6 \times 9)))}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times 38))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 \times 69))}{5 + (4 + (1 \times (3 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 + ((0 \times 6) - 9))}{5 + (4 - ((1^3)^8))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 9)))}{5 + (4 + (1 \times (3 + 8)))} \\
 := \frac{2 - (7 + (0 - 69))}{((5 \times 4) - (1 + 3)) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2 - (70 \times (6 - 9))}{(54 - (1^3)) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((7 + (-06)) \times 9)}{(5 \times (4 + 1)) + (3 + 8)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times ((70 - 6)^9)}{(5 + (41 \times 3))^8}
 \end{array}$$

$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - ((0 \times 6) - 9))}{(5 + (4 - (1^3))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 - (4 + (1 - (3 \times 8)))}$	$:= \frac{((2 + 70) \times 9) - 3}{5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 86)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (6 + 9)))}{(5 + (4 - (1 - 3))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 - (6 + 9))}{(5^{4-1}) - (3 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{((2 - 7) \times (-09)) + 3}{5 + (4 + (1 + 86))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 + (4 - ((1^3) - 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 + (6 - 9))}{5 + (((4 + 1)^3) + 8)}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times (-09))) \times 3}{5 \times ((4 \times 18) + 6)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 \times 69))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1^3))) + 8}$	$:= \frac{27 - ((0 \times 6) - 9)}{(5 + (4 \times (1^3))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (-09))) \times 3}{5 + (4 + (1 + (8 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - 69))}{(5 + (4 - 1)) \times 38}$	$:= \frac{27 - (0 - 69)}{(5 + (4 - 1)) \times (3 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (-09)))^3}{(5 \times 4) + (18 \times 6)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 9))}{(5 \times (4 \times 13)) - 8}$	$:= \frac{27 \times ((0 \times 6) + 9)}{54 \times (1^3 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 9))) + 3}{(5 \times (4 \times 1)) + (8 + 6)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 + (41 + 38)}$	$:= \frac{27 + (0 - (6 - 9))}{5 \times (4 + ((1^3) \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 9))) - 3}{5 + (4 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 9)))}{5 \times (4 \times (13 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{270 - (6 \times 9)}{54 \times ((1^3) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (-09))) + 3}{((5 + (4 - 1)) \times 8) + 6}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 - (4 - (1 + 38))}$	$:= \frac{270 - (6 - 9)}{541 - (3 - 8)}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (-09))) - 3}{5 + (4 + (1 + (8 \times 6)))}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (70 - (6 + 9))}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (3 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{270 + (6 \times 9)}{54 \times (1 + (3 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (09))) - 3}{(5 + (4 \times (1 + 8))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (70 + (6 - 9))}{(5 \times (4 \times 13)) + 8}$	$:= \frac{270 + (6 + 9)}{5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 38)}$	$:= \frac{(2 \times 70) - 93}{5 + (4 - (1 - 86))}$
$:= \frac{2^{7-06} \times 9}{(5 + (41 \times 3)) \times 8}$		$:= \frac{(2^{7+0 \times 9}) + 3}{((5 - (4 - 1))^8) + 6}$
$:= \frac{2^{7+06-9}}{5 + (4 - (1 - (3 \times 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27081}{46359} := \frac{2 + 7 \times 08 + 1}{4 \times (6 \times 3 + 5) + 9}$	$:= \frac{(2^{7+0 \times 9}) - 3}{(5^{4-1}) \times (8 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{2^7 + 0 \times 69}{(5 - (4 - (1^3)))^8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27081}{93456} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (08 - 1)}{(9 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{(2^7 + 0) \times (9 - 3)}{((5 - (4 - 1))^8) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 + ((7 + (-06)) \times 9)}{5 - (4 - (13 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 70 + 81}{(9 + 3) \times 4 \times (5 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{(2^7 + 0) + (9 + 3)}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 + 6)))}$
$:= \frac{2 + ((7 + (-06))^9)}{5 - (4 + (1 \times (3 - 8)))}$		$:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 3}{(5 + (4 \times (1^8))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 9)))}{5 + (4 + (1 + 38))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27084}{53619} := \frac{2 \times (70 + 8 - 4)}{5 - 36 \times (1 - 9)}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (-09))) \times 3}{(5 + (4 + (1 + 8))) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 - (4 - (1 \times (3 + 8)))}$		$:= \frac{(2 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 + 3)}{(54 - 18) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 69))}{5 + (4 + (1^3 + 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27093}{54186} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 9) \times 3}{((5 \times (4 - 1)) + 8) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (7 - 0)) \times 93}{(5 + 4) \times 186}$
$:= \frac{2 + (7 \times (0 - (6 - 9)))}{5 + (4 - (1 - 38))}$	$:= \frac{((2 + (7 - 0))^9) \times 3}{((5 + 4) \times (1 + 8)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{(2 + (70 \times 9)) \times 3}{((5^4) - (1 - 8)) \times 6}$

$:= \frac{(2 + (70 + 9)) \times 3}{(5 + 4) \times ((1 + 8) \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 \times 3)))}{54 \times (1 \times (8 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{27 \times (0 + (9 + 3))}{54 \times (18 - 6)}$
$:= \frac{(2 + (70 - 9)) \times 3}{54 \times ((1^8) + 6)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 - 3)))}{((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 8) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{27 \times (0 + (9 - 3))}{(5 + (41 + 8)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(2 - 7) \times (0 - (9 \times 3))}{(5 + ((4 + 1) \times 8)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2^{7+0 \times 9-3}}{5 + (41 - (8 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{27 + ((0 \times 9) - 3)}{5 - (4 + (1 - (8 \times 6)))}$
$:= \frac{(27 \times (09))^3}{54 \times ((1 + 8)^6)}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((7 - (-09)) \times 3)}{(5 + (4 + 1))^{8-6}}$	$:= \frac{270 + (9^3)}{(5 + (41 \times 8)) \times 6}$
$:= \frac{(27 \times (09)) + 3}{(54 \times (1 + 8)) + 6}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (9 \times 3)))}{((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{270 - 93}{5 \times 4 \times 18 - 6}$
$:= \frac{(27 \times (09)) - 3}{5 \times (4 \times (18 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (9 + 3)))}{((5 \times (4 - 1)) - 8) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{2709 + 3}{5418 + 6}$
$:= \frac{2 - ((7 \times (0 \times 9)) - 3)}{5 + (4 + (1^{86}))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (9 - 3)))}{5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2709 - 3}{5418 - 6}$
$:= \frac{2 - ((7 + (-09)) \times 3)}{5 - (4 - (1 + (8 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 93))}{(5 + (4 \times 1)) \times (8 - 6)}$	
$:= \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 - (9 + 3)))}{(5 - (4 - 1)) \times 86}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{5 + (4 + (1 + (8 - 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27094}{36518} := \frac{27 + 0 \times 9 - 4}{3 + 6 \times (5 + 1) - 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 3)))}{5 - (4 - (1 + 86))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (0 - (9 - 3)))}{5 + (4 - (1 + (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 09 - 4}{3 \times (6 \times 5 + 1^8)}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 \times (0 \times 93))}{5 - (4 - (1 + (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 - (9 \times 3))}{5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 70 - 94}{(3 + 6) \times (5 + 1) + 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 3)))}{5 + (41 - (8 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 - (9 + 3))}{5 \times (4 \times ((1^8) \times 6))}$	
$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 3)))}{5 - (4 + (1 - (8 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 - (9 - 3))}{5 + (41 + 86)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27135}{89640} := \frac{(2 + 7 + 1)^3 + 5}{(89 - 6) \times 40}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (0 - (9 - 3)))}{5 - (4 - (1^{86}))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 + (9 \times 3))}{(5 - (4 \times (1 - 8))) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27135}{94068} := \frac{2 - 7 + 1 \times 35}{(9 + 4 + 0 \times 6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 - (70 - 93)}{5 - (4 - (1 + (8 \times 6)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 + (9 - 3))}{((5 + 4) \times 18) - 6}$	$:= \frac{2 - 7 + 13 \times 5}{9 \times 4 \times 06 - 8}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times (09)) - 3)}{5 \times (4 \times (18 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (70 + 93)}{5 \times ((4 \times 18) - 6)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 1 + 3) \times 5}{9 \times 40 - 6 \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{27 - ((0 \times 9) - 3)}{5 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(2 + 7 \times 1) \times 3 \times 5}{9 \times (4 + 06 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 3)))}{54 - (1 \times (8 - 6))}$	$:= \frac{27 - (0 - (9 + 3))}{((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8) + 6}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 1) \times 3 \times 5}{(9 + 4) \times 06 \times 8}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 \times 93))}{(5 - (4 - 1)) \times (8 + 6)}$	$:= \frac{27 - (0 - (9 - 3))}{(5 \times (4 + (1 \times 8))) + 6}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 1) + 3^5}{(9 + 4) \times 068}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - 93))}{(5 \times (4 \times 1))^{8-6}}$	$:= \frac{27 \times ((0 \times 9) + 3)}{(5 + (4 + 18)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27135}{96480} := \frac{2 \times (7 - (1 \times (3 - 5)))}{96 - (4 \times (8 - 0))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{2 + (7 + (13 + 5))}{(9 - 6) \times (4 \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{2 - 7 + 1 + 68}{3 + 90 - 5 + 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27306}{49815} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 30) \times 6}{4 - 9 + 815} \\
 &:= \frac{27 + (1 + (3 + 5))}{96 + (4 \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{(27 + 1 + 6) \times 8}{390 + 5 - 4} & \\
 &:= \frac{27 + (1 + 35)}{(9 \times (6 \times 4)) + (8 - 0)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{59430} := \frac{2^{7-1+6-8}}{(5 \times (9 + 4)) - 30} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27309}{54618} := \frac{((2 \times 7) + (3 - 0)) \times 9}{(54 \times 6) - 18} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (71 + (3 + 5))}{9 \times ((6 \times 4) + (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (1^6))) \times 8}{5 \times (9 - (4 - 30))} &:= \frac{((2 + 7) \times 30) - 9}{(5 + (4 \times 6)) \times 18} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 \times 1)) \times (3 \times 5)}{(9 + 6) \times (4 \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 - (1^6)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times 4)) + 30} &:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times 3)) \times (-09)}{(54 \times 6) + 18} \\
 &:= \frac{27 + 135}{96 + 480} &:= \frac{2 - (71 \times (6 - 8))}{5 \times (9 \times (4 + (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - 3)) \times (-09)}{5 + ((4 \times 6) - (1 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + 1) \times (3 \times 5)}{(96 + 4) \times (8 - 0)} &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 16) - 8)}{5 \times (94 - (3 - 0))} &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - 30)) \times 9}{5 \times ((4 + 6) \times (1 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{27 + (1 \times (3^5))}{(9 - 6) \times (4 \times 80)} &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 + 1) \times (6 \times 8))}{(5 + 9) \times (4 \times 30)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (3 - 0))) + 9}{(5 \times 4) + (6 + (1 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (1 + 35)}{96 \times (4 + (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (1 \times (6 \times 8)))}{((5 \times 9) + 4) \times 30} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (3 - 0))) + 9}{(5 \times (4 \times 6)) - 18} \\
 &:= \frac{27 \times (1 \times (3 \times 5))}{9 \times ((6 - 4) \times 80)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - 1)) - 6) \times 8}{5 \times (9 + (4 \times (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (3 - 0))) - 9}{54 - (6 - 18)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - 1))^3) \times 5}{96 \times (4 \times 80)} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) + 9}{(5 \times (4 + (6 \times 1))) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 - (1 + 3))^5)}{9 \times (6 \times (4 \times (8 - 0)))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27189}{35640} := \frac{(2^7 - 1) \times 8 - 9}{3 \times (5 + 6) \times 40} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) - 9}{5 + (4 + (6 - (1 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (1 - (3 - 5))}{9 \times (6 \times (48 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27189}{36450} := \frac{(2^7 - 1) \times 8 - 9}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{2 \times 7^{3+0 \times 9}}{((5^4) + 61) \times 8} \\
 & &\blacktriangleright \frac{27189}{40356} := \frac{2 \times 71 + 8 + 9}{4 \times (03 + 56)} &:= \frac{(2 \times 7) + (30 - 9)}{5 - (4 - (61 + 8))} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27160}{58394} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 1 + 6 + 0}{58 - 3 \times (9 - 4)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27189}{43605} := \frac{2^{7+1^8} + 9}{(4 + 3) \times 60 + 5} &:= \frac{(2^{7-3+0}) + 9}{5 \times (4 + (6 \times (1^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 7 + 1) \times 6 + 0}{5 - (8 - 39) \times 4} & &:= \frac{(2^7) - (3 - (-09))}{(5 + (4 \times (6 \times 1))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 1) \times 60}{(5 \times 8 + 3) \times 9 \times 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27195}{64380} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 1 \times (9 + 5)}{6 \times 4^3 + 80} &:= \frac{(2^7) + (3 - (0 \times 9))}{(54 \times (6 - 1)) - 8} \\
 & &\blacktriangleright \frac{27195}{84360} := \frac{2 + 7 - (1 - 9) \times 5}{8 + 4 \times 36 + 0} &:= \frac{(2^7) + (3 - (-09))}{5 \times (4 \times (6 + (1 \times 8)))} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{39054} := \frac{2^{7-1+6-8}}{3 \times 9 + 0 \times 5 - 4} & &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (3 - 0))) \times 9}{(5 \times (4 \times (6 - 1))) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{7+1 \times 6-8}}{3 \times (9 + 05) + 4} &\blacktriangleright \frac{27306}{48951} := \frac{2^7 + 30 + 6}{4 \times 8 \times 9 + 5 + 1} &:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (3 - 0))) \times 9}{(5 + 4) \times (6 + 18)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(2 + (7 + 30)) \times 9}{54 \times (6 - (1 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (3 - (-09)))}{(5 \times 4) + ((6 + 1) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{27 \times (3 - (-09))}{((5 \times 4) + 61) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (3 \times (09))}{(5 + 4) \times (6 \times (1 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (30 - 9))}{(5 \times (4 \times (6 \times 1))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{27 + (3 - (-09))}{5 + (4 + (61 + 8))}$
$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (30 - 9)}{54 \times (6 + (1^8))}$	$:= \frac{2^{7-3+0 \times 9}}{(5 + (4 - (6 - 1))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{273 - (0 \times 9)}{546 \times (1^8)}$
$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times 309}{(5 + 4) \times 618}$	$:= \frac{2^7 + 3 \times 0 \times 9}{(5 + (4 - (6 + 1)))^8}$	$:= \frac{273 - (-09)}{546 + 18}$
$:= \frac{(27 - (3 - 0)) \times 9}{(54 - 6) \times (1 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{2^{7+3-09}}{5 + (4 - (6 - (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{273 \times (09)}{546 \times (1 + 8)}$
$:= \frac{(2 - 7) \times (3 \times (-09))}{5 \times (46 + (1 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 9)}{(5 - (4 - (6 + 1))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{273 + (-09)}{546 - 18}$
$:= \frac{(27 \times (3 - 0)) + 9}{5 \times ((4 \times (6 + 1)) + 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 + ((7^3 + 0) - 9)}{54 + 618}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{(27 + (3 - 0)) \times 9}{(54 + 6) \times (1 + 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{5 + (4 - (6 - (1 + 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27318}{65940} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 3) + 1 + 8}{65 + 9 - 4 + 0}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 - (3 - (-09)))}{5 + (4 + (6 - (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (3 \times (0 \times 9)))}{((5 - 4)^6) \times 18}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 73 - 1^8}{6 \times 59 - 4 + 0}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 - (30 + 9))}{(5 \times (4 + 6)) + 18}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (3 \times (-09)))}{((5 + 4) \times 6) + 18}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (3 \times (-09)))}{5 + (46 + (1 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (3 + (-09)))}{5 \times (4 - (6 - (1 \times 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27354}{60819} := \frac{273 + 5 + 4}{608 + 19}$
$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (3 + (-09)))}{5 + (4 - (6 + (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 \times (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{((5 + 4) \times (6 \times 1)) - 8}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 9)}{5 \times (4 \times (6 \times (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{5 + (4 + (6 + (1 + 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27360}{41895} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 3 + 6) + 0}{4 + (18 - 9) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 0)) - 9)}{(5 - (4 - (6 - 1))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (3 - (-09)))}{(5 \times (4 + (6 \times 1))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 3 + 60)}{(41 + 8) \times (9 - 5)}$
$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 + (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{5 \times ((4 + (6 - 1)) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (3 + (-09)))}{5 - (4 - (6 - (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{(27 - 3) \times 60}{(41 + 8) \times 9 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{5 + (4 + (6 + (1^8)))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (30 + 9))}{54 - (6 \times (1 - 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27360}{51984} := \frac{2^{7-3} - 6 + 0}{5 + 1 + 9 + 8 - 4}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (3 \times (0 \times 9)))}{5 + ((4 \times 6) - (1^8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (30 - 9))}{5 \times ((4 \times (6 - 1)) - 8)}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 3 + 6) + 0}{5 + 1^9 + 8 \times 4}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (3 + (-09)))}{5 + (46 + (1^8))}$	$:= \frac{2 + (73 + (-09))}{(5 \times (4 \times (6 + 1))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 3 - 6) + 0}{5 \times 1 \times 9 + 8 + 4}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (3 \times (09)))}{54 \times (6 + (1 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{27 - (3 \times (0 \times 9))}{5 - (4 - (61 - 8))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27360}{91485} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 3 + 6) + 0}{(9 + 1 + 4) \times 8 - 5}$
$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{54 - (6 + (1 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{27 \times (3 - (0 \times 9))}{54 + (6 \times 18)}$	<hr/>

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27390}{45816} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 3) + 90}{4 \times (5 \times 8 \times 1 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 39 + 0}{4 - (5 - 81) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - 7 + 390}{4 + 5 \times 8 \times 16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27391}{58604} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (3 + 9 \times 1)}{(5 \times 8 + 6) \times 04}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27401}{39856} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 - 4 + 01}{3 - 9 - 8 + 5 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 4 \times 01)}{3 - 9 + 8 + 5 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 74 + 01}{3 + 98 + 5 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{2^7 + 4 \times 01}{(3 - 9 + 8)^5 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 - 7 + 401}{(3 + 98 - 5) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27405}{81693} := \frac{2 \times (740 - 5)}{8 + 1 \times 6 \times 9^3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27405}{86913} &:= \frac{(2 - 7 + 40) \times 5}{8 \times 69 \times 1 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 7 + 40) \times 5}{86 \times 9 \times 1 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (40 - 5)}{86 + 913} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27405}{96831} &:= \frac{2 - 7 + 4 \times 05}{9 + 6 \times 8 - 3 - 1} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 4 + 0 \times 5}{96 + 8 + 3 - 1} \\ &:= \frac{(-2 + 7 + 4) \times 05}{9 + 6 \times (8 \times 3 + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27450}{86193} := \frac{(2 + 7 - 4) \times 50}{8 \times (6 + 1) + 9^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27450}{91683} := \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4) \times 5 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 6) \times 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27451}{86039} := \frac{27 + 4^{5-1}}{860 + 3 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27458}{96103} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times 4) - 5)) + 8}{9 + (6 \times (10 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (4 - 5))) + 8}{(9 \times 6) + (10 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (4 - 5))) + 8}{9 + (61 - (0 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 7) + ((4 \times 5) + 8)}{(9 \times (6 + 10)) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 7) + ((4 - 5) \times 8)}{9 - (6 \times (1 + (-03)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 74) - (5 \times 8)}{9 \times (6 \times (10 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^7) + ((4 \times 5) + 8)}{(9 \times (61 - 0)) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (7 - 4)) \times 58}{9 + (6 + (10^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 7) \times (4 \times (5 - 8))}{(9 + (61 - 0)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (7 - (4 - (5 - 8)))}{9 - (6 - (1 - (-03)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (7 + (4 - (5 + 8)))}{9 + (6 - (10^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - ((4 - 5) \times 8))}{(9 + 6) \times (10 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (4 + (5 - 8)))}{(9 + (6 - (1 - 0))) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 - (5 - 8)))}{96 - (1 + (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((7 - 4) \times 58)}{9 + (610 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (4 - (5 + 8)))}{9 \times (6 + (10^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (7 - (4 + (5 - 8)))}{9 + (6 + (10 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (7 + (4 - (5 - 8)))}{(9 \times 6) - (1 + (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (74 - (5 \times 8))}{96 + (10 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27459}{30618} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 45) + 9}{3 \times 06 \times (-1 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27459}{81360} := \frac{2 + (7 + (4 + (5 + 9)))}{8 \times (1 + (3 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times (4 - 5))) \times 9}{(8 - (1 + 3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (4 + 5))) \times 9}{8 \times ((1^3) \times 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5) \times 9}{(8 + (1 + 3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^7) + (4^5)) \times 9}{(8 \times (1 \times 3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 \times 59))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 \times 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times ((4^5) \times 9)}{(8 \times (1 + 3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 45) + 9)}{8 \times ((1 + 3) \times 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{27 \times (45 - 9)}{8 \times (1 \times 360)}$$

$$:= \frac{27 \times (4 + 59)}{(81 + 3) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27459}{83106} := \frac{(27 \times 4 + 5) \times 9}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27485}{69310} := \frac{27 \times 4 - 85}{6 \times 9 + 3 + 1 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27486}{50391} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (4 - 8))) + 6}{50 - ((3 \times 9) + 1)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - ((7 \times (4 - 8)) + 6)}{5 - (0 - (39 \times 1))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 \times (8 - 6)))}{5 \times ((03 + (9 - 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - (4 + 8))) \times 6}{50 + (3 \times (9 \times 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8)) + 6}{5 - (0 - (3 + 91))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 - (8 - 6)))}{5 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{7-4}) - (8 - 6)}{5 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{27 \times (4 \times (8 - 6))}{5 - (0 - 391)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - 4)) \times (8 \times 6)}{5 \times (0 - (3 - 91))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + 4)^{8-6}}{503 + 91} \\ &:= \frac{2^{7+4-8} \times 6}{50 + (39 - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{30186} := \frac{(2 \times 7 \times 4 - 9) \times 5}{3 \times 01 \times 86}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{36801} := \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4 + 9) \times 5}{3 \times (6 + 80 + 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{38610} := \frac{2 + (7 + 49) \times 5}{386 + 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{63180} := \frac{2 - 7 + 4 + 95}{6^{3 \times 18} + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 7 \times 4 - 9) \times 5}{(6 - 3) \times 180}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^7 + 4 + 9) \times 5}{(6 + 3) \times 180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{68103} := \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4 + 9) \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 10 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27501}{94863} := \frac{2 + 7^{5-01}}{9^4 + 8 \times 6^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27508}{39146} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 50 + 8)}{3 - 91 \times (4 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 5 + 08}{3 \times 9 + 14 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{40698} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (5 - 3 + 1)}{40 - 6 \times (9 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 5 \times 3 + 1)}{4 \times (06 + 9) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{49680} := \frac{2 + 7 + 5^3 - 1}{(4 \times 9 - 6) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 5^3 + 1)}{4 \times (9 + 6) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)}{4 \times (9 - 6) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((7 + 5)^3 + 1)}{(4 + 9) \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{64980} := \frac{2^7 \times 5 + 3 + 1}{(6 + 4 + 9) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{86940} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (5 + 3) - 1}{86 + 94 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 5 + 3 \times 1)}{8 \times 6 \times (9 - 4) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 75 \times (3 - 1)}{8 \times (6 + 9) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 75 \times 3 + 1}{(8 - 6) \times 9 \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{96048} := \frac{2 + 7 + 5^3 - 1}{(9 \times 6 + 04) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 5^3 + 1)}{960 - 4 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27540}{39168} := \frac{27 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{3 \times (9 - 1 - 6)^8}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{(39 - 1 - 6) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{27 \times (5 + 40)}{(3 + 9)^{1-6+8}}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times (5 + 40)}{(3 + 9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27540}{81396} := \frac{(2 \times 7 - 5) \times 40}{8 \times (139 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{30618} := \frac{2 + 7 \times 5 + 9 \times 4}{(3 + 06) \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^7 + 5 + 9 + 4}{3 \times 06 \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 7 \times (5 - 9 \times 4)}{3^{06-1^8}}$$

$$:= \frac{(27 + 5) \times 9 + 4}{3 \times 06 \times 18}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{38106} := \frac{2 - 7 - 5 + 94}{(3 + 8) \times 10 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 7 + 5 \times 9 \times 4}{3 \times (81 + 06)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - 75 + 94}{3 \times 8 - 1 + 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{83160} := \frac{2 - 7 \times (5 - 9 \times 4)}{(8 + 3 \times 1) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27639}{41085} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (6 + 3) + 9}{(4 + 10 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6 + 3 \times 9}{(41 - 08) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27648}{31590} := \frac{2^7 \times (6 - 4) \times 8}{(31 - 5) \times 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27648}{35910} := \frac{2^{7+6+4-8}}{35 \times (9 + 10)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27654}{93018} &:= \frac{27+6 \times (5-4)}{93+018} & & & & & & & & := \frac{2+7+(8-6)^3}{9+01+45} \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27693}{81450} &:= \frac{2+76-9 \times 3}{(8-1-4) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+(7+6+9) \times 3}{8 \times (1+4) \times 5+0} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7+6 \times 9)-3}{(8-1^4) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times (6+9))-3}{(8+1 \times 4) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 7+69 \times 3}{(8+1+4) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{27 \times (6 \times 9-3)}{(8+1) \times 450} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27804}{91356} &:= \frac{2+7+8+04}{9+1+3+56} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2-7+8+04}{9+1 \times 3+5+6} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 7+8 \times 0 \times 4}{(9-1^3) \times 5+6} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{34695} &:= \frac{27 \times 8-10}{(34-6) \times 9+5} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{43569} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8 \times 1)+0}{4 \times (3+5+6)-9} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+7+81+0}{4 \times 3 \times (5+6)+9} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{54693} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8 \times 1)+0}{5-(4-6) \times 9 \times 3} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+7+81+0}{(5 \times (4+6)+9) \times 3} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2^7-8 \times 1+0}{5 \times 46+9-3} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{(2^7-8) \times 10}{5 \times (469+3)} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{35406} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 8-1^9)}{35 \times (4-0 \times 6)} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 8+1+9)}{3 \times 54+06} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{64053} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 8 \times (1+9)}{6^4-05+3} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{65340} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 8 \times (1+9)}{(6+5) \times 3 \times 40} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27830}{56419} &:= \frac{2+78+30}{56 \times 4-1^9} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27839}{51604} &:= \frac{2+78-39}{5 \times 16-04} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{27+8 \times (3+9)}{(51+6) \times 04} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+(7+8+3) \times 9}{5 \times 1 \times 60+4} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{31059} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8+4-6)}{(3+1) \times 05+9} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 7-8+46}{3+10+5 \times 9} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{31590} &:= \frac{(2+7 \times 8) \times 4+6}{3 \times 1^5 \times 90} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{39015} &:= \frac{2^7+8+46}{3 \times (90-1 \times 5)} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27860}{49153} &:= \frac{2+78+60}{(49+1) \times 5-3} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27863}{90145} &:= \frac{2 \times (7-8+6 \times 3)}{90+1 \times 4 \times 5} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27864}{35910} &:= \frac{2^{7+8-6}+4}{35 \times (9+10)} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27864}{93150} &:= \frac{2+78+6^4}{(93-1) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27891}{35640} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 8+9 \times 1}{3 \times (5+6) \times 40} & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27891}{36450} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 8+9 \times 1}{(3+6 \times 4) \times 50} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27904}{35861} &:= \frac{(2-7+9)^{04}}{3^5+86 \times 1} & & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & & & & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{30456} &:= \frac{2-(7-(9-(1-8)))}{3 \times (0-(4 \times (5-6)))} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2-(7-(9+18))}{(3+(0-(4-5))) \times 6} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (7+9))+(1^8)}{30-((4-5) \times 6)} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{27+(9+(1 \times 8))}{(3-((0 \times 4)-5)) \times 6} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+((7 \times (9-1))+8)}{(3-(0-(4+5))) \times 6} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times 7)-(9 \times (1-8))}{30+((4+5) \times 6)} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{2+(7 \times (9+(1 \times 8)))}{3 \times ((04 \times (5+6)))} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{(27 \times 9)-(1^8)}{(30 \times (4+5))-6} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times 79)-(1-8)}{3 \times ((04+56))} & & & & & & & & \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (7+9))+1) \times 8}{(3-(0-45)) \times 6} & & & & & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{35046} := \frac{2+7 \times 9-18}{35+04 \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{43065} := \frac{2 \times (7+91)-8}{(4^3-06) \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{46530} := \frac{((2 \times 7)+9) \times 18}{46 \times (5 \times (3-0))}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (9-1)))+8}{(46 \times 5)-30}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (7+(9 \times 1)))-8}{4+(6^{5-3}+0)}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times 7)+(9-(1 \times 8))}{4+(6+(5 \times (3-0)))}$ $:= \frac{(2+(7+(9 \times 1))) \times 8}{4 \times ((6 \times 5)+30)}$ $:= \frac{(2+(7+9)) \times 18}{4+(6+530)}$ $:= \frac{2-(7-((9+1) \times 8))}{(4+6-5)^3+0}$ $:= \frac{2-(7-(9-(1^8)))}{4+((6-5)^3+0)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times (9+1))+8)}{(46 \times 5)+30}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times (9-1))-8)}{4+(6+(5 \times 30))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7-(9-(1 \times 8)))}{((4-6) \times 5)+30}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+((9+1) \times 8))}{(4 \times 65)+30}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+(9-(1^8)))}{(4-6) \times (5-30)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+(9+(1 \times 8)))}{(4+6) \times (5+(3-0))}$ $:= \frac{2+((7+(9+1)) \times 8)}{(4 \times 65)-30}$ $:= \frac{2+(7-(9-(1+8)))}{(4+6-5) \times (3-0)}$ $:= \frac{2+(7 \times (9+(1^8)))}{4 \times ((6-5) \times 30)}$ $:= \frac{2+(7+(9 \times (1 \times 8)))}{4+(6+(5^3+0))}$	$:= \frac{2+(7+(9 \times (1+8)))}{(4+6-5) \times 30}$ $:= \frac{2+(7+(9+(1+8)))}{4+(6+(5+30))}$ $:= \frac{2+(791+8)}{4+((6+5)^3+0)}$ $:= \frac{27 \times ((9+1) \times 8)}{4 \times (6 \times (5 \times 30))}$ $:= \frac{27 \times (9-(1^8))}{4 \times (6 \times (5 \times (3-0)))}$ $:= \frac{27 \times (9+(1^8))}{(4+6+5) \times 30}$ $:= \frac{27+(9+18)}{(4-(6-5)) \times 30}$ $:= \frac{279+18}{465+30}$ $:= \frac{279-18}{465-30}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{53460} := \frac{2+7 \times 9-18}{5 \times (3 \times 4+6)+0}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+91)-8}{5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{63450} := \frac{2-7+9-1+8}{(6+3-4) \times 5+0}$ $:= \frac{2+79-1+8}{(6+34) \times 5+0}$ $:= \frac{2+79+18}{6^3+4+5+0}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 9 \times 1-8)}{(6+3-4) \times 50}$ $:= \frac{279-1+8}{(6+3+4) \times 50}$ $:= \frac{(2 \times (7+9)+1) \times 8}{(6-3) \times 4 \times 50}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{65340} := \frac{2 \times (791+8)}{(6+5) \times 340}$	$:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times (9-3)+0}{6+(1+8) \times 4 \times 5}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{40158} := \frac{2^{(7-9+3)} \times 6}{4 \times (015+8)}$ $:= \frac{2-7+9 \times 3-6}{(4-01) \times 5+8}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+9) \times (3+6)}{401+5+8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{48015} := \frac{2 \times (7-9+3 \times 6)}{(4+8-01) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{2+7+93-6}{(4 \times 8+01) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7+9) \times (3+6)}{480+15}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{51840} := \frac{2 \times (7+93)-6}{5 \times 18 \times 4+0}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{61830} := \frac{2 \times (7+94)+5}{61 \times 8-30}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{63180} := \frac{2-(7-9) \times 45}{6^{3 \times 1}-8+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{68310} := \frac{2+(7-(9-(4+5)))}{6+(8 \times (3-(1-0)))}$ $:= \frac{2+(7+(9+(4+5)))}{6 \times (8+(3 \times (1-0)))}$ $:= \frac{2 \times (7-(9-(4 \times 5)))}{6+(83-(1-0))}$ $:= \frac{2+(7-(9-45))}{6+(8 \times (3+10))}$ $:= \frac{2+(7+(9+45))}{(6 \times (8 \times 3))+10}$ $:= \frac{2+(7-(9 \times (4-5)))}{6+(8+(3 \times 10))}$ $:= \frac{2+(79+45)}{6-(8-310)}$ $:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 9)+45)}{6+((8^3)+10)}$
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$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{27 \times (9 - (4 - 5))}{6 \times ((8 + 3) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 7) \times ((9 \times 4) - 5)}{683 - (1 - 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{83106} &:= \frac{(2 \times 7 + 9) \times 45}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27963}{51480} &:= \frac{2 + 796 \times 3}{(51 + 4) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 79 \times (6 - 3)}{(51 + 4) \times 8 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27965}{84130} := \frac{2 \times (7 \times 9 - 6) + 5}{8 \times 41 + 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28013}{76954} := \frac{2^8 + 01^3}{7 + 695 + 4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28059}{36417} &:= \frac{280 - 5 \times 9}{3 \times 6 + 41 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28059}{73461} &:= \frac{2 \times (805 - 9)}{73 + 4^6 - 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28063}{91574} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 06 + 3}{9 + 1 \times 57 - 4} \\ &:= \frac{28 \times (06) + 3}{9 \times (1 + 57 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28105}{73964} := \frac{2^8 \times 10 - 5}{(73 + 9)^{6-4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28106}{79534} := \frac{(2 + 8) \times 10 - 6}{7 \times (9 - 5 + 34)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28134}{60957} &:= \frac{2 + (8 \times (1 - (3 - 4)))}{60 - (9 + (5 + 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + ((1^3) \times 4))}{(6 \times (09)) + (5 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (8 - (1 \times (3 \times 4)))}{6 - (0 - (9 + (5 - 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (1 + (3 \times 4)))}{(6 \times ((09 + 5))) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 - (1 - 3))) \times 4}{6 - (0 - ((9 + 5) \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((8 + (1^3)) \times 4)}{6 \times (0 - (9 - (5 \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (8 + 134)}{6 \times (((09 \times 5) + 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 - (1^3))) \times 4}{60 - (9 \times (5 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (8 \times (1 + 34))}{609 - (5 - 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28143}{50976} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 1 \times 43}{5 + 097 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 143}{(50 - 9 + 7) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{2^8 - (1 - 4) \times 3}{5 \times (09 + 7) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28193}{64075} &:= \frac{2 + (8 + (1 \times (9 + 3)))}{(6 + (4 - (0 \times 7))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + (1^9))) \times 3}{((6 + (4 - 0)) \times 7) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2 + ((8 - 1) \times (9 - 3))}{(6 + (4 - 0))^{7-5}} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 1)) \times (9 - 3)}{(6 - (4 - 0)) \times 75} \\ &:= \frac{28 + (1 \times 93)}{(6 \times 40) + (7 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{2 \times ((8 \times (1 + 9)) - 3)}{(6 + (4 - 0)) \times (7 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 1)) \times (9 \times 3)}{640 + (7 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((2^8) - (1 - 9)) \times 3}{6 \times (4 \times (075))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (8 \times (1 - 9))) \times 3}{6 \times (40 + (7 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28194}{36075} &:= \frac{2 + (8 - 1) \times 9 \times 4}{360 - 7 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28194}{50673} &:= \frac{2^{8-1} + 94}{50 + 6 + 7^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28341}{56079} := \frac{2 + (8 + 3) \times 4 + 1}{5 \times 6 + 07 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{41796} &:= \frac{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}{4 + (1 + 7)^{9-6}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{49167} &:= \frac{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}{4 + 9 \times 1 \times 67} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{69174} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 3) \times 5 + 0}{6 \times (9 - 1) + 74} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{69741} &:= \frac{2^{8-3} \times 50}{6 \times (9 + 7) \times 41} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{91476} &:= \frac{(2 + 8) \times 3 \times 5 + 0}{9 - 1 + 476} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28356}{71094} &:= \frac{2 \times (83 + 56)}{710 - 9 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28356}{91740} &:= \frac{2 + 8 \times (3 - 5 + 6)}{(9 + 1) \times (7 + 4) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 35 + 6}{91 + 74 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28359}{41607} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times (3+5) + 9}{(4-1) \times (60+7)} \\ & \frac{28359}{47610} := \frac{2^8 - (3-5) \times 9}{(4+7 \times 6) \times 10} \\ & \frac{28359}{60417} := \frac{2 \times (8+3+5) - 9}{(6-0 \times 4+1) \times 7} \\ & \quad := \frac{2^8 - (3+5) \times 9}{(60-4 \times 1) \times 7} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28469}{70315} := \frac{2+8+4+69}{70 \times 3 \times 1-5} \\ & \frac{28476}{53901} := \frac{2+8-(4-7) \times 6}{53+9 \times 0 \times 1} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+8+4+7 \times 6}{5 \times 3+90+1} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (84+7 \times 6)}{53 \times 9 \times 01} \\ & \quad := \frac{28+476}{53+901} \\ & \quad := \frac{28 \times (4 \times 7+6)}{(5-3) \times 901} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{2 \times (84 \times (7-6))}{9+(1+530)} \\ & := \frac{28 \times (47+6)}{9 \times (1 \times 530)} \\ & \frac{28539}{76104} := \frac{((2^8-5) \times 3) - 9}{(7-6) \times (10 \times 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{((2+8) \times (5 \times 3)) + 9}{(7 \times (6 \times 10)) + 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{((28-5) \times 3) + 9}{((7 \times 6) + 10) \times 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2-(8-(5 \times 3))) \times 9}{(7-61) \times (-04)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2-(8-5)) \times (3-9)}{7+(6-(1+(-04)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times ((8-5)^3)) + 9}{7 \times (6 \times (1 \times (04)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2+(8 \times 5)) \times 39}{7 \times (6 \times 104)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2+(8-5)) \times 39}{(7+6) \times (10 \times 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{2-(8-(5 \times (3 \times 9)))}{(76+10) \times 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{2-(8+(5 \times (3-9)))}{7+(61+(-04))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8-(5-(3+9)))}{76-(1 \times (-04))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8-(5+(3-9)))}{(7+(6-(1-0))) \times 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(8+(5-(3+9)))}{7+(6-(1-(-04)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(8+(5-(3-9)))}{(7+(6+(1-0))) \times 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(8+(5+(3+9)))}{7+(61-(-04))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(85+(3 \times 9))}{76 \times (1 \times (04))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(85+(3+9))}{(76-10) \times 4} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28364}{90157} := \frac{2 \times (8+3 \times (6-4))}{90+1+5-7} \\ & \quad := \frac{2^{8-3} \times 6+4}{(90-1^5) \times 7} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28476}{90513} := \frac{2+8-(4-7) \times 6}{90-5+1+3} \\ & \frac{28476}{91530} := \frac{2+(8+(4 \times (7-6)))}{9+(1+(5+30))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(8-((4-7) \times 6))}{(9-(1+5)) \times 30} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+((8 \times (4+7))-6)}{9 \times ((1^5) \times 30)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2+(8+(4+7))) \times 6}{9 \times (15+30)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times 4)) + 76}{(9+(1+5)) \times 30} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+(8 \times (4+(7-6)))}{9+(1+(5^3+0))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2^8)-(4-(7 \times 6))}{915+30} \\ & \quad := \frac{(28 \times 4)-(7 \times 6)}{9+((1+5)^3+0)} \end{aligned}$	
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28379}{40651} := \frac{28+37+9}{40+65+1} \end{aligned}$		
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28431}{59670} := \frac{2 \times (84-3 \times 1)}{5 \times 9 \times 6+70} \end{aligned}$		
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28457}{36019} := \frac{2+84+57}{3 \times 60+1^9} \\ & \quad := \frac{2+84 \times 5+7}{3+60 \times 1 \times 9} \\ & \quad := \frac{2^8+4^5+7}{(3 \times 60+1) \times 9} \end{aligned}$		
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28461}{37590} := \frac{2 \times (8 \times 4-6)+1}{(3-7) \times 5+90} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8+46-1)}{(3+7) \times (5+9)+0} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{28+476}{9 \times ((1+5) \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (8+(47-6))}{9 \times (1 \times (5+30))} \\ & := \frac{((2 \times 84)+7) \times 6}{(9+(1+5))^3+0} \end{aligned}$	
$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28461}{39750} := \frac{2 \times (84+6)-1}{(3+9-7) \times 50} \end{aligned}$		

$$:= \frac{2 + (85 - 39)}{((7 \times 6) - 10) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{28 \times ((5 \times 3) - 9)}{7 \times ((6 + 10) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{28 + (5 - (3 - 9))}{(7 - 6) \times 104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28560}{43197} := \frac{2 + (8 + 5) \times 6 + 0}{(4 \times 3 - 1)^{9-7}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28576}{39104} := \frac{2 \times (8 - 5) + 7 + 6}{3 + 9 + 10 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (8 + 5 - 7) \times 6}{3 + 9 + 10 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + 5) - 7) \times 6}{39 \times 1 \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times 85 + 7 - 6}{39 \times (10 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(28 \times 5 - 7) \times 6}{3 \times 91 \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 8 + 5) \times 76}{39 \times 10 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28695}{40173} := \frac{(2 \times (8 + (6 - 9))) + 5}{(4 \times (0 - (1 - 7))) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (6 - (9 - 5)))}{4 - (0 - ((1 + 7) \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (8 - ((6 - 9) \times 5))}{(4 \times ((01 + 7))) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (8 + (6 + (9 + 5)))}{40 - ((1^7) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + (6 - 9))) - 5}{4 + (0 - (1 - (7 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (8 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}{40 - (1 - (7 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 8) + (6 \times (9 - 5))}{4 \times ((017 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 8) - (6 - (9 \times 5))}{4 - (0 - (1 \times 73))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (8 - (6 - 9))) \times 5}{40 + (17 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 8) + ((6 \times 9) + 5)}{(4 - (-01)) \times (7 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (8 \times (6 + 9))) + 5}{(4 \times (0 \times 1)) + (7^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (8 - (6 + (9 \times 5)))}{(4 - (0 - 17)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((8 - 6) \times (9 - 5))}{4 - (0 - (1 \times (7 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 8) + (69 - 5)}{40 - (1 - 73)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{43956} := \frac{2 \times 87 \times 10}{(439 + 5) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{45936} := \frac{((2 \times 8)^7) \times 10}{4 \times ((5 + (9 \times 3))^6)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times 8) + 7) \times 10}{4 \times (5 + (93 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2^8)^7) \times 10}{(4^5)^{9+3-6}}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + 7)) + 10}{4 + (5 \times (9 - (3 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 7)) \times 10}{4 \times (59 + (3 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 8) \times (7 - (1 - 0))}{4 + (5 + (93 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(28 \times 7) - (1 - 0)}{(4 + ((5 \times 9) + 3)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (8 - (71 - 0))}{4 \times (5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((8 - 7) \times 10)}{4 - (5 - ((9 \times 3) + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{4 \times ((5 - 9) \times (3 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (7 + 10))}{4 - (5 - (9 \times (3 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (7 - 10))}{4 + ((5 - 9) \times (3 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (8 + (7 \times 10))}{4 \times (5 - (9 - 36))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (8 + 710)}{4 \times (((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (87 + (1 - 0))}{4 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{28 + (7 \times (1 - 0))}{4 \times (5 - (9 - (3 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{28 + (7 + 10)}{4 + (59 + (3 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{28 + (7 - 10)}{4 + ((5 \times (9 - 3)) + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{63945} := \frac{2 \times (8 - 7 + 10)}{6 + (3 + 9) \times 4 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (8 \times 7 - 1) + 0}{(6 + 39 + 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28714}{50396} := \frac{28 + 7 + 14}{50 - (3 - 9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28739}{60451} := \frac{2 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 9}{6 + 04 + 51}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 87 + 3 \times 9}{60 \times 4 + 5 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 8 \times (7 - 3) \times 9}{604 + 5 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28740}{53169} := \frac{(2 + 8 - 7) \times 40}{53 + 169}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 8 + 7) \times 40}{5 \times (3 + 1) + 6 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28743}{90651} := \frac{287 - 4 + 3}{906 - 5 + 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{28764}{39015} := \frac{2 \times ((8+7) \times 6 + 4)}{3 \times (90 - 1 \times 5)} \\ & \frac{28905}{41736} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 90 - 5}{4 \times ((1+7)^3 + 6)} \\ & \frac{28907}{41356} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9 - 07}{4 \times (1 + (3+5) \times 6)} \\ & \frac{28914}{35076} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 9 \times (1+4)}{3 - 5 + 076} \\ & \frac{28914}{75603} := \frac{2^8 - 9 + 1 - 4}{7 \times 5 + 603} \\ & \frac{28917}{36450} := \frac{2 \times (8+9 \times 1) \times 7}{3 \times (6-4) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times 8 - 9) \times 17}{3 \times (6+4) \times 5 + 0} \\ & \frac{28917}{40635} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times (9+1) - 7}{4 + 06^3 - 5} \\ & \frac{28917}{45360} := \frac{289 + 17}{4 \times (5-3) \times 60} \\ & \frac{28917}{46053} := \frac{2+8+9+1+7}{46+0 \times 5 - 3} \\ & \frac{28917}{46305} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times (9+1) - 7}{(46+3) \times 05} \\ & \frac{28917}{53460} := \frac{2 \times (8+9 \times 1) \times 7}{5^3 \times 4 - 60} \\ & \frac{28940}{36175} := \frac{((2 \times 8) + 9) \times (4-0)}{3 + (61 \times (7-5))} \\ & \quad := \frac{((2 \times 8) + 9) \times 40}{((3^{6-1}) + 7) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{((2 \times 8) - 9) \times (4-0)}{36 - (1^{75})} \\ & \quad := \frac{((2 \times 8) - 9) \times 40}{(3 + (6+1)) \times (7 \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 - (8-9)) \times (4-0)}{3 \times (6 - (1^{75}))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 - (8-9)) \times 40}{(36 + (1-7)) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4-0)}{(36 - (1^7)) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times 9)) + (4-0)}{(3 \times 61) + (7-5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 \times 8) + (9 \times (4-0))}{((3 + (6+1)) \times 7) - 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 + (8+9)) \times (4-0)}{(36 - 17) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 + (8+9)) \times 40}{((3 \times 61) + 7) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 + (8-9)) \times (4-0)}{3 + (6 + ((1^7) - 5))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2 + (8-9)) \times 40}{(3 + (6 + (1^7))) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(28 \times 9) - 40}{(36 + 17) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times ((8 \times 9) + (4-0))}{(3 + ((6-1) \times 7)) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times ((8 \times 9) + 40)}{(3 + (6-1)) \times (7 \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40)}{(3 + (6 + (1 \times 7))) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8 \times (9 - (4-0)))}{3 + ((6 \times 17) - 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8 \times (9 \times (4-0)))}{3 \times (6 \times ((1+7) \times 5))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8 \times (9 + (4-0)))}{(3 + ((6+1) \times 7)) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8 + (9 \times (4-0)))}{3 + ((6 \times 17) + 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 \times (8 + (94-0))}{(3 + (6 \times (1+7))) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{2^{8-9+4+0}}{3 + (6 + (1^{75}))} \\ & \quad := \frac{2 + (8 + (94-0))}{(3 + (6+17)) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{28 \times (9 \times (4-0))}{36 \times (1 \times (7 \times 5))} \\ & \frac{28945}{60371} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 94 - 5}{6 + 03 \times 71} \\ & \frac{28946}{70315} := \frac{2 + 8 \times (94-6)}{70^3 \times 1 \times 5} \\ & \frac{28950}{61374} := \frac{(2+8-9) \times 50}{6 \times 13 + 7 \times 4} \\ & \frac{28967}{40135} := \frac{2-8+96-7}{40 \times 1 \times 3-5} \\ & \frac{28971}{36540} := \frac{(2+8 \times 9) \times (7-1)}{(3+6+5) \times 40} \\ & \frac{28971}{43065} := \frac{2-8+9+71}{4+3 \times 06 \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(2+8 \times 9) \times 71}{4+30+6^5} \\ & \frac{28975}{34160} := \frac{(2+8)^{9-7} - 5}{(3+4) \times 16+0} \\ & \frac{29013}{78546} := \frac{2^9 \times 01 - 3}{7^{8-5} \times 4 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29016}{43758} &:= \frac{2^9 - 016}{4 \times 37 \times 5 + 8} & \frac{29067}{58134} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) - 6) \times 7}{(5 + (8 + 1)) \times (3 \times 4)} & &:= \frac{2 - ((9 \times (-06)) + 7)}{5 + (81 + (3 \times 4))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29016}{75348} &:= \frac{2^9 - 016}{((7 - 5) \times 3)^4 - 8} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 \times 6))) + 7}{5 \times (8 + (1 - (3 - 4)))} & &:= \frac{2 - ((9 \times (-06)) - 7)}{(5 \times (8 + 1)) + (3^4)} \\
 & & & & &:= \frac{2 - (9 \times (0 \times 67))}{5 - (8 - (1 \times (3 + 4)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29053}{78614} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 05 + 3)}{7 + 86 - 1^4} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (-06))) + 7}{5 + (81 - (3 \times 4))} & &:= \frac{2 - (9 + (0 - (6 \times 7)))}{5 \times (8 - (1 - (3 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 + 05) \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times (6 - 1) - 4} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (-06))) - 7}{5 + (8 - (1 - 34))} & &:= \frac{2 - (9 + (0 - (6 + 7)))}{5 + (8 + (1 \times (3 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 05^3}{(7 + 86 - 1) \times 4} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (0 \times 6))) + 7}{5 + (8 - (1 \times (3 - 4)))} & &:= \frac{2 - (9 + (0 - 67))}{5 \times ((8 + (1 - 3)) \times 4)} \\
 & & & & &:= \frac{2 \times ((9 - (-06)) \times 7)}{5 \times ((8 + 13) \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{67134} &:= \frac{2 + 9 \times (-05 + 8)}{67 - 1 - 3 + 4} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 + 7)}{5 \times (8 + (1 - (3 + 4)))} & &:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) + 7)}{(5 \times (8 \times 1)) - (3 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 9 + 05 \times 8}{67 \times (1 - 3 + 4)} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 - 7)}{((5 + (8 + 1)) \times 3) - 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (06)) + 7)}{5 + ((81 \times 3) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{29 + 058}{67 + 134} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 + 7)}{58 + ((1^3) \times 4)} & &:= \frac{2 \times ((9 + (-06)) \times 7)}{(5 - (8 \times (1 - 3))) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{290 + 58}{67 \times 1 \times 3 \times 4} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 - 7)}{(5 \times (8 + (1 - 3))) + 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 6) - 7))}{(5 \times (8 + (1 + 3))) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{29 \times (0 \times 5 + 8)}{67 \times (1 + 3 + 4)} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - 0)) + 67}{(58 \times (1 \times 3)) - 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (0 - (6 - 7)))}{5 - (8 - (1 + 34))} \\
 &:= \frac{29 \times (05 + 8)}{67 \times (1 + 3 \times 4)} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (90 + 6)) + 7}{(5 \times 81) - (3 + 4)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (0 \times 67))}{(5 \times (8 \times (1^3))) - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{71643} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 + 05 \times 8}{7 \times (16 + 4) + 3} & &:= \frac{(2 \times (90 + 6)) - 7}{5 \times (81 - (3 + 4))} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7))}{5 + ((81 \times 3) + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{73146} &:= \frac{2 + 9 \times (-05 + 8)}{7 - (3 - 14) \times 6} & &:= \frac{(2 \times 90) + (6 + 7)}{(5 \times (81 - 3)) - 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (0 + (6 + 7)))}{((5 \times 8) - 1) \times (3 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 9 + 05 \times 8}{(7 + 31) \times 4 - 6} & &:= \frac{(2^9 - 06) + 7}{5 - (8 + (1 - 34))} & &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (0 - (6 - 7)))}{5 \times (8 - (1 + (3 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 90 - 5) \times 8}{73 \times 1 \times 4 \times 6} & &:= \frac{(2^9 - 06) - 7}{5 + (8 + (1 - (3 \times 4)))} & &:= \frac{2 \times (90 - (6 \times 7))}{((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 3) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{29 + 058}{7 \times 31 - 4 + 6} & &:= \frac{(2 - 9) \times (0 - (6 \times 7))}{581 + (3 + 4)} & &:= \frac{2 \times (90 + (6 + 7))}{(5 \times 81) + (3 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (90 + 5 - 8)}{73 \times 1^4 \times 6} & &:= \frac{(2 - 90) \times (6 - 7)}{((5 \times 8) + (1 + 3)) \times 4} & &:= \frac{2 \times (90 + (6 - 7))}{(5 + (81 + 3)) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{29 \times (0 \times 5 + 8)}{73 \times (14 - 6)} & &:= \frac{2 - ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) - 7)}{5 + (8 + (1^3 + 4))} & &:= \frac{2 \times (90 - 67)}{58 + (1 \times 34)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{2^{9+0 \times 6-7}}{5-(8+(1-(3 \times 4)))} & := \frac{(2-9) \times ((0 \times 7)-1)}{4-((5 \times (6-8))+3)} & := \frac{(2 \times 90)-(7 \times 3)}{(58-(1+4)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2+(9-(0-(6+7)))}{5+(8+(1+34))} & := \frac{(2-9) \times (0-(7 \times 1))}{4+((5 \times (6+8))+3)} & := \frac{(2+(9-(0 \times 7))) \times 3}{(5-(8-14)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2+(9-(0-(6-7)))}{5+(8+(1 \times (3+4)))} & := \frac{2-(9 \times (0-(7-1)))}{4-(5-(6+83))} & := \frac{(2+(9-(-07))) \times 3}{(5+(8+(1+4))) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2+(9-(0 \times 67))}{5+(8+(13-4))} & := \frac{2+(90+7-1)}{4+(5 \times (6 \times (8-3)))} & := \frac{(2+(9-0)) \times (7-3)}{5+(81-(4-6))} \\
 & := \frac{2+(9-(0-67))}{(5 \times (8 \times (1+3))) - 4} & := \frac{2 \times (90-(7-1))}{4 \times (((5 \times 6)-8) \times 3)} & := \frac{(2+90) \times (7+3)}{5 \times (8 \times (1 \times 46))} \\
 & := \frac{2+(9+(0-(6-7)))}{5+(8-(1-(3 \times 4)))} & := \frac{2 \times (90+71)}{(4^5)-(6+(8^3))} & := \frac{(29-(-07)) \times 3}{((5 \times (8 \times 1))-4) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2+(90-(6 \times 7))}{5 \times (8+(1 \times (3 \times 4)))} & := \frac{(2^9+0) \times (7 \times 1)}{((4^5) \times 6)-(8^3)} & := \frac{(2-9) \times (0-(7 \times 3))}{((5 \times (8+1))+4) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2+(90+(6+7))}{5 \times (8+(1 \times 34))} & & := \frac{(2-9) \times (0-(7+3))}{5 \times (8+(14+6))} \\
 & := \frac{29-(0-(6-7))}{(5+(8+(1^3))) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29073}{58146} := \frac{((2 \times (9-0))+7) \times 3}{5 \times ((8+(1-4)) \times 6)} & := \frac{2-((9 \times (0 \times 7))-3)}{5+(8-(1-(4-6)))} \\
 & := \frac{29-(0 \times 67)}{58-(1+(3-4))} & := \frac{((2+(9-0)) \times 7)+3}{5 \times (8+(1 \times (4 \times 6)))} & := \frac{2-((9 \times (-07))+3)}{(5 \times 8)+(14 \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{29 \times ((0 \times 6)+7)}{(5 \times 81)-(3-4)} & := \frac{((2-9) \times (-07))+3}{(5 \times (8+14))-6} & := \frac{2-(9 \times (0-(7-3)))}{5+(81-(4+6))} \\
 & := \frac{29 \times (0+(6+7))}{58 \times (1+(3 \times 4))} & := \frac{(2-(9 \times (-07))) \times 3}{5 \times ((8+(1+4)) \times 6)} & := \frac{2-(9 \times (0 \times 73))}{5+(8+(1-(4+6)))} \\
 & := \frac{29+((0 \times 6)-7)}{(5 \times (8 \times (1^3)))+4} & := \frac{(2 \times (9-(-07)))+3}{5 \times (8+((1^4) \times 6))} & := \frac{2-(9+(0-(7 \times 3)))}{58-((1+4) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{29+(0-(6-7))}{5 \times (8+((1^3) \times 4))} & := \frac{(2 \times (9-(-07)))-3}{5+(8-(1-46))} & := \frac{2-(9+(0-(7+3)))}{5-(8+(1-(4+6)))} \\
 & := \frac{290-(6-7)}{581-(3-4)} & := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (07)))+3}{((5 \times 8)-(1-4)) \times 6} & := \frac{2-(9+(0-73))}{5+(81+46)} \\
 & & := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (07)))-3}{(5+((8+1) \times 4)) \times 6} & := \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 7))+3)}{5+(8+(1+(4-6)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29071}{45683} & := \frac{2+(90-71)}{(4+(5-(6-8))) \times 3} & := \frac{(2 \times (9-0))+(7 \times 3)}{(5+(8 \times (1^4))) \times 6} & := \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (07))+3)}{((5 \times (8 \times 1))+4) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{29+((0 \times 7)-1)}{4 \times (5-((6-8) \times 3))} & := \frac{(2 \times (9-0))+(7+3)}{58+(1 \times (4-6))} & := \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (07))-3)}{5 \times (8 \times ((1^4) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{29-(0-(7-1))}{4+(56-(8-3))} & := \frac{(2 \times (9-0))+(7-3)}{5-(8-(1+46))} & := \frac{2 \times ((9+(-07)) \times 3)}{5+(8+(1+(4+6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2-9) \times (0-(7-1))}{((4 \times 5)-(6-8)) \times 3} & := \frac{(2 \times (90-7))+3}{((5+81) \times 4)-6} & := \frac{2 \times ((9+(-07))^3)}{(5 \times 8)-(14-6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 3))}{(5 + (8 - (1 + 4))) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 \times 3)))}{5 \times (8 \times (1 - (4 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 - 3)))}{58 - ((1^4) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 - (0 \times 73))}{5 + (8 - (1 - (4 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (0 + (7 + 3)))}{5 \times ((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 3)))}{5 - (8 + (1 - (4 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (90 - (7 + 3))}{5 \times (8 \times (14 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (90 + (7 + 3))}{5 \times (8 \times (1 \times (4 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (90 - 73)}{58 + (1 \times (4 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{2^{9-07+3}}{(5 - (8 - (1 + 4)))^6} \\
 := \frac{2 + ((9 + (-07)) \times 3)}{5 + (8 + (1 - (4 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (9 - (0 - (7 + 3)))}{5 - (8 + (1 - 46))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (9 - (0 - (7 - 3)))}{5 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (9 - (0 \times 73))}{5 + (8 - (1 - (4 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (9 + (0 - (7 + 3)))}{5 + (8 - (1 + (4 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (9 + (0 - (7 - 3)))}{5 + (8 - (1 + (4 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2 + (90 - (7 \times 3))}{58 + (14 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (90 - (7 - 3))}{((5 + 8) \times 14) - 6} \\
 := \frac{2 + (90 + (7 \times 3))}{(58 \times 1 \times 4) - 6} \\
 := \frac{2 + (90 + (7 + 3))}{58 + 146}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{2 + (90 + 73)}{5 \times ((8 - (1 - 4)) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{2 + (90 - 73)}{5 + (8 + (1 + (4 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{29 \times ((0 \times 7) + 3)}{(5 - (8 \times (1 - 4))) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{29 \times (0 + (7 + 3))}{58 \times (1 \times (4 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{29 + (0 - (7 - 3))}{5 \times (8 - (1 \times (4 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{2907 + 3}{5814 + 6} \\
 := \frac{2907 - 3}{5814 - 6} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29078}{31465} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 07 + 8}{(31 + 4 - 6) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29078}{45136} := \frac{2 + 9 + 07 \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times (1 + 3) + 6)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29103}{75864} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 - 3}{(7 - 5)^8 - 6 \times 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29103}{85674} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 - 3}{(8 + 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{37485} := \frac{(2 + 9 \times 1) \times 06}{3 - 7 + 4 + 85} \\
 := \frac{2^9 + 10 + 6}{(3 \times 7 - 4) \times 8 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{45738} := \frac{2 + (9 - (10 - 6))}{4 - (5 - (7 - (3 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1 - 0))) - 6}{4 + (5 + ((7 \times 3) - 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1 + (-06)))}{4 - (5 - (7 + 38))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{29 - (1 \times (-06))}{(4 \times 5) - (7 \times (3 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{(2 - (9 \times 1)) \times (-06)}{4 + (57 - (3 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{2 \times (91 - (0 \times 6))}{(4^5) - 738} \\
 := \frac{2 - (9 \times (1 \times (-06)))}{4 \times (5 - (7 - (3 \times 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{57834} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times (1 + 06)}{57 + 8 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{73458} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times 10 - 6)}{(73 - 4 \times 5) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{83457} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 + 6}{8 + (34 + 5) \times 7} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29145}{76380} := \frac{(2 - 9 \times (1 - 4)) \times 5}{(7 - 6) \times 380} \\
 := \frac{29 + 145}{76 + 380} \\
 := \frac{29 \times 1 \times 4 \times 5}{7 \times 6^3 + 8 + 0} \\
 := \frac{29 \times (1 + 4 \times 5)}{7 \times 6 \times 38 + 0} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29150}{34768} := \frac{(2 + 9 \times 1) \times 50}{(3^4 + 7 - 6) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 9) \times 150}{(34 + 7) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{35478} := \frac{(29 + 1) \times 6 + 0}{3 + (5 \times 4 + 7) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(2 + 9 - 1) \times 6 + 0}{3 \times (5 \times 4 + 7) - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{37584} := \frac{29 + 16 + 0}{3 - 7 + 58 + 4} \\
 := \frac{29 + 1 + 60}{(3 + 7 + 5) \times 8 - 4}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(29+1) \times 6 + 0}{((3+7) \times 5 + 8) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{(29+1) \times 60}{(3+7) \times 58 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{38475} & := \frac{2+9+1+60}{(3 \times (8-4) + 7) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{47385} & := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 - (6-0)))}{4 - (7 - (3 + (8+5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1^6 + 0))}{4 - (7 - ((3 \times 8) + 5))} \\
 & := \frac{2 + (9 + (1 + 60))}{4 - (7 - (3 \times (8 \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times ((9+1) \times (6-0))}{(4 - (7 \times (3-8))) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2^9) + 160}{4 \times (7 \times (3 \times (8+5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 + (6-0)))}{4 \times (7 + (3 + (8-5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2^9) - 160}{(47-3) \times (8+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{53784} & := \frac{(29+1) \times 6 + 0}{(5+37) \times 8 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{57834} & := \frac{(2+9-1) \times 60}{5 \times (78 \times 3 + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{73845} & := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 60}{7^3 \times 8 - 4 - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{74358} & := \frac{2 \times (9 + 1^6) + 0}{74 - 3 \times 5 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 + 1 + 60)}{7 \times (4^3 - 5 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - 1) \times 60}{(7 \times 43 + 5) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{84375} & := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 60}{((8-4) \times 3 - 7)^5} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29180}{36475} & := \frac{((2 \times 9) + 1) \times (8 - 0)}{(3 \times 64) - (7 - 5)} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times 9) - 1) \times (8 - 0)}{(3 + ((6 \times 4) + 7)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (9 + 1)) + (8 - 0)}{(3 - (6 - 4)) \times (7 \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (9 + 1)) + 80}{(3 - (6 - (4 \times 7))) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (9 - 1)) - (8 - 0)}{((3^{6-4}) - 7) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (9 - 1)) + (8 - 0)}{(3 + (6 + 4 - 7)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2^9 \times 1) + (8 - 0)}{(3^6) - (4 + 75)} \\
 & := \frac{(2^9) - 180}{(36 + 47) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (9 - 1)) \times (8 - 0)}{(3 + (6 + (4 + 7))) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(29 + 1) \times (8 - 0)}{(3 + (64 - 7)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(29 + 1) \times 80}{(36 + 4) \times 75} \\
 & := \frac{(29 - 1) \times (8 - 0)}{(3 + (6 + 47)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times ((9 - 1) \times 80)}{(36 + 4)^{7-5}} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1 - (8 - 0)))}{3 + (6 - (4 - (7 \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1^8 + 0))}{3 - (6 - ((4 \times 7) - 5))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1 - 80))}{(3 - (6 - 47)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}{(3 \times 64) - (7 + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1^8 + 0))}{3 + (6 + (4^{7-5}))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 + (8 - 0)))}{3 - (6 - (4 \times (7 + 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 + 80))}{3 \times (((6 + 4) \times 7) + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{2^{9-1^8+0}}{(36 + (4 \times 7)) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{2^{9+1-8+0}}{3 - (6 - (4 \times (7 - 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 + (9 \times (18 - 0))}{(3 \times ((6 + 4) \times 7)) - 5} \\
 & := \frac{2 + (9 + (1^8 + 0))}{3 + (6 \times (4 - (7 - 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 + (9 + (1 + 80))}{((3 \times (6 + 4)) - 7) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{29 - (1 - 80)}{3 \times (6 + (4 + (7 \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{29 \times (1 \times (8 - 0))}{3 + ((6 \times 47) + 5)} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29184}{53760} & := \frac{2 \times (9 \times 1 \times 8 + 4)}{5 \times (3 - 7 + 60)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (91 + 8 - 4)}{5 \times (3 + 7 + 60)} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{30456} & := \frac{2 \times (9 - 1^8) + 7}{(3 - 04 + 5) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 - 1 + 8 + 7)}{(3 + 0 \times 4 + 5) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{291 - 8 - 7}{(3 + 045) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + 918) \times 7}{30 \times 4 \times 56} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{40365} & := \frac{2 \times (9 + 18) - 7}{(4 + 03 + 6) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(29 + 18) \times 7}{(4 + 03) \times 65} \\
 & := \frac{2 + 91 + 8 - 7}{40 + 3 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{53406} & := \frac{2 \times (9 + 18) - 7}{5 + 3^4 + 0 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{63450} & := \frac{2 + 91 - 8 + 7}{(6 + 34) \times 5 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{291 - 8 - 7}{(6 - 3) \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{2 + 9 \times 1 \times 8 \times 7}{(6^3 + 4) \times 5 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - 1 + 87}{(6 + 3 - 4) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29304}{51876} := \frac{2 - 9 + 3^{04}}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29304}{57816} := \frac{2 + 9 + 30 - 4}{5 - 7 + 81 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29307}{58614} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times 3)) \times (-07)}{(5^{8-6}) \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (9 + 3)) \times (-07)}{5 \times (8 + (6 + 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - (9 - 3)) \times (-07)}{(5 \times (8 + 6)) - 14}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (3 - 0))) + 7}{58 - (6 + 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (3 - 0))) - 7}{5 \times (8 - (6 \times (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (3 - 0))) - 7}{5 + (86 - (1 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9^3 + 0)) + 7}{586 \times (1 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 - 0))) + 7}{5 - (8 - (61 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 - 0))) - 7}{58 - (6 \times 1 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + 30)) + 7}{5 \times ((8 \times 6) - 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + 30)) - 7}{58 + (6 \times 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 9) + (30 - 7)}{58 + (6 \times 1 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{9-3+0} \times 7}{(58 + 6) \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) - 307}{5 \times (86 - (1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (9 + (3 - 0))) \times 7}{(5 \times (8 \times (6 - 1))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times (3 - (-07))}{5 \times ((8 \times (6 \times 1)) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(29 - (3 - 0)) \times 7}{(5 + (86 \times 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 9) \times (3 \times (-07))}{(58 \times (6 - 1)) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(29 \times (3 - 0)) + 7}{((5 \times 8) + (6 + 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(29 \times (3 - 0)) - 7}{5 \times (8 + (6 \times 1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 93) \times (-07)}{(5 + 86) \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (3 - (-07)))}{5 + (8 - (6 + 1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (30 \times 7))}{58 \times (6 + 1^4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (30 + 7))}{5 \times ((8 - (6 - 1)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (30 - 7))}{(5 + (8 - (6 - 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 \times (3 \times (0 \times 7)))}{5 - (8 - (6 + 1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 + (3 \times (-07)))}{(5 + (8 - (6 \times 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - 307)}{586 + 14}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (3 - 0)) + 7)}{((5 \times 8) - (6 \times 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{5 \times (8 - (6 - 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 + 30) \times 7)}{(5 + 8) \times (6 \times 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 + (8 + (6 + (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 \times (0 \times 7)))}{((5 \times (8 - 6)) - 1) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 \times (-07)))}{5 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 + (-07)))}{5 + ((8 \times 6) - (1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (3 - (-07)))}{5 \times (8 \times (6 - (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 + ((8 \times 6) - (1 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 - (-07)))}{(5 + (8 + (6 \times 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 + (-07)))}{5 + (8 + (6 + 1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (93 - (-07))}{5 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (93 + (-07))}{(58 \times (6 \times 1)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{9+3-07}}{58 + (6 \times (1^4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((9 - (3 - 0)) \times 7)}{5 + (86 + (1 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((9 \times (3 - 0)) + 7)}{(5 + (8 + (6 - 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((9 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{((5 \times (8 - 6)) + 1) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 + (8 + (6 + (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (3 - (-07)))}{5 - (8 - (6 - (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (3 \times (0 \times 7)))}{5 + (8 + (6 - (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (3 + (-07)))}{5 \times (8 - (6 - (1 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{5 + ((8 \times 6) + (1 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 - (-07)))}{((5 \times 8) + (6 \times 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (3 - (-07)))}{(5 - (8 - 6)) \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (3 + (-07)))}{5 + (8 + (6 - (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (30 + 7))}{5 + (86 + (1 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (30 - 7))}{58 + (6 + (1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (93 - (0 \times 7))}{5 \times (8 + (6 \times (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (93 - (-07))}{(5 \times (8 \times (6 - 1))) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (3 \times (-07))}{5^{8-6 \times 1} \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (3 + (-07))}{(5 \times (8 + (6 \times 1))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (30 - 7)}{5 + (8 - (6 - (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 \times (3 - (0 \times 7))}{58 \times (6 + (1 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 \times (3 - (-07))}{58 \times (6 + (1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (3 - (-07))}{5 + (8 + (61 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (3 + (-07))}{5 \times (8 + (6 - (1 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (30 + 7)}{((5 \times 8) - (6 + 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (30 - 7)}{((5^{8-6}) + 1) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + 307}{58 + 614}$$

$$:= \frac{293 - 0 \times 7}{586 \times (1^4)}$$

$$:= \frac{293 - 07}{586 - 14}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29308}{71546} := \frac{29 - 3 + 08}{7 \times (15 - 4) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29346}{70518} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 3 + 46}{7 \times (05 + 18)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29358}{67104} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (3 - 5))) - 8}{(6 \times (7 - (1 - 0))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (3 - (5 + 8)))}{6 \times (7 + (1^{04}))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((9 \times (3 - 5)) - 8)}{67 + (1 + (-04))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (3 - (5 - 8))}{6 + ((7 \times 10) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 - (5 - 8)))}{((6 \times 7) - 10) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 - 9) \times (3 \times (5 - 8))}{6 \times ((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (3 - 58)}{6 \times ((7 + (1 - 0)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 9) \times 3) + 58}{((6 \times 7) + 10) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (9 + 3)) \times (5 + 8)}{(6 \times (7 \times 10)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) - (3 - 58)}{6^{7+1-04}}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 935) - 8}{(6 \times 710) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29364}{80751} := \frac{2^{9+3-6-4}}{8 - (0 - (7 - (5 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 + (6 - 4)))}{80 - (7 + 51)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (3 + (6 + 4)))}{8 - (0 - (7 + 51))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 + (6 - 4)))}{80 - (7 - (5 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 - (6 + 4)))}{8 \times ((07 + (5 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 \times (6 - 4)))}{80 + (75 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (3 \times 6))) - 4}{80 \times (7 + (5 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 - (6 - 4)))}{8 - (0 - ((7 \times 5) + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times ((3 \times 6) - 4))}{8 \times (0 - (7 - 51))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) + 364}{8 - (0 - (7^{5-1}))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29367}{45180} := \frac{2 + (9 + (3 + (6 - 7)))}{4 \times (5 \times (1^8 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (93 - 67)}{4 - (5 - (1 + 80))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - ((9 - (3 \times 6)) \times 7)}{(4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (36 + 7))}{4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (((9 + 3) \times 6) - 7)}{(4 \times 5) + 180}$$

$$:= \frac{(29 + 3) \times (6 + 7)}{(4 + (5 - 1)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-3}) \times (6 + 7)}{4 \times ((5 - 1) \times 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{(29 - 3) \times (6 \times 7)}{((4 \times 5) + 1) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) + ((3^6) + 7)}{4 \times ((5 + 1) \times 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29367}{51480} := \frac{293 - 6 \times 7}{(51 + 4) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29370}{65148} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 37 - 0}{6 \times (5 + 14) + 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{40851} &:= \frac{2^{9-3} \times (7-6)}{4+085 \times 1} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9+(3+8))) + 5}{(4+(7-(-01))) \times 6} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+(3+(8-5)))}{4 \times (7+(0-(1-6)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{50184} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times (7-6))}{5+(01+8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9+(3+8))) - 5}{4 \times (7-(0-(1+6)))} &:= \frac{2 \times (93-(8+5))}{4 \times (70-(1 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times 7-6)}{50+1 \times 8 \times 4} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9-3)) + (8+5)}{4+((7+(-01)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{2+(9-(3+(8-5)))}{4 \times (7-(0-(1-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times (7+6))}{(50-1-8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9-3)) + (8-5)}{4 \times (7+(0-(1^6)))} &:= \frac{2+(93+(8 \times 5))}{4 \times (70-16)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3) \times (7+6)}{501+8 \times 4} &:= \frac{(2 \times (93-8)) - 5}{(4 \times 70) - 16} &:= \frac{2+(93+85)}{(47-(-01)) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{51408} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9+(3-7))) + 6}{(5 \times (1 \times (4-0))) + 8} &:= \frac{(2^{9-3}) \times (8 \times 5)}{4^{7-01^6}} &:= \frac{2+(93-85)}{4^{7+01-6}} \\
 &:= \frac{2+(9-(3 \times (7-6)))}{5+((1^4+0)+8)} &:= \frac{(2^9) \times (3 \times (8 \times 5))}{(4^{701}) \times 6} &:= \frac{293-(8-5)}{470-(1 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9+(3 \times (7+6)))}{((5-1) \times 40) + 8} &:= \frac{(2+((9 \times 3)+8)) \times 5}{(4 \times 70) + 16} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29385}{76401} := \frac{2-(9-(3^{8-5}))}{7+(6+(40-1))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{9-3}) + 76}{5 \times (1+(40+8))} &:= \frac{(2+((9 \times 3)-8)) \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times (0+(1 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9-3)) + (8+5)}{(7+6) \times (4-(-01))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29+3) \times (7+6)}{(51+40) \times 8} &:= \frac{(2+(9+(3 \times 8))) \times 5}{4 \times (70 \times 1^6)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9+(3+8))) + 5}{76+(40+1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (3-(7-6)))}{51+(4-(-08))} &:= \frac{(2+(9+(3+8))) \times 5}{(4+(7-0)) \times 16} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 3)+8)) - 5}{(7 \times (6 \times (4-0))) + 1} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (93+(7+6))}{51+(40 \times 8)} &:= \frac{(2+938) \times 5}{470 \times 16} &:= \frac{(2+(9+(3 \times 8))) \times 5}{7 \times (64-(-01))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{51840} &:= \frac{2 \times (93-76)}{5 \times 1 \times (8+4) + 0} &:= \frac{(29-(3+8)) \times 5}{4 \times ((7+(-01)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((2 \times 9) - 3) \times (8+5)}{(7+6) \times (40-1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{9-3} - 7 - 6}{5+1+84+0} &:= \frac{(29+(3 \times 8)) \times 5}{4+(70 \times (1 \times 6))} &:= \frac{2 \times ((9+(3+8)) \times 5)}{(7+6) \times (40 \times 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (93-7 \times 6)}{5 \times (1+8) \times 4+0} &:= \frac{(29+(3-8)) \times 5}{4 \times ((7-(-01)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(((2+9) \times 3) + 8) \times 5}{(7+6) \times (40+1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^9 - 376}{5 \times 1 \times (8+40)} &:= \frac{2-(9-(3^{8-5}))}{4 \times (7-(0-(1^6)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9-3)) + (8-5)}{(7-6) \times (40-1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{58140} &:= \frac{2 \times 93 - 7 \times 6}{5+((8-1) \times 40)} &:= \frac{2-(9 \times (3-85))}{(4+70) \times 16} &:= \frac{2+(9-(3+(8-5)))}{7+(6-(4 \times (0 \times 1)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{84150} &:= \frac{2^{9+3-7} \times 6}{(8+4-1) \times 50} &:= \frac{2 \times (((9 \times 3) - 8) \times 5)}{4 \times (70+(1 \times 6))} & \\
 & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29385}{47016} &:= \frac{((2^{9-3}) - 8) \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times (0+16))} &:= \frac{2 \times ((9+38) \times 5)}{47 \times (0+16)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{51678} := \frac{(2+9) \times 4 \times 03}{((5+1) \times 6-7) \times 8} \\
 & &:= \frac{2 \times (9+(3+(8+5)))}{4+(70+(1 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(-2+9+4) \times 03}{51+6-7+8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{2-9+403}{(5 \times 16+7) \times 8} & & := \frac{29+406}{37+518} & & := \frac{2 \times ((9-4)^3+0)}{7+(651-8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{57816} &:= \frac{294+03}{578+1 \times 6} & & & & := \frac{2+(9 \times (4+(3-0)))}{(7+6) \times (5+(1 \times 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{61578} &:= \frac{294+03}{6 \times 15 \times 7-8} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29408}{61573} &:= \frac{2^9-40 \times 8}{(6+1) \times 57+3} & & := \frac{(2+(9+4)) \times 30}{(7+6) \times (5 \times 18)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{67518} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4 \times 03}{(67-5 \times 1) \times 8} & & & := \frac{2^{9+4-08}}{6+1+57+3} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29430}{81675} := \frac{2 \times 94+30}{(8 \times 16-7) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{294+03}{675-1+8} & & & & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{81675} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (40^3))}{(8-(1-(6+7)))^5} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29410}{87365} &:= \frac{2-9+41+0}{87+3+6+5} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29475}{61308} := \frac{(2 \times (9-4))^{7-5}}{6^{1 \times 3}-08} \\
 &:= \frac{(2-(9-4)) \times (-03)}{8-(1-(6+(7+5)))} & & & & & := \frac{(29-4) \times (7+5)}{6 \times 13 \times 08} \\
 &:= \frac{2+(9+(4-(-03)))}{8+(1+(6+(7 \times 5)))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29415}{60738} &:= \frac{2 \times (94+1)-5}{60 \times 7-38} & & := \frac{2 \times (9-4) \times 7 \times 5}{(61+30) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2-(9-(40+3))}{(8-(1-(6+7))) \times 5} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29415}{68370} &:= \frac{2^9-4 \times 1+5}{6+8 \times (3+7)+0} & & \\
 &:= \frac{(2+(9+(4-0))) \times 3}{8+((16 \times 7)+5)} & & & := \frac{2+94+15}{6 \times 8+3 \times 70} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29536}{70148} := \frac{2-9-5 \times (3-6)}{7+01 \times 4+8} \\
 &:= \frac{2+(9+(40+3))}{(8-(1 \times 6)) \times 75} & & & & & := \frac{2-9+5+3 \times 6}{7-01+4 \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (4-(0 \times 3)))}{8+(16 \times (7+5))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29430}{76518} &:= \frac{2-(9-(4 \times (3-0)))}{7-(6-(5-(1-8)))} & & := \frac{2-9-5+36}{70-1-4-8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2-(9-40)) \times 3}{((8 \times (1 \times 6))+7) \times 5} & & & := \frac{2+(9-(4-(3-0)))}{7+(6-(5-18))} & & := \frac{2^{9+5-3-6}}{70+14-8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (4 \times (03)))}{(8+(16 \times 7)) \times 5} & & & := \frac{2 \times (9+(4-(3-0)))}{(7+6) \times (5-(1^8))} & & := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (5-3+6)}{70 \times (1+4)-8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9^{4+0 \times 3})}{81 \times (6 \times 75)} & & & := \frac{(2 \times 9)+(4+(3-0))}{7+(65+(1-8))} & & \\
 &:= \frac{2+(940+3)}{(81-6) \times (7 \times 5)} & & & := \frac{2 \times ((9-4) \times (3-0))}{(7 \times (6+(5-1)))+8} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29547}{36180} := \frac{2 \times ((9+5) \times 4-7)}{3 \times (6-1) \times 8+0} \\
 & & & & := \frac{(2^9-4)+(3-0)}{7-(6-(5 \times 18))} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29406}{37518} &:= \frac{29 \times 4+0 \times 6}{37 \times (5-1^8)} & & & := \frac{2 \times (9-(4-30))}{(7+6) \times (5+(1+8))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29574}{38160} := \frac{2 \times (9+5)+7-4}{3 \times 8+16+0} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 9+40) \times 6}{37 \times (5-1+8)} & & & := \frac{2+(9+(4^3+0))}{(7 \times ((6 \times 5)-1))-8} & & := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (5 \times 7-4)}{(3+8+1) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{29+4 \times 0 \times 6}{3+7 \times (5+1)-8} & & & := \frac{(2+(9-4)) \times 30}{7 \times (6 \times (5+(1 \times 8)))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{29574}{80136} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 5+7-4}{(8-01) \times 36}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 5) + 7 - 4}{80 + 1 - 3 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29578}{63014} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 5) + 7 + 8}{63 - 014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29583}{46710} := \frac{2 \times (9 + 5 + 8 - 3)}{(4 + 6) \times (7 - 1) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - 5) + 8 + 3}{(4 + 6 - 7) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{43758} := \frac{29 - 6 \times 01}{4 + 3 \times (7 - 5 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^9 - 6 \times 01}{4 \times 37 \times 5 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{73485} := \frac{2^9 + 60 \times 1}{(73 \times 4 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{75348} := \frac{2 + (9 - (6 \times (0 \times 1)))}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 + (60 - 1)}{7 \times ((5 + (3 - 4)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (6 - 0)) + 1)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (6 - (-01))}{7 + (53 + (4 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times (60 \times 1)}{((7 + 5)^3) - 48}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times 60) - 1)}{7 \times ((53 - 4) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((9 \times (6 - 0)) - 1)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times (6 \times 01)}{7 \times ((5 - 3) \times (4 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) + (6 \times (-01))}{(((7 - 5) \times 3)^4) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29610}{58374} := \frac{29 + 6 \times 1 + 0}{5 - 8 \times (3 - 7 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9 + 6) \times 10}{(5 \times 8^3 - 7) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29610}{83754} := \frac{29 + 6 \times 1 + 0}{8 + 37 + 54}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + 61) + 0}{8 \times (3 + 7) \times 5 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29631}{85407} := \frac{2 - 9 + 6 \times (3 + 1)}{(8 - 5 + 4) \times 07}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - 6 + 31)}{(8 + 5 \times 4) \times 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29637}{40851} := \frac{296 + 37}{408 + 51}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6 + 3)) - 7}{4 \times (0 \times 8 + 51)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 9 - 6) \times 37}{(4 + 08) \times 51}$$

$$:= \frac{296 - 37}{408 - 51}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29637}{84105} := \frac{2 + 9 + (6 + 3) \times 7}{(8 \times 4 + 10) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6 + 3)) - 7}{84 \times 1 \times 05}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 9 - 6) \times 37}{84 \times (10 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29638}{71540} := \frac{2 + 9 - 6 + 3 \times 8}{7 \times (1 + 5 + 4) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (96 - 38)}{7 \times 1^5 \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{29 \times (6 - 3) \times 8}{7 \times (1 + 5) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29640}{31785} := \frac{2 \times 96 - 40}{3 \times 1 \times 7 \times 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29640}{73815} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 6 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (38 - 1^5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29645}{38710} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times 6 + 4) + 5}{3 \times 8 \times 7 - 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29670}{41538} := \frac{(2 \times 9) - (6 + (7 - 0))}{((4 + (1^5)) \times 3) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 + (6 - (7 - 0)))}{4 + (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-6}) + (7 - 0)}{4 + (1 + (5 + (3 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))}{4 - (1 + (5 \times (3 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{29 - (6 - (7 - 0))}{4 + ((1^5) \times 38)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (6 \times (7 - 0)))}{4 + (1 \times (53 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 - (67 - 0))}{(4 \times 15) + (3 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (6 - 70))}{41 + ((5 + 3) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times 6)) + (7 - 0)}{41 + (5 \times (3 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (6 + 70))}{((4 - 1)^5) + (3 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 96) - (7 - 0)}{4 - (1 - ((5 - 3)^8))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 \times (6 \times (7 - 0)))}{4 \times (1 \times ((5^3) + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) - (67 - 0)}{(41 \times (5 \times 3)) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29673}{80541} := \frac{2 + 9 + 6 \times (7 - 3)}{80 + 5 \times (4 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{2+9+6 \times 7+3}{8 \times (05 \times 4-1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-9+6 \times 7) \times 3}{80+5 \times 41}$$

$$:= \frac{(2+9 \times 6) \times (7+3)}{80 \times (5 \times 4-1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29678}{30514} := \frac{2+9 \times 6+7+8}{3+05 \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9+6+7 \times 8)}{30 \times 5 \times 1-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29680}{57134} := \frac{(2+9-6) \times 8+0}{5+71-3+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29684}{37105} := \frac{(((2+9) \times 6)+8) \times 4}{(3+(71-0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times 6)) - 8) \times 4}{(3+7) \times (10 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times (9+6)) + 8) \times 4}{(37+(1-0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (8+4)}{(37-(1-0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (8-4)}{3+(7+(10 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((2+(9 \times 6)) \times 8) - 4}{37 \times (10+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2+(9-6)) \times 8)^4}{(3+(7+10))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2-(9 \times (6-8))) \times 4}{(3+(7+10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times ((9-6) \times 8)) - 4}{(3+(7+(1-0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times 6)) - (8 \times 4)}{((3+7) \times 10) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (96+8)) - 4}{3 \times ((7+10) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (96-8)) - 4}{(3 \times (7 \times 10)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 96) - (8-4)}{(37+10) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 96) - 84}{(37-10) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9+6-8}) - 4}{((3 \times 7) + 10) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-6}) - (8-4)}{3+(7+(1 \times (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-6}) \times (8+4)}{3 \times ((7+(1-0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-6}) + (8-4)}{3+(7-(1 \times (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2-((9 \times (6-8)) + 4)}{(3-(7 \times 1)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{2-((9 \times (6-8)) - 4)}{(3-(7-10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (((9-6) \times 8) - 4)}{(3+(7 \times (1-0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9-(6-8)) \times 4)}{((3 \times 7) + (1-0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times 6) - (8+4))}{3 \times (7 \times (1 \times (05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9+6) \times (8-4))}{(3+7) \times (10+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9-6) \times (8+4))}{3 \times ((7-(1-0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6-(8-4)))}{3+(7 \times (1-(-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6+(8-4)))}{3 \times ((7 \times 10) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{2^{9+6-8-4}}{3+(7 \times (1^{05}))}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(9 \times (6-(8-4)))}{3+(7+(10+5))}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(9 \times (6+(8+4)))}{(3 \times (7 \times 10)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2+(9 \times (6+(8-4)))}{3+(7+105)}$$

$$:= \frac{296-(8-4)}{(3+(7 \times 10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{296+(8-4)}{(37 \times 10) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{2968+4}{3710+5}$$

$$:= \frac{2968-4}{3710-5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29714}{83056} := \frac{2+9^{7-1-4}}{8 \times (30+5-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29718}{36504} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 7 + 1^8}{3 \times (6+50-4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29718}{65403} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 71 - 8}{65 \times (40+3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29736}{58410} := \frac{2 \times ((9-7)^3 + 6)}{5 \times (8+4-1) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{2-9+7 \times (3+6)}{5 \times (8+4+10)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (7-3) + 6)}{5 \times (8 \times 4 + 1) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29748}{61305} := \frac{2+9 \times (74+8)}{61 \times (30-5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29750}{81634} := \frac{2^9 - 7 - 5 + 0}{(8-1^6)^3 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{31806} := \frac{2+9-7+54}{31 \times (8-06)}$$

$$:= \frac{29 \times (7+5-4)}{31 \times 8 + 0 \times 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{29 \times (7 + 5 \times 4)}{31 + 806} \\ &:= \frac{29 \times (7 \times 5 - 4)}{31^{8-06}} \\ &:= \frac{29 \times ((7 + 5) \times 4)}{31 \times 8 \times 06} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{36018} := \frac{2 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 4}{3 \times (6 - 01) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{36801} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (7 + 5) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 \times 8 - 01)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{83106} := \frac{29 \times (7 + 5 - 4)}{8 \times 3^{10-6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{86130} := \frac{2 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 4}{86 - 1 - 30}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{29760}{41385} &:= \frac{2 + 9 - 7 + 60}{4 \times (13 + 8) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{2^{9-7+6} + 0}{4 \times (1 + 3 + 85)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29785}{41630} := \frac{2^9 - 7 + 8 + 5}{4 \times (1 + 6 \times 30)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29830}{76145} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times (8 + 30)}{7 \times 6 + 1 + 4^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{40716} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8 - 3) - 5}{4 + 07 \times 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{41067} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8 - 3) - 5}{4 + 106 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{61047} := \frac{2 \times (98 - 3) + 5}{(61 - 04) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{61074} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8 - 3) - 5}{6 \times (1 + 07 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{67014} := \frac{2 \times (98 - 3) + 5}{6 \times (70 - 1 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{71604} := \frac{(((2 + 9) \times 8) + 3) \times 5}{7 \times (160 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((2 + 9) \times (8 - 3)) + 5}{(7 - 1) \times (6 \times (04))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (8 + 3))) + 5}{(7 \times (16 - 0)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (8 + 3))) - 5}{7 \times (16 + (-04))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^{9-8+3}) \times 5}{(7 + 1) \times (6 \times (04))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2^9) + (83 + 5)}{(7 - 1) \times (60 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + ((9 - 8) \times 3)) \times 5}{(7 - 1) \times (6 - (-04))}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + ((9 - 8)^3)) \times 5}{(7 - 16) \times (-04)}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + (9 + (8 + 3))) \times 5}{(7 - (1 - 60)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 98) \times (3 + 5)}{(7 + 1) \times (60 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 - (9 + (8 - 35))}{(7 - (1 - (6 - 0))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 \times 8) + (3 + 5))}{(7 - 1) \times (60 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 + (8 - 3)) \times 5)}{(7 - 1) \times (60 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times ((9 - 8) \times 35)}{7 \times (1 \times (6 \times (04)))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (8 + (3 - 5)))}{7 + (1 + (60 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + ((9 - 8) \times (3 + 5))}{(7 - (1^6 + 0)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + (9 - (8 + (3 - 5)))}{7 - (1 - (6 - (0 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{298 - (3 - 5)}{716 - (-04)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29845}{67310} := \frac{2 \times (9 + 8 + 4) + 5}{6 + (7 + 3) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29850}{36417} := \frac{2 + 98 - 50}{3 \times 6 \times (4 - 1) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29853}{40176} := \frac{29 \times 8 - 5^3}{4 \times (-01 + 7) \times 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{29853}{67410} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 85 - 3}{6 \times 7 \times (4 + 1) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + 9) \times 8 + 5) \times 3}{(67 - 4) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29861}{73504} := \frac{2 + 9 + 8 - 6 \times 1}{(-7 + 3 \times 5) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times (8 + 6 - 1)}{7^3 + 5 + 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(2 \times 9)^{8-6} + 1}{(7 - 3) \times 50 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{2 + 9 + 8 + 6 + 1}{7 + 3 + 50 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30128}{49765} := \frac{(3 + 01) \times 28}{(4 - 9 + 7 \times 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30128}{95764} := \frac{(3 - 01) \times 28}{(9 + 5) \times (7 + 6) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + 12) \times 8}{(9 + 5) \times 76 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30129}{68475} := \frac{3 - (0 - (1 - (2 - 9)))}{(6 \times (8 + 4 - 7)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (2 \times 9)))}{6 - (8 - (47 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 29))}{((6 + (8 - 4)) \times 7) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (-01)) \times (2 + 9)}{(6 + (8 - 4))^{7-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1+2)) + 9}{(6 - (8 - 47)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - 129)}{6 \times (8 + (47 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (1 \times (2+9))}{(6 + (8 - 4)) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1+6)) + 5}{(7 \times 84) - 29}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - 16) \times 5}{7 \times (8 + ((4 - 2) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 6 + 5))}{(7 \times (8 - 4)) + (2 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 6 - 5))}{7 - (8 + (4 - (2 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - ((1 - 6) \times 5))}{(7 \times (8 \times 4)) - 29}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (1 - (6 + 5)))}{((7 + 8) \times 4) + (2 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((1 + 6) \times 5))}{7 \times ((8 \times (4 + 2)) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 5)))}{((7 \times (8 - 4)) - 2) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times 65))}{7 - (8 + (4 - (2^9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 - ((1^6) \times 5)}{(7 \times ((8 - 4) \times 2)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{30 - ((1 - 6) \times 5)}{7 - (8 - ((4^2) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (1 \times (6 + 5))}{7 + (842 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (1 + 6 + 5)}{((7 \times 8) - 4) \times (2 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (16 + 5)}{(7 + 84) \times (2 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + ((1^6) \times 5)}{7 - ((8 + 4) \times (2 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 68}{(5 \times ((2 \times 7) + 9)) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 16)) + 8}{5 - (27 - (9 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 16)) + 8}{5 + (2 + (7 \times (9 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 16)) - 8}{5 \times (2 + (7 + (9 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^6)))^8}{(5 + 2) \times ((7 + 9) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 8}{(5 + ((2 \times 7) + 9)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times (6 + 8)}{(5 + 2)^{7-9+4}}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1 \times 6)) + 8}{5 + ((2 + 79) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1 \times 6)) - 8}{(5 + 2) \times (7 + (9 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + (1 \times 6)) \times 8}{((5 \times 27) - 9) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + (1 - 6)) \times 8}{5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (9 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((1^6) + 8))}{5 - (2 \times ((7 - 9) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (6 \times 8)))}{5 + (2 \times (7 + (9 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 68))}{5 + (27 + 94)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 8)))}{5 + ((27 \times 9) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (16 - 8))}{5 + (2 + (7 \times (9 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (1 \times (6 \times 8))}{5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (9 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (6 + 8))}{5 + ((2 + (7 + 9)) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30158}{49672} := \frac{3 + 01 + 5 + 8}{4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 1 - 5 + 8}{4 + 9 - 6 + 7^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (01 + 5) \times 8}{4 \times (9 - 6) + 72}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - 1) \times 5 + 8}{4 \times (9 + 6 \times (7 + 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30162}{47985} := \frac{(3 + 01) \times 6 - 2}{47 - 9 - 8 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 16 - 2}{(4 - 7 + 9 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 01 + 62}{4 + 7 + 9 + 85}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - 1) \times 6 + 2}{(4 \times (7 + 9) - 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 16^2}{(4 + 79 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30165}{78429} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 \times 6))) \times 5}{(7 + (8 - (4 - 2))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 5}{((7 + (8 - 4))^2) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - 16)) \times 5}{(7 \times ((8 \times 4) + 2)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^6))) \times 5}{7 + (8 + (4 - (2 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - (1^6)) \times 5}{7 - (8 - (42 \times 9))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30167}{84592} := \frac{30 + 1 \times 67}{8 \times (45 - 9 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30168}{52794} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 8}{5 \times ((2 \times (7 + 9)) - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 1)) + (6 \times 8)}{(5^2) + ((7 \times 9) - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30168}{94275} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1^6))) \times 8}{9 + ((4^2) + 75)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 8}{(9 \times 4) + (2 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 6)))^8}{((9 \times 4) + (2 \times 7))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 16)) + 8}{9 + (4 \times (2^{7-5}))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 16)) - 8}{((9 \times (4 - 2)) + 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^{-01+6}) \times 8}{(9^{4-2}) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 8}{(9 + (4 + 27)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times (6 \times 8)}{(9 + (4^2)) \times (7 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times 68}{(94 - (2 + 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - (1 - 6)) \times 8}{(9 + (4^2)) \times (7 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + (1 - 6)) \times 8}{(9 + (4^2))^{7-5}}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - 16) \times 8}{(9 - 4) \times (2 \times (7 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 68))}{(9 + (4 \times (2 + 7))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((1 + 6) \times 8))}{(9 - (4 - 2)) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (16 - 8))}{9 - (4 - (2 \times (7 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + 168)}{9 \times ((42 - 7) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (1 - (6 + 8)))}{9 + (4 + (2 + (7 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (16 - 8)}{(9 - 4) \times (2 \times 75)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30172}{98456} := \frac{3 \times (017 + 2)}{9 \times (8 - 4) \times 5 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{30 - 1 + 7 + 2}{98 - 4 + 5 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30178}{69524} := \frac{3 \times (01 + 78)}{6 \times 95 - 24}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{42957} := \frac{(3 + 01) \times 8 - 6}{4 \times 2 \times 9 - 5 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times 18 + 6}{(4 \times 29 - 5) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 01 + 8 \times 6}{4 \times 2 \times 9 - 5 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 1 \times 8 \times 6}{(4 + 2) \times 9 + 57}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + 1 + 8) \times 6}{4 + (2 + 9 \times 5) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{45279} := \frac{((3 - (-01)) \times 8) + 6}{4 - ((5 \times 2) - (7 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 \times 8))) \times 6}{(((4 + 5) \times 2) - 7) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1^8))) \times 6}{4 \times (5 + (2 - (7 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (-01)) \times (8 \times 6)}{4 + (5 + 279)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (-01)) \times (8 + 6)}{(4 \times (5^2)) - (7 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - 18)) \times 6}{(4 \times (5 \times (2 + 7))) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 1)) + (8 + 6)}{(4 \times (5^2)) - 79}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 86}{(4 \times 52) - 79}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times 8))) + 6}{4 + (5 + (27 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 18)) + 6}{4 + (5 + (2 + 79))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 18)) - 6}{(4 - (5 - (2 + 7))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^{01 \times 8}) \times 6}{(4 + 5)^{2 \times 7 - 9}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^8))) \times 6}{4 - ((5 + 2) \times (7 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^8)))^6}{(4 - 52) \times (7 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times (8 \times 6)}{4 \times ((5 \times (2 + 7)) - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times (8 + 6)}{4 - ((5^2) - (7 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - (1 \times 8)) \times 6}{(4 + ((5^2) - 7)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - (1^8)) \times 6}{(4 - (5 \times (2 - 7))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1 + 8)) + 6}{(45 \times (2 + 7)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times (1 + 8)) - 6}{(45 \times (2 + 7)) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + (1^8)) \times 6}{(45 - (2 \times 7)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + 1) \times (8 - 6)}{(4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 - 1) \times (8 \times 6)}{(45^2) + (7 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((1^8) + 6))}{4 - (52 - (7 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1^{86}))}{(4 - (5 + 2)) \times (7 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (8 + 6)))}{4 + (5 + (2 + (7 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (8 - 6)))}{4 + (5 - (2 + (7 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 86))}{4 + (5 + (2 \times (7 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8 \times 6)))}{4 \times ((5 \times (2 + 7)) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8^6)))}{(4^5) \times ((2^7) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8 + 6)))}{(4 \times ((5^2) - 7)) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (18 \times 6))}{(45 + (2 + 7)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (18 + 6))}{4 - (52 \times (7 - 9))}$$

$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (18 - 6))}{4 + (5 - ((2 - 7) \times 9))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{97524} := \frac{((3 - (-01)) \times 8) - 6}{(9 \times (7 + 5)) - 24}$	$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 + 9))) + 5}{7 \times (2 \times (4 - (6 - 8)))}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + 186)}{((4 \times (5^2)) - 7) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(30 \times 18) + 6}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 + 2) \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^9))) \times 5}{(7 - (2 - (4 - 6))) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - ((1^8) - 6))}{(4 \times (5 + 2)) - (7 + 9)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}{9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 - 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - 9))) \times 5}{(7 \times (2 \times (4 + 6))) - 8}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (1 - (8 \times 6)))}{(4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)) - 9}$	$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (8 \times 6)))}{(9 - (7 - 5)) \times 24}$	$:= \frac{(3 + (-01)) \times (9 \times 5)}{(7 + (2 \times (4 + 6))) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}{4 + (5 \times (2 - (7 - 9)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (8 \times 6))}{9 \times (7 + (5 + (2^4)))}$	$:= \frac{(30 - (1 \times 9)) \times 5}{7 \times (2 \times (4 + (6 + 8)))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (1^{86}))}{4 - (5 - (2 - (7 - 9)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (1 + 86)}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 2) - 4))}$	$:= \frac{(30 - (1 + 9)) \times 5}{(7 + (2 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{30 \times ((1^8) + 6)}{((4 \times (5 + 2)) + 7) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(30 + (1 + 8)) \times 6}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 - 2) \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(30 \times (1 \times 9)) - 5}{(7 \times (2 \times 46)) - 8}$
$:= \frac{30 \times (18 \times 6)}{4 \times (5 \times (27 \times 9))}$	$:= \frac{301 - (8 - 6)}{(97 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4}$	$:= \frac{(30 + (1 \times 9)) \times 5}{(7 + 2) \times (4 + (6 \times 8))}$
$:= \frac{30 \times (18 - 6)}{4 + (527 + 9)}$		$:= \frac{(30 + (1 + 9)) \times 5}{(7 \times 2 + 46) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{30 + ((1 + 8) \times 6)}{(4 + (5 - (2 - 7))) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{42768} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{(4 - 2 + 7) \times 6 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(30 + 19) \times 5}{7 \times ((2 \times 46) - 8)}$
$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (8 \times 6))}{(4 - (5 - (2 \times 7))) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{46728} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{4 \times (6 + 7 \times 2 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - ((1 - 9) \times 5))}{((7 \times (2 + 4)) - 6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (8 + 6))}{(4^{5-2}) - (7 - 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{46827} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{468 - 2 + 7}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((1 + 9) \times 5))}{(7 - 2) \times (4 + 68)}$
$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (8 - 6))}{4 \times (((5 - 2) \times 7) - 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{64782} := \frac{(3 - 01 + 9) \times 5}{6 \times (4 \times 7 - 8) - 2}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (1 + (9 - 5)))}{(7 \times (2 - (4 - 6))) + 8}$
$:= \frac{30 + (18 \times 6)}{(4 + (5 + (2 \times 7))) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(3 + 019) \times 5}{6 \times (47 - 8) + 2}$	$:= \frac{30 - ((1 - 9) \times 5)}{(7 + ((2 \times 4) + 6)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{30 + (18 + 6)}{(4 \times ((5^2) - 7)) + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{72468} := \frac{((3 \times (-01)) + 9) \times 5}{(7 + ((2 \times 4) - 6)) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (1 \times (9^5))}{((7 - (2 - 4))^6) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{30 + 186}{(4 + (5 + 27)) \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 \times 9))) \times 5}{72 + (4 + 68)}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (1 \times (9 + 5))}{7 \times (2 \times (4 + 68))}$
$:= \frac{3018 + 6}{4527 + 9}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1^9))) \times 5}{(7 - (2 + 4)) \times (6 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (1 + (9 \times 5))}{(7 + 2) \times (46 \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{3018 - 6}{4527 - 9}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (-01)) \times (9 \times 5)}{(7 - (2 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (19 + 5)}{(7 + 2) \times (4 \times (6 \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{49725} := \frac{3 \times 01 \times 86}{(4 + 9 + 72) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - 19)) \times 5}{(7 + (2 + (4 \times 6))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{30 + ((1 + 9) \times 5)}{(7 \times 2 + (4 + 6)) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{74529} := \frac{3 \times 01 \times 86}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)}$	$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 19)) + 5}{(7 \times 2) - (4 + (6 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (1 \times (9 \times 5))}{(7 \times (2^4)) + 68}$

$$:= \frac{30 + 195}{72 + 468}$$

$$:= \frac{301 + (9 + 5)}{7 \times (2 \times (46 + 8))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{76824} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{82764} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{8^2 \times (7 + 6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{86427} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 9) + 5}{864 + 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{86742} := \frac{(3 - 01 + 9) \times 5}{(8 + 67 + 4) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times 1 \times 9 + 5}{8 \times 6 + 742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30257}{86941} := \frac{30 + (2 + 5) \times 7}{(8 \times 6 + 9) \times 4 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30258}{97416} := \frac{3 + 0 - 2 + 5 \times 8}{97 + 41 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30264}{51798} := \frac{3 \times 026 \times 4}{517 + 9 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{54891} := \frac{3 + (02 + 6) \times 7}{(5 \times 4 - 8) \times 9 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{58941} := \frac{3 \times (-02 + 6) + 7}{5 + 8 \times (9 - 4 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (2 + 6) + 7}{58 \times 9 - 41}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 + 2 + 6) \times 7}{58 \times 9 - 4 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{85491} := \frac{3 \times (02^6 - 7)}{8 + 5 \times (4 + 91)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30275}{89614} := \frac{3 + 027 - 5}{8 + 9 + 61 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 2 \times 7 \times 5}{8 \times (9 + (6 + 1) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 027) \times 5}{8 \times (9 \times 6 + 1) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{51678} := \frac{3 \times (-02 + 9) - 4}{5 \times 1 \times 6 + 7 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(30 \times 2 - 9) \times 4}{5 \times (1 + 67) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{51867} := \frac{3 \times (02 \times 9 + 4)}{5 \times (18 + 6) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{57618} := \frac{(30 \times 2 - 9) \times 4}{5 \times 76 \times 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{65178} := \frac{3 \times (02 \times 9 + 4)}{65 - 1 + 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{81675} := \frac{3 \times (-02 + 9 \times 4)}{(8 \times 1 \times 6 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{86751} := \frac{3^{02} + 9 + 4}{8 \times (6 + 7 - 5) - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 2 \times 9 - 4}{8 + 67 + 51}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{87516} := \frac{3 \times (0 - (2 - (9 - 4)))}{8 + (7 - (5 - 16))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (2 + (9 + 4)))}{87 - (5 \times (1 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{-02+9-4}}{8 + (7 \times (5 - (1 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (29 + 4))}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (1^6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (2 + 94))}{(8 \times (7 \times (5 \times 1))) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 2) + (9 \times 4))}{(8 - (7 - 51)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((02 \times (9 \times 4)))}{8 \times ((7 + (5 + 1)) \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30426}{81597} := \frac{30 - 4 + 2 - 6}{8 - 1 + 59 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 4 \times 2 + 6}{8 \times 15 - 9 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + 4 \times 2^6}{(81 + 5) \times 9 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30429}{86751} := \frac{304 + 2 \times 9}{867 + 51}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30456}{71928} := \frac{3 + 04 \times (5 + 6)}{7 \times (19 - 2) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30472}{59186} := \frac{3 + 047 + 2}{5 + 9 + 1 + 86}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30481}{69275} := \frac{3 \times ((04 + (8 - 1)))}{6 + ((9^2) - (7 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + (4 \times (8 + 1))}{6 + (9 + (27 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (4 - 8))) - 1}{6 + (9 - (2 - (7 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{30 + (48 - 1)}{((6 \times (9 - 2)) - 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (4 + 81))}{((6 \times 9) - (2 \times 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((04 \times 8) + 1))}{((6 \times 9) - (2 + 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (4 - 81))}{(6 + (92 + 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{304 - (8 - 1)}{(6 + 9) \times ((2 + 7) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times (4 + (8 - 1))}{6 \times ((9 \times 2 + 7) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{30 \times ((4 \times 8) + 1)}{(6 + 9) \times (2 \times 75)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{30485}{79261} := \frac{((3^{04}) - 8) \times 5}{(79 \times (2 \times 6)) + 1} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 \times 8))) \times 5}{7 \times (((9 + 2) \times 6) - 1)} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 + 8))) \times 5}{((7 + 9)^2) - 61} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 48)) + 5}{7 + (9 + (2 - (6 - 1)))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (04)) + (8 + 5)}{(7 \times (9 \times 2)) - 61} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (0 - (4 - 8))) \times 5}{7 \times (9 - (2 - (6 \times 1)))} \\ & := \frac{(30 \times 4) - (8 \times 5)}{(7 + 9) \times ((2 \times 6) + 1)} \\ & := \frac{(30 \times 4) + (8 \times 5)}{(7 + 9) \times (26 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - ((4 \times 8) + 5))}{7 + (92 + (6 - 1))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{7 + ((9 \times (2 + 6)) - 1)} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (4 \times (8 + 5)))}{79 + (2^6 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{((7 + 9) \times 2) + (6 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (4 + (8 + 5)))}{7 - (9 \times (2 - (6 + 1)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (4 + (8 - 5)))}{7 + (9 + (2 \times (6 - 1)))} \\ & := \frac{30 + (4 \times (8 \times 5))}{7 + (((9^2) \times 6) + 1)} \\ & \frac{30492}{51876} := \frac{(3 + 04) \times (9 + 2)}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6} \\ & \frac{30492}{57816} := \frac{(30 + 4) \times 9 + 2}{578 + 1 \times 6} \\ & \frac{30492}{61578} := \frac{(30 + 4) \times 9 + 2}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8} \\ & \frac{30492}{67518} := \frac{3 + 04 + 9 - 2}{6 - 7 + (5 - 1) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 + (-04 + 9)^2}{67 - 5 \times 1^8} \\ & := \frac{(30 + 4) \times 9 + 2}{675 - 1 + 8} \\ & \frac{30492}{81675} := \frac{3 + (-04 + 9)^2}{(8 + 1^6 \times 7) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 04 \times (9 - 2)}{(8 + 1 - 6) \times 75} \\ & := \frac{30 \times (4 + 9) + 2}{(8 + 1 \times 6) \times 75} \\ & := \frac{30 + (4 + 9) \times 2}{(8 - 1 \times 6) \times 75} \\ & \frac{30495}{82176} := \frac{3^{04} + 9 + 5}{(8 \times 2)^{1+7-6}} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 04 \times 95}{8^{2+1^7} \times 6} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (0 \times 4 + 95)}{8 \times 2 \times (1 + 7) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(30 - 4) \times 95}{8^{2+1} \times (7 + 6)} \\ & \frac{30498}{51267} := \frac{(30 - 4) \times (9 + 8)}{5^{1+2} \times 6 - 7} \\ & \frac{30528}{41976} := \frac{3 + (0 - (5 - (2 + 8)))}{4 - (1 - (9 - (7 - 6)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (2 \times 8)))}{41 - (9 - (7 - 6))} \\ & := \frac{30 + ((5 \times 2) - 8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 + (7 - 6)))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 - 2))) \times 8}{(4 + ((1^9) \times 7)) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{((3 - (-05))^2) - 8}{(4 \times 19) + (7 - 6)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (((05 - 2) \times 8))}{4 - (1 - ((9 + 7) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}{(4 \times (19 + 7)) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8}{4 + ((19 \times 7) + 6)} \\ & := \frac{(30 + 52) \times 8}{41 \times (9 + (7 + 6))} \\ & := \frac{(30 \times 5) + (2 - 8)}{((4 \times (1 + 9)) - 7) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - 2)) \times 8}{4 + (1 \times (9 + (7 \times 6)))} \\ & := \frac{(3^{7-4-1}) \times 8}{((4 - 1) \times 97) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5^2))) \times 8}{4 \times ((1^9) + 76)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (2 \times 8)}{4 + ((1 + (9 - 7)) \times 6)} \\ & \frac{30582}{91746} := \frac{((3 - (-05)) \times 8)^2}{(9 + (1 - 7)) \times (4^6)} \\ & := \frac{((3 - (-05)) \times 8) + 2}{9 \times (1 \times ((7 \times 4) - 6))} \\ & := \frac{((3 \times (05)) + 8) \times 2}{(9 + (1 - 7)) \times 46} \\ & := \frac{((30 - 5) \times 8) + 2}{(9 \times (17 \times 4)) - 6} \\ & := \frac{((30 - 5) \times 8) - 2}{9 \times (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)) \times 2}{(9 - (1 - (7 - 4))) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 \times 8))) \times 2}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + 8))) \times 2}{(9 \times (1 + 7)) + (4 \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (-05)) \times (8 \times 2)}{(9 + (1 \times 7)) \times (4 \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (-05)) \times (8 - 2)}{91 + (7 + 46)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8))^2}{9 \times ((1 + 7) \times (4 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3^{05}) - (8 \times 2)}{(9 \times (1 + 74)) + 6} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (8 + 2)))}{9 \times (1 + (7 + (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8)) + 2}{9 - (1 - (7 \times (4 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3^{05}) \times (8^2)}{(9 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))^6} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (8 - 2)))}{(9 + (1 - (7 - 4))) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))^2}{9 \times (17 + (4 + 6))} &:= \frac{(3^{05}) \times (8 + 2)}{(9 + 1) \times ((7 - 4)^6)} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + 82))}{9 \times (((1^7) + 4) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) + 2}{9 + ((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3^{05}) \times (8 - 2)}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (58 - 2))}{9 + (1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) - 2}{9 - ((1 - (7 - 4)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (5 - 8)))^2}{9 \times ((1 - 7) \times (4 - 6))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 \times (5 - 82))}{9 \times (1^{746})} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8 \times 2)}{9 - (1 \times (7 - 46))} &:= \frac{(30 - (5 + 8)) \times 2}{(9 \times (1 + (7 + 4))) - 6} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - 582)}{9 + 1746} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8^2)}{(9 - (1^7)) \times (4 \times 6)} &:= \frac{(30 \times 5) - (8 \times 2)}{((9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 4) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 - (5 - 8))^2)}{9 \times (1 \times (7 - (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8 + 2)}{(9 - (1 + (7 - 4))) \times 6} &:= \frac{(30 \times 5) + (8 \times 2)}{(9 + (1 \times 74)) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 + 2))}{9 \times (1 + (7 - (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + 82}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) - 6} &:= \frac{(30 \times 5) + (8 + 2)}{(91 - (7 + 4)) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 82)}{9 + (1 \times ((7 - 4)^6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))) - 2}{((9 \times (1 \times 7)) - 4) \times 6} &:= \frac{(30^5) \times (8 + 2)}{(9 + (17 + 4))^6} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 58) + 2)}{9 + (1 \times (7 - (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + 8))) + 2}{(9 \times (17 - 4)) + 6} &:= \frac{(30 + 5) \times (8 \times 2)}{(9 + 1) \times (7 \times (4 \times 6))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (5 - (8 + 2)))}{9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + 8))) - 2}{(9 \times (17 - 4)) - 6} &:= \frac{(30 + 5) \times (8 - 2)}{9 \times (1 \times (7 \times (4 + 6)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) + 2))}{(91 - (7 \times 4)) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (05)) + (8 \times 2)}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) - 6} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 \times 2))}{91 - ((7 \times 4) + 6)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) - 2))}{9 \times (((1 + 7) \times 4) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (05)) + (8 - 2)}{9 + (1 + (7 + 46))} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 + 2))}{9 - (1 - (7 + (4 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((5 + 8) \times 2))}{9 \times (((1 + 7) \times 4) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 58)) + 2}{(91 - (7 - 4)) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 5) - 82)}{(9 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))) - 6} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((5 + 8)^2))}{9 \times (1 + (7 \times (4 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (-05)) + 82}{9 + ((1 + 7) \times (4 \times 6))} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 58) - 2)}{9 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 6)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5 \times (8 \times 2)))}{9 \times (1 \times (74 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 5 + 8} \times 2}{(9 \times (1 + (7 - 4))) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 - (8 - 2)))}{9 + (1 \times (7 - (4 + 6)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5^{8-2}))}{9 \times (((1^7) + 4)^6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^{-05+8}) \times 2}{9 \times (1 + (7 + (4 + 6)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 \times (8 + 2)))}{91 + (74 - 6)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 \times 2)))}{9 + (174 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^{-05+8}) + 2}{9 + ((17 - 4) \times 6)} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (8 \times 2)))}{(9 + (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5 + (8^2)))}{9 \times (1 + (74 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^{-05+8}) - 2}{9 + (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 6))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (8^2)))}{9 \times ((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 + 2)))}{9 \times (1 - (7 \times (4 - 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 - 2)))}{9 \times ((1^7) + (4 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{3058 - 2}{9174 - 6}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (6 - 18))}{4 + (5 - (9 \times (2 - 7)))}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (58 - 2))}{(9 + (1 + 74)) \times 6}$		$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((6 + 1) \times 8))}{4 + (5 + (9 \times 27))}$
$:= \frac{3^{-05+8}^2}{9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 6)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{45927} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 6) - 1)) \times 8}{4 - (5 - ((9 - 2) \times 7))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((6 - 1) \times 8))}{4 \times (59 - (2 \times 7))}$
$:= \frac{3^{0 \times 58 + 2}}{9 + (1 + (7 + (4 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (6 + 1))) \times 8}{4 \times (5 + (9 \times 2 + 7))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (6 \times (1 \times 8)))}{4 \times (5 + ((9 - 2) \times 7))}$
$:= \frac{3^{-05+8+2}}{9 \times (1 + (74 + 6))}$	$:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 \times 1))) + 8}{4 + (((5 + 9) \times 2) + 7)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (6 \times 18))}{(4 + (5 + 9)) \times 27}$
$:= \frac{3 + ((0 - (5 - 8))^2)}{9 \times (1 - (7 - (4 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(30 - (6 \times 1)) \times 8}{4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 27)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (6 \times (1^8)))}{4 + (5 - (9 - 27))}$
$:= \frac{3 + ((0 \times 58) - 2)}{9 - (1 + (7 + (4 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(30 \times (6 - 1)) + 8}{(4 \times (59 + 2)) - 7}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (6 + (1 \times 8)))}{4 + ((5 \times 9) + (2 \times 7))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (5 - (8 + 2)))}{9 + (1 - (7 \times (4 - 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(30 \times (6 - 1)) - 8}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 + 2))) - 7}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (6 + 18))}{4 + (5 + (92 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (5 - (8 - 2)))}{9 - (1 \times (7 - (4 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{(30 \times 6) + 18}{((4 \times 5) - 9) \times 27}$	$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (6 - (1 + 8)))}{4 + (5 - (9 - (2 + 7)))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (5 - 82))}{(9 + (1^7)) \times (4 \times 6)}$	$:= \frac{(30 + (6 \times 1)) \times 8}{459 - 27}$	$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (6 + (1 - 8)))}{(4 \times 5) - (9 - (2 - 7))}$
$:= \frac{30 - (5 - (8^2))}{(9 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))) + 6}$	$:= \frac{(30 + (6 + 1)) \times 8}{4 + (5 \times ((9^2) + 7))}$	$:= \frac{30 \times ((6 + 1) \times 8)}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (2 \times 7)))}$
$:= \frac{30 - (5 - (8 + 2))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) + 6}$	$:= \frac{(30 - 6) \times (1 + 8)}{(45 - 9) \times (2 + 7)}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (6 - (1^8))}{(4 + 5) \times (9 \times 2 + 7)}$
$:= \frac{30 \times (5 + (8 - 2))}{(91 + 74) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 6) - (1 + 8))}{4 - ((5 - (9 - 2)) \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (6 \times 18)}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 27))}$
$:= \frac{30 + (5 \times (8 \times 2))}{9 - (1 - (7 \times 46))}$	$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (6 - (1 - 8)))}{4 + (5 \times (9 + (2 - 7)))}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (6 + (1 \times 8))}{(4 + (5 + (9^2))) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{30 + (5 \times (8 - 2))}{(9 + (17 + 4)) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (6 + (1^8)))}{(4 \times 5) + (9 - (2 \times 7))}$	$:= \frac{30 + ((6 + 1) \times 8)}{4 + (5 \times (9 \times 2 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{30 + (5 + (8 \times 2))}{9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 + 6)))}$	$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (6 + (1 - 8)))}{4 - (5 - (9 + (2 - 7)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + ((6 - 1) \times 8)}{(4 \times ((5 + 9) \times 2)) - 7}$
$:= \frac{305 - (8^2)}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) - 6}$	$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (61 - 8))}{4 - (5 - (92 - 7))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (6 - (1 \times 8))}{(4 - (5 - (9 - 2))) \times 7}$
$:= \frac{305 + 8 \times 2}{917 + 46}$	$:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 6) + 18)}{45 + (9 + 27)}$	$:= \frac{30 + (6 \times (1 + 8))}{45 + (9 \times (2 + 7))}$
$:= \frac{305 - 82}{9 \times (1 + 74) - 6}$	$:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 61) + 8)}{4 \times (5 + (9 + (2 - 7)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (6 \times 18)}{4 + (((5 + 9)^2) + 7)}$
$:= \frac{3058 + 2}{9174 + 6}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (6 \times (1 - 8)))}{(4 + (5 + (9 \times 2))) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{30 + (6 + (1 \times 8))}{4 + ((5 \times (9 + 2)) + 7)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{30 + (61 \times 8)}{(4 \times ((5 + 9)^2)) - 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30619}{47528} & := \frac{30 \times (6 + 1) - 9}{4 + 7 \times (52 - 8)} & := \frac{((3 - (-07))^2) \times 9}{(6 - 1) \times (45 \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{30 + 618}{45 + 927} & & & := \frac{((3 + (-07)) \times 2) + 9}{(6 \times (1 \times (4 - 5))) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{306 \times (1 + 8)}{459 \times (2 + 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30621}{84597} & := \frac{30 \times 6 - 2 - 1}{8 - 4 + 5 \times 97} & := \frac{((30 + 7) \times 2) + 9}{6 + (1 \times (4 \times (5 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{306 + (1 \times 8)}{4 + ((5 \times 92) + 7)} & & & := \frac{((30 + 7) \times 2) - 9}{(6 + (1 \times 4)) \times (5 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{49572} & := \frac{3 \times (06 + 1^8)}{4 + (9 - 5) \times 7 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30624}{98571} & := \frac{(30 - 6) \times 2 \times 4}{(98 + 5) \times (7 - 1)} & := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 7) - 2))^9}{(6 + (1 \times 4)) \times (5^8)} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times (06 + 1 \times 8)}{4 + 9 + 57 - 2} & & & := \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times (2 \times 9)}{(6 - (1 - 4)) \times (5 \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times (06 + 1) \times 8}{4 \times (9 + 57 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30672}{58149} & := \frac{30 - 6 + 72}{(5 + 8 + 1) \times (4 + 9)} & := \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times (2 + 9)}{(6 - 1) \times (4 + (5 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{30 \times 6 + 1 + 8}{(49 - 5) \times 7 - 2} & & := \frac{(30 - 6) \times 7 \times 2}{(5 + 8 \times 1) \times 49} & := \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times 29}{(6 + (1 \times 4)) \times 58} \\
 & := \frac{30 + 6 \times (1 + 8)}{4 \times (9 + 5 \times (7 - 2))} & & & := \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 72)) + 9}{6 - (1 \times (4 \times (5 - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times 06 \times (-1 + 8)}{(4 + (9 + 5) \times 7) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30685}{47291} & := \frac{(3 + 06 + 8) \times 5}{4 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 + 1} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 \times 2))) + 9}{6 \times (1 \times (4 + (5 + 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{52974} & := \frac{306 + 1 + 8}{5 + 2^9 + 7 \times 4} & & := \frac{30 \times (6 + 8) + 5}{4 + 7 \times (2 + 91)} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7^2))) + 9}{6 \times (1 \times (4 \times (5 + 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{59724} & := \frac{(3 + 06) \times (1 + 8)}{5 - 9 \times (7 - 24)} & & & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 2))) + 9}{6 \times (1 \times ((4 \times 5) - 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{72954} & := \frac{(3 + 06) \times (1 + 8)}{7 + 2 \times 95 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30687}{49215} & := \frac{3 - 06 + 8 \times 7}{4 + 9^{2^{15}}} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 2))) - 9}{6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 - 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{74592} & := \frac{3^{06^{18}}}{(7 - 4) \times 592} & & & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 - 2))) + 9}{6 \times (1 + (4 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{79542} & := \frac{30 \times 6 + 1 + 8}{7 + 9 \times 54 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30694}{57812} & := \frac{3 + 06 + 94}{((5 + 7) \times 8 + 1) \times 2} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 - 2))) - 9}{6 - (1 - (4 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{94752} & := \frac{3^{06^{18}}}{94 \times (7 + 5) \times 2} & & & := \frac{(3 \times (07)) - (2 + 9)}{(6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{95742} & := \frac{3 \times 06 \times (-1 + 8)}{(9 + 5) \times 7 \times 4 + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30721}{58469} & := \frac{3 + 07 + 21}{5 \times (8 - 4 + 6) + 9} & := \frac{(3 \times (07)) + (2 + 9)}{(6 + (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{97524} & := \frac{3 + 06 + 18}{9 - 7 \times (5 - 2^4)} & & & := \frac{3^{07-2} + 9}{(6 + 1) \times ((4 + 5) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times (0 \times 6 + 18)}{(9 + 75) \times 2 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30729}{61458} & := \frac{((3 - (-07)) \times 2) + 9}{6 + (1 \times (4 \times (5 + 8)))} & := \frac{3^{07-2} - 9}{6 \times ((14 \times 5) + 8)} \\
 & & & := \frac{((3 - (-07)) \times 2) - 9}{6 - (1 - (4 + (5 + 8)))} & := \frac{(30 - (7 \times 2)) \times 9}{(6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(30 \times (7 \times 2)) - 9}{6 \times (145 - 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - (2 \times 9)))}{6 \times (14 + (5 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 + (2 - 9))}{6 - (1 \times (4 - 58))}$
$:= \frac{(30 \times (7 + 2)) - 9}{(6 - (1 - 4)) \times 58}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - (2 + 9)))}{6 + (1 + (4 + (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{30 \times (7 + 29)}{6 \times (1 \times (45 \times 8))}$
$:= \frac{(30 \times (7 - 2)) + 9}{6 \times (1 + (4 \times (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - 29))}{((6 + 1) \times (4 \times 5)) - 8}$	$:= \frac{30 + (7 \times 2 + 9)}{(6 \times (14 + 5)) - 8}$
$:= \frac{(30 \times 7) - (2 - 9)}{(6 + 1) \times (4 + 58)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7^2) + 9))}{6 \times ((1^4) \times 58)}$	$:= \frac{30 + ((7 \times 2) - 9)}{6 - ((1 - (4 + 5)) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{(30 \times 7) + (2 - 9)}{(6 + 1^4) \times 58}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7^2) - 9))}{6 \times ((1^4) \times (5 \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 + ((7^2) - 9)}{(6 - 1) \times ((4 \times 5) + 8)}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 \times 2 + 9))}{(6 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) - 8}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7 - 2) \times 9))}{6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 \times 8)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (7 - (2 \times 9))}{6 - (((1^4) - 5) \times 8)}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((7 \times 2) - 9))}{6 + (1 - (4 - (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7 - 2)^9))}{6 \times ((1 + 4) \times (5^8))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (7 - (2 - 9))}{(6 + ((1^4) \times 5)) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((7^2) + 9))}{(6 \times (14 + 5)) + 8}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 - (2 - 9)))}{6 + ((14 \times 5) + 8)}$	$:= \frac{30 + (72 + 9)}{6 \times (1 - (4 - (5 \times 8)))}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((7^2) - 9))}{6 + ((1 + (4 + 5)) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + (2 + 9)))}{6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 + 8)))}$	$:= \frac{30 + (72 - 9)}{(61 \times 4) - 58}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((7 - 2) \times 9))}{6 \times ((1 - (4 - 5)) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + 29))}{(6 + (1 + (4 \times 5))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{307 - (2 - 9)}{((6 - 1)^4) - (5 - 8)}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 - (2 - 9)))}{6 + (1 \times ((4 \times 5) + 8))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (72 - 9))}{6 \times (1 + (4 + 58))}$	$:= \frac{307 + 29}{614 + 58}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 \times 29))}{(6 \times (14 \times 5)) - 8}$	$:= \frac{3^{-07+2+9}}{6 \times (14 + (5 + 8))}$	$:= \frac{307 - 29}{614 - 58}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + (2 \times 9)))}{(6 - (1 \times (4 - 5))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - (2 \times 9)))}{(6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) - 8}$	
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + (2 + 9)))}{6 \times (1 \times (4 - (5 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - (2 + 9)))}{6 + (1 + (4 - (5 - 8)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{30792}{61584} := \frac{((3 - (-07)) \times 9) + 2}{(6 + (1(5 \times 8))) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + 29))}{6 \times (1 - (4 \times (5 - 8)))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - 29))}{6 + (1 \times (4 + (5 \times 8)))}$	$:= \frac{((3 \times (07)) - 9) \times 2}{6 \times (1 - (5 - (8 + 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - (72 + 9))}{6 \times (1 \times ((4 \times 5) + 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 - (2 \times 9))}{(6 \times 1 \times 4) + 58}$	$:= \frac{((30 - 7) \times 9) - 2}{((6 + 1) \times 58) + 4}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 \times (7 - 29))}{6 \times 1^{458}}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 - (2 + 9))}{6 + (1 \times (4 + 58))}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 2}{6 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4))}$
$:= \frac{3 - (0 - 729)}{6 + 1458}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 - (2 - 9))}{(6 - (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 2}{(6 + (1 \times (5 + 8))) \times 4}$
$:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 7) + 29)}{6 \times (1 + ((4 \times 5) + 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 \times (2 - 9))}{6 - ((1 - (4 \times 5)) \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times (9 \times 2)}{6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 72) + 9)}{6 \times (1 - ((4 - 5) \times 8))}$	$:= \frac{30 - (7 + (2 \times 9))}{6 + ((1^4) - (5 - 8))}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times (9 + 2)}{(6 - 1) \times ((5 \times 8) + 4)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 - (-07)) \times (9 - 2)}{61 - (5 - 84)} &:= \frac{(30 + (7 \times 9)) \times 2}{6 \times (1 \times (58 + 4))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7 + 9)^2))}{6 \times ((1 - (5 - 8))^4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - 79)) \times 2}{((6 \times 15) - 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(30 + (7 - 9)) \times 2}{((6 \times (1 + 5)) - 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 - 2)))}{((6 - 1) \times 58) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 7) + 9)) + 2}{6 + (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 79) - 2)}{6 + ((1^5) \times (8 - 4))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 2)))}{61 + (5 + 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (7 - 9)))^2}{(6 - (1 - (5 + 8))) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - ((7 + 9) \times 2))}{61 + (5 + (8 - 4))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 + 2)))}{6 \times (1 + (5 + (8 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (7 - 9))) + 2}{6 + (1 + (5 + (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 \times (9 + 2)))}{6 + (158 - 4)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 2)))}{6 - (1 + (5 - 84))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 - (7 - 9))) - 2}{6 + (1 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + (9 \times 2)))}{(6 + ((1^5) \times 8)) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (7 + 92))}{6 \times (15 + 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 79)) + 2}{6 - (1 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 2)))}{6 - (1 - (5 + (8 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + (79 + 2))}{6 + (15 \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) + 2}{((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8) + 4} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 2)))}{6 + (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 79 + 2}}{6 - (1 \times ((5 - 8) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) - 2}{((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8) - 4} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (7 + 92))}{((6 - 1) \times (5 \times 8)) + 4} &:= \frac{3^{-07 + 9 + 2}}{6 - ((1 - (5 \times 8)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (07)) + (9 \times 2)}{6 \times (1 - ((5 - 8) \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (79 + 2))}{6 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + ((0 \times 79) - 2)}{6 - ((1^5) \times (8 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (07)) + (9 + 2)}{(6 + (1 - 5)) \times (8 \times 4)} &:= \frac{3 - (0 \times (7 - 92))}{6 \times (1^{584})} &:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 2)))}{(6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (-07)) + (9^2)}{6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - 792)}{6 + 1584} &:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 2)))}{6 - (1 - (5 + (8 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (-07)) + 92}{(6 \times (15 + 8)) + 4} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 7) + 92)}{6 \times ((15 + 8) \times 4)} &:= \frac{3 + (0 - (7 - 92))}{((6 \times (1 + 5)) + 8) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^{-07+9}) \times 2}{6 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 79) + 2)}{6 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{30 - (7 - (9 \times 2))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 + 8))) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^{-07+9}) + 2}{6 - (1 - (5 + (8 + 4)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - (9 \times 2)))}{6 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 4)))} &:= \frac{30 - (7 - (9 + 2))}{6 + (1 \times (58 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 2}{(6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) - 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - (9^2)))}{((61 - 5) \times 8) - 4} &:= \frac{30 - (7 - (9 - 2))}{6 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))^2}{6 + (1 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4))} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 2)))}{6 + (1 + (5 + (8 + 4)))} &:= \frac{30 - (7 + (9 - 2))}{6 - (1 + (5 - (8 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 - (7 + 9))^2}{((6 \times 15) + 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (7 - 92))}{6 \times ((1^5) + 84)} &:= \frac{30 \times ((7 \times 9) - 2)}{61 \times (5 \times (8 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times 7) - (9 \times 2)}{(6 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 \times 4)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) - 2))}{6 \times (1 + (5 \times (8 + 4)))} &:= \frac{30 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2))}{6 \times (15 \times 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times 7) + (9 - 2)}{(6 + 1) \times (58 + 4)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 2))}{6 \times ((1^5) \times (8 \times 4))} &:= \frac{30 \times (7 \times (9 - 2))}{(6 + 1) \times (5 \times 84)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{30 \times (7 + (9 + 2))}{6 \times (15 \times (8 + 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 \times (7 + (9 - 2))}{(6 - (1 - 5)) \times 84} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 - (9 \times 2))}{(6 \times (15 - 8)) - 4} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 - (9 + 2))}{(6 + (15 - 8)) \times 4} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 \times (9 \times 2))}{6 \times (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 + (9^2))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 \times 8))) - 4} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 + (9 + 2))}{6 + (1 + (5 + 84))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (7 + (9 - 2))}{(6 \times (1 + (5 + 8))) + 4} \\
 := \frac{30 + (79 + 2)}{6 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 \times 4)))} \\
 := \frac{307 - (9^2)}{((61 - 5) \times 8) + 4} \\
 := \frac{3079 + 2}{6158 + 4} \\
 := \frac{3079 - 2}{6158 - 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30794}{86152} := \frac{30 + 79 \times 4}{8 \times (6 + 1 \times 5)^2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30798}{54162} := \frac{3 - 0 + 7 \times 9 - 8}{5 \times (4 + 16) + 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30814}{67592} := \frac{3 - 0 + (8 - 1) \times 4}{6 + 7 + 5 \times (9 + 2)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30825}{96174} := \frac{3 \times (08 + 2) - 5}{9 - 6 + 1 + 74}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{30 \times (8 - 2) - 5}{9 \times 61 - 7 + 4} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (08 + 2) \times 5}{9 \times (6 \times (1 + 7) + 4)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30846}{71295} := \frac{308 + 4 + 6}{7 \times (12 + 9) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{30 \times 8 \times 4 - 6}{7^{1 \times 2} \times 9 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30846}{79152} := \frac{308 + 4 + 6}{791 + 5^2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30852}{69417} := \frac{((3 \times (08))^5) \times 2}{(6 + (9 - (4 - 1)))^7} \\
 := \frac{((30 + 8) \times 5) + 2}{6 + (9 + 417)} \\
 := \frac{((30 - 8) \times 5) + 2}{6 \times ((9 - (4 - 1)) \times 7)} \\
 := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 8) - 5)) \times 2}{6 + (9 + (4 + 17))} \\
 := \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 + 5))) \times 2}{6 \times (9 + (4 - (1^7)))} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 8)) + 52}{6 + (94 + 17)} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times (-08)) + 52}{6 + (9 + (41 + 7))} \\
 := \frac{(30 \times (8 - 5)) + 2}{69 \times (4 - (1^7))} \\
 := \frac{(30 \times (8 - 5)) - 2}{6 \times (9 - (4 \times (1 - 7)))} \\
 := \frac{(30 \times 8) + 52}{6 + ((94 - 1) \times 7)} \\
 := \frac{(30 + (8 \times 5)) \times 2}{(6 + 9) \times (4 + 17)} \\
 := \frac{3 - (0 - ((8 - 5)^2))}{6 + (9 + (4 + (1 + 7)))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (0 - (8 - (5 + 2)))}{6 - (9 - (4 + (1 + 7)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 - (0 - (8 - (5 - 2)))}{6 - (9 - (4 + 17))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (0 - (8 + (5^2)))}{69 + (4 + (1 + 7))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 \times 2)))}{6 \times (9 \times (4 - (1 - 7)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 - 2)))}{6 \times (9 \times (4 - (1^7)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (0 - (8 - (5^2)))}{6 - (9 - (41 + 7))} \\
 := \frac{30 - ((8 - 5) \times 2)}{((6 + 9) \times 4) + (1 - 7)} \\
 := \frac{30 + ((8 + 5) \times 2)}{6 \times (9 + (4 + (1 + 7)))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (8 + (5 \times 2))}{6 + (94 + (1 + 7))} \\
 := \frac{308 \times (5 + 2)}{(694 - 1) \times 7} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30857}{49162} := \frac{3 \times 08 + 5 \times 7}{4 - 9 \times (1 - 6) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{3^{0 \times 8 + 5} - 7}{4 \times 91 + 6 \times 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30861}{74295} := \frac{3^{08-6+1}}{((7 + 4) \times 2 - 9) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{3^{0 \times 8 + 6 - 1}}{(7 + 4 + 2) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30879}{51246} := \frac{3 \times (08 \times 7 - 9)}{5 \times 12 \times 4 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30879}{62415} := \frac{3 \times (08 \times 7 - 9)}{(62 - 4 - 1) \times 5} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30912}{48576} := \frac{(((3 \times (09)) + 1) \times 2)}{(4 + (85 - (7 - 6)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) - 2)}{(4 + (8 \times (5 \times (7 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 - 2))) \times 7}{(6 + (1^8)) \times (5 \times 4)} &:= \frac{(3 + (-09)) \times (2 - 7)}{6 \times (1 + (8 + (5 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 \times (9 - 1)) - 2)}{(4 \times (85 + 7)) + 6} &:= \frac{(3 - (-09)) \times (2 \times 7)}{6 \times ((1 + (8 + 5)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(30 - (9 + 2)) \times 7}{(6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 5)) - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + (1 \times 2))))}{((4^{8-5}) - (7 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 9)) - (2 - 7)}{6 + ((1^{85}) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(30 \times (9 - 2)) + 7}{(61 \times 8) - 54} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 - (1 \times 2))))}{(4 - (8 + (5 - (7 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (2^7)}{(6 + (1 - (8 - 5)))^4} &:= \frac{(30 \times 9) - (2 \times 7)}{(6 \times (1 + 85)) - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 + 12)))}{(48 + (57 - 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (2 + 7)}{6 - (1 \times (8 - (5 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(30 \times 9) - (2^7)}{((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 5)) + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times (91 \times 2))}{(4 + 8576)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))) - 7}{6 - (1 - (85 + 4))} &:= \frac{(30 + (9 \times 2)) \times 7}{618 + 54} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (9 + (1 + 2)))}{(48 + (5 + (7 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9^2))) + 7}{((6 - 1)^{8-5}) \times 4} &:= \frac{(30 + 9) \times (2 + 7)}{(6 - (1 - 8)) \times 54} \\
 &:= \frac{(309 - (1^2))}{(485 - (7 - 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 + 2))) + 7}{(6 + (1 + (8 + 5))) \times 4} &:= \frac{(30 + 92) \times 7}{61 \times (8 + (5 \times 4))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30912}{56784} &:= \frac{3 + 091 - 2}{(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) + 4} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 - 2))) + 7}{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times (5 - 4))} &:= \frac{(30 - 9) \times (2 + 7)}{6 \times (1 + (8 + 54))} \\
 & &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 - 2))) - 7}{(6 + (1^{85})) \times 4} &:= \frac{(30 - 9) \times 27}{6 \times (185 + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30927}{48165} &:= \frac{3 \times 09 \times 2 + 7}{(4 + 8 + 1 + 6) \times 5} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) - (2 \times 7)}{6 + ((1^8) \times (5 \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 9) - (2^7))}{6 + ((1 + (8 - 5))^4)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - 09 + 2^7}{(4 \times 8 \times 1 + 6) \times 5} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) - (2 + 7)}{6 \times (1 - (8 - (5 + 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - ((0 \times 92) - 7)}{(6 - (1^{85})) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30927}{61854} &:= \frac{((3 - (-09)) \times 2) + 7}{6 + ((1 + (8 + 5)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) + (2 \times 7)}{(6 \times (1 \times (8 + 5))) + 4} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 - (2 - 7)))}{6 + (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (-09))^2) - 7}{(6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 5)) + 4} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) + (2^7)}{(6 - 1) \times (8 + 54)} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 \times (2 + 7)))}{6 \times (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (09)) - 2) \times 7}{6 + ((1 + 85) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) + (2 + 7)}{6 \times (1 \times ((8 - 5) \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 \times 27))}{6 \times (1 + (85 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 + 9) \times 2) + 7}{6 + ((1 + (8 \times 5)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (09)) + (2 - 7)}{6 + (18 + (5 \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 + (2 \times 7)))}{6 - (1 \times (8 - 54))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 + 9) \times 2) - 7}{(6 \times (18 + 5)) + 4} &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} \times 7}{6 \times ((1^8) + (5 \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 + (2^7)))}{(6 + (1 \times 8)) \times (5 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 - 9) \times 2) + 7}{6 + ((18 + 5) \times 4)} &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} + 7}{(6 - (1 - (8 - 5))) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 + (2 - 7)))}{6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 9) - 2)) \times 7}{61 + (8 + (5 - 4))} &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} - 7}{6 - (1 - (8 - (5 + 4)))} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (9 + 27))}{6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + 2))) \times 7}{((6 \times (1 + 8)) - 5) \times 4} &:= \frac{(3 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))^7}{6 - ((1^{85}) \times 4)} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (92 + 7))}{(6 + ((1 + 8) \times 5)) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 - (0 \times (9 - 27))}{6 \times (1^{854})} \\
 := \frac{3 - (0 - 927)}{6 + 1854} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 9) + (2 + 7))}{6 \times (1 + (8 \times (5 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 - (9 - (2 \times 7)))}{6 \times ((1^{85}) + 4)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 - (9 \times (2 - 7)))}{6 \times (1 + ((8 \times 5) + 4))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 - (9 - 27))}{6 \times (1 + (8 + (5 + 4)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 \times 2 + 7))}{61 + (85 + 4)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + ((9 \times 2) - 7))}{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5) - 4} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + ((9 - 2) \times 7))}{6 \times (((1 + 8) \times 5) + 4)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 - (2 - 7)))}{(61 - (8 \times 5)) \times 4} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 \times (2 \times 7)))}{(6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 54} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 \times (2 + 7)))}{6 \times (1 \times (85 - 4))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9^{2+7}))}{6 \times ((1 + 8)^{5+4})} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 + (2 - 7)))}{6 + (1 + (8 + (5 + 4)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + (9 + 27))}{6 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 5) - 4))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (0 + 927)}{618 \times (5 + 4)} \\
 := \frac{3^{09+2-7}}{6 - ((1 - (8 \times 5)) \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (0 - (9 - (2 \times 7)))}{6 + (1 + (8 + (5 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (0 - (9 - (2^7)))}{(6 \times (1 \times (8 \times 5))) + 4} \\
 := \frac{3 + (0 - (9 \times (2 - 7)))}{6 + (1 + (85 + 4))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 + (0 - (9 - 27))}{6 \times (1 \times (8 - (5 - 4)))} \\
 := \frac{30 \times ((9^2) - 7)}{6 \times (185 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{30 \times (9 + (2 \times 7))}{(61 + 8) \times (5 \times 4)} \\
 := \frac{30 \times (9 + (2 + 7))}{6 \times ((1 + 8) \times (5 \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 \times (9 + 27)}{6 \times (18 \times (5 \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 \times 2 + 7)}{((6 + 1) \times 8) + 54} \\
 := \frac{30 + ((9^2) + 7)}{(6 \times (1 \times (8 \times 5))) - 4} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 - (2 \times 7))}{6 + (1 \times ((8 \times 5) + 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 - (2 - 7))}{6 + (1 + (85 - 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 \times (2 \times 7))}{6 \times (1 \times ((8 + 5) \times 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 \times (2 + 7))}{6 \times (1 + ((8 \times 5) - 4))} \\
 := \frac{30 + (9 + (2 - 7))}{6 + (1 \times (8 + 54))} \\
 := \frac{309 - 27}{6 \times ((18 \times 5) + 4)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30962}{41785} := \frac{30 \times (9 + 6) + 2}{41 \times (7 + 8) - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30972}{65148} := \frac{30 \times (9 - 7) - 2}{6 \times (5 + 14) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31027}{86549} := \frac{(3 + 10) \times 2 - 7}{8 + (6 - 5 + 4) \times 9} \\
 := \frac{31 - 0 \times 2 + 7}{(8 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31052}{48796} := \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - (5 - 2)))}{4 + ((8 - 7)^9 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - (5 \times 2)))}{4 + (8 + (7 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (1 \times ((05 + 2)))}{4 + (8 + (7 \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - 52))}{4 + (87 - (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{((3 + 10) \times 5) - 2}{4 - (8 - (7 + 96))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (10 + (5^2))}{((4 + (8 + 7)) \times 9) - 6} \\
 := \frac{3 - (1 \times (0 - (5^2)))}{4 - ((8 \times 7) - 96)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{57186} := \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{5 \times 71 - 8 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{75168} := \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{(75 + 1) \times 6 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{87156} := \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{8 \times 71 - 5 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30958}{41726} := \frac{3 \times (0 \times 9 + 5) + 8}{4 - 1 - 7 \times (2 - 6)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31059}{82467} := \frac{(3 + 1) \times 05 + 9}{8 - 2 + 4 + 67} \\
 := \frac{3 + 10 + 5 \times 9}{(8 + 2 \times 4 + 6) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31062}{48597} := \frac{(3 - 1)^{06} - 2}{(4 - 8 + 5) \times 97} \\
 := \frac{310 \times 6 \times 2}{(4 + 8) \times 5 \times 97}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(3+1) \times 062}{485-97} \\ & := \frac{31 \times 06 \times 2}{485+97} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31064}{57892} & := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 06 + 4}{5 + (7+8-9)^2} \\ & := \frac{3-1+064}{5 \times 7 + 8 \times (9+2)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (10+6) - 4}{5-7-8+92} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31065}{98427} & := \frac{(3+10+6) \times 5}{(9-8+42) \times 7} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31075}{49268} & := \frac{310-7 \times 5}{4 \times 92 + 68} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31076}{42958} & := \frac{(3+1) \times 07 + 6}{4 - (2-9) \times 5 + 8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31095}{74628} & := \frac{((3 \times 10) - 9) \times 5}{7 \times (4 + ((6-2) \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (1 \times (-09))) \times 5}{(7 - (4 - 6)) \times (2 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (1^{09})) \times 5}{(7 + (4 - (6 + 2))) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (1 + (-09))) \times 5}{(7 \times ((4 + 6) \times 2)) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (1 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5)}{(7 \times (4 \times (6 + 2))) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (1 + 09)) + 5}{7 \times ((4 - 6) \times (2 - 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (1 + 09)) - 5}{(7 \times (4 + 6)) - (2 + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (0 \times 9))) + 5}{(7 - 4) \times ((6 \times 2) - 8)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (10 \times 9)) + 5}{(7 + 4) \times (6 \times (2 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (10 \times 9)) - 5}{(7 \times (46 \times 2)) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 10) + (9 \times 5)}{(7 - 4) \times (6 \times (2 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 10) + 95}{(7 \times (46 - 2)) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (1^{09})) \times 5}{(7 \times (4 + (6 - 2))) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (10 + 9)) \times 5}{(7 + ((4 \times 6) + 2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5)))}{74 + (6 + 28)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 - 5)))}{(7 - 4) \times (6 - (2 - 8))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5)))}{74 - (6 - (2^8))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (10 \times (9^5))}{(((7 - 4)^6)^2) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (10 \times (9 - 5))}{(7 \times (4 + (6^2))) + 8} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (10 + 95)}{7 \times (((4 + 6)^2) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{31 + 20 - 7}{((9 - 6) \times 4 + 5) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 + 1 + 2^{07}}{(96 - 45) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 + 1 \times 20 \times 7}{9 \times (6 + 4) \times 5 - 8} \\ & := \frac{3 - 1 + 207}{9 + 645 - 8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31209}{47586} & := \frac{3 + 1209}{(4 \times 75 + 8) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{312 - 09}{(4 \times 7 + 5) \times (8 + 6)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31240}{86975} & := \frac{312 + 40}{(8 + 6)^{9-7} \times 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{57960} & := \frac{31 \times (2 - 4 + 8)}{5 \times (7 \times 9 + 6) + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{59706} & := \frac{3 \times (1 + 2 + 4) \times 8}{5 \times 9 \times 7 + 06} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{60795} & := \frac{31 \times (24 - 8)}{60 \times (7 + 9) + 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{69750} & := \frac{31 \times 2^4 + 8}{(6 + 9) \times 75 - 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{75609} & := \frac{(3 + 1 + 24) \times 8}{7 - 5 + 60 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{95760} & := \frac{3^{1+2} - 4 + 8}{95 \times (7 - 6) + 0} \\ & := \frac{31 + 248}{9 \times (5 \times 7 + 60)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 248}{(9 \times 5 - 7) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{31 \times (24 + 8)}{(9 - 5) \times 760} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{97650} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 2 + 4 + 8}{(9 + 7 - 6) \times 5 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31206}{95847} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 2 \times 06}{9 - 5 - 8 + 47} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (20 - 6)}{9 - 5 \times 8 \times (4 - 7)} \\ & := \frac{31 \times 2 - 06}{95 + 84 - 7} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{31207}{96458} & := \frac{3 - 1 + 2 + 07}{96 - 4 - 58} \\ & := \frac{3 + 12 + 07}{9 + 6 + 45 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 12 \times 4 - 8}{(9 + 76) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 1 + 2^4) \times 8}{9 \times (7 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 2^4) \times 8}{(9 + 7 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 8}{(9 - 7) \times 6 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 1^2)^4 \times 8}{(9 - 7 + 6) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31280}{49657} := \frac{(3 - 1^2) \times 80}{4 + (9 - 6)^5 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1^2) \times 80}{496 + 5 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31406}{85792} := \frac{31 + 4 + 06}{8 + 5 + 7 + 92}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31407}{52896} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4 + 07}{5^2 - 8 + 9 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + 4) \times 07}{(5 - 2 + 8 - 9)^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31407}{92568} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4 + 07}{(9 + 2 \times (5 - 6)) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31408}{56927} := \frac{3 + (1 + (4 - (-08)))}{5 + (6 - (9 - 27))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (1 - (4 - 0))) \times 8}{5 - (6 - ((9^2) + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 40)) - 8}{(5 \times (6 \times (9 - 2))) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (40 + 8))}{(5 \times (6 \times 9)) - (2 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times (40 + 8)}{(5 \times (69 + 2)) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times (40 \times 8)}{5 \times (((6 + 9)^2) + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (1 - 40)) \times 8}{(56 \times (9 + 2)) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (1^4 + 0)) \times 8}{(5 \times (6 + (9 - 2))) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31426}{57890} := \frac{3 - 1 + 42 - 6}{5 - 7 + 8 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 4^2) + 6}{(5 + 7) \times 8 + 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4 + 2^6}{5 + (7 + 8) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + 4) \times 2^6}{5 \times 7 \times (8 + 9) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31482}{70596} := \frac{3 \times (14 + 8) \times 2}{70 \times 5 - 9 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 4 \times 8) \times 2}{(70 - 5 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31485}{62970} := \frac{((3 - (1 - 4)) \times 8) + 5}{((6 - 2) \times 9) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 1) \times 48) + 5}{((6^2) \times 9) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - ((1^4)^8))^5}{62 + (9 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (1^4)) \times (8 + 5)}{(6^2) + (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 + 4)) + 85}{6 + (2 \times (97 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (14 + 8)) + 5}{((6 + 2) \times 9) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 14) + (8 \times 5)}{6 + (2 \times (9 + 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 14) + 85}{((6^2) \times 9) - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (1 \times 4)) \times 85}{(6 + (2 + 9)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1^4) \times (8 + 5)}{(6 \times 29) - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times ((4 \times 8) - 5)}{6 \times (29 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 485}{(6 - 2) \times 970}$$

$$:= \frac{(31 + 4) \times (8 + 5)}{(6 - (2 - 9)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((1 - (4 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(6 - 2) \times (9 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{6 - ((2 \times 9) - 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{62 \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{6 + (29 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - (4^{8-5}))}{6 + (2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - (4 + (8 + 5)))}{6 + (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 \times ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{62 - (9 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 \times (4 - (8 + 5)))}{6 \times (2^{9-7+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 \times (4 - 85))}{(6 + (2 \times 9)) \times (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 + (4 - (8 - 5)))}{6 - (2^{9-7+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - 485)}{6 - (2 - 970)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((1 + 4) \times 8) - 5)}{((6 \times 2) - 9) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 5)}{6 \times ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((1 + 48) \times 5)}{((6 \times 2) + 9) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((14 \times 8) - 5)}{(6 \times 2) + (9 \times 70)}$$

$:= \frac{3 \times (1 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}{62 - (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (4 - (8 - 5)))}{6 + (2^{9-7+0})}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 1^5 \times 90}{4 \times 86 + 72}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{(6^2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (4^{8-5}))}{(6 \times (2 + 9)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 5) \times 90}{48 \times (6 + 7) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{6 + (29 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (48 \times 5))}{(62 \times 9) - 70}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 90}{4 \times 8 \times (67 - 2)}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + (4 \times (8 - 5)))}{62 + (9 + (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (1 + 485)}{6 + (2 + 970)}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{62478} := \frac{31 + 59 + 0}{6 \times (24 + 7) - 8}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + (4^{8-5}))}{6 \times (2 + (9 \times (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{3 + 1485}{6 + 2970}$	$:= \frac{(3 + 1^5) \times 90}{(6 \times 2^4 - 7) \times 8}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + (4 + (8 + 5)))}{6 \times (2 + (9 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{31 + 485}{62 + 970}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (15 + 90)}{624 + 7 - 8}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (14 - (8 - 5))}{6 \times ((2 \times 9) - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{314 - (8 - 5)}{629 - (7 - 0)}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{76284} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9 - 0}{7 \times 6 + 284}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (14 \times (8 - 5))}{(6 - 2) \times (9 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{314 + (8 - 5)}{6 - (2 - (9 \times 70))}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{78624} := \frac{31 + (59 - 0)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 - 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (14 + 85)}{6 \times (2 + (97 - 0))}$		$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + (5 + (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (8 + (6 - (2 - 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 \times (1^{485})}{6 - (2 - (9 - (7 - 0)))}$	▶ $\frac{31569}{74280} := \frac{3 - 1 - 5 \times (6 - 9)}{(7 - 4 + 2) \times 8 + 0}$	$:= \frac{(3 + (1^5)) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times ((6 - 2) \times 4))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (((1^4)^8) \times 5)}{(6 - 2)^{9-7+0}}$	$:= \frac{3 - 1 - 5 + 6 \times 9}{7 \times 4^2 + 8 + 0}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (5 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (8 + ((6^2) + 4))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1^4 + (8 + 5))}{(6^2) - (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{3 + (1 \times 5 + 6) \times 9}{(7 \times 4 + 2) \times 8 + 0}$	$:= \frac{(31 + 5) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times 24))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1^4 + (8 - 5))}{(6 \times 2) + (9 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{31 \times 5 + 6 + 9}{(7 - 4 + 2) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (1 + (59 - 0))}{7 \times (8 \times (6 - (2 - 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1^4 + 85)}{(6 \times (2 \times 9)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 5 \times 6) \times 9}{(7 + 4 - 2) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(3 - (1 - 5)) \times 90}{7 \times ((8 + 6) \times (2^4))}$
$:= \frac{3 + ((1 + 48) \times 5)}{6 - ((2 - 9) \times 70)}$		$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 + 5)) - (9 - 0)}{7 \times (8 + (62 \times 4))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (4 + (8 \times 5)))}{6 + ((2 \times 9) + 70)}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{42768} := \frac{31 \times 5 - 90}{4 \times (2 \times 7 + 6) + 8}$	$:= \frac{315 - 90}{7 \times ((8 + (6 \times 2)) \times 4)}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{6 - (2 - (9 + (7 - 0)))}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{47268} := \frac{3 \times 1^5 \times 90}{472 - 68}$	$:= \frac{3 \times ((1^5) \times 90)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 + 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (48 \times 5))}{6 \times (2 + (9 + 70))}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{47628} := \frac{31 \times 5 - 90}{(47 + 6) \times 2 - 8}$	$:= \frac{(3 + (1 + 5)) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times (2 + 4)))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1^{485})}{(6 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}$	▶ $\frac{31590}{48672} := \frac{(3 + 15) \times 90}{4 \times 8 \times (6 + 72)}$	$:= \frac{((3 + 1)^5) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times ((6 + 2)^4))}$
$:= \frac{3 + (1 + ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{6 - (2 \times (9 - 70))}$	$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9 + 0}{4 \times (8 + 6 \times 7 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times (15 + 90)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 \times 4)))}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(3-1) \times (5 \times 90)}{7 \times (8 \times ((6^2) + 4))} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31608}{94752} &:= \frac{3^{1+6} + 08}{94 \times 7 \times 5 \times 2} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31620}{58497} &:= \frac{3+1+6^2+0}{(5+8-4) \times 9-7} \\ &:= \frac{(3+1+6)^2+0}{5 \times (8+4 \times 9-7)} \\ &:= \frac{(31+6) \times 20}{(5+8 \times 4)^{9-7}} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31620}{89745} &:= \frac{3 \times 16+20}{8+((9+7 \times 4) \times 5)} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31650}{78492} &:= \frac{31-6+50}{(7 \times (8+4) + 9) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(31-6) \times 5+0}{7 \times (8+4 \times 9) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{(3+1^6) \times 50}{7 \times 84-92} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31650}{97482} &:= \frac{31-6+50}{9+7 \times 4 \times 8-2} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31652}{87904} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 65-2}{8 \times 7 \times 9+04} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31689}{45270} &:= \frac{3-(1 \times (6-(8+9)))}{(45 \times 2) - 70} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (6-(8-9)))}{(4 \times (5^2)) - 70} \\ &:= \frac{(3+1) \times (6-(8-9))}{4 \times (5-(2-(7-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 6)) + (8+9)}{45-(2-(7-0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(31 \times 6) + (8+9)}{(4 \times 5) + 270} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (68+9))}{((4 \times 5)^2) - 70} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 16) - (8-9)}{(4-(5-2)) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times ((6+8) \times 9))}{4 \times (5 \times (27-0))} \\ &:= \frac{31+(6+89)}{4 \times (5 \times (2+(7-0)))} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31689}{70245} &:= \frac{(3-1)^6 \times 8-9}{70 \times 2^4-5} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31689}{72450} &:= \frac{(3-1)^6 \times 8-9}{(7+2^4) \times 50} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31689}{74025} &:= \frac{(3-1)^6 \times 8-9}{(7+40) \times 25} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31692}{45870} &:= \frac{(3+1+6+9) \times 2}{4-5+8 \times 7+0} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31692}{50874} &:= \frac{(3+1+6+9) \times 2}{50+8+7-4} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31695}{82407} &:= \frac{3+(1 \times (6-(9-5)))}{8+(2-(4+(-07)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (6+(9-5)))}{82-(4-(0 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (6+9))) - 5}{8 \times (2+(4-(-07)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3-(1-(6 \times 9))) \times 5}{((8^2) + 40) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{3+(16-(9-5))}{8-(2-(40-7))} \\ &:= \frac{(3+(1+(6+9))) \times 5}{((8-2) \times 40) + 7} \\ &:= \frac{(3-(1-6)) \times 95}{8 \times (240+7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rightarrow \frac{31724}{58960} &:= \frac{3^{1 \times 7} - 24}{(58+9) \times 60} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31724}{98056} &:= \frac{3-1+(7-2) \times 4}{98-05 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3-1+7+24}{(9+8+0 \times 5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (17+2^4)}{9 \times (8 \times 05-6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3+17)^2-4}{9 \times (80+56)} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31725}{60489} &:= \frac{3 \times (1+7 \times 2^5)}{6^{-04+8}-9} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31728}{45609} &:= \frac{3+1 \times 7-2+8}{4 \times 5-6+09} \\ &:= \frac{3+17+28}{4+56+09} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31728}{69405} &:= \frac{3+(1 \times (7-(2-8)))}{6+(9-(4 \times (-05)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3+(1^{72})) \times 8}{69-(4+(-05))} \\ &:= \frac{3+(17+28)}{6+(94-(-05))} \\ &:= \frac{(3+(1 \times (7+2))) \times 8}{(6+(9 \times (4-0))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (72-8))}{6+(9+405)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (72+8))}{(6+9) \times (40-5)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((1+7) \times 28)}{6 \times ((9+40) \times 5)} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31752}{46980} &:= \frac{(3 \times 17+5)^2}{(4+6 \times 9) \times 80} \\ \rightarrow \frac{31752}{48069} &:= \frac{(3-1) \times (7+5)^2}{4+8 \times 06 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{60984} := \frac{3 - (1 - 7) \times 52}{609 - 8 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{94608} := \frac{3 + 1 - 7 + 52}{94 + 60 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 17) \times 5 - 2}{(9 - 4) \times 60 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 1 + 7 + 5)^2}{(9 + 4 + 60) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31758}{46029} := \frac{(3 - 1) \times 75 + 8}{4 \times 60 - 2 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31768}{59204} := \frac{3 - 1 \times 7 + 6 \times 8}{5 + 9^2 - 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31790}{65824} := \frac{3 - 1 - 7 + 90}{6 \times 5 \times (8 - 2) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31790}{82654} := \frac{3 - (1 \times (7 - (9 - 0)))}{8 - (2 - (6 + (5 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (7 + (9 - 0)))}{8 + ((2^6) - (5 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((1^7) + (9 - 0))}{82 - ((6 - 5) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 17) + (9 - 0)}{(8 + (26 + 5)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (7 + 90))}{8 - ((2 - 65) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (17 + 90)}{(((8^2) - 6) \times 5) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 17) \times (9 - 0)}{(8 \times ((2^6) - 5)) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{42579} := \frac{31 \times (8 - 06)}{4 + 2 \times 5 \times 7 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{31 \times (8 + 06)}{4 - 2 + 579}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{59427} := \frac{3 - 1 + 80 - 6}{5 + 9 \times 4^2 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{75924} := \frac{31 - 8 \times 0 \times 6}{7 - 5 + 9 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{57096} := \frac{((3 + 1) \times 8)^2 - 4}{5 \times (70 - 9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{59670} := \frac{3 - (1 - (8 + (2 - 4)))}{5 + (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 - 2))) \times 4}{5 - (9 + (6 - 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2 \times 4)))}{5 + (9 + (6 + 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + 2))) \times 4}{5 \times ((9 - 6) \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2^4)))}{59 + (6 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (18 \times 2)) - 4}{(5^{9-6}) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times ((8^2) + 4)}{5 \times (9 + (6 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 1)^8) - (2 \times 4)}{(5 \times 9) + (6 \times 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 1)^8) + 24}{5 \times ((9 + 6) \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{318 - (2 + 4)}{5 \times (9 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{79560} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (8^2))) \times 4}{(7 + (9 - 5)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 - 2))) \times 4}{79 - (5 - (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 82)) - 4}{(7 \times 95) - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + 2))) \times 4}{7 \times (9 + (5 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 18) \times 24}{(7 + (9 + 5)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(31 \times (8 - 2)) - 4}{7 \times (9 + (56 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1 - (8 + (2 - 4)))}{((7 + 9) \times 5) - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (1^{824})}{7 + (9 - (5 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 \times (2 \times 4)))}{(7 + 9) \times (5 \times (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2^4)))}{(7 - (9 - 5)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (18 + (2^4))}{(7 \times (9 \times 5)) - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 - (8 - 24))}{((7 - 9) \times 5) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + ((8 + 2) \times 4))}{(7 - 9) \times (5 - 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 - (2 + 4)))}{7 + (9 + (5 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 + (2^4)))}{7 \times (9 - (5 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 + 24))}{79 + (5 + (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{31 \times (8 + (2 + 4))}{7 \times (95 + 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{318 \times (2 + 4)}{795 \times (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{318 + 24}{795 + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{318 - 24}{7 \times ((9 \times 5) + 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{90576} := \frac{3 - 1 + 8 + 2^4}{9 + 05 \times (7 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 1 \times 8)^2 - 4}{9 \times (-05 + 7 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times (82 - 4)}{90 + 576}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{57096} := \frac{3 + (1 + 8 + 4) \times 2}{5 - 7 - 0 + 9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{79056} := \frac{3 + (1 + 8 + 4) \times 2}{7 + 9 - 0 + 56}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{79605} &:= \frac{((3 \times 18) + 4) \times 2}{(7 - (9 - 60)) \times 5} &:= \frac{(31 - 8) \times (4 + 2)}{((7 \times 9) + (6 - 0)) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (84 - 2))}{((7 \times 9) + 60) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 18) - 4) \times 2}{7 + ((9 - (6 - 0))^5)} &:= \frac{(31 - 8) \times 42}{7 \times ((9 + 60) \times 5)} &:= \frac{3 + (1 - (8 - 42))}{(79 - 60) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4))) - 2}{(7 - (9 \times 6)) \times (-05)} &:= \frac{3 - (1 - ((8 + 4)^2))}{(79 - (6 - 0)) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 + (1^{842})}{7 + (9 - (6 - (0 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4))) - 2}{79 + (6 - (0 \times 5))} &:= \frac{3 - (1 - (8 - (4 - 2)))}{(7 - (9 - (6 - 0))) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 - (4 + 2)))}{7 + (9 - (6 + (-05)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (18 - 4)) + 2}{(7 + (9 + (6 - 0))) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 - (1 - (8 + (4 + 2)))}{(7 - (9 + 6)) \times (-05)} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 \times (4 - 2)))}{(7 + (9 - (6 - 0))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (18 - 4)) - 2}{(7 \times (9 + (6 - 0))) - 5} &:= \frac{3 - (1 - (84 \times 2))}{(79 + (6 - 0)) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + (8 + (4^2)))}{7 \times (9 + (6 + (-05)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 18) + (4 - 2)}{7 \times (9 + (6 - (-05)))} &:= \frac{3 - (1^{842})}{7 + (9 - (6 - (-05)))} &:= \frac{3184 + 2}{7960 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + 4))) \times 2}{79 + (6 + (-05))} &:= \frac{3 - (1 + (8 - 42))}{79 + (6 - (-05))} &:= \frac{3184 - 2}{7960 - 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times (8 \times 42)}{7 \times (96 \times (05))} &:= \frac{3 \times (((1 + 8) \times 4) + 2)}{((7 \times 9) - (6 - 0)) \times 5} &\blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{96075} := \frac{(3 + 1 \times 84) \times 2}{(9 + 6) \times 07 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times (8^{4 \times 2})}{((7 + 9)^6 + 0) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times ((18 \times 4) - 2)}{7 \times ((9 + (6 - 0)) \times 5)} & \\ &:= \frac{(31 \times (8 - 4)) - 2}{(7 + (9 \times (6 - 0))) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times ((8 - 4) \times 2))}{(7 - 9) \times (6 \times (-05))} & \\ &:= \frac{(31 \times 8) - 42}{(7 + (96 - 0)) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8^{4-2}))}{(7 + 9) \times (6 \times (05))} & \\ &:= \frac{(31 + 8) \times 42}{7 \times (9 \times (60 + 5))} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (4 + 2)))}{7 \times (9 + (6 - (0 \times 5)))} & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31850}{42679} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 \times 8) \times 50}{4 \times 26 \times 7 + 9} &:= \frac{(3 - 1 + 8) \times 5 + 0}{9 \times 4 \times 2 + 76} &\blacktriangleright \frac{31860}{59472} &:= \frac{3 + 18 - 6 + 0}{5 \times (9 + 4 - 7) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 18 \times 50}{(4 + 2) \times 67 \times 9} & & &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8 + 6 + 0}{5 \times (9 + 4) - 7 - 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8 \times 50}{(4 + 26) \times 7 - 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{31856}{74029} &:= \frac{318 \times 5 - 6}{(7 + 402) \times 9} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 8 + 6) + 0}{(5 + 9 + 4 \times 7) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 1^8) \times 50}{42 \times 6 + 7 + 9} & & &:= \frac{3 \times 18 + 6 + 0}{59 + 4 + 7^2} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - 1 + 8) \times 5 + 0}{4 \times (26 - 7) - 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{31860}{47259} &:= \frac{3 \times 18 + 6 + 0}{4 \times 7 + 2 + 59} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31850}{94276} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^8 \times 50}{(9^{4-2} - 7) \times 6} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 \times 8) \times 60}{4^{7-2} - 5 \times 9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{31875}{46920} &:= \frac{3 \times (18 + 7) \times 5}{4 \times 69 \times 2 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1875}{46 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31902}{67485} := \frac{(3+1+9) \times 02}{6+7 \times (4+8-5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31904}{57826} := \frac{3+1 \times 9+04}{5+(7+8) \times 2-6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-1)^{9-04}}{5-7+(8+2) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1 \times 9) \times 04}{5+78-2+6}$$

$$:= \frac{3-1+90+4}{(5 \times 7-8+2) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1^9)^{04}}{57 \times 8+2+6}$$

$$:= \frac{(-3+19) \times 04}{(5+7 \times 8) \times 2-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31920}{56784} := \frac{3+1 \times 92+0}{(5+6) \times (7+8)+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31924}{86750} := \frac{3-1+(9+2) \times 4}{8+67+50}$$

$$:= \frac{3+1+92-4}{(8+6 \times 7) \times 5+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31926}{80754} := \frac{3+19+2 \times 6}{80+7-5+4}$$

$$:= \frac{3-1+(9+2) \times 6}{(8+07 \times 5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31928}{45760} := \frac{3+19 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 5+7 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31947}{80562} := \frac{3+1 \times 9+4+7}{80-(5+6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{319-4+7}{(80 \times 5+6) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31950}{47286} := \frac{3 \times (1+9)-5+0}{47-2 \times 8+6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-1^9) \times 50}{4+72 \times (8-6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1+9) \times 50}{(4+7)^2 \times 8-6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 50}{4 \times (7^2+8)-6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1^9) \times 50}{4 \times (72+8-6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 950}{4+7^2 \times 86}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31950}{72846} := \frac{(3+1 \times 9) \times 50}{(7^2+8) \times 4 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1^9) \times 50}{(72+8-4) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1) \times 9 \times 50}{7 \times 2+8^4-6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 50}{(7+2) \times (8 \times 4+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{47520} := \frac{(3-1+9) \times 6+8}{(4+7) \times 5 \times 2+0}$$

$$:= \frac{319+6+8}{475+20}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-1)^9-68}{(4 \times 7+5) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{52704} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (9+6)-8}{5+2 \times 7 \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 96+8}{(52+70) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{57024} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (9+6)-8}{5 \times 7 \times 02-4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-1+9) \times 6+8}{(5 \times 7-02) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{319+6+8}{570+24}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{72504} := \frac{(3-1)^9-68}{7+250 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31975}{48602} := \frac{3+1+9+7+5}{4 \times 8+6+0 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1^9 \times 7) \times 5}{(4 \times 8+6) \times 02}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+1+9+7) \times 5}{4 \times 8+60 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{((3-1) \times 9+7) \times 5}{4 \times 8 \times 6-02}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 75}{4 \times 86-02}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31976}{50248} := \frac{3-(1 \times (9-(7+6)))}{5-(0-(2-(4-8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((1^97)+6)}{(5^{-02+4})+8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 9))+(7-6)}{50-(2-(4-8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3-(1+(9-(7 \times 6)))}{5-(0-(2+48))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9+7))) - 6}{50+(24-8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 19)-(7-6)}{(5 \times ((02^4))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (19+7))+6}{(50 \times 2)+(4 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3+(1+(9+(7-6)))}{(5 \times ((02+4))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+(1 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 6)}{(50 \times (2^4)) - 8}$$

<hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{32015}{49876} := \frac{3 \times (20 - 1) \times 5}{4 \times (98 + 7 + 6)}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{32016}{47589} := \frac{(3 + 20) \times 16}{475 + 8 \times 9}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{32016}{54897} := \frac{(3 + 20) \times 16}{5^4 + 8 - 9 + 7}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{32054}{79618} := \frac{3 + (2 + 05) \times 4}{7 \times (9 - 6 + 1 \times 8)}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{32058}{96174} := \frac{((3 \times (2 - 0))^5) \times 8}{9 \times ((6 - (1 - 7))^4)}$	$:= \frac{(3^2 + 0) \times (5 + 8)}{9 \times (((6 - 1) \times 7) + 4)}$ $:= \frac{(3^2 + 0) \times 58}{9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 \times 4)))}$ $:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 \times 5))) \times 8}{96 - ((1 - 7) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (-05))) \times 8}{((9 \times 6) - (1 - 7)) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{(3 + (2 - 0)) \times (5 + 8)}{(9 + 6) \times (17 - 4)}$ $:= \frac{(3 + (20 - 5)) \times 8}{9 \times ((6 - (1 - 7)) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{(3 + 2)^{-05+8}}{(((9 \times 6) - 1) \times 7) + 4}$ $:= \frac{3 - ((2 \times (-05)) - 8)}{9 \times (6 + (1^{74}))}$ $:= \frac{3 - ((2 + (-05)) \times 8)}{9^{6-1-7+4}}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 - (0 - (5 - 8)))}{9 + (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 - (0 \times 58))}{9 - (6 \times (1^{74}))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 \times ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{9 + ((6 - (1 - 7)) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (0 - (5 + 8)))}{9 + (6 \times (17 - 4))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (0 \times 58))}{9^{6-1^7-4}}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (5 \times 8)))}{96 - (1 - (7 \times 4))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (5 + 8)))}{9 + (6 - (1 - (7 \times 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - 58))}{9 + (6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (20 - (5 \times 8))}{9 - (6 \times (1 - (7 + 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 - (20 - (5 \times 8))}{9 - (6 \times (1 - (7 + 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((2 - (-05)) \times 8)}{9 \times ((6 + (1 + 7)) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((2 - (-05))^8)}{9 \times (((6 + 1) \times 7)^4)}$	$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (05)) + 8)}{9 \times (6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((2^{05}) + 8)}{(96 + (1 - 7)) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((2^{05}) - 8)}{9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((20 \times 5) + 8)}{961 + (7 + 4)}$ $:= \frac{3 \times ((20 \times 5) - 8)}{9 \times ((6 + 17) \times 4)}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 - ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{9 + (6 + (1 + 74))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 - (5 + 8)))}{9 + (6 \times (17 + 4))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 \times 58))}{9 \times (6 - (1 + (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))}{9 \times (6 \times (1^{74}))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (0 + (5 \times 8)))}{9 \times (6 + (1 \times 74))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2^{-05+8})}{9 \times (6 - (1 - (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (0 - (5 - 8)))}{9 \times (6 - (1^{74}))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (20 \times (5 \times 8))}{96 \times (1 + 74)}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (20 + (5 + 8))}{9 \times (6 - (1 - (7 \times 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (20 + (5 - 8))}{9 \times (6 + (1 \times (7 + 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3 \times (20 + 58)}{9 \times (6 \times (17 - 4))}$ $:= \frac{3^2 + 0 \times 58}{9 \times (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))}$ $:= \frac{3^{2-05+8}}{9 \times (6 + (1 + 74))}$ $:= \frac{3^{20-5-8}}{9^{6+1-7+4}}$ $:= \frac{3 + ((2^{05}) + 8)}{(9 \times 6) + (1 + 74)}$
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$$:= \frac{3 + ((20 \times 5) - 8)}{(96 - 1) \times (7 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 - (5 - 8)))}{9 - (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 \times 58))}{9 + (6 \times (1^{74}))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 - 58))}{9 + (6 + 174)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2^{-05+8})}{9 + (6 \times (1 + (7 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (0 - (5 - 8)))}{9 - (6 - (17 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 - (5 + 8))}{9 - (6 + (1 - (7 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 - (5 - 8))}{9 - (6 - (1 + 74))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 + (5 + 8))}{((9 + (6 + 1)) \times 7) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 + (5 - 8))}{(9 + (6 \times (1^7))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 + 58)}{9 \times (6 + (17 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (205 + 8)}{9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 2058}{9 + 6174}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (0 - 58)}{9 \times (6 \times ((1^7) + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (0 - (5 - 8))}{96 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (0 + (5 + 8))}{96 \times (17 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{320 + 58}{9 \times (6 \times (17 + 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32064}{79158} := \frac{320 - 64}{79 \times ((1^5) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (06))) - 4}{7 + (9 \times ((1^5) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{32^{06-4}}{(7 + 9) \times 158}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (20 \times 64)}{79 \times (15 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (064)}{((7 \times 91) - 5) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4)}{79 \times (1 - (5 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 - (-06)) \times 4)}{79 + 158}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32074}{51968} := \frac{3 + 2 + 074}{51 + 9 + 68}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{45198} := \frac{3 + 20 - 7 + 6}{4 \times 5 + 19 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{49815} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 07 \times 6)}{(49 - 8 \times 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{320 + 76}{(49 - 8) \times 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{91854} := \frac{3 + 20 - 7 + 6}{9 \times 1 \times (8 - 5 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{98415} := \frac{3 \times (2 - 0 + 7 \times 6)}{9 \times 8 \times (4 + 1) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32079}{64158} := \frac{((3 \times (2 - 0)) + 7) \times 9}{6 - (4 \times (1 - 58))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 + (-07))) \times 9}{6 \times ((4 - (1^5)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 \times 9)}{6 + ((4 - 1) \times (5 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 + 9)}{(6 \times (4 \times (1^5))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 0)) \times 79}{6 + ((4 + 15) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (-07))) + 9}{6 \times (4 + ((1^5) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (-07))) - 9}{6 \times (4 - (1 + (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (07))) + 9}{6 \times (4 + (1 \times (5 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (07))) - 9}{6 \times (4 + (15 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - 0)) + (7 + 9)}{6 + (41 + (5 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - 0)) + (7 - 9)}{6 + (4 + (1 + (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - 0)) + 79}{6 + (4 \times (1 + (5 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (20 + 7)) + 9}{6 + ((4 - 1) \times 58)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (20 - 7)) - 9}{6 - (4 - (1 \times 58))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 20) - (7 + 9)}{(6 + (4 + (1^5))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 20) + (7 + 9)}{(6 \times (4 \times (1 + 5))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 20) + (7 - 9)}{(6 - (4 \times 1)) \times 58}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2 + 0) - (7 - 9)}{6 + (4 \times (1 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2 + 0) + 79}{(6 - (4 \times (1 - 5))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 \times 7))) \times 9}{(6 + 4) \times ((1^5) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 \times 7)))^9}{(6 + (4 \times 1)) \times (5^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (-07))) \times 9}{6^{4-158}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (0 - (7 - 9))}{6 - (4 + (1 + (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 20) \times (7 - 9)}{6 + (4 + (1 \times 58))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((2 \times (-07)) + 9)}{6 - (4 - (1 + (5 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((2 \times (-07)) - 9)}{(6 \times (4 + (1 + 5))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((2 + (-07)) \times 9)}{6 \times (4 \times (1 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - (0 \times 79))}{6 - (4 \times 1^{58})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{6 \times (4 - (1 - (5 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (0 - (7 + 9)))}{6 + ((4 - (1 - 5)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (0 \times 79))}{6 - (4 - (1 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + ((0 \times 7) - 9))}{((6 - 4) \times (1 + 5)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{(6 + (4 + (1 + 5))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (7 + 9)))}{6 + (4 \times (15 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - 79))}{6 - (4 - 158)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (20 \times (7 - 9))}{6 + ((4 + (1 + 5)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (0 \times 7)) + 9)}{6 - (4 \times (1 - (5 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (07)) + 9)}{6 \times (((4 - 1) \times 5) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (07)) - 9)}{6 \times (4 + ((1^5)^8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{6 \times ((4 + 1) \times (5 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}{6 \times (4 + (1 + (5 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 \times 79))}{6 + (4 - (1 + (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (0 - 79))}{6 + (4 \times (15 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (0 + (7 + 9)))}{6 \times (4 \times ((1^5) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2^{0 \times 7 + 9})}{64 \times ((1 + 5) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2^{-07 + 9})}{6 + (4 + (1 + (5 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (20 + 79)}{6 \times (41 + 58)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (207 + 9)}{6^4 \times 1^{58}}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2 \times 0 \times 7 + 9}}{6 \times ((4 - (1^5))^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3^2 + 0 \times 79}{6 - (4 \times (1 \times (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2^{-07 + 9}}}{6 - (4 \times (1 - (5 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2^{07}) + 9)}{((6 \times (4 + 1)) + 5) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((20 \times 7) + 9)}{(6 \times 41) + 58}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((20 \times 7) - 9)}{(6 \times (41 + 5)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((20 - 7) \times 9)}{6 \times ((4 + (1^5)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - ((0 \times 7) - 9))}{(6 - 4) \times (1 + (5 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{(6 - (4 - 15)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}{6 \times (4 - (1 \times (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 \times 79))}{6 + (4 \times 1^{58})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (0 - 79))}{6 + (4 + 158)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2^{-07 + 9})}{6 + (4 + (1 - (5 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 - (7 - 9))}{6 + (4 + (1 \times (5 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (20 + (7 + 9))}{6 \times (4 + ((1^5) + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 2079}{6 + 4158}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)}{(6 \times (4 \times 1)) + 58}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (0 \times 79)}{(6 - (4 - (1 + 5))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (0 - 79)}{64 + 158}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times ((0 \times 7) + 9)}{64 \times ((1^5) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{32 + ((0 \times 7) - 9)}{6 + ((4 + (1^5)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{320 - (7 - 9)}{641 - (5 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32085}{47196} := \frac{(3 + 20 + 8) \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times 1 \times 9 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32085}{61479} := \frac{3 \times (20 \times 8 - 5)}{6 \times 147 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 20 + 8) \times 5}{6 \times (1 + 47) + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32096}{58174} := \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (9 + 6)))}{5 + (8 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (09))) - 6}{5 + (8 + (1 \times 74))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 0)) \times 96}{58 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (0 - 96)}{58 \times (1 + (7 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2^{0 \times 9 + 6})}{5 + ((8 - 1)^{7 - 4})}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (0 \times 96)}{5 + (81 - (7 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{320 + 96}{58 \times (17 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32097}{86415} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 0 \times 9 + 7}{(8 - 6 + 4 + 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + 09) - 7}{8^{6 - 4} + 1 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - 09) \times 7}{(8 + 6) \times (4 + 1 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3+20+9+7}{86+4+15}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+09 \times 7)}{8 \times (64+1) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32154}{76890} := \frac{3 \times (2+1+5 \times 4)}{7+68+90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32154}{97860} := \frac{3+2 \times (1+5+4)}{9-7+8+60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32160}{97485} := \frac{32 \times (1 \times (6-0))}{97 \times ((4 \times 8)^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (1^6+0)}{9+(7-(4-85))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times 160}{97 \times (4 \times (8 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (16-0))}{((9+(7 \times 4)) \times 8) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-2) \times 160}{(9+((7+4) \times 8)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1 \times (6-0)))}{97+485}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (1+(6-0))}{(9 \times 74) + (8+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (1 \times 60)}{97 \times ((4+8) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1+(6-0)))}{97 \times (4 \times (8-5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32170}{54689} := \frac{3+((2-1) \times (7-0))}{((5-4)^6) \times (8+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^{2+1}) - (7-0)}{(5^{4+6-8}) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1+(7-0)))}{5-(46 \times (8-9))}$$

$$:= \frac{32+(1+(7-0))}{5+(4+(68-9))}$$

$$:= \frac{3-(2+(1-70))}{(5-(4-6)) \times (8+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-(2-1)) \times 70}{((5 \times 4) - 6) \times (8+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3+(21 \times (7-0))}{(5+(4+6)) \times (8+9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-2) \times 170}{(5 \times (4 \times (6+8))) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times 170}{(54 \times (6 \times 8)) + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32175}{48906} := \frac{(3+(2-1) \times 7) \times 5}{4+8 \times 9+0 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3-2-1+75}{(4+8) \times 9+06}$$

$$:= \frac{3+217+5}{(48+9) \times 06}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+2-1) \times 75}{(4+8 \times 9) \times 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32175}{60489} := \frac{3-2 \times (1-7-5)}{6+04 \times 8+9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+2 \times 1) \times 7 \times 5}{60 \times 4+89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32184}{65709} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 1 \times (8-4)}{65-7-09}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times (1+8) \times 4}{6 \times (5+70) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32184}{75096} := \frac{3-(2-(1 \times (8 \times 4)))}{7 \times (5-((0 \times 9)-6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (1 \times 8)) + 4)}{7 \times (5-(0-(9+6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2-(1-(8+4)))}{7+((5-(-09)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2-(1-(8-4)))}{7 \times (5-(0 \times 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times ((1+8) \times 4))}{(75-(-09)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1 \times (8-4)))}{7 \times (5-(0-(9-6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1^{84}))}{7 \times (5+(0-(9-6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1 \times (8+4)))}{7-(5+(0-96))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1 \times (8-4)))}{7 \times ((5 \times (0 \times 9)) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1+(8 \times 4)))}{7 \times (50-(9+6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1+(8+4)))}{7 \times (5 \times (0+(9-6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(1+(8-4)))}{7^{5-09+6}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2+(18 \times 4))}{((7-(5-0))^9) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (21 \times (8-4))}{7 \times ((5-(-09)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (21+(8 \times 4))}{7 \times (50+(9-6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (21+84)}{750-(9+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2-1^{84}}}{7-(5 \times (0 \times 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2 \times 1^{84}}}{75+(0-(9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2+1+8-4}}{7+5096}$$

$$:= \frac{3+(2+(1+84))}{7 \times (5 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3+(218+4)}{7 \times (5 \times (0+(9+6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{32+(1+84)}{7 \times ((5 \times (09)) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{32+(18+4)}{(7+(5-(-09))) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32186}{97405} := \frac{3+21+8+6}{(9 \times 7-40) \times 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{32410}{67598} := \frac{3 + 2^{4+1} + 0}{6 \times (7+5) + 9 - 8} \\ & \frac{32457}{80619} := \frac{3 + 2^4 + 5 + 7}{80 + 6 - 1 \times 9} \\ & \frac{32480}{91756} := \frac{(3+2) \times 48 + 0}{9 \times (1+75) - 6} \\ & \frac{32480}{96715} := \frac{(32-4) \times 8 + 0}{96 \times 7 \times 1 - 5} \\ & \frac{32496}{71085} := \frac{3 + (2 - (4 - (9 + 6)))}{7 \times ((1^{08}) \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{32^{4-9+6}}{(7 - (1 + (-08))) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 - ((4 - 9) \times 6))}{7 \times (10 \times (8 - 5))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times ((2^4) \times (9 - 6))}{7 \times ((1 - (-08)) \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 + ((4 + 9) \times 6))}{7 \times ((10 \times 8) - 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times 49)) - 6}{7 \times ((10 + 8) \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{32 + (4 \times 96)}{7 \times (10 \times (8 + 5))} \\ & \quad := \frac{32 \times (4 + 96)}{7 \times (10^{8-5})} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times ((2 + 4) \times 96)}{7 \times (108 \times 5)} \\ & \frac{32508}{41796} := \frac{((3^2) + (5 - 0)) \times 8}{41 + (7 + 96)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 - (2 \times 5)) \times (-08)}{4 \times ((1 - (7 - 9)) \times 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times 50)) + 8}{(4 - (1 - (7 \times 9))) \times 6} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^2) - (5 \times (-08))}{(4 + 17) \times (9 - 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + (2^5 + 0)) \times 8}{4 \times (1 - (7 - 96))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + (25 - 0)) \times 8}{(4 - (1^7)) \times 96} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 2) \times (50 - 8)}{(4 + (1^7)) \times (9 \times 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 - 2) \times (50 - 8)}{((4 - 1) \times (7 + 9)) + 6} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 - (2 - (5 - (-08)))}{(4 \times (1 - (7 - 9))) + 6} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times ((2 + (5 - 0)) \times 8)}{4 \times ((1^7) \times (9 \times 6))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 - (5 \times (-08)))}{(4 - (1^7)) \times (9 \times 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))}{4 + (1 + (7 + (9 + 6)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (2^{5+0 \times 8})}{(4 - (1^7)) \times (9 + 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (2 + (50 + 8))}{(4 - 1)^{7-9+6}} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (25 - (0 \times 8))}{4 \times (1 - (7 - (9 + 6)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (250 - 8)}{(4 + 17) \times (9 + 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{32 \times (50 - 8)}{4 \times ((1 + 7) \times (9 \times 6))} \\ & \frac{32508}{69174} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 50 + 8}{6 \times 91 + 7 - 4} \\ & \frac{32508}{71946} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 50 + 8}{7 + 1 \times 94 \times 6} \\ & \frac{32508}{74691} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 5) \times 08}{7 \times (46 + 9) + 1} \\ & \frac{32508}{91476} := \frac{3 - 2 + 50 - 8}{9 \times (1 + 4) + 76} \\ & \frac{32509}{41876} := \frac{(3 - 2) \times (50 + 9)}{4 \times (18 + 7 - 6)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 2) \times (50 + 9)}{(4 + 1^8) \times 76} \\ & \quad := \frac{32 \times (50 + 9)}{4 \times 1 \times 8 \times 76} \\ & \frac{32571}{60489} := \frac{3 + (25 - (7 \times 1))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8)) - 9} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (2 + (5 \times (7 - 1)))}{(6 \times (-04)) + 89} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 + (7 \times 1)))}{6 \times (0 - (4 - (8 + 9)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 - (25 - 71)}{6 + (0 - (4 - 89))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{6 \times ((048 - 9))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 25) \times (7 - 1)}{(60 \times 4) + (8 \times 9)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 25) \times (7 + 1)}{60 + (4 \times 89)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^2) + (5 \times 71)}{604 + (8 \times 9)} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 + (2 \times (5 \times (7 - 1)))}{60 + (48 + 9)} \\ & \frac{32589}{61047} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8 - 9)}{(61 - 04) \times 7} \\ & \frac{32589}{67014} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8 - 9)}{6 \times (70 - 1 + 4)} \\ & \frac{32589}{76041} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (5 + 8))) - 9}{7 \times ((6 \times (04)) - 1)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 \times (2^5)) + (8 \times 9)}{7 \times (60 - (4 \times 1))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 \times (2 + 58)) + 9}{7 \times (60 + (4 - 1))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 \times 25) - (8 \times 9)}{7 - (6 \times (0 \times 41))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 25) + (8 \times 9)}{7^{6-04+1}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 + 5)) \times (8 \times 9)}{7 \times (60 \times (4 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (25 + 8)) \times 9}{760 - (4 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times ((5 - 8) \times 9))}{7 \times (60 - 41)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (5 - (8 + 9)))}{7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (5 - 89))}{7 \times (60 - (4 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (5 \times (8 - 9)))}{7 \times (6 + (0 - (4 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((2^5) - 8) \times 9)}{7 \times (6^{04-1})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((2 + 5) \times 8) + 9)}{7 \times (60 + (4 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((2 + 5) \times 8) - 9)}{7 \times (6 - (0 - 41))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times 5) - (8 - 9))}{7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (5 \times (8 - 9)))}{7^{6-04 \times 1}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2^{5-8+9})}{7 \times (60 + (4 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 + (8 + 9)))}{7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 + (8 - 9)))}{7 - (6 + (0 - 41))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (((2 \times 5) + 8) \times 9)}{7 \times (60 - (4 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times 5) + (8 + 9))}{7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (5 - (8 - 9)))}{7 \times (6 + ((0 \times 4) - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9)))}{7 \times ((60 \times 4) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (5 \times (8 + 9)))}{7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 + 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (5 + (8 - 9)))}{7 \times (6 + (0 - (4 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (58 - 9))}{7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 2589}{7 + 6041}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32604}{97185} := \frac{(32 - 6) \times 04}{(9 \times (7 - 1) + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32619}{54780} := \frac{3 + 2^{6+1^9}}{5 \times 4 \times 7 + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32691}{48075} := \frac{3 - 2 + 6 + 9 + 1}{(4 + 8 - 07) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 2 \times (6 + 9) + 1}{48 + 07 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 26 + 91}{4 + 8 \times (07 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{32 + 6 \times 9 - 1}{(4 \times 8 - 07) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3^2 \times (69 - 1)}{(4 + 8) \times 075}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32709}{65418} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (7 - 0)) \times 9}{(6 + (54)) \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3^2) \times 70) - 9}{(65 + 4) \times 18}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 2)^7 + 0) + 9}{(6 \times (5 - (4 - 1))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 \times 7)) \times (-09)}{6 \times (5 - (4 \times (1 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 70)) \times 9}{6 \times ((5 \times 41) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (7 - 0))) + 9}{6 \times (5 + (4 + (1 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (7 - 0))) - 9}{6 + (5 \times (4 + (1 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2^7 + 0)) - 9}{6 \times (5^{4-1^8})}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (7 - 0))) + 9}{6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (7 - 0))) - 9}{6^{5-4+1^8}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2)^{7+0 \times 9}}{(6^5) \times (4 \times 18)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (7 - (0 \times 9))}{6 + (5 \times (4 \times (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (7 - (-09))}{6 + (5 + (41 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (7 + (-09))}{6 + (5 - (4 - (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (70 - 9)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 1)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + 709}{65 \times (4 + 18)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) - (7 - (0 \times 9))}{6 - (5 - (4 - (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) - (7 + (-09))}{6 + (5 + (4 - (1 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times (7 - (0 \times 9))}{6 + (5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times (7 - (-09))}{6^{5-4+1} \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times (70 - 9)}{(65 - 4) \times 18}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 \times (7 - 0))) \times 9}{(6 \times 54) - 18}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 + (7 - 0))) \times 9}{6 \times (54 - 18)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (27 - 0)) \times 9}{(6 + 54) \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 2) \times (7 \times (09))}{6 + ((5^4) - (1^8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (70 + 9)}{(6 \times (5 \times (4 + 1))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-2) \times (70-9)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 4) - 1)) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(32 \times (7-0)) - 9}{6 + ((54-1) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(32 + (7-0)) \times 9}{6 \times ((5^4-1) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3-27) \times (-09)}{6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((2 - (7-0)) \times 9)}{6 \times (5 + (4 - (1-8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{6 + (5 + (4 + (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - (7 - (-09)))}{6 - (5 - (41 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9)))}{((6-5)^4) + (1^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (7 \times (-09)))}{(6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 1))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 + (7 + (-09)))}{6^{5-4 \times 1^8}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (27 \times (-09))}{6 + (54 \times (1 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (7-0)) + 9)}{6 \times ((5 \times (4-1)) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2 + (7-0))^9)}{6 \times ((5+4) \times (1+8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((2-7) \times (-09))}{6 \times (5 + ((4+1) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9)))}{6 \times (5 - (4 - (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (7 \times (-09)))}{6 \times (5 \times (4 + (1 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (7 + (-09)))}{6 + (5 + (4 + (1 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (7 - (-09)))}{(65 - 41) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{6 \times (5 + (4 \times (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (7 - (-09)))}{6 \times (5 + (4 + (1 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (70 \times 9))}{6 \times ((5^4) - (1 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (70 + 9))}{6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (1 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (70 - 9))}{6 \times (54 + (1 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^2 + 7 \times 0 \times 9}{6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{2-7+09}}{6 \times (5 + (4 + 18))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times (7-0)) + 9)}{(6 \times (5 + (4 + 1))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times 70) - 9)}{(6 \times (5 + 41)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2^7 + 0) + 9)}{((6 \times 5) + (4 + 1)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9)))}{((6-5)^4) + (1+8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - (7 + (-09)))}{6 + (5 + (4 - (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (7 - (-09)))}{6 + ((5 + (4 - 1)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (70 + 9))}{(6 \times (54 + 1)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2^{7+0 \times 9})}{6 + ((5 - (4 - 1))^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (7 - (-09)))}{6 \times ((5 \times (4 - 1)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (70 + 9))}{6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (70 - 9))}{(6 + 5) \times (4 + (1 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (27 - (0 \times 9))}{6 \times (5 + (4 + (1^8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (27 - (-09))}{6 + ((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 2709}{6 + 5418}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (7 - (0 \times 9))}{6 - (5 - (41 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (7 - (-09))}{(6 - (5 - (4 - 1))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (7 \times (0 \times 9))}{(6 + (5 - (4 - 1))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 - (7 + (-09))}{(6 \times (5 + (4 + 1))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (7 - (0 \times 9))}{(6 \times 5) + 418}$$

$$:= \frac{32 \times (70 + 9)}{(6 + ((5^4) + 1)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{32 + (70 + 9)}{6 \times (5 + (4 \times (1 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{32 + (70 - 9)}{6 + (5 \times (4 \times (1 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{327 - 0 \times 9}{654 \times (1^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{327 \times 09}{654 \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{327 + 09}{654 + 18}$$

$$:= \frac{327 - 09}{654 - 18}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32716}{40895} := \frac{(((3^2) \times 7) - 1) \times 6}{(4 - (0 - 89)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + 7)) - 1) \times 6}{(40 + (8 - 9)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 7)) \times 16}{40 \times (8 - (9 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - 71)) \times 6}{(4 - (-08)) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + 7)) - (1 + 6)}{(4 + (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 27) + (1 - 6)}{(4 \times (0 \times 8)) + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times ((7 + 1)^6)}{(4^{08}) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 \times 7)) \times 16}{4 \times (0 + ((8 + 9) \times 5))}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(32+7-1) \times 6}{(40+(8+9)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{3-(2-(7 \times 1^6))}{4+(0-(8-(9+5)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2^7-1) \times 6)}{4 \times (0+(8 \times (9 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2^7) \times (1+6))}{40 \times (89-5)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2+7+1) \times 6)}{(40 \times 8) - 95} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2+7-1) \times 6)}{4 \times ((0 \times 8) + (9 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (7 - (1^6)))}{(4 \times (0 \times 8)) + (9 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (7 + (1+6)))}{(4 - (0 - (8+9))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (2^{7 \times 1^6})}{40 \times (8 + (9 - 5))} \\
 := \frac{3 + ((2 \times 7) - (1^6))}{4 \times ((0 \times 89) + 5)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (2 - (7 - (1 \times 6)))}{(4 \times (0 \times 89)) + 5} \\
 := \frac{3 + (2 + (7 \times 1^6))}{(4 - (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{3 + (2 + (7 + 16))}{40 + ((8 - 9) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{32 \times (7 \times 16)}{40 \times (8 \times (9 + 5))} \\
 := \frac{32 \times (7 + (1 + 6))}{(40 + (8 \times 9)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{32 \times (71 + 6)}{40 \times ((8 \times 9) + 5)} \\
 := \frac{32^{7+1-6}}{40 \times (8 \times (9 - 5))} \\
 := \frac{32 + 716}{40 + 895} \\
 := \frac{327 - (1 + 6)}{40 + (8 \times (9 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{327 - (1 - 6)}{(40 \times 8) + 95}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32758}{61049} := \frac{3-2-7 \times (5-8)}{6-1+04 \times 9} \\
 := \frac{327-5+8}{6 \times 104-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{41958} := \frac{(3 \times 2 + 7) \times 60}{41 + 958} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{91854} := \frac{(32+7) \times 60}{91^{85 \times 4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{94185} := \frac{3^2-7+6+0}{9 \times 4 \times 1-8-5} \\
 := \frac{3+27-6+0}{9+(4+1 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{32 \times (7-6)+0}{94+1-8+5} \\
 := \frac{(3^2-7)^6+0}{94+18 \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(3^2-7) \times 60}{9-4 \times (1-85)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32784}{90156} := \frac{3 \times (2^{7-8+4})}{9-(0-(1+56))} \\
 := \frac{(3-(2-7)) \times (8-4)}{(9+(-01)) \times (5+6)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2-(7-8)) \times 4)}{9 \times ((01 \times (5+6)))} \\
 := \frac{3-(2-(7+(8 \times 4)))}{(9-(-01)) \times (5+6)} \\
 := \frac{3+(2+(7+(8 \times 4)))}{90+(1+(5 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3-(27-84)}{9-(0-156)} \\
 := \frac{3-(2-(7+(8-4)))}{9+(0-((1-5) \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times ((2^7)-8))+4}{(90+1) \times (5+6)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{((3 \times 27) + 8) \times 4}{(90 - 1) \times (5 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (7 \times 8)) + 4)}{901 + 56} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (2 \times ((7 + 8) \times 4))}{90 \times (1 \times (5 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (2 + (7 + (8 - 4)))}{((9 - (-01)) \times 5) - 6} \\
 := \frac{3 - (2 - (7 - (8 - 4)))}{9 - (0 - (1 - (5 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(32 + 7) \times 84}{9015 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32795}{68401} := \frac{(3+2-7+9) \times 5}{6 \times (8+4) + 01} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{41796} := \frac{3+2+80 \times 5}{4+(1+7)^{9-6}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{49167} := \frac{3+2+80 \times 5}{4+9 \times 1 \times 67} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{61479} := \frac{3+2+805}{6 \times (1+4 \times 7 \times 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{79461} := \frac{3 \times (2+8+05)}{7 \times 9+46 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32810}{97465} := \frac{32-8+10}{97+4 \times (6-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32841}{76095} := \frac{3-2+8 \times (4+1)}{(7-6) \times 095} \\
 := \frac{3+284 \times 1}{760-95} \\
 := \frac{(3-2+8) \times 41}{760+95} \\
 := \frac{(3+2+8) \times 41}{(7+6) \times 095}
 \end{array}$$

$$:= \frac{328 \times 4 \times 1}{760 \times (9 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32850}{47961} := \frac{(3^2 - 8) \times 50}{4 + 7 \times 9 + 6 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(32 + 8) \times 5 + 0}{4 \times (79 - 6 \times 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32876}{41095} := \frac{(((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 7) - 6}{(4 + (10 + 9)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 76}{(4 + 10) \times 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times 8)) + 76}{((4 \times 10) - 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (8 \times 7))) + 6}{(4 + (1 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + ((8 \times 7) + 6)}{(4 \times 10) + (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (8 + (7 \times 6))}{(4 + (1 + 09)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 28) + 76}{4 \times ((1 + 09) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) + (8 - (7 - 6))}{4 \times (1 - (0 - (9 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (28 + 7)) \times 6}{(4 - (1 - 0)) \times 95}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (28 - 7)) \times 6}{4 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))}{4 \times (10 + 95)}$$

$$:= \frac{(32 + 8) \times 76}{4 \times (10 \times 95)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (2 - (8 - (7 - 6)))}{4 + ((1^{09}) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (8 - (7 \times 6)))}{(4 \times 10) + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6))}{(4 \times (1 + 09)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7 - 6)))}{4 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (8 + 76))}{(4 + 10) \times (9 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times 8) + (7 - 6))}{(4 + (1^{09})) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2^8) + (7 + 6))}{4 \times ((10 \times 9) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 - ((8 - 7)^6))}{4 + (1 - (0 \times 95))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (2 + (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(4 - (1^{09})) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (28 + (7 + 6))}{41 - (0 - (9 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (28 + (7 - 6))}{((4 + (1 - 0)) \times 9) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (287 - 6)}{(4 \times (10 \times 9)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{32 + (8 \times (7 - 6))}{4 + (1 - (0 - (9 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{328 + 76}{410 + 95}$$

$$:= \frac{328 - 76}{410 - 95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32901}{47856} := \frac{3 - (2 - (9 - (-01)))}{4 \times (7 + (8 - (5 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (9 \times (-01)))}{(4 + (7 - (8 - 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0)) - 1}{4 \times (7 + (8 - (5 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) + (90 \times 1)}{(4 + (7 + (8 + 5))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 1)}{((4 - 7) \times 8) + 56}$$

$$:= \frac{329 - (-01)}{4 \times ((7 + (8 + 5)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + 90)) - 1}{4 + ((78 \times 5) + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32907}{65814} := \frac{((3^2) \times (9 - 0)) - 7}{((6 \times 5) + (8 - 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((3^2) + (9 - 0)) \times 7}{(6 + (58 - 1)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0)) - 7}{(6 + (5 + (8 \times 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 2)^9 + 0) + 7}{6 + (5 + (8 + (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 \times 9)) \times (-07)}{6 \times (5 \times (8 - (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 + 9)) \times (-07)}{(6 - 5) \times (8 \times 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (9 - 0))) + 7}{(6 + (5 + (8 + 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (9 - 0))) - 7}{65 - (8 + (1 + 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + 90)) + 7}{6 + (5 \times (8 \times 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (29 - 0)) + 7}{6 + ((5 + 8) \times 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) - (9 + (-07))}{6 - (5 - (8 - (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2)^{9-07}}{6 \times (5 + (8 - (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (9 - (-07))}{(6 + 5) \times (8 - (1 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 2) + (90 + 7)}{6 + (5 \times (8 \times (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times (9 - (-07))}{6 \times ((5 + (8 - 1)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) \times (9 + (-07))}{6 - (5 \times (8 - 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) + (9 + (-07))}{6 + (5 + (8 - (1 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^2) + (90 - 7)}{(6 + (5 \times (8 \times 1))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (2 \times (9 - 0))) \times 7}{6 \times ((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3+2) \times (9 - (0 \times 7))}{6 \times (5 \times (8 - (1+4)))} &:= \frac{3^{2^{9-07}}}{6 \times (5 + (8+14))} &:= \frac{32 + (9 + (-07))}{(6 \times (5 + (8 - 1))) - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (9 \times (07))}{6 - (5 \times (8 \times (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7)}{65 - (8 + 1^4)} &:= \frac{32 + (90 - 7)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 8) - 1)) - 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (9 + (-07))}{6 + (5 - (8 - (1^4)))} &:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times 90) - 7)}{(6 \times (58 \times 1)) + 4} &:= \frac{329 - (0 \times 7)}{658 \times (1^4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (9 + (-07))}{6 + (5 - (8 - (1^4)))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7)))}{6 - (5 - (8 + 1^4))} &:= \frac{329 - (-07)}{658 + 14} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 2) \times (90 - 7)}{6 + (5 \times (8 \times 1 \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (9 - (-07)))}{65 + (8 + (1 - 4))} &:= \frac{329 + (-07)}{(6 + (5 \times 8)) \times 14} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{6 + (5 + (8 + 1^4))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (90 - 7))}{(6 \times (58 - 1)) - 4} & \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 - (-07)))}{(6 \times 5) + (8 - (1 \times 4))} &:= \frac{3 + 2^{9-07}}{6 + (5 + (8 - (1 + 4)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32947}{80615} := \frac{(3 - 2 + 9) \times 4 + 7}{80 + (6 + 1) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7)))}{6 + (5 - (8 + 1^4))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{(6 - 5) \times ((8 - 1) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(3 + (2 + 9) \times 4) \times 7}{806 - 1^5} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 + (-07)))}{6 - (5 - (8 + (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 + (9 - (-07)))}{6 + ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4)} & \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (2 \times (9 \times (-07)))}{6 \times ((5 \times 8) - (1 - 4))} &:= \frac{3 + (2 + (90 + 7))}{(6 + (5 \times (8 + 1))) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{41580} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (9 + 6) + 7)}{4 \times 15 + 80} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7)}{6 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + (29 - (0 \times 7))}{6 + (58 \times (1^4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{51084} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (9 + 6) + 7)}{(51 - 08) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7)))}{6 - (5 - (8 - (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + (29 - (-07))}{6 \times (5 + (8 \times (1^4)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{51840} := \frac{3 + 29 \times 6 \times 7}{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 40} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2 - (9 \times (-07)))}{6 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 + 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + (29 + (-07))}{6 + ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) + 4)} & \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2^{9-07})}{6 + (5 + (8 + (1 + 4)))} &:= \frac{3 + 2907}{6 + 5814} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32970}{46158} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}{4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{6 \times (5 - (8 - 14))} &:= \frac{32 - (9 - (0 \times 7))}{6 + (5 \times (8 \times (1^4)))} &:= \frac{32 - (9 - (7 - 0))}{4 + (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (2 + (9 - (-07)))}{6 \times (5 + (8 + (1 + 4)))} &:= \frac{32 - (9 - (-07))}{(6 - (5 - (8 - 1))) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 + (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))}{4 + (6 - (1 - (5 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (29 - (0 \times 7))}{6 \times (5 - (8 \times (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{32 - (9 \times (-07))}{((6 \times 5) + 8) \times (1 + 4)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + 9)) + (7 - 0)}{4 - (6 - (1 \times 58))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (29 - (-07))}{6 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4)} &:= \frac{32 - (9 + (-07))}{6 \times (5 + (8 + (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0))}{4 + (61 + (5 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (29 + (-07))}{(6 + 5) \times (8 + (1 \times 4))} &:= \frac{32 + (9 - (0 \times 7))}{(6 \times (5 + (8 \times 1))) + 4} &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 + 70))}{(4 + (6 - (1 - 5))) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{3^2 + 9 \times 0 \times 7}{6 + (5 + (8 - (1^4)))} &:= \frac{32 + (9 - (-07))}{6 \times (5 + (8 - (1 - 4)))} &:= \frac{32 + (9 \times (7 - 0))}{(((4 \times 6) + 1) \times 5) + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{32976}{84501} := \frac{3 + 29 \times (7 - 6)}{8 \times 4 + 50 \times 1} \\ & \frac{32981}{70564} := \frac{3 + 2 \times 9 \times (8 - 1)}{(70 + 5 - 6) \times 4} \\ & \frac{34017}{85629} := \frac{3 \times 4 + 017}{8 + 5 \times (6 - 2 + 9)} \\ & \frac{34056}{71928} := \frac{(3 + 40) \times (5 + 6)}{71 + 928} \\ & \frac{34056}{71982} := \frac{3 \times 40 + 56}{(71 - 9) \times (8 - 2)} \\ & \frac{34056}{89712} := \frac{(3 + 40) \times (5 + 6)}{89 \times 7 \times 1 \times 2} \\ & \frac{34056}{91872} := \frac{(3^4 + 05) \times 6}{(9 - 1) \times 87 \times 2} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 - 40 \times (5 - 6)}{(9 - (1 - 8) \times 7) \times 2} \\ & \frac{34125}{87906} := \frac{3 + 4 + (1 + 2)^5}{8 + 7 \times 90 + 6} \\ & \frac{34128}{56970} := \frac{(3^4 \times 1 - 2) \times 8}{5 + (6 + 9) \times 70} \\ & \frac{34170}{58692} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 1) + 70}{(58 + 6 + 9) \times 2} \\ & \frac{34182}{56970} := \frac{((3 \times (4 - 1))^8) \times 2}{5 \times (6 \times (9^7 + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(3 \times 4) + (18^2)}{(5 - (6 - 9)) \times 70} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 41) + (8 - 2)}{5 - ((6 - 9) \times 70)} \\ & := \frac{(3^4 - 1^8) \times 2}{5 + (6 + (9 + 70))} \\ & := \frac{(3^4 \times 1) + (8 - 2)}{(5 \times (6 + 9)) + 70} \\ & := \frac{(341 \times 8) + 2}{(56 + 9) \times 70} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (1 \times 82))}{56 + (9 + 70)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 - (1 - 8)) \times 2)}{5 \times (6 + (9 + (7 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 - (1 - (8^2)))}{5 \times (6 - (9 - 70))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 - (1^{82}))}{5 - (6 - (9 + (7 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 - (1 - 82))}{5 \times (6 + (9 + 70))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times ((1^8) + 2))}{5 - (6 + (9 - 70))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 + 2)))}{(5 \times (6 \times 9)) - 70} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 2)))}{(5 + (6 - 9)) \times 70} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (1 \times (8^2)))}{(5 \times (6 \times 9)) + 70} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (1 + (8^2)))}{5 \times (6 + (9 \times (7 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (1 + (8 - 2)))}{(5 \times (6 - 9)) + 70} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (41 + (8^2))}{5 \times ((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (41 + (8 - 2))}{5 \times ((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{3^4 - 1^8 - 2}{(5 \times (6 + 9)) - 70} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{3 + (4 + (1 + (8 \times 2)))}{5 \times (6 + (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 + (41 \times (8 - 2))}{(5 \times 69) + 70} \\ & := \frac{3 + (41 + (8^2))}{5 \times (6^9 - 7 + 0)} \\ & := \frac{3 + 4182}{5 + 6970} \\ & \frac{34182}{75960} := \frac{3 \times (4 - (1^{82}))}{(7 \times 5) - (9 + (6 - 0))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3^4 - 1^{82}}{7 + (59 - (6 - 0))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 - (4 - (1 \times (8^2)))}{7 \times (5 + (9 + (6 - 0)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 - (4 - (1 \times 82))}{(7 + (5 - 9)) \times 60} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 4) \times (18^2)}{(75 + 9) \times 60} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^4 + 1^8) \times 2}{(7 - 5) \times (9 \times 60)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^4) \times (1 + (8 - 2))}{(7 + (5 + 9)) \times 60} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^4) \times (18 \times 2)}{(7 + 5) \times (9 \times 60)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^4 \times 1) \times (8^2)}{(7 + 5) \times 960} \\ & \frac{34187}{92506} := \frac{(3^4 - 1^8) + 7}{92 - (5 \times (0 \times 6))} \\ & \quad := \frac{34 + 187}{92 + 506} \\ & \quad := \frac{3 \times (((4 - 1) \times 8) - 7)}{(9 - (2^5)) \times (-06)} \\ & \quad := \frac{34 \times (18 - 7)}{92 \times (5 - (-06))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3^4) \times 187}{(9^2) \times 506} \\ & \quad := \frac{(3 + 4) \times 187}{(9 - 2) \times 506} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{34 \times (1 \times (8 \times 7))}{92 \times (50 + 6)} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34209}{71568} & := \frac{3^4 \times 20 + 9}{71 \times (56 - 8)} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34251}{97860} & := \frac{3 \times (4 - 2 + 5 \times 1)}{(9 - 7 + 8) \times 6 + 0} \\ & := \frac{3^4 \times 2 + 5 + 1}{(9 + 7 - 8) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{342 - 5 - 1}{(9 - 7) \times 8 \times 60} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 42 \times (5 - 1)}{(9 + (7 + 8)) \times 60} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34278}{59160} & := \frac{(3 + 4) \times 27 + 8}{5 \times (9 - 1 + 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34278}{91605} & := \frac{3 \times 4 \times (2 + 7) + 8}{9 + 1 + 60 \times 5} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34281}{59670} & := \frac{3 + 4 \times 2^{8+1}}{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 70} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34290}{76581} & := \frac{(3 - 4 + 2) \times 90}{7 \times 6 \times 5 - 8 - 1} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34502}{96871} & := \frac{3 \times (4 + 50 - 2)}{9 \times 6 \times 8 + 7 - 1} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34506}{81792} & := \frac{3^{4+5-06}}{8 \times ((1^7) + (9 - 2))} \\ & := \frac{34 + 506}{8 \times ((1 + 79) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5 - 0))) - 6}{8 \times ((17 - 9) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (45 - (0 \times 6))}{(81 + 79) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 + 50) \times 6)}{(8 + 1) \times ((7 + 9)^2)} \\ & := \frac{3^{4-5+06}}{8 + (1 + (7 \times (9^2)))} \\ & := \frac{3^{4-5 \times 0 \times 6}}{8 \times (17 + (9 - 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34506}{97128} & := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5 - 06}{(9 + 7 + 1 + 2) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3^{4-5+06}}{9 \times (7 \times 12 - 8)} \\ & \text{---} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34510}{89726} & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) + 10}{8 + (97 + (2 \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) - 10}{8 - (9 - (72 - 6))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (4 - 5)) \times 10}{89 + (7 + (2 + 6))} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (4 + 5)) \times 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7 - 2) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (4 - 5)) \times 10}{(8^9 - 7) - (2 \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (4 - 5)) \times 10}{(8 + 9) \times (7 - 2) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 4) \times 10}{89 + (7 + (2 + 6))} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) + 10}{8 + (97 + (2 \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (1 - 0)))}{(8 + (9 + (7 + 2))) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (4 + 5)) \times 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7 - 2) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{(34 \times 5) - 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7^2) - 6))} \\ & := \frac{(34 - 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (97 - 2)) - 6} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 10)}{(((8 + 9) \times 7) - 2) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{345 - 10}{897 - 26} \\ & := \frac{345 + 10}{897 + 26} \\ & := \frac{(34 + 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 2))) + 6} \\ & := \frac{34 \times (5 + 10)}{(8 + 9) \times (72 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34510}{89726} & := \frac{(3 + (4 - 5)) \times 10}{(8^9 - 7) - (2 \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) - 10}{8 - (9 - (72 - 6))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (5 + (1 - 0)))}{(8 - (9 - (7 \times 2))) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (1 - 0))}{((8 + 9) \times (7 - 2)) + 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (4 - 5)) \times 10}{89 + (7 + (2 + 6))} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) + 10}{8 + (97 + (2 \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (1 - 0)))}{(8 + (9 + (7 + 2))) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (4 + 5)) \times 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7 - 2) \times 6))} \\ & := \frac{(34 \times 5) - 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7^2) - 6))} \\ & := \frac{(34 - 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (97 - 2)) - 6} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 10)}{(((8 + 9) \times 7) - 2) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{345 - 10}{897 - 26} \\ & := \frac{345 + 10}{897 + 26} \\ & := \frac{(34 + 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 2))) + 6} \\ & := \frac{34 \times (5 + 10)}{(8 + 9) \times (72 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34517}{98620} & := \frac{3 - (4 - (5 + 17))}{(9 \times 8) - (6 \times (2 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (5 \times 1))) \times 7}{(9 \times 8) + (6 + (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (4 + ((5 - 1) \times 7))}{((9 + 8) \times 6) - (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (4 + (5 \times (1 \times 7)))}{(9 - 8) \times (6 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (4 + ((5 + 1) \times 7))}{(9 - (8 - 6)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (45 + (1 + 7))}{98 + (62 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (1^7))}{9 \times (8 + (6 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (4 + (5 - 1))) \times 7}{(9 + (8 - 6)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 4) + (5 + 1)) \times 7}{9 \times ((8 - 6) \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (4 \times (5 \times 1))) \times 7}{(9 + (8 + 6)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (4 \times (5 + (1 - 7)))}{(9 \times (8 - 6)) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((4 \times 5) - 1) \times 7)}{(9 + (8 \times 6)) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34528}{79016} := \frac{3 - 4 + 5 + 2^8}{7 \times (90 + 1 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{78912} := \frac{(3 + 4 - 5) \times 60}{7 + 89 \times (1 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{89712} := \frac{(3 + 4 + 5) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times (1 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 4 + 5) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times 1^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 45) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times 12}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{91728} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 560}{91 \times 7 \times 28}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{98172} := \frac{(3 + 45) \times 60}{9 + 8172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34572}{61908} := \frac{3 - 4 - 5 + 7^2}{6 - 1 + 9 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34596}{78120} := \frac{3 - 4 + 5^{9-6}}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 4 - (5 - 9) \times 6}{7 \times (8 + 1 \times 2) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4 \times 5 \times 9 + 6)}{7 \times (8 + 1) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 4^5 - 96}{7 \times (8 \times 120)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34608}{95172} := \frac{((3 \times 4) + (6 - 0)) \times 8}{9 \times ((5 + 17) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (6 - 0))) \times 8}{(9 \times (5 + (1 \times 7))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) + 8}{((9 \times 5) - 1) \times (7 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) - 8}{9 - (5 - 172)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (4 - (6 - 0))) \times 8}{9 + (5 - (1 - (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(34 - (6 - 0)) \times 8}{((9 \times 5) - 1) \times (7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 46) \times (-08)}{951 - (7 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) + 8)}{9 + (51 \times (7 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) - 8)}{9 + (51 + 72)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((4 + (6 - 0)) \times 8)}{((95 - 1) \times 7) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4 - (6 \times (0 \times 8)))}{9 + (5 + (17 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4 \times (6 - (0 \times 8)))}{9 \times ((5 - (1 - 7)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{34 - (6 - (0 \times 8))}{9 - (5 - (1 + 72))}$$

$$:= \frac{34 - (6 - (-08))}{9 + (51 - (7 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{34 - (6 + (-08))}{9 \times (5 + (1 + (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{34 + (6 + (-08))}{(9 + (5 \times (1 \times 7))) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34612}{89075} := \frac{34 \times 6^{1^2}}{(8 + 90 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34615}{87290} := \frac{3 + 4 \times (6 - 1^5)}{87 - 29 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{34 + 6 + 1 + 5}{87 + 29 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 4 \times (6 - 1)) \times 5}{(8 - 7) \times 290}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 46 \times 15}{(8 \times 7 + 2) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(346 - 1) \times 5}{(8 + 7) \times 290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34692}{71508} := \frac{(3 + 46) \times (9 - 2)}{715 - 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34780}{59126} := \frac{(3 \times 4 - 7) \times 8 + 0}{5 - 9 \times (1 - 2 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{34 \times 7 - 8 + 0}{5 \times 91 - 2^6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (4 \times 7 - 8) + 0}{(5 + 9 + 1 + 2) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34809}{72165} := \frac{3^4 - 8 + 09}{7 - 2 + 165}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{34821}{70596} := \frac{3 \times 48 + 2 \times 1}{70 \times 5 - 9 \times 6} \\ & := \frac{(3^4 - 8) \times (2 + 1)}{(70 - 5 + 9) \times 6} \\ & \frac{34821}{70956} := \frac{3 + 48 + 2 \times 1}{7 + 095 + 6} \\ & \frac{34826}{79150} := \frac{3 - 4 + 8 + 26}{(7 + 9 - 1) \times 5 + 0} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 4) \times (8 \times 2 + 6)}{7 \times (9 + 1) \times 5 + 0} \\ & := \frac{348 - 2 + 6}{(7 + 9 \times 1) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{348 + 26}{(7 + 9 + 1) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 4 \times (82 + 6)}{(7 + 9) \times 150} \\ & \frac{34827}{91650} := \frac{34 + (8 - 2) \times 7}{(9 + 1 - 6) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{(3 - 4) \times (8 - 27)}{(9 + 1^6) \times 5 + 0} \\ & := \frac{3^4 + 8^2 + 7}{(9 - 1^6) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{3 + 4 \times (8 - 2) \times 7}{9 \times 1^6 \times 50} \\ & := \frac{3 + 4 \times 8^2 + 7}{(9 - 1 + 6) \times 50} \\ & := \frac{34 + 8 \times 2 + 7}{(9 - 1 \times 6) \times 50} \\ & \frac{34851}{69702} := \frac{((3 - (4 - 8)) \times 5) - 1}{(6 \times 9) - (7 \times (-02))} \\ & := \frac{((3^4) - 8) \times (5 - 1)}{(6 \times (97 - 0)) + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{((3 + (4 \times 8)) \times 5) - 1}{6 \times (9 + (7^{02}))} \\ & := \frac{((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5) + 1}{(69 + (7 - 0)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 8) + (5 \times 1)}{(6 \times 9) + (70 - 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times ((4 \times 8) - 5)) + 1}{6 + ((9 + 70) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))) + 1}{69 + (7 + (-02))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times 8)) + (5 - 1)}{6 - (97 \times (-02))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (4 + (8 - 5))) + 1}{(6 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (4 + 8)) - (5 + 1)}{69 - (7 - (-02))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (4 + 8)) - (5 - 1)}{6 + (9 + (7^{02}))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 4) - (8 - (5 - 1))}{(6 - (9 - (7 - 0)))^2} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 4) + (85 \times 1)}{(6 \times 9) + (70 \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 4) + (85 - 1)}{6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 48) - (5 \times 1)}{(69 + 70) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{(3^4) - (8 \times (5 - 1))}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) + 2} \\ & := \frac{(3^4) - (8 + (5 - 1))}{6 \times (9 - (7 \times (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{(3^4) - (8 - 51)}{((6 \times 9) + 70) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{(34 \times (8 - 5)) + 1}{(6 + (97 - 0)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{3 - ((4 - 8) \times (5 \times 1))}{6 - (9 - (7^{02}))} \\ & := \frac{3 - ((4 - 8) \times (5 + 1))}{6 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - ((8 \times 5) - 1))}{69 + (7 - (0 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{3 - (4 - (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{6 - (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (8 - (5 + 1)))}{6 - (9 - (7 + (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (8 \times (5 \times 1)))}{69 + (7 - (-02))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (8 \times (5 - 1)))}{69 - (7 - (0 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{6 + (9 + (7 - (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 - (85 + 1))}{(6 + (9 + 70)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{3 - (4 + (8 - 51))}{6 \times (9 + (7 + (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1)}{6 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 2)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 \times (8 \times 5)) + 1)}{69 \times (7 \times (02))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times ((4 + 8) \times 51)}{6 \times (9 \times (70 - 2))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 - (8 - (5 + 1)))}{6 \times (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{(6^9 - 7 + 0) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (8 - (5 - 1)))}{6 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4^{8-5+1})}{6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0))^2)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + ((8 \times 5) + 1))}{6 \times (9 \times (7 + (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{(6 - 9) \times (7 \times (-02))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (8 - (5 + 1)))}{6^{9-7+0 \times 2}} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (8 + (5 + 1)))}{6 \times (9 + (7 - (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (4 + (8 + 51))}{6 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (48 + 51)}{6 \times (97 - (-02))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{3^{4-8+5 \times 1}}{6 - (9 - (7 - (-02)))} & := \frac{3 + (48 + (5 + 1))}{(6 - (9 \times 7)) \times (-02)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34986}{57120} := \frac{3^4 + 9 \times 8 - 6}{(5 + 7 \times 1) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1)}{6 - ((9 - 70) \times 2)} & := \frac{3 + 485 + 1}{6 + 970 + 2} & := \frac{3 - (4 - 9) \times 8 + 6}{5 \times (7 + 1) \times 2 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (((4 + 8) \times 5) - 1)}{(69 - (7 - 0)) \times 2} & := \frac{3 + 485 - 1}{6 + 970 - 2} & := \frac{(3 \times 4 + 9)^{8-6}}{(5 \times 7 + 1) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{3 + ((4 + 8) \times (5 \times 1))}{(6 \times 9) + (70 + 2)} & := \frac{3 + 4851}{6 + 9702} & := \frac{3 \times (4 \times 9 \times 8 + 6)}{(5 + 7) \times 120} \\
 & := \frac{3 + ((48 \times 5) - 1)}{(6 + (9 + (7 - 0)))^2} & := \frac{3485 + 1}{6970 + 2} & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 - (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{6 + (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2)))} & := \frac{3485 - 1}{6970 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35046}{81972} := \frac{35 + 04 \times 6}{8 \times (1 + 9 + 7) + 2} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 - (8 - (5 + 1)))}{6 + (9 - (7 + (-02)))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{35046}{87912} := \frac{35 + 04 \times 6}{8 + 7 \times (9 + 1) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 \times (8 - (5 - 1)))}{(6^{9-7+0}) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34860}{71295} := \frac{34 \times 8 + 60}{7 \times 1 \times (2 + 95)} & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 \times (8 \times (5 + 1)))}{6 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 2)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{35061}{42978} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times 06 + 1)}{4 + 2 \times (9 \times 7 - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1)))}{6 + ((9 + (7 - 0))^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34907}{68251} := \frac{3 + 4 \times (9 + 07)}{68 \times 2 - 5 \times 1} & := \frac{3 \times 50 + 6 - 1}{4 + 2 \times 97 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 \times (8 + (5 + 1)))}{69 + (7^{02})} & & \\
 & := \frac{3 + 4^{8-5 \times 1}}{(6 - (9 - 70)) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34916}{52780} := \frac{(34 + 9) \times 16}{5 \times 2^7 + 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35084}{97216} := \frac{(350 + 8) \times 4}{(9 \times 7)^2 - 1^6} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{6 + (9 + (7 + (-02)))} & & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (8 - (5 - 1)))}{6 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34920}{57618} := \frac{(3 \times 4 - 9) \times 20}{5 + 76 + 18} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35092}{87164} := \frac{(3 + 5 + 09) \times 2}{8 + 71 - 6 + 4} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (8 \times (5 \times 1)))}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 2} & := \frac{(3 + 4 + 9) \times 20}{(5 \times (7 + 6) + 1) \times 8} & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{(6 \times 9) + (7 \times (-02))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34920}{71586} := \frac{(3 \times 4 - 9) \times 20}{71 + 58 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35096}{74128} := \frac{35 \times 09 + 6}{7^{4-1} \times 2 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (8 + 51))}{6 - (9 \times (7 \times (-02)))} & := \frac{(3^4 + 9) \times 2 + 0}{71 \times 5 + 8 + 6} & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (4 + (85 - 1))}{(6 - 97) \times (-02)} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{35109}{68724} := \frac{3^5 + 1 - 09}{68 \times 7 - 2^4} \\
 & := \frac{3 + (48 \times (5 \times 1))}{6 \times (9 \times (7 - (-02)))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34970}{52186} := \frac{3^4 - 9 - 7 + 0}{5 \times 2 + 1 + 86} & \\
 & := \frac{3 + (48 \times (5 + 1))}{6 \times (97 - (0 \times 2))} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{35148}{70296} := \frac{((3 \times 5) - 1) \times 48}{7 \times (0 + (2 \times 96))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(3 \times (5 + 1^4)) + 8}{(7^{02}) + (9 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times (5 - 1)) + 48}{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times 9))) - 6} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times 51) - 48}{7 \times (0 + (2 \times (9 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(3^{5-1^4}) + 8}{70 + (2 \times (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{(3^{5 \times 1}) - (4 + 8)}{7 \times (0 + ((2 + 9) \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{(3^5 \times 1^4) \times 8}{(70 + 2) \times (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{(3^{5-1}) - (4 + 8)}{((7 \times (02)) + 9) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{(3^5) + (1 - 48)}{7 \times (0 + (2 + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5 + 1)) \times (4 \times 8)}{70 + ((2^9) - 6)} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5 + 1)) \times 48}{(7 - (-02)) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5 - 1)) \times 48}{7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 96)} \\
 := \frac{(3 + 5) \times (1 + (4 \times 8))}{(70 + (2 \times 9)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 - (1 - (4 - 8)))}{7 - (0 - (2 - (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 - (1 \times (4 + 8)))}{7 + (0 - (2 - (9 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 - (1 + (4 \times 8)))}{70 - (2^{9-6})} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 - (1 + 48))}{70 + ((2 \times 9) + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 \times ((1^4) - 8))}{70 + (2 \times (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 \times ((1 - 4) \times 8))}{(70 - 29) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 \times (1 \times (4 - 8)))}{(7^{02}) - (9 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 + ((1 - 4) \times 8))}{(70 \times 2) - 96} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 + (1 - (4 \times 8)))}{70 - ((2 \times 9) - 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 + (1 \times (4 - 8)))}{70 - (2 + (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 + (1 + (4 - 8)))}{7 + (0 - (2 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 + (1 + (4 - 8)))}{7 + (0 - (2 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((5 \times 1 \times 4) + 8)}{7 \times (0 + ((2 \times 9) + 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((5 + (1 + 4)) \times 8)}{(7 + (-02)) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 - (1 - (4 \times 8)))}{(7 - (0 - 29)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 - (1 - (4 + 8)))}{(7 - ((0 \times 2) - 9)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 - (1 \times (4 - 8)))}{(7 \times (0 \times 2)) + (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 - (1 - 48))}{(70 - (2 \times 9)) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (1^4 + 8))}{(7 + (-02)) \times (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (1 - (4 - 8)))}{(7 - (0 - (2 \times 9))) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1^{48}}{7 - (0 - (29 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5^{1^4+8})}{((7 + (-02))^9) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 + (1^4 + 8))}{(7 + (0 - (2 - 9))) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 + (1 + (4 + 8)))}{(7 - (0 - (2 + 9))) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 + (1 + (4 - 8)))}{7 - (0 - (2 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (51 \times (4 + 8))}{(70 - 2) \times (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (51 + (4 + 8))}{7 \times ((0 \times 2) + (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (51 + 48)}{(70 + 29) \times 6} \\
 := \frac{3^{5+1+4-8}}{70 + (2 - (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + ((5 - 1) \times (4 \times 8))}{70 + (2 \times 96)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - ((1^4)^8))}{70 - (2 + (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - ((1 - 4) \times 8))}{(7^{02}) + (9 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - (1 - (4 \times 8)))}{70 + (2^{9-6})} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - (1 \times (4 - 8)))}{7 - (0 - (2 + (9 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - (1 + (4 - 8)))}{7 - ((0 \times 2) - (9 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 - (1 - 48))}{(7 \times (02)) + 96} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times ((1^4) \times 8))}{(70 \times 2) - (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times (1 - (4 - 8)))}{7 \times (0 + (2^{9-6}))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times (1 \times (4 + 8)))}{70 + (2 + (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times (1 \times 48))}{(7 - (-02)) \times (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times (1 + (4 + 8)))}{70 + ((2 + 9) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1^4 + 8))}{(7^{02}) - (9 + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 \times (4 + 8)))}{(7 \times (-02)) + (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 \times (4 - 8)))}{7 + (0 - (2 - (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 \times 48))}{70 - ((2 - 9) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 + (4 \times 8)))}{(7 \times (-02)) + 96} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 + (4 + 8)))}{7 \times (0 + (2 \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (1 + (4 - 8)))}{7 - ((0 \times 2) - (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (14 \times 8))}{((7^{02}) - 9) \times 6}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (14 - 8))}{70 + ((2 - 9) \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + (51 + (4 + 8))}{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times 9))) + 6} \\
 := \frac{3 + (51 + (4 - 8))}{70 + (2 \times (9 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (51 + 48)}{(70 - 2) \times (9 - 6)} \\
 := \frac{35 - ((1^4)^8)}{(7 \times (02)) + (9 \times 6)} \\
 := \frac{35 - (1 - 48)}{70 - (2 - 96)} \\
 := \frac{35 \times ((1^4) \times 8)}{70 \times (2^{9-6})} \\
 := \frac{35 \times (1 - (4 - 8))}{70 \times (2 + (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{35 \times (1 \times (4 + 8))}{70 \times ((2 \times 9) - 6)} \\
 := \frac{35 \times (14 - 8)}{70 \times (2 \times (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{35 + (14 \times 8)}{7 \times (0 - ((2 - 9) \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{35 + 148}{70 + 296} \\
 := \frac{351 + 48}{702 + 96} \\
 := \frac{351 - 48}{702 - 96} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35190}{72864} := \frac{3 \times 51 \times 90}{(7 \times 2 + 8) \times 6^4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35192}{48760} := \frac{3^{5-1^9} + 2}{48 + 7 + 60} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35216}{98704} := \frac{(35 \times 2 + 1) \times 6}{(9 + 8) \times 70 + 4}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35217}{80496} := \frac{((3^5 - 2) - 1) \times 7}{(80 \times 4) + 96} \\
 := \frac{((3 + 5) \times 21) + 7}{8 \times (0 - (4 - (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 21)) + 7}{8 \times (0 - (4 - 96))} \\
 := \frac{(3^{5-2 \times 1}) \times 7}{8 \times ((0 \times 4) + (9 \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5 \times 21)) \times 7}{8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5^{2-1})) \times 7}{(8 \times (04)) + 96} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5^2)) \times (1 + 7)}{8 \times (0 + (4^{9-6}))} \\
 := \frac{(3 + (5 + 21)) \times 7}{8 \times (0 + (4 + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{(3 + 5) \times 217}{8 \times (0 + 496)} \\
 := \frac{3 - (5 \times (2 \times (1 - 7)))}{80 + (4^{9-6})} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (((5^2) - 1) \times 7)}{(8 - (-04)) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((5 \times 21) + 7)}{8 \times ((0 \times 4) + 96)} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((5 + (2 \times 1)) \times 7)}{8 \times (0 + ((4 \times 9) + 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times ((5 + (2 + 1)) \times 7)}{(8 + (-04)) \times 96} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 \times ((2 - 1) \times 7))}{8 \times (0 - ((4 - 9) \times 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (2 \times (1 \times 7)))}{8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 + 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (21 + 7))}{80 \times (4 \times (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{3 \times (5 + (2 \times (1^7)))}{8 \times ((0 \times 49) + 6)} \\
 := \frac{3 + ((5^{2 \times 1}) + 7)}{80^{4-9+6}}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{3 + (5 - (2 - (1^7)))}{80 - (4^{9-6})} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 \times (2 + 17))}{8 - (0 - (4 \times (9 \times 6)))} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5^2 \times 1^7)}{(8 + (-04))^{9-6}} \\
 := \frac{3 + (5 + (2 \times 17))}{8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 := \frac{35 \times ((2 - 1) \times 7)}{80 \times (4 + (9 - 6))} \\
 := \frac{35 \times (2 + (1 + 7))}{8 \times (0 + (4 + 96))} \\
 := \frac{35 \times (2 + 17)}{80 \times (4 + (9 + 6))} \\
 := \frac{35 + 217}{80 + 496} \\
 := \frac{3521 + 7}{(80 + 4) \times 96} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35219}{80746} := \frac{35 - 2 - 1 + 9}{8 \times (07 + 4) + 6} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{41976} := \frac{(3^5 + 2) \times 8 + 0}{4 \times (1 + 97 \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{47916} := \frac{35 \times 28 + 0}{(4 + 7)^{9-1 \times 6}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{67914} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (7 \times 9 + 14)} \\
 := \frac{352 + 8 + 0}{679 + 14} \\
 := \frac{3 - 5 + 2 + 80}{67 + 91 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{69174} := \frac{35 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (9 + 174)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{97461} := \frac{3 - 5 + 2 + 80}{(9 + 7 \times 4) \times 6 - 1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35416}{97280} := \frac{3^5 - 4 - 1 \times 6}{9 \times 72 - 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (5 - 4)) \times (8 \times 1)}{(70 - (9 \times 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((5 \times (4 - 8)) + 1)}{(7 - (0 - (9 + 6))) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35469}{81072} := \frac{(3 \times 5) - (4 + (6 - 9))}{(8 + (1 - (-07))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (5 - 4)) \times (8 - 1)}{7 - (0 - (9 + (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - ((4 \times 8) + 1))}{(7 \times (0 \times 9)) + 62}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - (5 - 4)) \times 6) + 9}{8 \times (1 - (0 - (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (5 - 4))^{8-1}}{(70 - (9 \times 6))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (4 \times (8 \times 1)))}{7 + (0 - (9 - 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - (4 - (6 - 9))}{8^{1^{07} \times 2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times ((5 + 4) \times 8)) + 1}{7 \times ((0 \times 9) + 62)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (4 \times (8 - 1)))}{7 - (0 - (9 + (6^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (46 - 9))}{8 - (1 \times (0 - 72))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 4)) - (8 - 1)}{70 + (9 \times (6 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (48 + 1))}{((7 - (-09)) \times 6) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (4 + (6 - 9)))}{8 - (1 + (0 - (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 4)) + (8 + 1)}{((7 \times (09)) + 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 \times (4 - (8 + 1)))}{7 \times ((0 \times 9) + (6 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (4 + (6 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((1 - (-07)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + (4 + 8))) - 1}{(7 - (0 - (9 - 6)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 \times (4 - (8 - 1)))}{(7 \times (0 \times 9)) + (6^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 4) + (6 \times 9))}{(81 - (-07)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + 4)) + (8 \times 1)}{70^{9-6-2}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 + (4 - (8 \times 1)))}{7 - (0 - (9 - (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (4 \times (6 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((1 - (-07))^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + 48)) - 1}{(70 + 9) \times (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 + (4 - (8 - 1)))}{7 + (0 - (9 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (54 + 6)) \times 9}{(8 + 10) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 5) + 481}{(7 - (-09)) \times 62}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (48 + 1))}{70 \times (9 + (6 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 5) \times 469}{8 \times 1072}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^5) - ((4 \times 8) + 1)}{70 \times ((9 - 6) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + (4 - (8 - 1)))}{7 - (0 - (9 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35481}{70962} := \frac{(((3 \times 5) - 4) \times 8) + 1}{70 + (9 \times (6 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^5) - (48 - 1)}{7 \times (0 + ((9 \times 6) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{5+4-8 \times 1}}{7 + (0 - (9 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - (5 - 4)) \times 8) + 1}{7 + (0 - (9 - (6^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^5) + (4 - 81)}{(70 + 96) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{5+4-8+1}}{70 - ((9 \times 6) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 5)^4) \times (8 \times 1)}{(7 - (-09))^{6-2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times 4)) \times (8 \times 1)}{((70 - 9) \times 6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times (4 + 8)) + 1)}{(7 - (-09)) \times (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 54) \times 8) - 1}{70 \times (9 + (6 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (5 + 4)) \times (8 \times 1)}{(7 - (-09)) \times (6 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 4) + 81)}{(70 \times (9 - 6)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 5) \times 4) + 81}{(70 + (9 - 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (5 - 4)) \times (8 \times 1)}{(7 - (-09)) \times (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 48) + 1)}{(70 - 9) \times (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{((35 + 4) \times 8) + 1}{(70 \times 9) - (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 5) \times (4 \times (8 + 1))}{(7 - (-09)) \times (6^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 48) - 1)}{(7 - (0 - (9 + 6)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{((35 + 4) \times 8) - 1}{(70 \times 9) - (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 5) \times (4 - (8 \times 1))}{7 - (0 - ((9 - 6)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5^4) + (8 \times 1))}{((70 \times 9) + 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((5 - 4) \times 81)}{70 + (96 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (4 - (8 \times 1)))}{7 - (0 - (9 + (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (4 - (8 + 1)))}{(7 - ((0 \times 9) - 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (4 - 81))}{(70 + (9 + 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 \times (4 + (8 \times 1)))}{70 + ((9 \times 6) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 \times (48 - 1))}{((70 + 9) \times 6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) - 1))}{7 - (0 - (9 + 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (4 - (8 \times 1)))}{7 - (0 - (9 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (4 - (8 - 1)))}{7 + (0 - (9 - (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (4 + (8 \times 1)))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (4 + (8 + 1)))}{7 \times (0 + ((9 - 6) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (48 + 1))}{((7 \times (09)) - 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (48 - 1))}{(70 - (9 + 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (54 - (8 \times 1))}{((7 - (-09)) \times 6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - (4 - (8 - 1))}{70 + ((9 - 6) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - (4 \times (8 - 1))}{7 \times ((0 \times 96) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (4 \times (8 + 1))}{70 \times (9 \times (6 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (4 \times 81)}{70 \times (9 \times (6^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 + (4 \times (8 + 1))}{70 + (9 \times (6 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 + (48 - 1)}{70 + (96 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{35 + 481}{70 + 962}$$

$$:= \frac{354 - 8 \times 1}{70 \times 9 + 62}$$

$$:= \frac{3548 + 1}{7096 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3548 - 1}{7096 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35489}{61720} := \frac{3 - 5 \times 4 \times (8 - 9)}{6 + 17 \times 2 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 54 + 8 - 9}{(6 + 1 + 7) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 5 \times (4 - 8)) \times 9}{(6 - 1) \times 72 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 4 \times 8 + 9)}{(6 - (1 - 7)) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35490}{72618} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (4 + 9) + 0}{7 \times (2^6 + 1 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35490}{81627} := \frac{(3 - 5) \times (4 - 9) + 0}{8 + 1 \times 6 + 2 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 - 4 + 9) + 0}{(8 - 1) \times 6 + 27}$$

$$:= \frac{35 - 4 + 9 + 0}{8 + 1 \times 6 \times 2 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times 4 - 90}{(8 + 1) \times 6 \times 2 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 - 4) \times 90}{(8 + 1) \times (62 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 4) \times 90}{81 \times (62 + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35496}{87210} := \frac{3^5 + 4 - 9 - 6}{(8 + 7^2) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35604}{91287} := \frac{3 \times 56 + 04}{9 \times (1 - 2 + 8) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35612}{74908} := \frac{(3 + 56 - 1) \times 2}{7 \times 4 \times 9 - 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35621}{80794} := \frac{356 + 2 \times 1}{807 + 9 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35627}{48019} := \frac{3 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 7}{4 + 8 + 019}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 + 6 \times (2 + 7)}{4 + 80 + 1 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{71928} := \frac{3 + 56 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (19 - 2) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{81972} := \frac{3 + (5 + (6 - (4 - 0)))}{8 + (1 + (9 + (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (6 - (4 - 0)))}{8 + (1 \times ((9 \times 7) - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (6 - (4 - 0))}{(8 \times 19) + (7 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (5 - 6)) \times 40}{8 \times (1 \times (9 + (7 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (5 - 6)) \times 40}{8 \times (1 + (9 \times (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (6 + (4 - 0))}{819 - (7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))}{819 + (7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{87219} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 4 + 0}{872 + 1 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{87912} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (6 - 4) + 0}{8 + 7 \times 9 + 1 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 + 6 \times 40}{8 \times 79 - 1 - 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{91872} &:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 6 + 4) + 0}{(9 - (1 - 8) \times 7) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{35 + 640}{(9 + 1) \times 87 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (56 + 4) + 0}{(9 - 1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 5)^{6-4} + 0}{(9 + 1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 + (1 - 0)))}{(9 \times (2 + (8 \times 4))) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{35 \times (7 - (1 - 0))}{(9 - (2 - 84)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + 7)) - (1 - 0)}{9 + (2 + (8 \times (4 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 + (7 \times 10))}{(9^2) + (84 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3^5) + (7 - 10)}{(92 + (8 + 4)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 - 4))}{69 - (0 - 12)} \\ &:= \frac{(35 - 7) \times (8 + 4)}{6 \times (9 \times (012))} \\ &:= \frac{(35 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4}{690 + 12} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4)))}{6 \times (90 \times 12)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35706}{42198} &:= \frac{3 - 5 + 7 + 06}{4 - 2 + 19 - 8} \\ &:= \frac{35 - 7 - 06}{4 + 2 \times (19 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 57 + 06}{4 + 2 + 1 \times 9 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 5 + 7) \times 06}{4 \times 21 + 9 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 5 \times 7 + 06}{4 \times (2 + 19 - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3^5 + 70 + 6}{(42 - 1) \times 9 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(3^5) + (7 \times (1 - 0))}{((9^2) \times 8) - (4 - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35784}{92016} &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 + 7)) - 8) \times 4}{9 \times (2 \times (0 + 16))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (7 - 8))) - 4}{(9 - (2 - (-01))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 84}{9^2 \times 01 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{40896} := \frac{3 + (5 + 7 - 1)^2}{40 + (8 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{94860} &:= \frac{(3 + 5) \times (7 + 1) \times 2}{(9 - 4) \times (8 + 60)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + 5) \times (7 - 1))^2}{(94 + 8) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{96480} := \frac{3 + (5 + 7 - 1)^2}{9 + 6 + 4 \times 80}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 7)) - 84}{9 \times ((2 + (-01)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3^5) - (7 + (8 + 4))}{9 \times (2^{01 \times 6})} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - 7)) \times 84}{9 + (201 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(35 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4}{920 + 16} \\ &:= \frac{(35 + 7) \times (8 + 4)}{(9^2 + 0) \times 16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35710}{92846} &:= \frac{3 + (5 + (7 - 10))}{9 - (2 - (8 + (4 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (5 - (7 + 10))}{9 - (2 - (8 + (4 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (5 + (7 + 10))}{9 + (2 + (8 + 46))} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (57 - 10)}{92 - (8 - 46)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (57 + 10)}{92 + (84 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 \times (2 + ((8 - 4) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9^2) + (8 \times (4 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 10}{9 + (284 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35721}{86940} := \frac{35 + 7^{2+1}}{(8 + 6 + 9) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35724}{96180} := \frac{3 + 5 + 7 + 24}{96 + 1 + 8 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35784}{69012} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (7 - 8))) - 4}{6 + (9 - (0 - 12))} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (5 \times (7 - (8 + 4)))}{6 \times (9 - (0 \times 12))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + (7 + 8))) - 4}{6 \times (9 \times ((01 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - 7)) \times 84}{6 \times (9 \times ((01 + 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 - (5 \times (7 - (8 + 4)))}{9 \times (2 - (0 - (1 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 - 4)))}{9 \times (20 \times (1 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times (7 \times 8)) + 4)}{9 + ((2 - (-01))^6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 \times 4))}{9 \times (20 \times 1^6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 - 4))}{9 \times (2 \times (0 + (1 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{35 - (7 \times (8 - 4))}{9 \times (2 - (0 \times 16))} \\ &:= \frac{35 + (7 \times (8 - 4))}{9 \times (2 - (0 - 16))} \\ &:= \frac{35 + (7 + 84)}{9 \times (20 + 16)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{357+84}{9 \times ((20+1) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times 8 \times 1 + 9)}{(7+6) \times 024}$$

$$:= \frac{358 + (2 - 0)}{967 + (1 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{41769} := \frac{(3 - (5 - (8 - 0))) \times 2}{4 + (1 \times (7 - (6 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 8) + 1 + 9}{(7+6) \times 02 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35840}{97216} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 8 + 40}{9 \times 7^2 - 1 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 + (8 - (-02)))}{((4 + (1^7)) \times 6) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35820}{96714} := \frac{(3 - (5 - 8)) \times 20}{9 \times (6 \times (7 - (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 5 + 8) \times 40}{9 \times (72 + 1) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (8 \times (-02)))}{4 - ((1 + 7) \times (6 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 8)) + 20}{9 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1^4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (8 - 0)))^2}{41 + ((7 - 6)^9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 8)) - 20}{9 \times (6 + ((7 - 1) \times 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35862}{91740} := \frac{3 \times (5 + 8) + 6 - 2}{(9 + 1) \times (7 + 4) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (8 - (0 \times 2)))}{4 - (1 - (7 + (6 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^5) \times (8 \times 20)}{(9 - 6) \times (7 - 1)^4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 5) \times (8 + (-02))}{4 + (1 + ((7 \times 6) + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^5) \times (8 + (2 - 0))}{9^{6-7+1+4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{46872} := \frac{35 \times (9 + 10)}{(4 + 6) \times 87 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(35 - (8 - 0)) \times 2}{((4 + (1 + 7)) \times 6) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(35 \times 8) + 20}{96 + 714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{62874} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{62 \times 8 + 7 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 \times (02)))}{4 \times ((1^7) + 69)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 - (82 - 0))}{9 \times (6 \times (7 + (1 - 4)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{67284} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{6 \times (7 - 2 + 84)}$$

$$:= \frac{358 - (-02)}{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times (6 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (5 + (8 - 20))}{9 + (6 + (7 + (1 + 4)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{68742} := \frac{(3^5 + 9) \times 10}{6 + (8 + 7^4) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{64719} := \frac{(3 - 5 + 80) \times 2}{6 \times 47^{19}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((5 \times 8) - 20)}{9 \times (6 + (7 + (1 + 4)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{78624} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{78 \times (6 - 2 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{96174} := \frac{35 + 8 \times 02}{9 \times (6 + 1) + 74}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 - 0)))}{9 \times (6 + (7 + 14))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{84672} := \frac{35 \times (9 + 10)}{(8 + 4 \times 6) \times 7^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{97461} := \frac{3 + 5 + 8 + 02}{9 - 7 + 46 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 \times (2 - 0)))}{9 \times (6 \times (7 + (1 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 5 + 8)^{02}}{9 + 7 \times 4 + 61}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 \times 20))}{9 \times (6 + 714)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35986}{40721} := \frac{3^5 + 9 + 8 + 6}{40 \times 7 + 21}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (8 - 02)}{9 \times 7 \times 4 - 6 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 + (2 - 0)))}{9 \times ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{358 + 02}{974 + 6 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 + 20))}{9 \times (6 \times (7 + 14))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36018}{57942} := \frac{3 \times (6 - 01) + 8}{5 + 7 + 9 + 4^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{97614} := \frac{35 + 80 + 2}{9 \times 7 \times (6 - 1) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (5 - (8 - 20))}{9 + ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 + 1 + 8)}{5 \times (7 \times 9 + 4) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35819}{76024} := \frac{3 + 5 + 81 + 9}{(7 + 6) \times 02^4}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (8 - (2 - 0))}{9 \times (67 - (1 \times 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36019}{42785} := \frac{3 \times 60 + 1^9}{4 + 27 \times 8 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{35 \times (8 \times (2 - 0))}{9 \times (6 \times (7 \times 1 \times 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36019}{84527} := \frac{3 \times 60 + 19}{8 + 452 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 + 45)}{7 \times (2 + (89 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times 45}{728 + 91}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36025}{41789} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 02 + 5}{4 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6 \times 02) \times 5}{4 + 1 - 7 + 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 025}{(4 + 17 + 8) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 \times 2 + 5)}{(4 + 1) \times (78 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{89712} := \frac{3 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}{8 \times (9 - (7 - 12))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5))}{8 \times (9 + (7 + 12))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5)}{8 \times ((9 \times (7 - 1)) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^6 + 0) - (4 + 5)}{(897 - 1) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 60) + 45}{8 \times ((9 \times (7 + 1)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 + 45)}{8 \times (97 + (1^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 \times 5)))}{897 - (1^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times 45}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{71289} := \frac{3 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}{((7 + (1 + 2)) \times 8) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 \times (4 + 5))}{((7 - 1)^2) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5)}{(7 - (1 + 2)) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^6 + 0) - (4 + 5)}{(7 + 1) \times (2 \times 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 60) + 45}{(7 - (1 \times 2)) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 + 45)}{7 \times ((1^2) \times 89)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 \times 5)))}{(7 + (1^2)) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times 45}{(7 + (1 \times 2)) \times 89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{72891} := \frac{3 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}{(7 + (2 - 8)) \times 91}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5))}{7 \times ((2 \times 8) + (9 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (60 \times (4 \times 5))}{728 \times (9 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (6 \times (-04))) \times 5}{7 + ((2^8) + (9 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{360 \times (4 + 5)}{728 \times (9 \times 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36047}{81925} := \frac{(3 \times (6 - (0 \times 4))) - 7}{8 + (1 - (9 - 25))}$$

$$:= \frac{36 - (0 - (4 - 7))}{(8 + (1 \times (9 - 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (6 + (0 - 47))}{(8 + (1 + (9 + 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 + 7)}{(8 + (1^9)) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (6 - 0)) + 4) \times 7}{((8 \times (1 \times 9)) - 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 + 7)))}{(8 + (1 + (9^2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 60) \times (4 + 7)}{(8 - 1) \times (9 \times 25)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^6 + 0) \times (4 + 7)}{81 \times (9 \times 25)}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times ((04 + 7))}{(81 + 9) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{49572} := \frac{3 + (6 + 1) \times 08}{(4 \times (9 - 5) - 7)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3^6 - 10 \times 8}{(4 + 95) \times (7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{59472} := \frac{3 + 6 + 1 \times 08}{5 \times (9 + 4 - 7) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 \times 1 \times 08}{(5 + 9 + 4 \times 7) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{36 - 10 + 8}{5 \times (9 + 4) - 7 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{36075}{94128} := \frac{360 - 7 \times 5}{(94 + 12) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36075}{98124} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 07 + 5}{(9 + 8 \times 1) \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{360^{7-5}}{(9 + 8) \times 12^4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 \times (07 + 5)}{(9 + 8) \times (1 + 2) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times 075}{9 \times (812 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6 \times 07) \times 5}{9 \times (8^{1 \times 2} + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36084}{71295} := \frac{360 + 8 + 4}{7 \times (12 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36084}{79152} := \frac{360 + 8 + 4}{791 + 5^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 60 - 8 \times 4}{7 + 9 + 1 \times 52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36102}{47589} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 10 - 2}{4 \times (7 + 5 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + 10 - 2}{4 - (7 - 5 - 8) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{95472} := \frac{3 + (6 + 1) \times 08}{(9 + 5) \times (4 + 7) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times (20 + 7)}{5 + 4 + 9 \times 81}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36410}{85729} := \frac{(3 \times 6 + 4) \times 10}{8 + 5 - 7 + 2^9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{98415} := \frac{3 + 6 + 20 \times 7}{9 \times (8 \times (4 + 1) + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36120}{47859} := \frac{(3 + 6 + 1) \times 20}{4^{7-8+5} + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{71928} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 4) \times 5 + 0}{(7 + 1) \times (9 + 28)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36208}{41975} := \frac{3 \times 62 \times 08}{(4 + 19) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 4) \times 50}{((7 + 1) \times 9 + 2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36125}{49708} := \frac{3^{6-1} + 2 + 5}{(4 \times 9 + 7) + 0 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{79218} := \frac{3 \times (6 - 4) \times 50}{7 \times 92 \times 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36210}{94785} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 2) + 10}{9 + 4 \times (7 + 8 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{91728} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 450}{91 \times 7 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36180}{95274} := \frac{3 \times (6 - 1) \times 8 + 0}{(9 + 5 \times 2 \times 7) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36218}{49750} := \frac{3^6 - 2 + 1^8}{(4 + 9 + 7) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36480}{71592} := \frac{(3 - 6 + 4) \times 80}{71 + 5 + 9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36190}{75482} := \frac{3 \times (6 - 1) + 90}{75 + (4 + 8)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{36 - 1^{90}}{7 \times (5 + 4) + 8 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36240}{75198} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2 + 4 + 0}{7 + 5 - 1 + 9 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36498}{50127} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 4 \times 9 - 8}{(50 + 12) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 6)^2 - 4 + 0}{(75 - 1 + 9) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36498}{70152} := \frac{3 + 6 + 4 \times (9 + 8)}{(70 - 1 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36192}{47850} := \frac{3 \times (61 + 9) - 2}{(47 + 8) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36192}{57408} := \frac{3 - (6 - 19) \times 2}{5 - 7 + 40 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{36 - 1 + 9^2}{(-5 + 7 \times 4) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36270}{45198} := \frac{3 - 6 - 2 + 70}{4 + 5 + 1 \times 9 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3^6 - 2 \times 7 + 0}{(4 + 5) \times (1 + 98)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36504}{91728} := \frac{3 \times 65 \times 04}{(9 + 1) \times 7 \times 28}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36504}{92781} := \frac{3 + 65 + 04}{(9 + 2 \times 7) \times 8 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times 19 + 2)}{(-5 + 74) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36270}{59148} := \frac{3 - 6 - 2 + 70}{59 - 1 + 48}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36519}{87024} := \frac{3 - 6 + 5 \times (1 + 9)}{8 \times 7 \times (-02 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{49815} := \frac{3 + 6 + 20 \times 7}{(49 - 8 \times 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 62) \times 7 + 0}{9 \times (5^{4-1} + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times 5 - 1 + 9}{8 \times 7 \times 02 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{54981} := \frac{3 \times 6^2 + 0 \times 7}{5 \times 49 - 81}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 + 207}{(5 + 4 \times 9) \times 8 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36278}{50149} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times (2 + 7 + 8)}{(50 + 1 - 4) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36540}{72819} := \frac{36 \times 5 - 40}{7 + 281 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{6 \times 2 - 07}}{(5 + 4 \times 9) \times (8 + 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36540}{91872} := \frac{36 - 5 + 4 + 0}{9 - 1 + 8 + 72}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times 5 - 40}{9 - (1 - 8) \times 7^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36549}{78120} := \frac{36 \times 5 - 49}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36570}{49128} := \frac{3 \times 65 + 70}{4 \times (9^{1 \times 2} + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36570}{94128} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 5 + 70}{(9 \times 4 + 1^2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36708}{41952} := \frac{3 \times (6 - (7 + (-08)))}{4 \times (1 \times (9 - (5 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + (7 + (-08))}{4 \times ((1 + (9 - 5)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 + (7 - (-08)))}{((4 + (1 + 9)) \times 5) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (67 - (0 \times 8))}{4 \times (1 + (9 + (5 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + (70 - 8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 \times (5 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 6) \times (7 \times (-08))}{4 - ((1 - 95) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{4 \times (((1^9) + 5^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^6) + (70 - 8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 \times (5^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^6) \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 \times (1 \times 9))^{5-2}}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (670 - 8)}{4 \times (1 \times (95 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 - (1 - (9 \times 5)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 \times ((1^9) + 5))^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36712}{45890} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (7 \times 1))) \times 2}{4 + (5 - (8 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 + (7 + 12))}{4 + ((5 \times 8) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 - (7 + 1)) \times 2}{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (1 + 2)))}{(4 + (5 - 8)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (67 - 1)) + 2}{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2))}{(45 \times 8) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 712}{(4 + 5) \times 890}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times (7 + (1 + 2))}{(45 \times 8) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{36 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2))}{(4 - (5 - 8)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + 712}{45 + 890}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 6) \times (7 + 1))^2}{(4 + 5) \times (8 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((7 + 1)^2))}{4 \times (5 \times (8 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{48195} := \frac{(3 + 6 + 7) \times 2 + 0}{4 - 8 + 1 + 9 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 6 + 7) \times 20}{(4 + 8 + 1 \times 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times 7 + 2 + 0}{(4 + 8 \times 1) \times (9 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6 + 7) \times 20}{(4 + 8 \times (1 + 9)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{49815} := \frac{36 \times 7 + 20}{4 + (9 \times 8 + 1) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{51948} := \frac{3^6 - 7^2 + 0}{5 \times 194 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{84915} := \frac{(3 - 6 + 7)^2 + 0}{(8 - 4) \times (9 - 1) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6 + 7) \times 2 + 0}{84 - 9 - 1^5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 6 + 7) \times 20}{((8 - 4) \times 9 + 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times 7 + 2 + 0}{8 \times (4 \times (9 - 1) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + 7 \times 20}{8 \times 49 + 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{91584} := \frac{36 + 7^2 + 0}{(9 \times 1 \times 5 + 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{91854} := \frac{3^6 - 7^2 + 0}{9 \times (185 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{98415} := \frac{36 \times 7 + 20}{9^{8-4-1^5}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36728}{45910} := \frac{((3 - (6 - 7))^2) \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times (9 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 6) - (7 + 2)) \times 8}{4 - (5 - (91 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 6)^{7+2}) \times 8}{((4 + 5)^9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - ((6 - 7) \times 2)) \times 8}{4 + ((5 \times 9) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (6 - (7 \times 2))) \times 8}{(4 \times 5) + (9 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (6 - (7^2))) \times 8}{459 + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (6 - (7 + 2))) \times 8}{4 \times (5 + (9 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (6 \times 7)) + (2 + 8)}{(4 \times (5 \times 9)) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + ((6 + 7) \times 2)) \times 8}{((4 \times 5) + 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 + (7 - 2))) \times 8}{4 \times ((5 \times 9) - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 + 7)) \times (2 + 8)}{4 \times (5 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 + 7)) \times 28}{4 \times ((5 + 9) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 + 72)) \times 8}{(4 + 5) \times (9 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 728}{(4 + 5) \times 910}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 - (7 \times 2)) \times 8}{4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 \times (7 + 2)) + 8}{(45 \times 9) + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 \times (7 + 2)) - 8}{(45 \times 9) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 \times (7 - 2)) + 8}{(4 \times 59) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 - 7) \times 28}{(4^5) - (9 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (67 - (2^8))}{4 \times (59 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((6 - (7 - 2)) \times 8)}{(4 \times 5) + (9 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((6 + (7 + 2)) \times 8)}{45 \times (9 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 - (7 \times (2 - 8)))}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 2) - 8))}{45 + (9 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 \times (72 + 8))}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 - (7 + (2 - 8)))}{4 + (5 - (9 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 + (7 + 28))}{(4 \times (5 + 9)) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (67 + (2 + 8))}{4 + (5 + (91 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (67 + (2 - 8))}{(4 - (5 - 9)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + 728}{45 + 910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36729}{41580} := \frac{3 + 6 + 7 \times 29}{(4 - 1^5) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36729}{48510} := \frac{(3 + 6 + 7)^2 + 9}{4 \times 85 + 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36740}{89512} := \frac{3 + (6 + 7) \times 4 + 0}{(8 \times 9 - 5 \times 1) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 6 - 7) \times 40}{8 \times (9 + 5^{1+2})}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36751}{82940} := \frac{36 \times 7 + 5 \times 1}{8^2 \times 9 + 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36780}{51492} := \frac{((3 \times 6) - 7) \times 80}{((5 \times 1 \times 4) - 9) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 6) \times 7) - (8 - 0)}{5 + (1 \times (4 \times (9 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (6 - 7)) + (8 - 0)}{5 - (1 + (4 - (9 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 6) + (7 + 80)}{51 + (4 + 92)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (6 + 7)) \times 80}{((5 - 1)^4) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 67) \times (8 - 0)}{(5 + (14 + 9))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (6 - (78 - 0))}{5 + ((1 + 49) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (6 + (7 - 80))}{5 + (1^4 + 92)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 + (7 - (8 - 0)))}{5 + (1 + (4 + (9 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((6 \times 7) + 80)}{5 + (1 + ((4 + 9)^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 - (7 - (8 - 0)))}{5 - (1 + ((4 - 9) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 \times (7 + 80))}{5 \times (149 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (6 + (7 \times (8 - 0)))}{5 + (1 + (4 + (9^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{36 + (7 - (8 - 0))}{5 + (1 \times (4 \times (9 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{367 + (8 - 0)}{514 + (9 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{51408} := \frac{3 + (6 + 7) \times (9 + 2)}{51 \times 4 + 0 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{80154} := \frac{3 - 67 + 92}{8 - 01 + 54}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{85410} := \frac{3 - 67 + 92}{(8 + 5) \times (4 + 1) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36801}{59247} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8 - 01}{5 \times (9 + 2) \times 4 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36801}{75429} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8 - 01}{7 \times 5 \times 4 \times 2 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36851}{40279} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times 8 - 5 \times 1)}{4 + 02^7 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36897}{51204} := \frac{(3 + 6 \times 8 - 9) \times 7}{51 \times 2 \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 6 \times 8 - 9 + 7}{(5 + 12) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (6 + 8)^{9-7}}{51 \times 2^{04}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 6 \times (8 + 9)) \times 7}{5 \times 1 \times 204}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36912}{80745} := \frac{3+6+9-1 \times 2}{8+07+4 \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(3-6+91) \times 2}{(80-7+4) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (69+1) - 2}{(80+7+4) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(3+6 \times 9-1) \times 2}{80 \times (7-4)+5} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 6 \times (9-1)^2}{8 \times 07 \times 45} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (6+9+1))^2}{80 \times 7 \times (4+5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{3+(6 \times (9+(1^8)))}{5 \times ((2 \times 7)+(4-0))} \\ & := \frac{36-(9-(1^8))}{5+(2-(7-40))} \\ & := \frac{369+(1+8)}{5 \times (27 \times (4-0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{((3+6) \times 9)+(7-4)}{((5+8) \times 10)+2} \\ & := \frac{3+((6^9-7)-4)}{5 \times (8+(1-(-02)))} \\ & := \frac{36+(9 \times (7-4))}{5-(8-102)} \\ & := \frac{3+((6-(9-7))^4)}{(5 \times (81-0))+2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36918}{52740} := \frac{(3-(6-(9+1))) \times 8}{52+(7 \times (4-0))} \\ & := \frac{(3-(6+9)) \times (1-8)}{((5 \times 2)-7) \times 40} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (69-1))-8}{5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (4-0)))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times 69)-18}{5 \times ((2 \times 7)+40)} \\ & := \frac{(36 \times (9-1))-8}{(5-(2-7)) \times 40} \\ & := \frac{(3-69) \times (1-8)}{5 \times ((2^7)+(4-0))} \\ & := \frac{3-((6-(9+1)) \times 8)}{5-(2-(7+40))} \\ & := \frac{3-(6-((9+1) \times 8))}{5 \times (2 \times (7+(4-0)))} \\ & := \frac{3-(6-(9+(1^8)))}{5+(2+(7-(4-0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (6+(9-(1 \times 8)))}{5 \times (2 \times (7-(4-0)))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (6+(9 \times 18))}{((5^2)-7) \times 40} \\ & := \frac{3+(6 \times (9+(1 \times 8)))}{5 \times (2+(7 \times (4-0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36921}{54870} := \frac{36 \times (9+2)+1}{5 \times (48+70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36971}{84025} := \frac{3+6+9-7 \times 1}{8 \times 4-02-5} \\ & := \frac{3697-1}{840 \times 2 \times 5} \\ & := \frac{(3-6) \times 9+71}{(8-4) \times 025} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (6+9+7 \times 1)}{(8 \times 4-02) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{36+97-1}{(8+4) \times 025} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36972}{50481} := \frac{3+6 \times 9-7+2}{(5+04) \times 8-1} \\ & := \frac{369-7+2}{504-8+1} \\ & \frac{36972}{51480} := \frac{3^{6-9+7}-2}{5 \times (14+8)+0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36974}{58102} := \frac{3+(6+(9-(7+4)))}{5+(8+(1 \times (-02)))} \\ & := \frac{3+(6+(9+(7-4)))}{5+(8+(10 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (6+((9-7) \times 4))}{58+(10-2)} \\ & := \frac{3-(6-((9 \times 7)-4))}{(5 \times (8+10))-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36975}{41820} := \frac{3+6 \times 97-5}{41 \times 8 \times 2+0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{36981}{47250} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times 98-1)}{(47-2) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37051}{62489} := \frac{3+70-5-1}{6 \times 2^4+8+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37054}{86912} := \frac{3 \times (70-5)-4}{8 \times (6 \times 9 \times 1+2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37056}{91482} := \frac{3+7 \times 5-6}{9 \times (1^4+8)-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37062}{58149} := \frac{3-7+062}{5+81-4+9} \\ & := \frac{370+6^2}{(5+8 \times 1) \times 49} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37084}{69215} := \frac{(3+70) \times (8-4)}{(6 \times 9 \times 2+1) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37085}{96421} &:= \frac{3 + (7 + ((0 \times 8) - 5))}{9 + (6 - (4 - (2 \times 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (7 - ((0 \times 8) - 5))}{9 + (6 \times (4 + (2 - 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (7 + (-08))) \times 5}{9 + (64 - 21)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (7 - (0 - (8 - 5)))}{(9^{6-4}) - (2 + 1)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 - (-08))) - 5}{9 + ((6 \times (4^2)) - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (7 - 0)) \times 8) - 5}{(9 \times (6 \times 4)) - 21} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 - (-08))) \times 5}{9 \times ((6 \times 4) + (2 \times 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 70) - 85}{(9 \times (6^{4-2})) + 1} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((7 - (-08)) \times 5)}{9 \times (64 + (2 - 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 70) + (8 \times 5)}{9 + (642 - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (7 \times (-08))) \times 5}{(96 \times (4 \times 2)) - 1} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 - 0))^{8-5}}{9 + (((6^4) \times 2) - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37092}{56481} &:= \frac{37 + 09 - 2}{56 + 4 + 8 - 1} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 7 \times 09) \times 2}{5^{6-4} \times 8 + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{52164} := \frac{3 \times (70 + 9) - 8}{(52 + 1) \times 6 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{64152} := \frac{3 \times (70 + 9) - 8}{6 \times (41 + 5^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{65124} := \frac{3 \times (70 + 9) - 8}{6 \times (51 + 2^4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37125}{40986} &:= \frac{(37 - 12) \times 5}{(40 - 9 - 8) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 + 2)^5)}{(40 + 98) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 7 - 1)^2 \times 5}{(40 \times 9 + 8) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37128}{50694} := \frac{3 + 7 \times (1 - 2 + 8)}{5 \times (06 + 9) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37148}{69025} := \frac{37 \times 1^4 \times 8}{6 \times 90 + 2 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37149}{85260} := \frac{3 + 71 - 4 - 9}{8 \times 5^2 - 60}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37150}{69842} &:= \frac{3 + 7 + 15 + 0}{6 - 9 + 8 + 42} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 7 \times 1) \times 5 + 0}{(6 + 9 + 8 \times 4) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1 \times 50}{6 + 984 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{40896} := \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 + 5)^2)}{40 + (8 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{80496} := \frac{3 + (7 + (1 + (5^2)))}{(8 + (0 - (4 - 9))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{80 - (4 - (9 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - (1 \times 52))}{8 - ((0 \times 4) - 96)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (15 - 2))}{80 - (4 - (9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{371 + (5 + 2)}{804 + (9 + 6)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 \times ((71 - 5) \times 2)}{804 + (9 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (1^5))^2)}{(80 \times 4) + 96} \\ &:= \frac{37 \times ((1 + 5)^2)}{(80 \times (4 \times 9)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (71 + (5^2))}{8 \times (((04 + 9) \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{96480} := \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 + 5)^2)}{9 + 6 + 4 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37185}{46029} := \frac{37 \times 1^8 \times 5}{4 \times 60 - 2 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{37 \times 18 \times 5}{(460 - 2) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37185}{92460} := \frac{37 \times 1 \times (8 - 5)}{9 \times 24 + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (71 + 8 \times 5)}{9 \times 2 \times 46 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (71 + 8 - 5)}{92 + 460}$$

$$:= \frac{37 \times 18 \times 5}{9 \times 2 \times 460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{58194} := \frac{37 + 2 + 0 \times 6}{58 - 1^9 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{59148} := \frac{37 + 2 - 0 \times 6}{5 + 9 + 1 \times 48}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 7^2) \times 06}{(59 - 1 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{91584} := \frac{(3 \times 7) - (2 - (-06))}{(9 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 7) \times (2 - 0)) + 6}{9 + (1 + (58 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7^{2-0 \times 6})}{(9 + (15 + 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (20 \times 6))}{(9 + (1^5)) \times (8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (72 - (-06))}{((9 + 1) \times 58) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{37 + (2 - (0 \times 6))}{(9 + 15) \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (7^2 + 0)) \times 6}{(9 + 15) \times (8 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37240}{61985} := \frac{(3 - 7) \times (2 - 40)}{6 + 19 \times (8 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37245}{91680} := \frac{3 + (7 + (2 - (4 - 5)))}{(9 + (1 - 6)) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - ((2 + 4) \times 5))}{(9 \times 16) - 80}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 + (2 - 45))}{9 + (1 + (6 + 80))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times ((7 - 2) \times 4)) + 5}{(9 - (1 + 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 7)^2) - (4 + 5)}{(9 \times 16) + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (24 \times 5))}{(9 + (1 - 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (2 + 4)) \times 5)}{(9 + 1) \times (6 \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(((3 + 7)^2) + 4) \times 5}{(9 + (1 + 6)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (7^2)) \times (4 + 5)}{9 \times (16 \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (72 - (4 \times 5))}{(9 - 1) \times (6 \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 \times (2^4)) + 5)}{9 \times (16 + 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 \times (2 - (4 + 5)))}{(9 + (1 + 6)) \times (8 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(37 + 2) \times 45}{9 \times (1 \times (6 \times 80))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37250}{61984} := \frac{3 + 72 + 50}{6 + 198 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 7) \times 25 + 0}{(6 + 1 \times 98) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 72) \times 5 + 0}{(61 - 9) \times (8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 7) \times 2 \times 50}{(61 - 9) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{49815} := \frac{3 \times 72 + 60}{4 + (9 \times 8 + 1) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{94185} := \frac{3 + 7 + 26 + 0}{9 - 4 + 1 + 85}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 7 + 2 + 60}{(9 + 4 + 1) \times (8 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 72 \times 60}{(9^4 - 1 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{98415} := \frac{3 \times 72 + 60}{9^{8-4-1^5}}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 7 + 2) \times 60}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37268}{94501} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (2 - 6 + 8)}{9 + 4 \times (50 + 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37294}{61085} := \frac{3 - 7 + 294}{6 \times 10 \times 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{41580} := \frac{37 \times (2 \times 9 - 6)}{415 + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{51408} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 2 \times (9 + 6))}{5 + 140 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{37 + 296}{51 + 408}$$

$$:= \frac{37 \times (2 \times 9 - 6)}{51 \times (4 + 08)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 7^2 + 96}{51 \times 4 + 0 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 7^2 - 9 - 6}{51 + 4 \times 0 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{51840} := \frac{37 \times (29 + 6)}{5 \times (1 + 8) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{37 \times (2 + 96)}{(5 + 1) \times 840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37410}{85269} := \frac{3 + 7 \times 41 + 0}{85 + 2^6 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37468}{91205} := \frac{3 - 7 + (4 + 6) \times 8}{9 \times 1 \times 20 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (74 - 6 + 8)}{(91 + 20) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37485}{92610} := \frac{(3 \times 7 - 4) \times (8 - 5)}{9 \times 2 \times (6 + 1) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 7 + 4 + 85}{(9 + 2 \times 6) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 7 + 4 + 8 - 5}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 1 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 7 + 4 \times 8 \times 5}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37512}{46890} := \frac{((3 \times 7) + 51) \times 2}{(4 + (6 - 8)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{((3^{7-5}) - 1)^2}{4 - (6 + (8 - 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times ((7 \times 5) - 1)) + 2}{4 + ((6 + 8) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (7 + (5 \times 1)))^2}{(4 + (6 + 8)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (7 \times 51)) \times 2}{4 + (6 + 890)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - (5 \times 12))}{4 - (6 - (8 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 \times (5 - 12))}{(4 \times (6 + 8)) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (((7 \times 5) + 1)^2)}{(46 + 8) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (5 \times 1))^2)}{(4 - (6 - 8)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + 5) \times (1 + 2))}{(4 + 68) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (5 \times (1^2)))}{46 + (8 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 - (5 - (1 + 2)))}{4 - (6 \times (8 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 \times (5 \times (1 + 2)))}{46 + (89 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (5 - (1 + 2)))}{4 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (5 \times (1 \times 2)))}{(4 \times 6) - (8 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (5 + (1^2)))}{4 \times (6 + (8 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{49062} := \frac{3 + (7 - (5 - (1 \times 8)))}{4 + (9 - (0 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 7) + (5 \times (1^8))}{4 + ((9 - (-06)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (5 + (1^8)))}{49 - ((0 \times 6) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 7) \times (5 - 18)}{4 \times (9 - (0 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (75 \times (1^8))}{4 + (90 + (6 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (7 \times 5)) - 1) \times 8}{(4 + (90 \times 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (5 + 1)) \times 8)}{4 \times (90 + (6 \times 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{62049} := \frac{(3 \times 7 + 5) \times 18}{(6 + 20 \times 4) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{90246} := \frac{3 \times (75 - 1^8)}{90 \times (2 + 4) - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37521}{64809} := \frac{3 - 7 + 5 \times (2 + 1)}{6 - 4 + 8 + 09}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 7 + 5 + 21}{6 + 4 \times (8 - 0 \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + 5 \times (2 + 1))}{6 + (4 + 8) \times 09}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37528}{46910} := \frac{(((3 \times 7) - 5)^2) + 8}{((4 \times 6) + 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (7 - 5)) + 2) \times 8}{(4 + 6) \times (9 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + (5^2)) \times 8}{46 \times (9 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + 5) \times 28}{(4 + 6) \times (91 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3^7) - (5 - 2)) \times 8}{4 \times (6 \times 910)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 7)^{5+2}) \times 8}{(4 + 6)^{9-1+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{((37 + 5) \times 2) + 8}{(4 \times 6) + (91 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (7 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8}{4 \times (6 + (9 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times ((7 + 5)^2)) + 8}{4 + (6 \times (91 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (7 - (5 + 2))) + 8}{4 - (6 \times (9 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (7 - (5 - 2))) - 8}{(4 \times 6) - (9 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3^7) + (5 + (2 \times 8))}{4 \times (69 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (7 \times (5 \times 2))) \times 8}{(4 + 69) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (7 \times (5 - 2))) \times 8}{4 \times (6 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(37 + (5 \times 2)) \times 8}{469 + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - ((7 \times 5) - (2^8))}{4 \times (69 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - ((5 + 2) \times 8))}{46 + (9 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - ((5 - 2) \times 8))}{(4 \times 6) - (9 - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (7 - (52 + 8))}{(4 - (6 - 9)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 - (5 - (2 + 8)))}{46 + (9 - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + ((5^2) - 8))}{(4 + 6) \times (9 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (5 + 28))}{((4 \times 6) - 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((7 \times (5 + 2)) - 8)}{46 + (9 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((7 \times (5 - 2)) - 8)}{4 \times (6 + (9 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 - (5 \times (2 - 8)))}{(4 \times (6 + 9)) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 \times (5 - (2 - 8)))}{4 \times (6 + (9 + 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + ((5 \times 2) - 8))}{(4 \times 6) - (9 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37582}{96140} := \frac{3 + (7 + 5 + 8) \times 2}{9 + 61 + 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37584}{60291} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5 + 8 - 4)}{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + 5) \times (8 + 4)}{602 + 91}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37584}{60912} := \frac{(3 + 7 + 5) \times 8 - 4}{6 + 091 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 7 \times (5 - 8) \times 4}{60 + 9^{1 \times 2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{37590}{46182} := \frac{3 \times 7 + 5 + 9 + 0}{46 - 1^8 - 2} \\ & := \frac{3 + 7 + 5 + 90}{4 + 61 + 8^2} \\ & := \frac{(3 - 7) \times 5 + 90}{(4 + 6 + 1) \times 8 - 2} \\ & \frac{37590}{81624} := \frac{3 \times 7 + 5 + 9 + 0}{8 \times (1 + 6 + 2) + 4} \\ & := \frac{3 + 7 + 5 + 90}{(8 + (1 + 6)^2) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{(3 - 7) \times 5 + 90}{8 \times (1 - 6 + 24)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 5 \times 9 + 0}{8 \times 16^2 + 4} \\ & \frac{37604}{51982} := \frac{3 + 7 + 6 \times 04}{5 \times (1^9 + 8) + 2} \\ & \frac{37620}{41895} := \frac{3 - 7 + 620}{(41 + 8) \times (9 + 5)} \\ & := \frac{37 \times 6 - 2 + 0}{((4 + 1) \times 8 + 9) \times 5} \\ & \frac{37620}{51984} := \frac{37 \times 6 - 2 + 0}{(5 - 1 + 9 \times 8) \times 4} \\ & \frac{37620}{91485} := \frac{376 + 20}{9 \times (14 \times 8 - 5)} \\ & \frac{37620}{95418} := \frac{37 \times 6 - 2 + 0}{9 \times (54 + 1 \times 8)} \\ & \frac{37650}{48192} := \frac{3 + ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 0))}{4 \times (8 + (1 + (9 - 2)))} \\ & := \frac{3 + (7 + (65 - 0))}{4 \times (8 \times ((1^9) + 2))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (7 - 6)) \times 50}{4 \times ((8 - (1 - 9)) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 7) \times (65 - 0)}{4 + ((8 + 1) \times 92)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (7 - 6)) \times 50}{4 \times (8 \times (1 + (9 - 2)))} \\ & := \frac{((3 \times 7) - 6) \times 50}{48 \times ((1 + 9) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (7 + 6)) \times 50}{4^{8-1^9-2}} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 - 0))}{4 \times (8 \times (1 + (9 + 2)))} \\ & := \frac{((3 \times 7) + 6) \times 50}{(4 + 8)^{1^9+2}} \\ & \frac{37658}{49210} := \frac{3 + 76 \times (5 + 8)}{(4 \times 9)^2 - 1 + 0} \\ & \frac{37680}{95142} := \frac{(3 + 7 \times 6) \times 8 + 0}{951 - 42} \\ & \frac{37692}{51840} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 6) \times 9 - 2}{(5 - 1 + 8) \times 40} \\ & \frac{37694}{85012} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 6 - 9 - 4}{8 + (50 - 1) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{(3 - 7 + 6) \times 94}{8 \times (50 + 1 + 2)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + 7 - 6) \times 94}{850 - 1 \times 2} \\ & \frac{37812}{50964} := \frac{37 - (8 - 1) \times 2}{50 - 9 - 6 - 4} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (7 + 8 + 1) - 2}{50 + (9 - 6) \times 4} \\ & \frac{37819}{60254} := \frac{37 + (8 + 1) \times 9}{6 \times 02^5 - 4} \\ & \frac{37824}{91605} := \frac{3 - 7 + 8^2 + 4}{(91 - 60) \times 5} \\ & \frac{37845}{60291} := \frac{(3 + 7 \times (8 + 4)) \times 5}{602 + 91} \\ & \frac{37890}{52416} := \frac{3^7 + 8 - 90}{(5 + 2) \times 416} \\ & \frac{37890}{56142} := \frac{3^7 + 8 - 90}{5^{6-1} - 4 - 2} \\ & \frac{37905}{62814} := \frac{3 \times 7 + 9 + 05}{6 \times (2 + 8 - 1) + 4} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 9 \times 05}{6 \times (2^8 + 1 + 4)} \\ & := \frac{3 + 7 + 90 + 5}{6 \times (28 + 1^4)} \\ & \frac{37908}{51246} := \frac{37 + 9 + 08}{51 - 2 + 4 \times 6} \\ & \frac{37908}{61425} := \frac{3 + 7 + 90 + 8}{(6 + 1^4) \times 25} \\ & \frac{37908}{64152} := \frac{3 - 7 + 9 + 08}{6 + 4 \times (1 + 5 - 2)} \\ & := \frac{3 - 7 + 90 - 8}{(6 + 4 \times 15) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{(-3 + 7 + 9) \times 08}{6 \times 4 + 152} \\ & \frac{37908}{65124} := \frac{3 - 7 + 90 - 8}{65 \times 1 \times 2 + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37914}{86052} := \frac{((3+7) \times 9 - 1) \times 4}{860 - 52}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38014}{56792} := \frac{3 + 80^{14}}{(5 - 6 + 7 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 - (-09))) \times 2}{4 + ((7 \times 6) - (1 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (80 + 9)) \times 2}{(4 + (7 \times (6 \times 1))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{48510} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 9^2) - 6}{4 \times 85 - 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38016}{45792} := \frac{38 + 01 \times 6}{4 + (5 - 7 + 9)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 + (0 - (9^2)))}{4 + (76 + 15)}$$

$$:= \frac{379 + 2 + 6}{485 + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 80 - 1 + 6}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 9) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - (0 \times 92))}{(4 + (7 - (6 - 1))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{51084} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (9 + 2 \times 6)}{510 + 84}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 016}{4 \times (5 \times 7 + 9 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2))}{4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 15)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{51408} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (92 - 6)}{51 \times (40 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38016}{47952} := \frac{3 + 80 - 1 + 6}{(4 \times 7 + 9) \times (5 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 \times 2)))}{(47 + 61) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{54180} := \frac{(3 - (7 - (9 + 2))) \times 6}{5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 016}{4 - 7 + 9 \times 5^2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 + 2)))}{(4 + 7) \times (6 \times (1 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (7 + (9 - (2 \times 6)))}{5 + (4 + (1^8 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 - 2)))}{(47 - (6 - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (79 - 26)}{5 - (4 + (1 - 80))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38049}{65721} := \frac{3 + 8 + 0 \times 49}{6 + 5 + 7 + 2 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8^{0 \times 9 + 2})}{4 \times ((7 + (6 - 1)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 7) + ((9 - 2) \times 6)}{5 + (4 + (1 + 80))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 + 0 \times 4 + 9}{65 - 7 - 2 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (0 - (9^2)))}{((4 \times 7) - (6 - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (79 - (2 \times 6))}{(5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - 8 + 049}{6 - 5 \times (7 - 21)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (0 - (9 - 2)))}{4 + (7 - (6 \times (1^5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (9 + (2 \times 6)))}{5 \times ((4 - 1) \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{380 + 49}{6 + 5 \times 7 \times 21}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (80 - (9 + 2))}{(4 + (7 + (6 + 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (7 + 9)) + (2^6)}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 04 \times 9)}{6 \times (5 \times 7 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (80 + (9^2))}{(47 - (6 \times 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (9 + 26))}{5 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 04 \times 9}{6 \times 57 \times 2 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{38 - (0 - (9 \times 2))}{((4 + 7) \times 6) - (1 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (9 - 2)) \times 6)}{5 \times (4 \times (18 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38056}{97412} := \frac{3 \times 80 \times 5 + 6}{9 \times 7^{4-1^2}}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + ((0 \times 9) - 2)}{(4 - (7 - 6)) \times 15}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2 + 6))}{(5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + (0 - (9 \times 2))}{(4 + (7 - (6 \times 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{380 - 92}{(4 + (7 + 61)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37962}{40185} := \frac{37 \times (9 - 6) \times 2}{(40 - 1 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38092}{47615} := \frac{(3 - (8 + (-09))) \times 2}{4 + (7 - (6 - (1 \times 5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37962}{81054} := \frac{3 + 7 - 9 + 6^2}{8 \times 10 - 5 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (8 + (-09)))^2}{4 + (7 - (6 - 15))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38097}{54621} := \frac{(3 \times 80 + 9) \times 7}{(5 \times (4 + 6))^2 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 - 0)) + 92}{(4 \times (7 \times (6 - 1))) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38097}{61254} := \frac{3 \times (80 - 9 \times 7)}{61 + 25 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38125}{46970} := \frac{((3-8) \times (1-2))^5}{(46+9) \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38145}{76290} := \frac{((3 \times 8) + (1 + 4)) \times 5}{(7-6) \times 290}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (8 - 14)) \times 5}{((7-6)^2) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times ((8-1) \times 4)) + 5}{((7+6)^2) + (9-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 - (1^4))) + 5}{7 + ((6^2) + (9-0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (1^4))) + 5}{76 - (2 \times (9-0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8+1)) + (4 \times 5)}{76 + (2 \times (9-0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 81) + (4+5)}{7 \times ((6+2) \times (9-0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 81) - 45}{((7 \times 6) + 2) \times (9-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 45}{(7 + (6-2)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 + (1+4))) \times 5}{((7+6)^2) - (9-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8-1)) \times (4+5)}{(7-6) \times (2 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+8) \times (1+(4 \times 5))}{7 \times (6 \times (2+(9-0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+8) \times (1-(4-5))}{(76 \times 2) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+81) \times 45}{7 \times (6 \times (2 \times 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{(38-1) \times (4+5)}{(76-2) \times (9-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(381-4) \times 5}{(7+6) \times 290}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (1 \times (4 \times 5)))}{7 - (6 - (29 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (1 \times (4 + 5)))}{7 - (6 + (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (1 + (4 + 5)))}{7 + ((6 \times 2) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (14 \times 5))}{(7 \times 6) - (2 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 \times (1 + (4 - 5)))}{7 + (6 + (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 + (1 - (4 \times 5)))}{7 + ((6 \times 2) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 + (1 - 45))}{7 + (62 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times 1 \times 4) + 5)}{(7 \times 6) + (2 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times 14) + 5)}{(76 + 2) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 5)}{((7 \times 6) - 2) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 + 1^4) \times 5)}{(7 - (6 - 2)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - (1^4 + 5))}{7 - (6 - (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 - (1 - (4 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (6^2)) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (1 - (4 - 5)))}{7 + (62 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 \times 5)))}{7 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 - 5)))}{7 + (6 + (29 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (1 + (4 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (6 \times 2)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (81 - (4 \times 5))}{76 + 290}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (81 + 45)}{7 \times (6 \times (2 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((8 - (1 - 4)) \times 5)}{((7 + 6) \times 2) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((8 - 1) \times 45)}{7 + (629 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 - (4 - 5)))}{(7 - 6) \times (2 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 \times (4 + 5)))}{7 - ((6 \times 2) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 \times (4 - 5)))}{7 + (6 + (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 + (4 + 5)))}{7 + (6 - (2 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 \times (1 + (4 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (6^2)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 \times (1 - (4 - 5)))}{(7 \times 6) + (2 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1^4 + 5))}{7 + ((6^2) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1 \times (4 \times 5)))}{(76 \times 2) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1 \times (4 - 5)))}{7 + (6 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1 + (4^5)))}{7 \times (6 + 290)}$$

$$:= \frac{38 - (1 - (4 + 5))}{(7 - 6) \times (2 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{38 - (1 - 45)}{76 - (2 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + (1 + (4 \times 5))}{(7 \times (6 - 2)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{381 \times (4 + 5)}{762 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{381 + 45}{762 + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{381 - 45}{762 - 90}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38152}{47690} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times 1)) + 52}{4 + (7 - (6 - 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (1^5)))^2}{(4 + 76) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 + 5))) + 2}{4 + ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 + 5))) - 2}{47 - (6 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 \times 5))) \times 2}{4 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 + 15)) \times 2}{4 + (7 + (6 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (1 \times (5^2)))}{4 - (7 \times (6 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times (1 \times 5)) \times 2)}{(4^7) \times (6 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times ((1 + 5) \times 2))}{4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + ((1 + 5) \times 2))}{((4 + 7) \times 6) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + ((1 + 5)^2))}{(4 + 7) \times (6 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{4 + ((7 - 6)^9 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1 \times (5^2)))}{(4 + (7 - 6)) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (1 + 52))}{4 + (7 + (69 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 + (15^2))}{(4 \times 76) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (81 + 52)}{4 + (76 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{381 + (5 + 2)}{476 + (9 - 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38157}{92046} := \frac{(3 + 81 - 5) \times 7}{(9 + 20) \times 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38160}{45792} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times 1)) + (6 - 0)}{4 \times (5 - (7 - (9 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 - 1)) - (6 - 0)}{4 + ((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 8) + (1 + 60)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 8) + (16 - 0)}{4 - (5 - (7 \times (9 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 60}{(4 + 5) \times (7 + (9^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 + 1)) \times 60}{4 \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (8 - 1)) \times (6 - 0)}{4 + (57 + (9 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 8) \times (1 - (6 - 0))}{(4 \times (5 - (7 - 9))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (8 - (1 \times 60))}{(4^{5+7-9}) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (1 + (6 - 0)))}{4 + (57 - (9 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (81 - (6 - 0))}{(4 \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 \times (6 - 0)))}{(4 \times 5) - (7 + (9 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1^6 + 0))}{4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (8 - (1 - 60))}{4 - (5 + (7 - 92))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (81 + (6 - 0))}{4 + (5 + (7 + 92))}$$

$$:= \frac{381 - (6 - 0)}{457 - (9 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38160}{52947} := \frac{(3 + 8 + 1) \times 60}{52 + 947}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38165}{70942} := \frac{(3 + 8 \times 1 \times 6) \times 5}{(70 + 9) \times (4 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8 + 1 \times 6) \times 5}{(70 + 9) \times (4 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38190}{45627} := \frac{38 \times (1 + 9) + 0}{4 \times 5 + 62 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38192}{45760} := \frac{3 + 8 \times 1 \times 9^2}{4 \times 5 + 760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38210}{64957} := \frac{3 + (8 - (2 - (1 - 0)))}{6 + (4 + (9 + (5 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + 2)) - 10}{6 + (4 \times (9 + (5 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + 2)) + 10}{6 - (4 - (9 + 57))}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + (2 + 10)}{64 + (9 + (5 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (2 + 10))}{((6 + (4 + 9)) \times 5) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + 8)^2) - (1 - 0)}{6 \times ((4 \times 9) + (5 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 - 2) \times 10)}{6 \times (49 - (5 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((8 + 2) \times 10)}{((6 - 4)^9) + (5 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(38 - 2) \times 10}{6 \times (4 + ((9 + 5) \times 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38214}{60795} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 2 \times 1 - 4}{60 - (7 - 9) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 82 - 1 + 4}{60 + (7 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38241}{60795} := \frac{38 \times 2^4 - 1}{60 \times (7 + 9) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38250}{41769} := \frac{(38 + 2) \times 50}{(4 - 1)^7 + 6 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38250}{64719} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 2) \times 50}{6 \times 47 \times 1 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38259}{46107} &:= \frac{3+8+2 \times (5+9)}{46+1^{07}} &:= \frac{(3 \times (8-4)) - (5+1)}{7 - (6 - (9 - (-02)))} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (4 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 \times (6 - (9 \times (0 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3+8 \times 2+59}{4 \times 6+10 \times 7} &:= \frac{(3 \times (8-4)) - (5-1)}{(7+(6-(9-0)))^2} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (4 \times (5 \times 1)))}{7 \times (6 - (9 \times (-02)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3+(8-2) \times 5 \times 9}{(46+1) \times 07} &:= \frac{(3 \times (84+5)) - 1}{76 \times (9+(-02))} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (4 + (5 \times 1)))}{((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(382-5) \times 9}{4^6 \times 1 - 07} &:= \frac{(3 \times 8) + (4 \times (5 \times 1))}{(7-6) \times (90-2)} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (4 + 51))}{7 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38259}{71604} &:= \frac{3 \times (8^2 + 5 \times 9)}{7+1+604} &:= \frac{(3 \times 8) + (4 + (5 \times 1))}{((7 \times 6) - (9 - 0)) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 + (((8 + 4) \times 5) - 1)}{(7 - 69) \times (-02)} \\
 & &:= \frac{(3^{8-4}) + 51}{((7 \times 6) + 90) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 + ((8 \times (4 + 5)) + 1)}{(7 + (69 - 0)) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38295}{41607} &:= \frac{3-8+2 \times 95}{(4-1) \times (60+7)} &:= \frac{(3+(8+4)) \times (5+1)}{(7-6) \times (90 \times 2)} &:= \frac{3 + ((8 \times 4) - (5 + 1))}{76 + (9 \times (-02))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38295}{47610} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 + 2 \times 9 - 5}{4+7 \times 6 \times 1+0} &:= \frac{(3+8) \times ((4 \times 5) + 1)}{7 \times (6 \times (9 - (-02)))} &:= \frac{3 + (8 - (4 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 + (6 + (9 - (-02)))} \\
 & &:= \frac{(38 \times (4 + 5)) + 1}{7 \times (6 + (90 + 2))} &:= \frac{3 + (8 - (4 + (5 \times 1)))}{7 + (6 - (9 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38410}{65297} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 4 - 10}{6 - 52 + 9 \times 7} &:= \frac{(38 \times (4 + 5)) - 1}{(76 \times (9 - 0)) - 2} &:= \frac{3 + (8 - (4 + (5 + 1)))}{7 + (6 - (9 - (-02)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 4 \times 1 + 0}{6 - 5 \times (2 - 9) + 7} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (4 + (5 \times 1)))}{7 - (6 - (9 + (-02)))} &:= \frac{3 + (8 \times (4 + (5 - 1)))}{(76 - (9 - 0)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - 8) \times (4 - 10)}{6 - 52 + 97} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (4 + (5 + 1)))}{7 - (6 - (9 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{3 + (8 + (4 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 + (6 + (9 + (-02)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + 8 - 4) \times 10}{6^{5-2} - 97} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (4 + 51))}{(7 - (6 - (9 - 0)))^2} &:= \frac{3 + (8 + (4 - (5 + 1)))}{(7 - 6) \times (9 \times (02))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times (4 + 1) + 0}{6 - 5 + 29 \times 7} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (45 + 1))}{7 - (6 - (9^{02}))} &:= \frac{3 + (84 - (5 \times 1))}{76 + (90 - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{38 \times (4 + 1) + 0}{6 \times 5 \times (2 + 9) - 7} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (45 - 1))}{7 + (69 - (-02))} &:= \frac{3 + (84 + (5 - 1))}{(7 - (6 - 90)) \times 2} \\
 & &:= \frac{3 - (8 \times (4 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 + (6 + (9 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{38 - (4 - (5 - 1))}{7 + (69 - (0 \times 2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38451}{76902} &:= \frac{(3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5)) + 1}{(7 + (6 \times (9 - 0))) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 - (8 \times (4 - (5 - 1)))}{7 + (6 - (9 + (-02)))} &:= \frac{38 \times (4 + (5 \times 1))}{76 \times (9 - (0 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 \times 4)) + 51}{7 \times (6 \times (9 + (-02)))} &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times (4 \times 5)) + 1)}{7 \times (69 \times (02))} &:= \frac{38 + (4 - (5 \times 1))}{7 + (69 + (-02))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5))) + 1}{(76 + (9 - 0)) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times 4) + (5 \times 1))}{(7 \times 6) + (90 \times 2)} &:= \frac{38 + (4 \times 51)}{(7 + (6 + (9 - 0)))^2} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 - 5))) + 1}{(7 + (6 + (9 - 0))) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 - (4 - (5 + 1)))}{(7 \times 6) - (9 \times (-02))} &:= \frac{38 + (4 + (5 \times 1))}{7 + (6 + (9^{02}))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + (4 + (5 - 1))}{(7 - 6) \times (90 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{38 + 451}{76 + 902}$$

$$:= \frac{384 - 5 - 1}{7 \times 6 \times 9 \times 02}$$

$$:= \frac{3845 + 1}{7690 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3845 - 1}{7690 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38467}{91520} := \frac{3 + (8 + 4) \times 67}{(91 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{47196} := \frac{38 - 5 - 02}{4 \times (7 + 1^9) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{61479} := \frac{(3 + 8 \times 50) \times 2}{6^{1-4+7} - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{69471} := \frac{38 + 50 \times 2}{6 + 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38570}{49126} := \frac{3 + 85 + 7 + 0}{4 + 9 \times (1 + 2 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38571}{62049} := \frac{3 + 8 + 57 + 1}{62 + 049}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times 5 + 7 - 1)}{6 + (20 + 4) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38594}{67120} := \frac{3 \times 85 - 94}{(6 + 7 + 1) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38610}{49725} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 6 \times 1 + 0}{4 + 9 \times (7 \times 2 - 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38617}{52049} := \frac{3 + 8 + 6 - 1 + 7}{5 + 2 \times (04 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times (6 + 1) - 7}{52 \times 04 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38625}{41097} := \frac{(3 + 8 - 6) \times 25}{(4 + 10) \times 9 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(38 + 62) \times 5}{4 \times (10 + 9) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38625}{79104} := \frac{(3 + 8 - 6) \times 25}{(7 \times 9 + 1) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8 - 6)^{2+5}}{(7 + 9) \times 10^4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38640}{97152} := \frac{3 + 8 + 6 \times 4 + 0}{(9 + 7 \times 1 \times 5) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 6 + 4 + 0}{(9 + 7) \times (1 + 5 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 6 - 4 + 0}{9 + 7^{1 \times 5 - 2}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38701}{95264} := \frac{3 - 8 + 70 \times 1}{(9 + 5 + 26) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times 7 + 01}{95 \times 2 + 6 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 87 + 01}{(9 + 5) \times (2 \times 6 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 7 + 01}{(9 - 5) \times 26 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 70 \times 1)}{9 \times (5 \times 2 \times 6 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38710}{64925} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 7 - 10}{(6 + 49 - 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38715}{69420} := \frac{3 + 8 + 71 + 5}{6 \times (9 + 4) \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38719}{62450} := \frac{38 - 7 \times 1^9}{6 - 2 - 4 + 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 8) \times (71 - 9)}{(6 + 2^4) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times (71 - 9)}{6 \times 2 \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38724}{69150} := \frac{3 + 8 - 7 + 24}{6 \times 9 + 1 - 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 8 + 7 + 24}{(6 + 9 \times 1) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 87) \times (2 - 4)}{6 \times (9 + 1) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2 \times 4}{6 \times (9 - 1) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(387 - 2) \times 4}{(6 \times 9 + 1) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38742}{51069} := \frac{3 - 8 + 7 + 42}{5 - 1 + 06 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38794}{52160} := \frac{3 \times (87 - 9) + 4}{5 \times 2^{1 \times 6} + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38796}{51240} := \frac{3 \times (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6)}{5 \times 1 \times (2 + 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{38 \times 7 - 9 \times 6}{(5 + 1 \times 2) \times 40}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{38907}{41265} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 + 9 + 0 \times 7}{4 - 1 + 2 + 6 \times 5} &:= \frac{(3 + (8 + 9)) \times (2 + 5)}{4 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 + 89 + 07}{(4 + 1) \times (26 - 5)} &:= \frac{3 - ((8 - 9) \times (2^5))}{(4 \times (6 + 7)) - 10} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 8 + 9) \times 07}{(41 + 2 + 6) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 - (8 - (9 \times 25))}{4 \times (67 - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + 90 \times 7)}{(412 - 6) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 - (9 - 2)) \times 5)}{4 + (6 + (7 + (1 - 0)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38907}{64152} &:= \frac{3 + 8 \times (9 + 07)}{6^{4-1}5^2} &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 \times 9) - (2^5))}{4 \times (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))} \\ & &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 + (9 \times 2)) \times 5)}{467 + (1 - 0)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{40572} &:= \frac{38 + 9 \times 1^6}{4 + 05 \times (7 + 2)} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (9 - (2 + 5)))}{4 \times (6 - (7 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{(38 + 9) \times 16}{(4 \times (0 \times 5 + 7))^2} &:= \frac{3 \times (8 + (9 - (2 - 5)))}{4 + (67 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 8 + 916}{4 \times 05 \times 7^2} &:= \frac{3 + (8 - (9 + (2 - 5)))}{4 - (6 - (7 + (1 - 0)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{74025} &:= \frac{3 \times (89 + 1) + 6}{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)} &:= \frac{3 + (8 + (9 - (2 \times 5)))}{4 \times (6 + (7 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 89) \times 16}{7 \times 40 \times 2 \times 5} &:= \frac{3 + (8 + (9 + 25))}{46 + (7 + (1 - 0))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{74520} &:= \frac{3 \times (89 - 1 + 6)}{(7 + 4 \times 5) \times 20} &:= \frac{38 \times (9 \times (2 \times 5))}{(4^6) + (7 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(38 + 9) \times (1 + 6)}{7 \times 45 \times 2 + 0} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38925}{46710} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 8) - 9)^2) + 5}{46 \times (7 - (1 - 0))} & \\ &:= \frac{(3 - ((8 - 9) \times 2)) \times 5}{(4 + (6 - 7)) \times 10} & \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times 9) - 2)) + 5}{(4 \times 67) - 10} & \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) + 5}{(4 + 6) \times (7 - (1 - 0))} & \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) - 5}{4 \times (6 + (7 - (1 - 0)))} & \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 89) - (2 + 5)}{(46 \times 7) - 10} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38957}{62140} &:= \frac{3 + 8 + 9 \times 5 \times 7}{(6 \times 2 + 1) \times 40} & \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{38964}{71052} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 9 + 6 - 4}{7 - 1 + 05^2} & \\ &:= \frac{3 + 8 \times (9 + 6) - 4}{7 + 105 \times 2} & \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (8 \times 9 + 6) + 4}{7 \times (10 + 52)} & \\ &:= \frac{389 + 6 - 4}{710 + 5 - 2} & \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (89 + 6) + 4}{7 + 10 \times 52} & \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9 - (0 \times 12))}{4 + ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9 - (0 - 12))}{4 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (90 + (1 + 2))}{4 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{39 - (0 - (1^2))}{(4 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{390 - (1 \times 2)}{(4 + (87 + 6)) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39015}{42687} := \frac{3 \times (90 - 1 \times 5)}{4 + 268 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39015}{64872} := \frac{3 \times (90 - 1 \times 5)}{6^4 - 872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39024}{71568} := \frac{3 \times 902 + 4}{71 \times 5 \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39025}{87416} := \frac{3 + 90 + 2 + 5}{8 \times 7 \times 4 \times 1^6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 90 + 2^5}{8 \times 7 \times (4 + 1^6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(-3 + 9) \times 025}{8 \times (7 + 41 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{57186} := \frac{3^{9-04} - 2}{5 \times 71 - 8 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{71658} := \frac{3 + 90 \times 4 \times 2}{7 + 165 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{75168} := \frac{3^{9-04} - 2}{(75 + 1) \times 6 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{87156} := \frac{3^{9-04} - 2}{8 \times 71 - 5 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39057}{68142} := \frac{3 + 9 + 05 \times 7}{(6 - 8) \times (1 - 42)}$$

$$:= \frac{39 \times 05 - 7}{6 + 81 \times 4 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 90 + 5 + 7}{6 + 81 \times (4 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39072}{54168} := \frac{3 + 90 - 7^2}{5 + 4 \times 1 \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 90 - 7 + 2}{54 + 1 \times 68}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9 \times 07) \times 2}{5 \times (41 - 6) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39074}{86521} := \frac{39 - 07 - 4}{8 + 6 \times (5 \times 2 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{39 + 07 - 4}{86 + 5 + 2 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39078}{52416} := \frac{390 - 7 \times 8}{(5 + 2) \times 4 \times 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39102}{87465} := \frac{39 + 1 - 02}{(8 + 7 - 4 + 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39104}{65728} := \frac{3 + 91 - 0 \times 4}{6 \times 5 \times (7 - 2) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 91) \times 04}{(65 + 7 \times 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 910 - 4}{6 + 572 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{42768} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{(4 - 2 + 7) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{46728} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{4 \times (6 + 7 \times 2 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{46827} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{468 - 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{76824} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{82476} := \frac{(3 + 9 - 1) \times 05}{8 \times 24 - 76}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9 + 10) \times 5}{8 \times (2^4 + 7 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{82764} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{8^2 \times (7 + 6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{86427} := \frac{39 \times 10 + 5}{864 + 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{86742} := \frac{(3 + 9 - 1) \times 05}{(8 - 6)^7 - 4 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9 + 10) \times 5}{(8 \times 6 + 74) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 10 + 5}{86 \times 7 + 4 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39120}{54768} := \frac{((3 \times 9) - 1) \times 20}{(5 + 47) \times (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (9 \times 1)) - (2 - 0)}{5 - (4 - ((7 \times 6) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (9 + 1)) + 20}{5 + (4 - (7 - 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (9 \times 1)) \times 20}{(5 - 4) \times (7 \times (6 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (9 + 1)) \times 20}{(54 \times 7) - (6 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(39 + 1) \times (2 - 0)}{(5 - (4 - (7 + 6))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (9 - (1 + 20))}{(5 - 4) \times (7 + (6 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((9 + 1) \times (2 - 0))}{5 + (4 + (7 + 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((9 + 1)^2 + 0)}{5 \times (4 \times (7 + (6 + 8)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times (1 \times 20))}{(5+4) \times (76+8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 120)}{54 \times (76+8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 + (1^2 + 0))}{5 - (4 + (7 - (6 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 + (1 + 20))}{(5 \times (4 \times 7)) - (6 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (9 - (1 \times (2 - 0)))}{5 + (4 + (7 + (6 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{39 + (1^2 + 0)}{5 - (4 - (7 + (6 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{39 + (1 - 20)}{(5 \times (4 \times (7 - 6))) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39125}{87640} &:= \frac{(3+9-1 \times 2) \times 5}{8 \times 7 \times (6-4) + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 9 \times 1 - 2) \times 5}{(8-7+6) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 + 1^2) \times 5}{(8+76) \times 4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 - 1) \times 25}{8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 + 1)^2 \times 5}{(8 + 76) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39150}{64728} := \frac{3 \times (9 + 1) \times 5 + 0}{(6 - 4)^7 \times 2 - 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{40752} &:= \frac{(39 + 1 - 6) \times 8}{40 \times 7 + 5 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{45072} &:= \frac{(39 + 1 - 6) \times 8}{45 \times 07 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{47520} &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 16 - 8)}{475 + 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{54720} &:= \frac{(39 + 1 - 6) \times 8}{5 \times (4 + 72) + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{57024} &:= \frac{3 + 9 + (1 + 6) \times 8}{5 + 70 + 24} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 16 - 8)}{570 + 24} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{74052} &:= \frac{(3 + 9 \times 1) \times 6 - 8}{(7 + 4 - 0 \times 5)^2} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8}{(7 \times 4 + 05)^2} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 91 - 6) \times 8}{7 + 4)^{05-2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{51678} &:= \frac{3 \times (92 - 04)}{5 \times (1 + 67) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 - 9 + 204}{5 + (1 - 6 + 7)^8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 20 - 4)}{(5 \times 16 + 7) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{51876} &:= \frac{3 \times (9 + 20 + 4)}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{57618} &:= \frac{3 \times (92 - 04)}{5 \times 76 \times 1 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 2 + 04)}{57 + (6 - 1) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{57816} := \frac{392 + 04}{578 + 1 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{61578} := \frac{392 + 04}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{61875} := \frac{3 \times (920 + 4)}{(6 - 1) \times 875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{67518} := \frac{3 + 9 + 2 + 04}{6 - 7 + (5 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{3 + 9 + 20 + 4}{67 - 5 \times 1^8} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times (20 + 4)}{(67 - 5) \times 18} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (92 + 04)}{(67 - 5 \times 1) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{392 + 04}{675 - 1 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 2^{04}}{(6 \times 7 + 51) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{81675} := \frac{3 + (9 - (2 \times (0 \times 4)))}{8 - (1 - (6 + (7 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 - (0 \times 4))}{8 + (1 + (6 + (7 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9 + (20 + 4))}{(8 + ((1^6) \times 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - 9) \times (2 \times (-04))}{(8 - (1 - (6 + 7))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (9 \times 2)) \times (-04)}{8 + ((16 \times 7) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 - (-04))}{(8 - (1 \times 6)) \times 75}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9^{2+0 \times 4})}{(((8 - 1) \times 6) - 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 \times (04))}{8 + (16 \times (7 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((9 + (2 - 0)) \times 4)}{((8 \times (1 \times 6)) + 7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2^{04})}{(81 + (6 - 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (92 - (-04))}{(8 + (16 \times 7)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 9)^2 + 0) \times 4}{(8 + 1) \times 675}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times (2^{04}))}{(81 - 6) \times (7 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{87516} := \frac{3 - 9 + 204}{87 \times 5 + 1 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39240}{76518} := \frac{3 + 9 + 2 \times 4 + 0}{7 + 6 \times (5 - 1) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 + 5 - 1) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + 9^2 - 4 + 0}{(7 + 6) \times (5 - 1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 \times 5 - 1) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+9)^2 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 \times 5 + 1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 92 + 4 + 0}{7 \times 6 \times (5 + 1 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39270}{45186} := \frac{3 \times (9+2) \times 70}{(451-8) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39270}{68145} := \frac{39+2-7+0}{6+8+1 \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39280}{75614} := \frac{3+9+28+0}{7 \times (5+6 \times 1^4)}$$

$$:= \frac{39 \times 2 \times 80}{7+5 \times (6+1)^4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+9) \times (2+8) + 0}{7 - (5-61) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+9-2) \times 80}{7 \times (56-1) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 5 \times (6 + 1 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{392 + 8 + 0}{756 + 14}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39410}{87265} := \frac{3 \times (9-4) - 1 + 0}{8 - 7 \times (2-6) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9+4+1) + 0}{8 \times (7-2+6) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{3+94+1+0}{87+2 \times 65}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39420}{57816} := \frac{39-4-20}{5-7+8+16}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9-4) \times 2 + 0}{57-8+1-6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9+4+2) + 0}{5+7+(8+1) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9-4+20)}{5 \times (7+8+1+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9-4) \times 20}{57 \times 8 - 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39420}{61758} := \frac{3 \times (9-4) \times 2 + 0}{6-17+58}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9-4) \times 20}{6+(1+7) \times 58}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39456}{70281} := \frac{39+4-5-6}{7^{0^2} + 8 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39480}{72615} := \frac{(3-9) \times 4 + 80}{7 \times 2 \times (6+1) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39487}{62051} := \frac{(3 \times (9-4)) - (8-7)}{6 + (2^{0^5-1})}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (9 - (48 - 7))}{6 - (2 + (0 - 51))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9 + (4 + (8 - 7)))}{6 \times ((2 \times (0^5)) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (9+4)) + 87}{6 \times ((2^{0^5}) + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 - (9 - (48 + 7))}{6 + (20 + 51)}$$

$$:= \frac{(((3+9) \times 4) + 8) \times 7}{620 - (5-1)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9 - (4 + (8 - 7)))}{(6 \times (2 - (0 \times 5))) - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39501}{82467} := \frac{3+9 \times (5+01)}{8 \times (2 \times 4+6) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39501}{82764} := \frac{3 \times 9 - 5 - 01}{(8+2+7-6) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (9+5 \times 01)}{8 \times (2+7+6-4)}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times (50-1)}{8+2764}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39514}{68720} := \frac{3-9 \times 5 \times (1-4)}{6 \times 8 \times (7-2) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (95+1-4)}{6 \times (8+72) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times 95 + 14}{6 \times 87 - 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39520}{67184} := \frac{(3 \times (9-5)) - (2-0)}{6 + (7 + (1 \times (8-4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times 9) - (5 + (2-0))}{6 + (7 \times (1 \times (8-4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + (9 \times (5 - (2-0)))}{6 - ((7 \times (1-8)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 \times (9+5)) - (2-0)}{(6 - (7-18)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 + ((9 \times 5) + (2-0))}{6 + (7 + (18 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3+9) \times 5) + 20}{6 + ((7 \times 18) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+9) \times (5 \times (2-0))}{((6 \times 7) + (1+8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times ((9-5) \times 20)}{6 \times (((7+1) \times 8) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(3+9) \times (5+20)}{6 + (7 \times (18 \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (9-5)) \times 20}{((6+7) \times 18) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (9+5)) \times 20}{6 + ((71 \times 8) + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39540}{61287} := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 - 40}{6 \times (12-8) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{39+5-4+0}{6+1^2 \times 8 \times 7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 \times 40}{61^2 - 8 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39540}{67218} & := \frac{(3-9) \times 5 + 40}{6-7+2 \times (1+8)} \\ & := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 - 40}{6 \times 7 \times (2-1) - 8} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (9+5-4) + 0}{6 + (7-2) \times (1+8)} \\ & := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 + 40}{(6+7)^2 + 1^8} \\ & := \frac{39+5-4+0}{6 \times (7+2+1) + 8} \\ & := \frac{(3-9) \times (5-40)}{6+7^{2+1} + 8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39564}{70812} & := \frac{3-9+5 \times 64}{70 \times 8 \times 1 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39564}{71820} & := \frac{3-9+5 \times 64}{71 \times 8 + 2 + 0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39567}{42108} & := \frac{3+9 \times (5+6) + 7}{4 \times (21+08)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39576}{41820} & := \frac{(395-7) \times 6}{(4-1) \times 820} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39627}{51408} & := \frac{3-9+6^2+7}{(5+1^{40}) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{3 \times 9 \times 6 - 2 \times 7}{5 \times 1 \times 40 - 8} \\ & := \frac{3+9 \times 6 + 2^7}{5 \times 1 \times (40+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39627}{84150} & := \frac{(3+9 \times 6 \times 2) \times 7}{(8 \times 4 + 1) \times 50} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39648}{51072} & := \frac{3+(9-6+4) \times 8}{5-1+072} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39652}{41807} & := \frac{3+96-5-2}{41+8 \times 07} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39672}{58140} & := \frac{3 \times (9-6) + 7^2}{5 \times (8+1) + 40} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39712}{65408} & := \frac{39+7-12}{(6+5-4) \times 08} \\ & := \frac{3+9 \times 7 \times 1 + 2}{6 \times 5 \times 4 - 08} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (9+7+1) \times 2}{6 \times (5 \times 4 + 08)} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (9 \times 7 - 12)}{65 \times 4 - 08} \\ & := \frac{39 \times 7 - 1^2}{(6+5) \times 40 + 8} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39725}{46081} & := \frac{(3+9-7) \times 2 \times 5}{4+6 \times (08+1)} \\ & := \frac{3+97+25}{4+60+81} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (9 \times 7 + 2) + 5}{4 \times 60 - 8 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (97-2+5)}{4 \times (6+081)} \\ & := \frac{(3+9) \times 7 \times 25}{4 \times (608+1)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{41652} & := \frac{3+9-7+80}{4 \times 16+5^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{46215} & := \frac{3+9+7 \times 8+0}{4-(6-21) \times 5} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{46512} & := \frac{3 \times (9+7 \times 8) + 0}{46 \times 5 \times 1 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{52416} & := \frac{3+9-7+80}{(5-2+4) \times 16} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{61425} & := \frac{3+9+7 \times 8+0}{6-1+4 \times 25} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39786}{45021} & := \frac{(3+9+7) \times (8-6)}{45-02 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{3+97+8+6}{4+5^{02+1}} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39812}{54607} & := \frac{(3+9 \times 8-1) \times 2}{(5+4 \times 6) \times 07} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39816}{40527} & := \frac{3 \times (9+8) - 1 + 6}{4^{05-2} - 7} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39824}{61570} & := \frac{(3 \times 9 - 8) \times 2 \times 4}{61 \times 5 - 70} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39840}{61752} & := \frac{3+9+8+40}{6+17 \times 5+2} \\ & := \frac{(3-9+8) \times 40}{61 \times (7-5) + 2} \\ & := \frac{(3+9) \times 8 + 4 + 0}{6-1+75 \times 2} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39852}{46170} & := \frac{3+9 \times 8 + 5 + 2}{4 \times 6 + 1 + 70} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{39861}{42570} & := \frac{(3+9) \times 8 + 6 + 1}{4 \times 2 \times 5 + 70} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39861}{70452} &:= \frac{3+9 \times (8+6 \times 1)}{70 \times 4 - 52} \\ &:= \frac{3-9+8 \times 6+1}{70-4+5 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39862}{45107} &:= \frac{(3 \times (9+8)+6) \times 2}{4+5^{10-7}} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times 9-8) \times (6+2)}{4 \times (5 \times 10-7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39864}{70215} := \frac{3+9^{8-6}+4}{70 \times 2+15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39867}{45210} := \frac{(3+9) \times 8-6+7}{4 \times 5^2+10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40139}{56782} &:= \frac{40+1^{39}}{56-(7-8) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(40+1^3) \times 9}{5 \times (6+7) \times 8+2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40152}{67398} &:= \frac{4-01+5^2}{6-7-(3-9) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{4+01 \times 52}{6-7-3+98} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40158}{63729} := \frac{401+5+8}{6+3+72 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{53289} := \frac{4 \times (-01+7) \times 6}{5 \times (32+8)-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{83592} := \frac{4 \times 017-6}{8+3+59 \times 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{85932} &:= \frac{(4+01+7) \times 6}{(8+5) \times (9+3)-2} \\ &:= \frac{(40+1+7) \times 6}{8 \times (5 \times 9+32)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40215}{76983} &:= \frac{(40+2 \times 1) \times 5}{7 \times 6 \times 9+8 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{40 \times (2+1 \times 5)}{7 \times (69+8)-3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40215}{76983} := \frac{40+2 \times 15}{7 \times 6+9+83}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40236}{58917} := \frac{4 \times (-02+3+6)}{58-9-1-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40257}{61983} := \frac{4+02+57}{6-1+9+83}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40271}{53869} := \frac{4+02+71}{5+3+86+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40281}{76395} &:= \frac{40-2-8-1}{7+6+3 \times (9+5)} \\ &:= \frac{40+2 \times (8+1)}{76+39-5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40281}{76395} := \frac{4+02+81}{7+63+95}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40281}{76395} := \frac{4 \times (028+1)}{(7+6 \times 3) \times 9-5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40293}{67518} &:= \frac{4+(02+9) \times 3}{67-5 \times 1^8} \\ &:= \frac{40+293}{6 \times (75+18)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40293}{81675} &:= \frac{4+(02+9) \times 3}{(8+1^6 \times 7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{40 \times 2-9+3}{(8-1 \times 6) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40293}{81675} &:= \frac{40+293}{(8 \times 16+7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{40+2^9+3}{(8+1+6) \times 75} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40321}{78659} &:= \frac{4^{03}-2-1}{7 \times (8+(6-5) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{40 \times 3+2 \times 1}{7+8 \times 6 \times 5-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40352}{61789} &:= \frac{4+03+5^2}{(6-1^7) \times 8+9} \\ &:= \frac{(40+3+5)^2}{(6+1) \times 7 \times 8 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40352}{61789} := \frac{4^{(03+5) \times 2}}{(6+1) \times 7 \times 8^9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40356}{97128} := \frac{4 \times (03+56)}{9 \times (7+1)^2-8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40365}{81972} &:= \frac{(4+03+6) \times 5}{8-(1-9 \times 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{(4-(-03)) \times (9 \times 2)}{(8 \times (7 \times 5)) - (1+6)} \\ &:= \frac{40+3 \times 6 \times 5}{8+1 \times (9+7)^2} &:= \frac{4 \times ((03 \times (9+2)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (5 \times 1))) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 3 + 65)}{8 \times (1+9 \times 7+2)} &:= \frac{4 \times ((0-(3-9))^2)}{(8-(7-51)) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40365}{91287} &:= \frac{40 \times (3 \times 6 - 5)}{(9+12) \times 8 \times 7} &:= \frac{4 \times ((03+(9^2)))}{8 \times (75+16)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 03 \times 65}{9 \times 1 \times 28 \times 7} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9))^2}{8 \times ((7 \times 51) - 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40386}{57912} &:= \frac{40+(3+8) \times 6}{5+7 \times (9+12)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{40528}{76139} &:= \frac{40 \times (5+2) - 8}{7 \times (61+3+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{51867} &:= \frac{4+03+9^2}{5 \times (18+6) - 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{40572}{96138} &:= \frac{4 \times 05+72}{(9+61) \times 3+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{51876} &:= \frac{40 \times 3 - 9 \times 2}{5 \times (18+7) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{40629}{51837} &:= \frac{(4+06) \times 2+9}{5-1 \times 8 \times (3-7)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{57618} &:= \frac{(40+3-9) \times 2}{57+(6-1) \times 8} & &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 6 + 29)}{(5-1^8) \times 37} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{65178} &:= \frac{4+03+9^2}{65-1+78} & &:= \frac{4 \times 06 \times 29}{51+837} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{87516} &:= \frac{4-((0 \times 39) - 2)}{8+(7+(5-(1+6)))} & &:= \frac{406-29}{(5+1 \times 8) \times 37} \\ &:= \frac{4+(0-(3-(9+2)))}{8+(7-(5-16))} & &:= \frac{406+29}{518+37} \\ &:= \frac{4-(0-(3+(9+2)))}{8+(7+((5-1) \times 6))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{40635}{71982} &:= \frac{(4+06-3) \times 5}{7-1 \times 9+8^2} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (03)) + (9 \times 2)}{(8^{7-5}) + (1^6)} & &:= \frac{(40+6+3) \times 5}{(7-1) \times 9 \times 8+2} \\ &:= \frac{40+(3-(9-2))}{8+(7 \times (5-(1-6)))} & &:= \frac{(4+06) \times 35}{(71-9) \times (8+2)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (03)) + 9) \times 2}{(8 \times (7+5)) + (1-6)} & &:= \frac{40 \times (6+3+5)}{(71-9) \times 8 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (0-((3-9) \times 2))}{8 \times (7+(5+(1^6)))} & & \\ &:= \frac{40+(3+(9+2))}{87+(5 \times (1 \times 6))} & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40836}{51792} &:= \frac{4 \times 08 + 3 + 6}{5 \times (1^7 + 9) + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{63279} &:= \frac{(4 + 08) \times 51}{(6 + 3 \times 2) \times 79} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (08 + 5) - 1}{(6 - 3 - 2) \times 79} \\ &:= \frac{408 - 51}{(6 + 3 - 2) \times 79} \\ &:= \frac{408 + 51}{632 + 79} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{67932} := \frac{4 + 085 \times 1}{67 + 9 \times 3^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{73692} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 8 + 51)}{(7 + 3 - 6) \times 92} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (08 + 5) - 1}{(7 - 3 + 6) \times 9 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{408 - 51}{7 + 3^6 - 92} \\ &:= \frac{408 + 51}{7 + 3^6 + 92} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40893}{67521} := \frac{40 - (8 - 9) \times 3}{6^{7-5} \times 2 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40896}{73152} := \frac{40 + (8 + 9) \times 6}{7 \times (31 + 5) + 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40917}{65823} &:= \frac{40 - 9 - 1 - 7}{6 \times 5 + 8 + 2 - 3} \\ &:= \frac{40 + 91 + 7}{6 \times 5 + 8^2 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40918}{62375} &:= \frac{409 + 1^8}{62 \times (3 + 7) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{40 \times (9 - 1) + 8}{(6 + 2)^3 - 7 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40976}{58312} &:= \frac{4 + 09 + 7 + 6}{5 + 8 \times (3 + 1^2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 9 + 7 + 6)}{(5 + 8 \times (3 + 1)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (09) + 7 \times 6}{(5 \times 8 - 3) \times (1 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (097 - 6)}{5 + 8^3 + 1^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40986}{52371} := \frac{(4 - 09 + 8) \times 6}{5 + 2 \times (3 + 7 - 1)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times 09 \times (8 - 6)}{(5 + 2^3) \times 7 + 1} \\ &:= \frac{4 - 0 \times 9 + 86}{5 \times (2 + 3 \times 7 \times 1)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times 09^{8-6}}{(5 + 2)^3 + 71} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{40 \times 9 \times (8 - 6)}{5 \times 23 \times (7 + 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40986}{57132} := \frac{40 - 9 + 8 - 6}{(5 + (7 - 1) \times 3) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 09 + 86}{5 \times 7 \times (1 + 3) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (09 \times 8 - 6)}{5 \times (71 + 3) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41025}{86973} := \frac{(4 - 1 + 02) \times 5}{(8 + 6) \times 9 - 73}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 10 \times 2 \times 5}{8 \times (6 + 97 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 10 \times 25}{8 + 6 \times (9 + 7^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41038}{56729} := \frac{(4 + 10) \times 3 - 8}{5 + 6 + 7 + 29}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41038}{67592} := \frac{(4 - 1) \times 03 + 8}{6 + (7 - 5 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 10) \times 3 - 8}{6 - 7 + 59 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 10 + 3 + 8}{6 \times (7 - 5) \times (9 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (10 + 3 \times 8)}{(67 + 5 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41063}{59728} := \frac{4 + (10 - (6 - 3))}{(5 \times (9 - 7)) - (2 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 \times (0 - (6 \times 3)))}{5 - (9 \times (7 - (2 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 - (-06))) \times 3}{(5 - (9 - 7)) \times (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{41 - (0 - (6 - 3))}{((5 \times (9 - 7)) - 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 + (0 - 63))}{5 + (97 + (2 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (10 + 63)}{5 + (97 + (2 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 - (1 - 0))^6) - 3}{(59 + 7) \times (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 \times (0 - (6^3)))}{5 + (9 \times (7 + 28))}$$

$$:= \frac{410 + 63}{(5 + (9 + 72)) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41067}{85293} := \frac{4 + (10 + (6 - 7))}{8 + (5 + (2 + (9 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((1 + (-06)) \times 7)}{(8 + ((5 \times 2) + 9)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times ((06 + 7)))}{8 + (5 + (2 + 93))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& := \frac{(4 + (1 - 0)) \times (6 + 7)}{(8 - (5 - 2)) \times (9 \times 3)} \\
& := \frac{(4 + 10) \times (6 + 7)}{85 + 293} \\
& := \frac{((4 + 10) \times 6) + 7}{8 - (5 - (2 \times 93))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (106 + 7)}{((8 - 5)^2) \times (9 \times 3)} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41067}{95823} & := \frac{(4 - (1 + (-06))) \times 7}{((9 - (5 - 8))^2) + 3} \\
& := \frac{(4 - (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 7)}{(9 + (5 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 3)} \\
& := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (-06))) - 7}{9 - (5 \times (8 \times (2 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{(4 \times (10 - 6)) - 7}{9 + (5 + (8 + (2 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{(4 + 10) \times (6 \times 7)}{(((9 \times 5) - 8)^2) + 3} \\
& := \frac{4 - (1 - (0 \times 67))}{9 + (5 - (8 + (2 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 - (1 + (0 - (6 \times 7)))}{(9 + ((5 + 8) \times 2)) \times 3} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (1 \times (0 + (6 \times 7)))}{(9 + (5 \times 8)) \times (2^3)} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (10 + (6 - 7))}{9 - (5 \times (8 - 23))} \\
& := \frac{4 + ((1^{06}) + 7)}{9 + (5 + (8 + (2 \times 3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (1 - (0 - (6 + 7)))}{9 + ((5 + (8 - 2)) \times 3)} \\
& := \frac{4 + (1 + (0 - (6 - 7)))}{9 + (5 - (8 - (2^3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (10 - (6 - 7))}{9 - (5 - (8 + 23))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (10 + (6 + 7))}{9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 \times 3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (10 + 67)}{9 \times (5 + (8 + (2^3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (106 + 7)}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 - 2))) + 3} \\
& := \frac{41 - ((0 \times 6) - 7)}{(9 \times (5 + 8)) - (2 + 3)} \\
& := \frac{41 - (0 - (6 + 7))}{9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{41 - (0 - 67)}{(9 + 5) \times ((8 - 2) \times 3)} \\
& := \frac{41 + (0 - (6 - 7))}{95 + (8 - (2 + 3))} \\
& := \frac{410 - (6 - 7)}{958 - (2 - 3)} \\
& := \frac{410 + (6 + 7)}{(9 + (5 \times (8^2))) \times 3} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41072}{83956} & := \frac{4 \times (10 + 7) \times 2}{8 \times (39 - 5) + 6} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41097}{56238} & := \frac{4 - 1 + 09 + 7}{5 + 6 + 23 - 8} \\
& := \frac{4 \times 10 - 9 + 7}{5 \times (6 + 2 \times 3) - 8} \\
& := \frac{4 - 10 + 9 \times 7}{5 \times (6 + 2^3) + 8} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (10 + 9) \times 7}{56 \times (2 + 3 + 8)} \\
& := \frac{(4 + 10) \times 9 + 7}{(56 + 2) \times 3 + 8} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41205}{76983} & := \frac{41 \times 2 \times 05}{7 + 69 \times (8 + 3)} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41256}{80793} & := \frac{(4 + 1 - 2 + 5) \times 6}{8 - 07 + 93} \\
& := \frac{(4 + 1 + 2 + 5) \times 6}{(8 \times 07 - 9) \times 3} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41265}{83709} & := \frac{4 - 1 + 2 + 6 \times 5}{8 \times (3 + 7) - 09} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41265}{90783} & := \frac{((4 + 1) \times (2^6)) - 5}{9 \times (0 + (7 \times (8 + 3)))} \\
& := \frac{(4 - (1 - (2 \times 6))) \times 5}{((9 \times (07)) - 8) \times 3} \\
& := \frac{(4 - (1 - (2 + 6))) \times 5}{90 + (7 + (8 \times 3))} \\
& := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (2 - 6))) - 5}{9 - ((0 \times 7) - (8 \times 3))} \\
& := \frac{(4 + (1 - (2 - 6))) \times 5}{9 - (0 - (7 + 83))} \\
& := \frac{(4 + (1 \times (2 \times 6))) \times 5}{(9 - (-07)) \times (8 + 3)} \\
& := \frac{(4 + (1 \times (2 + 6))) \times 5}{(9 \times (0 + (7 + 8))) - 3} \\
& := \frac{(41^2) - (6 + 5)}{90 + (7 \times (8^3))} \\
& := \frac{4 - (1 - (2 \times (6 + 5)))}{90 - (7 \times (8 - 3))} \\
& := \frac{4 \times ((1^{26}) \times 5)}{9 - (0 - (7 \times (8 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 \times ((12 + 6) \times 5)}{9 - (0 - 783)} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (1 - (2 - (6 + 5)))}{90 - (7 - (8 - 3))} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (1 \times (2 \times (6 \times 5)))}{9 - (0 - (7 + (8^3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + ((1^{26}) + 5)}{(9 + (-07)) \times (8 + 3)} \\
& := \frac{4 + 1^{265}}{9 - (0 - (7 - (8 - 3)))} \\
& := \frac{4 + (1 + (2 \times (6 \times 5)))}{90 + ((7 \times 8) - 3)} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{41268}{59730} & := \frac{4 + 1 \times 26 + 8}{5^{9-7} + 30} \\
& := \frac{4 \times (1 + 26 - 8)}{5 \times (9 + 7) + 30}
\end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 2^6 - 8)}{5 \times (9 \times 7 + 3) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1 \times 3 \times 7) \times 5}{(9 + 26) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times 50)) \times 8}{7 \times (2 \times (63 - 9))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41283}{95076} := \frac{(4 + 1 + 28) \times 3}{(9 \times 5 - 07) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1 - 3) \times 75}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1^5 + 0)) \times 8}{7 - ((2 - (6 + 3)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 2^{8-3})}{(9 - 5) \times 076}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 13 - 7) \times 5}{9 \times (2^6 - 8) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (5 - 0))) \times 8}{7 \times (2 + (6 + (3 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times (3 + 7) \times 5}{92 \times 6 + 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (15 - 0)) \times 8}{7 \times (2 - (6 \times (3 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 375}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 - (5 - 0)) \times 8}{7 \times ((2^{6-3}) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41293}{86750} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 29 + 3}{(8 + 6 \times 7) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41382}{70965} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times (3 + 8)^2}{(70 + 96) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 + (5 - 0)) \times 8}{7 - (2 - 639)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((1 - 50) \times 8)}{7 \times ((2 + (6 + 3)) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41325}{87609} := \frac{4 - 1 - 3 + 25}{8 \times 7 + 6 - 09}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 - (5 - (-08)))}{7 - (((2 - 6) \times 3) - 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41392}{87560} := \frac{4 + 1 + 3 \times (9 - 2)}{8 \times 7 + 5 - 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 \times (5 \times (-08)))}{7 - (2 - (6 \times (3 + 9)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41328}{57960} := \frac{4^{1+3} - 2 - 8}{5 \times (7 \times 9 + 6) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{41 + 39 - 2}{(8 + 7) \times (5 + 6) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1^5 + 0) \times 8)}{7 \times (2 - (6 - (3 + 9)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41328}{95760} := \frac{(4 + 1 \times 3)^2 - 8}{95 \times (7 - 6) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 3 + 9) \times 2}{8 \times 7 \times 5 - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1^5 + 0) + 8)}{7 + (2 + (63 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{41 \times (3 - 2 + 8)}{9 \times (5 \times 7 + 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 1) \times 39 \times 2}{87 \times 5 + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1 - 5) \times (-08))}{7 \times (26 - (3 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{41 \times (3 + 2 + 8)}{95 \times (7 + 6) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 39 \times 2}{8 \times 75 + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (5 - (0 \times 8)))}{(7 \times 2) - (6 - (3 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{41 \times (32 - 8)}{(9 \times 5 - 7) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (50 + 8))}{7 \times ((2^6) + (3 - 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 328}{(9 - 5) \times 760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41508}{72639} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - 0))) + 8}{7^{2-6-3+9}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))}{7 + (2 - (6 - 39))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times 50)) + 8}{7 \times ((2^6) - (3 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (5 - (-08)))}{7 \times (2 + (6 - (3 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + 50)) + 8}{7 \times (26 + (3 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (15 - (0 \times 8))}{7 \times ((2 \times (6 - 3)) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (15 - 0)) + 8}{7 \times ((2^{6-3}) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (15 - (-08))}{7 \times (2 - (6 - (3 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - 0))) - 8}{7 \times (263 - 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 - (5 + (-08)))}{7 + ((2 \times (6^3)) + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41375}{92680} := \frac{4 - 1 - 3 + 75}{(9 + 2 \times 6) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times (5 - 0))) \times 8}{(7 - (2 - (6 + 3))) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1^{508})}{7 - (2 \times (6 + (3 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 1 - 3 + 75}{6 \times (2 + 8 + 9) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 - 3) \times 75}{6 \times (2 + 8 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (15 - (0 \times 8))}{7 \times ((2 \times (6 - 3)) + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 - 3) \times 75}{6 \times (2 + 8 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 - 3) \times 75}{6 \times (2 + 8 \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (15 - (-08))}{7 \times (2 - (6 - (3 \times 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((1^5 + 0) \times 8)}{7 + (2 + (6 - (3 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((1 + 50) \times 8)}{7 \times ((2^6) + 39)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 - (5 + (-08)))}{7 \times (2 - (6 + (3 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 1508}{7 + 2639}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41520}{73698} := \frac{4 \times 15 + 20}{(7 + 3) \times (6 + 9) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 1 + 5) \times 20}{(7 - 3) \times 69 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 15 \times 20}{7^3 \times 6 + 9 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5 \times 2 + 0}{7 + 3 + 69 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41520}{78369} := \frac{4 \times 15 + 20}{7 + 8 \times (3 + 6 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 - 5) \times 20}{(7 + 8 \times 3 \times 6) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41538}{62790} := \frac{4 + 15 + 3 \times 8}{(6 + 2) \times 7 + 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{76329} := \frac{4 \times 15 + 80}{7 \times (6 + 32) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{76923} := \frac{(4 + 1^5) \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 6 + 9 + 23}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 1 - 5 + 80}{7 + 69 \times 2 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 1) \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{(7 + 69 - 2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 6 \times 9 - 2^3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1 \times 5) \times 80}{7 - 6 + (9 + 2)^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{79632} := \frac{415 + 80}{79 \times (6 + 3 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{96327} := \frac{(4 - 1) \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{9 \times 6 + 32 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 1^5) \times 80}{9 \times (63 - 2) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41652}{87309} := \frac{(4 - 1) \times 6 \times 52}{(8 + 7 \times 30) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41683}{75920} := \frac{41 \times (6 + 8) - 3}{(7 + 5 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41706}{95328} := \frac{4 + (17 - (0 \times 6))}{((9 - 5)^3) - (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (7 - (0 \times 6)))}{(9 + (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times (7 - (0 \times 6))}{(9 - (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{41 + (7 + (-06))}{95 + ((3^2) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (7 - (-06)))}{9 + ((5^3) + (2 - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{41 + (70 - 6)}{(9 + (5 \times 3)) \times (2 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (17 - 0)) \times 6}{(9 - (5 - 32)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times (06)))}{(9 + (5 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 170) + 6}{(95 + 3) \times (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times (7 \times (06))}{(9 + (53 - 2)) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41736}{58092} := \frac{4 \times (17 + 3) - 6}{5 + 80 + 9 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41769}{80325} := \frac{4 - (1 - (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(8 \times (0 \times 3)) + 25}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))}{(8 + (-03)) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 17) \times (6 - 9)}{80 - ((3 - 2) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 + (7 - 69))}{(8 + (-03)) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + 1) \times 7) + 69}{(8 - (0 - 32)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((41 - 7) \times 6) - 9}{(80 - (3 + 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((1 + (7 + 6)) \times 9)}{(80 \times 3) + (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + ((7 \times 6) + 9))}{80 \times ((3 - 2) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41796}{58320} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9 + 6}{5 \times 8 \times 3^2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41796}{83205} := \frac{4 + 1 + 7 + 96}{(8 + 3) \times 20 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41823}{69705} := \frac{(4 - ((1 - 8) \times 2)) \times 3}{6 + (9 + (70 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (8^2))) \times 3}{(6 - (9 - 70)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (1^{82})) \times 3}{6 + (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (1 - 82)) \times 3}{(6 + (9 + 70)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (18 \times 2)) - 3}{((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times (8 - 2))) \times 3}{6 + (9 - (7 \times (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (8 \times 2))) \times 3}{(6 - 9) \times (7 \times (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (8^2))) \times 3}{(6 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 + (8 \times 2)) \times 3}{(6 - (9 \times 7)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 + (8^2)) \times 3}{(6 + 9) \times (7 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 - ((8 - 2)^3))}{6 + (9 + (70 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 - (8 - (2 - 3)))}{(6 - (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 + (8 - 23))}{(6 + 9) \times (7 + (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (((1^8) + 2)^3)}{(6^{9-7+0}) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + 8) \times (2^3))}{6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 + (2 \times 3)))}{((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (18 - (2 \times 3))}{6 + (9 + (70 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (18 \times (2 \times 3))}{6 + (9 + 705)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 + ((8 \times 2) + 3))}{(6 + (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 + ((8^2) - 3))}{(6 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 + (8 + 23))}{6 \times ((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (182 - 3)}{((6 \times 9) + (7 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{418 + (2 - 3)}{(69 + 70) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4182 + 3}{6970 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4182 - 3}{6970 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{50796} := \frac{4 + 1 + 8 + 3 - 2}{5 - (07 - 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times (8 + 3) - 2}{5 \times (0 \times 7 + 9) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 1 + 83 - 2}{(5 + 07) \times 9 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 8 \times 3) - 2}{50 + 7 \times 9 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 - 83) \times 2}{(50 - 7 - 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 1 + (8 + 3)^2}{50 + 7 + 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{59760} := \frac{4 + (1 + (8 + (3 - 2)))}{(5 \times (9 + 7)) - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (1 \times (8 - 32))}{5 \times (9 - (7 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((1^8) - 32)}{5 \times (9 + (7 - (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (8 + 3))) - 2}{5 \times ((9 - 7) \times (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 18) - (3^2)}{5 + (9 + (76 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 + (8 \times (3^2)))}{5 \times (9 + (7 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 \times 3))) - 2}{(5 \times (9 + 7)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((18 \times 3) + 2)}{5 \times ((9 - 7)^6 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(41 + 8) \times (3 \times 2)}{(5 + (9 - 7)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + ((1^8) \times 3))^2}{(5 \times (9 - 7)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (1 + ((8 + 3)^2))}{(5 - (9 - 7)) \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{60795} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 83 \times 2}{60 \times (7 + 9) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{70965} := \frac{4 - (1 - 83) \times 2}{(7 \times 09 - 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41839}{50267} := \frac{4 + (18 - 3) \times 9}{50 \times 2 + 67}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41856}{73902} := \frac{(4 + 1 - 8 + 5)^6}{7 \times 3 + 90 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41860}{79235} := \frac{4 + 18 + 6 + 0}{7 + 9 + 2 + 35}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 1 \times 8 + 60}{7 + 9 \times (2 \times 3 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 8 \times 6) + 0}{7 \times (9 \times 2 + 35)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41860}{93275} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8 + 60}{(9 \times 3 + 2 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{63270} := \frac{4 + 1 \times 89 + 5}{6^3 + 2 - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (18 - 9) \times 5}{(6 + 3)^2 - 7 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{67032} := \frac{4 - (1 - (8 + (9 + 5)))}{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 3))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 5}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1^8) + (9 + 5))}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(((4 - 1) \times 8) - 9) \times 5}{6 \times ((7 - (-03)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 5}{(6 \times (7 \times (03))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 - (9 - 5)))}{(6 + (7 - (-03))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 1) \times (8 \times (9 - 5))}{(6 + (7 - (-03)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (1^8)) \times 95}{6 \times (70 + (3 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + (8 + 9)) \times 5)}{(6 \times (7 + (-03)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (8 \times 9))) \times 5}{6 \times ((7 - (-03))^2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((1^8) + 9)) + 5}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (1^{895})}{6 - (7 + (0 - (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + 8) \times (9 \times 5))}{(6^{7-03}) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{70623} &:= \frac{4 - 1 + 8 \times (9 - 5)}{7 \times (06 + 2) + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - 1 + 8 \times 9 - 5}{70 + 6 \times 2^3} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 1) \times 8 + 9) \times 5}{7 \times (062 - 3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{72063} &:= \frac{(41 + 8) \times 95}{7 + 20^{6-3}} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41896}{52370} &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (8 + 9))) \times 6}{5 \times (23 + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (8 - 9)))^6}{5 + (2 + (3 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times 18) + 96}{5 \times (2 \times (3 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 6}{(5 \times 23) - 70} \\
 &:= \frac{(41 \times 8) + 96}{523 + (7 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (((1^8) - 9) \times 6)}{(5 \times (2 - 3)) + 70} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (1 \times (8 - 96))}{5 \times (2 + (3 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (((1 + 8) \times 9) - 6)}{5 \times (2 + (3 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + (8 \times 9)) \times 6)}{5 - (2 - (3^7 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 - (8 - (9 \times 6)))}{(5^2) + (3 \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 - (8 - (9 + 6)))}{5 - (2 - (37 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 9) + 6))}{5 \times ((2^3) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (8 - (9 - 6)))}{5 + (2 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 + 96))}{52 \times (3 + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + ((8 \times 9) + 6))}{(5^2) + 370} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 - (9 - 6)))}{5 \times (2 - (3 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 \times (9 - 6)))}{52 + (3 + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 + (9 - 6)))}{5 \times (2 + (3 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 + 96))}{(5^2) \times (3 \times (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (89 - 6))}{(5 - (2 - 3)) \times 70} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (18 - (9 - 6))}{5 \times ((2^3) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1^{896})}{5^{2^3-7+0}} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (1 - (8 - (9 + 6)))}{52 - (37 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (1 \times (8 \times (9 - 6)))}{5 + (23 + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (1 + (8 + (9 - 6)))}{5 + ((2^3) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (1 + (89 - 6))}{(5 \times (2^3)) + 70} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (18 + (9 \times 6))}{(5 \times (2 + 3)) + 70} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 1896}{5 + 2370} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41902}{63875} &:= \frac{(4 - 1) \times 902}{(63 - 8) \times 75} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41923}{58760} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 92 + 3}{5 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) + 0} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 &:= \frac{41925}{80367} := \frac{(4 + 1 \times 9) \times 25}{(80 + 3 + 6) \times 7} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41952}{76038} &:= \frac{4 + 1 \times 9 + 5 - 2}{7 \times (6 - 03) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 1 - 9 + 52}{76 + 03 + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 9 \times 5) \times 2}{7 + 60 \times (3 + 8)} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41958}{62370} &:= \frac{4 + 1 + (9 - 5) \times 8}{6 \times 2^3 + 7 + 0} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41975}{63802} &:= \frac{(4 + 1 \times 9 + 7) \times 5}{6^3 - 8^{02}} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + 19 + 7) \times 5}{6 \times 38 + 0 \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times 1^9 \times 75}{6 \times 38 \times 02} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 9) + 7 \times 5}{6 \times (3 + 8 \times 02)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 9) \times 75}{6 \times 380 \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times 19 \times 75}{6 \times 38^{02}} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41976}{53280} &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + 97 \times 6)}{(5 + 32) \times 80} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42107}{96538} &:= \frac{4 \times (2 + 10) - 7}{9 \times (6 + 5) + 3 - 8} \\
 & \text{-----}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42108}{76593} := \frac{4 \times (21 + 08)}{76 + 5 \times 9 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42159}{70863} := \frac{4 - 2 + 1 \times 5 \times 9}{7 + 08 \times (6 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(42 + 1 \times 5) \times 9}{708 + 6 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42160}{95387} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 1) \times 60}{9 \times (5^3 + 8 \times 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{65379} := \frac{4 + (2 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}{6 + (5 \times (3 - (7 - 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{42 + (18 - 0)}{6 + (5 + (3 + 79))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4^2) - 1) \times (8 - 0)}{6 - (5 \times ((3 - 7) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (2 \times (1 \times 80))}{(65 - 3) \times (7 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (2 \times 1)) \times 80}{6 + (5 + (3 \times 79))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 2) + 1) \times 80}{(6 + ((5^3) - 7)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (2 - 1)) \times 80}{6 \times ((5^3) - (7 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 2) \times 180}{(6 + ((5 + 3) \times 7)) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{69375} := \frac{4 \times 21 - 8 + 0}{(6 + 9 + 3 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{79365} := \frac{4 \times 21 - 8 + 0}{(7 + 9 - 3) \times (6 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42315}{87906} := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 31 \times 5}{8 + 7 \times 90 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42350}{79618} := \frac{(42 + 3) \times 5 + 0}{7 - (9 - 61) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 2) \times 3 \times 50}{7 + 9 \times 61 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 2 \times 3) \times 5 + 0}{7 + 96 - 1 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42351}{98076} := \frac{4 - 2 + 35 + 1}{9 + 80 - 7 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (23 \times 5 - 1)}{980 + 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42360}{75189} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 3 \times 6) + 0}{7 + 5 \times (18 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 2) \times 3 \times 60}{7 \times 5 \times 18 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42513}{60897} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 5 \times 1 - 3}{60 + (8 - 9) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42579}{83106} := \frac{4 + (25 - 7) \times 9}{8 + 310 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42581}{90376} := \frac{(4^2 + 5) \times (8 - 1)}{90 + 37 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42598}{61370} := \frac{4 + 2 + 5 \times 9 + 8}{6 \times 13 + 7 - 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42630}{89175} := \frac{4 + 2^6 \times 3 + 0}{(89 - 1 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42639}{58017} := \frac{4 + 2 \times 6^3 - 9}{580 + 17}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42687}{95013} := \frac{(4 - 2) \times (6 + 87)}{9 \times (50 - 1 - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42693}{51870} := \frac{(42 - 6) \times 9 - 3}{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 70)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42718}{90365} := \frac{(4 + 2 + 7) \times 18}{(90 + 3 + 6) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42750}{83961} := \frac{(4 \times 2 + 7) \times 50}{8^3 + 961}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42756}{80931} := \frac{4 + 2 \times (7 - 5) \times 6}{80 - 9 \times 3 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (27 - 5 + 6)}{(80 - 9) \times 3 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (2 + (7 - 5) \times 6)}{80 + 9 \times 3 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42768}{50193} := \frac{(4 - 2 + 7) \times 6 \times 8}{501 + 9 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42795}{61830} := \frac{4 - 2 + 7 \times 9 \times 5}{61 \times 8 - 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42803}{57691} := \frac{4 + 2 \times 8 + 03}{5 \times 7 + 6 - 9 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 2)^8 - 03}{5 + 7 \times 6 \times (9 - 1)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42806}{59173} := \frac{4 \times (2+8) - 06}{5-9+17 \times 3} \\ & := \frac{4^2 + 80 + 6}{(5 \times (9-1) + 7) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{4+2 \times 80+6}{(5+9) \times 17-3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42896}{50173} := \frac{4 \times 28 \times (9-6)}{50+1 \times 7^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42813}{56079} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 8 + 1) + 3}{5 \times 6 + 07 \times 9} \\ & := \frac{428+1-3}{560+7-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42813}{67095} := \frac{4+(2+8) \times 13}{6 \times 7 \times (0 \times 9 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42816}{73590} := \frac{4 \times 2^{8+1-6}}{7+3+5 \times 9+0} \\ & := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 8 \times 1^6}{(7-3) \times 5+90} \\ & := \frac{4+2 \times 81-6}{73 \times 5-90} \\ & := \frac{(4+2) \times 81-6}{735+90} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42873}{69150} := \frac{4-2+8+7 \times 3}{6 \times 9+1-5+0} \\ & := \frac{(4+2+8 \times 7) \times 3}{6 \times (9+1) \times 5+0} \\ & := \frac{4^2 \times 87+3}{(6+9) \times 150} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42891}{63075} := \frac{4^2+8+9+1}{(6-3+07) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{4-2-8+91}{(6 \times 3+07) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42908}{76351} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times (9+08)}{(7-6) \times (3^5-1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42930}{58671} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 9 - 3) + 0}{5 \times 8 + 6 \times 7 \times 1} \\ & := \frac{4+29-3+0}{5 \times 8-6+7 \times 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42930}{81567} := \frac{4^2-9+3+0}{(8-1-5) \times 6+7} \\ & := \frac{(4^2-9) \times 30}{8-1+56 \times 7} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (2+93) + 0}{(8-1 \times 5)^6-7} \\ & := \frac{4+29-3+0}{8+1 \times 56-7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42957}{86301} := \frac{(4+2) \times 9+57}{8+6^3-01} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{42968}{53710} := \frac{((4^2)+9) \times 68}{(5^3) \times (7+10)} \\ & := \frac{((4^2)-9) \times (6 \times 8)}{(5+37) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{((4-2)^{9-6})^8}{((5+3)^7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{((4-2)^9)+68}{(5 \times 3)+710} \\ & := \frac{(4-(2-(9 \times 6))) \times 8}{(5+3) \times (7 \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (2 \times (9+6))) - 8}{(5-3) \times (7 \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (2 \times (9-6))) + 8}{(5 \times (3+7)) - 10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(4 \times (2 + (9 + 6))) + 8}{(5 \times (3 \times 7)) - 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (2 + 9)) + (6 \times 8)}{(5 \times (3 \times 7)) + 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (2 + 96)) + 8}{5 \times ((3 + 7) \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (29 + 6)) + 8}{5 \times (37 \times (1 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (29 - 6)) - 8}{5 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4^2) \times (9 - (6 - 8))}{((5 \times 3) + 7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (2 \times 9)) \times (6 \times 8)}{((5^3) + 7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (2^{9-6})) \times 8}{5 \times (3 \times (7 + (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (2 + (9 \times 6))) \times 8}{(53 + 7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (2 + (9 - 6))) \times 8}{5 \times (3 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 2) \times ((9 - 6) \times 8)}{5 \times (37 - (1 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4 - 2) \times (96 + 8)}{(5 + (3 \times 7)) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{4 - ((2 - (9 + 6)) \times 8)}{5 \times (37 - 10)} \\ & := \frac{4 - ((2 - (9 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 + (3 + (7 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 - ((2^9-6) - 8)}{5 - (3 + (7 - 10))} \\ & := \frac{4 - (2 - ((9 \times 6) - 8))}{(5 \times (3 + 7)) + 10} \\ & := \frac{4 - (2 \times (9 \times (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (3 + (7 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 - (2 + (9 \times (6 - 8)))}{5 + (3 + (7 + 10))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (((2 + 9) \times 6) + 8)}{5 \times (3 + (71 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((2 \times (9 + 6)) + 8)}{5 \times (37 + (1 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{4 \times ((2 \times 96) + 8)}{(5^3) \times (7 + (1 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times ((2^{9-6}) + 8)}{((5 \times 3) - 7) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{4 \times ((2 + (9 - 6))^8)}{5^{3+7-1+0}} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (2 - (9 \times (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (3 + (7 + 10))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (2 \times ((9 \times 6) - 8))}{(53 - 7) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (2 \times (9 - (6 - 8)))}{5 \times ((3 \times 7) + (1 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (2 \times (9 + (6 - 8)))}{53 + (7 + 10)} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (2 + (9 + (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (3 + (7 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (29 - (6 - 8))}{5 \times ((3 \times 7) + 10)} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (29 + (6 + 8))}{5 + (3 \times (7 \times 10))} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 \times (9 \times 6)) + 8)}{(5 + (3 + 7)) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 \times 9) - (6 + 8))}{5 - (3 - (7 + (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 \times 96) + 8)}{5 \times (3 \times (7 + 10))} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 \times 96) - 8)}{5 \times (37 + 10)} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2^{9-6}) \times 8)}{(5 \times 3) + (7 \times 10)} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 + (9 + 6)) \times 8)}{(5 \times 37) - 10} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((2 + (9 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 \times (3 + (7 + (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (2 - (9 \times (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (3 - (7 - 10))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (296 - 8)}{5 \times (3 + (7 \times 10))} \\
 := \frac{4 + 2968}{5 + 3710}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43056}{81972} := \frac{4 + (3 + 05) \times 6}{8 + 19 + 72} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43056}{91728} := \frac{4 + 30 - 5 - 6}{9 - 1 + 7^2 - 8} \\
 := \frac{430 + 5 \times 6}{(91 + 7) \times (2 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43065}{72819} := \frac{4 \times 30 - 65}{7 \times 2 \times 8 - 19} \\
 := \frac{(4 + 3 \times 06) \times 5}{7 \times 28 - 1 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43065}{91872} := \frac{(4 - (3 - 0)) \times (6 \times 5)}{(9 - (1 \times (8 - 7)))^2} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 6) + 5))}{(9 - (1 - (8 \times 7))) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times 30) - (6 \times 5)}{(9 + (1 \times 87)) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (30 \times (6 - 5))}{(9 + ((1^8) \times 7))^2} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times 30) + (6 \times 5)}{(9 - 1) \times (8 \times (7 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (30 + (6 \times 5))}{(9 + (1 - 8))^{7+2}} \\
 := \frac{(4^3 + 0) \times (6 \times 5)}{(9 - (1 - (8 \times 7)))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43068}{71295} := \frac{4 + 3 \times 06 \times 8}{7 \times (1 + 29 + 5)} \\
 := \frac{430 + 6 + 8}{7 \times (12 + 9) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43068}{79152} := \frac{4 + 3 \times 06 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times (15 + 2)} \\
 := \frac{430 + 6 + 8}{791 + 5^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43081}{72659} := \frac{4 \times 30 + 81}{(72 - 6) \times 5 + 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43089}{56127} := \frac{4 + 3 \times 089}{5 \times 6 \times 12 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43092}{81567} := \frac{4 + (3 + 09) \times 2}{8 \times 15 - 67} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (3 + 09 + 2)}{(8 + 1) \times (5 + 6) + 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43092}{86751} := \frac{4 \times (3 + 092)}{8 + 6 + 751} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43095}{81627} := \frac{(43 - 09) \times 5}{(8 \times 1 \times 6 - 2) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43120}{86975} := \frac{(43 + 1)^2 + 0}{(86 \times 9 + 7) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43152}{90768} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 15 + 2}{9 \times 07 + 6 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43168}{59072} := \frac{43 - 16 - 8}{(-5 + 9) \times 07 - 2} \\
 := \frac{4 - 3 + (1 + 6) \times 8}{5 \times (9 + 07) - 2} \\
 := \frac{4 + 3 + 1 + 68}{5 + 90 + 7 + 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43168}{79520} := \frac{43 - 16 - 8}{7 + (9 + 5) \times 2 + 0} \\
 := \frac{4^{3+1} + 6 \times 8}{7 \times (9 - 5) \times 20}
 \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43250}{71968} := \frac{(4+3 \times 2) \times 50}{(7+1+96) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43281}{60795} := \frac{43 \times 2 \times 8 - 1}{60 \times (7+9) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43290}{75816} := \frac{43 + 2^9 + 0}{(7-5) \times 81 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43290}{85176} := \frac{43 + 2^9 + 0}{(85-1) \times (7+6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43512}{97608} := \frac{4-3+(5+1)^2}{97-6-08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43512}{97680} := \frac{(4 \times (3+5-1))^2}{(9+7+6) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43516}{92708} := \frac{4+35-16}{9-(2-7) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43560}{87912} := \frac{435+60}{87+912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43560}{91872} := \frac{43 \times 5 + 60}{(9+1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43576}{92180} := \frac{4-3+57-6}{9+21+80}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((3+5) \times (7+6))}{(9+2 \times 1) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43581}{60297} := \frac{4 \times (3-5) + 81}{6-02+97}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43602}{51987} := \frac{4^3 - 6 \times 02}{5 \times (19-8) + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (3+60) \times 2}{5 + (1+9) \times (8+7)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (3+6^{02})}{51+9 \times (8+7)}$$

$$:= \frac{4+3 \times 60 \times 2}{((5+1) \times 9+8) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43602}{97851} := \frac{43 \times (6+02)}{97 \times 8 - 5 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (3^6 + 02)}{9^{7-8+5} + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43659}{71280} := \frac{(4+3)^{6+5-9}}{(7+1+2) \times 8+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+3) \times (65-9)}{(7+1^2) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+3) \times 6 \times (5+9)}{(7-1) \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(43+6) \times (5+9)}{7 \times 1 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+(3+6) \times 5) \times 9}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43675}{82109} := \frac{(4+3+6+7) \times 5}{8+2 \times 10 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43710}{69285} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 7 + 10}{6+(9+2) \times (8+5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43719}{65208} := \frac{4^3 + (7-1) \times 9}{(6+5) \times 2 \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43769}{51208} := \frac{437+69}{5 \times 120-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43802}{57196} := \frac{4+3 \times 80-2}{5 \times (71-9) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43809}{72156} := \frac{(4-3) \times (8-(-09))}{7 \times (2 \times (1-(5-6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4+(38-(-09))}{7 \times (2-(1-(5+6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^3)+(80+9)}{7 \times ((2 \times 15)+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+3) \times (8-(-09))}{(7 \times 2) \times (1-(5-6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (3 \times (8-(-09)))}{7 \times ((2+(1+5)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4+(3+809)}{7 \times ((2 \times (1 \times 5)) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^3)-(8 \times (-09))}{7 \times (2+(1 \times (5 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4-38) \times (-09)}{7 \times (2 \times ((1+5) \times 6))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43810}{92675} := \frac{4 \times (38+1) + 0}{9+(2^6-7) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4+38+10}{9+26+75}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43875}{91260} := \frac{(4+3+8) \times 7-5}{(9-1) \times 26+0}$$

$$:= \frac{4+(3+8)^{7-5}}{(9+1) \times 26+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+3+8) \times 7 \times 5}{91 \times 2 \times 6+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+3+8) \times 75}{9 \times 1 \times 260}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{43928}{70516} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 - 9 \times (2 - 8))}{70 \times 5 + 16} &:= \frac{43 + (9 + (8 - 0))}{6 + (1 + (5 + 72))} &:= \frac{(45 + (-09)) \times 6}{(7 + 32) \times (8 + 1)} \\ & & &:= \frac{(4 \times 50) - 96}{(7 \times (32 - 8)) + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{43956}{71280} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + 9) - 5 - 6}{(7 - 1) \times (2 + 8) + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{45018}{69372} &:= \frac{4 + 50 - 1 + 8}{6 + 9 \times (3 + 7) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (3 + 95) \times 6}{(7 - 1) \times 2 \times 80} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{45103}{69782} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times 10 + 3)}{(6 - 9 + 7) \times 82} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{43980}{61572} &:= \frac{((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 80}{6 \times (1 + (57 - 2))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{45072}{81693} &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (-07))) \times 2}{8 - (1 - ((6 \times 9) - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (3 + 9)) - (8 - 0)}{(6 + (15 + 7)) \times 2} & & \blacktriangleright \frac{45108}{69273} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 10 - 8)}{6 \times 9 - 2 \times 7 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 3) + (98 - 0)}{(6 + (1 \times 5)) \times (7 \times 2)} & & &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 1 + 08)}{6 + 9 - 2 + 73} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (0 - (7^2))))}{81 - (6 - (9 + 3))} & & &:= \frac{(45 - 10) \times 8}{6 + 9^2 + 7^3} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - (-07))^2)}{(81 + 6) \times (9 + 3)} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - (-07)) \times 2)}{8 + (169 - 3)} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{45126}{87309} &:= \frac{4 - (5 - 12) \times 6}{8 \times (7 + 3) + 09} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (-07)))^2}{8 \times (1 + ((6 \times 9) + 3))} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4^{5 \times 0 \times 7 + 2}}{8 - (1 \times (6 - (9 \times 3)))} & & & \blacktriangleright \frac{45129}{73680} &:= \frac{4 + 5 \times 1^2 \times 9}{(7 - 3 + 6) \times 8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{4^{5 + 0 \times 7 - 2}}{(8 \times 16) - (9 + 3)} & & & &:= \frac{(45 + 1)^2 - 9}{(7 + 36) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4^3) - (9 - 80)}{(6 + 15) \times (7 + 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{45096}{73281} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (0 - (9 - 6)))}{7 - (3 - (2 + (8 - 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 3) \times (9 \times 80)}{((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 7)^2} & & &:= \frac{4^{5 - 09 + 6}}{7 + (3 + (2 \times (8 \times 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times (9 \times 80)}{(6 + 1) \times ((5 + 7)^2)} & & &:= \frac{4 + (5 - (0 - (9 + 6)))}{7 + (3 + (28 + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (3 - (9 + 80))}{(6 + (1 \times 57)) \times 2} & & &:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (0 - (9 - 6)))}{7 + (3 \times ((2 \times 8) - 1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 - (39 - 80)}{6 - (15 - 72)} & & &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (-09))) \times 6}{7 + (((3^2) \times 8) - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((3 \times 9) + (8 - 0))}{(6 + (15 - 7))^2} & & &:= \frac{(4^5 + 0) + 96}{7 \times (3 + ((2^8) + 1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times (3 + (9 \times (8 - 0)))}{6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (7 \times 2)))} & & &:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times 36))}{70 - (9 - (2 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((3 + 9) \times (8 - 0))}{(6 - (1 - 5)) \times (7 \times 2)} & & &:= \frac{4 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 6))}{7 - (0 - (9 \times 2 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (3 \times (9 + (8 - 0)))}{6 + (1 + (5 \times (7 \times 2)))} & & &:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 + (3 - 6)))}{7 - (0 - (9 + 28))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 + (39 - (8 - 0))}{6 - (1 + (5 - (7^2)))} & & &:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times 36))}{70 - (9 - (2 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{43 + (9 \times (8 - 0))}{6 + (157 - 2)} & & &:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 \times (3 + 6)))}{70 - (9 - (2 \times 8))} \\ & & & &:= \frac{4 + (51 + 36)}{70 + ((9^2) - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + (13 \times 6)}{70 + (92 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (1 + 36))}{((7 - (-09))^2) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{5-1}) - (3 \times 6)}{(70 \times 9) - (2^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{451 + (3 - 6)}{(7 - (0 - (9^2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{451 + (3 \times 6)}{709 + 28}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times (3 + 8)))}{9 + (0 - (2 - (7 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + (3 + 8)))}{9 - ((0 \times 2) - (7 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + 38))}{(9 \times (0 \times 2)) + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (1 - (3 + 8)))}{(9 - (0 - (2 + 7))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (1 \times (3 - 8)))}{(9 \times (-02)) + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (1 - 38))}{9 \times ((0 \times 2) + (7 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + ((1^3) - 8))}{9 - (0 - (2 + (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (1 - (3 + 8)))}{9 \times (0 + (2 \times (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (1 - 38))}{9 \times (0 + ((2 \times 7) - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - (1^3)) \times 8)}{(90 \times 2) + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 \times 13) - 8)}{(90 - (2 \times 7)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 8))}{90 + (2 + 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 - (3 \times 8)))}{90 + ((2^7) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 - (3 + 8)))}{(9 \times (0 + (2 \times 7))) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 \times (3 - 8)))}{(9^{02}) - (7 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1^3 + 8))}{9 \times (0 - (2 - (7 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + ((1^3) \times 8))}{(90 \times 2) - 76}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (1 - (3 - 8)))}{90 - (2 \times (7 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 138)}{(90 - 2) \times (7 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (51 - (3 \times 8))}{(9 - (0 - 27)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{5+1+3-8}}{9 + (0 - (2 - (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 3)) + 8)}{9 \times ((0 \times 27) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 3)) - 8)}{90 + (2 \times 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - ((1^3)^8))}{90 + (2 - 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 8))}{90 + (2 - (7 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (1 - (3 \times 8)))}{(9 + ((0 \times 2) - 7))^6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (1 - (3 - 8)))}{9 + (0 - (2 + (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (1 - 38))}{90 + (2 \times (7 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (1^3 + 8))}{90 + ((2 \times 7) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 - (3 - 8)))}{(9^{02}) - (7 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1^3 + 8))}{90 - ((2 + 7) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + ((1 + 3) \times 8))}{(9^{02}) + (7 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 - (3 - 8)))}{9 - (0 - (27 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 \times (3 \times 8)))}{((9 \times (02)) - 7) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 \times 38))}{(9^{02}) + (7 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 + (3 + 8)))}{9 - (0 - (27 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 + 38))}{(9 - ((0 \times 2) - 7)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (13 + 8))}{(9 \times (02)) + (7 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + 138)}{(9 + (-02)) \times (7 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (51 + (3 + 8))}{(9 \times (0 + (2 \times 7))) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45138}{90276} := \frac{(((4 \times 5) - 1) \times 3) + 8}{90 - (2 - (7 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 5) + 1) \times (3 + 8)}{(9 - (-02)) \times (7 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 3) + 8}{90 - ((2 \times 7) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 38}{90 + (2 \times (7 + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (1^3))) - 8}{9 - (0 - (2 + (7 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{5-1^3} \times 8}{(9 - (0 - (2 - 7)))^6}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{5-1^3} + 8}{((9^{02}) + 7) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{5+1^3} - 8}{(90^2) + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 38}{9 \times ((0 \times 2) + 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1^3))) \times 8}{90 + ((2 + 7) \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (1 + 38)}{9 \times (0 + (2 + 76))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 138}{9 \times (0 + 276)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 - (3 - 8)))}{9 - (0 - (2 - (7 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times (3 \times 8)))}{90 - (2 + (7 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{45 - (1 - (3 + 8))}{90 + ((2 \times 7) + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 - (1 - 38)}{90 - (2 - 76)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 \times ((1^3) \times 8)}{90 \times ((2 \times 7) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 \times (13 + 8)}{90 \times (27 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 \times 1^{38}}{90^{2-7+6}}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + (1 \times (3 \times 8))}{(9 - (0 - (2 \times 7))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + 138}{90 + 276}$$

$$:= \frac{451 + 38}{902 + 76}$$

$$:= \frac{451 - 38}{902 - 76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45186}{90372} := \frac{((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 8) + 6}{9 - (0 - (3 \times (7^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 8) - 6}{90 + (3 \times (7 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((45 + 1) \times 8) - 6}{(9^{03}) - (7 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (5 \times (1 - 8))) \times 6}{9 \times (0 + (3 + (7^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - 8))) \times 6}{9 \times (0 + (3 + (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 - 8))) - 6}{9 - (0 - (3 + 72))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1^8))) + 6}{(9 - (0 - (3 \times 7))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1^8))) - 6}{9 - (0 - (3 \times (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5) - (1 + (8 - 6))}{(9 \times (0 - (3 - 7))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + (1 + (8 + 6))}{90 - ((3 + 7) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + (18 \times 6)}{(9 - ((0 \times 3) - 7))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1 + 8))) \times 6}{(9 - (-03)) \times (7^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times 1)) \times (8 \times 6)}{(9 - (-03)) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times 1)) \times (8 + 6)}{9 - (0 - (3^{7-2}))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1^8))) \times 6}{9 \times (0 + (3 + (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (1 + (8 - 6))}{9 \times (0 - (3 - (7 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (18 \times 6)}{9 \times (0 + (3 \times 72))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 186}{9 \times (0 + 372)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 5)^{1^8+6}}{9^{0 \times 3 + 7} \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 518) \times 6}{(90 - 3) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{(45 + (1 + 8)) \times 6}{9 \times ((0 \times 3) + 72)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((5 - 18) \times 6)}{90 + (37 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - ((1^8) \times 6))}{(9 - (0 - (3 - 7))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - ((1 + 8) \times 6))}{(90 - 37) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times (8 + 6)))}{9 - (0 - (3 + (7 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(9 \times (0 \times 37)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + (8 \times 6)))}{90 - (3 - (7 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + (8 - 6)))}{9 + ((0 \times 3) - (7 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + 86))}{(90 + (3 - 7)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (1 - (8 + 6)))}{(90 - (3 \times 7)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + ((1 - 8) \times 6))}{((9 - (-03)) \times 7) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (1 - (8 \times 6)))}{(9 - (0 - 37)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (1 - 86))}{(9 - (-03)) \times (7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}{9 \times ((0 - (3 - 7))^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1^{86}))}{9 - (0 - ((3 \times 7) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 - 86))}{(9^{03}) - (7 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(90 + (3 + 7)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1^{86}))}{((9 + (-03)) \times 7) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + ((1^8) \times 6))}{(9 \times (0 + (3 + 7))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (1^{86}))}{9 - (0 - (37 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (1 + (8 \times 6)))}{(9 + (-03)) \times 72}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (1 + (8 + 6)))}{(90 - (3 + 7)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (18 - 6))}{90 - (3 - (7^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 8)) - 6)}{(9 \times (03)) + (7^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (1 + 8)) + 6)}{90 + ((3 + 7) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (1 + 8)) - 6)}{((9 - (-03)) \times 7) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 + 18) \times 6)}{(90 \times 3) + (7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - ((1 - 8) \times 6))}{90 + (3 + (7 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}{9 - (0 - (37 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{9 - ((0 \times 3) - (7 - 2))}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{4 + (5 - (1^{86}))}{90 - (37 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 - (1 - 86))}{(90 - (3 - 7)) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times ((1^8) \times 6))}{((9 \times (03)) + 7) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times ((1^8) + 6))}{9 + (0 - (3 - 72))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{9 - (0 - ((3 \times 7) - 2))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 + (8 - 6)))}{(9 \times (0 - (3 - 7))) + 2} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{9 - ((0 \times 3) - (7^2))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 \times (1^{86}))}{9 \times (0 - (3 - (7 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + ((1^8) \times 6))}{(9 + (-03)) \times (7 - 2)} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + ((1 + 8) \times 6))}{9 \times ((0 \times 3) + (7 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(9 \times (-03)) + (7^2)} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + (1 \times 86))}{90 + ((3 + 7)^2)} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + (1^{86}))}{9 + (0 - (3 - (7 \times 2)))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + (1 + (8 - 6)))}{9 - (0 - (3 \times (7 - 2)))} \\
 := \frac{45 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))}{9 \times (0 + ((3 + 7) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{45 \times (1 + (8 + 6))}{90 \times (3 \times (7 - 2))} \\
 := \frac{45 \times (18 - 6)}{90 \times (3 + (7 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{45 + ((1 + 8) \times 6)}{(90 \times 3) - 72} \\
 := \frac{45 + (18 \times 6)}{90 + (3 \times 72)} \\
 := \frac{45 + 186}{90 + 372}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{451 - (8 - 6)}{(90 \times (3 + 7)) - 2} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45190}{76823} := \frac{4 + (5 + (1^9 + 0))}{7 - (6 - (8 + (2^3)))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1^9 + 0))}{(7 \times 6) + (8 \times (2 - 3))} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times 5) + (1 + (9 - 0))}{(7 - (6 - (8 \times 2))) \times 3} \\
 := \frac{4 + ((5 - 1) \times (9 - 0))}{7 - (6 - ((8^2) + 3))} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 + (1 + 90))}{((7 \times 6) - 8) \times (2 + 3)} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 90}{7 + (6 \times ((8 + 2) \times 3))} \\
 := \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + 90))}{((7 + 68) \times 2) + 3} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (9 - 0)))}{(((7 + 6) \times 8) - 2) \times 3} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1 + (9 - 0)))}{(76 - 8) \times (2 + 3)} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 190)}{76 \times (82 + 3)} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (51 + (9 - 0))}{(76 - 8) \times (2 \times 3)} \\
 := \frac{451 + (9 - 0)}{((7 \times 6) - 8) \times 23} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45230}{76891} := \frac{4 + (5 - (2 - (3 - 0)))}{7 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 1)))} \\
 := \frac{45 + (2 + (3 - 0))}{7 + (6 + (8 \times (9 \times 1)))} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times (5^2)) - 30}{7 + ((6 + 8) \times (9 - 1))} \\
 := \frac{(4 \times (5^2)) + 30}{(7 + 6) \times (8 + (9 \times 1))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (2^3 + 0))}{(7 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)) - 1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(45 \times 2) - 30}{7 + (6 + (89 \times 1))} \\
 := \frac{4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 30)}{(76 - 8) \times (9 \times 1)} \\
 := \frac{(4 + (5 \times 2)) \times 30}{7 \times (6 \times (8 + (9 \times 1)))} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45279}{63180} := \frac{4 \times 5 + 2 \times 7 + 9}{6 \times (3 - 1 + 8) + 0} \\
 := \frac{4^5 \times 2 + 7 + 9}{6^{3-1} \times 80} \\
 := \frac{(45 - 2) \times (7 + 9)}{6 \times (3 - 1) \times 80} \\
 := \frac{4 + 5 + 2^7 \times 9}{(6 + 3) \times 180} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45279}{86301} := \frac{(4 - 5 + 2 \times 7) \times 9}{8 + 6^3 - 01} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45287}{93610} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (28 + 7)}{9 + 361 + 0} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45309}{78261} := \frac{4 - 5 + 3 + 09}{7 + 8 - 2 + 6 \times 1} \\
 := \frac{4 + (5 - 3) \times 09}{7 - 8 \times (2 - 6) - 1} \\
 := \frac{45 - 3 - 09}{7 + (8 + 2) \times (6 - 1)} \\
 := \frac{4 \times (5 - 3 + 09)}{7 + ((8^2) + (6 - 1))} \\
 := \frac{4 - 5 + 309}{7 \times (82 - 6 \times 1)} \\
 \text{▶ } \frac{45312}{86907} := \frac{4^{5-3+1 \times 2}}{8 + 69 \times 07}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\blacktriangleright \frac{45318}{69720} &:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 + (1^8)))}{6 + (9 + (7 - (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{45 \times (3 + (6 - 0))}{89 \times (7 + (1 \times 2))} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((5 \times 3) + 8)) - 1}{(90 + (7 - 6)) \times 2} \\
&:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 \times (1 + 8)))}{6 \times 9 - (7 \times (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{91287} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{91 \times 2 \times 8 - 7} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (3 - 8))) - 1}{9 - (0 - (7 + 62))} \\
&:= \frac{4 + (53 - 18)}{69 - (7 + (2 - 0))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{91728} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times 60))}{91 \times (72 + 8)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times 3)) - (8 + 1)}{(9 - (0 - (7 \times 6))) \times 2} \\
&:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) - 8}{(6 - (9 - 7)) \times 20} &&:= \frac{4 + ((5^3) + (6 - 0))}{9 + (1 + (7 + (2^8)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (3 \times 8))) + 1}{9 \times (0 + ((7 + 6) \times 2))} \\
&:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (3 + 18))}{(6 + (9 - 7)) \times 20} &&:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 360}{9 \times (1 \times 728)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (3 + 8))) + 1}{90 + ((7 \times 6) - 2)} \\
&:= \frac{4 + ((5^3) + (1^8))}{6 + (97 \times (2 - 0))} &&:= \frac{4 + (5 + (36 - 0))}{(9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 28} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (3 - 8))) + 1}{(9 \times (0 \times 76)) + 2} \\
&:= \frac{4 - (5 - (31 \times 8))}{(6 \times (9 \times 7)) + (2 - 0)} &&:= \frac{(45 + 3) \times 60}{91 \times (72 - 8)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + 38)) - 1}{90 + (7 \times (6^2))} \\
&:= \frac{4 \times ((5^3 \times 1) - 8)}{(6^{9-7}) \times 20} &&:= \frac{45 \times 360}{((9 - 1)^{7-2}) - 8} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - 3))^8 \times 1}{((9 - (-07))^6) \times 2} \\
&&&:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times (6 - 0)))}{(9 + 17) \times 28} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - 3)) + 81}{9 - (0 - ((7 + 6)^2))} \\
\hline
\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{81792} &:= \frac{(45 - 3) \times 60}{8 \times (1 + 7 \times 9^2)} &:= \frac{45 \times (3 + (6 - 0))}{91 + 728} &:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + ((3 \times 8) + 1)}{90 \times (7 - 6)^2} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{87129} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{871 + 2^9} &\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{98721} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{9 \times 87 \times 2 + 1} &:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + (3 + (8 \times 1))}{((9 + (-07))^6) - 2} \\
\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{89712} &:= \frac{4 + (536 - 0)}{89 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2)} &&:= \frac{(4^{5-3}) - (8 \times 1)}{(9 + (0 - (7 - 6))) \times 2} \\
&:= \frac{45 \times (36 - 0)}{89 \times ((7 - 1)^2)} &&:= \frac{(4^{5-3}) - (8 + 1)}{9 + (0 - (7 - (6 \times 2)))} \\
&:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 360}{8 + ((9 + 71)^2)} &&:= \frac{(4^{5-3}) + (8 + 1)}{90 - ((7 \times 6) - 2)} \\
&:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 + (6 - 0)))}{89 \times (7 - (1 + 2))} &\blacktriangleright \frac{45381}{90762} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) - 3) \times 8) - 1}{90(7 - (6 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + 3)) \times (8 \times 1)}{(9 - (-07)) \times (6 \times 2)} \\
&:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (36 - 0))}{89 \times ((7 + 1) \times 2)} &&:= \frac{((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 8) + 1}{90 - (7 \times (6 + 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + 3)) \times (8 - 1)}{90 + (76 + 2)} \\
&:= \frac{45 + (3 \times 60)}{89 \times (7 - (1 \times 2))} &&:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8)) - 1}{(90 - 76)^2} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (3 + (8 - 1))}{90 \times ((7 - 6) \times 2)} \\
&:= \frac{4 + (5 + (36 - 0))}{8 + (9 \times (7 + (1 \times 2)))} &&:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times 38) + 1}{(9 \times (0 + 76)) + 2} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (38 + 1)}{9 \times (0 + (76 + 2))} \\
&:= \frac{(45 + 3) \times 60}{89 \times ((7 + 1)^2)} &&:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times 38) - 1}{(9 \times (0 + 76)) - 2} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (38 - 1)}{9 \times (0 + (76 - 2))} \\
&:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times (6 - 0)))}{89 \times (7 + (1^2))} &&:= \frac{(4 - (5 - 3)) \times 81}{9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6^2))} &:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times 381}{9 \times (0 + 762)}
\end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{(45 \times (3+8)) + 1}{(9 - (-07)) \times 62}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (3 + (8 \times 1)))}{(9 - (-07)) \times (6 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 \times 81))}{9 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 + 2)))}$
$:= \frac{(45 \times 3) - (8 + 1)}{9 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (53 - (8 \times 1))}{9 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) - 2))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 1)))}{9 + (0 - (7 - (6^2)))}$
$:= \frac{(45 - 3) \times (8 + 1)}{9 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (53 + (8 + 1))}{((90 - 7) \times 6) - 2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (38 \times 1))}{((9 - (-07)) \times 6) - 2}$
$:= \frac{4 - ((5 \times (3 - 8)) + 1)}{(9 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (((5 + 3) \times 8) + 1)}{((9 \times (07)) + 6) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (38 + 1))}{(90 - (7 \times 6)) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - ((3 \times 8) - 1))}{(9 - (0 - (7 + 6))) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (((5 + 3) \times 8) - 1)}{90 + ((7 \times 6) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (38 - 1))}{90 + ((7 - 6) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 \times 1)))}{90 - ((7 \times 6) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times (3 + 8)) - 1)}{90 + ((7 + 6) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (53 - (8 \times 1))}{((9 - (-07)) \times 6) + 2}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 + 1)))}{9 - (0 - (7 + (6^2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times 3) - (8 - 1))}{9 - (0 - (7 + (6 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (53 - (8 - 1))}{(9 - (0 - (7 - 6)))^2}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 \times 81))}{(9 - (0 - (7 + 6)))^2}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5^3) - (8 \times 1))}{90 + (76 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{45 - (38 + 1)}{9 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 2)))}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 + (8 \times 1)))}{9 - (0 - (7 + (6 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5 - 3) \times (8 - 1))}{9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 - 2))}$	$:= \frac{45 \times (3 + (8 \times 1))}{90 \times (7 + (6 - 2))}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (3 + (8 - 1)))}{9 \times ((0 \times 76) + 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5 - 3) \times 81)}{(90 + 76) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{45 \times (3 + 81)}{90 \times (7 \times (6 \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (3 - (8 \times 1)))}{9 - (0 - (7 - (6 + 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((5 - 3)^{8-1})}{(90 + (7 \times 6)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{45 + (3 + (8 + 1))}{((9 \times (07)) - 6) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (3 - (8 - 1)))}{9 + (0 - (7 - (6 - 2)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (3 - (8 \times 1)))}{9 - (0 - (7 + (6 \times 2)))}$	$:= \frac{45 + (38 - 1)}{90 + (76 - 2)}$
$:= \frac{4 - (5 + (3 - 81))}{(90 - (7 + 6)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (3 - (8 + 1)))}{(9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{45 + 381}{90 + 762}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 + 3) \times (8 + 1))}{(9 - (-07)) \times (6^2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (3 - 81))}{90 + (7 \times (6 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{4538 + 1}{9076 + 2}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - 3) \times (8 + 1))}{((9 + (-07)) \times 6)^2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (3 + (8 \times 1)))}{90 + (7 \times (6 - 2))}$	$:= \frac{4538 - 1}{9076 - 2}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - 3)^{8+1})}{((9 + (-07))6)^2}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (3 + (8 - 1)))}{9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 2))}$	
$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (3 - (8 + 1)))}{90 - ((7 - 6) \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (38 \times 1))}{(90 + 7) \times (6 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45612}{83079} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 6 + 12)}{8 + 307 - 9}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (3 - (8 - 1)))}{(9 + (-07)) \times (6^2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + ((3 \times 8) - 1))}{9 + (0 - (7 - 62))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 5 \times (6 + 1) \times 2}{8^3 + 07 - 9}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (3 - 81))}{(90 - 7) \times (6 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 - (8 - 1)))}{9 + (0 - (7 - (6 + 2)))}$	
$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (3 \times (8 + 1)))}{9 - 07^{6+2}}$	$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 \times (8 \times 1)))}{((9 + (-07))6) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45621}{73980} := \frac{4 \times 56 - 2 \times 1}{7^3 + 9 + 8 + 0}$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (56 \times 2 - 1)}{(7 + 3) \times 9 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + 6 - 2) + 1}{7 - 3 \times 9 + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45621}{93708} := \frac{4 \times (5 + 6 - 2) + 1}{(9 + 3) \times 7 - 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45627}{81039} := \frac{4 + (5 + 6 - 2) \times 7}{8 \times 10 + 39}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{72891} := \frac{(4 \times 5 + 6) \times 30}{7 \times 2 \times 89 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{91728} := \frac{(45 - 6) \times 30}{(91 - 7) \times 28}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5 + 6) \times 30}{(91 + 7) \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{92781} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (6 - 3) + 0}{9 + 2 \times 7 \times 8 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 56 + 30}{(9 + 2 \times 7) \times 8 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{60192} := \frac{457 - 3 + 8}{601 + 9 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{60291} := \frac{4 + 5 + 7 \times 3 - 8}{60 \times 2 - 91}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + 7^3 + 8}{(60 - 2) \times 9 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(45 + 7 + 3) \times 8}{(60 - 2) \times (9 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - 7 \times 3) \times 8}{6 \times 029 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{92610} := \frac{4 + (57 + 3) \times 8}{(92 + 6) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45792}{80136} := \frac{((4 - (5 - 7)) \times 9)^2}{(8 + (-01)) \times (3^6)}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 5) - (7 + 9)) \times 2}{8 - ((0 \times 13) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times 2}{80 + (1 \times (3 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (7 - 9)))^2}{(8 + (-01)) \times 36}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 57) + 92}{80 \times (13 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 2)}{(80 + (1 + 3)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) + 2)}{((8 - (-01)) \times 3) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) - 2)}{(8 \times (-01)) + 36}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times 2))}{(8^{-01+3}) + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (7 \times (9 - 2)))}{80 + (1 - (3 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (7 - (9 + 2)))}{(8 + (0 - (1^3))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 \times (7 - (9 - 2)))}{8 + (0 - (1^{36}))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 2)}{(8 \times (0 + 13)) - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 - (7 - (9 + 2)))}{(8 + (-01)) \times (3 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 2))}{(80 - (1 \times 3)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times 7) - (9 - 2))}{8 \times (0 + (13 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (57 + (9 + 2))}{(8 - (0 - 13)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{457 + (9 + 2)}{801 + (3 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45810}{73296} := \frac{(4 - (5 - 8)) \times 10}{7 \times (3 - (2 - (9 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) - 10}{(7 + (3 \times (2 + 9))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (5 - 8)) \times 10}{7 + (3 + (2 \times (9 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5) \times (8 \times 10)}{(7 + 3 + 2) \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{(45 \times 8) - 10}{(7 + 3) \times (2 + (9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (5 - (81 - 0))}{(7 \times 32) - 96}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 \times 8) + 10)}{(7 \times 32) + 96}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 \times 8) - 10)}{(7 - (3 + 2)) \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (8 - (1 - 0)))}{(7 - 3) \times (2 + (9 \times 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 - 0)))}{(7 + (32 + 9)) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (8 + 10))}{(7 - (3 - 2)) \times 96}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (81 - 0))}{(((7 \times 3)^2) - 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((5 \times 8) + (1 - 0))}{73 + (2 - (9 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{45 \times (8 - (1 - 0))}{7 \times (3 \times ((2 \times 9) + 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{45 \times (8 + (1 - 0))}{(7 + 3 + 2) \times (9 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + (8 \times 10)}{(73 \times 2) + (9 \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45902}{87136} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (9 + 02)}{8 \times (7 + 13 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45906}{72138} := \frac{4 - (5 - (9 - (-06)))}{(7 \times (2 \times (1^3))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 5) + (9 - (-06))}{7 + (2 \times (1 \times (3 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{45 - (9 + (-06))}{7 + (21 + 38)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 \times (9 - (0 \times 6)))}{7 \times (2 + (1^3 + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 - (9 \times (-06)))}{(7 + (2 \times 1)) \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^5) + (90 + 6)}{(7 + 213) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (5 + (90 + 6))}{(7 \times 2 + 1) \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (9 - (0 \times 6)))}{(7 + (2 - (1 - 3))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((5 - (9 - 0)) \times 6)}{7 - (2 - (1 + 38))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((5 + (9 - 0)) \times 6)}{((7^2) - 1) \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45907}{82316} := \frac{4 + 5^{9-07}}{8^2 - (3 - 1) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45927}{83106} := \frac{(4 - 5 + 9 - 2) \times 7}{83 - 1 - 06}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 5 + 92 - 7}{8 \times (3 + 10 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + 9 \times (2 + 7)}{(8 + 3 \times 10) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 5 + 9)^2 \times 7}{8 + (3 + 1)^{06}}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 59) \times 27}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45927}{83160} := \frac{45 + 927}{(8 + 3) \times 160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45936}{71280} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (9 + 3) - 6}{7 + 1 + 2 + 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45936}{87120} := \frac{4 \times 5 - 9 + 3 \times 6}{8 \times 7 - 1^{20}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 5 \times (9 + 3) - 6}{(8 \times 7 - 1) \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45960}{71238} := \frac{4 + 5 - 9 + 60}{71 + 2 \times (3 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{4^5 + 96 + 0}{((7 - 1) \times 2)^3 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 5 \times 9 - 60}{(7 - 1) \times (23 + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45960}{78132} := \frac{45 - 9 - 6 + 0}{7 \times (8 - 1^3) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 5 - 9 + 60}{78 + 1 + 3 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times 9 + 60)}{7 \times (8 \times 13 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45961}{80237} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (9 - 6) - 1}{80 + 2 + 3 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46023}{58719} := \frac{4 \times (6 + 02) - 3}{5 \times 8 + 7 - 1 - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 60 + 23}{5 + 87 + 19}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 60 - 2 \times 3}{5 \times (8 + 7) - 1^9}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 602 + 3}{58 + 719}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46029}{81753} := \frac{4 \times 6 + 02^9}{8 \times (1 - 7 + 5^3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46031}{92785} := \frac{(4 + 60) \times 3 - 1}{(92 - 7 - 8) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46035}{71982} := \frac{4 \times 60 + 35}{(7 - 1) \times 9 \times 8 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46053}{71982} := \frac{4 \times 60 - 5 + 3}{(71 - 9) \times (8 - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46137}{89250} := \frac{4 + 6 + 1 \times 3^7}{(8 + 9) \times 250}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46152}{98073} := \frac{4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 2)))}{9 + (8 - (0 \times 73))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (1 + (5^2)))}{(9 + (8 - (0 \times 7))) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 - 2)))}{9 - ((8 \times (-07)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5 - 2)))}{9 + (80 - (7 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 + 2)))}{98 - (0 - (7 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5 + 2)))}{98 - (0 - (7 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 - (1 - 5)) \times 2)}{(9 + (8 - 0)) \times (7 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5^2)))}{9 - (80 - (7^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{(9 + (8 - 0)) \times (7 \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{52839} := \frac{4 \times (6 - 1) + 70}{5 + 2 + 8 \times (3 + 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 6 + 170}{5^2 \times 8 - 3 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{92853} := \frac{4 \times (6 - 1) + 70}{(9 - 2) \times 8 + 5^3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 6 + 170}{(9^2 - 8) \times 5 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{98325} := \frac{46 + 1 + 7 + 0}{(9 + 8 + 3 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (61 - 7) + 0}{(98 - 3 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(46 - 1) \times (8 - 5)}{9 \times (23 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 - (1 - (8 - 5)))}{9 + ((2^3) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((6 \times (1 - 8)) + 5)}{92 - (3 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((6 \times (1 - 8)) + 5)}{92 - (3 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 - (1 \times (8 - 5)))}{(9^2) + (3 - 70)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46185}{92370} := \frac{(((4 \times 6) - 1) \times 8) + 5}{9 \times (2 \times (3 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - ((1^8) + 5))}{9 - ((2^3) - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (1 \times (8 - 5)))}{9 - (2 - (37 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 6) + (1^8)) \times 5}{(9^2) \times 3 + (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (1 \times (8 - 5)))}{(9 \times (2^3)) - 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1 - (8 - 5)))}{9 - ((2 - 3) \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + (6 - 1)) \times 8) + 5}{(9^2) + (3 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (1 + (8 \times 5)))}{9 + (2 - (3 - 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1 \times (8 - 5)))}{((9 + 2) \times 3) - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + 6) \times 18) - 5}{(9 - 2)^3 + (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 + (1 - (8 \times 5)))}{9 - (2 + (3 - 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1^{85}))}{9 + ((2 \times 3) + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + 61) \times 8) + 5}{(9 + (2 \times 3)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(9 + (2 - 3)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1 + (8 \times 5)))}{9 + (23 + 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (1 \times 8))) \times 5}{(9^2) - (3 \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 5))}{(9 + 23) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1 + (8 - 5)))}{9 - (2 - (3 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (1 + 8))) \times 5}{(9 - (2^3)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (1^{85}))}{((9 + 2) \times 3) + (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (18 \times 5))}{(9 \times 23) - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (6 - 18))^5}{(9 + (2 - 3))^7 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1 \times (8 - 5)))}{9 \times (23 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (61 - (8 - 5))}{(9 \times (2 \times 3)) + 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times 1)) + (8 - 5)}{9 \times (2 - (3 - (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1^{85}))}{9 + (2 + (37 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (61 + (8 \times 5))}{(9 - (2 \times 3)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (1^8))) - 5}{(9 \times (2 + 3)) - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + ((1^8) \times 5))}{92 + (3 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{46 - (1 + (8 - 5))}{9 + (2 + (3 + 70))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 6) - (1 - (8 - 5))}{(9 \times (2 + 3)) + (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + ((1^8) + 5))}{92 - (3 - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{46 + (1 \times (8 + 5))}{(9^2) + (37 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 6) + (18 \times 5)}{9 \times 2 + (3 \times 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 - (8 - 5)))}{9 + (2 + (3 \times (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{461 - (8 - 5)}{923 - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 61) - (8 + 5)}{92 + 370}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1^{85}))}{9 - (23 - 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 - 8))) \times 5}{9 + (23 \times (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (8 - 5)))}{9 - (2 - (3 + 70))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46190}{78523} := \frac{4 + (6 \times (1^9 + 0))}{7 - (8 + (5 - 23))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 \times 8))) \times 5}{9 \times (2 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((6 \times 18) - 5)}{(9 \times 23) + (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (1^9 + 0))}{7 + ((8 \times (5 - 2)) + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (1^8))) \times 5}{(9 + 2) \times (3 + (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(9^2) - (3 - 70)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 \times (9 - 0)))}{(7 \times (8 + (5 + 2))) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 + 18)) \times 5}{(9 - (2 + 3)) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 - ((1^8) \times 5))}{9 + ((2^3) - (7 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 - 1)) + 90}{7 + ((8 + 52) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 6) \times (1 - 85)}{((9 - 2)^3) - (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 - (1 - (8 \times 5)))}{(9 + (2 + 3)) \times (7 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 - 0)}{(7 - (8 - 52)) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times ((6-1) \times (9-0))}{7 + ((8+5) \times 23)} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1 + (9-0)))}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (2^3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46197}{82305} & := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 1 + 9 \times 7}{(8+23) \times 05} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46215}{70389} & := \frac{(4+6+2+1) \times 5}{7+03+89} \\ & := \frac{4^{6-2} - 1 + 5}{7+0389} \\ & := \frac{(46 \times 2 - 1) \times 5}{7 \times (03+8) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46230}{71958} & := \frac{46 \times (2+3) + 0}{7 \times (1+9) \times 5 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46230}{78591} & := \frac{4 \times (6 + (2 - (3-0)))}{7 + ((8-5) \times (9 \times 1))} \\ & := \frac{4 - (6 - (2 + 30))}{(7 \times 8) + (5 - (9 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{(4+6) \times (2 + (3-0))}{7 - (8 + (5 - 91))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((6 \times 2) + (3-0))}{7 + (85 + (9 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{4 + (6 + (2 \times 30))}{7 + (8 \times (5 + (9 \times 1)))} \\ & := \frac{(4+6) \times (2^3 + 0)}{78 + (59 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{4 + (6 + 230)}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (9 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{((4+6)^2) \times (3-0)}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (9 + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46275}{98103} := \frac{4 - 6 + 2 + 75}{9 \times (8 + 10) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46305}{91287} := \frac{(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times (2 \times 8 + 7)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46310}{59782} & := \frac{4 \times 6 + 31 + 0}{5 - 9 - 7 + 82} \\ & := \frac{4 + 6^3 \times 1 + 0}{59 + (7 + 8)^2} \\ & := \frac{(4+6)^3 - 10}{5 \times (9-7)^8 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46312}{57890} & := \frac{4 \times ((6^{3-1}) \times 2)}{(5 + (7 - 8)) \times 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((6^{3-1}) + 2)}{(5 \times (7 \times 8)) - 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((6+3) \times 12)}{(5 - (7 - 8)) \times 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((6+31) \times 2)}{(5 \times (7 \times 8)) + 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 - (3 - (1 + 2)))}{5 \times (7 + (8 - (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 - (3 \times (1^2)))}{5 - (7 - (8 + (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 \times ((3+1)^2))}{5 \times (7 + (89 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (3 + (1^2)))}{5 \times (7 + (8 + (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6^{3-1^2})}{(5 + (7 + 8)) \times (9 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 + ((3+1)^2))}{5 + (7 + (8 + 90))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 + (3 - (1^2)))}{5 \times (7 - (8 - (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 + (3 \times (1 + 2)))}{(5 \times (7 + 8)) + 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (6 + (3 + 12))}{((5 + 7) \times 8) + (9 - 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times (63 - (1 + 2))}{(5 \times 78) - 90} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (63 + (1 \times 2))}{5 \times ((7 \times 8) + (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4^{6-3 \times 1^2}}{5 - (7 + (8 - 90))} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((6 \times 31) - 2)}{5 \times ((7 \times 8) - (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((6^{3-1}) \times 2)}{5 - ((7 - 8) \times 90)} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((6 + (3 - 1))^2)}{(5 \times (7 - 8)) + 90} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((6 + 3) \times 12)}{5 + ((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + 6312}{5 + 7890} \\ & := \frac{46 \times (3 + (1 + 2))}{5 \times (78 - (9 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46315}{87920} := \frac{4^{6-3 \times 1} - 5}{8 \times (7 + 9 - 2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46320}{97851} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times 3 + 2) + 0}{((9 - 7) \times 85) - 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(4+6) \times 32 + 0}{(9 \times ((7+8) \times 5)) + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46325}{87091} & := \frac{4 - 6 + 32 - 5}{8 \times 7 - 09 \times 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46328}{57910} & := \frac{((4 \times 6) + 3) \times 28}{(5 \times 7) + 910} \\ & := \frac{((4^{6-3}) + 2) \times 8}{(57 + 9) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{((4 + (6 - 3))^2) \times 8}{5 \times (7 + (91 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (3^2))) \times 8}{(5 - (7 - 9)) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((6^3) - 2)) + 8}{(5 + 7) \times (9 \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3^2))) + 8}{5 \times (7 \times (9 - (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3^2))) - 8}{((5 \times 7) - 9) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3 - 2))) + 8}{5 \times (7 - (9 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3^2))) + 8}{5 \times (7 + (9 + (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (63 - 2)) + 8}{5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 63) + 28}{5 \times (7 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4^6 \times (3 - 2)) + 8}{57 \times (9 \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(4^{6-3}) \times (2 + 8)}{5 \times ((7 + 9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((6 - 3)^2)) \times 8}{5 \times (7 + (9 + 10))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (6 - (3 - 2))) \times 8}{(5 \times (7 + 9)) + 10} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{5 \times (79 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (3^2))) \times 8}{579 + (1 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{4 - ((6 - 32) \times 8)}{5 \times ((7 \times 9) - 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (6 + (3 \times (2 - 8)))}{5 + (7 + (9 - (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (((6 + 3)^2) + 8)}{5 \times (79 + 10)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 \times (3^2)) + 8)}{5 \times ((7 \times 9) - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 + (3 \times 2)) \times 8)}{(57 - 9) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 + 3 + 2) \times 8)}{((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 + (3 - 2))^8)}{5 \times (7^{9-1+0})} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 - ((3^2) - 8))}{5 - ((7 - 9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (3 - (2 + 8)))}{57 + (9 - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (3 \times (2 - 8)))}{(5 + 7) \times (9 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (3 + (2 - 8)))}{(5 \times 7) + (9 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 \times 8)))}{57 \times (9 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 + 8)))}{5 \times (79 - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6^{3^2-8})}{5 \times (7 + (9 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (3 - (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (7 + (9 - (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (3 + (2 \times 8)))}{(5 \times 7) + (9 \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (63 - (2 - 8))}{5 \times (79 - 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (63 \times (2 + 8))}{5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 10))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (63 + (2 \times 8))}{5 \times (79 \times (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{4^{6+3 \times 2-8}}{5 \times ((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4^{6+3+2-8}}{5 \times (7 + (9 \times (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (((6 \times 3) - 2) \times 8)}{5 + ((7 + 9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((6 + 32) \times 8)}{(5 \times 79) - 10} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8)))}{5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 10)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (3 \times 28))}{5 + (7 \times (9 \times 10))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (32 + 8))}{(5 \times (7 \times 9)) - 10} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 6328}{5 + 7910} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46389}{72051} &:= \frac{4^{6-3} - 8 - 9}{72 - ((0 \times 5) - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times ((3 \times 8) - 9))}{(7 \times 20) + (5 + 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46389}{75012} &:= \frac{4^{6-3} - 8 - 9}{75 + 01^2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times (3 \times 8 - 9)}{(75 + 01) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46398}{50172} &:= \frac{4 - 6 \times (3 - 9 \times 8)}{501 - 7^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46398}{72150} &:= \frac{4 - 6 \times (3 - 9 \times 8)}{(7 \times 2 - 1) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46501}{73892} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 + 50 - 1}{(7 + 3 \times (8 + 9)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 + 501)}{7 \times ((3 \times 8) + 92)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46512}{83790} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (5 + 1) - 2)}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46593}{78120} := \frac{4 \times 65 - 93}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 65 + 9^3}{7 \times 8 \times 1 \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4^6 + 5 - 93}{7 \times 8 \times 120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46710}{52938} := \frac{4 - 6 + 7 + 10}{5 - 2 + 9 - 3 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 6 - 7) \times 10}{5 - (2 - 9) \times 3 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 7 - 1 + 0}{5 - 2 + (9 - 3) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 6) \times (7 - 1) + 0}{5 \times 2 \times (9 - 3) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 671 + 0}{5 + (2 + 93) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 6 + 710}{(5 + 29) \times 3 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46712}{58390} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times (7 \times 1))) \times 2}{(5 \times (8 - 3)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6 + 7 - 1)) \times 2}{5 + (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (71 \times 2))}{5 \times (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (((6 \times 7) + 1) \times 2)}{(5 \times 8) + 390}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 \times 7) + (1 + 2))}{5 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (7 - (1 + 2)))}{5 \times (8 + (3 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times ((7 + 1) \times 2))}{5 \times (8 \times (3 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times ((7 - 1)^2))}{5 \times (8 \times (3 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1^2)))}{(5 \times (8 \times 3)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times (7 + 12))}{5 \times ((8 \times 3) + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + ((7 - 1) \times 2))}{5 - (8 - (3 + 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (7 \times (1 \times 2)))}{5 + (8 - (3 - 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (7 + (1 \times 2)))}{5 \times ((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (7 + (1^2)))}{5 \times (8 - (3 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (67 - (1 \times 2))}{(5 \times 83) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (7 - (1^2)))}{5 + ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (7 - (1^2)))}{5 + ((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (7 \times (1 \times 2)))}{(5 \times (8 \times 3)) - 90}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (7 + (1 + 2)))}{5^{8+3-9+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (67 - (1 + 2))}{58 + (3 \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 6712}{5 + 8390}$$

$$:= \frac{46 \times (7 + (1^2))}{5 \times (83 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{46 + (71 \times 2)}{5 \times (8 + (39 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46719}{83520} := \frac{46 + 7 \times 19}{(8 + 3 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46728}{50193} := \frac{4 \times (6 + 7 \times 2 \times 8)}{501 + 9 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46731}{82095} := \frac{46 - 7 - 3 + 1}{8 \times 20 - 95}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 67 + 3 \times 1}{8 + 2 \times 09 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46759}{81320} := \frac{4 \times (6 + 7 - 5) - 9}{8 \times 1 \times (3 + 2) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 6) \times 7 + 5 \times 9}{(8 - 1 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{46 \times (7 + 5 + 9)}{(81 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{46 \times (7 \times 5 - 9)}{8 \times (13 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{46 \times (7 + 5 - 9)}{(8 + 1 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 6 \times (7 - 5 - 9)}{8 \times (1 + 3^2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{53901} := \frac{4 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 2)}{53 - (9 \times (0 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 2)}{53 \times (9 + (-01))}$$

$$:= \frac{46 \times (7 + 82)}{53 \times (90 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 2}{53 \times (9 \times 01)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (78 - 2))}{53 \times (9 - (-01))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 2)))}{(5 \times 3) + (90 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{46 + 782}{53 + 901}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{90513} := \frac{4 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 2}{90 - 5 + 1 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{91530} := \frac{4 + (6 + (7 + (8 - 2)))}{9 + (1 + (5 + 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 2)}{(9 - (1 + 5)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (7 + (8^2)))}{9 + (1 + (5^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 2}{9 \times ((1^5) \times 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+6) \times (7+(8 \times 2))}{(9+(1+5)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+(6 \times 7)) \times (8-2)}{9+(1+530)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((6 \times (7+8)) + 2)}{(9+15) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{467+(8 \times 2)}{915+30}$$

$$:= \frac{46+782}{9 \times ((1+5) \times 30)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46793}{51280} := \frac{46+7+93}{(5-1-2) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{4+6 \times (7+9) \times 3}{(5-1^2) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{4+6 \times 7+9 \times 3}{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 8+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+6+7 \times 9) \times 3}{(5-1 \times 2) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6+7 \times 93)}{(5+1)^2 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46795}{82130} := \frac{4-(6-7) \times 9 \times 5}{82+1+3+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46827}{50193} := \frac{468-2+7}{501+9-3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46851}{93702} := \frac{((4+(6-8)) \times 5) - 1}{(9 \times 3) - (7 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4+68) \times 5) + 1}{(9^3) - (7 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((46-8) \times 5) - 1}{9 \times (3 \times (7 \times (02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times ((6 \times 8) + 5)) - 1}{(9-3) \times 70 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (8-5))) + 1}{9 - (3 - (70 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (8-5))) - 1}{93 + (7^{02})}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8-5))) + 1}{9 - (3 - (70-2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6+8)) - 51}{(9+(3-(7-0))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6-8)) + 51}{93 - (7 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 6) + (8 - (5 \times 1))}{(9-3) \times (7 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+(6+8)) \times (5 \times 1)}{9 \times ((3+(7-0)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+(6+8)) \times 51}{9 \times (3 \times (70-2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+6) \times (8 - (5+1))}{((9-3) \times (7-0)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+6) \times (85-1)}{(9+3) \times (70 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4+6)^{8-5-1}}{(93+(7-0)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+68) \times (5+1)}{(9+3) \times (70+2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(46 \times 8) - (5+1)}{(9^3) - (7 + (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{(46 \times 8) + 51}{(9+3) \times 70 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (((6-8) \times 5) - 1)}{9 + (3 \times (7 - (0 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - ((8 \times 5) + 1))}{9 - (3 - (70 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{(9 - (3 + 7)) \times (-02)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 \times 1)))}{(9 \times 3) + (7^{02})}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 + 1)))}{(9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 - 1)))}{(9 + (3 \times (7 - 0))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{(9 \times 3) - (7 + (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (8 + (5 - 1)))}{9 - (3 + (7 \times (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 - (85 + 1))}{(9+3) \times (7 \times (02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (6 + (8 - 51))}{((9+3) \times (7-0)) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (3 \times (7 + (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times ((8 \times 5) - 1))}{9 \times ((3 \times 70) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 \times (3 + (7 + (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (8 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (3 + (70 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (8 \times (5 + 1)))}{(9-3) \times (70+2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (8 \times 51))}{9 \times (370 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (3 + (70 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (85 + 1))}{(9^3) + (7 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (85 - 1))}{(9^3) - (7 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{6-8+5-1}}{9 + ((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((6 \times (8 - 5)) - 1)}{(9 - 3) \times (7 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((6^{8-5}) - 1)}{(9 + (3 \times 70)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 - (8 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (3 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (37 + (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (8 - (5 - 1)))}{(9 - 37) \times (-02)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{(9 + (3 + 70)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + ((8 \times 5) + 1))}{93 + (7 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + ((8 \times 5) - 1))}{93 + (7 + (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (3 - (7 \times (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + ((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 \times (5 \times 1)))}{93 + (7 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 \times (5 - 1)))}{9 + (3 + (70 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 + (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (37 - (0 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (6 + (8 + (5 + 1)))}{9 + (37 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (68 + (5 + 1))}{9 + (3 \times (7^{02}))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (685 \times 1)}{9 + (37^{02})}$$

$$:= \frac{46 - (8 - (5 + 1))}{(9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{46 - (8 + (5 - 1))}{((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{46 + (8 \times (5 \times 1))}{(93 - (7 - 0)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{46 + (8 - 51)}{9 - (3 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4685 + 1}{9370 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4685 - 1}{9370 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46872}{90153} := \frac{4 \times (6 + 8 \times 7) \times 2}{901 + 53}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 \times 8 + 7 \times 2)}{9 \times 01 \times 53}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46893}{50127} := \frac{4 + 6 - 8 + 9 \times 3}{5 - 01 + 27}$$

$$:= \frac{(46 - 8 - 9) \times 3}{50 \times 1 \times 2 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46893}{50721} := \frac{4 - 6 + (8 + 9) \times 3}{5 + 07^2 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 6 - 8 - 9)^3}{50 \times 7 + 21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46920}{73185} := \frac{4 \times 69 \times 2 + 0}{7 \times 3 \times (1 + 8 \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46970}{81235} := \frac{(4 - 6) \times (9 - 70)}{8 \times (1 + 2)^3 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46971}{58023} := \frac{4 + 6 \times 9 - 7 \times 1}{(5 + 8 \times 02) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 9) + 7 + 1}{5 + 80 + 2 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{469 + 7 \times 1}{580 + 2^3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (6 - 9 + 7) + 1}{5 + 8 + 02^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47016}{52893} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (-01)))^6}{(5 - 2) \times ((8^9) \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 70) - 16}{5 + (289 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (7 - (-01))) \times 6}{((5 \times 2) + (8 + 9)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (7 - 0)) \times 16}{(5 + 28) \times (9 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 - (-01)) \times 6)}{(5 + (2 + (8 - 9)))^3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (0 - (1^6)))}{5 + ((2 \times (8 + 9)) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 + 6)))}{(5 \times (2 - 8)) + 93}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 - 6)))}{5 + (2^{8-9+3})}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 \times 6)))}{5 + (2 \times (89 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (0 - (1^6)))}{5 + (2 + (8 + (9 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 6)))}{5 - (2 - ((8 + 9) \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (70 - (1 \times 6))}{(5 + (2 + 89)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (70 + (1 \times 6))}{((5^2) + 89) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{7+01-6}}{(5 \times (2 - (8 - 9))) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((7 + (-01)) \times 6)}{5 + (2 \times (8 + (9 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (70 + (1 \times 6))}{(5 + (2 + 8)) \times (9 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{470 - (1 \times 6)}{528 - (9 - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47025}{83619} := \frac{(4 + 7) \times 025}{83 \times 6 \times 1 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47031}{86925} := \frac{4^{7-03} + 1}{(8 + 6 + 9^2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47128}{50396} := \frac{4 \times 71 - 2 - 8}{5 + 03 \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47130}{65982} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + 1)) + (3 - 0)}{6 + (59 - (8 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 7 + 1) \times 30}{6 \times ((5 + 9) \times (8 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+7-1) \times (3-0)}{6 \times (5 + ((9-8) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((7+1) \times 30)}{6 \times ((5+9) \times (8 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 - (3 - 0)))}{(6 \times (5 \times (9 - 8))) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (13 - 0))}{6 + (((5 \times 9) + 8) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((7-1)^3 + 0)}{(6 \times (59 - 8)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (7 - (1^3 + 0))}{6 + (5 + (9 - (8 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (7 - (1 - 30))}{6 - (5 + (9 - (8^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (7 \times (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{6 - (5 - ((9 + 8) \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (7 \times (13 - 0))}{6 + ((5 \times 9) + 82)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (7 + (1 + (3 - 0)))}{6 + (5 \times (9 - (8 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (71 + 30)}{6 + (59 + 82)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (71 - 30)}{65 - ((9 - 8) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{47 + (1 \times (3 - 0))}{6 - ((5 - 9) \times (8 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{47 + (13 - 0)}{6 + (5 - (9 - 82))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47136}{58920} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1^3)))^6}{5 \times ((8^9) \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (7 + (1 \times 3))) \times 6}{5 + (8 + (92 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(47 - (1^3)) \times 6}{5 \times (89 - 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (7 - (13 - 6))}{5^{8-9+2+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (7 + (1 - 36))}{58 - (9 \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (((7+1)^3)^6)}{5 \times ((8^9)^2 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 \times (1 + 3)) + 6)}{5 \times ((8 + 9) \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 + (1 - 3)) \times 6)}{58 + (92 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 + 1) \times (3 \times 6))}{5 \times (8 \times (9 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - ((1 - 3) \times 6))}{5 \times (8 - (9 - 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 \times 6)))}{(5 - (8 - 9)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 + 6)))}{5 \times (8 + (9 - (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 - 6)))}{5 - (8 - (9 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 \times (1 + (3 + 6)))}{5 \times ((8 \times 9) - (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + ((1^3) \times 6))}{(5 \times (8 + 9)) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 \times (3^6)))}{5 \times (8 \times (92 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 \times (3 - 6)))}{5 + (8 + (9 - (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 + (3 \times 6)))}{5 \times (8 + (9 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 + (3 - 6)))}{5 - ((8 - 9) \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (1 + 36))}{(5 \times 8) + (9 \times 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (13 \times 6))}{(5 \times 89) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (71 - (3 - 6))}{5 \times ((8 \times 9) + (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (71 + (3 \times 6))}{5 \times (8 + (9^2 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (71 + (3 - 6))}{(5 \times (8 \times 9)) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{7-1+3-6}}{(5 + (8 - 9)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((7 + 1) \times (3 \times 6))}{5 \times (8 + (9 + 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 7136}{5 + 8920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47152}{96830} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (1 + 5) \times 2}{(9 + 6 + 8) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47163}{82950} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (1 + 6) + 3}{(8 \times 2 - 9) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47196}{53820} := \frac{4 - 7 + (1 + 9) \times 6}{5 \times (3 + 8 + 2) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 7 - 1 + 9) \times 6}{5 \times (3 \times 8 + 2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47208}{61539} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (20 - 8)}{6 \times (1 + (5 + 3) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47215}{69083} := \frac{(47 \times 2 + 1) \times 5}{690 + 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47236}{91580} := \frac{4 + 7 + 2 + 36}{9 + 1 + 5 + 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(47 + 2) \times (3 + 6)}{9 \times (15 + 80)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47310}{86925} := \frac{4 \times (73 + 10)}{(8 \times (6 + 9) + 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47318}{60952} := \frac{4 + 73 - 18}{60 - 9 + 5^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{47320}{81965} := \frac{47 + 3^2 + 0}{(8 + 1 \times 9) \times 6 - 5} \\ & := \frac{(4 + 7 + 3) \times 20}{8 \times (1 + 9) \times 6 + 5} \\ & \frac{47328}{59160} := \frac{(((4 + 7) \times 3) + 2) \times 8}{5 \times (9 + (1 + 60))} \\ & := \frac{(4 - (7 - (3^2))) \times 8}{59 + (1^6 + 0)} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 \times 2))) - 8}{5 - (9 + (1 - 60))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3^2))) + 8}{5 + (91 - (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + 32)) + 8}{(5 \times 9) + 160} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (73 \times 2)) - 8}{5 \times (9 \times (16 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (73 - 2)) - 8}{5 \times (9 + (1 \times 60))} \\ & := \frac{(4^{7-3}) - (2 \times 8)}{5 \times ((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4^{7-3}) + (2 \times 8)}{5 \times (9 - (1 - 60))} \\ & := \frac{(4 + ((7 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8}{5 \times (9 \times (1 \times (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (7 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 + 1)) + 60} \\ & := \frac{(47 + 3) \times (2 + 8)}{5^{9+1-6+0}} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 8)}{5 \times ((9 - 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times ((73 + 2) \times 8)}{5 \times ((9 + 1) \times 60)} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 - (2 + 8)))}{5 \times (9 - (1 - (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 \times (2 - 8)))}{5^{9-1 \times 6+0}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 + (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 + (1^6 + 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 \times ((3 + 2)^8))}{(5^9) \times (1 + (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 \times (3 - (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 \times (1 + (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 \times (32 - 8))}{(5 + (9 \times 1)) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + ((3 \times 2) + 8))}{(5 \times (9 \times 1)) + 60} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + ((3^2) + 8))}{59 + (1 + 60)} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + ((3^2) - 8))}{5 \times (9 - (1^6 + 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{5 + (9 + (1 + 60))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 - (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 + (1 + (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 + (2 + 8)))}{(5 \times (9 - 1)) + 60} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 + (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 + (1 - (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 \times (7 + (32 - 8))}{5 \times (91 - 60)} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 8)}{5 + ((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((7 + 32) \times 8)}{(5 \times 91) - 60} \\ & := \frac{4 + ((73 + 2) \times 8)}{5 \times (91 + 60)} \\ & := \frac{4 + (7 - (3 - 28))}{5 \times (9 \times (1^6 + 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + (7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8)))}{5 \times (91 - (6 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + (7 + ((3^2) - 8))}{5 + (9 + (1^6 + 0))} \\ & := \frac{4 + (7 + (3 - (2 - 8)))}{5^{9-1-6+0}} \\ & := \frac{4 + (7 + (3 + (2 + 8)))}{5 + (9 + (16 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{4 + (7 + (3 + (2 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 - (1 + (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{4 + 7328}{5 + 9160} \\ & \frac{47329}{51680} := \frac{(47 + 3)^2 - 9}{(5 - 1) \times 680} \\ & \frac{47368}{59210} := \frac{((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6) \times 8}{5 \times (9 \times (2 \times 10))} \\ & := \frac{((4 \times (7 + 3)) + 6) \times 8}{5 \times (92 \times (1 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{((4 \times (7 - 3)) - 6) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 \times 2)) + 10} \\ & := \frac{((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6) - 8}{5 \times (9 + (2 - (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 - (7 - (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{5 \times (9 + (21 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times ((7 \times 3) + 6)) + 8}{5 \times (9 + (2 \times 10))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 \times 6))) + 8}{5 \times (9 \times (2 + (1 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times (73 + 6)) + 8}{5 \times (9^{2 \times 1+0})} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times 73) + 68}{(5 \times 92) - 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 \times 73) - 68}{(5 + 9) \times (2 \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (7 - (3 - 6))) \times 8}{5 \times (9 \times 2 + 10)} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 - 6))) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 \times 2)) - 10} \\ & := \frac{(4 + (7 + 36)) \times 8}{(5 \times 92) + 10} \\ & := \frac{4 - ((7 - (3 \times 6)) \times 8)}{5 + ((9 + 2) \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{4 - ((7 - (3 + 6)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 - 2)) - 10} \end{aligned}$$

$:= \frac{4 - (7 - (3 + 68))}{5 \times (9 - (2 - 10))}$	$:= \frac{4 + 7368}{5 + 9210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{59823} := \frac{(4 + 7 \times 6) \times 10}{5 + 9 \times 8^2 - 3}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 \times ((9^2) - (1 - 0))}$	<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{82593} := \frac{(4 + 7 \times 6) \times 10}{825 - 9 \times 3}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 \times (3 + 6)) + 8)}{5 \times ((9^2) - 10)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47385}{91260} := \frac{4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 8 - 5)}{(9 - 1) \times 26 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{98325} := \frac{4 + 7 \times 6 \times 1 + 0}{9 + 83 - 2 + 5}$
$:= \frac{4 \times ((7 + (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{(5 + (9 + 2)) \times 10}$	$:= \frac{47 + 3 + 85}{(9 + 1) \times 26 + 0}$	$:= \frac{(4 + 7 \times 6) \times 10}{(98 - 3) \times 2 \times 5}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 - (6 + 8)))}{5 \times (9 \times (2 \times (1 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(4 + 7 \times 38) \times 5}{(9 + 1) \times 260}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 \times (6 - 8)))}{(5 \times (9 + 2)) + 10}$	<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47628}{90153} := \frac{4 \times (7 - 6 - 2 + 8)}{(9 - 0 + 1) \times 5 + 3}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 - (3 + (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 - (2 + (1 - 0)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47502}{96831} := \frac{(4 + 7 \times 5) \times 02}{9 + 6 \times (8 \times 3 + 1)}$	$:= \frac{4^{7-6+2} - 8}{90 + 1 + 5 \times 3}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 \times ((3 \times 6) - 8))}{5 \times ((9 - 2) \times 10)}$	$:= \frac{(47 + 5) \times 02}{9 + 68 \times 3 - 1}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (76 + 2 - 8)}{(9 + 01) \times 53}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7^{3+6-8})}{5 \times (9 - (2 \times (1 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{47 + 5 - 0 \times 2}{96 + 8 + 3 - 1}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times (6 + 2 + 8)}{901 - 53}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + ((3 + 6) \times 8))}{(5 \times (9^2)) - 10}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{476 + 28}{901 + 53}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 - (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 + (2 + (1 - 0)))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47530}{86912} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times 5 \times 3 + 0}{8 \times 6 \times (9 - 1) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times (6 + 28)}{901 \times (5 - 3)}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 + (6 + 8)))}{(5 + (9 - 2)) \times 10}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (7 \times 5)^3 + 0}{(8 \times (69 + 1))^2}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (3 + (6 - 8)))}{5 \times (9 - (2 - (1 - 0)))}$	<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47680}{93125} := \frac{4 \times 76 + 80}{(9 - 3) \times 125}$
$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + (36 + 8))}{(5 \times 9) + 210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47539}{68012} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 5 - 3) + 9}{(6 + 8 \times 01)^2}$	<hr/>
$:= \frac{4^{7+3 \times (6-8)}}{5^{9+2-10}}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times 7 \times 5 - 3) \times 9}{(6 \times (8 - 01))^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47859}{63210} := \frac{47 - 8 + 5 + 9}{(6 + 3 - 2) \times 10}$
$:= \frac{4 + ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 \times (9 + (2 + 10))}$	<hr/>	<hr/>
$:= \frac{4 + ((7 + (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{5 \times (9 \times (2 - 1 + 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47601}{83592} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 6 - 01)}{8 \times 3 \times (5 + 9 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47960}{81532} := \frac{4 \times (7 + 9 - 6) + 0}{81 - 5 \times 3 + 2}$
$:= \frac{4 + ((7 - 3) \times (6 + 8))}{5 + ((9 - 2) \times 10)}$	$:= \frac{47 - 6 \times 01}{8 \times (3 - 5 + 9 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{47 + 9 - 6 + 0}{81 - 5 + 3^2}$
$:= \frac{4 + (7 - (3 - 68))}{5 \times (9 \times 2 + (1 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47601}{85239} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 6 + 01)}{8 + 5^2 \times (3 + 9)}$	$:= \frac{4 + 7 + 9 + 60}{8 + 1 + 5^3 + 2}$
$:= \frac{4 + (7 + (3 + (6 - 8)))}{5 + (9 + (2 - (1 - 0)))}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(4 + 7 - 9) \times 60}{81 + 5^3 - 2}$

$:= \frac{4 \times (7 + 9) + 6 + 0}{8 \times 15 - 3 + 2}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 1)) + 35}{(9 \times (6 + 2)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 1) \times 35)}{9 \times ((6 - 2) \times 70)}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 13)) + 5}{(9 \times (6 \times 2)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (1 - (3 - 5)))}{(9 \times 6) - (2 \times (7 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{47982}{50163} := \frac{4 - 7 + 9 + 8 \times 2}{5 + 01 \times 6 \times 3}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - 1)) + 35}{(9 \times 6) + (2 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (1^3 + 5))}{(9 - 6) \times (2^7 + 0)}$
$:= \frac{47 - 9 + 8 - 2}{50 - 1 - 6 + 3}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times 8) + (13 \times 5)}{(9 \times 6) + (2 \times 70)}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + ((1 + 3) \times 5))}{96 + (2^7 + 0)}$
$:= \frac{4 + 7 - 9 + 8^2}{5 + 01 + 63}$	$:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (1^3))) \times 5}{96 + (2 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (81 \times 35)}{9 \times ((6^2) \times 70)}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times 13)) \times 5}{(9 + 6) \times (2 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (81 + (3^5))}{96 \times (27 - 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48015}{63729} := \frac{(4 \times 8 + 01) \times 5}{6 \times (37 - 2) + 9}$	$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (1 - 3))) \times 5}{((9 + 6) \times 2) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4^{8+1-3-5}}{9 - (6 + (2 - (7 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{480 + 15}{6 + 3 + 72 \times 9}$	$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 1)) \times 35}{(9 + (6 - 2)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((8 - (1^3)) \times 5)}{9 + (62 + (7 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48015}{76923} := \frac{480 + 1 \times 5}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2 + 3)}$	$:= \frac{(48 \times (1 + 3)) + 5}{(9 \times (6^2)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((8 + (1 - 3)) \times 5)}{(9 \times 6) + (2 \times (7 - 0))}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{(48 + 1) \times (3 \times 5)}{(9 + (6 \times 2)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((8 + 13) \times 5)}{((9 + 6)^2) - (7 - 0)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48120}{63759} := \frac{4 \times (8 + 1 \times 2) + 0}{6 + 3 + 7 \times 5 + 9}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - ((1^3) \times 5))}{(9 \times (6 + 2)) - 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + ((81 \times 3) + 5)}{9 \times ((6 + 2) \times (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(4 + 8 \times 1) \times 20}{6 - 3 + 7 \times 5 \times 9}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (1^3 + 5))}{9 - ((6 \times 2) - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 - ((1^3) \times 5))}{9 + ((6 \times 2) - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times 120}{6 \times (3 + 7 \times 5 \times 9)}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (1 + 35))}{9 + (62 - (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (1^3 + 5))}{9 - (6 - (2 + (7 - 0)))}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (13 \times 5))}{(96 \times 2) - 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (1 - (3 \times 5)))}{9 + ((6^2) + (7 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48135}{96270} := \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 1)) + 3) \times 5}{(9 - (6 - 2)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times ((1 - 3) \times 5))}{96 + (2 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (1 - (3 + 5)))}{9 + ((6^2) - (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{((4 + (8 - 1)) \times 3) + 5}{(9 - 6) \times 2 + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (1 - (3 \times 5)))}{((9 + 6)^2) + (7 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (1 \times (3 - 5)))}{9 + ((6 \times 2) + (7 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (1 - 3))) - 5}{(9 - (6 + 2)) \times 70}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (1 + (3 - 5)))}{9 + (6 + (2 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (1 - (3 - 5)))}{962 + 70}$
$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (1 \times 3))) - 5}{(9 \times 6) + (2^7 + 0)}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 + (1 - (3 + 5)))}{9 + (6 - (2 + (7 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 + ((1^3) - 5))}{((9 - 6)^2) + (7 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (1^3))) + 5}{96 - (2 \times (7 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - 135)}{(96 \times 2) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (1 - (3 + 5)))}{9 + (6 + (2 - (7 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (1 + 3))) + 5}{(9 \times (6 - 2)) + 70}$	$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 \times (1 + 3)) - 5)}{(9 - 6) \times (2 + 70)}$	$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (1 - (3 - 5)))}{9 - (6 - (27 - 0))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{4 + (8 + (1 \times (3 - 5)))}{9 + (6 - (2 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + (8 + (1 + (3 + 5)))}{9 + (6 + (27 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{48 - (1 - 35)}{96 - (2 - 70)} \\
 & := \frac{48 \times ((1 + 3) \times 5)}{(9 + 6) \times (2^7 + 0)} \\
 & := \frac{48 \times (1 + (3 + 5))}{96 \times (2 + (7 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{48 + 135}{96 + 270} \\
 & := \frac{481 - 35}{962 - 70} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48192}{76053} & := \frac{4 \times (8 - 1 + 9) \times 2}{7 + (60 + 5) \times 3} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{62370} & := \frac{4 + 8 + 1 + 9 - 5}{6 + 23 - 7 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{48 - 1 + 9 - 5}{62 - 3 + 7 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{62730} & := \frac{4 \times 8 - 1 + 95}{6 + 2^7 + 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{67320} & := \frac{4 \times 8 \times (1 + 9) - 5}{6 \times 73 + 2 + 0} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{57096} & := \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + 12))}{5 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (3 \times 1))) + 2}{5 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (8 + (3 \times (1^2)))}{5 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + ((8^3 - 1) \times 2)}{((5 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{4 + (83 \times (1 + 2))}{(5 \times (70 - 9)) - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{79056} & := \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + 12))}{(7 - (9 + (-05))) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{48 - (3 + 12)}{7 - (9 + (0 - 56))} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (8 + (3 \times (1^2)))}{7 + (9 - (0 - 56))} \\
 & := \frac{48 + (31 - 2)}{(7 + (9 + 05)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{4 - (8 - 312)}{(79 - (-05)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{((4 + 8) \times 31) + 2}{(7 + (90 + 5)) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{4 + ((8^3 - 1) - 2)}{7 + (90 + (5 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + ((8^3) + (1^2))}{790 + 56} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48503}{76219} & := \frac{4 + (8 + (5 + (-03)))}{7 - (6 - (2 + 19))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - 0))) \times 3}{7 + (6 + (2 \times (1 + 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{4 - (8 - (50 + 3))}{7 + (62 - (1 - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{48 - (5 \times (-03))}{(7 + (6 - (2 \times 1))) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (8 + (5^{03}))}{76 \times (2 + (1 \times 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(48 + 50) \times 3}{7 \times (6 \times (2 + (1 \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{48 + (5 - (-03))}{7 + ((6 + (2 + 1)) \times 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{79605} & := \frac{4 \times (8 + 3 \times 12)}{(7 - 9 + 60) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{96075} & := \frac{4 \times (8^3 - 1 + 2)}{(9 + 6) \times 07 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48320}{67195} & := \frac{4^{8 \times 3 - 20}}{6 + 7 \times (1 + 9) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48321}{50976} & := \frac{(48 - 3) \times 2 + 1}{5 + 097 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48321}{79650} & := \frac{(4 + 8)^3 + 2 - 1}{(7 \times 9 - 6) \times 50} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48351}{96702} & := \frac{((4 \times 8) + 3) \times (5 + 1)}{(9 - 6) \times (70 \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{((4 + 8) \times (3 + 5)) + 1}{(9 \times 6) + (70 \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times ((8 \times 3) + 5)) + 1}{9 \times ((6 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) + 1}{96 + (7 \times (-02))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (0 \times 3))) + (4 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) - 1}{7 + (6 - (2 \times (1^9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times 3)) + (5 + 1)}{(9 - 6) \times (70 - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (3 + 5))) - 1}{(9 \times 6) + (70 + 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + 3)) - (5 + 1)}{9 + (67 - (0 \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (83 + 5)) - 1}{9 \times (6 + (70 + 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times 83) + (5 \times 1)}{(96 \times (7 - 0)) + 2} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times 83) + (5 + 1)}{(96 - 70)^2} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 + 3)) \times (5 + 1)}{9 \times (6 - (7 \times (-02)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + 8) \times (3 \times 51)}{9 \times (6 \times (70 - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4+8) \times (3+(5+1))}{(9-6) \times (70+2)} \\ &:= \frac{(48-3) \times (5-1)}{9 \times ((6 \times (7-0)) - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - ((3^5) + 1))}{96 \times (7 + (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 \times (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (6 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 \times (5 - 1)))}{(9 + (6 - (7 - 0))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + (5 \times 1)))}{9 - (6 - (7 + (-02)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + (5 - 1)))}{9 + (6 - (7 - (-02)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + 51))}{(9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))^2} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (35 + 1))}{9 + (6 + (7^{02}))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (3 - (5 \times 1)))}{(9 \times 6) + (7 \times (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (3 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (6 + (7 - (-02)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (3 \times (5 + 1)))}{((9 - 6) \times 70) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (((8 + 3) \times 5) - 1)}{(9 - 67) \times (-02)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 3) - (5 + 1))}{(9 + (6 + (7 - 0))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 3) + (5 \times 1))}{(9 - (6 \times 7)) \times (-02)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((8^3) - (5 + 1))}{(9 + 6) \times (70 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 3) \times (5 + 1))}{(9 \times 6) - (7 \times (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (3 - (5 \times 1)))}{96 - (70 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (3 + (5 - 1)))}{9 + (6 - (7 + (-02)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (3 \times (5 \times 1)))}{((9 \times 6) + 70) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (3 + (5 + 1)))}{(9 + (67 - 0)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + ((3 \times 5) - 1))}{9 - (6 - (7^{02}))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (3 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (6 + (7 + (-02)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (3 - (5 + 1)))}{9 \times ((6 - 7) \times (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (3 \times (5 \times 1)))}{9 \times (6 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (3 + (5 + 1)))}{(9 - 6) \times (7 \times (02))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (35 \times 1))}{((9 \times 6) - (7 - 0)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (35 + 1))}{96 - (7 \times (0 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (83 - (5 \times 1))}{96 + (70 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (83 \times (5 - 1))}{96 \times (7 - (0 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{48 - (3 - (5 + 1))}{(9 + (6 \times (7 - 0))) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{48 \times ((3 \times 5) - 1)}{96 \times (7 \times (02))} \\ &:= \frac{48 \times (3^{5+1})}{9 \times 6^{7-02}} \\ &:= \frac{48 \times (3 + (5 + 1))}{96 \times (7 - (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{48 + (3 + (5 - 1))}{96 - (7 \times (-02))} \\ &:= \frac{48 + (35 + 1)}{96 + (70 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{48 + 351}{96 + 702} \\ &:= \frac{4835 + 1}{9670 + 2} \\ &:= \frac{4835 - 1}{9670 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{48375}{61920} := \frac{4 \times (8 + 37 + 5)}{(6 + 1 + 9)^2 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 8 + 3) \times 7 + 5}{(6 + 1 + 9) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + 37) \times 5}{6 \times 192 + 0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48503}{79261} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 5 - 03}{79 - 2 \times 6 \times 1} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48510}{76923} := \frac{(4 + 8 - 5) \times 10}{(7 + (6 + 9) \times 2) \times 3} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48510}{96327} := \frac{4 \times 85 + 10}{9 \times 63 + 2^7} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48513}{97026} := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1) \times 3}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 2) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 5)) + 1) \times 3}{970 + (2 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times 8) - 5) \times 13}{9 \times (70 + (2 + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times (5 + 1)) - 3}{(9 - (7 \times (-02))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 + 1))) + 3}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 2) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1))) + 3}{((9 + (7 - 0))^2) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1))) - 3}{((9 + (7 - 0))^2) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (85 + 1)) + 3}{(9 \times 70) + (2^6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (85 - 1)) - 3}{9 \times (70 - (2 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 8) - (5 + (1^3))}{9 + ((7^{02}) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 8) + (5 \times (1 + 3))}{9 \times ((70 \times 2) + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times 85) - 13}{(9 \times (70 + 2)) + 6} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 \times (1^3)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (2 + 6)))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 + (1^3)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (2 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4^{8-5+1} \times 3}{((9 + (7 - 0))^2) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 - 13))}{(9 - (7 - 0)) \times (2^6)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times ((5 - 1) \times 3))}{(97 \times (02)) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 5) + 1)) \times 3}{9 \times ((7 + (-02)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 - (1^3)))}{(9 - (7 - 0))^{2+6}} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 - (1^3)))}{9 \times ((7 \times (02)) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - 1)))^3}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times (2^6)} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 + (1 - 3)))}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times (2 \times 6)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 + (1 + 3)))}{((9 + 70) \times 2) - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 + 1))) \times 3}{(9 + (7 - (-02))) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{5-1-3}}{9 + ((7^{02}) + 6)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (51 - 3))}{97 \times (0 + (2 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 51)) \times 3}{9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 6))} &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{5-1+3}}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))^6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - (1 + 3)))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2) - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times (51 \times 3)}{9 \times ((70 - 2) \times 6)} &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{5+1+3}}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)^6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - (1 - 3)))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 - (5 + 1)) \times 3}{9 \times (7 \times (0 - (2 - 6)))} &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{5+1-3}}{(9 - (7 + (-02)))^6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 \times (1 \times 3)))}{9 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 2)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 \times (5 \times 1)) + 3}{9 \times ((7 - (-02)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 \times 3)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (2^6)))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 + (1 + 3)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - 26))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 \times (5 + 1)) + 3}{97 \times ((0 \times 2) + 6)} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1^3)))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (51 + 3))}{(9 \times (7 \times (02))) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 \times (5 + 1)) - 3}{(97 + (-02)) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 - 3)))}{(9 \times (7 \times (02))) - 6} &:= \frac{4 + (85 + (1^3))}{9 \times ((7 \times (02)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 + 51) \times 3}{9 \times (70 + (2 - 6))} &:= \frac{4 \times (85 - (1 \times 3))}{(9 \times 70) + 26} &:= \frac{48 \times (5 + (1 + 3))}{9 \times (70 + 26)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 - (1 - 3)))}{9 - (7 - (0 - (2 - 6)))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times (5 - 1)) - 3)}{9 - (7 + (0 - (2^6)))} &:= \frac{485 - (1 + 3)}{970 - (2 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 \times (1^3)))}{9 - (7 - (0 \times 26))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 5) + (1 - 3))}{(9 + (7 + (-02))) \times 6} &:= \frac{485 - (1 - 3)}{970 - (2 - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + (1^3)))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (2 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8^5) - (1 + 3))}{9 + 7)^{-02+6}} &:= \frac{485 + (1 + 3)}{970 + (2 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + 13))}{9 - (7 + (0 - 26))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1 \times 3)))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (2 - 6)))} &:= \frac{485 + 13}{970 + 26} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 + (5 - 13))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (2 + 6)))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1^3)))}{9 + (7 - (0 \times 26))} &:= \frac{4851 + 3}{9702 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (85 \times (1 - 3))}{(9 + (7^{02})) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1 + 3)))}{9 + (7 - ((0 \times 2) - 6))} &:= \frac{4851 - 3}{9702 - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((8^{5 \times 1})^3)}{((9 + (7 - 0))^2)^6} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1 - 3)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (2 + 6)))} &:= \frac{485 - 13}{970 - 26} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 5) \times (1 + 3))}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times 26} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 \times (1^3)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (2 \times 6)))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48516}{97032} &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 5)) - 1) \times 6}{9 \times ((70 \times 3) + 2)} &:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + (5 - 1)) \times 6)}{9 \times (70 - (3 \times 2))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1 + 6)))}{9 - ((7 \times (-03)) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 - 5)) - 1) \times 6}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 3) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 - (1^6)))}{9 - ((7 \times (-03)) - 2)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 \times (1 - 6)))}{9 + (70 - (3 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 8) - 5) \times (1 + 6)}{9 \times (7 \times (0 + (3 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 - (1 + 6)))}{9 + (70 + (3 - 2))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 + (1^6)))}{(9 - (7 - 0)) \times (3 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 \times 1))) - 6}{(9 \times (7 - (-03))) + 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 + (1 - 6)))}{(9 - (7 - 0)) \times 32} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - 16))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - 1))) + 6}{9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 + 2)))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (5 - 16))}{(9 + (70 - 3)) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 - (1^6)))}{9 - (7 \times (0 - (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 5)) - (1^6)}{97 - (0 - (3 + 2))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times ((5 + 1) \times 6))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3)^2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 \times 1^6))}{(9 \times (7 - (-03))) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - 5)) - (1 + 6)}{9 + (7 + (0 - (3 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 - (1^6)))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 3)))^2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 + (1 + 6)))}{(97 - (-03)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (85 - 1)) + 6}{9 \times (70 + (3 \times 2))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1^6)))}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times (3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - (1 \times 6)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (3 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times 8) - (5 - (1 + 6))}{(9 \times (7 - 0)) + 3 + 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 + 6)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - 32))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - (1 - 6)))}{9 - (7 \times (0 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4^{8-5}) - (1^6)}{9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 3) + 2))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 - 6)))}{9 \times (7 - (0 - (3^2)))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 \times (1 \times 6)))}{9 + (70 + 3 + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - 5)) \times (1 + 6)}{97 - (0 - (3 - 2))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 \times 16))}{(9 + (7^{03})) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 + (1^6)))}{(9 - (7 - 0)) \times 3^2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - ((8 - 5) \times (1 - 6))}{(9 + (7 - (-03))) \times 2} &:= \frac{4^{8-5+1^6}}{(9 - (7 - 0))^{3^2}} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (51 \times 6))}{(9 \times 70) + (3 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 \times (1 + 6)))}{(9 \times (7 - 0)) - (3 - 2)} &:= \frac{4^{8+5-1-6}}{((9 + (7 - 0))^3) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - 16))}{9 - (7 - (0 \times 32))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + (1^6)))}{9 - (7 + ((0 \times 3) - 2))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times (5 - 1)) - 6)}{(9 - (7 \times (-03))) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (85 - (1 - 6))}{(97 + (-03)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + 16))}{9 - (7 + (0 - 32))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 5) + (1 - 6))}{9 + (70 - (3 - 2))} &:= \frac{4 + (85 + (1^6))}{9 \times ((7 - (-03)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (51 + 6))}{97 - (0 - (3^2))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 5) + 16)}{(9 \times (7 - 0)) - 3) \times 2} &:= \frac{48 - (5 + 16)}{9 \times (7 + (0 - (3 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (5 + (1 - 6)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (3 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 + (5 \times 1)) \times 6)}{(9 + (70 + 3)) \times 2} &:= \frac{48 - (51 - 6)}{((9 - (7 - 0))^3) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - (8 + (5 - 16))}{9 + (7 + ((0 \times 3) - 2))} &:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 5) \times (1 + 6))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3) + 2} &:= \frac{48 \times (5 + 16)}{9 \times (7 \times (0 + 32))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (((8 \times 5) - 1) \times 6)}{9 \times ((70 \times 3) - 2)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1 \times 6)))}{(9 + (7 + (-03))) \times 2} &:= \frac{485 \times (1 \times 6)}{970 \times (3 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + (5 \times 1)) \times 6)}{(9 \times 70) - (3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (1^6)))}{9 + (7 - (0 \times 32))} &:= \frac{485 \times 1^6}{970 \times (3 - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{485 + 16}{970 + 32}$$

$$:= \frac{485 - 16}{970 - 32}$$

► $\frac{48531}{97062} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times 5) - 31}{9 + 7^{0 \times 6 + 2}}$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 + 3))) + 1}{9 - (7 - (0 \times 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1}{970 - (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1}{970 - (6 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - 3))) - 1}{9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)}{(9 + 70) \times (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 \times 3))) - 1}{(97 + (-06)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - 3))) - 1}{9 + (7 - (0 - 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - 5)) - (3 + 1)}{9 + (7 - (0 \times 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (85 + 3)) - 1}{9 \times (70 + (6 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 8) - (5^{3-1})}{9 - (7 + (0 - (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 85) + (3 \times 1)}{(9 \times (70 + 6)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 85) - 31}{(9 \times 70) - (6 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{8-5}) - (3 - 1)}{(9 - (7 - 0)) \times 62}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{8-5}) \times (3 - 1)}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 6)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{8-5})^{3+1}}{((9 + (7 - 0))^6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{8-5}) - 31}{((9 - (7 - 0))^6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)}{(9 - (7 \times (-06))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 5))^{3-1}}{(9 \times (70 - 6)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))}{9 \times ((7 \times (06)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times (53 \times 1)}{((9 \times 70) + 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times (53 - 1)}{((9 \times 70) - 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 \times 5) - (3 + 1)}{((9 + 70) \times 6) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 \times 5) - (3 - 1)}{((9 + 70) \times 6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 \times 5) + (3 - 1)}{(9 + (7 - (-06)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 \times (3 + 1)))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 6))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + (3 \times 1)))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + (3 - 1)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (5 + 31))}{9 - (7 + (0 - 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (53 \times 1))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (53 + 1))}{(9 + (7 + (-06)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 + (5 - 31))}{(9 + (7 - (-06))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 \times 5) + 31)}{(9 \times 70) - 62}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8^{5-3}) - 1)}{9 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8^5)^3 \times 1)}{((9 + (7 - 0))^6)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))}{((9 - (7 - 0))^6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times (6 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (5 + (3 + 1)))}{(9 + (7 - 0)) \times (6^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8^{5-3+1})}{((9 - (7 - 0))^6)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 - (3 + 1)))}{9 \times (70 - 62)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (5 \times (3 - 1)))}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 6)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 5) + (3 \times 1))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 53) + 1)}{(9 + (70 \times 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8^{5-3}) + 1)}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8^5) - (3 + 1))}{(9 + (7 - 0))^{6-2}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 5) \times 31)}{97 \times ((0 \times 6) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 5)^3 \times 1)}{((9 - (7 - 0))^6) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (3 \times 1)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (3 - 1)))}{9 \times ((7 + (-06)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))}{9 + (7 + (0 - (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 + (3 - 1)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (5 + 31))}{(97 \times (06)) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8^{5-3-1})}{9 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8^{5-3+1})}{970 + 62}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 + ((5 \times 3) - 1))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (6^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 - (3 \times 1)))}{9 + (7 - (0 - (6 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (5 + (3 - 1)))}{9 - (7 + (0 - (6^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (85 - (3 + 1))}{(9 + (70 + 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{48 + (5^{3-1})}{(9 + (70 - 6)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{48 + (5 + (3 + 1))}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 6) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{485 - (3 - 1)}{970 - (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{485 \times (3 + 1)}{970 \times (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{485 + (3 + 1)}{970 + (6 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{485 + (3 - 1)}{970 + (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{4853 + 1}{9706 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4853 - 1}{9706 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{485 - 31}{970 - 62}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48609}{75123} := \frac{4 - 8 + 6 + 09}{7 + 5 \times (1 - 2 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{48 - 6 - 09}{(7 + 5 \times 1 \times 2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - 6 + 09)}{75 + 1 - 2^3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 86 + 09}{75 \times 1 \times 2 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 - 6) \times 09}{7 + 5 - 1 + 23}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 8 + 6 \times 09}{7 \times 5 \times (1 + 2) - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48615}{97230} := \frac{((4 \times 8) - (6 - 1)) \times 5}{9 \times (7 + (23 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 8) - (6 - 1))^5}{(9^7) \times (2 \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times 6) + 15}{(9 + (7^2)) \times (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (6 + 1))) \times 5}{9 - (7 + (2 - 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (6 + 1))) - 5}{(9 \times (7^2)) - (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times 6)) + (1 + 5)}{9 \times (7 \times 2 + 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times 6)) + 15}{9 \times ((7^2) - (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 \times 1))) - 5}{97 + (2 + (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (86 \times 1)) - 5}{(9 \times 72) + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (86 - 1)) + 5}{(9 + (7 \times 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 - 1))) \times 5}{9 + (7 \times (23 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 6)) \times 15}{(9 + (7 + 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 - (6 \times 1)) \times 5}{(9 + (7 - 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 + (6 \times 1))^5}{972^3 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - ((6 + 1) \times 5))}{9 - (7 - (2 \times 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 - (1^5)))}{9 + (7 \times (2 - (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 + 15))}{9 - (7 - (2 + 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 + (6 - 15))}{9 - (7 - (2^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 - (6 - 1))^5)}{9 \times (72 \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 \times 6) + 15)}{9 \times (7 \times (2^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (1^5)))}{9 + (7 + (2^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (1 + 5)))}{(9 - (7 - 2))^3 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 \times (1 - 5)))}{(9 - 7)^{2^3+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 \times (1^5)))}{9 - (7 \times (2 - (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 + (1 - 5)))}{9 + (7 + (2 + 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 + 5)))}{((9 + 7)^2) \times (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 8^{6+1^5}}{9 + 7)^{2 \times 3 + 0}}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8^{6+1-5})}{(9 + 7) \times (2 + 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 + (1^5)))}{(9 - (7 - 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 + (1 - 5)))}{(9 + 7) \times (2 + (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 + 15))}{9 - (7 - 230)}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-6+1 \times 5}}{((9 + 7) \times 2)^3 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-6+1^5}}{(9 + 7) \times (2^3 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-6 \times 1^5}}{9 - 7)^{2+3} + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-6-1^5}}{9 + (7 - (2^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 - (6 + 1)) \times 5)}{9 \times (7 - (2 + (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times (6 - 1)) + 5)}{97 - (2 - (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times (6 - 1)) - 5)}{9 + (72 - (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 6) - (1 + 5))}{97 - (2 + (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 6) + 15)}{9 + ((7 - 2)^3 + 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 6) \times 15)}{(9 \times 7) + (2 + (3 - 0))}$$

$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 - (1 \times 5)))}{9 + (7 + (2 \times (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{48 \times (6 - (1 - 5))}{(9 + 7) \times (2 \times 30)}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 6)) - (5 + 1)}{97 + (3 - (0 \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 \times (1 - 5)))}{9 \times (7 - (2 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{48 \times (6 + 15)}{9 \times (7 \times (2 + 30))}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 6)) - 51}{9 + (7 + (3 \times (-02)))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 \times (1^5)))}{(9 - (7 - 2)) \times (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{48 + (6 \times (1^5))}{9 \times (7 + (2 + (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 65)) - 1}{97 \times (3 \times (02))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 + (1 - 5)))}{9 + ((7 \times 2) - (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{486 \times (1 + 5)}{(9 + (7 + 2))^3 + 0}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - 6)) - (5 \times 1)}{(9 - 7) \times (3 - (0 \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 - 15))}{(9 + (7 - 2)) \times (3 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{486 + 15}{972 + 30}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times 8) + (6 - (5 - 1))}{(9 \times 7) + (3 - (-02))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (6 - (1^5)))}{9 + ((7^2) + 30)}$	$:= \frac{486 - 15}{972 - 30}$	$:= \frac{(4^{8-6}) + 51}{(97 - 30) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (6 + (1 - 5)))}{(9 \times 7) - (23 - 0)}$		$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 \times 1)}{9 \times ((7 + (3 - 0)) \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + ((6 - 1) \times 5))}{97 - (23 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48625}{73910} := \frac{4 + 8 + 6 + 2^5}{(7 - 3) \times (9 + 10)}$	$:= \frac{(4 + (8 - 6)) \times (5 \times 1)}{(9 + (7 \times (3 - 0))) \times 2}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 - (1 \times 5)))}{9 + (7 \times 2 + (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(4 + 86) \times 2 - 5}{7 \times (39 - 1) + 0}$	$:= \frac{(4 + 86) \times (5 \times 1)}{9 \times ((7 + (3 - 0))^2)}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 - (1 - 5)))}{9 + (7 - (2 - 30))}$		$:= \frac{4 - (8 - ((6 \times 5) - 1))}{((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0)) + 2}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (1 \times 5)))}{9 + (72 + (3 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48651}{97302} := \frac{(((4 \times 8) + 6) \times 5) - 1}{9 \times (7 \times (3 \times (02)))}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 \times 51))}{(9 - 7) \times 302}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (1 + 5)))}{(9 \times (7 \times 2)) - 30}$	$:= \frac{((4 - (8 - 6)) \times 5) - 1}{9 \times (7 - (3 - (-02)))}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 + (5 + 1)))}{9 + 7^{3-02}}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (1^5)))}{9 + ((7 + 2) \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times 6) - (5 + 1)}{((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0)) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 + (5 - 1)))}{(9 - 7) \times (3 \times (02))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 + (1 \times 5)))}{(9 - 7) \times (23 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{((4 + 86) \times 5) + 1}{9 - (7 - (30^2))}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (6 + 51))}{97 + (3^{02})}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 + (1 - 5)))}{9 + ((7^2) - 30)}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times ((8 - 6)^5)) - 1}{(97 + 30) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (65 - 1))}{(9 - 7) \times (30 \times 2)}$
$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (61 + 5))}{9 + ((7^2) \times (3 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) + 1}{((9 - 7) \times 30) - 2}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (6 - (5 + 1)))}{9 - (7 + (3 \times (-02)))}$
$:= \frac{4 + (861 + 5)}{(9 + (7^2)) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) - 1}{9 \times (7 - (3 + (-02)))}$	$:= \frac{4 - (8 + (6 - 51))}{9 + (73 - (0 \times 2))}$
$:= \frac{48 - (6 - (1^5))}{(9 \times 7) + (23 - 0)}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))) + 1}{(9 \times 7) + (3 - (0 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (((8 - 6) \times 5) + 1)}{(9 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) - 2}$
$:= \frac{48 - (6 - (1 - 5))}{9 + (7 + (2 \times 30))}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))) - 1}{9 - (7 - (30 \times 2))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 6) \times (5 - 1))}{(9 + 7) \times (30 - 2)}$
$:= \frac{48 - (6 + 15)}{9 \times (7 + (2 - (3 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + 6)) - (5 \times 1)}{97 + (3 - (-02))}$	$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{(9 - 7) \times (30 - 2)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (7 + (30 + 2))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 + (5 - 1)))}{((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0)) - 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 + (7 + 2)))}{501 - (9 - 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 - (5 - 1)))}{(9 - 73) \times (-02)} &:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (6 + (5 + 1)))}{(97 + (3 - 0)) \times 2} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - 6))^{7+2}}{501 + (9 \times 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 \times (5 + 1)))}{((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0))^2} &:= \frac{4 + (8^{6-5 \times 1})}{(9 - (7 \times 3)) \times (-02)} &:= \frac{4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 72)}{501 + 93} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 + (5 \times 1)))}{(9 + (7^3 + 0)) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{(9 + (7 - (3 - 0))) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (7 \times 2)))}{5 - (0 - (1 + 93))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (65 - 1))}{9 + 7)^{3+0 \times 2}} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) - 2)} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (7 \times 2)))}{50 + (19 - 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8^{6-5 \times 1})}{(9 - (7 - 30)) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (73 - (-02))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + ((6 \times 7) - 2))}{5 - (0 - 193)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{6-5+1}}{9 - 7)^{3^{02}}} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 1)))}{97 - (3 + (-02))} & & \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 \times (7 + (3 + (-02)))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 + (5 \times 1)))}{((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0)) - 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{48723}{96105} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 7 - 2 \times 3}{(96 - 10) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (73 + (-02))} &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 + (5 - 1)))}{9 + (7 \times (3 - (-02)))} & & \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 \times 1)))}{9 - (7 - 302)} &:= \frac{4 + (86 + (5 - 1))}{(97 - (3 - 0)) \times 2} &\blacktriangleright \frac{48725}{91603} := \frac{4 - 8 + 7^2 + 5}{91 + 6 - 03} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 + 1)))}{9 + 7^{3+0 \times 2}} &:= \frac{48 - ((6 \times 5) + 1)}{9 - (7 - (30 + 2))} &:= \frac{(4 - 8 + 7) \times 25}{9 \times 16 - 03} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (6 + (5 - 1)))}{9 \times (7 + (3^{02}))} &:= \frac{48 - ((6 \times 5) - 1)}{(9 \times (7 - (3 - 0))) + 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + 7 + 2 \times 5)}{9 - 1 + 60 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4^{8-6+5-1}}{((9 + 7)^3 + 0) \times 2} &:= \frac{48 - (6 \times (5 \times 1))}{9 \times (7 - (3 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + 72) + 5}{9 - 1 + 603} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (((8 - 6) \times 5) + 1)}{9 + (7 \times (3 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{48 - (6 + (5 - 1))}{9 + (7 + (30 \times 2))} & & \\
 &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times (6 + 5)) + 1)}{(9 \times 7) + 30) \times 2} &:= \frac{48 \times (6 + (5 - 1))}{(9 + 7) \times (30 \times 2)} &\blacktriangleright \frac{48732}{60915} := \frac{(4 \times 87) + 32}{(60 \times (9 - 1)) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 6) - (5 \times 1))}{97 - (3 - (0 \times 2))} &:= \frac{48 + (6 - (5 \times 1))}{97 + (3 + (-02))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (7 - 3))) \times 2}{6 \times (0 + (9 + (1 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + ((8 \times 6) - (5 + 1))}{(9 + (7 + 30)) \times 2} &:= \frac{4865 + 1}{9730 + 2} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (7 + 3))) \times 2}{(6 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + ((8 - 6) \times (5 + 1))}{9 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 2)} &:= \frac{4865 - 1}{9730 - 2} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (7 + 3)))^2}{(60 \times (9 + 1)) + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{9 + (7 - (3 \times (-02)))} & &:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times ((7 \times 3) + 2)}{(60 + (9 \times 1)) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (6 + (5 \times 1)))}{9 - 7^{3-02}} &\blacktriangleright \frac{48672}{50193} := \frac{4 \times (8^{6-7+2})}{5 - (0 - (1 + (9 \times 3)))} &:= \frac{(4 + 8) \times ((7 + 3) \times 2)}{6 \times (0 + ((9 + 1) \times 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(4+8) \times (7 \times (3+2))}{(60 \times 9) - 15}$$

$$:= \frac{(48 - (7-3)) \times 2}{60 + ((9+1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (7 \times 32))}{((6 \times (09)) + 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 - (7 + (3^2)))}{6 - (0 - (9 \times (1^5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (7 - (3^2)))}{(6 + ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (7 - 32))}{(60 - (9 \times 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + (7 + 3)) \times 2)}{60 \times (9 - (1 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 7) \times 32)}{60 \times ((9 - 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 73) \times 2)}{6 \times (0 + (9 \times 15))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((87 + 3) \times 2)}{60 \times (9 + (1 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((87 - 3) \times 2)}{60 \times (9 + (1 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (7 - (3^2)))}{(6 \times (09)) + (1 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (7 - (3 - 2)))}{6 - (0 - (9 - (1 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (7 - (3 - 2)))}{6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (7 + 3 + 2))}{60 \times (9 - (1^5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 \times (73 + 2))}{60 \times ((9 + 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + ((7 + 3)^2))}{60 \times (9 \times (1^5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 - (3 \times 2)))}{60 - (9 + (1 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 - (3^2)))}{6 - (0 - (9 + 15))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 - (3 - 2)))}{(6 - (0 - (9 - 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 \times (3 \times 2)))}{(60 - (9 + 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 \times (3 - 2)))}{(6 - (0 - (9 \times 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 + (3 \times 2)))}{60 + (9 \times (1 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 + 3 + 2))}{60 + ((9 - 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 + (3 - 2)))}{(6 - (0 - (9 + 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (87 + 32)}{(60 \times (9 + 1)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-7+3-2}}{6 - (0 - (9 + (1 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{8-7 \times (3-2)}}{(6 \times (0 \times 91)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times ((7 \times 3) - 2))}{60 + (9 \times 15)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (7 - (3 - 2)))}{(6 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times (73 + 2))}{(60 + 91) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 + (7 + (3^2)))}{(6 - ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{48 \times (7 + (3 \times 2))}{60 \times (9 - (1 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{48^{7-3 \times 2}}{6 \times (0 + (9 + (1^5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{48 + (7 \times 32)}{(60 + (9 - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{48 + 732}{60 + 915}$$

$$:= \frac{487 + 3 + 2}{609 + 1 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{487 + 3 - 2}{609 + 1^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48756}{93210} := \frac{487 - 5 - 6}{(93 - 2) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48762}{90153} := \frac{4 + 8^{7-6+2}}{901 + 53}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48792}{51360} := \frac{4 - (8 - ((7 \times 9) - 2))}{(5 - (1 + 3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 - (7 - (9 \times 2)))}{(5 \times (1 + 3)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - ((8 - (7 \times 9)) \times 2)}{5 \times ((1 + 3) \times (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (7 - 9))) - 2}{5 - (1 - (36 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 7)) \times (9 \times 2)}{(5 + (1^3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 + (8 + 7)) \times 9)^2}{513 \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (8 \times (7 - 92))}{(5 - 1) \times (3 \times 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 \times (9 - 2)))}{(5 - (1^3)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (8 \times ((7 + 9)^2))}{(5 + 1) \times 360}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (87 - (9 + 2))}{5 \times (1 + (3 + 60))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48927}{63501} := \frac{4 + 8 \times (9 + 2 \times 7)}{(6 - 3)^5 + 01}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((8 + 9)^2 - 7)}{6 \times (3^5 + 01)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48930}{51726} := \frac{4 - 8 + 9 + 30}{5 - 1 + 7 + 26}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 8 + 93 + 0}{5 \times 17 + 26}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{48951}{67032} := \frac{4 \times (89 \times 5 - 1)}{(6 + 70) \times 32}$ <hr/>	$:= \frac{4 + ((9^2 + 0) + 3)}{(7 + (15 - 6)) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49032}{75168} := \frac{4 + 90 \times (3 + 2)}{(7 + 5 \times 16) \times 8}$ <hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49160}{83572} := \frac{4 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 0}{(8 - 3 + 5 + 7) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 1^6) + 0}{(8 - 3 + 5) \times 7 - 2}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 16) + 0}{8 + 3 \times (5 + 7^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49038}{51267} := \frac{4 \times 9 + 0 \times 3 + 8}{5 + 1 - 2 + 6 \times 7}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 03 \times 8)}{5 - 1 + 2 \times 67}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (90 - 3 \times 8)}{(5 - 1) \times (2 + 67)}$ $:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times (03 + 8)}{(5 + 1) \times (2 + 67)}$ <hr/>	$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 1 \times 6) + 0}{83 + 5 + 7 \times 2}$ $:= \frac{4 \times 91 + 6 + 0}{(8 + 3) \times 57 + 2}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49203}{56871} := \frac{(-4 + 9^2) \times 03}{(5 \times 6 + 8) \times 7 + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49058}{67132} := \frac{4 + 9 \times 05 + 8}{6 \times (7 + 1 + 3 + 2)}$ $:= \frac{4 - 9 \times (0 \times 5 - 8)}{(6 + 7) \times (1 + 3) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{4 + 90 + 58}{(6 + 7) \times (1 + 3)^2}$ <hr/>	$:= \frac{4 + (9 - (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{7 - (1 + (5 \times (6 - 8)))}$ $:= \frac{4 + (9 \times (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{((7 - 1) \times 5) - (6 - 8)}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{(7 - (1 \times (5 - 6))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{4 - (9 - (20 \times 3))}{7 + (1 \times (5 + 68))}$ $:= \frac{(4 + (9 \times (2 - 0))) \times 3}{7 + (1 + ((5 + 6) \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49062}{85137} := \frac{4 + (9 + 06) \times 2}{(8 + 5) \times (1 + 3) + 7}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 06 + 2)}{8 + 5 \times (1 + 3 \times 7)}$ $:= \frac{4 + 90 + 6 + 2}{8 \times 5 + 137}$ <hr/>	$:= \frac{(4 + (9 + 20)) \times 3}{(7 + (1 \times (5 + 6))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{4 + ((9 \times 20) + 3)}{(((7 + 1) \times 5) - 6) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{4 - (9 - 203)}{(7 - (1 - (5 \times 6))) \times 8}$ $:= \frac{(4 + (9 - (2 - 0))) \times 3}{(7 + (1 \times (5 - 6))) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49068}{71253} := \frac{4 \times (90 + 6) - 8}{7 \times (1 + 25) \times 3}$ <hr/>	$:= \frac{(4 - (9^2)) \times (-03)}{7 \times (1 \times (56 - 8))}$ $:= \frac{(4 - 92) \times (-03)}{(7 \times (1 \times 56)) - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49086}{52731} := \frac{490 - 86}{(5 + 2 + 7) \times 31}$	$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 + (2 - 0)) \times 3)}{(((7 - 1) \times 5) - 6) \times 8}$
	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49210}{83657} := \frac{4 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 0}{8 - 3 - 6 \times (5 - 7)}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 2 - 1) + 0}{8 - 3 + 6 + 57}$ $:= \frac{49 + 21 + 0}{8 \times (3 + 6 + 5) + 7}$ $:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 21) + 0}{(8 + 3 + 6) \times (5 + 7)}$ $:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 2) \times 10}{8 \times (36 - 5) + 7}$ $:= \frac{(4 + 9) \times 2 \times 10}{8 - (3 - 65) \times 7}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49215}{70638} := \frac{4 \times (9^2 - 1 + 5)}{(70 - 6 - 3) \times 8}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49275}{61830} := \frac{(4 - 9) \times (2 - 75)}{61 \times 8 - 30}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49280}{57316} := \frac{4 \times (9 + 2) \times 80}{5 - 7 + (3 + 1)^6}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49302}{71658} := \frac{4 + 9 + 30^2}{7 + 165 \times 8}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49305}{76812} := \frac{(49 - 30) \times 5}{(7 + 68 - 1) \times 2}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{49312}{85760} := \frac{4 \times (9 - 3) - 1^2}{8 \times 5 \times (7 - 6) + 0}$

$$:= \frac{4+9+31+2}{8+5+7+60}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 9 + 31 + 2}{(8+5+7) \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{51786} := \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0)))}{(5 + (1 - (7 - 8))) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 3))^2 + 0}{5 \times (1 \times (7 + (8 + 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)}{5 + ((1 + 7) \times (8 - 6))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 9) - 3) \times 20}{5 + ((1 + 7) \times 86)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))}{5 + (178 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times 20}{5 \times (1 - (7 - (8 \times 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))}{5 + (((1 + 7) \times 8) - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 + 3)) \times 20}{(5 - 1) \times (78 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 - 3) \times 20)}{(5 + (1 + 78)) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{56718} := \frac{4 \times (9 + 3 - 2) + 0}{5 + 6 \times 7 - 1^8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9 - 3) \times 2 + 0}{5 - (6 - 7) \times 18}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times (3 + 2) + 0}{5 \times (6 \times 7 + 1) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 3 \times 2) + 0}{(5 + 6) \times 7 \times 1 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 3) \times 20}{(5 + 6 \times 7 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{67815} := \frac{4 + (9 - (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (8 - (1 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - ((8 + 1) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 \times (8 - 15))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (8 + (1 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 + ((7 \times 8) + 15)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3^2 + 0))}{6 + (7 + (81 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (8 + 15))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - 20))}{67 + (81 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times 20}{(6 + (7 \times (8 - 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{9-3 \times (2+0)}}{6 + (78 - (1 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 - 3))^2 + 0}{6 + (781 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49368}{57120} := \frac{49 + (3 + 6) \times 8}{5 \times (7 + 1 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 9 + 368}{5 \times 7 \times 12 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49368}{70125} := \frac{(4 + 9 + 3 + 6) \times 8}{7 + (01 + 2)^5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times 3 \times 6 - 8)}{7 \times 0125}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (93 \times 6 - 8)}{(7 - 01 \times 2)^5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49380}{61725} := \frac{((4 \times 9) - 3) \times (8 - 0)}{6 \times (1 + ((7^2) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 \times 3)) - 80}{(6 + (1^{72})) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + 3)) - (8 - 0)}{6 + (1 \times ((7^2) - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 - 0)}{(6 + ((1^7) \times 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 - 3)) + 80}{(6 + (1 \times 7)) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 9) - (3 \times (8 - 0))}{6 - (1 - (7 - (2 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 93) - 80}{6 - (1 - (72 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 \times 3)) \times (8 - 0)}{(61 \times (7 - 2)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 + 3)) \times (8 - 0)}{(6 - (1^7)) \times (2^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9) \times (3 \times (8 - 0))}{(6 + (1 \times 72)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(49 + 3) \times (8 - 0)}{((6 \times 17) + 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - (9 + (3 - 80))}{6 \times (1 + (7 + (2 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 \times 3) - (8 - 0))}{(6 - (1 - (7 \times 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 \times 3) + (8 - 0))}{(6 + (1^7)) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 + 3) \times (8 - 0))}{6 \times ((1 + 7) \times (2 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 - 3) \times (8 - 0))}{6 \times (1 + (7 + (2^5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - (8 - 0)))}{(6 - (1 - (7 + 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - 80))}{(61 \times 7) - (2 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (3 \times (8 - 0)))}{(6^{1^7+2}) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (3^8 + 0))}{(6 - 1) \times ((7 + 2)^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 - (8 - 0)))}{6 + (1 \times (7 + (2 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 \times (8 - 0)))}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) - 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 + (8 - 0)))}{(6 + (1 \times (7 \times 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (38 - 0))}{(61 - (7 \times 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (93 - 80)}{(6 \times (1 + (7 + 2))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + ((9+3) \times (8-0))}{6 + (17 \times (2+5))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 \times (3 \times (8-0)))}{(6 + (1 \times (7^2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + (3 - (8-0)))}{6 + (1 \times (7 + (2-5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + (3 + (8-0)))}{6 - (1 + (7 - (2^5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + (3 + 80))}{6 \times (1 + (7 \times 2 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{49 \times (3 \times (8-0))}{6 \times (1 \times ((7^2) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{49 + (3 - (8-0))}{6 + (1 \times (7 \times (2+5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{49 + (3 + (8-0))}{6 - (1 - (7 \times (2 \times 5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49518}{67203} := \frac{4 + 9 \times 5 + 1 - 8}{(6 - 7 + 20) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{49 + 5 \times (1 - 8)}{6 + 7 + 2 \times 03}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49530}{71628} := \frac{4 \times (95 - 30)}{(7 \times (1 + 6) - 2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49536}{71208} := \frac{4 + 9 \times (5 - 3) - 6}{7 + 1 \times 2 \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (5 - 3) - 6)}{71 - 2 + 0 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(49 + 5 \times 3) \times 6}{(71 - 2) \times 08}$$

$$:= \frac{49 - 5 \times (3 - 6)}{7 \times 12 + 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49536}{81270} := \frac{(49 + 5 \times 3) \times 6}{(8 + 1^2) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{(9-5-3) \times 6}}{8 \times 12 \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4^{9+5-3-6}}{8 \times (1+2) \times 70}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times 5 + 3) \times 6}{(8-1) \times 270}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9+5) \times 3 \times 6}{(8-1 \times 2) \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49572}{83106} := \frac{4 \times (9 + 5 \times (7 - 2))}{(8 + 3 \times 10) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(49 - 5) \times 7 - 2}{8^3 + 1^{06}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49632}{81075} := \frac{4 \times 96 - 32}{(8 + 107) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49651}{70238} := \frac{(4 + 9) \times 6 + 5 - 1}{70 \times 2 - 3 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49651}{78023} := \frac{4 + (9 + (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 - (8 + (0 - 23))}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 - 9) \times 6) + 51}{((7 + (8 - 0)) \times 2) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (6 - 5))) - 1}{7 - (8 \times (0 - (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + (6 \times (5 + 1)))}{7 \times (8 - ((0 \times 2) - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (((9 - 6) \times 5) - 1)}{7 + (80 - (2 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + (6 + 51))}{7 + (80 + 23)}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times ((9 \times (6 + 5)) - 1)}{7 \times (80 + (2^3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 6)) \times 51}{(7 \times 80) - (2 - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49680}{57132} := \frac{4 + 96 - 80}{5 + 7 + 13 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9 - 6) \times 80}{5 + 71 \times 3^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 9 + 6) \times 80}{5 \times (7 - 1) \times 3 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 6 + 80)}{5 + (7 - 1)^3 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49708}{62135} := \frac{((4 \times 9) - (7 - 0)) \times 8}{(62 - (1 + 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((4 \times 9) + 70) \times 8}{(6^2) + ((1 + 3)^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (9 - (7 - 0)))^8}{((6 - (2 \times 1))^3) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))) - 8}{62 + (1 \times (3^5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) + 8}{6 \times ((2 + (1^3)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 8}{6 + (2^{1^3+5})}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + 70)) + 8}{(6 + 21) \times (3 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + 70)) - 8}{((6 \times 2) - 1) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 9) - (7 \times (-08))}{((6^2) - 13) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times 970) + 8}{(6^2) \times 135}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{9-7+0}) \times 8}{(6 + (2 \times 13)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{9-7+0}) + 8}{6 \times (2 + (1 - (3 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 8}{6 \times (2 + (1 \times (3 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 8}{((6^2) + (1 + 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(49 - (7 - 0)) \times 8}{6 \times (2 \times (1 \times 35))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - 97) \times (-08)}{62 \times (1 \times (3 \times 5))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4 - ((9 - 70) \times 8)}{((6 \times 21) - 3) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (9 \times (7 \times (0 \times 8)))}{6 + (2 - (1 - (3 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^8)}{((6 - 2) \times (1 + 3)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{6 + (2 - (1 \times (3 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 8)))}{(6 + (2 + (1^3))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (7 \times (-08)))}{(62 + (1 \times 3)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 - (7 + (-08)))}{(6 + (2 - (1 - 3))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(6 + (2 + 1)) \times 35} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{62 + (13 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (7 - (-08)))}{6 \times (2 + (13 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (7 + (-08)))}{6 - (2 - (1 + 35))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (97 - (-08))}{((6^2) - 1) \times (3 \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{4^{9-7+0 \times 8}}{6 - (2 \times (1 - (3 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 8)}{((6^2 \times 1) - 3) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(6 - (2 - (1^3))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (9 + (7 - (-08)))}{(6 + (2 - (1^3))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (9 + (7 + (-08)))}{6 + (2 - (1 - (3 + 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49712}{83650} := \frac{(4+9) \times 712}{(8-3)^6 - 50}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{49725}{63180} &:= \frac{4 - 9 + 7 \times 25}{6^3 \times 1^8 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (9 + 7)^2 - 5}{6 \times 3 \times 18 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 72) \times 5}{(6 - 3) \times 180} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49731}{52608} := \frac{4 \times (9 + 7 \times 3) + 1}{(5 \times 2 + 6) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49761}{52380} := \frac{4 \times (9 \times 7 - 6 \times 1)}{5 \times 2 \times 3 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 + 9) \times 76 \times 1}{(5 + 2^3) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{49 \times 76 \times 1}{(52 - 3) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49803}{65127} := \frac{4 + 9 + 8 \times 0 \times 3}{6 + 5 + 1 - 2 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(-4 + 9 + 8) \times 03}{6 + (5 \times (1 \times (2 + 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + 8) - 03}{6 - (5 - (12 \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{4 - 9 + 80 + 3}{6 \times (5 \times 1 \times 2 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9) \times 8 + 0 \times 3}{6 - 5 \times (1 - 27)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9) \times (80 - 3)}{651 \times 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{62370} := \frac{498 - 1 - 5}{623 - 7 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(49 - 8) \times 15}{(6 + 2 + 3) \times 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{62730} := \frac{4 - 9 + 81 + 5}{6 \times (2 \times 7 + 3) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (8 + 1) \times 5)}{62 + 7 \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{73062} := \frac{4 + 9 + 8 - 1 - 5}{7 + 3 - 0 + 6 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + 9 - 8 \times (1 - 5)}{7 - 3 + 062}$$

$$:= \frac{4 \times (9 - 8) \times 15}{7 + 3^{06-2}}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 8 \times 1) \times 5}{7 \times (30 - 6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{49 + 81 + 5}{7 \times 30 - 6 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 8) \times 15}{7 \times (30 + 6^2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{76302} := \frac{(49 - 8) \times 15}{7 \times 6 + 30^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49830}{56172} := \frac{(4 - 9) \times (8 - 30)}{(56 - 1 + 7) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{4 + (9 + 8) \times 3 + 0}{5 \times (6 - 1 + 7) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50172}{96348} := \frac{50 + 17^2}{9 - 6 + 3^4 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50184}{67932} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 8 \times 4}{6 + 7 \times (9 + 3 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{62478} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 93}{6 \times (24 + 7) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{76824} := \frac{501 + 9 - 3}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{78624} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 93}{7 \times 8 \times (6 + 2 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{82764} := \frac{501 + 9 - 3}{8^2 \times (7 + 6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{86427} := \frac{501+9-3}{864+2+7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (0 \times 4 + 63)}{(7-1 \times 2) \times 89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{89712} := \frac{((50-4) \times 6) + 3}{8 \times ((9 \times 7) - 1^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{504-63}{7 \times 1^2 \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 3}{8 + (9 \times (7 + (1^2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50196}{84372} := \frac{50-1 \times 9+6}{8-4+3+72}$$

$$:= \frac{(5+04) \times 63}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 3}{8 \times (9 - (7 \times (1^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{50 \times 4 \times 6 - 3}{(7+12) \times 89}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04)) \times (6 \times 3)}{8 \times (9 \times (7 - (1 + 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50274}{81396} := \frac{5 \times (-02+7) - 4}{8-1+3^{9-6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{72891} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 3}{(7^2) + (8 + (9 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04)) \times (6 + 3)}{8 \times (9 + (7 + (1 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{50 - 2^{7-4}}{8 + (1^3 + 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 3}{7 + ((2 \times 8) - (9 + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04)) \times 63}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{50+2+7+4}{8+1-3+96}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04)) \times (6 + 3)}{(7 - (2 - 8)) \times (9 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04))^{6+3}}{8 \times ((9^{7+1}) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{50+2+74}{(8-1+3 \times 9) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (-04)) \times 63}{728+91}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (0 - 46)) \times 3}{8 \times ((9 + 7 + 1) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50371}{82964} := \frac{5 \times (0 \times 3 + 7) - 1}{(8 + 2 \times (9 - 6)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (-04)) \times 63}{(7 + (2 - 8)) \times 91}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (0 + (4 \times 6))) - 3}{(8 + (97 - 1)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (03 + 7) + 1}{(8 - 2 + 9 + 6) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(50 \times (4 \times 6)) - 3}{7 \times ((2^8) - (9 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (-04)) \times (6^3)}{8 \times ((9 + 7) \times (1 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{50 + 3 \times (7 - 1)}{8 \times 2 \times (9 - 6 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(50 + (4 - 6)) \times 3}{((7 + (2 \times 8)) \times 9) + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (-04)) \times 63}{8 \times (9 - (7 - 12))}$$

$$:= \frac{5^{03} - 7 + 1}{8 + 2 \times 96 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + (6 \times 3)))}{7 + (2 \times (8 + (9 - 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(50 + (4 - 6)) \times 3}{(8 \times (9 - (7 \times 1)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (-03 + 71)}{8 \times ((2 + 9) \times 6 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 3)))}{7 + (2 + (8 + (9 \times 1)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(50 + 4) \times 63}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 12))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + 63))}{7 - (2 - (8 + 91))}$$

$$:= \frac{(50 + 46) \times 3}{8^{9-7+1^2}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (46 + 3))}{7 - (2 - ((8 \times 9) + 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + (6 \times 3)))}{8 - (9 - (7 \times (1 \times 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50394}{72186} := \frac{50 - (3 - 9) \times 4}{7 \times 2 \times 1 \times 8 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((0 \times 4) + (6 \times 3))}{(7 - (2 - 8)) \times (9 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 3)))}{8 \times (9 + (7 - 12))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 3)))}{(7 \times (28 + 9)) + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (4 + 63))}{8 \times (9 + (7 \times (1^2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50421}{63798} := \frac{50 - 4 + 2 + 1}{6 + 3 \times (7 + 9) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{50 + (46 + 3)}{72 + ((8 \times 9) - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (0 - (46 + 3))}{89 + (7 \times (1^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{504 \times (6 + 3)}{728 \times (9 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((0 \times 4) + (6 \times 3))}{(8 + (9 \times (7 + 1))) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{71289} := \frac{(5 - 04) \times 63}{(7 + 1 + 2) \times 8 + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{504 - 63}{7 \times (2 + (89 \times 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((0 \times 4) + 63)}{8 \times ((9 \times (7 + 1)) - 2)}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{5 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) + 3))}{8 \times (9 + (7 \times (1 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 3)))}{(89 + 71) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{50 \times (4 \times (6 \times 3))}{(8 + (9 \times (7 + 1)))^2} \\
 := \frac{50 + (4 - (6 \times 3))}{8^{9-7 \times 1^2}} \\
 := \frac{50 + (4 + (6^3))}{8 \times ((9 \times 7) - (1 + 2))} \\
 := \frac{50 + (46 + 3)}{(8 + (9 + 71)) \times 2} \\
 := \frac{504 - (6 \times 3)}{8 \times (9 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{504 + (6^3)}{8 \times ((9 + 71) \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{504 - 63}{8 \times (97 + (1^2))} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50481}{79632} := \frac{(5 + 04) \times 8 - 1}{7 \times (9 + 6 + 3 - 2)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50672}{91843} := \frac{5 + 06 + 7 - 2}{9 + 1 \times 8 + 4 \times 3} \\
 := \frac{5 - 06 + 7^2}{91 + 8 - 4 \times 3} \\
 := \frac{50 + 6 \times (7 - 2)}{9 \times (1 + 8) + 4^3} \\
 := \frac{50 + 6 + 72}{(9 - 1) \times (8 \times 4 - 3)} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 067) \times 2}{9 + 1 \times 84 \times 3} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50692}{81374} := \frac{5 - 0 + 69 + 2}{81 + 37 + 4} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50732}{84169} := \frac{5 + 07 + 32}{8 - 4 + 1 \times 69} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50764}{91238} := \frac{(50 - 7 - 6) \times 4}{(9 - 1 \times 2) \times 38} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50784}{91632} := \frac{50 + (7 - 8) \times 4}{9 \times 1 \times (6 + 3) + 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50862}{97314} := \frac{(50 + 8) \times 6 - 2}{9 \times (73 + 1) - 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50963}{74128} := \frac{5 - (0 - (9 - (6 - 3)))}{7 + (4 - (1 + (2 - 8)/))} \\
 := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 9) - 6)) \times 3}{(7 - (4 - (1 + 2))) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{50 - (9 - (6 - 3))}{(7 + (4 - (1 + 2))) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{5 - (0 - (9 + 63))}{7 \times (4 \times (12 - 8))} \\
 := \frac{50 + (96 - 3)}{((7 \times (4 \times 1)) - 2) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{50 + (9 + (6^3))}{(7 + (41 + 2)) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{5 - (0 - 963)}{(7 + 4) \times 128} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50964}{87132} := \frac{50 - 9 - 6 - 4}{8 \times (7 - 1) + 3 + 2} \\
 := \frac{50 + (9 - 6) \times 4}{(8 \times 7 \times 1 - 3) \times 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50976}{81243} := \frac{5 \times 09 - 7 - 6}{8 \times 1 \times (2 + 4) + 3} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{5 + 097 - 6}{81 + 24 \times 3} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51084}{72369} := \frac{(5 - (10 - 8)) \times 4}{7 - (2 + (3 - (6 + 9)))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (1^{08})) \times 4}{7 + ((2 \times (3 + 6)) + 9)} \\
 := \frac{(5 - (1 + (-08))) \times 4}{(7 \times (2 + (3 + 6))) - 9} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((1 - (-08)) \times 4)}{(7 \times 2 + 3) \times (6 + 9)} \\
 := \frac{(5 - (1 - 0)) \times 84}{7 \times (2 - (3 - 69))} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((10 + 8) \times 4)}{7 + ((2^3 + 6) - 9)} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (1 - 0)) \times 84}{((7 + 2)^3) - (6 + 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51084}{76329} := \frac{(51 - 08) \times 4}{7 \times (6 + 32) - 9} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51240}{67893} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4 + 0}{67 - 8 - 9 + 3} \\
 := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 24 + 0}{(6 + 7 \times 8 - 9) \times 3} \\
 := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 40}{67 \times 8 - 9 + 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51240}{98637} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2 \times (4 - 0)))}{9 + (8 + (6 \times (3 + 7)))} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2^4 + 0))}{98 + (63 - 7)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (24 - 0))}{(9 + (8 \times (6 - 3))) \times 7} \\
 := \frac{(5 - (1^2)) \times 40}{(9 - 86) \times (3 - 7)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((1^2) \times 40)}{(9 \times ((8 + 6) \times 3)) + 7} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (1 \times 2)) \times 40}{98 + (63 \times 7)} \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2 \times 40))}{(9 \times 86) + (3 - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 + (3 + 94))}{8 - (0 - 762)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51243}{87609} := \frac{5 - 1 + 24 + 3}{8 \times 7 + 6 - 09}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((1 + (3 \times 9)) \times 4)}{80 \times (7 + (6 - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51624}{70983} := \frac{((5 \times (1 \times 6)) + 2) \times 4}{(7 - (-09)) \times (8 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + (1 + 6))^2) \times 4}{709 + 83}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51268}{97043} := \frac{5 + 1 + 2 + 6 \times 8}{9 \times 7 + 043}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{67932} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4 + 08}{6 + 7 + (9 + 3) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (1 - (6 + 2))) \times 4}{70 - (9 - (8 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 14 \times 08}{6 + 7 + 9^3 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 16) + (2 \times 4)}{70 + ((9 + 8) \times 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{79632} := \frac{51 \times (4 + 08)}{79 \times (6 + 3 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (1 + (6^2))) \times 4}{7 \times (0 + (9 + (8 \times 3)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51293}{74608} := \frac{5 \times (1 - (2 - (9 + 3)))}{74 + (6 - (0 \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{51 + 408}{79 + 632}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (1 + (6 + 2))) \times 4}{7 \times ((0 \times 9) + (8 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (1 - (2 \times 9))) \times 3}{(7 \times 4) + (60 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{51 - 4 \times 0 \times 8}{7 - 9 + (6 + 3)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 16) \times 24}{7 \times (0 + (9 \times (8 + 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (12 \times (9 - 3))}{7 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 1) \times (6 \times (2^4))}{7 - (0 - (9 + (8^3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (1 - (2 + 93))}{(7 - 4) \times (6 \times (08))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{92736} := \frac{51 + 408}{9 \times (2^7 - 36)}$$

$$:= \frac{(51 \times (6 - 2)) + 4}{70 + (9 \times (8 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 - ((2 - 9) \times 3))}{(7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{51 \times (4 - 0 \times 8)}{92 \times (7 + 3 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (1 - (6 + (2 - 4)))}{7 - (0 - (9 - (8 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 + (29 \times 3))}{(74 + (6 - 0)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{51 + 4 \times 0 \times 8}{9^2 - 7 + 3 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 \times (6 - (2 - 4)))}{70 + (9 - (8 \times 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (1 + (2 + (9^3)))}{(74 + 60) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 140 + 8}{9 + 273 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 \times (6 \times 24))}{7 - (0 - 983)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51394}{80762} := \frac{5 - (1 \times (3 - (9 - 4)))}{8 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51480}{67392} := \frac{51 - 4 + 8 + 0}{6 + 73 - 9 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (16 + (2 \times 4))}{((7 \times (09)) - 8) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (1 + ((3 - 9) \times 4))}{(8 \times (07)) - (6 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (14 + 8) + 0}{6 \times (7 \times 3 - 9) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (1 - (6 - (2^4)))}{7 + (0 - (9 - (8 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (1 + (39 + 4))}{8 - (0 - (7 + 62))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 + 4 \times 8) + 0}{6^{7+3-9+2}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (1 + (62 + 4))}{7 - (0 - (9 + 83))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (1 \times (3 + 9))) - 4}{8 \times ((07) + (6 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (1 - 4 + 80)}{6 \times (73 + 9 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51642}{83790} := \frac{51 + (6 + 4)^2}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - ((1^3) - 94)}{80 + (76 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(51 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (7 - 3 + 92)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 13) - 9) \times 4}{8 \times (((07 \times 6) + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 1480}{6 \times (7 - 3) \times 9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51680}{97432} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 68 + 0}{9 \times (7 + 4^3) + 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51832}{64790} := \frac{((5-1) \times (8 \times 3))^2}{((6-4)^7) \times 90} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (1 - (8 \times 3))) \times 2}{6 + (4 \times (7 + (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (1^8)) \times 32}{(6+4) \times (7 + (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (1^8))^{3+2}}{(6^4) - (7 + (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (1 + (8 - 3))) + 2}{(6 \times 4) + (7 + (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times 18) - (3 \times 2)}{6 + ((4 + 7) \times (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times 18) + (3 \times 2)}{6 \times (4 + (7 + (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + ((1^8) \times 3))^2}{64 + (7 + (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + 1)^{8-3-2}}{(6+4-7) \times 90} \\ & := \frac{5 - ((1 - 8) \times (3^2))}{6 - (4 + (7 - 90))} \\ & := \frac{5 - (1 - (8 \times (3 \times 2)))}{6 - (4 - (7 \times (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((1 + (8 - 3)) \times 2)}{(6 \times (4 + 7)) + (9 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 + (8 - (3 + 2)))}{6 + ((4 \times 7) - (9 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{5 + (1 \times (8 - (3^2)))}{((6 - 4) \times 7) - (9 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{51 \times (8 \times (3 \times 2))}{(6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 90} \\ & := \frac{518 - (3 \times 2)}{6 + (4 + (7 \times 90))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 - (4 - 0)))}{67 - (39 + 2)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 + (4 - 0)))}{6 + ((7 - 3) \times (9 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (18 - (4 - 0))}{6 + (7 - (3 - (9^2)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times 8)) + 40}{6 + (7 \times (3 + (9 + 2)))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (18 + (4 - 0))}{6 - (7 - ((3 + 9)^2))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 \times (4 - 0)))}{(67 \times 3) + (9 - 2)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((1 + 8) \times (4 - 0))}{6 \times ((7 \times 3) + (9 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 + 40))}{(6 + 7) \times ((3 + 9) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{(5 + (1 + 8)) \times 40}{6 - (7 - ((3 \times 9)^2))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (18 + 40)}{(6 + 7) \times ((3 \times 9) + 2)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (84 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (3 + (9^2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{5 - (1 - (8 + 76))}{(9 - (4 - 3)) \times 20} \\ & := \frac{5 + (1 + (87 + 6))}{9 \times (4 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (1 + (8 + (7 + 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3)) \times 20} \\ & := \frac{5 - (1 - (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times 87)) - 6}{(9 + 4) \times (3 \times 20)} \\ & := \frac{5 - (1 - 876)}{(9 - 4) \times 320} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51948}{60372} := \frac{51 - 9 + 4 \times 8}{(6 + 037) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{5 - (1 - 9 + 4) \times 8}{60 - 3 - 7 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51948}{70362} := \frac{5 \times 194 - 8}{7 + 036^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51840}{73926} := \frac{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 40}{7 \times 392 - 6} \\ & \frac{51840}{79632} := \frac{5 \times 18 \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (9 \times (6 + 3) - 2)} \\ & \frac{51840}{92736} := \frac{5 + 1 + 84 + 0}{9 + 2 \times 73 + 6} \\ & \frac{51840}{97632} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 4) + 0}{97 + 6 \times 3 - 2} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 40)}{9 + 7 \times 63 + 2} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 18 \times 4 + 0}{9 \times 76 - 3 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51972}{63048} := \frac{(5 - (1 - 9) \times 7) \times 2}{6 \times (30 - 4) - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51984}{70623} := \frac{(5 - 1 + 9 \times 8) \times 4}{7 \times (062 - 3)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 19 \times 8 \times 4}{70 \times (62 - 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52038}{67914} := \frac{520 + 3 + 8}{679 + 14} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51840}{67392} := \frac{(5 + (1 \times 8)) \times 40}{(6 - (7 - (3 \times 9)))^2} \\ & := \frac{5 + (1 + (8 - (4 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (3 + (9 + 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{51876}{94320} := \frac{5 + (18 - (7 - 6))}{(9 - (4 + 3)) \times 20} \\ & := \frac{5 + (1 \times (8 + (7 \times 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3))^2 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52041}{68973} := \frac{5 + 204 \times 1}{6 - 8 \times 9 + 7^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52073}{89614} := \frac{(5+20) \times 7 - 3}{8 \times (9 + (6+1) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52380}{74196} := \frac{5 + 2 \times 3 \times 80}{741 - 9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52438}{61790} := \frac{5 + (2^4 + 3) \times 8}{6 + 179 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52104}{93687} := \frac{52 \times (10 + 4)}{93 \times (6 + 8) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52394}{70618} := \frac{5 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 4}{7 + 06 + 18}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52470}{63918} := \frac{52 - 4 + 7 + 0}{6 - 3 + (9 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52143}{87096} := \frac{5 + 2 \times 1 \times 43}{8 \times 7 + 096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52407}{93168} := \frac{5 + (2 + (4 - (-07)))}{9 - ((3 \times (1 - 6)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 \times (4 - (-07)))}{9 - (3 \times (1 - (6 + 8)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52481}{69730} := \frac{52 \times (4 \times 8 + 1)}{(69 + 7) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52164}{79380} := \frac{(5 + 2 + 16) \times 4}{7 \times (9 + 3 + 8) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (2 - (40 - 7))}{(9 \times (3 - (1 - 6))) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52610}{89437} := \frac{5 - (2 - (6 + (1 - 0)))}{8 + (9 - (4 + (3 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 + (40 + 7))}{(9 + (3 \times 1^6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^2) - (6 - (1 - 0))}{8 + (9 - (4 - (3 \times 7)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52173}{94860} := \frac{(5 \times 2 + 1) \times (7 - 3)}{94 - 8 - 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 - 2)^4 + 0) \times 7}{(9 - 3) \times 168}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 - (1 - 0)))}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 3) - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 - 1 + 7 + 3)}{(9 - 4) \times 8 + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 2)^{4+0 \times 7}}{9 \times (3 - (1 - (6 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + (1 - 0)))}{(8 + (9 \times (4 - 3))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 21 + 73}{94 + 86 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 \times (40 + 7))}{(9 - (3 - 16)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 \times 10))}{(8 + 94) \times (3 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(52 - 1 - 7) \times 3}{(9 - 4) \times 8 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((2^4 + 0) \times 7)}{(9 \times ((3 + 1) \times 6)) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (26 \times (1 - 0))}{(((8 \times 9) + 4) \times 3) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^2 - 1) \times 7 - 3}{(9 + 4 - 8) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (2 - (4 - 0)))^7}{(9^{3-1}) \times (6 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 26) + 10}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + (3 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 2 \times (1 + 7^3)}{(9 + 4 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((2^4 + 0) - 7)}{9 + (3 + (1 \times 68))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + 10))}{8 \times (9 + (4 + (3 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 + 407)}{(93 - (1^6)) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{((5^2) - 6) \times 10}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 3) + 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52316}{87904} := \frac{5 - 2 + 316}{8 \times (7 \times 9 + 04)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^2) + 407}{(9 - 3) \times (16 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((2 + 6) \times 10)}{(8 + 9) \times (4 \times (3 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{52 + 407}{(9 + (3 \times 1)) \times 68}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (26 - 10)}{8 \times (9 + (4 - (3 - 7)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52360}{91784} := \frac{5 \times (23 - 6) + 0}{9 + 17 \times 8 + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2^3 + 60)}{9 - 1 + 7 \times 84}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52416}{79380} := \frac{(5 \times 2)^4 - 16}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52614}{70389} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times (6 + 1) + 4}{7 + 03 + 89}$$

$$:= \frac{52 + 61 \times 4}{7 + 0389}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52630}{89471} := \frac{5 + ((2 \times 6) + (3 - 0))}{8 - ((9 \times (4 - 7)) + 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 - (3 - 0)))}{8 + ((9 \times 4) + (7 \times 1))} \\ & := \frac{5 + (2 + (63 - 0))}{(8 \times 9) + (47 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2 + (6 \times (3 - 0)))}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + 7 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + 30))}{(8 + 94) \times (7 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((2 + 6) \times (3 - 0))}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + 7 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times 26) + 30}{8 \times (((9 - 4) \times 7) - 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (26 + 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (4 \times (7 \times 1))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((2^6) + 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (47 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (2 - 6)) \times 30}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 7) - 1)} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (2^6)) - 30}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 7) + 1)} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (2^6)) + 30}{(89 - 4) \times (7 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{((5 \times 2) + 6) \times 30}{8 \times (94 + 7 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2^{6-3+0})}{(8 \times 9) + (4 - (7 + 1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52710}{96384} := \frac{5 \times (2 + 7) - 10}{(9 \times 6 - 38) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (27 + 1) + 0}{(9 + 6 - 3 - 8)^4} \\ & := \frac{5^2 \times 7 \times 1 + 0}{(9 + 63 + 8) \times 4} \\ & := \frac{5 \times 2^7 - 10}{96 \times 3 \times (8 - 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52710}{98643} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 7 \times 10}{9 + 8 + 6^4 - 3} \\ & := \frac{(5 - 2) \times 7 \times 10}{9 \times (8 \times 6 - 4) - 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52716}{93840} := \frac{5^2 \times 7 + 16}{(93 - 8) \times 4 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52730}{89641} := \frac{5 - ((2 - 7) \times (3 - 0))}{8 - (9 + (6 - 41))} \\ & := \frac{5 + (2 - (7 - 30))}{(8 + 9) \times (6 - (4 - 1))} \\ & := \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + 30))}{8 + ((9 + 6) \times (4 \times 1))} \\ & := \frac{527 + (3 - 0)}{896 + (4 + 1)} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2 + (7 + (3 - 0)))}{(8 \times 9) + (6 \times (4 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{89 + (6 \times (4 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2^{7-3+0})}{8 \times ((9 \times (6 - 4)) - 1)} \\ & := \frac{((5 \times 2) - 7) \times 30}{(8 \times (9 + (6 + 4))) + 1} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{8 + (9 \times (6 \times (4 - 1)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - 2) \times (7 \times 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (64 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (2 - 7)) \times 30}{(8 + 9) \times (6 \times (4 + 1))} \\ & := \frac{(5^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{(8 + 9) \times ((6 \times 4) + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52731}{86940} := \frac{527 + 31}{(8 + 6 + 9) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52734}{81906} := \frac{5^2 + 73 - 4}{8 \times 19 - 06} \\ & \frac{52734}{91086} := \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + (3 \times 4)))}{(9 + 10) \times (8 - 6)} \\ & := \frac{5 + (2 \times (7 + (3 + 4)))}{9 - (1 \times (0 - (8 \times 6)))} \\ & := \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + 34))}{(9 \times 10) - (8 + 6)} \\ & := \frac{5 + (2 \times ((7 \times 3) + 4))}{9 - (1 \times (0 - 86))} \\ & := \frac{((5^2) \times 7) + 34}{(9 + 10)^{8-6}} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (27 + 3)) + 4}{(9 + 10) \times (8 + 6)} \\ & := \frac{((5 \times 27) - 3) \times 4}{(9 + 10) \times (8 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52780}{91364} := \frac{5 \times (2 + 7 \times 8) + 0}{(9 - 1)^3 - 6 - 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52836}{97104} := \frac{5 + 2^{8+3-6}}{(9 + 7 + 1) \times 04} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52839}{74160} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 8 + 39}{74 + 1 \times 6 + 0} \\ & := \frac{(52 + 8) \times 3 - 9}{(7 - 4 + 1) \times 60} \\ & := \frac{(52 + 8 - 3) \times 9}{(7 + 4 + 1) \times 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{52893}{76401} := \frac{5 + (2^{8-9+3})}{7 + (6 - (4 \times (0 \times 1)))} \\ & := \frac{5 + (2 + (8 + (9 + 3)))}{(7 - 6) \times (40 - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((2 \times (8 + 9)) - 3)}{7 + (6 + (40 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 \times (8 + (9 + 3)))}{(7 + 6) \times (4 - (-01))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 2) + (8 + 9)) \times 3}{76 + (40 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(52 + 8) \times (9 - 3)}{(7 + 6) \times (40 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (2 \times (8 + 9))) \times 3}{(7 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))) + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52904}{87136} := \frac{5 + 29 - 0 \times 4}{8 \times 7 \times 1^{36}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 + 9) - 04}{(8 - 7 + 13) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 29) \times 04}{8 \times 7 \times (1 - 3 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52910}{78364} := \frac{5 + 2 \times 9 \times 10}{(7 + 8) \times 3 \times 6 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52947}{80136} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times (9 + 4 \times 7)}{80 \times (13 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 + (9 - 4) \times 7)}{8 \times (-01 + 36)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 29 - 4 + 7}{8 \times (013 - 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52974}{61803} := \frac{5 + ((2 \times 9) - (7 + 4))}{6 + (1 \times (8 - (0 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 4))}{(6 + (1^8 + 0)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (2 - (9 \times (7 - 4)))}{(6 + 1) \times (8 + (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (2^{9-7})) \times 4}{(6 + (1 \times (8 - 0))) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (2 + 9)) \times (7 - 4)}{61 - (8 + (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 - (9 - 74))}{6 + (1 + (80 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 + (9 + 74))}{(6 \times (18 - 0)) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 + (97 + 4))}{6 \times (18 - (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (29 - (7 \times 4))}{6 + (1^{803})}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (2 + ((9 + 7) \times 4))}{(6 - 1) \times (80 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5^2) \times (9 + 7)) - 4}{6 \times (1 \times (80 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (2 + ((9 \times 7) - 4))}{(6 + 1) \times (8 - (-03))}$$

$$:= \frac{(52 - (9 + 7)) \times 4}{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times (03))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53064}{91872} := \frac{5 \times (3 + 064)}{(9 + 1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53124}{97860} := \frac{5 + 31 - 2 + 4}{9 - 7 + 8 + 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53148}{70692} := \frac{5^3 - 14 - 8}{70 + 69 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53169}{80472} := \frac{5 \times (3 + 1) + 6 \times 9}{8 \times (0 \times 4 + 7 \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 1) \times 6 - 9}{(8 + 04) \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{53 - 1 - 6 - 9}{(8 - 04) \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53176}{92480} := \frac{53 - 1^7 - 6}{(9 - 2 \times 4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 - 1^7)^6}{(9 + 2 + 4) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 3 \times (1 - 7)) \times 6}{(9 - 2 - 4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 317) \times 6}{(9 - 2) \times 480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53217}{84096} := \frac{53 + 21 + 7}{8 + 40 \times (9 - 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{5^3 \times 2 \times 1 - 7}{(8 - 4) \times 096}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3^{(2-1) \times 7}}{8 \times 40 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53217}{94608} := \frac{5 \times (3^2 \times 1^7)}{94 - (6 - (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (32 + 17)}{94 - (6 + (-08))}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + (21 + 7)}{9 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) - (2 - (1 - 7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) + (2 - (1^7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3^{2+1^7})}{(9 - 4) \times (6 \times (08))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (32 \times 1)) - 7}{(94 - 60) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (32 - 1)) + 7}{9 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) + 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53240}{79618} := \frac{(53 + 2) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (9 \times 6 + 1 - 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53274}{81960} := \frac{5 + (3 + (27 + 4))}{8 + (1 - (9 - 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - (2 + 74))}{8 \times (1 \times (9 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + (2 + (7 - 4)))}{(8 \times (1 + 9)) - 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 3) + (2 + 74)}{(8 \times (1 + 9)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (27 - 4))}{8 \times (19 + (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) + (2 \times 74)}{(8 - (1^9)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 3) - 2) \times (7 \times 4)}{8 \times (1 + (9 + 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 3)^2) + (9 + 8)}{(7 \times (10 + 6)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (3 + 2)) - (9 - 8)}{7 + (1 - (0 - (6 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) - (2 - (9 \times 8))}{(71 + (-06)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) + (2 - (9 - 8))}{7 \times (1 \times (0 + (6 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^3) + (2 + (9 + 8))}{(7 + (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + ((3 - 2)^9)) \times 8}{(7 + (1 - 0))^{6-4}}$$

$$:= \frac{(53 - (2 + 9)) \times 8}{7 \times (1 \times (0 + 64))}$$

$$:= \frac{(53 \times 2) - (9 - 8)}{7 \times (10 \times (6 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(53 - 29) \times 8}{((7 \times 10) - 6) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - ((3 - (2 + 9)) \times 8)}{(7 + (10 + 6)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - ((3 \times (2 - 9)) + 8)}{(7 - (10^6)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - ((3 - 29) \times 8)}{71 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - ((2 \times 9) - 8))}{7 - (1 + (0 - (6 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - (2 - (9 - 8)))}{7 - (1 - (0 - (6 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - (2 \times (9 + 8)))}{(7 - (1 + (-06))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - (2 + (9 + 8)))}{7 \times ((10^6) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - (29 + 8))}{(7 - (1 \times (-06))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 \times (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 6) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3^{2 \times (9-8)})}{(7 \times 10) - (6 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((3 \times (2 \times 9)) - 8)}{(7 \times 10) - (6 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((3 \times 29) - 8)}{7 \times ((10 - 6) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 - (2 \times (9 - 8)))}{7 + (1 - (0 \times 64))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + (2 - (9 - 8)))}{7 + ((10^6) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + (2 \times (9 + 8)))}{(7 + (1 - (-06))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + (2 + (9 + 8)))}{(7 - (1 - 0))^{6-4}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + (2 + 98))}{(7 - (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (3 + 298)}{(7 + 10) \times (6 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (32 + (9 + 8))}{7 + (1 - (0 - 64))}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + ((2 \times 9) - 8)}{7 \times (10 + (6 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + (2 \times (9 + 8))}{(7 \times (10 + 6)) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{532 - (9 - 8)}{710 - (6 - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{76140} := \frac{5 + (3 - (2 - (9 - 8)))}{7 + (6 + (1 - (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 - ((2 \times 9) + 8))}{7 - (6 + (1 - 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 3) + (2 \times (9 + 8))}{7 \times (6 + (1 \times (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + (2 + (9 - 8))}{(7 - (6 - 1)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + ((2 \times 9) - 8)}{76 + (14 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (3 + (2 - 98))}{7 \times (6 + (14 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (3 - 2)) \times 98}{(7 + (6 + 1)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3 + 2) \times 98}{7 \times ((6 - 1) \times 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 3) - 2) \times 98}{(7 + 6) \times 140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53276}{98140} := \frac{5 - 3 - 2 + 76}{(9 - 8) \times 140}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 3 + 2) \times 76}{(9 + 8) \times 140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53284}{79061} := \frac{(5 + 3^2 \times 8) \times 4}{7 + 90 \times (6 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{532 + 84}{7 + 906 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53289}{67041} := \frac{5 - 3 + 2 + 89}{6 + 70 + 41}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3^2 + 8 + 9}{(6 + 7) \times (04 - 1)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{70641} := \frac{5^3 + 2 - 9 + 8}{7 \times 06 \times 4 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{71064} := \frac{((5 \times (3 \times 2)) + 9) \times 8}{(7 \times (10 \times 6)) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times (3^2)) - 9) \times 8}{(7 - (1 - 0)) \times 64}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 3) \times 2) + (9 + 8)}{(7 + (10 - 6)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (3^2)) \times 98}{7 \times ((6+1) \times 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{(53 - (2+9)) \times 8}{(7 + (6-1)) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53406}{71982} := \frac{5 + 3 \times 4 + 06}{7 - 1 + 9 + 8 \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3^4 + 06}{7 \times (1 + 9 + 8) - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 + 406}{7 \times (1 + 9) \times 8 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53406}{81972} := \frac{53 - 4 - 06}{8 + 1 \times 9 + 7^2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3^4 + 0 \times 6}{8 - (1 - 9 \times 7) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 3^4) \times 06}{8 \times 1 \times (97 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 40) \times 6}{8 + 1972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53418}{79206} := \frac{53 - (4 - 1) \times 8}{7 - 9 \times (2 - 06)}$$

$$:= \frac{5^3 + 41 + 8}{(7 \times 9 - 20) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 3^4 + 1^8}{7 \times (92 - 06)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{71928} := \frac{5 \times (3 - 4) + 60}{71 + 9 + 2 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5^3 \times 4 - 60}{((7 + 1) \times 9 + 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 34 - 60}{7 \times (1 + 9) \times 2 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (3 - 4)) \times 60}{8 \times (1 + (9 \times (7 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (3^4)) - 60}{(8 - (1 - (9 + 7)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 \times (4 + 60))}{((81 \times 9) + 7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53628}{71940} := \frac{5 + 3 \times (6 - 2 + 8)}{7 - 1 + 9 + 40}$$

$$:= \frac{53 + 62 + 8}{71 + 94 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 6) \times 2 - 8}{7 \times (1 + 9) + 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{79218} := \frac{5^3 \times 4 - 60}{7 \times 92 \times 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{87219} := \frac{534 + 6 + 0}{872 + 1 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{81972} := \frac{534 + (6 - 0)}{819 + (7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{87912} := \frac{5 + 34 + 6 + 0}{8 + 7 \times 9 + 1 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((3 \times 4) - (6 - 0))}{(8 - (1 - (9 + 7))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 \times 4 + 6) + 0}{8 + 7 \times (9 + 1) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53714}{90862} := \frac{53 \times (7 + 1) + 4}{90 \times 8 + 6 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (34 + (6 - 0))}{8 + (1 \times ((9 \times 7) - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{98172} := \frac{5 \times (3 - 4) + 60}{98 + 1^7 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((3 \times 4) + (6 - 0))}{(8 \times (1 + (9 + 7))) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((3^4) - 60)}{(8 \times 19) + (7 + 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53482}{76109} := \frac{(53 + 4 + 8) \times 2}{76 + 109}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (3 \times 4)) + 60}{8 \times (1 \times (9 + (7 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{8 + (197 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (4 \times 60))}{81 \times (9 + (7 \times 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53498}{72106} := \frac{5 + 3 \times 4 + 98}{7^2 + 106}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3^4 - 9) + 8}{7^2 \times 10 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53742}{86190} := \frac{53 \times (7 - 4 - 2)}{86 - 1^9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{53 \times (7 + 4 - 2)}{(86 - 1) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53780}{91426} := \frac{5 \times (3 + (7 - (8 - 0)))}{9 + (1 \times (4 - (2 - 6)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (3 - (7 - (8 - 0)))}{9 - ((1^4) - 26)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(5-3) \times (7+(8-0))}{9 + ((1+(4+2)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (3-7)) + 80}{(9 + (1 \times (4 \times 2))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (7 + (8-0)))}{9 \times (1 - (4 \times (2-6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5^3) - (7 + (8-0))}{91 + ((4^2) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (3+7)) \times (8-0)}{(9 + ((1+4)^2)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (3-7)) \times 80}{9 \times (142 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((3+7) \times (8-0))}{(9+1) \times (4 + (2^6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{97461} := \frac{5 \times 3 \times 8 + 02}{(9 + 7 \times 4) \times 6 - 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 + (3 + (80 \times 2))}{6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7-4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5^3) + (8^02)}{69 + 174} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (3 \times (8 - (-02)))}{(6 + (9 \times 1)) \times (7-4)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + ((3 + (8-0))^2)}{6 \times (9 \times (1 \times (7-4)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 802)}{69 \times (1 + 74)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + 380) \times 2}{6 \times (91 + 74)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(5^3) - (9 - 28)}{6 \times ((7-4) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (3 \times (9+2))) \times 8}{((6 \times 7) - 4) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (39 + 2)) \times 8}{((6 \times 7) + 4) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(5-3) \times (9 \times 28)}{(67-4) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(5-3) \times (92-8)}{6 \times (7 \times (4 + (1-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(53 + (9 \times 2)) \times 8}{(67 + 4) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53790}{82641} := \frac{5 \times (3 + 7 \times 9) + 0}{8 \times 2^6 - 4 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53901}{64872} := \frac{5 \times (3 + 901)}{64 \times (87 - 2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 - (3 - (9 \times 2 + 8))}{6 + ((7 \times 4) + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{5 - (3 \times (9 - (2 + 8)))}{6 + (7 - (4 - (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 - (3 + (9 \times (2 - 8)))}{6 + (74 - 10)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{67914} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 \times 8 + 02}{67 + 91 - 4} \\ &:= \frac{53 + 8 - 0 \times 2}{67 + 9 + 1^4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53901}{87462} &:= \frac{53 - 9 \times 0 \times 1}{8 - (7 - 46) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{53 \times (9 - 01)}{8 \times (74 + 6 \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5 + ((3 \times 9) + (2 \times 8))}{6 \times (7 + (4 - (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + ((3 \times 9) - 28)}{6 - (7 + (4 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (3 \times ((9^2) + 8))}{(6 + (7 \times 4)) \times 10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{69174} &:= \frac{(5 \times 3) - (8 - (0 \times 2))}{6 - (9 - (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (3 + (8 + (-02)))}{6 + (9 + (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times 3) + (8 + (-02))}{6 + (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 3) - (8 - 0))^2}{(6 \times (9 + 1)) + (7 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(53 + 80) \times 2}{6 + ((91 - 7) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{53 + (8 - (-02))}{(6 - (9 + (1 - 7)))^4} \\ &:= \frac{5 - (3 - (80 + 2))}{6 + (91 + (7 + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(5^3) + (8 - (0 \times 2))}{6 - (9 - 174)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53928}{67410} &:= \frac{((5^3) + 9) \times (2 \times 8)}{67 \times (4 \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + 3) \times (9^2)) - 8}{(6 + 74) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 3) \times 9) - (2 - 8)}{(6 - (7 - 4)) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 3)^9) + (2 \times 8)}{6 \times ((7 + 4) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 3)^9) + 28}{674 + (1 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - ((3 - 9) \times 2)) \times 8}{(6 + (7 + 4)) \times 10} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (3 - (9 - 2))) \times 8}{6 + (74 + 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(5^3) - ((9^2) + 8)}{(6 \times 7) + (4 - (1 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53941}{60287} &:= \frac{(5 + 3 + 9) \times (4 - 1)}{(6 + 02) \times 8 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + 3 + 9) \times 4 \times 1}{6 + (02 + 8) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 9 + 4 + 1)}{6 + 02 + 87} \\ &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 94 \times 1}{60 - 2 + 8 \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(5+3) \times 9 \times 4 + 1}{60 + 2^8 + 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 3 \times (9 - 4 - 1)}{6 - 02 + 8 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54027}{68931} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 02 + 7}{6^{8-9+3} + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54027}{86913} := \frac{5 + 4 + 02 \times 7}{8 \times 6 - 9 + 1 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4^{02} + 7)}{(8 - 6) \times 91 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54087}{63921} := \frac{5 + 4 \times 08 + 7}{63 - 9 - 2 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 40 + 87}{6 \times (3 \times 9 - 2 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{540 - 8 + 7}{639 - 2 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (40 + 8 + 7)}{6 \times 3 \times 9 \times 2 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 0 \times 8 + 7)}{(6 + 3 \times 9) \times 2 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - 08) \times 7}{6 + 3 + 9 + 21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54201}{93786} := \frac{5 + 4 \times (20 + 1)}{(9 \times 3 - 7) \times 8 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54219}{60738} := \frac{5 - 42 \times (1 - 9)}{60 \times 7 - 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54237}{69810} := \frac{5 \times 4^2 + 3 \times 7}{(6 + 9) \times 8 + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5^4 + 2 - 3 \times 7}{(6 + 9 \times 8) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54270}{63918} := \frac{(5 - 4) \times 270}{6 + 39 \times 1 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - 2 + 7) + 0}{6 + 39 + 1 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - 2 + 70)}{(63 - 9 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54270}{68139} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 27 + 0}{6 \times (8 \times 13 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54279}{63081} := \frac{5 - 4 + 27 + 9}{6 + 30 + 8 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - 4 \times (2 - 7) \times 9}{6^3 - 0 \times 8 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54302}{87169} := \frac{54 + 30 \times 2}{8 + 7 \times (16 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54306}{89217} := \frac{5 + 43 - 06}{8 \times 9 - 2 - 1^7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 30 + 6}{8 - (9 - 21) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 3) \times 06}{89 + 2^{1+7}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4^3 + 06)}{8 + 9^2 \times 1 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54312}{67890} := \frac{((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 12}{(6 \times (7 \times 8)) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5^4) \times (3 - 1))^2}{(6 + (7 - 8))^9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 1)))^2}{((6 \times 7) + 8) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4 + (3 - 1))) + 2}{6 - ((7 \times 8) - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (3 \times 1)))^2}{(6 \times (7 + 8)) + 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 4) \times 312}{6 \times ((7 \times 8) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(54 + (3 - 1)) \times 2}{(6 \times 7) + (8 + 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - (3 - (1 + 2)))}{(6 \times 7) - (8 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (3 - (1^2)))}{67 - (8 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1^2)))}{6 + (78 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1 + 2)))}{(67 + 8) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (3 + (1 \times 2)))}{6 + (7 \times (8 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((4^3) - (1^2))}{6 + (7 + (8 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (3 \times (1^2)))}{6 - ((7 - 8) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (3 \times (1 + 2)))}{(6 + (7 - 8)) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (3 + 12))}{6 + (7 + (8 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54328}{67910} := \frac{((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2) \times 8}{(67 - 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 43) \times 2) + 8}{(6 + 7) \times (9 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{6 + ((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (4 - 32)) \times 8}{((6 \times 7) - 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 8)}{6 \times (7 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^4) - ((3^2) + 8)}{(67 + 9) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + ((4^3) - 2)) \times 8}{67 \times (9 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4 - (3 - 2))) \times 8}{(6 - (7 - 9)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8}{6 \times (7 + (9 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 43) \times (2 \times 8)}{6 \times ((7 + 9) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(54 - (3 \times 2)) \times 8}{6 \times (79 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(54 - 32) \times 8}{(6 + (7 + 9)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - (3 + 28))}{(6 + (7 - 9)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 + (3 + (2 - 8)))}{6 + (7 - (9 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((4 \times 32) + 8)}{(6 + 79) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (3 + (2 \times 8)))}{(6 \times 79) + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{6 + (79 - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (3 + 28))}{(6 \times 7) + (9 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (43 + 28)}{6 + (79 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{54 + ((3 \times 2) + 8)}{6 + (79 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54362}{91780} := \frac{(5^4 - 3 - 6) \times 2}{(9 + 17) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54372}{98106} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 3 - 7 \times 2}{9 + 8 \times 10 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54610}{92837} := \frac{(5 + 4) \times (6 \times 10)}{928 - (3 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4 - 6)) \times 10}{((9 + 2) \times 8) - 37}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - (6 - 10))}{((9 + (2 \times 8)) \times 3) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + (6 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9^2) + (8 + (3 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 - 4)^6) \times 10}{9 + (2 \times (8 + (3 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (61 - 0))}{(9 - 2) \times ((8 \times 3) - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4 \times 6)) - 10}{(9 + 2) \times ((8 \times 3) - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 \times (6 + (1 - 0)))}{(9 + (28 - 3)) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4 + 6)) \times 10}{9 + ((2^8) - (3 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((4 \times 6) + 10)}{9 + (28 \times (3 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (46 - 10)}{9 \times (2 - (8 \times (3 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (46 + 10)}{(92 - (8 \times 3)) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54630}{92871} := \frac{5 - 4 + 6 + 3 + 0}{9 \times 2 \times (8 - 7) - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - 6) + 30}{9 \times 2 + 8 + 7 + 1}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (46 - 30)}{9 \times 2 \times 8 - 7 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 4 - 6) \times 30}{9 \times (2 + 8 + 7 \times 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 4 \times (6 + 3) + 0}{9 \times (28 + 7 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{54 + 6 - 30}{9 - (2 - 8) \times 7 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54702}{63819} := \frac{(5 - (4 + 7)) \times (-02)}{6 - (3 + (8 - 19))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (7 - 0))) - 2}{6 + (3 + (8 \times 19))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times (70 + 2)}{(6 - (3 - 81)) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times 702}{(6 + 3) \times 819}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 4) \times (70 + 2)}{6 \times (3 - (8 - 19))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 47) \times (-02)}{(6 \times 3) + (8 \times (1 + 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - (7 + (-02)))}{6 + (3 + (8 - (1 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((4 - 7) \times (-02))}{6 + (38 - (1 \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 - (7 \times (-02)))}{6 + ((3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 9)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((4 + (7 - 0))^2)}{(6 \times ((3 \times 8) - 1)) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (7 - (-02)))}{6 - (3 - (8 + (1 + 9)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (47 - (-02))}{(6 \times (3 + (8 + 1))) - 9}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (7 - (0 \times 2))}{63 \times (8 - (1^9))}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (7 - (-02))}{63 \times (8 + (1^9))}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (7 \times (02))}{63 + 819}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (70 + 2)}{6 \times ((3 + 81) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54712}{68390} := \frac{((5 \times (4 + 7)) - 1) \times 2}{(6 \times (8 \times 3)) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 4) + 7 - 1)^2}{6 + (839 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 47) - 1) \times 2}{(68 - 3) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 \times 1)))^2}{6 + (83 - (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (4 - 7)) \times 12}{6 \times (8 + (3 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (4 + 7 - 1)) - 2}{(6 \times 8) + (3 + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + ((4 \times 7) + 1)) \times 2}{6 - (8 + (3 - 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times (7 + (1^2))}{(6 - (8 - 3)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times 712}{(6 + 83) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 47) \times (1 + 2)}{(68 \times 3) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - 4) \times (7 \times 12)}{6 + ((8 + 3) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(54 + 7 + 1) \times 2}{68 - (3 - 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - (7 \times (1^2)))}{6 - (8 - (3 + (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - (7 + 12))}{6 - (8 - (3 \times (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + (7 + (1^2)))}{(6 \times (8 + 3)) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (7 \times (1^2)))}{6 + (8 - (3 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (7 - (1^2))}{((6 \times 8) - 3) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (7 - (1 + 2))}{6 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54720}{81396} := \frac{5 \times (4 \times 7 + 20)}{(8 + 1) \times 39 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54720}{83619} := \frac{(5 + 4 + 7) \times 20}{83 \times 6 \times 1 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54736}{90812} := \frac{5 - 4 + 7 + 36}{9 + 08^{1 \times 2}}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 4 + 73 + 6}{(9 \times (08) + 1) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54780}{91632} := \frac{54 - 7 + 8 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 6 + 3) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54780}{93126} := \frac{5 + 4 - 7 + 8 + 0}{9 + 3 + 1 - 2 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 47 + 8 + 0}{(9 + (3 + 1) \times 2) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54891}{67203} := \frac{(5 \times 4 - 8) \times 9 - 1}{6 + (7 - 2)^{03}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54901}{86273} := \frac{(5 \times 4) + (9 + (-01))}{8 + (6 \times (2 + (7 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + ((4 \times (9 - 0)) + 1)}{8 + (62 - (7 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{54 - (9 \times (-01))}{(86 \times 2) - 73}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (4 + (9 - (-01)))}{8 + (6 \times ((2 \times 7) + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (4 - (90 \times 1))}{8 + (62 + 73)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (4 + (90 - 1))}{(8 + 6) \times ((2 \times 7) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((4 \times (9 - 0)) - 1)}{8 - (6 - 273)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54912}{87360} := \frac{5 - 4 + 9 + 12}{8 + 7 \times 3 + 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 49 + 12}{87 + 3 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(54 - 9 - 1) \times 2}{8 \times (7 + 3) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{54 \times (9 + 1 \times 2)}{(8 + 7) \times (3 + 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54913}{72806} := \frac{5 - 4 + 91 - 3}{7 \times 2 \times 8 + 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54918}{62037} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times (9 + 18)}{620 - 3 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54931}{87620} := \frac{(5 + 49) \times 3 + 1}{8 + 7 \times 6^2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54960}{83127} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 9 \times 60}{(8 + 3 \times 1)^2 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 4^{9-6} + 0}{8^3 - 1 - 27}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54963}{78012} := \frac{5 + (4 + 9 + 6) \times 3}{7 + (8 + 01)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 4 \times 9 + 6) \times 3}{780 + 12}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54963}{78120} := \frac{5 + 4^{9-6} \times 3}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56018}{73429} := \frac{5 + 60 + 1 + 8}{7 + (3 \times 4 - 2) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56079}{83214} := \frac{5 - 6 + 07 \times 9}{8 + 3 \times 2 \times 14}$$

$$:= \frac{560 + 7 - 9}{832 - 1 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56173}{82940} := \frac{5 + 6 \times (1 + 7) \times 3}{(8^2 - 9) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56203}{94178} := \frac{5 \times (6 + 2) - 03}{9 - 4 + 1 + 7 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{56 + 203}{9 + 417 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56238}{79104} := \frac{(56 + 2) \times 3 + 8}{(7 \times 9 + 1) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56278}{90341} := \frac{56 \times 2 + 78}{9 \times 034 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 6 + 27) \times 8}{9^{03} + 4 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56304}{81972} := \frac{5 + 63 + 0 \times 4}{8 + 19 + 72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56304}{91287} := \frac{(5 + 63) \times 04}{9 \times (1 - 2 + 8) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56329}{71804} := \frac{5^{6-3} + 2^9}{7 + 1 + 804}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56342}{80179} := \frac{5 \times (6 + 3) \times 4 + 2}{80 + 179}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56430}{97812} := \frac{5 \times 6 \times (4 - 3) + 0}{9 \times 7 - 8 - 1 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{56 + 4^3 + 0}{(97 + 8 - 1) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (6 \times 4 + 3) + 0}{9 + (7 + 8 \times 1)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 6 + 4^3 + 0}{(9 + 7 \times 8 \times 1) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 6 + 4) \times 30}{(9 + 7 \times 8) \times 12}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56472}{90138} := \frac{5 - 6 + 4 + 7^2}{90 + 1^3 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{56 \times (4 + 7 + 2)}{90 \times 13 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56481}{92730} := \frac{5^{6-4} \times 8 + 1}{(9 \times 2 - 7) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{56 + 4 + 8 - 1}{(9 + 2) \times (7 + 3) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56490}{71823} := \frac{5 \times (6 + 4 \times 9) + 0}{(7 + 1 \times 82) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (64 + 90)}{7 + 18^2 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56712}{93408} := \frac{(5 + 6 + 7 - 1) \times 2}{(9 + 3) \times 4 + 08}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 6 \times (7 - 1)^2}{93 \times 4 - 08}$$

$$:= \frac{(56 \times 7 - 1) \times 2}{(9 - 3)^4 - 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56832}{79104} := \frac{5 + 68 + 3 - 2}{7 \times 9 + 10 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56940}{71832} := \frac{5 + (6 + 9) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (1 + 8 + 3) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56943}{71820} := \frac{56 - 9 + 4^3}{7 \times (18 + 2) + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{56 + 943}{7 \times (1 + 8) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 69) \times 4 \times 3}{7 \times 1 \times 8 \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56943}{87210} := \frac{56 - 9 + 4^3}{(8 + 7 + 2) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{56984}{71230} := \frac{((5 \times 6) - 9) \times (8 - 4)}{7 \times (12 + (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - ((6 - 9) \times 8)) \times 4}{(71 \times 2) + (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 \times 8))) \times 4}{71 \times (2 + (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (6 - 9)) \times (8 + 4)}{(7 - (1 + 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (6 + 9)) \times (8 + 4)}{(7 + (1 + 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (6 - 9)) \times 84}{7 \times ((1^2) \times 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (6 - (9 - (8 - 4)))}{7 - (1 - (2 - (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (6 - (9 + (8 + 4)))}{7 - (12 - 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (6 - (9 + (8 - 4)))}{7 + (1 \times (2^3 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((6 - (9 - 8)) \times 4)}{(7 - (1 \times 2))^3 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (6 \times ((9 - 8) \times 4))}{(7 - (1 \times 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (6 + (9 - (8 + 4)))}{7 + ((1^2) \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (6 + (9 + (8 \times 4)))}{71 - (2 \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (6 + (9 + (8 + 4)))}{7 + (1 + (2 + 30))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (6 + (9 + (8 - 4)))}{7 + (1 \times (23 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (6 + (9 + 84))}{7 + (123 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{56 \times (9 \times (8 - 4))}{7 \times (12 \times 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{56 \times (9 + (8 + 4))}{(7 \times (1 \times 2)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{56^{9-8}^4}{71 + (2 - (3 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57024}{83916} := \frac{5 \times 70 - 2 + 4}{(83 - 9) \times (1 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57043}{92168} := \frac{5 + (70 - 4) \times 3}{(9 + 2 \times 16) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57120}{86394} := \frac{5 \times (7 + 1) \times 2 + 0}{86 + 39 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57132}{86940} := \frac{5 + 7 + 13 - 2}{8 \times 6 - 9 - 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (7 - 1) \times 3) \times 2}{(8 + 6) \times (9 - 4) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57168}{90432} := \frac{5 + 7 \times (1 + 6) \times 8}{90 \times (4 + 3) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{84930} := \frac{(5 \times 7 - 2 - 1) \times 6}{8 \times 4 \times 9 - 3 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (7^2 + 1) + 6}{8 + 4 \times 93 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{98304} := \frac{5 + (7 + 2) \times 16}{(9 - 8 + 3)^{04}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{98340} := \frac{5 + 7 \times (2 + 1) + 6}{98 - 3 - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7)^2 \times 16}{9 \times (8 + 3) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 7 \times 2 \times 1 - 6}{98 + 3 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times 2^{1 \times 6}}{(9 + 8 \times 3) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7)^2 - 16}{9 \times 8 \times 3 + 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57280}{61934} := \frac{5 \times (72 - 8) + 0}{6 \times 19 \times 3 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57312}{60894} := \frac{(5 + (7 + (3 + 1))) \times 2}{6 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7)^{3-1^2}}{60 + (89 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((7 - 3) \times (1 + 2))}{(60 + 8) \times (9 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 7) - 3) \times 12}{6 \times (((08 + 9) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (7 \times ((3 + 1)^2))}{608 - (9 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{573 + (1 + 2)}{6 \times ((08 + 94))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 7) \times (3 + 1))^2}{(60 + 8) \times (9 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57321}{69480} := \frac{5 \times (7 + 3 \times 2) + 1}{(6 - 9 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times (32 + 1)}{(6 + 9) \times 4 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{573 + 21}{(6 + 9) \times 48 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{86391} := \frac{5 \times (7 + 4) \times 20}{8 \times (6^3 - 9) - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{86913} := \frac{(5 + 7 \times 4) \times 20}{86 + 913}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{98136} := \frac{57 - 4 + 2 + 0}{98 - 1 + 3 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57429}{63810} := \frac{((5 \times (7 - 4))^2) + 9}{((6 \times 3) + 8) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times (7 - 4))^2) - 9}{(6 - 3) \times (8 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 2) \times 9}{(6 + (3 + 8)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 7) \times (4 + 2)) + 9}{6 + (3 + (81 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + 7)^{4-2}) \times 9}{6 \times (3 \times (8 \times 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (7 + (4 - 2))) - 9}{6 + ((3 \times 8) + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + ((7 - 4) \times 2)) \times 9}{(6 - (3 - 8)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (7 \times 4)) \times (2 \times 9)}{6 \times ((3 + 8) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times ((4 + 2) \times 9)}{(6 + 3) \times (8 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times (4 + 29)}{(6 + 38) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times (42 \times 9)}{63 \times (8 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(57 - (4 - 2)) \times 9}{(63 - 8) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (7 - (4 - (2 - 9)))}{6 - (3 - (8 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (7 \times (4 - (2 + 9)))}{6 + (3 \times (8 + 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((7 - 4) \times (2 \times 9))}{(6 + (3 \times 8)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (7 + (4 - (2 - 9)))}{((6 \times 3) - 8) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (((7 + 4) \times 2) - 9)}{6 + ((3 \times 8) - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (((7 + 4)^2) + 9)}{6 \times ((3 \times 8) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (7 + (4 + (2 + 9)))}{6 \times (3 - (8 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (7 + (42 + 9))}{63 + (8 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{57461}{82309} := \frac{5+7+4 \times 6+1}{8+(2+3) \times 09} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times 7-4) \times 6-1}{8 \times (2+30)+9} \\ & \frac{57694}{82103} := \frac{5 \times (7+6+9+4)}{82+103} \\ & \frac{57834}{92106} := \frac{5+7+8+34}{92-1 \times 06} \\ & := \frac{(5-7+8-3)^4}{9+2 \times 10 \times 6} \\ & \frac{57834}{92610} := \frac{578+34}{(92+6) \times 10} \\ & \frac{57902}{61438} := \frac{5+7 \times 9 \times 02}{6+(1+4)^3+8} \\ & \frac{57904}{81263} := \frac{(5-7+90) \times 4}{8^{1+2}-6 \times 3} \\ & \frac{57942}{86130} := \frac{5+7+9+4^2}{86-1-30} \\ & \frac{58160}{79243} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 1 \times 6+0}{(79+2) \times 4+3} \\ & \frac{58176}{90432} := \frac{5 \times 81-7+6}{90 \times (4+3)-2} \\ & \frac{58194}{76320} := \frac{58-1^9+4}{(7-6+3) \times 20} \\ & \frac{58239}{64710} := \frac{((5 \times 8)-(2 \times 3)) \times 9}{(6+(4 \times 7)) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{((5 \times 8)-23) \times 9}{(6+(4+7)) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times 8)+239}{((6 \times 4)+7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(5+((8^2)+3)) \times 9}{6+(4+710)} \\ & := \frac{(5+((8^2)-3)) \times 9}{6 \times ((4+7) \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(5+(8-(2 \times 3))) \times 9}{64+(7-(1-0))} \\ & := \frac{(5+(8-(2+3))) \times 9}{6+(4+(7 \times 10))} \\ & := \frac{(5+(8-(2-3))) \times 9}{(6-4) \times (7 \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{(5+(8 \times (2 \times 3))) \times 9}{(6+47) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(58+(2-3)) \times 9}{(64-7) \times 10} \\ & := \frac{(58-2) \times (3 \times 9)}{6 \times (4 \times (7 \times 10))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((8-(2-3)) \times 9)}{6 \times (4+(71-0))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times ((8+(2 \times 3)) \times 9)}{(6+4) \times (7 \times 10)} \\ & := \frac{5+(8 \times (23+9))}{6+(4 \times (71-0))} \\ & := \frac{5+(8+(2+(3+9)))}{6+(4 \times (7-(1-0)))} \\ & := \frac{5+(8+(2+(3-9)))}{6-(4-(7+(1-0)))} \\ & := \frac{5+(8+(2+39))}{6 \times (4+(7-(1-0)))} \\ & := \frac{5+(82+(3-9))}{(6-(4-7)) \times 10} \\ & \frac{58240}{91637} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 2^4+0}{(9+1^6)^3+7} \\ & \frac{58293}{61047} := \frac{(5 \times 8+2) \times 9+3}{(61-04) \times 7} \\ & \frac{58293}{67014} := \frac{(5 \times 8+2) \times 9+3}{6 \times (70-1+4)} \\ & \frac{58320}{96714} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 3^2+0}{9+6 \times 7 \times 14} \\ & \frac{58374}{60912} := \frac{(5 \times 8)-((3 \times 7)-4)}{6-(0-(9 \times (1 \times 2)))} \\ & := \frac{5+(8+(3 \times (7+4)))}{6 \times ((09-(1^2)))} \\ & := \frac{(5+(8+(3+7))) \times 4}{6 \times (((09-1) \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{((5+8)^3)+(7+4)}{(6 \times ((09-1)))^2} \\ & := \frac{5+(8+(37 \times 4))}{60+(9 \times 12)} \\ & := \frac{((5+(8 \times 3)) \times 7)+4}{6^{-09+12}} \\ & := \frac{5-(8 \times (3-(7+4)))}{6 \times ((09+(1+2)))} \\ & := \frac{5+(8 \times (3+74))}{6 \times ((09 \times 12))} \\ & := \frac{5+((8^3)-(7+4))}{(60 \times 9)-12} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (8+(3 \times (7 \times 4)))}{60 \times (9-(1^2))} \\ & := \frac{5 \times (8+(3 \times 74))}{60 \times ((9+1) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58401}{93627} &:= \frac{58+4+01}{9 \times 3 \times (6-2)-7} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times 8+401}{(93+6+2) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58473}{96120} &:= \frac{(5+8-4) \times 73}{9 \times 6 \times 1 \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(58-4) \times 73}{9 \times 6 \times 120} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58491}{72360} := \frac{5+84+9-1}{(7-2-3) \times 60}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58496}{73120} &:= \frac{((5-8) \times 4) + 96}{7 \times (3 + (12-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5-(8-(4+9))) \times 6}{73 + (1 \times (2-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5-(8+(4-9)))^6}{(7-(3 \times 1)) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(5-(8-4)) \times 96}{(7+3) \times (12-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(5-(8-49)) \times 6}{(7^3 \times 1) + (2-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(5+((8 \times 4)-9)) \times 6}{(7+3) \times (1+20)} \\ &:= \frac{(5+(8+(4-9))) \times 6}{(7-(3+1)) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{5-(8-(4+(9+6)))}{(7+(3 \times 1)) \times (2-0)} \\ &:= \frac{5-(8-(4+(9-6)))}{7-(3-(1^2+0))} \\ &:= \frac{5-(8+(4-(9+6)))}{7+(3 \times (1^2+0))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((8-4)^{9-6})}{((7 \times 3)-1) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{5+(8-(4-(9+6)))}{7+(3+(1 \times 20))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5+(8-(4-(9-6)))}{7+((3+1) \times (2-0))} \\ &:= \frac{5+(8+(4+(9+6)))}{7+(31+(2-0))} \\ &:= \frac{5+(8+(4+(9-6)))}{7-(3-(1+20))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{5+(8+(49+6))}{73+(12-0)} \\ &:= \frac{5+(8+(49-6))}{7+(3 \times (1+20))} \\ &:= \frac{5+(84+(9+6))}{7+(3+120)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{58+((4-9) \times 6)}{7 \times (3+(1 \times (2-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{58+(49 \times 6)}{((7 \times 3)+1) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58912}{73640} &:= \frac{((5 \times (8+9)) - 1) \times 2}{7 \times (3 \times (6+(4-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5+8) \times (9+1)) - 2}{(7+(3-6)) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{((5+8) \times 9) - (1^2)}{7+(3 \times (6+40))} \\ &:= \frac{(5-(8-(9 \times 1)))^2}{(7 \times 3) + (6 \times (4-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times 8) - (9 - (1^2))}{(7-(3-6)) \times (4-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times 8) - (9+(1+2))}{7 \times (3+(6-(4-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times 8) + ((9+1) \times 2)}{73+(6-(4-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5+(8+(9 \times 1))) \times 2}{(7 \times 3) - (6-40)} \\ &:= \frac{(5+(8-9)) \times 12}{((7 \times 3)-6) \times (4-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(5+8) \times (9 - (1^2))}{(7 \times (3 \times 6)) + (4-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(58 \times (9 \times 1)) - 2}{7+(3+640)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((89+1)^2)}{((7 \times 3)-6)^4+0}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (8 \times ((9+1) \times 2))}{(7+(3 \times 6)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (8 \times (9 - (1^2)))}{(7-(3-6)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (8 \times (9+(1+2)))}{((7 \times 3)-6) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (8+(9-(1^2)))}{(7+(3 \times 6)) \times (4-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5+(8-(9-12))}{7+(3+(6+(4-0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{5+(8+(9 \times (1+2)))}{7-(3-(6+40))}$$

$$:= \frac{58-(9-(1+2))}{7+((3 \times 6)+40)}$$

$$:= \frac{58+(9+(1^2))}{(7 \times 3)+(64-0)}$$

$$:= \frac{589+(1+2)}{7+((3^6)+(4-0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58920}{74136} := \frac{5+8 \times 920}{(7 \times (4-1))^3+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58941}{63720} := \frac{5+(8+9) \times 4+1}{6+37 \times 2+0}$$

$$:= \frac{58+941}{6^3 \times (7-2)+0}$$

$$:= \frac{(5-8+9)^4-1}{(63+7) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{5+8 \times (9-4-1)}{(6+3-7) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59048}{61732} := \frac{5+9+0 \times 4+8}{6+1+7+3^2}$$

$$:= \frac{5-9+048}{6+1+7+32}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 \times 04 + 8)}{6 + 1 \times 7 \times 32}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 \times (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 - (6 - ((7^2) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 + 14 + 8)}{(7 + 6 - 3) \times 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59064}{87312} := \frac{5 + 9 \times (06 - 4)}{8 - 7 + 31 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((9 - 1) \times 30)}{(8 + (6 \times 72)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(59 + 1) \times 4 + 8}{(7 + 6 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times 9 + 06 \times 4}{87 + 3 + 12}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59143}{82076} := \frac{(5 + 9) \times 14 \times 3}{(8 + 2^{07}) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59160}{72384} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 1 + 60)}{(7 + 2 \times 3) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (90 + 6 - 4)}{8 \times (73 + 12)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59147}{86032} := \frac{5 + (9 + (1 \times (4 - 7)))}{8 + (6 - ((0 \times 3) - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59182}{60347} := \frac{(5 + 9) \times 18 + 2}{(60 + 3) \times 4 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59102}{78463} := \frac{59 + 1 - 02}{78 - 4 + 6 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 + 102}{7 \times (8 - 4 + 6 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (9 + (1^4 + 7))}{8 \times (6 + ((0 \times 3) - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59184}{63072} := \frac{5 + 9 + 1 \times 8^4}{6 + 3^{07} \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59102}{87634} := \frac{59 + 1 - 02}{87 + 6 - 3 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + 9 + 102}{8 \times 7 \times (6 - 3) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 - (1 + 4 - 7))}{(8 \times (6 - 0)) + 32}$$

$$:= \frac{59 + (14 - 7)}{8 \times (6 - (0 - (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{67431} := \frac{5 \times 9 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{(6 + 7) \times (4^3 - 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{59 + (1 + (4 \times 7))}{8 \times ((6 \times (03)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 9) \times 280}{6 \times 743 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59124}{67083} := \frac{(5 + 9 - 1^2) \times 4}{6 + 7 \times 08 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (91 - (4 - 7))}{8 \times ((6 - (-03)) \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{73164} := \frac{5 \times 92 - 80}{7 \times (3 + 1 \times 64)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 9 - 1) \times 24}{6 \times (7 \times 08 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (9 \times 1)) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (60 - 32)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{73416} := \frac{5 \times (9 \times 2 + 8) + 0}{7 \times (3 + 4 + 16)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (((9 + 1) \times 4) - 7)}{8 \times (6 \times ((03 + 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59130}{86724} := \frac{5 + (9 + (1^3 + 0))}{8 - (6 - ((7 - 2) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 - (9 - (1 + 47))}{8 \times (6 - ((0 \times 3) - 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59328}{74160} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 28}{7 \times (4 \times (1 \times 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 - (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 - (6 - (7 \times (2 + 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times (9 - 1)) + 4) \times 7}{(8 + (6^{03})) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + (9 \times 3)) \times 2) - 8}{7 + (4 - (1 - 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 + (9 + (1 + 30))}{8 + ((6 \times (7 + 2)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 9) + 1) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (60 + 32)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3^2))) + 8}{7 + (4 - (1^6 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times (9 + (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 \times (6 + (7 + (2 - 4)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + 91) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (6 \times (032))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 + 2))) + 8}{7 \times (4 + (1^6 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (9 \times 1)) + 30}{8 - (6 \times (7 - 24))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 + 2))) - 8}{(7 \times (4 - 1)) - (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{5 \times ((9 - 1) \times (3 - 0))}{8 \times (((6 + 7) \times 2) - 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59148}{76320} := \frac{5 + 9 + 1 \times 48}{(7 - 6 + 3) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 - 2))) + 8}{(7 + (4 - 1)) \times (6 - 0)}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 + 3)) + (2 \times 8)}{(7 \times (4 + 1)) + 60} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (9 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{74 + (1 \times (6 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (9 - (3 + 2))) \times 8}{74 + (16 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (9 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8}{7 \times (4 + (16 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 9) \times ((3 \times 2) + 8)}{7 \times (41 - (6 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 9) \times ((3^2) \times 8)}{7 \times ((4 - 1) \times 60)} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 9) \times (32 \times 8)}{7 \times (4 \times 160)} \\
 := \frac{(5 - 93) \times (2 - 8)}{(7 + (4 \times 1)) \times 60} \\
 := \frac{5 - (9 - ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{7 + (4 - (1 \times (6 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{5 - (9 - (32 - 8))}{7 + ((4 - 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 - (93 - (2^8))}{7 \times ((4 + 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((9 + 3) \times 28)}{7 \times ((4 + 1) \times 60)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 \times 8))}{(7 + (4 - 1)) \times 60} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 - (3 + (2 - 8)))}{74 + (1^6 + 0)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 \times ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{(74 + 1) \times (6 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 \times (32 \times 8))}{((7^4) - 1) \times (6 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{5 + (93 + (2 + 8))}{74 + (1 + 60)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59328}{76014} := \frac{5 - 9 \times (3 + 2 - 8)}{7 \times 6 - 01^4} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 + 3) \times 2 + 8}{(7 \times 6 - 01) \times 4}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59340}{86172} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 3 + 40)}{8 \times 6 \times 1 \times 7 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59360}{84217} := \frac{(5 \times 9 + 3) \times 60}{8^4 - 2 - 1 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59368}{74210} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + (3 \times 6)) \times 8}{(7 - 4) \times 210} \\
 := \frac{((5 \times 9) + (3 - 6)) \times 8}{7 \times ((4 + 2) \times 10)} \\
 := \frac{((5 \times 9) - 36) \times 8}{(7 + (4 - 2)) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{((5 + 9)^3) \times (6 + 8)}{(7^4) \times (2 \times 10)} \\
 := \frac{(5 - (9 - (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{7 \times ((4 - 2) \times 10)} \\
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 + 3)) - (6 \times 8)}{7 - (4 - (2 + 10))} \\
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 - 3)) - (6 + 8)}{(7 \times 4) + (2 - 10)} \\
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 - 3)) - (6 - 8)}{(7 \times 4) + (2 + 10)} \\
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 - 3)) + (6 + 8)}{7 + (4 \times (2 + 10))} \\
 := \frac{(5 \times (9 - 3)) + (6 - 8)}{7 \times (4 + (2 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6)) \times 8}{((7 \times 4) - 2) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (9 \times 3)) \times (6 + 8)}{7 \times (4 \times (2 \times 10))} \\
 := \frac{(5 + (9 + (3 + 6))) \times 8}{(7 + (4^2)) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 9) \times (36 - 8)}{(7 + 42) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{(5 + 93) \times (6 \times 8)}{7 \times (4 \times 210)} \\
 := \frac{(5 - 93) \times (6 - 8)}{(7 + 4) \times (2 \times 10)}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{5 - (9 - (3 \times (6 \times 8)))}{7 \times (4 + (21 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 - (9 - (36 - 8))}{(7 \times 4) + (2 \times (1 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 - (9 \times (3 - (6 + 8)))}{(7 + (4 + 2)) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{5 \times ((9 + (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{((7 \times 4) + 2) \times 10} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 - (3 - (6 - 8)))}{7 + ((4 \times 2) + 10)} \\
 := \frac{5 \times (9 - (3 + (6 - 8)))}{7 + (42 + (1 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 + (9 - ((3 \times 6) - 8))}{7 - (4 - (2 \times (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{5 + (9 + (3 \times (6 - 8)))}{7 + (4 - (2 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{5 + (93 - (6 + 8))}{7 \times ((4^2) - (1 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{5 + (93 + (6 - 8))}{((7 + 4)^2) - (1 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{59 + (3 - (6 + 8))}{(7 - 4) \times (2 \times 10)} \\
 := \frac{59 + (3 + (6 + 8))}{74 + (21 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{59 + (3 + (6 - 8))}{74 + (2 - (1 - 0))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59670}{82134} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 6) + 70}{82 + 1 + 34} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59724}{86031} := \frac{(5 + 9 + 7) \times 2^4}{8 \times 60 + 3 + 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59831}{60724} := \frac{5 + 98 + 31}{60 + 72 + 4} \\
 := \frac{5 + 98 \times (3 - 1)}{(60 - 7 - 2) \times 4}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{59840}{73216} := \frac{5 \times (98 + 4) + 0}{(7 + 32) \times 16} \\ & \frac{60192}{83754} := \frac{601 + 9 - 2}{837 + 5 + 4} \\ & \frac{60195}{84273} := \frac{((6 \times (-01)) + 9) \times 5}{(8 + (4 + (2 - 7))) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{((6 + (-01)) \times 9) - 5}{8 + (4 \times (2 + (7 + 3)))} \\ & := \frac{(6 - (0 - (1 \times 9))) \times 5}{((8 - 4) \times 27) - 3} \\ & := \frac{(6 - (0 - (1^9))) \times 5}{(8 \times 4) + ((2 \times 7) + 3)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (0 \times 1)) + (9 \times 5)}{(8 + (4 + (2 + 7))) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (0 \times 1)) + 95}{8 + (((4 - 2)^7) - 3)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (1 + 9))) - 5}{8 - ((4 - 27) \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{(6 + (0 - (1^9))) \times 5}{8 + (4 + (2 + (7 \times 3)))} \\ & := \frac{(6 + (-01)) \times (9 \times 5)}{(8 \times 42) - (7 \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{(60 + (1 \times 9)) \times 5}{((84 \times 2) - 7) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{6 - (0 - (1 \times (9 + 5)))}{8 + (4 + (2^{7-3}))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (0 - (1 \times (9 - 5)))}{8 + (4 - (2 - (7 - 3)))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 - ((1 - 9) \times 5))}{8 \times ((4 - 2) \times (7 \times 3))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + ((1 + 9) \times 5))}{(8 + (4 + (2^7))) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + (1 + (9 + 5)))}{(8 - (4 - 2)) \times (7 \times 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{6 \times (0 + (1 + (9 - 5)))}{8 + (4 + (27 + 3))} \\ & := \frac{6 + (0 - (1^{95}))}{8 - (((4 \times 2) - 7)^3)} \\ & := \frac{6 + (0 - (1 - 95))}{(8 + (4 + 2)) \times (7 + 3)} \\ & := \frac{60 \times ((1^9) + 5)}{8 \times (42 + (7 \times 3))} \\ & := \frac{60 \times (1 \times (9 + 5))}{8 \times ((42 + 7) \times 3)} \\ & := \frac{60 \times (19 + 5)}{84 \times (27 - 3)} \\ & := \frac{60 \times (1^{95})}{8 - (4 \times (2 - (7 \times 3)))} \\ & := \frac{60 + ((1 + 9) \times 5)}{8 + ((4 - 2) \times 73)} \\ & := \frac{60 + (1 \times (9 \times 5))}{(8 \times (4 + (2 \times 7))) + 3} \\ & := \frac{60 + (1 \times 95)}{((8 + 4)^2) + 73} \\ & := \frac{60 + 195}{8 + (4 + (2 + (7^3)))} \\ & := \frac{601 + (9 + 5)}{(8 \times (4 \times 27)) - 3} \\ & \frac{60258}{79431} := \frac{6 \times (0 \times 2 + 5) - 8}{7 + 9 + 4 \times 3 + 1} \\ & := \frac{6 - 02 + 5 \times 8}{7 + 9 + 43 - 1} \\ & := \frac{6 + 02 + 58}{7 \times (9 + 4) - 3 - 1} \\ & := \frac{60 + 2 \times 58}{7 \times (9 \times 4 - 3) + 1} \\ & := \frac{(6 + 0 \times 2 + 5) \times 8}{7 + 9 \times 4 \times 3 + 1} \\ & \frac{60273}{84915} := \frac{60 \times (2 + 7) + 3}{8 \times (4 + 91) + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60291}{73458} := \frac{6 \times 029 \times 1}{(7 - 3) \times (45 + 8)} \\ & \frac{60291}{74385} := \frac{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1}{((7 - 4)^3 - 8) \times 5} \\ & \frac{60291}{85347} := \frac{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1}{8 \times 5 \times 3 - 4 - 7} \\ & \frac{60324}{79518} := \frac{(6 + 03) \times 2 + 4}{7 + 9 - 5 + 18} \\ & := \frac{(6 + 03 + 2) \times 4}{7 \times 9 - 5 \times 1^8} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (03 + 2 \times 4)}{(7 + 9) \times 5 - 1 + 8} \\ & := \frac{60 + 32 - 4}{7 \times (9 + 5) + 18} \\ & \frac{60324}{91857} := \frac{(6 + 03 + 2) \times 4}{9 + 1^8 + 57} \\ & := \frac{60 + 3 \times 24}{9 + 185 + 7} \\ & := \frac{60 + 32 - 4}{91 + 8 + 5 \times 7} \\ & \frac{60358}{71492} := \frac{60 + 3 + 5 \times 8}{71 + 49 + 2} \\ & \frac{60372}{85914} := \frac{6 - 0 \times 3 + 72}{8 \times (5 + 9) - 1^4} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (03 + 7^2)}{(8 \times (5 + 9) - 1) \times 4} \\ & \frac{60372}{89154} := \frac{(6 + 037) \times 2}{8 \times 9 + 1 + 54} \\ & \frac{60398}{74152} := \frac{6 \times (03 + 98)}{741 + 5 - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60523}{89741} := \frac{6 \times 05 + 2 - 3}{8 \times 9 - 7 \times 4 - 1} \\ & := \frac{60 + (5 - 2)^3}{8 \times (9 - 7)^4 + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60528}{73914} := \frac{(6 + 05 + 2) \times 8}{7 + 3 \times (9 + 1) \times 4} \\ & \frac{60528}{91374} := \frac{(6 + 05 + 2) \times 8}{9 + 1 \times 37 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60532}{71984} := \frac{60 + 53 - 2}{(7 + 1 + 9) \times 8 - 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60573}{82419} := \frac{60 + 5 - 7 + 3}{8 \times 2 \times 4 + 19} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60732}{84591} := \frac{(60 - 7 + 3) \times 2}{(8 + 4) \times (5 + 9 - 1)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 07 \times 3 \times 2}{8 \times 45 - 9 \times 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60738}{91425} := \frac{60 \times 7 - 38}{(9 + 14) \times 25} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60741}{89325} := \frac{6 + 07 + 4 \times 1}{(8 - 9 + 3 \times 2) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{6 + 07 \times 4 \times 1}{8 + (9 - 3) \times (2 + 5)} \\ & := \frac{(6 + 07) \times 4 - 1}{8 \times (9 + 3 - 2) - 5} \\ & := \frac{607 + 4 + 1}{893 + 2 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60792}{81354} := \frac{6 \times 079 + 2}{8 + 1 + 3 + 5^4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60813}{75492} := \frac{60 + (8 + 1) \times 3}{7 + 5 + 4 + 92} \\ & := \frac{(6 + 081) \times 3}{(7 + 5 \times 4 - 9)^2} \\ & := \frac{(608 + 1) \times 3}{7 \times (5 + 4 + 9)^2} \\ & := \frac{608 + 1^3}{7 \times (5 + 49) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{60 \times 8 + 13}{(7 + 5) \times (49 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60912}{83754} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (9 + 1))) \times 2}{8 + ((37^{-5}) \times 4)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times 1))) + 2}{83 - (7 - (5 - 4))} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + 91)) - 2}{8 + (37 \times (5 \times 4))} \\ & := \frac{(60 \times 9) + 12}{8 - (3 - 754)} \\ & := \frac{6 - ((0 \times 91) - 2)}{8 - (3 - (7 - (5 - 4)))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (0 - (9 + (1^2)))}{(8 \times (3 - 7)) + 54} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times 2))}{(8 \times ((3 \times 7) - 5)) + 4} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1)^2))}{8 \times (3 + (7 \times (5 + 4)))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + (9 - (1^2)))}{8 - (3 - (7 + 54))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + (9 \times 12))}{837 + 54} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (0 + (9 + (1 + 2)))}{8 + (37 + 54)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{60931}{72485} := \frac{6 \times 093 + 1}{(7 - 2)^4 + 8 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{61047}{82593} := \frac{6 + 1 \times 04 + 7}{8 - 2 + 5 + 9 + 3} \\ & := \frac{6 + 1 \times 04 \times 7}{8 + 2^5 + 9 - 3} \\ & := \frac{61 - 0 \times 4 + 7}{8 + 2 \times (5 + 9) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{61047}{89352} := \frac{(61 - 04) \times 7}{8 \times (9 + (3 + 5)^2)} \\ & \frac{61047}{98532} := \frac{(6 + 10) \times 4 - 7}{9 \times (8 + 5 - 3) + 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{61053}{94827} := \frac{6 + 10 + 5^3}{9 + (4 \times 8 - 2) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{61054}{87932} := \frac{61 + 05^4}{8 \times 7 + 932} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{61074}{85293} := \frac{61 - 07 + 4}{(8 + 5 \times 2 + 9) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{6 + 10 \times (7 + 4)}{(8 - 5) \times 2 \times 9 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times 107 - 4}{(8 + 5^2) \times 9 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + 07 \times 4)}{(8 - 5)^2 \times 9 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61074}{95823} &:= \frac{6 + 10 \times (7 + 4)}{(9 + 5) \times (8 + 2 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + 07 \times 4)}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 - 2))) + 3} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61075}{92834} &:= \frac{(6 - 1^{07}) \times 5}{9 + 28 - 3 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times 07 \times 5}{9 + 2^8 - 3 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 10 \times 7 + 5}{(9 + 2 + 8) \times 34} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 075}{9 \times (2 \times 8 + 3) \times 4} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61203}{98457} &:= \frac{6 + 1 \times 20 - 3}{98 - 4 - 57} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1)^2 - 03}{9 \times (8 - 4 + 5) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{6 + (1 + 20) \times 3}{98 + 4 \times 5 - 7} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (20 + 3)}{(9 + 8 + 4 \times 5) \times 7} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61254}{90387} &:= \frac{61 + 25 - 4}{90 + 38 - 7} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61290}{73548} &:= \frac{((6 + 1)^2) - (9 - 0)}{(7 - 3) \times ((5 \times 4) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{((6 - 1) \times 2) + 90}{(7 - ((3 - 5) \times 4)) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (1 \times 2)) \times 90}{(7 - (3 - 5)) \times 48} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(6 - (1^2)) \times (9 - 0)}{7 + (35 + (4 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (1 + 2)) \times 90}{(7 \times (35 \times 4)) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (2 \times 90)}{7 \times (3 \times ((5 + 4) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (2 + (9 - 0))}{7 - (3 - (54 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (2 + 90)}{7 - (3 - 548)} \\ &:= \frac{6 - ((1^2)^9 + 0)}{(7 \times (3 - (5 - 4))) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times ((1^2) + (9 - 0))}{7 + (3 + (54 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (29 - 0))}{(7 \times ((3 + 5) \times 4)) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{6 + ((1^2) \times (9 - 0))}{7 + (3 + ((5 - 4) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (29 - 0))}{7 + ((3 \times (5 + 4)) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + (1 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 + (3 - (5 \times (4 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{61 - (2 + (9 - 0))}{(7 + (3 - 5)) \times (4 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{61 + (29 - 0)}{(7 - (3 - 5)) \times (4 + 8)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61397}{85204} &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + 3 \times (9 + 7))}{8 + 5 \times 20 \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{6 + 1 - (3 - 9) \times 7}{8 - (5 - 20) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1^3) \times 9 \times 7}{(8 - 5) \times 204} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times 39 \times 7}{(8 + 5) \times 204} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61398}{75042} &:= \frac{6 + (1 + (3 + (9 + 8)))}{(7 \times (5 - (0 \times 4))) - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times (1 \times (3 - (9 - 8)))}{7 - (5 + (0 - 42))} \\ &:= \frac{61 + (3 - (9 - 8))}{7 \times (5 - (0 - (4 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (13 - (9 - 8))}{7 + ((5 - (-04))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (3 + (9 \times 8)))}{7 + (50 + 42)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (3 + (9 + 8)))}{7 \times ((5 \times (04)) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (39 + 8))}{(7 \times 50) + (4 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (3 + 98))}{750 - (4 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times 3)) \times (9 \times 8)}{750 + 42} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61408}{75392} &:= \frac{6 + 1408}{7 \times (5 + 3 \times 9^2)} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61425}{79380} &:= \frac{(6 + 1 + 4 + 2) \times 5}{79 - 3 + 8 + 0} \\ \hline \blacktriangleright \frac{61470}{98352} &:= \frac{(6 - (1 + 4)) \times 70}{(((9 + 8) \times 3) + 5) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (1 - 4)) \times 70}{983 + (5^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 + 4)) + 70}{((9 \times 8) + (3 + 5)) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1^4) \times 70}{(9 + ((8 \times 3) - 5))^2} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (4 \times 70)}{9 + (((8 - 3)^5) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (4 + (7 - 0))}{(9 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{(61 + 4) \times (7 - 0)}{(9 + (8 - 3)) \times 52} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - ((1^4)^7 + 0)}{9 + (8 - (3 \times (5 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - ((1^4) - 70)}{98 - (3 - (5^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (4 + 70))}{9 \times (8 \times (3 + (5 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 - (4 - (7 - 0)))}{(9 - 8) \times ((3 + 5) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (4 + 70))}{(9 + ((8 + 3) \times 5)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 + (4 \times (7 - 0)))}{9 - (8 - (3 + 52))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (14 + 70)}{9 + (83 + 52)}$$

$$:= \frac{61 - (4 + (7 - 0))}{((9 \times (8 - 3)) - 5) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{61 + (4 + 70)}{9 \times (8 + ((3 + 5) \times 2))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61537}{98042} := \frac{6 + (1 + 5 \times 3) \times 7}{(98 - 04) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 1 \times 53) \times 7}{(9 + 80 \times 4) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61570}{89342} := \frac{61 \times 5 - 70}{8 - 9 + 342}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61740}{89523} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times 7)) \times 40}{(8 \times 95) - (2 \times 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 - (7 - 40))}{8 + ((9 \times 5) + (2 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (74 - 0))}{89 + ((5 - 2)^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (1^7)) \times (4 - 0)}{8 - (9 - (5 \times (2 \times 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (7 \times (4 - 0))}{(8 + 95) \times 2 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (174 - 0)}{(((8 + 9) \times 5) + 2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (7 \times 40)}{8 + (((9 \times 5)^2) - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (1 - 7)) \times 40}{8 \times ((9 \times (5 \times 2)) - 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61803}{72594} := \frac{6 \times (18 + 03)}{7^2 + 5 + 94}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61830}{79245} := \frac{61 \times 8 - 30}{7 \times 9^2 + 4 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61830}{92475} := \frac{61 \times 8 - 30}{(9 \times 2^4 - 7) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61830}{92745} := \frac{((6 + 1) \times 8) - 30}{9 + (2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 - 1) \times 8) + 30}{92 - (7 - (4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (1 - 8)) \times 30}{9 \times (2 + (7 \times (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (1 + 8)) + 30}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times (4 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times 18)^3 + 0}{(9 - (2 - (7 + 4)))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times 18) - 30}{9 \times ((2^7 - 4) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times 8)) \times (3 - 0)}{9 + (2 + (7 + 45))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 30}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times 45}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (1^8)) \times 30}{9 \times (2 + ((7 \times 4) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times (3 - 0))}{9 \times (27 - (4 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times 30)}{9 \times (2 \times (7 \times (4 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (8 \times (3 - 0))}{(9 + (2 - 7)) \times 45}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - ((1^8) - (3 - 0))}{9 + ((2^7 - 4) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (1 - (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 - (2 - (7 - (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (1 - (8 + (3 - 0)))}{9 + (2 - (7 - (4 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (1 \times (8 - 30))}{(9 - 2) \times (7 + (4 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((1^8) \times 30)}{9 \times (2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((1^8) + (3 - 0))}{9 \times (2 - (7 - (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((1^8) + 30)}{9 \times (((2 + 7) \times 4) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((1 + 8) \times (3 - 0))}{(9 - (2 \times (7 - 4)))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((1 + 8)^3 + 0)}{9^{2-7+4+5}}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 - (8 - 30))}{9 \times ((2 \times 7) + (4 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 \times (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 - (2 + (7 - 45))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 \times (8 + (3 - 0)))}{9 \times ((2 \times (7 - 4)) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 \times (83 - 0))}{9 \times ((2^7) - 45)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 - ((2 - (7 + 4)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (8 \times (3 - 0)))}{9 \times ((2 + (7 - 4)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (8 + (3 - 0)))}{9 \times (2 \times (7 + (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (83 - 0))}{9 + (2 + 745)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (18 \times (3 - 0))}{9 \times (2 + (7 + 45))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (18 \times 30)}{9 \times (27 \times (4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (18 + (3 - 0))}{9 + ((2 + 7) \times (4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6^{1^8 \times 3 + 0}}{9 \times (27 + 4 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1^{830})}{9 - (2 + (7 - (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 \times ((2 \times (7 - 4))^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((1^8) - (3 - 0))}{9 - ((2^7 - 4) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((1 + 8) \times 30)}{9 \times (2 \times ((7 \times 4) - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 - (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 + (2 - (7 - (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (8 \times 30))}{9 - ((2 - 74) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 \times (8 + 30))}{9 + (2 + ((7 + 4) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 + (8 - (3 - 0)))}{9 + (2 - (7 \times (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 + (8 + (3 - 0)))}{9 + (2 + (7 + (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (1 + (83 - 0))}{9 + (2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (18 \times (3 - 0))}{9 \times (2 + (7 - (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (18 \times 30)}{(9 + 2) \times 74 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (18 + 30)}{9 \times (2 - (7 \times (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 1830}{9 + 2745}$$

$$:= \frac{61 - (8 - (3 - 0))}{92 - (7 - (4 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{61 - (8 + (3 - 0))}{(9 + (2 \times (7 - 4))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{618 + 30}{9 \times ((2^7) - (4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{618 - 30}{927 - 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61950}{78234} := \frac{(6 + 1^9) \times 50}{(7 + 8 - 2) \times 34}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62034}{91785} := \frac{6 \times (20 - 3) - 4}{(9 + 1) \times (7 + 8) - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62307}{94185} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3 + 07}{9 + 4 \times (1 + 8 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62307}{94815} := \frac{(6 \times (2 + (3 - 0))) - 7}{9 + ((4 \times 8) - (1 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^2) + (3 - (-07))}{(9 - (4 - (8 + 1))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - 2) \times (30 - 7)}{((9 \times 4) - (8 \times 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((6^2) \times (3 - 0)) + 7}{(9 - 4) \times ((8 - 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (2 - (3 \times (-07)))}{(9 + ((4 \times 8) + 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 2) \times (30 - 7)}{(9 + (48 - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (2 \times (30 - 7))}{((9 \times 4) - 8) \times 15}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^2) \times (30 - 7)}{9 \times (4 \times ((8 - 1) \times 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62310}{97485} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 310}{97 \times (4 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{62 \times 3 \times 1 + 0}{(9 + 7 \times 4) \times 8 - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 31 + 0}{97 + 485}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62370}{91854} := \frac{6 \times 2^3 + 7 - 0}{9 \times (1 + 8 \times (5 - 4))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62370}{98415} := \frac{(6^2 - 3) \times 70}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62375}{94810} := \frac{(6 - 2^3 + 7) \times 5}{9 \times 4 - 8 + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 2 + 37 + 5}{94 - 8 - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 2 \times 37 - 5}{(9 + 4) \times 8 + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 2 + 37) \times 5}{9 \times (48 - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 2 - 3) \times 75}{(9 + 48) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62403}{97185} := \frac{62 - 4 + 03}{97 + 1 - 8 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62415}{83790} := \frac{62 - 4 + 15}{8 + (3 + 7) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62478}{90513} := \frac{6 \times ((2 + (4 + 7)) \times 8)}{905 - (1^3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 2 - 4) \times 78}{90 \times 5 - 1 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62478}{93015} := \frac{6 \times (24 + 7) - 8}{9 \times 30 \times 1 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62481}{70953} := \frac{6 + 2^4 \times (8 - 1)}{70 + (9 - 5)^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62510}{97384} := \frac{6^2 \times 5 + 10}{(9 + 73 - 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62514}{78039} := \frac{(6 \times 25 + 1) \times 4}{7 + (80 + 3) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{62730}{81549} := \frac{6 + (27 - (3 - 0))}{8 - (1 \times (5 - (4 \times 9)))} \\ & := \frac{(6^2) + (7 - (3 - 0))}{8 - (1 \times (5 - 49))} \\ & := \frac{6 + ((2 \times 7) + 30)}{((8 + (1 + 5)) \times 4) + 9} \\ & := \frac{6 + (2 \times (7 + 30))}{8 \times ((1^5) \times (4 + 9))} \\ & := \frac{(6^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{((8 \times (1 + 5)) + 4) \times 9} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (2 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{(8 \times 15) + (4 \times 9)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (2 + (73 - 0))}{(8 + 1) \times (5 \times (4 + 9))} \\ & \frac{62730}{84915} := \frac{6 + 2 + 730}{84 + 915} \\ & \frac{62730}{98154} := \frac{62 - 7 + 30}{9 + 8 \times 15 + 4} \\ & \frac{62790}{81354} := \frac{6^2 + 79 + 0}{8 + 1 + 35 \times 4} \\ & \frac{62810}{75943} := \frac{(6 + 2 \times 8) \times 10}{7 \times (5 + 9 \times 4 - 3)} \\ & \frac{62814}{70395} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 8 - 1) + 4}{(7 - 03 + 9) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{6 - 2 + 8 \times 14}{70 + (3 + 9) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{6 \times 281 - 4}{70 \times 3 \times 9 - 5} \\ & \frac{62913}{80754} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 9) + 1^3}{80 + 7 - 5 + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{6 + 2^{9+1-3}}{(8 + 07 \times 5) \times 4} \\ & \frac{63018}{94527} := \frac{(6 \times (3^{01})) + 8}{((9 - 4) \times 5) + (2 \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (-01))) + 8}{9 - (4 + (5 \times (2 - 7)))} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (30 \times 1)) + 8}{94 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (30 + 1)) - 8}{(9 - 4) \times 52 + 7} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (30 - 1)) + 8}{(9 + 4) \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times 30) + 18}{9 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 2)) - 7)} \\ & := \frac{(6^{3-01}) \times 8}{(9 \times 45) + 27} \\ & := \frac{(6^{3-01}) + 8}{9 + ((4^5 - 2) - 7)} \\ & := \frac{(6^{3-01}) - 8}{(9 + (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{(6^3) \times (0 - (1 - 8))}{((9 + (4 + 5))^2) \times 7} \\ & := \frac{(6 + 30) \times 18}{945 + 27} \\ & := \frac{(6 - 30) \times (1 - 8)}{9 + ((4 + 5) \times 27)} \\ & := \frac{6 - ((3 \times (0 \times 1)) - 8)}{9 + (4 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (3 - (0 - (1^8)))}{9 + (4 - (5 - (2 - 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (3 \times (0 - (1 \times 8)))}{9 + (4 + (5 + 27))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (3 \times (0 \times 18))}{9 - (4 \times (5 + (2 - 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6 - (3 \times (0 - 18))}{(9 - (4 - 5)) \times (2 + 7)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times ((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 8)}{9 \times (4 - (5 - (2 + 7)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{6 \times ((3 + (-01))^8)}{(9 + (4 + 5)) \times (2^7)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 - (0 - (1 \times 8)))}{9 \times (((4 + 5) \times 2) - 7)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 - (0 - (1^8)))}{9 \times (4 - (5 + (2 - 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 - (0 - (1 + 8)))}{9 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 - (0 \times 18))}{9 - (4 + (5 - 27))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 - (0 - 18))}{9 + (4 \times (5 \times (2 + 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 \times (0 + (1 \times 8)))}{(9 + (4 - 5)) \times 27} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 \times (0 + 18))}{9 \times (45 + (2 + 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3^{-01+8})}{(9^4) \times ((5 \times 2) - 7)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3^{01 \times 8})}{9^{4 \times (5-2)-7}} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (3 + (0 - (1^8)))}{9 - ((4 - 5) \times (2 + 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 - (1 \times 8))}{9 \times (4 + ((5^2) - 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 - (1^8))}{9 \times (4 - (5 \times (2 - 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 \times 18)}{9 \times (4 \times (5 \times 27))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 \times (1^8))}{(9 - (4 - 5)) \times 27} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 + (1 \times 8))}{(94 \times 5) - (2^7)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 + (1^8))}{9 \times (45 - (2 \times 7))} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (30 + (1 - 8))}{9 \times (4 + (5 + (2 \times 7)))} \\ & := \frac{6^3 + 0 \times 18}{9 \times (4 + (5 + 27))} \\ & := \frac{6^{3+0-1^8}}{9 - (4 - ((5 + 2) \times 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((3 - (-01)) \times 8)}{(9 + (4 - 5))^2 - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((3 + (-01)) \times 8)}{(9 \times 4) - ((5 \times 2) - 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 - (0 - (1^8)))}{9 - (4 - (5 - (2 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (0 - (1 - 8)))}{9 - (4 - (5 + (2 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (30 \times (1 \times 8))}{9 - (4 - (52 \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (30 \times (1 + 8))}{9 + (45 \times (2 + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (30 + 18)}{9 + (4 \times ((5^2) - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 3018}{9 + 4527}$$

$$:= \frac{63 - (0 - (1 - 8))}{(9 - (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{63 \times (0 + (1 \times 8))}{9 \times (4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{63 + (0 - (1^8))}{9 + (4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{63 + (0 - (1 - 8))}{(9 - (4 - (5 \times 2))) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{630 - (1 \times 8)}{(94 \times (5 \times 2)) - 7}$$

$$:= \frac{630 \times (1 + 8)}{945 \times (2 + 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{630 - 18}{945 - 27}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63074}{95128} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 07 - 4}{(95 + 1) \times 2 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6^3 + 07 \times 4}{(9 \times 5 + 1^2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63124}{78905} := \frac{((6 \times (3 \times 1))^2) + 4}{(7 - 89) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times (3 \times 1)) + 2) \times 4}{7 + (8 + (90 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times (3 - 1)) + 2) \times 4}{(7 \times 8) + (9 + 05)}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times 31) - 2) \times 4}{7 + (8 + 905)}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 + (3 + 1))^2) + 4}{((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 + 3) \times 12) + 4}{((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times 31) - (2 - 4)}{((7 \times 8) - (9 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^{3-1^2}) + 4}{(7 - (8 + 9)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^{3-1}) + (2^4)}{(7 \times 8) + (9 - (0 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^3) \times (1 + 24)}{(7 + 8) \times (90 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + ((3 + 1)^2)) \times 4}{7 + (8 + (90 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(63 + (1 \times 2)) \times 4}{(7 - (8 \times 9)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{(63 - 1) \times (2 + 4)}{7 + (8 + (90 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (3 - (1 + 24))}{7 \times ((8 - 9) \times (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((3 - (1^2))^4)}{(7 + (8 + (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((3 - 1)^{2+4})}{(7 + (89 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((31 \times 2) - 4)}{(78 + (9 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 - (1 - (2^4)))}{(7 + 8) \times (9 - (0 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 - (1 - (2 + 4)))}{7 + (8 - (9 \times (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 + (1 - (2 - 4)))}{(7 - 8) \times (9 \times (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 + (1 + 24))}{(7 + 8) \times (9 + 05)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 - (1 - (2^4)))}{(7 + (8 - (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 - (1 - 24))}{(7 - (8 - (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (1 - (2 - 4)))}{7 + (8 - (9 \times (0 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6312 + 4}{7890 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6312 - 4}{7890 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63140}{78925} := \frac{((6 \times 3) - 1) \times 40}{(78 + 92) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (3 \times 1)) \times 40}{(7 + (8 - 9)) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (3 + 1)) \times 40}{(7 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (3 - 1)) \times (4 - 0)}{(7 + (8 - (9 + 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (3 - 1)) \times 40}{(7 - (8 - 9)) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + 1)) - (4 - 0)}{(7 + ((8 - 9) \times 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + 1)) + (4 - 0)}{7 \times ((8 - (9 - 2)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + 1)) + 40}{(7 - (8 - 9)) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 - 1)) + 40}{78 - ((9 \times 2) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^3 \times 1) - (4 - 0)}{((7 + 8) \times (9 \times 2)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^3 \times 1) + (4 - 0)}{((7 + 8) \times (9 \times 2)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^3 \times 1) + 40}{((7 - (8 - 9))^2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^{3+1}) + (4 - 0)}{((7 \times 8) + 9) \times 25}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^{3-1}) - (4 - 0)}{7 - (8 - (9 + (2^5)))}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(6^{3-1}) \times (4-0)}{7 + ((89 \times 2) - 5)} \\
 := \frac{(6^{3-1}) + (4-0)}{7 + (8 + ((9-2) \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) \times (1 + (4-0))}{(7+8) \times (9 \times (2 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) + 140}{(78 + (9+2)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6-3) \times 140}{7 \times ((8 + (9-2)) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 - (3 - (1^4 + 0))}{7 - (8 - (9 + (2 - 5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (3 - (1 + 40))}{7 + (8 \times (9 + (2 - 5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3-1) \times 40)}{(7 + (8+9)) \times 25} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 - (1^4 + 0))}{7 - (8 + (9 - 25))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 - (1 - 40))}{(7 + (8 \times (9 - 2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 \times (1 \times (4 - 0)))}{7 + ((8 \times (9 + 2)) - 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 + (1^4 + 0))}{(7 - (8 - (9 - 2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6^{3-1^4+0}}{(7 - ((8-9) \times 2)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 - (1^4 + 0))}{7 + ((8-9) \times (2 - 5))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 - (1 - 40))}{(7 + (8 - 9)) \times (2 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 + (314 - 0)}{(7 - (8 - (9^2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{63 + (1 - (4 - 0))}{7 - (8 - ((9^2) - 5))} \\
 := \frac{63 + (1 + (4 - 0))}{7 - (8 - ((9^2) + 5))} \\
 := \frac{63 + (1 + 40)}{(7 + (8 + (9 + 2))) \times 5}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63152}{78940} := \frac{((6 - (3 - 1)) \times 5)^2}{(7 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (3 \times 1)) \times 52}{(7 + 8) \times (9 + (4 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (3 - 1)) \times 52}{((7 \times 8) + 9) \times (4 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (1 \times 5))) + 2}{(7 \times (8 + 9)) - (4 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (1 + 5))) - 2}{78 - (9 + (4 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(6^{3 \times 1^5}) \times 2}{(7 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) + (1 + (5 + 2))}{7 \times (8 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{(6 + ((3 - 1) \times 5))^2}{(7 - (8 - 9)) \times 40} \\
 := \frac{(6 + ((3 - 1)^5)) \times 2}{((7 + 8) \times 9) - 40} \\
 := \frac{(6 + (3 - 1)) \times (5 \times 2)}{7 + (89 + (4 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{(63 + 1) \times (5 - 2)}{(7 + (8 - 9)) \times 40} \\
 := \frac{6 - (3 - (1 \times (5^2)))}{7 - (8 - (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3 - 1) \times (5^2))}{7 + (8 + (9 \times 40))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3 - 1)^{5+2})}{(7 + (8 + 9)) \times 40} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((31 - 5) \times 2)}{78 \times (9 - (4 - 0))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 + (1^{5^2}))}{7 - (8 + (9 - 40))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 + (15 + 2))}{(7 \times 8) + (94 - 0)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (31 + (5 - 2))}{7 - (8 \times (9 - 40))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 - (1^{5^2}))}{7 + (8 - (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 - (1 - 52))}{7 + ((8 + 9) \times (4 - 0))}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{6 + (3 \times (1 + (5^2)))}{(7 \times 8) + (9 + 40)} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 + (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{7 + (8 + (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 + (1 + (5 \times 2)))}{(7 \times 8) + (9 - 40)} \\
 := \frac{631 - (5 - 2)}{789 - (4 - 0)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63180}{74529} := \frac{(6 - 3) \times 180}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63180}{95472} := \frac{6 + 31 + 8 + 0}{9 + 54 + 7 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63270}{84915} := \frac{6 + (3 - 2) \times 70}{(8 + 4) \times 9 - 1 - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63270}{91485} := \frac{(6 + 3)^2 - 7 + 0}{(9 + 1 + 4) \times 8 - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63279}{84105} := \frac{(6 + 3 \times 2) \times 79}{84 \times (10 + 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 - 3 \times (2 - 79)}{8 \times 4 \times 10 - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63284}{79105} := \frac{(((6 + 3)^2) + 8) \times 4}{(79 + 10) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{((6 \times (3^2)) + 8) \times 4}{((7 \times 9) - (1 - 0)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{((6 \times 3)^2) - (8 - 4)}{(79 + (1 - 0)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{((6 \times 3) + 2) \times (8 \times 4)}{(7 + 9) \times (10 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{((6 \times 3) - 2) \times (8 - 4)}{(7 + (9 \times (1 - 0))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{((6 \times 3) - 2) \times 84}{(7 + 9) \times 105}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{((6 + (3 - 2))^8) \times 4}{(7^{9-1+0}) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (3 - (2 + 8))) \times 4}{(7 \times (9 + (1 - 0))) - 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (3 + 2)) \times (8 - 4)}{(7 - (9 - 1)) \times (-05)} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (3 - 28)) \times 4}{((7 + 9) \times 10) - 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))) + 4}{((7 \times 9) + 10) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times 2)) + (8 \times 4)}{(7 + (9 + (1 - 0))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times 28)) + 4}{(7 \times (9 \times 10)) + 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times 28)) - 4}{(7 \times (9 \times 10)) - 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times 32) + (8 \times 4)}{7 \times ((9 - (1 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times 32) + 84}{(79 - 10) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) - (28 \times 4)}{(7 + (9 + 10)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) + ((2^8) + 4)}{7 \times ((9 \times 10) - 5)} \\
 := \frac{(6^3) + (2 \times (8 \times 4))}{7 \times ((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(6 + ((3 \times 2) - 8))^4}{((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 + ((3 - 2) \times 8)) \times 4}{7 \times (9 + (1^{05}))} \\
 := \frac{(6 + (3 - (2 - 8))) \times 4}{(7 + (9 - (1 - 0))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 + 3 + 2) \times (8 + 4)}{((7 + 9) \times 10) + 5} \\
 := \frac{(6 + (3 - 2)) \times (8 + 4)}{7 \times (9 + (1 - (-05)))} \\
 := \frac{(63 - (2 + 8)) \times 4}{((7 \times 9) - 10) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(63 + (2 \times 8)) \times 4}{79 \times (1 \times (05))} \\
 := \frac{(63 - 2) \times 84}{7 \times (910 + 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 - ((3 \times (2 - 8)) - 4)}{7 \times (9 + (1 + (-05)))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (3 \times (2 - (8 - 4)))}{7 + (9 - (1^{05}))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (3 \times (2 - 84))}{7 \times (9 \times (1 \times (05)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 4)}{(7 - 91) \times (-05)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3 + (2 + 8)) \times 4)}{(79 - (1 - 0)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3 + 2) \times 84)}{7 \times (9 \times (10 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((3 - 2) \times (8 \times 4))}{(7 + 9) \times (10 + 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 + ((3 \times (2 + 8)) - 4)}{(7 - (9 - 10)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 + ((3 \times 2) - (8 - 4))}{7 + (9 - (1 - (-05)))} \\
 := \frac{6 + ((3 \times 2) + (8 - 4))}{7 + (9 - (1 + (-05)))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (3 \times (2 + (8 - 4)))}{(7 + (9 - 10)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{63 \times ((2 \times 8) - 4)}{7 \times (9 \times (10 + 5))} \\
 := \frac{632 - (8 - 4)}{(79 \times 10) - 5} \\
 := \frac{632 + (8 - 4)}{(79 \times 10) + 5} \\
 := \frac{6328 + 4}{7910 + 5} \\
 := \frac{6328 - 4}{7910 - 5} \\
 := \frac{63420}{75198} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4 - 2 + 0}{7 + 5 - 1 + 9 \times 8} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times 3 - 4) \times 20}{(7 \times 5 + 1) \times 9 + 8} \\
 := \frac{63428}{70195} := \frac{634 + 2 - 8}{70 \times (1 + 9) - 5} \\
 := \frac{63495}{70218} := \frac{6 + 34 + 9 \times 5}{70 + (2 + 1) \times 8} \\
 := \frac{63495}{82170} := \frac{6 + 3 + 4 + 9 - 5}{8 + 2 \times 1 \times 7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{6 - 3 + (4 + 9) \times 5}{82 - 1 + 7 + 0} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (3 \times (4 + 9) - 5)}{8 + 2^{1+7} + 0} \\
 := \frac{63504}{71928} := \frac{6^3 - 5 \times 04}{(7 - 1) \times (9 + 28)} \\
 := \frac{63504}{89712} := \frac{6 + 3 + 50 + 4}{8 + 9 \times (7 + 1 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{63 \times 5 + 0 \times 4}{89 \times (7 - 1 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{63 \times (5 + 04)}{89 \times (7 + 1 \times 2)} \\
 := \frac{(6 + 3) \times 504}{8 + (9 + 71)^2} \\
 := \frac{63504}{91287} := \frac{63 + 5 - 04}{9 \times (1 + 2 + 8) - 7} \\
 := \frac{(6 + 3 \times 50) \times 4}{912 - 8 - 7} \\
 := \frac{6 + 3 \times (50 - 4)}{9 \times 1 \times (2 \times 8 + 7)} \\
 := \frac{6 + 3 \times 50 + 4}{(9 + 1) \times (2 \times 8 + 7)} \\
 := \frac{(6 + 3 - 5) \times 04}{9 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 7} \\
 := \frac{63504}{91728} := \frac{(6 + 3) \times (5 - (-04))}{9 \times (1 \times (7 - (2 - 8)))} \\
 := \frac{(6 + 3) \times (5 \times (04))}{(9 + 17) \times (2 + 8)}
 \end{array}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+3) \times 504}{9 \times (1 \times 728)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times (5 - (0 \times 4)))}{(9+1) \times (7 - (2-8))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times (5 - (-04)))}{9 \times ((17 \times 2) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times (5 \times (04)))}{((9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 + (5 - (-04)))}{(9 - (1 - (7 - 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6^{3-5+04}}{9 + (1 - (7 \times (2-8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6^3 \times (5 - 04)}{((9-1) \times 7) + (2^8)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3^{5-04})}{9 + (1 - (7 - (2+8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (5 - (-04)))}{9 + (1 \times (7 + (2+8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (50 + 4))}{(9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 28}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (35 - (-04))}{9 - (1 - ((7^2) + 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{63 - (5 - (-04))}{9 - (1 - (7 \times (2+8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{63 \times (5 - (-04))}{91 + 728}$$

$$:= \frac{63 + (50 + 4)}{(9 \times 17) + (2 \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{635 - (-04)}{917 - (2-8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63510}{84972} := \frac{(63-5) \times 10}{(8-4) \times 97 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63512}{70984} := \frac{6+3+5+1+2}{7+0 \times 9+8+4}$$

$$:= \frac{6+3 \times 5 \times (1+2)}{70-9-8+4}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 3^{5-1} - 2}{7 \times 09 + 8 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^3 + 5) \times (1 + 2)}{709 + 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63528}{79410} := \frac{((6 - (3 - 5))^2) \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times (4 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}{7 + (94 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5^2))) - 8}{(7 + (9 + 4)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 + 2))) + 8}{79 - (4 - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 + 2))) - 8}{79 - (4 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 - 2))) - 8}{7 \times (9 - (4 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}{7 + (9 + (4 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (3 - 5)) \times (2 \times 8)}{(7 + 9) \times (4 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (35 + 2)) \times 8}{(7 + (9 \times 4)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - 3) \times ((5^2) \times 8)}{(79 - 4) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (3 - (5 + 28))}{(7 \times (9 - 4)) + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (3 \times (5 \times (2 - 8)))}{(7 + (9 - 4)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((3 - 5) \times (2 - 8))}{(7 \times (9 + 4)) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 - (5 - (2 + 8)))}{(7 \times 9) - (4 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 - (5 + (2 - 8)))}{7 + (9 + (4 + 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 + (5 - (2 - 8)))}{7 \times (9 - (4 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 \times ((5 \times 2) + 8))}{79 - (4 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (5 - (2 - 8)))}{(7 \times (9 - 4)) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 + (5 + (2 - 8)))}{7 + (9 + (4 - 10))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63549}{80127} := \frac{(6 - 3) \times 5 \times 4 + 9}{80 + 1^2 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (3 - 5) \times 4 + 9}{8 + (01 + 2) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63720}{94518} := \frac{(6 + 3 \times 7) \times 20}{(94 - 5) \times (1 + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{6^3 \times (7 - 2) + 0}{(94 - 5) \times 18}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63759}{84210} := \frac{6 \times (3 + 7 \times 5 \times 9)}{(8 + 4) \times 210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63825}{97014} := \frac{6 \times (3 + 82) \times 5}{(970 - 1) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63840}{71592} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 8 - 4 + 0}{71 + 5 + 9^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63910}{74285} := \frac{63 + 91 + 0}{(7 + 4^2) \times 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63918}{72504} := \frac{6 - 3 + (9 - 1) \times 8}{(7 \times 2 + 5) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63950}{74182} := \frac{6 + 3 - 9 + 50}{(7 + 4 + 18) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+39) \times 5 + 0}{7^{4-1} - 82}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (4-1))^{5-2}}{(703+8) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63954}{87210} := \frac{6 - (3 - (9 - (5 - 4)))}{8 + (7 \times (2 - 1 + 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64025}{97318} := \frac{(6+4) \times 02 + 5}{9+7 \times 3 \times 1 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64251}{90387} := \frac{6+4-2+51}{9 \times 03 + 8 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((3 \times (9 - 5)) + 4)}{(8 - (7 - 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+4) \times 2 \times 5}{(9+7+3 \times 1) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (3 \times (9 \times (5 - 4)))}{(8+7) \times (2 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 40 + 2 \times 5}{97 \times (3 + 1) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64253}{70819} := \frac{6+4+2+5^3}{70 + (8+1) \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{63 - (9 - (5 - 4))}{87 - (2 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+4)^{-02+5}}{(9 \times 7 \times 3 + 1) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (3 - (9 + 54))}{8 + (72 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6+4)^{02} \times 5}{(97 - 3 + 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64320}{71958} := \frac{(6-4) \times 320}{719 + 5 - 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(((6-3) \times 9) - 5) \times 4}{8 \times (7 - (2 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{64 \times (3+2) + 0}{7 \times (1+9) \times 5 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{63 + (95 - 4)}{(8 - 7) \times 210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64125}{83790} := \frac{6+4^{1+2} + 5}{8 + (3+7) \times 9 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (3 + (9 + 54))}{((8 \times 7) - 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (((3 \times 9) - 5) \times 4)}{8 \times ((7 + 2) \times 10)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64152}{70389} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 1 \times (5 - 2)}{7 - 0 \times 3 + 8 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{81972} := \frac{(6+4+3) \times 50}{819+7+2}$$

$$:= \frac{64 \times (5+1) \times 2}{7+938+0}$$

$$:= \frac{((6-4)^7) \times (3+2)}{80 \times (9 + (1^5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{87219} := \frac{(6+4+3) \times 50}{872+1 \times 9}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times 4)^{5-1^2}}{7 \times 9^3 \times 80}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times 4)^{7-3-2}}{80 \times (9 \times (1^5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{97812} := \frac{6+4^3+5+0}{(9+7) \times (8-1) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(6^4) - 732}{(80 \times 9) - 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64370}{98125} := \frac{6 \times (4+37) + 0}{(9 \times 8 + 1 + 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64701}{95823} := \frac{6+4+70-1}{9 \times (5-8 \times (2-3))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (4 + (7 - 3))) \times 2}{(8 + ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 43 + 70}{(98 + 1 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64728}{91350} := \frac{(6-4)^7 \times 2 - 8}{(9+1-3) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (47 - 3)) \times 2}{80 + (9 \times (1 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-4) \times (7 + (3^2))}{8 \times (0 + (9 + (1 - 5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64512}{79380} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 512}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64732}{80915} := \frac{((6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 3) + 2}{80 + ((9 + 1) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-4) \times (73 \times 2)}{((8 \times (09)) + 1) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6-4)^{7+3-2}}{8 \times (0 + ((9-1) \times 5))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(64 \times (7+3))^2}{80^{9-1-5}} & & := \frac{64 \times (7+(3-2))}{80 \times (9-(1^5))} & & \frac{64970}{83215} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 9 - 70}{8 \times (3+21) - 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6 - ((4 - (7^3)) \times 2)}{(80+91) \times 5} & & := \frac{64^{7-3 \times 2}}{8 \times (0+(9+(1^5)))} & & \frac{65032}{87941} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 03 - 2}{87 - 9 + 41} \\
 &:= \frac{6 - (4 + (7 - (3^2)))}{8 + (0 - (9 - (1+5)))} & & := \frac{64+7+3+2}{80+9+1+5} & & \frac{65043}{81972} := \frac{650+4+3}{819+7+2} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times ((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 2)}{(80 \times (9-1)) + 5} & & := \frac{64+732}{80+915} & & \frac{65043}{87219} := \frac{650+4+3}{872+1 \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times ((4 \times (7-3))^2)}{80 \times (9+15)} & & := \frac{647+3+2}{809+1+5} & & \frac{65120}{97384} := \frac{(6+5 \times 1) \times 20}{9+(7+3) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times ((4 \times 7) + (3 \times 2))}{(8 - (-09)) \times 15} & & := \frac{647+3-2}{809+1^5} & & \frac{65124}{78390} := \frac{6 \times (5-1 \times 2)^4}{(7+8) \times 39+0} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times ((4 \times 7) + 32)}{(80+(9+1)) \times 5} & & \frac{64752}{93081} := \frac{64-7-5^2}{9+30+8-1} & & \frac{65128}{70943} := \frac{6+5 \times 1 \times (2+8)}{(7+09) \times 4-3} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times ((4+7) \times (3 \times 2))}{(8 - (0-91)) \times 5} & & := \frac{(6+4-7+5)^2}{93+0 \times 8-1} & & := \frac{(6+5+1+2) \times 8}{70+9+43} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4 - (7 - (3^2)))}{(8 - ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5} & & := \frac{(6 \times (4-7+5))^2}{9 \times (3 \times 08-1)} & & := \frac{6 \times (5-1) \times 28}{(70-9) \times 4 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4 \times (7+3+2))}{8 \times (0+(9 \times (1 \times 5)))} & & \frac{64832}{90157} := \frac{(6+4-8) \times 32}{90+1+5-7} & & \frac{65142}{90783} := \frac{6 \times (5-1) \times 4-2}{(9+07) \times 8+3} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4 \times (7+(3-2)))}{80 \times (9-(1+5))} & & := \frac{64 \times (8-3+2)}{(90-1^5) \times 7} & & \frac{65148}{79032} := \frac{6+5 \times (-1+4+8)}{79-03-2} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4^{7-3 \times 2})}{80 - ((9+1) \times 5)} & & \frac{64870}{92315} := \frac{6 - (4-8) \times 70}{92+315} & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4^{7-3-2})}{8 \times (0+(9+(1+5)))} & & := \frac{6 \times (4 \times 8+7) + 0}{9 \times 2+315} & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4+(7-(3-2)))}{(8 \times (0+(9+1))) - 5} & & := \frac{(6-4) \times (8+70)}{9 \times 23+15} & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4+(7+(3-2)))}{(8 - (0 - (9+1))) \times 5} & & \frac{64872}{93015} := \frac{64+8 \times (7+2)}{(9+30 \times 1) \times 5} & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 + (((4 \times 7) + 3) \times 2)}{(8 - (0 - (9 \times 1))) \times 5} & & := \frac{6 \times (4-8+72)}{(9+30) \times 15} & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 + ((4+(7 \times 3)) \times 2)}{80 - (9+(1^5))} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 + (4 - (7 - (3^2)))}{(8 \times (0 \times 9)) + 15} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{6 + (4 + (7 \times (3 \times 2)))}{80 - (9 + (1 + 5))} & & & & \\
 &:= \frac{64 \times (7 + (3 \times 2))}{80 \times (9 - (1 - 5))} & & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65184}{73920} := \frac{65 + 1 \times 8 \times 4}{(7+3) \times (9+2) + 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65184}{93702} &:= \frac{6-5-1+8 \times 4}{9+37+0 \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(6-5+1)^8 \times 4}{(9^3+7) \times 02} \\ &:= \frac{(6-5+1) \times 8 \times 4}{9 \times (3+7) + 02} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (5+1^8) \times 4}{9 \times (3 \times 7 + 02)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (5+1) - 8) \times 4}{93+70-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65314}{90287} &:= \frac{6 + (5+3-1) \times 4}{9 \times (-02+8) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{65+3 \times 1^4}{9-02+87} \\ &:= \frac{(65+3) \times 14}{(90 \times 2+8) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{81972} := \frac{6+53-4+0}{8+1 \times 9 \times 7-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{87912} := \frac{6+53-4+0}{8+7 \times 9+1+2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{91872} &:= \frac{6 \times (5 \times 3 + 40)}{(9-1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (5^3 + 40)}{(9-1) \times 87 \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65349}{70281} := \frac{6-5+3+49}{7^{02}+8 \times 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65372}{94180} &:= \frac{6+5^3-72}{9-4+1 \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{(6+53) \times (7+2)}{9 \times (4+1+80)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65379}{80142} &:= \frac{6+5+3+79}{8 \times 014+2} \\ &:= \frac{6+5 \times (3-7+9)}{8 \times (01+4) - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65382}{71094} := \frac{65 + (3 \times 8)^2}{710-9-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65392}{81740} := \frac{6 + ((5 + (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 \times (7 - (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - ((5 + (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 - (7 - (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (5 + (3 - (9 \times 2)))}{8 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((5 - (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 - (7 \times (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 + (3 \times (9 - 2)))}{8 - (1 + (7 - 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 + ((3 \times 9) - 2))}{((8 - 1) \times 7) - (4 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 + (3 \times (9 + 2)))}{8 + (1 \times (7 + 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 + (39 - 2))}{(8 \times (1 + 7)) - (4 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 + (39 + 2))}{8 + (17 + 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 \times (3 + (9 - 2)))}{81 - (7 + (4 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (5 - 39)) \times 2}{(8 + 17) \times (4 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((5^3) - (9 - 2))}{81 + (74 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (((5 \times 3) + 9) \times 2)}{(8 + (1^7)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (5 - (3 - 9))) - 2}{(8 + (1 - 7)) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65403}{91728} := \frac{65 \times (40 + 3)}{(9 + 1) \times 7^2 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65403}{92781} := \frac{65 + 4^{03}}{(9 + 2 \times 7) \times 8 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65412}{70389} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times (4 - 1) + 2}{7 + 03 + 89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65412}{78039} := \frac{6 + 5^4 + 1^2}{7 + (80 + 3) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65432}{81790} := \frac{(6 - (5 - (4 + 3)))^2}{8 \times ((1^7) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (4 - 3))) + 2}{((8 - 1) \times 7) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(65 - (4 + 3)) \times 2}{(8 \times 17) + (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(65 - (4 - 3)) \times 2}{81 + (79 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(65 - 43) \times 2}{(8 \times (1 + 7)) - (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (5 - (4 - (3 - 2)))}{8 - (1 - (7 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 + (7 - 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((5 + 43) \times 2)}{8 \times ((1^7) \times 90)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (5 \times (4 + 32))}{(8 + (1 \times 7)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (5 + (4 + (3^2)))}{(8 + (1 \times 7)) \times (9 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (5 + (4 + 3 + 2))}{8 + (1 \times (7 + 90))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)}{(8 + (1 - 7)) \times 90}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (5 - (4 - (3 - 2)))}{8 - (1 \times (7 - (9 - 0)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))}{8 - (1 - (7 \times (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{6 + (5 + (4 + 3 + 2))}{8 + (1 + (7 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{6 + (5 + (43 - 2))}{(8 \times (1 \times 7)) + (9 - 0)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + (54 + 32)}{8 + (17 + 90)} \\
 & := \frac{654 - (3 \times 2)}{(8 + (17)) \times 90} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65709}{83142} & := \frac{65 - 7 - 09}{8^3 - 1^4 - 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65714}{89320} & := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 7 \times 1 - 4}{(8 + 9 - 3) \times 20} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65807}{91324} & := \frac{(-6 + 5 + 8) \times 07}{(9 - 1 + 3^2) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 80 + 7}{9 - 1 + 32 \times 4} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65824}{93170} & := \frac{65 \times 8 + 24}{(9 + 3 - 1) \times 70} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65873}{90142} & := \frac{6 - 5 + 8 + 7 + 3}{9 + 01 + 4^2} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times 5 + 8) \times (7 - 3)}{(90 + 14) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + 5 + 8) \times 7 \times 3}{(90 + 1) \times (4 + 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 \times 87 \times 3}{(901 - 4) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (5 + 8) - 7 \times 3}{90 - 14 + 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65930}{71482} & := \frac{6 + 59 + 30}{7 + 1 \times 48 \times 2} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65934}{71280} & := \frac{6 + 5 + 9 \times (3 + 4)}{(7 + 1 + 2) \times 8 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (5 + 93) + 4}{(7 + 1^2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{659 + 3 + 4}{(7 + 1 \times 2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{6 + 5 + 9 \times 3^4}{(7 + 1 + 2) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{(65 + 9) \times 3 \times 4}{(7 - 1) \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{(65 + 9) \times (3 + 4)}{7 \times 1^2 \times 80} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65984}{73201} & := \frac{(6 + 5 - 9) \times 8 \times 4}{73 - 2 \times 01} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (5 + 9 + 8) - 4}{7^3 - 201} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67014}{89352} & := \frac{(6 \times (7 - 0)) - (1 - 4)}{8 - ((9 - 35) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (7 - 0)) + (1 - 4)}{(8 - (9 \times (3 - 5))) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{(6^7) \times (0 - (1 - 4))}{((8 \times 9)^3) \times (5 - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(67 + (-01)) \times 4}{8 \times (((9 \times 3) - 5) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 - (7 \times (0 \times 14))}{8 - (9 \times (3 - (5 - 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{6 - (7 + (0 - (1 \times 4)))}{8 + (9 - (3 + (5 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times ((7 - (-01)) \times 4)}{8 \times (((9 - 3) \times 5) + 2)} \\
 \hline
 & := \frac{6 \times ((7 - (-01))^4)}{8^{9+3-5-2}} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times ((7 + (-01)) \times 4)}{(8 + (93 - 5)) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 \times 4)))}{(8 \times 9) + ((3 + 5) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 - (0 - (1^4)))}{8^{9+3-5 \times 2}} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 + 4)))}{8 + ((9 + 35) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 - 4)))}{8 - (9 - (35 - 2))} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 - (0 \times 14))}{8 + ((9 + (3 \times 5)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 \times 4)))}{8 - (9 - ((3 \times 5)^2))} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7^{-01+4})}{(8 + (9 - 3))^{5-2}} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 + (0 - (1^4)))}{8 - (9 + (3 - 52))} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 4)))}{(8 + ((9 \times 3) + 5)) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (70 - (1 + 4))}{(8 + (9 + (3^5))) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (70 - (1 - 4))}{8 \times (9 + ((3 + 5)^2))} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (70 \times (1^4))}{8 \times ((9 \times (3 + 5)) - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (70 + (1 \times 4))}{8 \times ((9 \times (3 + 5)) + 2)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (70 + 14)}{8 \times (9 + (3 \times (5^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{6^{7+01^4}}{8 \times ((9 - 3)^{5+2})} \\
 & := \frac{6^{7+01-4}}{8 \times ((9 - 3)^{5-2})} \\
 & := \frac{6^{7-01 \times 4}}{8 \times (9 + (3^5-2))} \\
 & := \frac{6 + ((7 + (-01)) \times 4)}{8 \times (9 + (3 - (5 + 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + ((7 + (-01))^4)}{8 + ((9 + 3)^{5-2})}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 - (0 - (1 + 4)))}{8 \times (9 - (3 + (5 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 - (0 - 14))}{8 - (9 - (35 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 + (0 - (1 \times 4)))}{8 - (9 - (3 + (5 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 + (0 - (1^4)))}{8 \times (9 + (3 - (5 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (70 - (1^4))}{((8 - (9 - 3)) \times 5)^2}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (70 + (1 + 4))}{8 + (93 + (5 + 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (70 + 14)}{8 \times (9 + (3 + (5 - 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 7014}{8 + 9352}$$

$$:= \frac{67 \times (0 - (1 - 4))}{(8 \times (9 \times 3)) + 52}$$

$$:= \frac{670 + (1 + 4)}{(8 + ((9 \times 3) - 5))^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67032}{94815} := \frac{6 + (70 + 3) \times 2}{(9 \times 4 + 8 - 1) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67032}{98154} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 03 \times 2}{9 \times (8 + 1) \times 5 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67053}{82194} := \frac{6 + 7 \times (05 + 3)}{8 - (2 - 19) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - 7 + 05^3}{(8 + 21 + 9) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (70 - 5 - 3)}{8 \times (21 + 9 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67095}{82431} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times (0 \times 9 + 5)}{(82 + 4) \times 3 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 70 \times (9 - 5)}{8 \times (2 + 4^{3+1})}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67124}{83905} := \frac{((6 \times (7 \times 1))^2) - 4}{8 \times ((3 \times 90) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times (7 \times 1)) - 2)^4}{(8 + (3 + (9 - 0)))^5}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times 71) - 2) \times 4}{8 \times ((3 \times 90) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 + 7 - 1)^2) - 4}{(8 + (3 \times (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1)^2)) - 4}{(8 - (3 - 90)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2)) + 4}{(8 - (3 \times 9)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - 1^2)) + 4}{8 + (3 \times (9 + 05))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - 1^2)) - 4}{8 + ((3 \times (9 - 0)) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times 12)) - 4}{(8 - 3)^{9-05}}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (1^2))) \times 4}{(8 - (3 - (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(67 + 1) \times 24}{8 \times (3 \times (90 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(67 - 1) \times (2 + 4)}{(8 + 3) \times (9 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (7 - ((1 + 2)^4))}{8 - (3 - (90 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (7 - (1 + (2^4)))}{8 + (3 \times (9 + (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (7 - (1 + 24))}{8 + ((3 \times (9 - 0)) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (7 \times (1 \times (2 - 4)))}{8 + (3 + (9 + 05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (7 + (1 - (2 + 4)))}{8 - (3 - (9 \times (0 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((7 + 1) \times (2 \times 4))}{8 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((7 + 12) \times 4)}{((8 \times 3) + 90) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((7 - 1) \times 24)}{8 \times (3 \times (9 \times (05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (7 - (1 - (2^4)))}{((8 \times 3) + (9 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (7 - (1 - (2 + 4)))}{8 - (3 - (90 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (7 - (1 - 24))}{(8 - 3) \times (9 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 - (2 - 4)))}{((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 + 24))}{8 \times ((3 - 9) \times (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 - (1 - (2^4)))}{8 + (3 \times (9 - (0 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 - (1 - 24))}{(8 - 3) \times (9 - (0 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 + (1 - (2 + 4)))}{(8 + (3 - (9 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (7 + (1 + (2 - 4)))}{8 + (3 + (9 + (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6712 + 4}{8390 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{6712 - 4}{8390 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67125}{84309} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + 1) + 2) \times 5}{8 + (4 + 30) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67140}{83925} := \frac{((6 \times 7) + 1) \times (4 - 0)}{(((8 - 3) \times 9) - 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times 7) - 1) \times (4 - 0)}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + 1)) - (4 - 0)}{((8 - 3) \times 9) + (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + 1)) + 40}{8 + (3 \times (9 + 25))}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(6 \times (7-1)) - (4-0)}{8 \times (3 + (9 - (2+5)))} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (7-1)) + 40}{8 - (3 - (9 \times (2 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{(6^{7-1}) \times (4-0)}{((8 \times (3 \times 9))^2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(6+7+1) \times (4-0)}{83 - ((9 \times 2) - 5)} \\
 := \frac{(6+71) \times (4-0)}{(8+3) \times ((9-2) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(67-1) \times (4-0)}{((8 \times 3) + 9) \times (2 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 - (1 + (4-0)))}{8 + (3 - (9 + (2-5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 - (1 + 40))}{8 + (39 - (2-5))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((7+1) \times (4-0))}{8 \times (3 - (9 \times (2-5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((7+1) \times 40)}{8 \times ((3+9) \times 25)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((7-1) \times (4-0))}{83 + (92+5)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((7-1)^4 + 0)}{8 \times (3 \times ((9^2) \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 - (1 - (4-0)))}{(8 \times (3 + (9-2))) - 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 - (1^4 + 0))}{8 + (3 + (9 + 25))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 \times (1 \times (4-0)))}{((8 \times 3) + (9 \times 2)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 \times (1 \times 40))}{((8^3) - 92) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 - (4-0)))}{8 + (3 + (9 + (2 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1^4 + 0))}{(8 - (3 - (9-2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 + (4-0)))}{(8 + (3 + (9-2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 + 40))}{(83 - (9+2)) \times 5}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{6 + (7 - (1 - (4-0)))}{(8 + (3 - (9-2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 - (1^4 + 0))}{8 + (39 - (2^5))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 - (1 + (4-0)))}{8 + (3 + (9 - (2 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 - (1 - 40))}{8 + (3 \times (9 + (2 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{67 + (1 - (4-0))}{(8 - (3 - (9+2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{67 + (1^4 + 0)}{(8 \times (3 + (9-2))) + 5} \\
 := \frac{67 + (1 - 40)}{((8 + (3+9)) \times 2) - 5} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67152}{83940} := \frac{((67-1) \times 5) + 2}{83 \times (9 - (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{(6 - (7 - 15))^2}{(8-3) \times (9+40)} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1-5))) + 2}{((8-3) \times 9) + 40} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (1^5))) + 2}{(8+3) \times (9 - (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1+5))) + 2}{(8 \times (3+9)) + (4-0)} \\
 := \frac{(6^{7+1}) \times (5-2)}{8 \times ((3^9) \times 40)} \\
 := \frac{(6 + (7 + 15)) \times 2}{83 - (9 + (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{(67 - (1 \times 5)) \times 2}{8 + (3 \times (9 + 40))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 - (1 + 52))}{(8-3) \times (9 + (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 - (15^2))}{8 \times (39 - (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 \times (1 - (5-2)))}{(8-3) \times (9 - (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 - (7 + (1 - (5 \times 2)))}{8 - (3 - (9 - (4-0)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{6 \times ((7+1) \times (5 \times 2))}{((8 \times 3) - 9) \times 40} \\
 := \frac{6 \times ((7+1)^{5-2})}{8 \times ((3+9) \times 40)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 - (1 - (5 \times 2)))}{8 \times (3 \times (9 - (4-0)))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 \times (1 \times (5 \times 2)))}{(8^3) + (9 + (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 \times (5+2)))}{8 + (3 + (94-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1 \times (5-2)))}{8 + ((3 \times 9) + 40)} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (1^{52}))}{8 + (3 + (9 + 40))} \\
 := \frac{6 \times (7 + (15+2))}{(8-3) \times (9 \times (4-0))} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 - (1 - 52))}{(8 + (3-9)) \times 40} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 \times (1 \times (5 \times 2)))}{((8+3) \times 9) - (4-0)} \\
 := \frac{6 + (7 + (1 - (5 \times 2)))}{((8-3) \times 9) - 40} \\
 := \frac{67 + (15^2)}{8 - (3 - (9 \times 40))} \\
 := \frac{671 - (5-2)}{839 - (4-0)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67230}{98415} := \frac{(6+7)^2 - 3 + 0}{9 \times (8+4+15)} \\
 \hline
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67284}{90153} := \frac{(6 \times 7 + 2) \times 8 + 4}{9 \times 01 \times 53} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67284}{90513} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2 \times (8-4)}{90 \times 5 - 1 + 3} \\
 := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2^{8-4}}{905 - 1^3}
 \end{array}$$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67314}{80259} &:= \frac{6-7+31-4}{8+02^5-9} \\ &:= \frac{673-1+4}{802-5+9} \end{aligned}$ <hr/>	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6+(73+(5^2))}{(8 \times (4+1))+90} \\ &:= \frac{673+(5+2)}{841+(9-0)} \end{aligned}$ <hr/>	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times (7-(5-12))}{8+(4+(3+90))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7 \times ((5+1) \times 2))}{(8-(4-3)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7 \times (5 \times 12))}{((8 \times 4)+3) \times 90} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67352}{84190} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7-(3-5)))-2}{84-(19-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (7+(3-5)))-2}{8+((4-1) \times (9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(6+(7+35))^2}{8 \times (4 \times (1 \times 90))} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(3+(5 \times 2)))}{(8 \times (4-1))-(9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(35+2))}{(8-(4-1)) \times (9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(35-2))}{8 \times (4+(1^9+0))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times ((7+(3-5)) \times 2)}{84-(1 \times (9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times ((73+5) \times 2)}{(8+(4+1)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7 \times ((3+5) \times 2))}{84 \times (1+(9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7+(3 \times (5-2)))}{(8+4) \times (1+(9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (73-(5^2))}{(8-(4 \times 1)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6^{7+3-5-2}}{(8-(4+1)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6+((7+(3-5)) \times 2)}{8+(4-(1-(9-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{6+((7+3) \times (5^2))}{8 \times (4 \times (1+(9-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{6+(7-(3 \times (5-2)))}{8-(4-(1^9+0))} \\ &:= \frac{6+(7 \times (3+(5+2)))}{8-(4-(1+90))} \\ &:= \frac{6+(7+(3+52))}{84+(1^9+0)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67405}{81923} &:= \frac{(6-7+40) \times 5}{((8+1) \times 9-2) \times 3} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67425}{98310} &:= \frac{(6+74) \times 2-5}{9 \times 8 \times 3+10} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67430}{81529} &:= \frac{6+74+30}{(8-1) \times (5 \times 2+9)} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67482}{93150} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+482)}{9 \times 3 \times 150} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67512}{84390} &:= \frac{(6-(7-51)) \times 2}{(8 \times 4)+(3+90)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (7+(5 \times 1)))^2}{(8+(4^3)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{(6^{7-5}) \times (1+2)}{(8+(4+3)) \times (9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{(6+(7-(5 \times 1)))^2}{8 \times (4-(3-(9-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6+(7+5)) \times (1+2)}{(84-3) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(5 \times (1^2)))}{8-((4 \times 3)-(9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(5+12))}{(8 \times 4)-(3+(9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{6-(7-(51+2))}{(8 \times (4+3))+ (9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times ((7+(5 \times 1))^2)}{(8-4) \times (3 \times 90)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{6 \times (7 \times (5+(1^2)))}{((8 \times 4)+3) \times (9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7+(5 \times (1^2)))}{(8-(4+3)) \times 90} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (7+(5+12))}{(8+(4 \times 3)) \times (9-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6^{7-5 \times 1^2}}{84-(39-0)} \\ &:= \frac{6+((7 \times 5)+(1+2))}{8-(43-90)} \\ &:= \frac{6+(7-(5 \times (1^2)))}{8-(4+(3-(9-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{6+(7 \times (5+(1^2)))}{8+(43+(9-0))} \\ &:= \frac{67 \times (5-(1^2))}{(8 \times 43)-(9-0)} \end{aligned}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{67854}{93102} := \frac{6+(7+8+5) \times 4}{(9+3) \times 10-2}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{67932}{84150} := \frac{6 \times (79-3-2)}{(8+4-1) \times 50}$ <hr/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{68013}{92745} := \frac{6-(8+(0-13))}{9-(2-(7-(4-5)))}$ $:= \frac{6+((8-(-01)) \times 3)}{9-(2+(7-45))}$ $:= \frac{(6 \times (8-0))-(1+3)}{9+((2 \times (7 \times 4))-5)}$ $:= \frac{68+(0-13)}{(9+(2 \times (7-4))) \times 5}$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (8 - (0 - (1 \times 3)))}{9 \times (2 + (7 - (4 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (80 + 13)}{9 + (2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (8 \times (0 - 13))}{(9^2) + (74 - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (8 \times (0 - (1 - 3)))}{9 - (2 - ((7 \times 4) - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 8013}{9 \times (27 \times 45)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (80 - (1 \times 3))}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68052}{79341} := \frac{(6 + 80) \times 5 - 2}{7 + (9 + 3) \times 41}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68103}{94752} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 1 - 03}{9 - 4 + 7 + 52}$$

$$:= \frac{68 + 1^{03}}{(9 + 4 + 7 \times 5) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(68 + 1) \times 03}{9 \times 4^{7-5} \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68125}{93740} := \frac{(6 \times 8 \times 1 + 2) \times 5}{(93 - 7) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68145}{72039} := \frac{6 + 8 + 1 + 4 \times 5}{7^2 - 03 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68145}{73920} := \frac{6 + 8 + 1 \times 45}{7 \times (3 + 9) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times 8 + 14 \times 5}{(73 - 9) \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68159}{73402} := \frac{(6 - 8) \times (1 - (5 + 9))}{(7 + (3 + (4 - 0))) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (8 \times (1^5))) - 9}{7 \times (3 \times (4 + (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (8 - ((1 + 5) \times 9))}{7 + ((3 + (4 - 0))^2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (8 + (1 - (5 - 9)))}{7 \times (3 \times (4 - (0 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (8 - 15)) \times 9}{7 \times (3 \times (4 - (-02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (((8 - 1) \times 5) - 9)}{7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (02)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (8 - 1)) \times (5 + 9)}{(7 + (3 + (4 - 0)))^2}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times ((8 \times (1 + 5)) - 9)}{7 \times (34 - (-02))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 \times (8 - (1 - (5 \times 9)))}{7 \times (3 \times (4^{02}))}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + (81 - (5 - 9))}{7 \times ((3 + (4 - 0)) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (8 - 1)) \times 59}{7 \times ((3 \times 40) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{68 + (1 + (5 - 9))}{7 \times ((3 \times (4 - 0)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{6 - (8 - (1 + (5 + 9)))}{7 + (3 + (4 - (0 \times 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68170}{94235} := \frac{6 - 8 + 1 \times 70}{9 \times (4 \times 2 + 3) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{68 \times 17 + 0}{94 \times (2 + 3 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{68 \times 1 \times 70}{94 \times 2 \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{68 + 170}{94 + 235}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68210}{73954} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2 - 1 + 0}{7 - 3 + 95 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{79350} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times (2 + 41)}{(7 + 9) \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{68 - 24 - 1}{7 + 93 - 50}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 82 + 41}{7 + 93 + 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{90735} := \frac{6 \times 824 + 1}{90 \times 73 + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{95703} := \frac{6 \times 824 + 1}{95 \times (70 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68250}{94731} := \frac{(6 \times 8 + 2) \times 5 + 0}{9 - 4 + 7^3 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68352}{79104} := \frac{6 + 8 + 3 \times 5^2}{7 \times 9 + 10 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68450}{91723} := \frac{(6 - 8 + 4) \times 50}{9 + (1 \times 7 - 2)^3}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 8 - 4) \times 5 + 0}{(9 - 17)^2 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + 84) \times 5 + 0}{9 \times ((1 + 7)^2 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68475}{92130} := \frac{68 + 47 - 5}{9 \times 2 + 130}$$

$$:= \frac{6 + 84 + 75}{9 + 213 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68571}{92340} := \frac{6 + 8 + 5^{7-1}}{9 \times 2340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68730}{91245} := \frac{68 - 7 - 3 + 0}{9 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4 + 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{68742}{91053} := \frac{6 \times (8 + 7 + 42)}{9 \times 10 \times 5 + 3} \\ & \frac{68904}{71253} := \frac{(6 - 8 + 90) \times 4}{7 \times (1 - 2 + 53)} \\ & \frac{68913}{72540} := \frac{6 - 8 \times (9 - 13)}{7 - 2 - 5 + 40} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + 89 \times 1^3}{(7 - 2) \times 5 \times 4 + 0} \\ & \quad := \frac{(6 \times 8 + 9 \times 1) \times 3}{(7 + 2) \times 5 \times 4 + 0} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 89 + 1 - 3}{(7 + 2 + 5) \times 40} \\ & \quad := \frac{(6 + 89) \times (1 + 3)}{(7 - 2 + 5) \times 40} \\ & \frac{68931}{74520} := \frac{6 + (8 + 9) \times (3 + 1)}{7 \times 4 + 52 + 0} \\ & \frac{69012}{73485} := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 01 \times 2}{7 - 3 \times (4 - 8 \times 5)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 90 \times 12}{(7^3 \times 4 + 8) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 90 \times 1 \times 2}{(7 \times 34 - 8) \times 5} \\ & \frac{69015}{78432} := \frac{6 \times 90 \times 1 - 5}{(7 + 8 + 4) \times 32} \\ & \frac{69048}{75213} := \frac{(6 + 9 \times 04) \times 8}{7 \times 52 - 1 + 3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{69054}{83271} := \frac{6 \times 9 - 05 \times 4}{8 \times 3 \times 2 - 7 \times 1} \\ & \frac{69102}{75384} := \frac{6 + (9 \times (1 - (-02)))}{7 - (5 - (38 - 4))} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + ((9 + 10) \times 2)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 + 4)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 9 - (1 + (-02))}{(7 - (5 - 3)) \times (8 + 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{691 - (-02)}{(7 + (5 - 3)) \times 84} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 - (1 \times (-02)))}{7 + (53 + (8 + 4))} \\ & \quad := \frac{69 + (10 - 2)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (8 - 4)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{((6 \times 9) - 10) \times 2}{((7 - 5)^3) \times (8 + 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 - (9 - 102)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 \times 4)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{((6 \times 9) + (1 - 0)) \times 2}{7 + ((5^3) - (8 + 4))} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + ((9 - (1 - 0)) \times 2)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 - 4)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{(6 \times 9) + (10^2)}{7 \times ((5 - 3) \times (8 + 4))} \\ & \quad := \frac{((6 \times 9) + (1 - 0))^2}{75 \times ((3 + 8) \times 4)} \\ & \frac{69125}{83740} := \frac{(69 + 1) \times 2 \times 5}{8 + 3 \times 7 \times 40} \\ & \frac{69148}{73250} := \frac{6 + (9 + 1 + 4) \times 8}{73 + 2 + 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (91 - 4 \times 8)}{(73 + 2) \times 5 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(6 \times 9 + 1 + 4) \times 8}{(7 + 3)^2 \times 5 + 0} \\ & \frac{69153}{87024} := \frac{6 + 91 - 5 - 3}{8 \times 7 \times (-02 + 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 9 - 1 + 5^3}{8 \times 7 \times (0 \times 2 + 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 1 \times 5 - 3}{8 \times 7 \times (02 + 4)} \\ & \frac{69174}{82350} := \frac{6 - (9 + ((1 - 7) \times 4))}{8 + (2 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 + (1 - (7 - 4)))}{8 - ((2^3) - 50)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 + ((1^7) + 4))}{(8 - (2 \times 3)) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + (9 \times ((1 + 7) \times 4))}{(8 + (2 - 3)) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (91 - (7 \times 4))}{(8 - (2 - 3)) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + (9 \times (1 \times 74))}{(8 + (2^3)) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))}{(8 - (2 + 3)) \times 50} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times ((9 + 1) \times (7 \times 4))}{8 \times ((2 + 3) \times 50)} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times ((91 - 7) \times 4)}{8 \times (2 \times (3 \times 50))} \\ & \frac{69175}{80243} := \frac{(6 - 9 + 1 + 7) \times 5}{8 + 024 - 3} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 - 1) \times 75}{80 + 2^{4 \times 3}} \\ & \frac{69215}{74803} := \frac{(6 \times 9 \times 2 + 1) \times 5}{74 \times 8 - 03} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{69240}{81357} := \frac{(6+9) \times 2 \times 4 + 0}{81 + 3 + 57} \\ & \frac{69258}{73041} := \frac{6 \times (9 + 2^5) - 8}{7 \times 30 + 41} \\ & \frac{69312}{75840} := \frac{(6+9+3+1)^2}{75 + 8 \times 40} \\ & \frac{69324}{81750} := \frac{6 + (9 \times 3 - 2) \times 4}{(8+17) \times 5 + 0} \\ & \frac{69325}{80417} := \frac{6 - 9 + 3 + 25}{8 + 04 + 17} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 9 \times (3+2) + 5}{80 \times 4 - 1^7} \\ & \quad := \frac{693 + 2 + 5}{804 + 1 + 7} \\ & \frac{69471}{80352} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 4 \times 7 + 1}{80 + (3+5) \times 2} \\ & \frac{69471}{82305} := \frac{6 + 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1)}{(8+2) \times 30 - 5} \\ & \frac{69483}{72105} := \frac{6 - 9 \times 4 + 83}{7 - 2 + 10 \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(6+9) \times 4 \times 8 - 3}{7^2 \times 10 + 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{694 - 8 + 3}{72 \times 10 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{69510}{73482} := \frac{6 + 9 + 510}{73 + 482} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 \times 5 - 10)}{7 \times 34 - 8 \times 2} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 5 + 10}{7 \times (34 + 8) + 2} \\ & \frac{69720}{83415} := \frac{6^{9-7} + 20}{8 \times 3 \times (4 - 1) - 5} \\ & \frac{69741}{83025} := \frac{6 + (9 - 7)^4 - 1}{(8 - 3 + 0 \times 2) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + 9 \times (7 - 4 + 1)}{(8 - 3) \times 02 \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 \times (7 - 4) + 1)}{8 \times (3 + 02) \times 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 \times (9 + 74 + 1)}{8 \times 3 \times 025} \\ & \quad := \frac{6 + 9 \times (7 + 4 \times 1)}{(8 - 3) \times 025} \\ & \frac{70146}{93528} := \frac{((7 + (-01))^4) + 6}{((9 + 3)^{5-2}) + 8} \\ & \quad := \frac{((7 + (-01))^4) - 6}{((9 + 3)^{5-2}) - 8} \\ & \quad := \frac{((70 - 1) \times 4) - 6}{(9 - 3) \times (52 + 8)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 \times 4))) \times 6}{(9 \times (3 + 5)) + (2 \times 8)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + 4))) \times 6}{((9 + 35) \times 2) + 8} \\ & \quad := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + 4)))^6}{((9 + 3)^5) \times (2 \times 8)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 - 4))) \times 6}{((9 + 3) \times 5) - 28} \\ & \quad := \frac{(7 - (-01)) \times (4 \times 6)}{(9 + (3 - (5 \times 2)))^8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(7 - (0 - 14)) \times 6}{((93 - 5) \times 2) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(7 \times (-01)) + (4 + 6)}{9 - (3 + ((5 \times 2) - 8))} \\ & := \frac{(7 \times (-01)) + 46}{9 + ((3 \times 5) + 28)} \\ & := \frac{(7^{-01+4} \times 6}{(93 + 5) \times 28} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1^4))) \times 6}{(9 \times 3) + (5 + (2 \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 - 4))) \times 6}{((9 + 35) \times 2) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (-01)) \times (4 \times 6)}{((9 \times 3) - (5 - 2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (-01)) \times 46}{(9 + (35 + 2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(70 - (1 \times 4)) \times 6}{(9 + 3) \times (52 - 8)} \\ & := \frac{(70 - (1 - 4)) \times 6}{(9 + ((3 + 5)^2)) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(70 + (1 \times 4)) \times 6}{((9 \times (3 + 5)) + 2) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{(70 + 1^4) \times 6}{(9 \times ((3 + 5)^2)) - 8} \\ & := \frac{(70 + (1 + 4)) \times 6}{(9 + 3) \times (5 \times (2 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(70 + 14) \times 6}{(9 + (3 \times (5^2))) \times 8} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - (1 + (4 + 6)))}{9 - (3 \times (5 - (2 + 8)))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - (1 + (4 - 6)))}{(9 \times (3 - (5 - 2))) + 8} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - (1 + 46))}{9 \times (3 - (5 - (2 + 8)))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - (14 + 6))}{9 \times (3 - (5 + (2 - 8)))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - (14 - 6))}{((9 - 3) \times 5) - (2 + 8)} \\ & := \frac{7 - (0 - 146)}{((93 + 5) \times 2) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((0 \times 14) + 6)}{9 - (3 - (5 \times (2 + 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 + ((1 + 4) \times 6))}{9 + ((3^5) + 28)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 + (1 - (4 - 6)))}{9 + ((3^{5-2}) - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 + (1 \times (4 \times 6)))}{9 + ((3^5) - 28)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (0 - ((1^4) - 6))}{(9 + (3 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (0 - (1 - (4 \times 6)))}{(9 + (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (0 - (1 \times (4 - 6)))}{9 - (3 \times (5 + (2 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{70 - ((1^4) - 6)}{(9 \times (3 + 5)) + 28}$$

$$:= \frac{70 - (1 + (4 \times 6))}{9 + (3 \times ((5^2) - 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{70 \times ((1^4) \times 6)}{((9 \times (3 + 5)) - 2) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (1 + (4 + 6))}{9 + (3 \times (5 + 28))}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (1 + (4 - 6))}{9 + (3 + (5 \times (2 \times 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (1 + 46)}{(9 - 35) \times (2 - 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (14 + 6)}{(9 + (3 + (5 - 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (14 - 6)}{(9 - (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + 146}{(9 + (3^{5-2})) \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{7014 + 6}{9352 + 8}$$

$$:= \frac{7014 - 6}{9352 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70195}{83426} := \frac{70 \times (1 + 9) - 5}{834 - 2 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70245}{96831} := \frac{70 \times (2^4) - 5}{(9 - 6) \times 8^3 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70254}{81963} := \frac{((7^{02}) + 5) \times 4}{(81 + (9 - 6)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (-02)) \times 54}{(8 + (1^9)) \times 63}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (0 \times 2)) + 54}{8 + (1 - (9 - 63))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times 5))) - 4}{(8 \times (1 + 9)) - (6 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^{02}) - (5 - 4)}{8 \times (1 + (9 - (6 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (-02)) \times 54}{(8 + (1 + 96)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(70 + 2) \times 54}{8 \times (1 \times (9 \times 63))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (0 - (2 + (5 + 4)))}{8 + (1 + (9 + (6 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (0 - (25 + 4))}{(8 + ((1^9) \times 6)) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 54)}{(8 - (1^9)) \times 63}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 - ((2 - 5) \times 4))}{8 + ((1 + 9) \times (6 + 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 + (2 \times 54))}{819 + 63}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (0 - (2 - (5 - 4)))}{8 - (1^{963})}$$

$$:= \frac{70 - (2 \times (5 \times 4))}{8 + (1 \times (9 \times (6 - 3)))}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (2 \times (5 - 4))}{(8 - 1) \times (9 + (6 - 3))}$$

$$:= \frac{702 \times (5 + 4)}{819 \times (6 + 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{702 - 54}{819 - 63}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70362}{91854} := \frac{7 + 036^2}{9 \times (185 + 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70425}{81693} := \frac{(7 - 04 + 2) \times 5}{8 - 1 \times 6 + 9 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 04 \times 2) \times 5}{81 - 6 + 9 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + (4 + 2) \times 5}{8 \times 16 - 9 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 04 + 2) \times 5}{8 + 169 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (0 \times 4 + 25)}{8 \times (16 + 9) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70561}{84329} := \frac{7 \times 05 + 6 \times 1}{8 \times (4 + 3 - 2) + 9}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + 5 + 6 + 1}{8 + (4 + 3 \times 2) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{85491} := \frac{(7 + 06 \times 2) \times 3}{8 \times 5 \times 4 - 91}$$

$$:= \frac{(70 + 6) \times 2^3}{8 \times (5 - 4 + 91)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{95418} := \frac{7 \times (062 - 3)}{9 \times (54 + 1 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{98154} := \frac{(7 \times (06 + 2)) + 3}{9 \times (8 + 1) + 5 - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{70 + 6 \times 2^3}{(9 - 8 \times (1 - 5)) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70649}{85312} := \frac{7 \times 06 \times 4 - 9}{8 \times (5 - 3) \times 12}$$

$$:= \frac{70 \times 6 - 49}{8 \times (53 + 1 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(70-6) \times 4 + 9}{8 \times 5 \times (3+1) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{7+1+2 \times 30}{9+8 \times (4+6) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{712-36}{890-45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70914}{83625} := \frac{70+9 \times 1 \times 4}{8 \times (3+6 \times 2) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71236}{89045} := \frac{((7+1)^2) \times (3 \times 6)}{8 \times (9 \times (0+(4 \times 5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71253}{96048} := \frac{7 \times (1+25) \times 3}{(96-04) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70914}{85632} := \frac{70+9 \times 1 \times 4}{8 \times (5+6+3+2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7-(1 \times (2+3)))^6}{8 \times (9+(0-(4-5)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71254}{96038} := \frac{7+(1-2+5) \times 4}{9+60-38}$$

$$:= \frac{7+091 \times 4}{8 \times 56 \times (3-2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times 2)) + (3 \times 6)}{8 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 4)) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7-1+2 \times 5 \times 4}{9 \times 6+0 \times 3+8}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times 2)) - (3-6)}{(8+(9+(-04))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7^{1 \times 2} + 5 \times 4}{9+60+3 \times 8}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1+2)) + (3-6)}{(89+(-04)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1+2+5 \times 4)}{9+6^{03}-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70965}{84132} := \frac{(70+96) \times 5}{8 \times (4+1)^3 - 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(7+(1 \times (2+3))) \times 6}{89+(0-(4-5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7+(1^2)) \times 36}{8 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71280}{94365} := \frac{712-8+0}{943-6-5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71085}{93426} := \frac{(7-1+08) \times 5}{(9+34) \times 2+6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7+1) \times (2+36)}{((8 \times (9-0)) + 4) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 \times 2) + (3 \times 6)}{8 \times ((9+(-04)) \times 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71309}{86254} := \frac{7^{1 \times 3} - 09}{(8 \times 6 \times 2 + 5) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times 10 \times (8-5)}{((9+3) \times 4-2) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{7-(1+((2^3)-6))}{(8 \times (9 \times (0 \times 4))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 08 \times 5}{93 \times 4 + 2 - 6}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((1-(2-3))^6)}{8 \times (90-(4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1+08) \times 5}{9 \times (34+2 \times 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1+(2+(3+6)))}{(8+(9-(-04))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71094}{82365} := \frac{7 \times 10+94}{8+2+36 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(1 \times (2-(3-6)))}{(8-(9+(-04))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(1 \times (23+6))}{(8 \times (9+(-04))) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71364}{89205} := \frac{(((7+1)^3)^6) \times 4}{((8^9)^2 + 0) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71208}{93654} := \frac{7 \times 12+08}{9 \times (3 \times 6-5) + 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(1 \times (2-(3-6)))}{(8-(9+(-04))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(1+(2+(3 \times 6)))}{(8 \times (9+(-04))) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times (1+3)) + 6) \times 4}{(8+9) \times (2 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{(71-2) \times 08}{9^3+6-5-4}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(12+(3^6))}{890+45}$$

$$:= \frac{7+(12+(3-6))}{(8-9) \times (0-(4 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7+1) \times 36) + 4}{(8-(9^2)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7-((1^3)-6))^4}{((8 \times 9)^2 + 0) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7-((1-3) \times 6)) \times 4}{(8-(9-20)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7-(1-(3+6))) \times 4}{(8+(9-(2-0))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71230}{98465} := \frac{7-1-2+30}{9 \times (8-4) + 6+5}$$

$$:= \frac{712 \times (3+6)}{890 \times (4+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{712 \times (3+6)}{890 \times (4+5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7-(1-3)) \times 64}{8 \times (9 \times (2 \times (05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 - (3 - 6))) + 4}{(8 \times 9) - (2^{05})}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + ((1^3) \times 6)) \times 4}{(8 \times 9) - (2 - (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (3^6))) \times 4}{8 \times (92 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (3 \times 6))) \times 4}{(8 + (9 \times (2 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (13 \times 6)) \times 4}{(8 + 9) \times (20 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 13)^{6-4}}{(8 + (92 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 - (3 - 6)) \times 4}{((8 \times 9) + (2 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times (36 \times 4)}{8 \times (9 \times (20 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 + (3 \times 6)) \times 4}{(8 + (9^2 + 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 + 3) \times (6 - 4)}{(8 + (9 + 20)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 \times (3 - (6 \times 4)))}{8 - (9 \times (2 + (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 - (3 - (6 + 4)))}{(8 \times 9) - (2 - (0 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times (36 + 4))}{((8 \times 9) - (2 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times (36 - 4))}{8 \times ((9 - (2 - 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((1^{36}) - 4)}{(8 - (9 - (2 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (3^{6-4}))}{8 + (9 - (2 + (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (3 + (6 - 4)))}{8 + (9 - (2 - (0 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 1^{364}}{8 + 9 - 2 - 05}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (3 \times (6 \times 4)))}{8 + (92 - (0 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (36 - 4))}{(8 - (9 \times 2)) \times (-05)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (13 + 64)}{8 + (92 - (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{7136 + 4}{8920 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7136 - 4}{8920 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71456}{89320} := \frac{((7 - (1 - 4)) \times 5) - 6}{8 + ((9 \times 3) + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - 4)) \times 56}{(8 + (9 \times 3)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) + 6}{89 + (3 \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) - 6}{8 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + ((1^4) \times 5)) \times 6}{89 + (3 - (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (4 + 5))) \times 6}{8 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 - 4)) \times (5 \times 6)}{((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 - 4)) \times 56}{(8 + (9 - 3)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (((1 - 4) \times 5) + 6)}{8 + ((9 - 3) \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (4 + (5 \times 6)))}{(8 \times (9 - 3)) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 \times (4 + (5 - 6)))}{8 - (9 - (3 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 + (4 - (5 \times 6)))}{8 + (9 + (3 + 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 - (4 - (5 + 6)))}{(8 + (9 \times 3)) \times (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (4 - (5 - 6)))}{8 + ((9 \times 3) - 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (4 + 56))}{(8 + 9) \times (3 + (2 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71460}{89325} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times 4)^6 + 0}{(8^9) \times (3 + (2 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1^4)) \times (6 - 0)}{8 + (9 + (3 + 25))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1^4)) \times 60}{(89 + (3 - 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1^4))^6 + 0}{8 \times ((9^3) \times (2 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - 4)) \times (6 - 0)}{(8 \times (9 + (3 - 2))) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - 4)) \times 60}{((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 1 \times 4) + 60}{(8 + (9 + 3 + 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 14) - (6 - 0)}{(8 + (9 + (3 \times 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 14) + (6 - 0)}{(8 + (9 + (3^2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1^4) \times (6 - 0)}{(8 + (9 - (3 + 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1^4) \times 60}{8 \times ((9 + (3 \times 2)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 + 4)) \times 60}{893 + (2 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 + 4))^6 + 0}{((8 \times 9)^3) \times (2 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 - 4)) \times (6 - 0)}{8 + (9 + (3 + (2 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (4 \times (6 - 0))}{8 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (4 \times 60)}{8 \times ((9 + 3) \times 25)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (4 + (6 - 0))}{(8 + ((9 - 3) \times 2)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (4 + 60)}{(8 + (9 + 3)) \times (2^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times (4 \times 60)}{8 \times (9 \times ((3 + 2) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times (4 + 60)}{8 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - ((1^4) - (6 - 0))}{8 + (((9 - 3) \times 2) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (4 - (6 - 0)))}{8 - (9 - (3 - (2 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (4 + (6 - 0)))}{8 - (9 - (3 \times (2 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (46 - 0))}{((8 + (9 \times 3)) \times 2) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 + (4 - (6 - 0)))}{8 + (9 + (3 - (2 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((1^4) \times 60)}{((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times (4 + 60))}{8 \times ((9 + 3 + 2) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1^4 + 60)}{(8 + (9 \times (3 - 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 - (4 - 60))}{8 \times (9 + ((3 - 2)^5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{8 \times (9 + (3 - (2 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (4 \times 60))}{(8 + (9 \times (3 \times 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (4 + 60))}{(8 + (9 + (3 - 2))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71495}{83260} := \frac{71 + 49 \times 5}{8 + 3 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + 4)^{9-5}}{8 \times (32 + 60)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71536}{89420} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times 5) + 36}{89 + (4 + (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 + (5 - 3))) \times 6}{(8 \times 9) - (42 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (5 - (3 - 6))}{8 + (9 \times (4 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 \times (5 - 3)) - 6}{(89 - 4) \times (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (5 \times (3 \times 6)))}{8 \times (9 + (4 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (5 + (3 + 6)))}{8 + (9 + (4 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 + (5 + (3 - 6)))}{8 - (9 - (4 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6))}{89 - (4 - 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 6)))}{((8 + 9) \times 4) + (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 + (53 - 6))}{(8 + (9 + 4)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 - (5 - (3 + 6)))}{8 - (9 + (4 - 20))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (5 \times (3 + 6)))}{89 - (4 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (5 + 36))}{(8 - (9 - 4)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (5 - (3 - 6)))}{(8 \times (9 - 4)) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{71 + ((5 \times 3) - 6)}{8 + (94 - (2 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71540}{98623} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{(9 + 86) \times 2 + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 + 5) \times 40}{(9 \times 86 - 2) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times 15 \times 4 + 0}{9 \times 8 \times (6 + 2) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71568}{90432} := \frac{7 \times (1 + 5 \times (6 + 8))}{90 \times (4 + 3) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71604}{85293} := \frac{7 + 1 + 604}{(8 - 5 - 2) \times 9^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71624}{89530} := \frac{((7 \times (1 + 6)) + 2) \times 4}{(8 + 9) \times (5 \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 1) \times (6 \times 2)) - 4}{(8 \times (9 + 5)) + (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - 6)) \times 24}{(8 + (9 - 5)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 16) - (2^4)}{(8 - (9 - 5)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times 6)) \times 24}{(8 \times (9 \times 5)) + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (6 \times 2))) \times 4}{8 + (95 - (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (16 + 2)) \times 4}{(8 \times 9) + (53 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (6 \times (2^4))}{8 \times ((9 - 5) \times 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (62 + 4)}{(8 + (9 + 5)) \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times (6 \times 24)}{8 \times (9 \times (5 \times (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 + (6 \times 2)) \times 4}{(89 \times 5) - 30}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 + 6) \times 24}{(8 \times 9) + 5 \times 30}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (6 + (2^4)))}{(8 \times (9 - 5)) + (3 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (62 - 4))}{8 + (9 \times (5 + (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 + (6 - (2^4)))}{8 + ((9 - 5) \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 \times (6 - (2 - 4)))}{8 + (9 + (53 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (16 \times 24)}{8 \times ((9 + 5) \times 30)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 - (6 \times (2 - 4)))}{8 + (9 + (5 + (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + ((6^2) - 4))}{8 + ((9 + 5) \times (3 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + ((6 - 2)^4))}{(8 \times (9 \times 5)) - 30}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (6 \times (2 + 4)))}{((8 + 9) \times 5) - 30}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + (6 + (2 - 4)))}{8 + (9 - (5 - (3 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + 624)}{(8 \times 95) + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{716 + 24}{895 + 30}$$

$$:= \frac{716 - 24}{895 - 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71632}{89540} := \frac{((7 - (1^6)) \times 3)^2}{(89 \times 5) - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (1^6))^3) \times 2}{8 \times ((9 - 5) \times 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - (6 \times 3)))^2}{(8 \times 95) - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (1 - 6)) \times 32}{(8 + (9 - 5)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (6 \times 3))) + 2}{(8 - (9 - 5)) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (6 + 3)))^2}{(8 \times (9 \times 5)) - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (6 - 3)))^2}{((8 + 9) \times 5) + 40}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (1^{63}))^2}{8 \times (9 + (5 - (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times ((6^3) \times 2)}{8 \times (9 \times (5 + 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times (6 \times 32)}{8 \times (9 \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(71 + 6) \times 32}{((8 \times 9) + 5) \times 40}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 - (6 \times (3 + 2)))}{((8 + 9) \times 5) - 40}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (1 + (6 - 32))}{8 \times ((9 \times 5) - 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (1 - (6 - (3^2)))}{89 - (54 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (16 \times 32)}{8 \times ((9 + 5) \times 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (((1 + 6)^3) + 2)}{8 \times (95 - 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 \times (63 + 2))}{89 + (5 - (4 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (1 + 632)}{(8 \times 95) + 40}$$

$$:= \frac{716 + 32}{895 + 40}$$

$$:= \frac{716 - 32}{895 - 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71685}{92340} := \frac{7 - 1 + 6 \times 8 + 5}{9 \times 2^3 + 4 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71804}{95326} := \frac{(7 + 1 \times 80) \times 4}{(9 \times 5 + 32) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71820}{94563} := \frac{(7 - 1) \times (8 + 2) + 0}{94 - 5 \times (6 - 3)}$$

$$:= \frac{718 + 2 + 0}{945 + 6 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{71950}{83462} := \frac{(7 - 1 + 9) \times 5 + 0}{83 - 4 + 6 + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 9 \times 50}{(83 + 4) \times 6^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1 + 9) \times 50}{834 + 6^2}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 1^9) \times 50}{(83 + 4) \times (6 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 1^9) \times 50}{8^3 - 4 \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{72063}{81954} := \frac{(7 + 2) \times 06 - 3}{8 + 1 + 9 \times 5 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{72063}{91845} := \frac{(7 + 2) \times 06 - 3}{(9 + 1 \times 8 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{72135}{90684} := \frac{7 \times (2 + (1 - (3 - 5)))}{(9 + (0 - (6 - 8))) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (2 + (1 \times (3 + 5)))}{90 - (6 - (8 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^2 \times 1^3) \times 5}{(9 - (0 - 68)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (2 \times ((1 + 3) \times 5))}{(90 + (6 - 8)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (2 \times 1)) \times 35}{9 \times (((06 \times 8) - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 21) \times (3 \times 5)}{(90 \times 6) - (8 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 2) - 1) \times 35}{(90 \times 6) + (8 \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (2 \times (1 \times 35))}{(9 \times (068)) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{72135}{94806} := \frac{7 \times (2 + 1 - 3 + 5)}{94 - 8 \times 06}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (2 + 1 \times 3 + 5)}{94 - 8 + 06}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (2 + 1^3) \times 5}{(-9 + 4 \times 8) \times 06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{72150}{83694} := \frac{(7 - 2 \times 1) \times 5 + 0}{8 - 3 \times (6 - 9 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{7^2 + 1 + 50}{8 + (36 - 9) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 2 \times 1) \times 50}{8 - (3 - 6) \times 94}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 21) \times 50}{8 \times (3 \times 69 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 2 + 1) \times 50}{8 \times (3 + 69) + 4}$$

<hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72354}{81690} := \frac{7^2 \times 3 - 54}{8 + 1 + 6 + 90}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72369}{84150} := \frac{72 + 3 + 6 \times 9}{(8 - 4 - 1) \times 50}$ $:= \frac{7 \times 23 + 6 \times 9}{(8 - 4 + 1) \times 50}$ $:= \frac{7 + 2^3 \times 69}{(8 + 4 + 1) \times 50}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{72369}{85140} := \frac{7 + 2 \times (3 + 6) + 9}{8 \times 5 \times 1^{40}}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 + 3 + 6) - 9}{8 \times (5 + 1 + 4) + 0}$ $:= \frac{7 + 23 \times 6 - 9}{8 \times 5 \times 1 \times 4 + 0}$ $:= \frac{72 + (3 + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 5 + 140}$ $:= \frac{7 - 2 + 369}{8 \times (51 + 4) + 0}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 - 3 + 69)}{8 \times 5 \times 14 + 0}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72450}{93618} := \frac{(7 - 2)^4 - 50}{9^3 + 6 + 1 \times 8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{72450}{96831} := \frac{(7 + 2^4) \times 50}{(9 - 6) \times 8^3 + 1}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72459}{80316} := \frac{72 + 4 \times 5 - 9}{80 + (3 - 1) \times 6}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72645}{98310} := \frac{7 + (2 + 6) \times 4 \times 5}{9 \times 8 \times 3 + 10}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{72693}{85104} := \frac{72 + 6 \times 9 - 3}{8 \times 5 + 104}$ $:= \frac{7 + 2 \times (6 + 93)}{8 \times 5 \times (10 - 4)}$ $:= \frac{7 - 2 + 6 \times (9 - 3)}{8 \times (5 + 1^{04})}$ $:= \frac{7 + 2^6 + 93}{8 \times (5 + 1) \times 04}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72810}{94653} := \frac{(7 + (2 - 8)) \times 10}{9 - (4 - (6 + (5 - 3)))}$ $:= \frac{((7 - 2) \times 8) - 10}{(9 + (4 \times (6 - 5))) \times 3}$ $:= \frac{(7^2) - (8 + (1 - 0))}{9 - (4 + (6 - 53))}$ $:= \frac{((7 - 2) \times 8) + 10}{9 + (4 \times (6 + (5 + 3)))}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 + (8 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9 \times (4 \times 6)) - (5^3)}$ $:= \frac{(7 \times (2 + 8)) + 10}{(9 + 4) \times (6 + (5 - 3))}$ $:= \frac{7 + (2 + (81 - 0))}{9 \times (4 - (6 - (5 \times 3)))}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 + (8 + 10))}{(9 + 4) \times (6 + (5 + 3))}$ $:= \frac{((7^2) - 8) \times 10}{9 + (4 \times (6 + (5^3)))}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{72836}{91045} := \frac{((7 \times 2 + 8) \times 3) + 6}{9 \times (1 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}$ $:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) - 8) \times 3) - 6}{9 + ((1^{04}) + 5)}$ $:= \frac{((7^2) + (8 - 3)) \times 6}{9 \times (1 \times (0 + 45))}$ $:= \frac{((7 + 2) \times 8) + 36}{(9 \times 10) + 45}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (2 - (8 - 3))) \times 6}{(9 + (10 - 4)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times ((2 + 8) \times 3)) + 6}{9 \times (10 + (4 \times 5))}$ $:= \frac{(7 \times (2 \times (8 + 3))) + 6}{(9 + (1 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5)}$ $:= \frac{(7 \times (2 + 8)) - (3 \times 6)}{(9 - (1 \times (-04))) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{(7 \times (2 + 8)) + (3 \times 6)}{(9 \times 10) + (4 \times 5)}$ $:= \frac{7 \times 2 + ((8 + 3) \times 6)}{91 - (0 - (4 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{7 \times 2 + (8 + (3 \times 6))}{(9 \times (1 - (-04))) + 5}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (2 - (8 - 3))) \times 6}{9 + (1 - (0 - (4 \times 5)))}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (2 - 8)) \times 36}{9 \times ((1^{04}) \times 5)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 2) \times (8 \times (3 + 6))}{9 \times (10 \times (4 + 5))}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 2) \times (8 + 36)}{9 \times (10 + 45)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 2) \times 836}{9 \times 1045}$ $:= \frac{(72 - (8 \times 3)) \times 6}{(9 - (1 - 0)) \times 45}$ $:= \frac{(72 + 8) \times (3 \times 6)}{9 \times (10 \times (4 \times 5))}$ $:= \frac{7 - (2 - (8 - (3 - 6)))}{(9 - (1 - (-04))) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{7 \times ((2 \times (8 - 3)) - 6)}{((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 4) - 5}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 \times ((8 \times 3) - 6))}{9 \times ((10 \times 4) - 5)}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 \times (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{91 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5)}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (2 + (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{(9 + (10 \times 4)) \times 5}$ $:= \frac{7 + (2 - (8 + (3 - 6)))}{9 + ((1^{04}) - 5)}$ $:= \frac{7 + (2 + (8 - (3 + 6)))}{9 + (1 - (0 \times 45))}$
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$:= \frac{7 + (2 + (8 - (3 - 6)))}{(9 + (1 \times (-04))) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{72963}{81405} := \frac{7 - 2 + 963}{8 \times (140 - 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73248}{91560} := \frac{((7 + (3^2)) \times 4) + 8}{(9 + (1 + 5)) \times (6 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{7 + (28 + (3^6))}{910 + 45}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 + 4))) \times 8}{((9 - 1) \times 5) + 60}$
$:= \frac{7 + (28 + (3 + 6))}{9 + (1 - (0 - 45))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73062}{98154} := \frac{7 + 30 + 62}{9 + 8 \times 15 + 4}$	$:= \frac{(7 - (3 + (2 - 4))) \times 8}{(9 + (1^5)) \times (6 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{7 + (28 + (3 - 6))}{(9 \times (1 - (-04))) - 5}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 \times 32) - (4 \times 8)}{(9 - (1 \times 5)) \times 60}$
$:= \frac{7 + (283 - 6)}{(9 \times (10 \times 4)) - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73125}{80496} := \frac{(7 - 3 + 1^2)^5}{80 \times (49 - 6)}$	$:= \frac{(7 + ((3 + 2) \times 4)) \times 8}{9 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{72 + (8 \times (3 + 6))}{9 \times (1 \times (0 + (4 \times 5)))}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 + ((3 - 2) \times 4)) \times 8}{(9 + 1) \times (5 + (6 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{72 + (8 \times (3 - 6))}{(9 - (1 + (-04))) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73146}{80592} := \frac{7 \times 3 + 146}{8 \times (05 + 9 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 + 4))) \times 8}{9 + (1 + (5 \times (6 - 0)))}$
$:= \frac{72 + (8 \times 36)}{(9 + (1 - 0)) \times 45}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times (2 \times 4))) \times 8}{9 + (1 + (5 \times 60))}$
$:= \frac{728 \times (3 + 6)}{910 \times (4 + 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73152}{96480} := \frac{7 \times (31 + 5) + 2}{9 + 6 + 4 \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times 2)) \times (4 \times 8)}{(9 - 1) \times (5 + 60)}$
$:= \frac{728 - 36}{910 - 45}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times 2)) \times (4 + 8)}{(9 \times 15) + 60}$
<hr/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73158}{92064} := \frac{7^3 \times 1 + 5 + 8}{(9 - 2) \times 064}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 \times 4))) \times 8}{(9 - (1 + 5)) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{72840}{96513} := \frac{(7 - 2) \times 8 + 40}{96 - 5 \times (1 - 3)}$	$:= \frac{7^3 - 1 + 5 \times 8}{9 \times 2 \times 06 + 4}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 - 4))) \times 8}{91 - (5 + (6 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(7 - 2) \times (8 + 40)}{9 + 6 \times 51 + 3}$	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(7 + (3 - 2)) \times 48}{(9 - (1^5)) \times 60}$
$:= \frac{(7 + 2 - 8) \times 40}{9 + (6 + 5) \times (1 + 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73194}{86502} := \frac{7 + 3 \times 1 \times (9 - 4)}{8 + 6 \times (5 - 02)}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times ((2 + 4) \times 8)}{(9 + (1^5)) \times 60}$
<hr/>	$:= \frac{7 + 3 + 19 + 4}{8 + 6 + 5^{02}}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times (2 \times (4 + 8))}{(9 + (1 - 5)) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{72864}{93150} := \frac{72 \times (8 \times 6 - 4)}{9 \times 3 \times 150}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 3 - 1) \times 9 - 4}{86 + 5 + 0 \times 2}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times (24 \times 8)}{(9 - 1) \times (5 \times 60)}$
$:= \frac{728 - 6 \times 4}{9 \times (3 - 1) \times 50}$	$:= \frac{7 + 3^{1^9 \times 4}}{8 \times (6 + 5 + 02)}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 32) \times (4 + 8)}{9 \times (1 \times (5 + 60))}$
$:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8 + 6^4}{9 \times (3 + 1) \times 50}$	$:= \frac{7 \times ((3 - 1) \times 9 + 4)}{(86 + 5) \times 02}$	$:= \frac{(73 - (2 \times 4)) \times 8}{(9 + 1) \times (5 + 60)}$
$:= \frac{(7 \times 2 + 8) \times 6^4}{9^{3 \times 1} \times 50}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (3 + 19) \times 4}{(8 + 6) \times (50 + 2)}$	$:= \frac{(73 - (2^4)) \times 8}{9 + (1 + 560)}$
<hr/>	<hr/>	$:= \frac{(73 + (2 \times 4)) \times 8}{9 \times (15 \times (6 - 0))}$

$:= \frac{(73+2) \times (4 \times 8)}{(9+1) \times (5 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73264}{91580} := \frac{((7-(3+2))^6)+4}{9+(1-(5-80))}$	$:= \frac{7+(3-(2-64))}{9+((1^5)+80)}$
$:= \frac{7-(3-((2^4) \times 8))}{9+(156-0)}$	$:= \frac{((7^3) \times 2)-(6-4)}{9 \times (15+80)}$	$:= \frac{7+(3+(2+64))}{9+(1+(5+80))}$
$:= \frac{7-(3-((2+4) \times 8))}{9+(1-(5-60))}$	$:= \frac{((7+(3^2)) \times 6)+4}{(9 \times (1 \times 5))+80}$	$:= \frac{7+(3+(26+4))}{9+(1+(5 \times (8-0)))}$
$:= \frac{7-(3-(2 \times (4+8)))}{91-(56-0)}$	$:= \frac{((7+(3-2)) \times 6)-4}{(9 \times 15)-80}$	$:= \frac{732-64}{915-80}$
$:= \frac{7-(3-(24+8))}{9+((1+5) \times (6-0))}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 6)))+4}{(9-(1 \times 5)) \times 80}$	
$:= \frac{7 \times ((3 \times 24)-8)}{(9+1) \times (56-0)}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (2+6)))+4}{(9 \times 15)+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73284}{91605} := \frac{((7+3)^2)-(8+4)}{(9+1) \times (6-(-05))}$
$:= \frac{7 \times ((3-2) \times (4+8))}{(9 \times (1 \times 5))+60}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times 32)+64}{9 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8-0)))}$	$:= \frac{((73+2) \times 8)+4}{(91+60) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (3 \times (24 \times 8))}{9 \times (1 \times 560)}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3 \times (2^6))) \times 4}{915+80}$	$:= \frac{(7-(3-(2+8))) \times 4}{(9-(1-(6-0))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (3 \times (24+8))}{(9+(1 \times 5)) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3 \times 2)) \times 64}{(9-(1-5)) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(7-(3 \times (2-8))) \times 4}{(9+(16-0)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7+(((3+2)^4)-8)}{(9-(1-5)) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3-2)) \times (6 \times 4)}{(9-(1+5)) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(7-(3-2)) \times (8+4)}{91-(6+(-05))}$
$:= \frac{7+(3-(2+(4-8)))}{9+((1^5) \times (6-0))}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3-2)) \times 64}{(9-(1^5)) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(7-(3-28))^4}{((9-1)^6+0) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7+(3-(2-48))}{9+((1^5)+60)}$	$:= \frac{(7+3) \times ((2^6) \times 4)}{(9-1) \times (5 \times 80)}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times ((3-2) \times 8))-4}{9+(1+(60-5))}$
$:= \frac{7+(3+(2-(4-8)))}{9+(1 \times (5+(6-0)))}$	$:= \frac{(7+3) \times ((2^6)+4)}{(9+1) \times (5+80)}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8)))+4}{(91-(6-0)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7+(3+(2+(4+8)))}{9+(15+(6-0))}$	$:= \frac{(7+3) \times ((2+6) \times 4)}{(9+(1-5)) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times (32+8))-4}{(9+(1 \times 60)) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{7+(3+(2+(4-8)))}{9-(1 \times (5-(6-0)))}$	$:= \frac{(7+3) \times (26+4)}{(91 \times 5)-80}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times 32)-(8 \times 4)}{(9-1) \times (6 \times (05))}$
$:= \frac{7+(3+(2+48))}{9+(1+(5+60))}$	$:= \frac{(7-3) \times (2+(6 \times 4))}{(9+1) \times (5+(8-0))}$	$:= \frac{(7+((3^2)-8)) \times 4}{9+(1-(6 \times (-05)))}$
$:= \frac{732-(4+8)}{(9+(1+5)) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{7-(3-((2^6)-4))}{(9+(1^5)) \times (8-0)}$	$:= \frac{(7+((3-2) \times 8)) \times 4}{9+(1+(60+5))}$
$:= \frac{732+48}{915+60}$	$:= \frac{7-(3-(2-(6-4)))}{9-(1-(5-(8-0)))}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3-(2-8))) \times 4}{(9+(1+(6-0))) \times 5}$
$:= \frac{732-48}{915-60}$	$:= \frac{7-(3-(2^{6-4}))}{9+((1^5)^8+0)}$	$:= \frac{(7+(3 \times 2)) \times (8 \times 4)}{(9-1) \times (60+5)}$
	$:= \frac{7+(3-(2-(6 \times 4)))}{(9+(1-5)) \times (8-0)}$	$:= \frac{(7+(32-8)) \times 4}{(91-60) \times 5}$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{(7+3) \times (2 \times (8+4))}{(9+1) \times (6 \times (05))} \\
 := \frac{(7+32) \times (8+4)}{9 \times (1 \times (60+5))} \\
 := \frac{(73+2) \times (8 \times 4)}{(9+1) \times (60 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(73-28) \times 4}{9 \times ((1-6) \times (-05))} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(2 \times (8 \times 4)))}{91-(6-(0 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(2 \times (8+4)))}{(9-16) \times (-05)} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(2^{8-4}))}{9+(16-(0 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(28+4))}{9 \times ((1^6+0) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{7 \times (((3^2)+8) \times 4)}{((9+1) \times 60)-5} \\
 := \frac{7 \times ((3-(2-8)) \times 4)}{9 \times ((1+(6-0)) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{7+((3^2)+(8 \times 4))}{(9+1) \times (6-(0 \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{7+(3-(2-(8 \times 4)))}{(9+(1^6+0)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{7+(3-(2-(8-4)))}{9+(1 \times (6-(0 \times 5)))} \\
 := \frac{7+(3-(2+(8-4)))}{9+((1^6+0)-5)} \\
 := \frac{7+(3+(2-(8-4)))}{9+(1^{605})} \\
 := \frac{7+(3+(2+(8 \times 4)))}{((9+1) \times (6-0))-5} \\
 := \frac{7+(3+(2+(8+4)))}{9+(16-(-05))} \\
 := \frac{7+(3+(2+(8-4)))}{9+(1 \times (6-(-05)))} \\
 := \frac{7328+4}{9160+5} \\
 := \frac{7328-4}{9160-5}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 \xrightarrow{\text{73456}} \frac{73456}{91820} := \frac{(7-((3-4) \times 5)) \times 6}{9 \times (1 \times (8+(2-0)))} \\
 := \frac{(7-(3-(4 \times 5))) \times 6}{9 \times (18+(2-0))} \\
 := \frac{(7-(3 \times (4-5))) \times 6}{91-(8 \times (2-0))} \\
 := \frac{(7 \times (3+(4-5)))+6}{9+(1 \times (8 \times (2-0)))} \\
 := \frac{(7+((3-4) \times 5)) \times 6}{9+(1 \times (8-(2-0)))} \\
 := \frac{(7+(3 \times (4-5))) \times 6}{9+((1^8)+20)} \\
 := \frac{(7-3)^{4-5+6}}{(9-1) \times (8 \times 20)} \\
 := \frac{(73+(4-5)) \times 6}{(9+18) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(4 \times (5 \times 6)))}{91+(8^2+0)} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(4 \times (5+6)))}{(9+1) \times (8-(2-0))} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(4+56))}{(9-1) \times (8+(2-0))} \\
 := \frac{7-(3+(4 \times (5-6)))}{9+(1^{820})} \\
 := \frac{7-(3+(4-56))}{(9 \times (1 \times 8))-(2-0)} \\
 := \frac{7+((3 \times 45)-6)}{9+(1+(8 \times 20))} \\
 := \frac{7+((3^4)-56)}{(9+(1-8)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{7+(3-(4-(5 \times 6)))}{9+(18 \times (2-0))} \\
 := \frac{7+(3 \times (4+(5-6)))}{9-(1+(8-20))} \\
 := \frac{7+(3 \times (45+6))}{(9+(1^8)) \times 20} \\
 := \frac{73-(4-(5+6))}{(9+(1^8))^2+0}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{l}
 := \frac{73-4+5-6}{91-8+2+0} \\
 \xrightarrow{\text{73460}} \frac{73460}{91825} := \frac{((7-3) \times 4)^6+0}{(9+1) \times (8^{2+5})} \\
 := \frac{((7-3) \times 4)+60}{9-(1-(82+5))} \\
 := \frac{((7-3)^4)+60}{((9 \times (1+8))-2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7-(3-4)) \times (6-0)}{9+(1+((8+2) \times 5))} \\
 := \frac{(7 \times (3 \times 4))+60}{(9+(1+8)) \times (2 \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(7 \times (3 \times 4))-60}{9+(1 \times ((8 \times 2)+5))} \\
 := \frac{(7+(3^4)) \times 60}{(9-1) \times 825} \\
 := \frac{(7+(3+4)) \times (6-0)}{((9+(1^8))^2)+5} \\
 := \frac{(7+(3-4)) \times (6-0)}{9 \times (1 \times (8+(2-5)))} \\
 := \frac{(7+(3-4)) \times 60}{(9-(1-82)) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7+3) \times (4 \times (6-0))}{(9+1) \times ((8-2) \times 5)} \\
 := \frac{(7+3) \times (4+(6-0))}{(9+(1 \times (8 \times 2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7+3) \times (4+60)}{((9 \times 18)-2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7-3) \times (4 \times (6-0))}{(9-(1-(8 \times 2))) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7-3) \times (4^6+0)}{(((9-1) \times 8)^2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{(7-3) \times (4+(6-0))}{9+(1+(8+(2^5)))} \\
 := \frac{(7-3) \times (4+60)}{((9-(1^8))^2) \times 5} \\
 := \frac{7-(3-(4 \times (6-0)))}{9+((1^8)+25)}
 \end{array}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - (4 + 60))}{9 - (1 - (82 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 + (4 - 60))}{(9 + (1 \times (8 - 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - 460)}{(9 \times (1 + (8^2))) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{9 \times (1 + ((8^2) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (34 + (6 - 0))}{((9 \times (1 \times 8)) - 2) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((3^4) + 60)}{(9 \times (18 + 2)) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 - (4 - (6 - 0)))}{9 + (1 + (8 + (2 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (4 - (6 - 0)))}{9 + (1^{825})}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (4 + (6 - 0)))}{9 - (1 + (8 - 25))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (46 - 0))}{(9 - (1 - (8 - 2))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{734 + (6 - 0)}{918 + (2 + 5)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73485}{92016} := \frac{(7 \times 3 \times 4 + 8) \times 5}{9 \times 2^{01 \times 6}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73512}{94680} := \frac{7 \times 3^{5+1} + 2}{9^4 + 6 + 8 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73548}{96021} := \frac{7 + 3 + 54 + 8}{96 - 02 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times 35 \times 4 - 8}{9 + 60 \times 21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73682}{91504} := \frac{7^3 - 68 + 2}{(91 - 5) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73684}{92105} := \frac{(((7 \times 3) - 6) \times 8) - 4}{(9 + (2 \times 10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8) + 4}{(9 + (2 + 10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + 6) \times (8 + 4)}{(9^{2 \times 1 + 0}) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (3 + 6)) \times 8) + 4}{(9 + 2) \times (10 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times 6) + (8 \times 4)}{((9 + 2) \times 10) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - 3) \times 6) + 84}{9 \times ((2 \times 10) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (6 + 8))) \times 4}{9 \times (2 \times (1 \times (05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 \times (6 - 8))) \times 4}{((9 - 2) \times 10) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 + (6 - 8))) \times 4}{(9 - (2 + (1 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 \times 4)}{((9^2) - (1 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 + (21 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 - 4)}{(9 + (2 - (1 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 36) + (8 \times 4)}{((9^2) - 10) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (6 - 8))) \times 4}{(9 - (2 - (1 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (3 + 6)) \times (8 - 4)}{(9^2) - (1^{05})}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 4)}{(9 + 2) \times (10 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times (6 \times (8 + 4))}{9 \times (2 \times (10 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times (6 + (8 + 4))}{9 \times ((2 \times 10) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - ((6 + 8) \times 4))}{(9^2) - (1 - (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - (6 \times (8 + 4)))}{(9 \times 2 + (1 - 0)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - (6 \times (8 - 4)))}{(9 - (2 \times (1 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (3 - (68 - 4))}{(9 - (2 - 10)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((3 - (6 - 8)) \times 4)}{(9 \times (2 \times 10)) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((3 + 6) \times (8 + 4))}{9 \times (21 \times (05))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (3 \times ((6 \times 8) - 4))}{(9 + 2) \times 105}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (3 \times (6 \times (8 + 4)))}{9 \times (2 \times 105)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (36 + (8 - 4))}{(9 - 2) \times (10 \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((3^6) - (8 - 4))}{(92 \times 10) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((3^6) + (8 - 4))}{(92 \times 10) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((3^6) - 84)}{((9^2) \times 10) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 - (6 - (8 \times 4)))}{9 \times ((2 - (1 - 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 - (6 - (8 - 4)))}{9 + (2 - (1^{05}))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (6 - (8 + 4)))}{9 + (2 - (1 - (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (6 - (8 - 4)))}{9 + (2 - (1 + (-05)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (6 + (8 \times 4)))}{(9 + (2 + (1 - 0))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (3 + (6 + (8 - 4)))}{9 + (21 + (-05))}$$

$$:= \frac{7368 + 4}{9210 + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7368 - 4}{9210 - 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{73692}{84105} &:= \frac{7^3 - 69 + 2}{8 \times 4 \times 10 - 5} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 3 - 6) \times 92}{84 \times 1 \times 05} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - 3)^6 \times 92}{8^4 \times 105} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{738 + 4 + 2}{905 + 1 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{96831} := \frac{(7 + 40) \times 25}{(9 - 6) \times 8^3 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{98136} := \frac{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)}{9 \times (81 - 3) - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{73905}{86412} := \frac{(7 - 3 + 9) \times 05}{(8 + 6 \times (4 + 1)) \times 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{73842}{90516} &:= \frac{7 - 3 \times (8 - 4^2)}{9 \times 05 - 1 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (3 + 8) + 4^2}{90 + (5 - 1) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{91368} &:= \frac{7 \times (40 + 2 \times 5)}{9 \times 1^3 \times 6 \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)}{9 \times (1 + 3 + 68)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74032}{86591} := \frac{7 \times 4^{0 \times 3 + 2}}{86 + 5 \times 9 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^4) - (1 + (-08))}{(92 - 6) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (1 \times (08)))}{(9 + 26) \times (3 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (1 - 0))) \times 8}{(9 + (2 + (6 + 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (10 + 8))}{9 \times (2 + (63 + 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74108}{92635} := \frac{((7 \times 4) - (1 - 0)) \times 8}{9 \times (2 \times ((6 - 3) \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 \times (1 - 0))) \times 8}{((9 + 26) \times 3) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (10 - 8))}{(9 + (2 + (6 - 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 4) + 10) \times 8}{(9 + ((2^6) + 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (1 - 0))) \times 8}{((9 + (2 - 6))^3) - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times 108)}{9 \times (2 \times (6 \times 35))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 4) - 10) \times 8}{9 \times ((2 \times 6) + (3 + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - 10)) \times 8}{9 + ((2 \times (6 - 3)) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (1^{08}))}{9 + (2 \times ((6 \times 3) - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (1 - 0))) \times 8}{9 + (2 - (6 - 35))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 4) \times 108}{((9^2) + (6^3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (10 - 8))}{9 + ((2 \times 63) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 \times (1 - 0))) \times 8}{9 - (2 - ((6 \times 3) + 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times 108}{9 \times (((2 \times 6) - 3) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 + (10 \times 8))}{(9 + (2 \times 6)) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 + (1 - 0))) \times 8}{9 + (2 - (6 - (3 \times 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 + 10) \times 8}{(9 \times 2 + 6) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (1 - (-08)))}{9 + (2 \times (6 - (3 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - 10)) \times 8}{9 + ((2 \times 63) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (1 - (-08)))}{9 - (2 - (6 - (3 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (1 + (-08)))}{9 - (2 - (6 - (3 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times 10)) + 8}{9 \times ((2^{6-3}) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((4 \times 10) + 8)}{((9^2) + (6 - 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (41 - (0 \times 8))}{(9^2) - (6 + (3 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (1 - 0))) + 8}{((9 \times 2) - (6 + 3)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((4 + (1 - 0)) \times 8)}{(9 - (2 - 63)) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (41 + (-08))}{(9 - (2 - (6 - 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 4) + (10 \times 8)}{(9 + (2 \times (6 + 3))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 - (1 \times (-08)))}{9 + (2 \times (6 \times (3 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{74 - (10 - 8)}{9 \times (2 + (6 - (3 - 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^{4-1+0}) \times 8}{(92 + 6) \times 35}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (1 - (-08)))}{(9 \times (2 + 6)) + (3^5)}$$

$$:= \frac{74 \times (10 - 8)}{(9 \times (2 + (6 \times 3))) + 5}$$

$$:= \frac{74 + (10 + 8)}{92 + ((6 \times 3) + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{74 + (10 - 8)}{(9^2) + (6 + (3 + 5))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74169}{85023} := \frac{(7 \times (4 + 1) + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 50 + 23}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74259}{86301} := \frac{7 - 4 + 25 + 9}{8 + 6 + 30 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 4 + (2 + 5) \times 9}{86 + 3 \times 0 \times 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + 2) \times 5) \times 9}{86 + 301}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74520}{83916} := \frac{(7 \times 4 - 5) \times 20}{(83 - 9) \times (1 + 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74528}{93160} := \frac{((7 \times 4) + 5) \times (2 \times 8)}{(9 + (3 - 1)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - 4)^5) \times (2 \times 8)}{(9^3 - 1) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - ((4 - 5) \times 2)) \times 8}{9 \times (3 + (1 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}{9 + (31 + 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times 5)) + (2 \times 8)}{9 + (31 \times (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 4) + ((5 - 2) \times 8)}{9 - (3 + (1 - 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (5^2))) \times 8}{(9 - (3 \times 1)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - 5)) \times (2^8)}{(9 + 3) \times 160}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - 5)) \times (2 + 8)}{(9^3 - 1) - (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 - (5 + 2)) \times 8}{(9^3) + (1 - 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (5 \times (2 \times 8))}{(9 - (3 + 1)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (52 \times 8)}{((9 \times 3) - 1) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (52 + 8)}{9 \times (31 - (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 45) \times (2 - 8)}{(9 \times 31) + (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (5 + (2 \times 8)))}{9 + (3 \times (1 + (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 + (5 + (2 - 8)))}{9 - (3 + (1^6 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (5 + (2 \times 8)))}{(9^3 \times 1) + (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 + (52 - 8))}{(9 - (3 - 1)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (5 - (2 + 8)))}{(9 \times 3) - (1 + (6 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74529}{80613} := \frac{7^{4+5+2-9}}{8 \times (06 + 1) - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 + 5 - 2) \times 9}{80 \times 6 \times 1 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74562}{89301} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 56 + 2}{8 \times 9 + 30 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74568}{93210} := \frac{((7 \times 4) - (5 - 6)) \times 8}{((9 \times 3) + 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (4 \times 5))^6) \times 8}{(9^3) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (4 - 5)) \times 6) + 8}{(9 \times (3 + 2)) + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - 4)^5) \times (6 \times 8)}{(9^3) \times (2 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 8}{9 + (321 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times 8}{(9 + 3 + 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 - 6))) \times 8}{9 + (3 - (2 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 + (5 - 6))) \times 8}{9 + (32 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times 5)) - 68}{9 \times ((3^2) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 4) + ((5 + 6) \times 8)}{((9 + 3)^2) + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 - 6))) \times 8}{(9 - 3) \times (2 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 \times (5 - 6))) \times 8}{(9 - (3 \times 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 8}{(9 + 32) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (5 - 6))) \times 8}{(9 + (3 - 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - 5)) \times (6 \times 8)}{((9 - 3)^2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 45) \times (6 + 8)}{(93 - 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 - (5 - 6)) \times 8}{(9^3) + (21 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (56 + 8)}{(9 + 3) \times (2 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 + (5 - 6)) \times 8}{(9^3) + (2 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (5 + 68))}{93 + (2 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 + (5 - (6 + 8)))}{9 + (3 \times (2 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((4 \times (5 - 6)) + 8)}{(9 \times (3 + 2)) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (5 - (6 + 8)))}{9 + ((3 \times 2) + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (5 - (6 - 8)))}{9 - (3 + (2 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (5 + (6 - 8)))}{9 + (3 - (2 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (5 + (6 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (3^2)) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (5 + 68))}{93 + (2 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (45 + 68)}{(9 + (3 \times 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{74 - ((5 \times 6) + 8)}{9 + (3 \times (2 + 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{74 + (5 \times (6 + 8))}{(9 + (3^2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 + (6 \times (1 - 0)))}{89 - (5 \times (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((4 \times 6) - (1 - 0))}{8 - (9 - (5 + 32))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (6 \times (1 - 0)))}{8 + (9 - (5 + (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (6 - 10))}{8 + (9 - (5 - (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 \times (6 + (1 - 0)))}{8 + (9 + (5 \times (3 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{74 \times (6 - (1 - 0))}{(89 \times 5) - (3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{74 + (61 - 0)}{(89 - (5 + 3)) \times 2}$$

$$:= \frac{746 - (1 - 0)}{895 - (3 - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (8 \times 16)}{(9 + (3 \times 5)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 \times (8 - 1)) - 6}{((9 \times 3) + 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (8 - (1 - 6)))}{(9 - (3 + 5)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (8 + (1^6)))}{9 + (3 + (5 - (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (8 - (1 \times 6)))}{(9 \times (3 + 5)) - (2 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (8 \times (1 + 6)))}{(93 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4 \times (8 + (1^6)))}{9 \times ((3 \times 5) + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (4^{8-1 \times 6})}{(9 + (3 - 5)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((4 \times 8) - (1 + 6))}{((9 + 3) \times 5) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((4 \times 8) + (1^6))}{((9 - 3) \times 5) + 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (8 - (1^6)))}{9 + (3 - (5 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 - (8 + (1 - 6)))}{((9 - 3) \times 5) - 20}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (8 - (1 - 6)))}{9 + (3 \times (5 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (4 + (8 + (1^6)))}{9 + ((3 + 5) \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (48 - (1 + 6))}{(9 - 3) \times (5 \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{74 + ((8 - 1) \times 6)}{93 + (52 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{748 + 16}{935 + 20}$$

$$:= \frac{748 - 16}{935 - 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74610}{89532} := \frac{((7 \times 4) + 6) \times 10}{8 \times ((9 \times 5) + (3 \times 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 4) \times 6) - (1 - 0)}{8 + ((9 \times (5 + 3)) - 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - 6)) \times 10}{8 + (95 + 3 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 + 6)) + 10}{8 - ((9 - 53) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (4 + 6)) - 10}{8 \times (9 - (5 - (3 + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7^4) - (61 - 0)}{8 - (9 - (53^2))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + 6)) \times 10}{8 + ((95 + 3) \times 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - 6)) \times 10}{(8 + (9 - 5)) \times (3 + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 4) \times (6 - (1 - 0))}{((8 - (9 - 5))^3) + 2}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 4) \times (6 \times 10)}{8 \times (9 \times (5 + (3 \times 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 4) \times (6 \times 10)}{89 + ((5^3) + 2)}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 \times 6) + (1 - 0)}{89 \times (5 + (3 - 2))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (4 - (6 + (1 - 0)))}{8 + (9 - (5 \times (3 - 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74816}{93520} := \frac{((7 \times 4) + (8 \times 1)) \times 6}{9 \times (3 \times (5 \times (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (8 + 1))) \times 6}{9 \times (3 + (5 + (2 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - 8)) \times 16}{(9 - (3 - 5)) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (4 - 81)) \times 6}{9 \times (35 \times (2 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 48) + 16}{((9 \times 3) - 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 8) + 1)) \times 6}{(9 + 3) \times (5 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (8 + 1)))^6}{((9 + 3) \times 5) + 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 + 1))) \times 6}{(9 - 3) \times (5 + 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 - 1))) \times 6}{9 \times (35 - 20)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 4) \times (8 \times 16)}{(93 - 5) \times 20}$$

$$:= \frac{(74 - (8 \times 1)) \times 6}{9 \times (3 + (52 - 0))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{74865}{90321} := \frac{7 - (4 - 8) \times 6 \times 5}{(90 + 3) \times 2 + 1}$$

<hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-bottom: 5px;"/> $\blacktriangleright \frac{74925}{83106} := \frac{(7-4) \times 925}{(8^3+1) \times 06}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75180}{92364} := \frac{7 \times 5^{1^8} + 0}{9+2+36-4}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$:= \frac{7 + ((5^2) + 49)}{83 + (6 + (1 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{7 + (5 + (2 + (4 + 9)))}{(8 - 3) \times (6 \times (1 - 0))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{75036}{98124} := \frac{(7 \times (5 - 0)) - (3 + 6)}{9 + (8 + (1 + (2^4)))}$ $:= \frac{7 + (50 - (3 \times 6))}{9 + ((8 - 1) \times (2 + 4))}$ $:= \frac{7 - (5 \times (0 - (3 + 6)))}{(9 + (8 \times (1^2))) \times 4}$ $:= \frac{75 + (0 - (3 - 6))}{(9 + (8 \times 1)) \times (2 + 4)}$ $:= \frac{7 - ((5 \times (0 \times 3)) - 6)}{9 - (8 - (1 \times (2^4)))}$ $:= \frac{7 + ((50 + 3) \times 6)}{(9 + 8) \times (1 + 24)}$ $:= \frac{(75 - (-03)) \times 6}{9 \times ((8 \times (1 \times 2)) + 4)}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75240}{81396} := \frac{7 \times 5 \times 2 + 40}{8 + 13 \times 9 - 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{75240}{83961} := \frac{(7 \times 5 - 2) \times 40}{8^3 + 961}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$:= \frac{7 + (5 + (24 + 9))}{(8 + (3 - 6)) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{7 + (52 + 49)}{8 \times (3 \times (6 - (1 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{7 + 5249}{8 \times ((3^6) + (1 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{752 + 49}{(83 + 6) \times 10}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>
$\blacktriangleright \frac{75096}{83142} := \frac{7 \times (5 - 0 + 9 - 6)}{8^3 - 1^4 - 2}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75249}{83610} := \frac{((7 - (5 - 2))^4) \times 9}{(8^3) \times (6 - (1 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{((7 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4) \times 9}{(8 + 3) \times (6 \times 10)}$ $:= \frac{((7 \times 5) - 24) \times 9}{(8 - (3 - 6)) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - (2^4))) \times 9}{((8 \times 3) - 6) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - (2 + 4))) \times 9}{8 \times (3 + (6 + (1 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 \times (2 - 4))) \times 9}{(8 + (3 + 6)) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - 24)) \times 9}{(8 + (3 \times 6)) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (5 + (2^4))) \times 9}{8 \times (36 - (1 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times ((2 + 4) \times 9)}{8 \times ((3 + 6) \times 10)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times (24 \times 9)}{8 \times (36 \times 10)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times (24 + 9)}{(8 + 36) \times 10}$ $:= \frac{7 - ((5^2) - (4 \times 9))}{8 - (3 \times (6 - 10))}$ $:= \frac{7 - (5 - (2 - (4 - 9)))}{8 - (3 - (6 - (1 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{7 - (5 + (2 - (4 \times 9)))}{((8 - 3) \times 6) + 10}$ $:= \frac{7 \times ((5 + (2 + 4)) \times 9)}{(83 - 6) \times 10}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75328}{94160} := \frac{(((7 - 5) \times 3)^2) \times 8}{(9 - (4 - 1)) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{((7 \times (5 - 3))^2) + 8}{9 + (41 \times (6 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{(9 - 4) \times (16 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - (3^2))) \times 8}{9 + (41 + 60)}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8}{9 + (4 + (1 + (6 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 + (3 - 2))) \times 8}{9 - (4 + (1 - (6 - 0)))}$ $:= \frac{(7 - (5 - 3)) \times (2 \times 8)}{94 + (1 \times (6 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(7 \times ((5 + 3)^2)) + 8}{(94 + 1) \times (6 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + ((5 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8}{(9 - (4 + 1)) \times 60}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (5 - (3^2))) \times 8}{(9 - (4 \times 1)) \times (6 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (5 + (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{9 \times (4 + (16 - 0))}$ $:= \frac{(7 + (5 + 3)) \times (2 \times 8)}{(9 + 41) \times (6 - 0)}$ $:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))}{(9 + (4 - 1)) \times 60}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>
$\blacktriangleright \frac{75106}{83942} := \frac{7+5-1+06}{8+3 \times 9-4^2}$ $:= \frac{7 \times (5 - 1) + 06}{8 - 3 - 9 + 42}$ $:= \frac{7 + 5 \times 10 - 6}{83 - (9 + 4) \times 2}$ $:= \frac{75 - 1 - 06}{83 + 9 - 4^2}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75130}{84692} := \frac{7+51-3+0}{8 \times (4+6) - 9 \times 2}$ <hr style="border: 0.5px solid red; margin-top: 10px;"/>	$:= \frac{(7 + (5 - (3^2))) \times 8}{(9 - (4 \times 1)) \times (6 - 0)}$

$$:= \frac{(75 + (3^2)) \times 8}{(9 + (4 + 1)) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{(75 + 3 + 2) \times 8}{(9 - 4) \times 160}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (5 \times (3 - 28))}{9 - (4 - 160)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 - ((3^2) - 8))}{94 + (1 - 60)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 - (3 - (2 + 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + 1)) + 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8)))}{((9 \times 4) - 1) \times 60}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 + (3 + (2 \times 8)))}{((9 \times 4) - 1) \times (6 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 + (3 + 28))}{9 \times (41 - (6 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 - ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{9 - (4 \times (1^6 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 \times (3 - (2 - 8)))}{9 - (4 - (1 \times 60))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 \times (3 + (2 + 8)))}{9 \times (4 + (1 \times (6 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 + (32 - 8))}{9 \times (4 + (1^6 + 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 + 328)}{9 + (416 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (53 + (2 \times 8))}{94 + (1^6 + 0)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{75368}{94210} := \frac{((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 6)) \times 8}{(9 + (4 \times 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7^5 - 3) - 6) \times 8}{9 + (421 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (5 - 3))^6) \times 8}{(9^4 + 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 5) \times (3 \times 6)) - 8}{(9 + 4) \times (2 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 5) \times (3 + 6)) + 8}{(9 \times (4^2)) + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 5) \times (3 + 6)) - 8}{(9 - 4)^{2+1+0}}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (5 - (3 + 6))) \times 8}{(9 + (4 - 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (5 - 36)) \times 8}{((9 \times 4) + 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6)) - 8}{94 + (2 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (5 - (3 - 6))) + 8}{(9^4 - 2) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (5 - (3 - 6))) - 8}{(9 - 4) \times (2 + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (5 - 3)) - (6 - 8)}{((9 - 4) \times 2) + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (5 - (3 + 6))) \times 8}{(9 - (4 + 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (5 - (3 - 6))) \times 8}{(9 + (4 + 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (53 - 6)) \times 8}{9 \times ((4 + 2) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 53) \times (6 + 8)}{(9 - 4) \times 210}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 5) \times ((3 + 6) \times 8)}{9 \times ((4 - 2) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 5) \times (3 \times 68)}{(9 + 42) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 5) \times 368}{(94 - 2) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(75 + (3 - 6)) \times 8}{9 \times (4 \times (2 \times 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (5 - (3 \times (6 + 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + 2)) + (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 - (5 + (3 \times (6 - 8)))}{9 + (4 - (2 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (5 - (3 + (6 - 8)))}{9 + ((4^2) + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((5 \times 3) + (6 - 8))}{9 + (4 + (2 + 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((5^3) + (6 \times 8))}{9 \times (4 + (21 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((5^3) + 68)}{(9 + (4^2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 - ((3 - 6) \times 8))}{9 \times (4 + (2 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 \times (3 + (6 + 8)))}{94 + (21 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5^{3+6-8})}{9 + (4 + (2 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 + ((3 + 6) \times 8))}{(9 - 4) \times (21 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 + (36 + 8))}{(9 - (4 - 2)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (5 + (36 - 8))}{9 + (42 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (53 + (6 \times 8))}{9 \times ((4^2) - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{75 - (3 + 68)}{9 + (4 + (2 - 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{75 + (3 - (6 - 8))}{(9 - 4) \times (2 \times 10)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{75421}{80396} := \frac{7 \times 54 + 2 - 1}{8 + 0396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{75429}{80631} := \frac{7 + (5 + ((4 \times 2) + 9))}{(8 \times (0 \times 6)) + 31}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (5 + (4 - 2))) + 9}{(8 + (-06)) \times 31}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + ((5^4 - 2) \times 9)}{8 \times ((0 \times 6) + 31)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (5 + 4)) \times 29}{8 \times ((063 - 1))}$$

$$:= \frac{754 - 29}{806 - 31}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (5 \times (4^2))) \times 9}{806 + 31}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times (4 \times 29)}{8 \times ((06 \times 31))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{75438}{96012} := \frac{7 - (5 - (4 - (3 - 8)))}{9 + (6 + (0 - (1^2)))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (5 + (4 \times (3 - 8)))}{(9 + (6 + (-01))) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{7 - (5 - (4 + 38))}{(9 \times (6 \times 01)) + 2} \\ & := \frac{7 + ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 8)}{9 + (60 + (1^2))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (54 - (3 - 8))}{96 + (0 - 12)} \\ & := \frac{7 \times ((5 - 4) \times (3 + 8))}{96 - (0 - (1 \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (54 + 38)}{9 \times ((6 - (-01)) \times 2)} \\ & := \frac{75 + (43 - 8)}{(9 + (60 + 1)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{7 - (5 - (4 \times 38))}{(9 + (6 + (-01)))^2} \\ & := \frac{75 - (4 + 38)}{(9 \times (6 - 0)) - 12} \\ & \frac{75609}{83142} := \frac{7 - 5 + 60 \times 9}{8 + 3 \times 14^2} \\ & \frac{75648}{93120} := \frac{756 + 4 \times 8}{9 + 31^2 + 0} \\ & \frac{75816}{92340} := \frac{7 \times (5 + 8 - 1) - 6}{9 + 2 \times (3 + 40)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + 5 \times (8 + 1)) \times 6}{(92 + 3) \times 4 + 0} \\ & \frac{76032}{91584} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 0 \times 3 + 2}{9 + 1 \times 5 \times 8 + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{76041}{98532} := \frac{7 \times (6 + 04) + 1}{9 \times (8 + 5 - 3) + 2} \\ & \frac{76184}{95230} := \frac{((7 - (6 - 1))^8) + 4}{95 + 230} \\ & := \frac{((7 \times 6) - (1 + 8)) \times 4}{9 + (52 \times (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{((7 \times 6) + (1 + 8)) \times 4}{(9 \times (5^2)) + 30} \\ & := \frac{((7 + 61) \times 8) - 4}{9 \times ((5^2) \times (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (6 - (1 + 8))) \times 4}{(9 \times 5) + (2 + (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(7 \times ((6 + 1) \times 8)) + 4}{9 \times (52 + (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(7 \times 6) - (18 - 4)}{95 - (2 \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1 \times 8))) \times 4}{((9 + 5) \times 2) - (3 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1^8))) \times 4}{(9 - (5 + 2)) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1 - 8))) \times 4}{95 + (2 + (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 \times (1 \times 8))) \times 4}{(9 \times 5) + 230} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 \times (5^2)) - 30} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 + (1^8))) \times 4}{(9 + 5) \times (2 + (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 + 18)) \times 4}{95 + (2 \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 - 1)) \times (8 \times 4)}{(9 + (5 + 2)) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 - 1)) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 - (5 - 2)) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{(7 + 6) \times ((1 + 8) \times 4)}{9 \times (5 + (2 \times 30))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(7 + 61) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 + (5^2)) \times 30} \\ & := \frac{7 - (6 + (1 - (8 \times 4)))}{(9 \times 5) - (2 + (3 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (6 + (1 - (8 - 4)))}{9 - (5 + (2 - (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{7 - (6 + (1 - 84))}{(9 \times 5) + (2 \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{7 \times ((6 + 18) \times 4)}{(9 + 5) \times (2 \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{7 \times (6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 4))}{9 \times ((5 + 2) \times 30)} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 - (8 + 4)))}{(9 \times (5 - 2)) + (3 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 - (8 - 4)))}{9 + (5 + (2 \times (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1^{84}))}{9 + (5 - (2 - (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 + (8 - 4)))}{9 - (5 - (2 \times (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 - 84))}{(9 \times (5 \times 2)) + 30} \\ & := \frac{7 + (61 + (8 - 4))}{9 \times (5 + (2 + (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{76 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4))}{95 \times (2 + 30)} \\ & := \frac{76 \times (1 + (8 - 4))}{95 \times (2 + (3 - 0))} \\ & \frac{76193}{82054} := \frac{7 + (6 \times (1^{93}))}{8 - ((2 \times (-05)) + 4)} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 + (1 + (9 + 3)))}{8 + (20 \times (5 - 4))} \\ & := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 - (9 \times 3)))}{8 - (20 - 54)} \\ & := \frac{76 + (1 - (9 + 3))}{(8 \times (2 - 0)) + 54} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 - 3)}{(8 \times (2 \times (05))) + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{76 + (1 + (9 \times 3))}{8 \times ((2 \times (05)) + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 + 3)}{8 \times (20 + (5 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 6) \times (19 - 3)}{8 \times ((2 - (-05)) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 6) \times (19 + 3)}{(82 + (-05)) \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 61) + 93}{(8 + 20) \times (5 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76239}{85104} := \frac{7 \times 6 - 2^3 + 9}{8 \times (5 + 1^{04})}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times 6 - 2) \times 3 + 9}{8 \times 5 + 104}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 - 2 + 39)}{(85 - 1) \times 04}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 6 \times 2 \times 3) \times 9}{8 \times (5 \times 10 + 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times 62 + 39}{8 + 5 \times 104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76248}{95310} := \frac{((7 - (6 - 2))^4) \times 8}{(9^{5-3}) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times (6 - 2)) - 4) \times 8}{(9 + (5 \times 3)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 6) + (2 + 4)) \times 8}{((9 \times 5) + 3) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (6^2)) \times 4) + 8}{9 \times (5^{3-1+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (6 - 2)) \times 4) + 8}{95 - (3 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 62) \times 4) + 8}{(9 \times 5) + 310}$$

$$:= \frac{((76 - 2) \times 4) + 8}{95 \times (3 + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (2 \times 4))) \times 8}{9 \times (5 \times (3 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (2^4))) \times 8}{(9 + (5 + 3)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6 \times (2 - 4))) \times 8}{95 \times (3 - (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6^2)) \times (4 - 8)}{(9 \times (5 \times 3)) + 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - 2)) \times (4 \times 8)}{(9 - 5) \times (3 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - 2)) \times 48}{9 \times (5 \times (3 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 - (2 + 4))) + 8}{9 + (5 - (3 + (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 - (2 - 4))) + 8}{(9^{5-3}) - (1 - 0)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 + (2 - 4))) + 8}{9 + (5 + (31 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 + (2 - 4))) - 8}{9 + ((5 \times 3) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 - 2)) + (4 \times 8)}{(9 \times 5) + (3 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (6 \times 2)) \times (4 + 8)}{95 \times (3 \times (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + (2 - 4))) \times 8}{(9 + (5 - 3)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + 62) \times (4 + 8)}{9 \times ((5^3) - 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{(76 + (2^4)) \times 8}{(95 - 3) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 62) \times (4 - 8)}{(95 \times 3) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((6 + (2 \times 4)) \times 8)}{(95 + 3) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 - (2 + (4 - 8)))}{(9 - (5 - 3)) \times 10}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 \times ((2^4) - 8))}{(9 + 5) \times (3 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 \times (2 - (4 - 8)))}{9 \times (5 + (3 \times 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 + (2 + (4 - 8)))}{9 - (5 - (31 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{76 - (2 \times (4 \times 8))}{(9 \times 5) - (3 \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{76 + (2 \times (4 + 8))}{(9 \times (5 \times 3)) - 10}$$

$$:= \frac{76 + (24 + 8)}{9 \times (5 \times (3 \times (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{76 + 248}{95 + 310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76302}{81954} := \frac{7 + 6 \times 3 + 02}{8 + 1^9 + 5 \times 4}$$

$$:= \frac{76 + 30 + 2}{8 \times (1 + 9 + 5) - 4}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 6 \times 30 + 2}{(8 - 1) \times (9 + 5 \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76302}{91845} := \frac{7 \times 6^3 + 0 \times 2}{91 \times (8 - 4) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76314}{82950} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 3 + 1^4}{(8 + 2 - 9) \times 50}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 63 - 1^4}{(8 - 2 + 9) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (6 \times 3 - 1) - 4}{(8 \times 2 + 9) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 63 \times (1 + 4)}{(8 \times 2 - 9) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76319}{84502} := \frac{7 \times (63 + 1) + 9}{8 - 4 + 502}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{76320}{91584} := \frac{(7 - (6 - 3)) \times 20}{(9 + 15) \times (8 - 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 + 3)) + (2 - 0)}{9 - (15 - 84)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (6 \times 3)) \times 20}{(9 + 1) \times (5 \times (8 + 4))}$$

$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + 3)) \times 20}{(91 + 5) \times (8 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76328}{95410} := \frac{((7 + (6 + 3))^2) \times 8}{((9 - 5)^4) \times 10}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (((6 - 3)^2) \times 8)}{9 \times (5 \times (4 + 10))}$
$:= \frac{(7 + (6 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)}{(9 + (1 \times (5 - 8))) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{((7 + (6 - 3))^2) + 8}{9 \times (5 \times (4 - (1 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{7 \times ((6 - (3 + 2)) \times 8)}{(9 + 5) \times (4 + (1 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(7 + (6 - 3)) \times 20}{9 - (1 - (58 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (3^2))) \times 8}{(9 + (5 - 4)) \times 10}$	$:= \frac{7 \times ((6 + (3 - 2)) \times 8)}{((9 \times 5) + 4) \times 10}$
$:= \frac{(7 + (6 - 3))^2 + 0}{(9 + (1^5)) \times (8 + 4)}$	$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - 3)) \times (2 + 8)}{(9 \times 5) + (4 + (1 - 0))}$	$:= \frac{7 + (((6 - 3)^2) + 8)}{9 + ((5 \times 4) + (1 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{(7 + 63) \times (2 - 0)}{9 - (1 - (5 \times (8 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(7 \times (6 \times 3)) + (2 + 8)}{(9 \times (5 \times 4)) - 10}$	$:= \frac{7 + (6 - ((3^2) - 8))}{((9 - 5) \times 4) - (1 - 0)}$
$:= \frac{(7 - 6) \times (3 \times 20)}{9 \times (1 - (5 - (8 + 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8}{9 \times ((5 \times 4) + 10)}$	$:= \frac{7 + (6 - (3 - (2 - 8)))}{(9 \times 5) - (4 \times 10)}$
$:= \frac{7 - (6 - (3^2 + 0))}{9 + (15 - (8 + 4))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + ((6 - 3)^2)) \times 8}{(9 - 5) \times (4 \times 10)}$	$:= \frac{7 + (6 - (3 + (2 - 8)))}{9 + (5 - (4 - 10))}$
$:= \frac{7 \times ((6 - 3) \times 20)}{9 \times ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (6 - (3 + 2))) \times 8}{(9 - (5 - 4)) \times 10}$	$:= \frac{7 + (6 + (3 + 28))}{9 + (5 + (41 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (6 - (3 - (2 - 0)))}{9 + ((1^5) + (8 \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (6 \times (3 + 2))) \times 8}{(95 \times 4) - 10}$	$:= \frac{76 - ((3 - 2) \times 8)}{(9 \times 5) + (4 \times 10)}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))}{9 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + (3 \times 2))) \times 8}{(9 \times (5 \times 4)) + 10}$	$:= \frac{76 - (32 + 8)}{9 - (5 - (41 - 0))}$
$:= \frac{7 \times (6 + (3^2 + 0))}{((9 + 1) \times (5 + 8)) - 4}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + 3 + 2)) \times 8}{9 \times (5 \times (4 \times (1 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{76 \times (32 + 8)}{95 \times (4 \times 10)}$
$:= \frac{7 + ((6 \times 3) - 20)}{9 - (15 - (8 + 4))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + 3)) \times 28}{(9 + 5) \times (4 \times 10)}$	$:= \frac{76 + 328}{95 + 410}$
$:= \frac{7 + ((6 + 3) \times (2 - 0))}{9 + (1 + (5 \times (8 - 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 63 \times 2) \times 8}{95 \times (4 + 10)}$	
$:= \frac{7 + (6 - (3 - 20))}{9 - (1 \times (5 - (8 \times 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(7 + 6) \times (32 - 8)}{(95 \times 4) + 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76384}{91520} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times (3 + 8) - 4}{(9 + 1) \times 52 + 0}$
$:= \frac{7 + (6 + (32 - 0))}{9 + (1 + ((5 \times 8) + 4))}$	$:= \frac{(7 - 6) \times ((3^2) \times 8)}{9 \times (5 + (4 + (1 - 0)))}$	$:= \frac{7 + 6 \times (3 + 8 \times 4)}{(9 - 1 + 5) \times 20}$
$:= \frac{7 + (63 + 20)}{9 + (15 + 84)}$	$:= \frac{(7 - 6) \times 328}{((9 \times 5) - 4) \times 10}$	
$:= \frac{7 + (63 - 20)}{9 - (1 - ((5 + 8) \times 4))}$	$:= \frac{(76 \times (3 + 2)) + 8}{(9 \times 54) - (1 - 0)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76531}{82940} := \frac{7 + 65 \times 3 + 1}{(8^2 - 9) \times 4 + 0}$
$:= \frac{76 - (3 - (2 - 0))}{9 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 4)))}$	$:= \frac{(76 + 3 + 2) \times 8}{9 \times ((5 + 4) \times 10)}$	
$:= \frac{76 - (3 \times (2 - 0))}{(9 - (1 - (5 + 8))) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{7 - (6 - (3 + 28))}{(9 \times 5) - (4 + (1 - 0))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76593}{81024} := \frac{(76 + 5 \times 9) \times 3}{8 \times (10 + 2) \times 4}$
	$:= \frac{7 - (6 + (3 - (2 + 8)))}{9 - (5 + (4 - 10))}$	$:= \frac{(76 + 5) \times 9 - 3}{8 \times (10^2 - 4)}$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{76923}{84150} := \frac{7 \times (6 \times 92 + 3)}{(84 + 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{76953}{82401} := \frac{(7 + 6 + 9) \times 5 + 3}{82 + 40 - 1} \\ & \frac{78120}{93465} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 1^{20}}{9 - 3 - 4 + 65} \\ & \frac{78120}{96534} := \frac{7 \times (8 + 12) + 0}{9 - 6 + 5 \times 34} \\ & \frac{78165}{90324} := \frac{7 \times (8 + 1^6) \times 5}{(90 + 3 - 2) \times 4} \\ & \frac{78246}{90153} := \frac{(7 - 8 + 2) \times 46}{(9 + 01) \times 5 + 3} \\ & \frac{78246}{93126} := \frac{7 \times (8 + 2 + 4) - 6}{90 + (1 + 5 \times 3)} \\ & \frac{78246}{90153} := \frac{7 \times (8^2 - 4) - 6}{9 \times 01 \times 53} \\ & \frac{78246}{90153} := \frac{782 - 46}{901 - 53} \\ & \frac{78246}{90153} := \frac{782 + 46}{901 + 53} \\ & \frac{78246}{90153} := \frac{(7 + 82) \times 46}{(90 - 1) \times 53} \\ & \frac{78246}{93150} := \frac{7 - 8 - 2 + 4 \times 6}{(9 - 3 - 1) \times 5 + 0} \\ & \frac{78246}{93150} := \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 + 4 \times 6)}{(9 - 3 - 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{78246}{93150} := \frac{7 \times (8 + 2 - 4) \times 6}{(9 - 3 \times 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{78246}{95013} := \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 + 4 - 6)}{9 + 5^{-01+3}} \\ & \frac{78246}{95013} := \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 \times 4 + 6)}{9 \times (5 + 01) - 3} \\ & \frac{78246}{95013} := \frac{7 \times (8 \times (2 + 4) + 6)}{9 \times (50 + 1^3)} \\ & \frac{78246}{95013} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times (2 \times 4 + 6)}{950 - 1 + 3} \\ & \frac{78435}{92610} := \frac{7 + 84 - 3 - 5}{9 \times 2 \times 6 - 10} \\ & \frac{78540}{93126} := \frac{7 \times (8 \times 5 + 40)}{9^3 - 1 - 2^6} \\ & \frac{78624}{93015} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times (6 + 2 - 4)}{9 \times 30 \times 1 - 5} \\ & \frac{78650}{91234} := \frac{(7 - 8 + 6) \times 5 + 0}{9 + 1 + 23 - 4} \\ & \frac{78650}{91234} := \frac{7 + 8 \times 6 - 5 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 2 + 3) + 4} \\ & \frac{79065}{81324} := \frac{7 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) + 5)}{8 + (1 + (3 + 24))} \\ & \frac{(7^8 - 2 - 4) \times 6}{(9 - 3 + 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{7 \times (8^2 - 4 + 6)}{(9 + (3 - 1)) \times 50} \\ & \frac{7 \times (82 - 4 - 6)}{(9 + 3 \times 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{78 \times (2 \times 4 + 6)}{(9 \times 3 - 1) \times 50} \\ & \frac{7 \times 8 \times (24 + 6)}{(9 + 31) \times 50} \\ & \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 + 4 - 6)}{9 + 5^{-01+3}} \\ & \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 \times 4 + 6)}{9 \times (5 + 01) - 3} \\ & \frac{7 \times (8 \times (2 + 4) + 6)}{9 \times (50 + 1^3)} \\ & \frac{7 \times 8 \times (2 \times 4 + 6)}{950 - 1 + 3} \\ & \frac{7 + 84 - 3 - 5}{9 \times 2 \times 6 - 10} \\ & \frac{7 \times (8 \times 5 + 40)}{9^3 - 1 - 2^6} \\ & \frac{7 \times 8 \times (6 + 2 - 4)}{9 \times 30 \times 1 - 5} \\ & \frac{(7 - 8 + 6) \times 5 + 0}{9 + 1 + 23 - 4} \\ & \frac{7 + 8 \times 6 - 5 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 2 + 3) + 4} \\ & \frac{7 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) + 5)}{8 + (1 + (3 + 24))} \\ & \frac{(7^9 - 06) \times 5}{((8 + 13)^2) \times 4} \\ & \frac{7 \times (9 - (0 - (6 - 5)))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 + (2 + 4)))} \\ & \frac{7 \times ((9 + (-06)) \times 5)}{81 + (3 + 24)} \\ & \frac{7 \times (90 \times (6 - 5))}{8 \times ((1^3 + 2)^4)} \\ & \frac{7 \times (90 - (6 \times 5))}{(8 + 1) \times (3 \times (2^4))} \\ & \frac{7 \times (9 - (0 - (6 + 5)))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 \times (2 + 4)))} \\ & \frac{7 \times (90 - 65)}{(8 + 1) \times ((3 + 2) \times 4)} \\ & \frac{7 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 6) + 5))}{((8 + (1^3))^2) \times 4} \\ & \frac{7 \times (9 \times ((06 \times 5)))}{81 \times (3 \times (2 \times 4))} \\ & \frac{(7 + (90 - 6)) \times 5}{(81 - 3) \times (2 + 4)} \\ & \frac{7 \times (9 + 1 \times 3 + 5)}{8 \times 2 \times 4 + 60} \\ & \frac{79135}{86240} := \frac{79 + 1 + 3^5}{8 \times (6 - 2 + 40)} \\ & \frac{79143}{86025} := \frac{7 + 9 + 1 \times 4 + 3}{8 + 6 \times 02 - 5} \\ & \frac{79143}{86025} := \frac{7 + (9 + 1 \times 4) \times 3}{8 + 6 \times (02 + 5)} \\ & \frac{79143}{86025} := \frac{7 \times (9 + 1) - 4 + 3}{8 + 60 + 2 + 5} \\ & \frac{79143}{86025} := \frac{79 + 1 + 4 \times 3}{(8 + 6 \times 02) \times 5} \\ & \frac{79143}{86025} := \frac{7 + 91 \times 4 - 3}{8 \times (60 - 2 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{79236}{80514} &:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 2 - 3) + 6}{8 + 051 + 4} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 2) + 3^6}{805 + 14} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{80325}{91476} &:= \frac{(80 + 3 + 2) \times 5}{9 - 1 + 476} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{80325}{97461} &:= \frac{80 - (3 - 2) \times 5}{(9 - 7) \times 46 - 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{81567}{92340} &:= \frac{8 \times 15 - 67}{(9 + 2 \times 3) \times 4 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + 1) \times (5 + 6) + 7}{(9 - 2 \times 3) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{79240}{86315} := \frac{(7 + 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0}{(8 + 6) \times (3 + 1) + 5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{80712}{93456} &:= \frac{8 + 07^{1 \times 2}}{9 - 3 + 4 + 56} \\ &:= \frac{80 - 7 + 1 + 2}{(9 + 3 - 4) \times (5 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{81760}{92345} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}{(9 + 2) \times 345}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{79453}{82016} := \frac{7 + (9 + 4 - 5) \times 3}{8 \times (-2 \times 01 + 6)}$$

$$:= \frac{79 - 4 \times 5 + 3}{8^2 + 0 \times 16}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + 94 - 5 - 3}{8 \times 2 \times 01 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(79 + 45) \times 3}{8^2 \times 01 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times ((9 + 4) \times 5 - 3)}{(8 + 20) \times 16}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(8 \times 07 + 1) \times 2}{9 + 3 + 4 \times 5 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (07 + 12)}{(9 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{81765}{92430} &:= \frac{8 + 1 + 7 + 6 \times 5}{9 \times 2 + 4 + 30} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - 1) \times 7 \times 6 + 5}{92 \times 4 - 30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{79542}{83106} := \frac{7 + 9 \times 54 - 2}{8^3 + 1^{06}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{80725}{93641} &:= \frac{(8 - 0 \times 7 + 2) \times 5}{93 + 6 - 41} \\ &:= \frac{80 + (7 + 2) \times 5}{(9 - 3) \times 6 \times 4 + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{8 + 07 + 2 \times 5}{9 - 3 + 6 \times 4 - 1}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 + 07) \times 25}{(93 - 6) \times (4 + 1)}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 + 07)^2 \times 5}{9 \times (36 \times 4 + 1)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{82017}{94635} &:= \frac{8 - 2 + 01 \times 7}{9 + 4 - 6 + 3 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{8^2 + 01^7}{(9 - (4 - 6) \times 3) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (20 - 1 \times 7)}{(9 - 4)^{6-3} - 5}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times 20 - 17}{(9 - 4 + 6) \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (20 - 1 + 7)}{(9 - 4) \times 6 \times (3 + 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{820 - 1^7}{9 \times (4 \times 6 - 3) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{79650}{81243} := \frac{(7 + 9 - 6) \times 5 + 0}{8 \times 1 \times (2 + 4) + 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 \times (9 + 6) - 5 + 0}{81 + 24 - 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - 9 + 6) \times 50}{(8^{1 \times 2} + 4) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{7 + (9 - 6)^5 + 0}{((8 + 1)^2 + 4) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{81270}{93654} := \frac{(8 + 1^2) \times 70}{9^3 + 6 - 5 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{81360}{92547} := \frac{8 \times (1 + 3 + 6) + 0}{9 \times (2 + 5) + 4 \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 + 1 + 3) \times 60}{(9 + 2 \times 54) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{82160}{93457} := \frac{8^2 + 16 + 0}{(9 + 3 - 4 + 5) \times 7}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 + 2) \times 16 + 0}{(9 - 3 + 4 \times 5) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{80154}{97236} := \frac{8 - 01 + 54}{9 - 7 + 2 \times 36}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 - 1 - 3) \times 60}{((9 - 2) \times 5 + 4) \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{82365}{97104} := \frac{8 + 2 + 36 \times 5}{(9 + 7) \times (10 + 4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{83160}{94752} &:= \frac{8-3+160}{9+4+7 \times 5^2} \\ &:= \frac{831-6+0}{94 \times (7+5-2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8+(4 \times 1 \times 2)^3}{9 \times 70-6 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8^{4-1}-2-3}{9 \times (7+06) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{85241}{90376} := \frac{8+5 \times (2^4-1)}{9+03+76}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{83421}{90675} &:= \frac{8+3 \times (4+2-1)}{90-(6+7) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8-3+42-1}{9+06+7 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8-3+4^{2+1}}{9 \times 0 \times 6+75} \\ &:= \frac{8+3^4+2+1}{(9+06) \times 7-5} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (3+4)^2-1}{90+67 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{8^3-4+21}{90 \times 6+7 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{84150}{96237} := \frac{(8+4-1) \times 50}{9+62 \times (3+7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{84160}{95732} := \frac{8 \times (4+16)+0}{9 \times 5 \times (7-3)+2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{84321}{90567} &:= \frac{8+43+2+1}{9+056-7} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (4+3 \times 2)+1}{9 \times 05+6 \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{85410}{97236} := \frac{(8+5) \times (4+1)+0}{9-7+2 \times 36}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{85671}{92340} := \frac{8 \times (5 \times 67-1)}{9 \times 2^3 \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{86125}{93704} := \frac{8+61 \times 2-5}{(9 \times 3+7) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{86301}{97524} := \frac{8+6^3-01}{9 \times (7+5+2^4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{83457}{96102} := \frac{8-3+4+57}{96-10 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{84672}{90153} := \frac{(8+4 \times 6) \times 7 \times 2}{9 \times 01 \times 53}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{86310}{92475} &:= \frac{(8+6) \times (3-(1-0))}{9-(2-((4 \times 7)-5))} \\ &:= \frac{(8+6) \times (3 \times (1-0))}{9+(24+(7+5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{83506}{91274} := \frac{(8+35) \times 06}{9-1+274}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{85137}{90624} := \frac{(8 \times 5-1) \times 37}{(90+6) \times 2^4}$$

$$:= \frac{86-(3 \times 10)}{9+((2 \times (4 \times 7))-5)}$$

$$:= \frac{8+(63-(1-0))}{(9-(2 \times (4-7))) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{83520}{97614} := \frac{(8+3+5) \times 020}{9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 1-4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{85176}{94302} := \frac{8 \times 5+1-7-6}{9 \times 4-3-02}$$

$$:= \frac{86-(3-(1-0))}{9+(2+(4+75))}$$

$$:= \frac{(8 \times (6-3))-10}{9-(2-(4 \times (7-5)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{84123}{97065} &:= \frac{8+4+1^{23}}{9+7-06+5} \\ &:= \frac{(8+4+1^2) \times 3}{9 \times (7-06) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (4-1)+2) \times 3}{9+70+6+5} \\ &:= \frac{(8+4+1) \times 23}{(9 \times 7+06) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{8 \times (5+1+7-6)}{94-30-2} \\ &:= \frac{(8+5+1^7) \times 6}{94-3+02} \\ &:= \frac{8 \times (5+17+6)}{(94+30) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{(8+5-1) \times 7 \times 6}{9 \times (4^3-02)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{8+((6+3) \times 10)}{9+(2 \times (4 \times (7+5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(8+6) \times (3+10)}{(9+(2+(4 \times 7))) \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(8+6) \times (3 \times 10)}{9 \times (2+(4 \times (7+5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{8 \times (63 \times 10)}{9 \times (2 \times (4 \times 75))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{86352}{97104} := \frac{(8 \times 6 + 3) \times 5 + 2}{9 + 7 \times 10 \times 4} \\ & \frac{86437}{92105} := \frac{(8 + 6 + 4) \times 3 + 7}{(9 - 2) \times 10 - 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(8^{6-4} - 3) \times 7}{(92 - 1) \times 05} \\ & \frac{86751}{92340} := \frac{(8 + 6 - 7) \times 51}{(92 + 3) \times 4 + 0} \\ & \frac{86754}{91320} := \frac{86 - (7 + 5) \times 4}{9 - 1 + 32 + 0} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 + 67 + 5 \times 4}{(9 + 1^3)^2 + 0} \\ & \quad := \frac{86 - 7 + 54}{(9 + 1 - 3) \times 20} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 \times (6 - 7 + 5 \times 4)}{(9 - 1^3) \times 20} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(8 \times 6 - 7) \times 5 + 4}{(9 - 1 + 3) \times 20} \\ & \frac{87120}{93456} := \frac{8 \times 7 - 1^2 + 0}{93 - 4 - 5 \times 6} \\ & \frac{87120}{93654} := \frac{8 \times (7 + 1 + 2) + 0}{(9 + 3 + 6) \times 5 - 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 + 712 + 0}{9 \times (3 \times 6 \times 5 - 4)} \\ & \quad := \frac{(8 + 7 - 1) \times 20}{9 \times 3 \times (6 + 5) + 4} \\ & \quad := \frac{(8 + 7 + 1) \times 20}{9 \times 36 + 5 \times 4} \\ & \frac{87210}{96543} := \frac{(8 + 7^2) \times 10}{9 - 6 + 5^4 + 3} \\ & \frac{87241}{96305} := \frac{8 + 72 - 4 + 1}{(9 - 6) \times 30 - 5} \\ & \quad := \frac{(8 \times 7 + 2) \times 4 - 1}{(9 \times 6 - 3) \times 05} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{87462}{90513} := \frac{8 - (7 - 46) \times 2}{90 - 5 + 1 + 3} \\ & \frac{87462}{91530} := \frac{87 - 46 + 2}{9 + 1 + 5 + 30} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 - (7 - 46) \times 2}{(9 - 1 - 5) \times 30} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 \times (74 + 6 \times 2)}{(9 + 15) \times 30} \\ & \quad := \frac{8^{7-4} + 6 - 2}{9 + 1 + 530} \\ & \frac{87543}{92016} := \frac{8 - 7 \times (5 - 43)}{9 \times 2 \times 016} \\ & \quad := \frac{8 \times (7 \times 5 \times 4 - 3)}{9 \times 2^{01+6}} \end{aligned}$$

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